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Introduction

Giada Bonu Rosenkranz and Donatella della Porta

The FIERCE Project

Increasing social inequalities, political disaffection and the rise of populist and anti-gender radical right groups represent a challenge to our democracy. The EU-funded FIERCE project aims to provide profound theoretical and practical knowledge and tools to understand feminist and anti-feminist/anti-gender movements, activities and discourses as well as their impact on institutions and policies during 2010–2021. The project will use framing, political ethnography and social network analyses to study the related actors in the fields of labour market, health and reproductive rights, LGBTQ+ rights, migration and gender-based violence in eight case studies representing a wide variety of country contexts. Moreover, it will introduce bottom-up initiatives that test solutions and innovations in partnership with feminist NGOs/movements/networks to experiment democratic innovation.

Feminist movements in time and space: an introduction

This report provides a comprehensive overview of the main feminist movement actors, mobilizations and trajectories in Denmark, France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, and Turkey. The report analyses the development of feminist movements according to the main themes of the project: labor market, health and reproductive rights, migration, LGBTQ+ rights, and gender-based violence.

In this report, we will first present the silences and voices of feminism in social movement studies. This introductory part will address interpretative lines as well as gaps which our project aims at filling in. Second, we will present the main objectives of the FIERCE project with regard to the state of the art of the literature on feminist movements, and the working definitions of feminist movements that we engaged with in our research. Third, we will give an overview of the feminist movements in time and space, by reviewing key findings of the literature on feminist movements in the eight countries. Fourth, we include the methodological guidelines according to which this report has been prepared. According to these guidelines, the national reports will be presented following sections of analysis. These sections will first outline the history of the feminist movements and the actors, organizational models and allies that have been developed as they are delineated in the existing literature. Then, the themes and agenda that comprise, but are not limited to, the five thematic areas explored by the FIERCE project (labor market, health and reproductive rights, migration, LGBTQ+ rights and gender-based violence) are explored. These sections also address repertoire of action, frames of arguments, and campaigns and debates for each country case. Finally, the national reports look at key policy related outcomes. Each report includes a list of feminist movements' campaigns related to the five thematic areas, or to further key issues/themes that have emerged from each specific national context. This list is intended to help the sampling of feminist campaigns and networks to be covered through fieldwork in the second stage of the project.

Feminism in social movement studies

Notwithstanding their importance for the advancement of civic, social and political rights, as well as their influence on other social movements in terms of 'spillover' effects (Meyer and Whittier 1994), social movement studies have dealt less with women's movement than with other 'old' and 'new' ones. Research on gender-related movements and on the gendering of other movements has been particularly important in highlighting issues of identity construction, cultural repertoires, emotional work, as well as how power penetrates everyday relations (Wolff, Bernstein and Taylor 2015). While rich in theoretical and empirical contributions, gender studies rarely had the women's movements at the core of their reflection (Reger 2021). While important research has been conducted on some women's mobilization, especially in the US, there is overall limited systematic cross-national comparisons. As we are going to show in this report, and in the introduction to it, the women's

mobilizations have renewed a variety of repertoire of actions, organizational models and collective framing possibilities.

The conceptualization of women's and feminist movements is still an open question. Women's movements have been defined as "all organizing of women explicitly as women to make any sort of social change" (Ferree and Mueller 2007, 577). This broad definition requires however some typologization as it tends to lump together not only women's claims for different types of rights and on different issues, but also mobilization on rather opposite claims, driven by different values and supported by different social and political groups. In fact,

"Women mobilize in response to gendered structures of oppression and opportunity within particular social, cultural, and political contexts. Participants in women's movements also form collective identities on the basis of their social position as women. Yet, women are not a monolith. As such, women's movements include participants with a broad range of heterogeneous racial/ethnic, socioeconomic, and sexual identities. While cisgender women represent the majority of participants in women's movements, many contemporary women's movements explicitly include of cisgender, transgender, and genderqueer individuals. Because gender oppression is inherently intertwined with other forms of inequality, women's movements, and especially those led by women of color, organize to address grievances about the intersections of sexism, racism, classism, or the interconnection between gender inequality and colonization. In addition, while many women's movements embrace a feminist identity and seek to advance the social position of women, it is not always the case. Women also mobilize around claims that are unrelated to or in opposition to feminism" (Crossley and McKee Hurwitz 2023).

In specifying this broad definition, the concept of feminism is an extremely important signifier, as it focuses attention upon a more homogeneous type of social movement, located within progressive coalition, which aims at rooting women's rights within emancipatory conceptions. "Feminist movements, in the broadest sense, are collective efforts to improve the situation of women, and they have emerged in most parts of the world, beginning in the mid-nineteenth century and continuing into the present" (Rupp and Taylor 2013). While the term feminism initially indicated the campaign to extend civil rights to women, it later covered also claims for equal rights more broadly, including social rights. So, feminists have been said to state that women and men are "inherently of equal worth" and that "social movements are necessary to achieve equality ... with the understanding that gender always intersects with other social hierarchies" (Freedman 2002, 7). Feminist movements went from claiming civil and political rights to questioning the paradigms on which those conceptions of rights and democracy were built. Referring to these paradigms as male-based paved the way for innovating democratic processes, not just in the mere extension of their perimeter, but in changing their foundations. Furthermore, the intersectional perspective, developed by Black feminism, integrated the analysis of gender with that of race, class, age, bodily abilities, sexuality and so on. With regard to sexuality, progressively feminist and LGBTQ+ movements have developed forms of collaboration, also as a result of the spread of queer theories.

Objectives and working definitions

Feminist movement

In our project, we refer to feminist movements as made of all those collective actors that contest the gender regime and the social production of gender based on inequality. Contemporary feminist movements have strived to support, develop and apply an intersectional analytical framework to fully grasp (and counteract) the multiple and intersecting forms of power and oppressions. Intersectionality also constitutes the aspired basis for national, transversal and transnational alliances and coalition-building with other movements and civil society actors. Yet, these undertakings are not unproblematic and can unleash tensions, internal conflicts and divisions that at times unravel the presence of very different (when not directly contradictory) approaches to feminist struggles, priorities, and potential allies. In this perspective, our project aims to provide a concrete laboratory of ideas to identify,

reinvigorate and renew democratic practices that build upon concrete alternatives and inclusive visions for the future of democracy. At the same time, it allows us to identify the internal challenges to these inclusive practices, by more openly addressing tensions, controversies and disagreements hindering the efforts to convey intersectionality in praxis.

Conceptions of Democracy

The central focus of our research is democratic innovation in social movements with a focus on the feminist movement. We do not wish, however, to measure degrees of democracy, but to conceptualize the various models of democracy that are present, in more or less 'pure' form. Even if the conceptualization of a "pure" democracy is neither feasible nor desirable, the research addresses some minimal principles of democracy, such as rights, egalitarianism, participation, diversity. Through social movements the project aims to outline how social movements contribute to the making of different combinations of democracy in action. A main assumption of our research is that the general principles of democracy such as power (kratos) by/from/for the people (demos) can be combined in different forms and with different balances: representative versus participatory, and majority versus deliberative. We assume that the plurality of repertoires that have been identified in contemporary movements is also reflected in the variety of conceptions of democracy they express.

Social Movement Organizations

We look at the conception of democracy in social movement organizations (SMOs), defined as formal and informal networks of individual and groups, with different degrees of structuration. We look at SMOs both as mobilization agents and as spaces of deliberation and value construction. First, we consider organizations as socializing agents and norm producers; second, we look at formal as well as informal practices; third, we seek for cognitive mechanisms: organizations do not automatically adapt to their environments; environmental pressures are filtered by organizational actors' perceptions, and their focus on everyday action and practical knowledge; fourth, in line with research on the feminist movement, we will look at organizations as emotional spaces, in which affective and cognitive dynamics interact. We aim to capture feminist mobilizations in each country through the various organizations and organizational models they establish.

Organizational actors perceive and frame environmental pressures in situation-specific ways and based on their accumulated practical knowledge and produce everyday actions accordingly. These knowledge productions and everyday actions, in turn, contribute to producing, reproducing and/or changing the political environment in which they operate. In other words, while considering environmental constraints as potentially important in shaping organizational behaviour, we believe that organizations play an important and active role in shaping their environments and the subjectivities of the activists. As a result, within the space of social movements, organizations are not just a means to changing the environment, conceptualized as outside of the organizations, but also an end itself, signifying that the organization is part of the environment in which activists live and act.

Democratic Innovations in Social Movements

Within a general attention to the participatory and deliberative qualities, visions and practices of democracy, debates tend to develop on two main dimensions. First, participatory conceptions that stress inclusiveness of equals (high participation) are contrasted with those based upon the delegation of power to representatives (low participation). In this sense, in our research we expect to observe the continued presence of direct forms of democracy that put a strong emphasis on the assembly, but also discover how institutionalization processes of social movement organizations have spread principles of delegation of power. A second dimension in existing literature contrasts the prevalence of a majoritarian decision-making process based upon vote with a more deliberative model which assigns a special role to public discussion, the common good, rational arguments, and transformation of preferences. On this, we expect that the traditional use of vote as decision-making mechanism even within the assembly organizational model is challenged by an emerging emphasis on values and

practices that stresses instead good communication. By exploring democratic innovations within feminist movements, we seek to document and analyse how they challenge, coalesce or enhance democracy at the national and international levels.

Feminisms in time: shared trends of changes

Feminist movements continuity

The reflection on the women's movements has pointed to the importance of specific moments of mobilization but also at the continuity of movements beyond moments of high mobilization. Between waves, periods of abeyance allow feminist discourses and structures to overcome low mobilization ebbs (Rupp & Taylor 1987).

When talking about waves of mobilization, these have been related with "periods of generalized social upheaval, when sensitivity to injustice, discrimination, and social inequalities has been widespread in the society as a whole" (Crossley and McKee Hurwitz 2023). General conditions for protest waves have been singled out as "Broad societal changes in the patterns of women's participation in the paid labor force, increases in women's formal educational attainment, shifts in marriage, women's fertility rates, and reproductive roles disrupt traditional social arrangements, setting the stage for women's movements. For example, industrialization, urbanization, and women's increased participation in education expanded women's public roles" (ibid.). Social and economic development brings about some opportunities for gender equality: new technology reduces the domestic workload and also (through birth control) the size of the family; mass education improves the resources available to women. Women's participation in the labor force and education has indeed been found to foster feminist attitudes (Banaszak and Plutzer 1993).

An apparent paradox noted in research on the outcomes of feminist mobilization is that women succeeded in influencing policy making without, however, being massively present in institutional politics. Feminist social movements were in fact the principal articulators of women's demands. The literature addresses the process of change of the feminist movements in the post-Beijing era and the building of women's machineries as important moments of change from within. Rather than evolving into political parties, women's movements have been described as cultural movements, particularly in so far as they focused their efforts on changes in everyday life to be reached via a deconstruction and reconstruction of roles and values (Rucht 1994, Eschle and Maiguascha 2018, Kantola and Outschoorn 2007, McBride and Mazur 2010). Nevertheless, more recent analyses have stressed the capacity of the women's movement to interact with the state, developing concrete projects and initiatives (Banaszak, Beckwith, and Rucht 2003; della Porta 2003, Woodward 2015). Although aiming at the construction of a different culture, women's movements throughout the world constantly interacted with political institutions (Rai 2003, Boris and Prugl 2016, Krook and Mackay 2011, Eschle 2018). Feminist movements are in fact deeply political, by also singling out the political character of private life (De Jong 2017, Ferguson 2018, Altan Olcay 2020, Boris and Prugl 2016, Rao. and Kellher 2005).

Moreover, the development of Marxist feminism integrated reflections on the gender regime (Walby 2003, 2020) with the economic model, and thus looked at how the emergence of capitalism is closely linked to the social production of female and male roles (Federici 2004, Dalla Costa and James 1972, MacKinnon 1982). This materialist perspective combined the cultural dimension of social change with the economic one, expanding the analysis to the labour market through innovative framing processes, such as with regard to social reproduction work and the role of care in neoliberalism.

To conclude, a significant contribution to feminist thought comes from Black feminism and third world feminism, that challenged the white bias of western based countries by addressing the interlocking system of oppression that, together with gender, combines race, age, class and so on (hooks 1991, Lorde 1984, Moraga and Anzaldúa 1981).

Struggles for recognition

While the metaphor of waves is challenged by scholars who point at continuities, some differences have nevertheless been observed, at least in Europe, between a first wave, emerged already in the second half of the XIX century and developing its organizational structure at the beginning of the XXth century; a second wave, growing since the late 1960s, and a third wave, spreading in the years 2010s.

Facing comparable legal situations throughout Europe, women's movements converged on the same issues in the first wave of feminism, such as the disadvantaged status of married women, unequal pay in the workplace, the situation of poor single mothers, organized prostitution, barriers to education and professions, and suffrage, which would become the principal concern. Organized women acted mostly by legal and respectable means, publishing papers, launching manifestos, organizing public conferences, or lobbying political actors. From the outset, efforts were made to link women's activities across national boundaries. A series of women's rights congresses were held in European cities from the late 1870s onwards, and a variety of international organizations appeared in the wake of the International Council of Women, founded in 1888 in Washington (Bereni 2023).

In a historical perspective, Karen Offen has distinguished especially in the first wave of feminism: individualist feminism (calling for women's rights for personal autonomy) and relational feminism (calling for women's equality). In this period a socialist current emerged, locating women's oppression within capitalist exploitation, and thus connecting gender to class oppressions.

Changes, low ebb and institutionalization

The second wave of feminism in Europe developed since the late 1960s. Arising in the wake of radical student protests, the new women's movements saw themselves as departing from past feminism. Rallying to the new motto "the personal is political," they advocated free contraception and abortion, railed against the dominant definition of women's roles as mothers and spouses, and denounced all forms of male violence against women, including in intimate relationships. Organizationally, sexual separatism became a central norm, and small, loosely interconnected groups were favored over conventional hierarchical organizations. Innovative militant practices were developed, such as consciousness raising and self-help. Throughout Western Europe, second-wave women's movements were divided into three dominant currents: liberal (or reformist) feminists called for a gradual improvement of women's rights, mostly through institutional lobbying; radical feminists sought to combat patriarchy through a profound challenge of existing social structures; and socialist feminists called for an inseparable fight against patriarchy and capitalism. In the 1970s, radical thinking gained an unprecedented influence among European women's movements (Bereni 2023).

In this second wave, "often divided on questions of ideology, strategy, goals, and membership, these late-twentieth-century movements mobilized around a broad range of issues, from reproductive rights to sexual and economic exploitation to violence against women. These feminist movements conceptualized women as sharing common experiences of oppression, asserting that "sisterhood is global," but increasingly, in response to critiques from women of color and women in the third world, came to emphasize differences among women on the basis of class, race/ethnicity, sexuality, and nation" (Rupp and Taylor 2013).

This wave was followed by a low ebb, with institutionalization processes: "By the turn of the 1980s, women's policy agencies, often referred to as "state feminism," were established to improve gender equality in many European countries, as well as at the European Union level. Women's organizations, therefore, became less confrontational and more professionalized" (Bereni 2023).

We see in the literature an intensification of feminist debates about the gains and problems ensued by gender mainstreaming efforts. There is emphasis on the problems of cooptation, technocratization and depoliticization of the very issues feminist actors fought to get the state institutions to recognize. In this period, while some organizations stayed out of state politics and remained connected to grassroots, others have been pulled into funding competition, requiring professionalization. This process, feminist authors have noted, have resulted in the NGOization of feminist politics, with

NGOization representing an unwarranted degree of depoliticization (Boris and Prugl 2016, Eschle and Maiguascha 2018).

The new wave of mobilization

According to Molyneux et al. 2021 (New Feminist Activism, Waves and Generations) there is a third-wave feminism that spanned from 1980s and 1990s. They address these characteristics: "the importance of policy-related

activism; the strengthening of feminist movements and rights advocacy in the Global South; and the consolidation of women's studies as a discipline." According to this study, the fourth wave started after the millennium. A different periodizations in the literature exists, but we aim to refer to the abovementioned.

A fourth wave developed in the years 2000, as women's movements became central actors in protests against the Great Recession and related austerity measures, and upon the so-called "refugee crisis. From the Arab Spring to the Indignados protest, from Gezi Park to the Iranian uprisings, feminists and feminist organizations have been most active introducing a gendered and sexual vision of the economic crises, growing political authoritarianisms and conservatism and demands for actions toward solutions.. Gender-based violence and intersectional inequalities became central for the analysis: Feminist movements reacted to a generalised backlash, i.e. the advance of the extreme right and populisms, the spread of anti-gender groups, the attack on women's and LGBTQ+ rights.

"By the turn of the 2010s, feminist mobilizations regained momentum in Europe, reflecting a global trend. A new generation of activists appeared on the scene, combining different forms of repertoires, from direct action to online campaigns. Fierce controversies arose, notably on the Muslim headscarf and sex work, as new radical groups of black, Muslim, trans-queer, or sex-positive feminists stood for the plurality of women's identities and interests. In spite of these political divides, transversal women's coalitions have continued to grow around common issues such as reproductive rights, equal pay and sexual violence, especially in the aftermath of the #MeToo transnational campaign" (Bereni 2023)

The fourth wave has rather focused on "such issues as sexuality, body image, gender identity, the environment, globalization, and popular media. Especially important is an emphasis on the intersections of class, race/ethnicity, and sexuality" (Rupp and Taylor 2013). This wave consolidates the intersectional perspective, coalition building with other social movements, and the challenge to the advancing backlash in most European countries.

In this report we will fill the gap in the literature on feminist mobilizations, through a systematic cross-national comparative analysis of the third wave of mobilization in the European context in a cross-national perspective and in the time frame 2010-2021. In doing this, we will also single out the different constellations of feminist movements as related to specific national political opportunities and networks of alliance and opposition.

Feminisms in space: types of feminism in Europe

Varieties of feminist movements across Europe

Various typologies of feminist movements have been proposed in different periods. In fact, it has been noted that "Feminist movements are by no means monolithic, encompassing as they do numerous ideological strands that differ in the scope of change sought, the extent to which gender inequality is linked to other systems of domination, and the significance attributed to gender differences. [...] At bottom, the basic divide in these categories is between those who emphasize the sameness of women and men and those who focus on difference. This ideological distinction has its counterpart in the goals of movements, some of which work to win identical treatment for women and men and some of which advocate different treatment as the proper route to equality in outcome" (Rupp and Taylor 2013). The national reports included in this research gave an overview of this variety: from the diffusion of grassroots movements in Italy, Turkey and Slovenia, to the articulation of autonomous group and state

feminism in Spain and France, to the progressive embeddedness of gender equality in institutions, in the case of Denmark.

The repertoires of action have been broad and varied, with high capacity at innovation: “Feminist movements have employed a variety of tactical repertoires in different times and places, sometimes dramatic public protests such as marches, demonstrations, and rallies, and sometimes consciousness-raising, self-help, or cultural and discursive forms of resistance oriented to cultural and social change. Not all tactical repertoires are aimed at the state.” (Rupp and Taylor 2013). Differences have been singled out also in the organizational structures: Participants in women's movement organizations develop a range of mobilizing structures to achieve their goals. Bureaucratically structured women's organizations have hierarchical leadership and primarily target mainstream arenas. They may work for women's rights in the public sphere, such as improving women's political representation and legal protection. In contrast, collective organizations use non-hierarchical leadership and decision-making processes, and often place importance on women's cultures and personal experiences. Collective organizations grew from radical feminists' attempts to structure relations among members, to equalize processes of decision making, and to establish group leadership in a way that prefigured an ideal future of gender, sexual, and racial equality. Women's grassroots organizing responds to traditional male-dominated political avenues of change, or top-down bureaucratic structures. Members of grassroots organizations value local knowledge and experiences, as well as the inclusion of women from a variety of social backgrounds. Grassroots organizations may preserve women's political participation in states undergoing postsocialist transition when neoliberal or capitalist policies may undermine the roles that women once held, as in the case of Slovenia. In other political settings, grassroots feminist movements counter-balance the institutionalization and professionalization of feminist claims within institutions, as in the case of Spain.

As for framing, identity building is especially central to feminist movements. Progressively, scholars have given attention to feminism as a collective identity established through participants engagement in organizations and networks that sought to change women's conditions and opportunities. As Rupp and Taylor specify: “a collective-identity approach to feminism shows how feminist culture and the maintenance of a feminist collective identity contribute to the continued vitality of women's movements” (2013). Also, collective identities vary on many different dimensions, in different balances and in different countries. In the feminist literature frames as motherhood, or intersectional frames such as rights of pious women, peasant women, are widely addressed. This attention witnesses the vitality and variety of feminist framing processes across Europe.

Women's political participation and political opportunity structure

Especially (but not only) looking at their identity framing, feminist movements have been distinguished in liberal, radical, or socialist.

Liberal feminism is most typical of mainstream US women's movements, and it “seeks equality for women within the existing social structure, working for equal opportunity in male-dominated economic and political arenas” (Rupp and Taylor 2013). Socialist feminism is rooted in a strong tradition in European movements: it addresses class and gender as responsible for creating inequality and aims to change both capitalism and patriarchy. As Rupp and Taylor note: “Radical feminism considers women a “sex class” and seeks a fundamental transformation of society based on “female values” of nurturing, egalitarianism, pacifism, and cooperation. Categories of feminism have proliferated to include black feminism, lesbian feminism, Islamic feminism, and ecofeminism, to name just a few. Increasingly the plural, “feminisms,” captures the diversity of feminist ideologies” (Rupp and Taylor 2013).

The liberal type of feminism has spread particularly in the US: “Liberal feminist ideology argues that women lack power because they are not, as women, allowed equal opportunity to compete and succeed in the male-dominated economic and political arenas but, instead, are relegated to the subordinate world of home, domestic labor, motherhood, and family. The major strategy for change

is to gain legal and economic equalities and to obtain access to elite positions in the workplace and politics" (Crossley and McKee Hurwitz 2023).

A socialist feminism has characterized a second wave in many European countries: "Socialist feminism, which has been the dominant form of feminism in some countries, shares with radical feminism the intent to transform society in fundamental ways but focuses on a class analysis of the ways that capitalism oppresses women" (Crossley and McKee Hurwitz 2023).

A third type of feminism has been labeled as radical: "radical feminist ideology dates to Simone de Beauvoir's early 1950s theory of "sex class," which was developed further in the late 1960s among small groups of radical women within the New Left. The radical approach recognizes women's identity and subordination as a "sex class," emphasizes women's fundamental difference from men, and recasts relations between women and men in political terms. To unravel the complex structure on which gender inequality rests, requires, from a radical feminist perspective, a fundamental transformation of all institutions in society. To meet this challenge, radical feminists formulated influential critiques of the family, marriage, love, motherhood, heterosexuality, capitalism, and more". (Crossley and McKee Hurwitz 2023). This approach relates also to Black feminism, third world feminism and the development of the concept of intersectionality.

Comparing the women's movements in the UK, USA and Sweden, Joyce Gelb (1989) distinguished three models of women's participation and activism: (a) interest group feminism, characterized by a focus on equal rights and legal equality, a strong network of lobbying organizations and inclusivity (e.g., the United States); (b) ideological, or left-wing, feminism, characterized by fragmented local groups, emphasis on ideological purity and a sectarian approach to politics (e.g., the United Kingdom); and (c) state equality, characterized by the absence of a visible women's movement and a high rate of female participation in institutional politics (e.g., Sweden). The different models appeared to have different levels of efficacy in term of women's rights: "women's groups that are separate from institutionalized interests such as parties and unions are more likely to develop independent strategies and political agendas of their own choosing, thus permitting greater political impact. [...] [A]utonomous feminist movements play a major role in the achievement of significant social change. Otherwise, women are acted upon as an object of social policy, but are not participants in their own destinies" (Gelb 1989, 2). However, despite at a distance from state institutions, autonomous groups play a significant role that can't be neglected, also in the case of Sweden.

The literature explores forms of cooptation or resistance of feminist movements, but this dichotomy needs to be questioned by further analysis (Eschle and Miagwascha 2018; de Jong and Kimm 2017; Altan-Olcay 2020).

Social and political developments were referred to in order to explain cross-national differences. For instance, in Southern Europe, a "Latin model" of access to citizenship was developed. Contrary to the "Anglo-Saxon" and the "Nordic" model, it was characterized by a long delay in terms of equal rights. "In 1945, the juridical code of the Latin countries and/or those countries with a Civil Code after the French model ... is one of women that, recently become citizens... [and] are still very subordinated to the power of a husband they have to obey" (Sineau 1992, 537).

As with other movements, women's movements are influenced by the opportunity structure presented by their respective political environments. In Southern Europe the interactions between the women's movements, the political parties, and the governments have been particularly important during paths of democratization. Women's movements and democratization interacted in two ways. First of all, in all eight countries included in the project, women took part, although with different organizational forms and identities, in the resistance against the authoritarian regime and in democratic consolidation. Second, the path to women's rights was facilitated under democratic regimes. In general, democracy entails equal political rights of all citizens to the State. Different pathways to democracy, however, may be more or less conducive to women's rights.

The importance of the party system for the development of social movements has often been emphasized (e.g., Kriesi et al 1995), and the influence of the Left on women's movements is not a new

subject. In fact, research on women's conditions stresses the importance of political alliances, particularly with the Left, and of positive action implemented by the State. Pippa Norris' research explained that parties have a direct influence on female pay levels and occupational segregation; on controversial, positional issues such as reproductive rights; on welfare issues, such as child-care facilities; and on opportunities for women in politics (Norris 1987, 73, 107, 131). As she remarks: "it was Mitterand who initiated the Ministry for women's rights in France, Papandreou, leader of PASOK, who created the Greek Council for Equal Rights, and the Labor Party which set up the Equal Opportunities Commission to monitor equal pay in Britain" (Norris 1987, 4).

Also, other social movements have been important as precursors of spillover of waves of mobilization. Explaining the emergence of the American women's liberation movement, Jo Freeman singled out "the need for a preexisting communications network or infrastructure within the social base of a movement" -- warning, however, that "Not any communications network will do. It must be a network that is cooptable to the new ideas of the incipient movement" (1975, 48). In fact, the civil rights movements in the United States and student movements in Europe were such "preexisting communications networks".

The strength of political and social allies may explain some characteristics of the women's movements. In general, women's movements have an ambivalent attitude towards politics: they emphasize autonomy from the State, though the welfare state is the necessary precondition for the emancipation of women; they developed within an egalitarian culture, but ask for positive discrimination; they stress "separatism", yet seek for political allies. As Lovenduski observed, the contemporary women's movement has "contradictory implications for the political role of women. On the one hand, its mobilizing capacity has involved numerous women in political activity. On the other hand, the movement's anti-hierarchical ethos and the separatism advocated by some feminists made many women extremely suspicious of highly structured, male dominated political institutions" (Lovenduski 1986, 115).

National women's movements have been particularly influenced by the characteristics of their allies--the left-wing parties in particular--which were available to act, at least in institutional politics, as advocate of women's rights, as the case of Spain shows. The relationship between women and the Left is however not an easy one. Mary Katzenstein, for instance, stated that, although "the socialist and communist parties of Western Europe have been far more supportive of feminist concerns than the (Christian Democratic) Center or the Right", "the ideological privilege they give to class over gender concerns has made them problematic allies" (1987, 6). Focusing on Mediterranean Europe, another study argued that although Communist Parties generally welcome the positive impacts of social movements, they continuously make efforts to control the movement's actions and development while stressing the central role of the party - as they have done in Italy, Spain and Greece" (Marantzidis 1996, 101-17). In Southern Europe, the improvement in women's conditions followed different paths in different countries: in Italy, a semi-autonomous women's movements allied with an Old Left which was always in the opposition; in Greece, feminism was associated with leftist parties as well as a PASOK-driven state feminism; in Spain, "pressure group feminism" developed with few direct contacts with a women's policy agency directly controlled by the PSOE; in Portugal a women's policy agency played a role in the creation of women's non-governmental organizations. The interaction between political parties and the civil society during democratization is a main key to understand these differences. Since the Left-wing parties acted as the political carriers of this accelerated modernization process, it is no wonder that Southern European women's movements appeared to position themselves nearer to the Old Left than was the case in other Western democracies.

Feminist movements trajectories

Building upon a typological approach, we can observe that our eight national reports pointed at different main trajectories. Some cases, such as Denmark or the EU level, have been involved in a process of NGOization, while most others, such as Greece, France, Italy, Slovenia, Poland, Spain, and Turkey, by a process of SMOization.

NGOization

With the concept of NGOization the literature addresses the modernisation of repertoire occurred in the late 1980s, with the replacement of massive protests with opinion formation and lobbying (della Porta 2013); the organizational structuration, and so a greater capacity to organize and channel requests to decision makers; and a depoliticization of frames, which means a focus on specific issues often in accordance with mainstream discourses, in order to increase the resonance with public opinion (Della Porta 2020). This form of hybridization combines the legacy of disruptive social movement organizations with the form of non-governmental organization. In countries like Denmark this process is specifically detectable with regard to the focus on gender equality, and a growing reframing of feminist issues in accordance with mainstream conceptualisations of gender.

SMOization

A second trajectory underlined by the literature is the SMOization. Developing in particular during the anti-austerity protests, this process concerns “an increasing tension between a representative and a participatory conception of politics” (Della Porta 2020: 944). It implies the use of diffusion of direct social action (such as the Urban Social Clinic providing free medical assistance in Greece); networking across issues and actors (e.g., between NGOs and grassroots organizations, in order to face the decline of access to policy-makers, as in the case of Poland); the politicization of discourses, that often happens in reaction to repression and crises (as in the case of Italy, Spain and Turkey with regard to gender-based violence, care, and rape culture).

Methodological notes

The report is composed of eight national reports, that explore the available literature on the feminist movements in each of the covered countries. As mentioned in the introduction, all the reports outline gaps in the study of feminist movements which have been in general less studied and less in-depth than other social movements. Especially, the last ten years of organization and mobilization have been particularly under-researched. To fill the gap in the literature, the national reports aim to collect the available literature, both from academia and “grey literature”.

The chapters review existing literature that presents, analyses, and discusses some main dimensions of feminist movements, including main organizational models and networks, repertoires of action, frames as well as debates and policy outcomes. The project pays specific attention to five main thematic domains: labour market; health and reproductive rights; migration; LGBTQ+ rights; and gender-based violence, but other “hot topics” emerged in the mapping phase, such as alimony in the case of Turkey, care in Spain, or women prisoners in Greece are included as well.

The analysis covers:

1. scholarly articles, book chapters, monographs, conference papers, etc.
2. Expert reports and other "grey literature" (any type of text (report, pamphlet, book, article, etc.) that cannot be classified as scientific but contains "expert knowledge" on the topic. These reports are usually produced by non-governmental organizations, movements, journalists, and other members of the "critical public".

The national reports cover all types of documents listed above in the period from 2010 to present times with regard to feminist movements (including transnational and EU-related texts related to each country). To this aim, they refer to scholarly literature and to secondary sources (press news, parliamentary debates, documents released by social movements and political actors, social media publications).

The composition of this report

The history of the feminist movements

The national reports give an overview of the history of feminist movements according to political developments and changes in political opportunity structures. In certain countries, such as Spain and Greece, dictatorships influenced the timing of the second wave of feminism, and a case like Turkey witnesses how feminist movements deal with the challenge of an authoritarian regime at the present time. Political opportunity structures have in fact influenced the development of feminist movements over time. In some countries, like Poland, the worsening of women's conditions, e.g., with the repeated attacks on the right to abortion, has triggered a growing politicisation around gender issues and, thus, a growth in feminist mobilisations. In other cases, such as Denmark, the close relations between movements, institutions and the state have impacted upon collective framing and repertoires of action around gender equality.

Actors, organizational models and allies

Secondly, the national reports address the composition of actors included in the network of feminist movements (movements, associations, anti-violence centres, NGOs, political parties) and the kind of alliances that feminist movements develop (both extra-institutional and within institutions). As already mentioned, the actors and the organizational models can be detected through the lens of the hybridization of social movement organizations and civil society organizations, in the form of NGOization and SMOisation. Some countries show a tendency to stronger alliances with leftist and progressive parties (such as Poland and Greece) but also widespread is the networking on issues and campaigns with other social movements, as with the environmental and LGBTQ+ movement in Turkey. As testified for by the case of Slovenia, there is often a split between two different approaches towards alliances: an anti-institutional one, and one open to negotiation.

Themes, agenda and frames

Later on, the national reports explore the five thematic policy areas mentioned above: (1) labor market, (2) health & reproductive rights, (3) migration, (4) LGBTQ+ rights, and (5) gender-based violence. They describe how these topics emerge in the feminist movements in each country and whether these policy issues trigger/ed feminist movements to mobilise. Moreover, they single out additional topics that emerged as important. While in some countries we can detect a vast majority of mobilisations around the issue of abortion and sexual and reproductive rights, as in the case of Poland, in others the last decade has been characterised by a clear focus on gender-based violence, as in Spain and Italy, as a result of framing work around specific cases, such as the gang rape during San Fermines in Pamplona. Looking at themes like migration we can observe cleavages within feminist movements between white (and native) activists and racialized groups, rather than cases of sharing of frames and actions. In almost all countries, LGBTQ+ rights are an integral part of feminist movements, and over the years there has been a progressive interweaving of gender and sexuality issues. Moreover, the labor market appears as a major theme in those countries that either engaged with the feminist strike, and thus with a specific focus on productive and reproductive work, or in those countries where strict correlation between movement and the state exists, such as Denmark. Some emerging themes are, for example, technology and art in Greece, the case of alimony in Turkey, academic freedom in Denmark, and education in Italy.

Repertoire of action, campaigns and debates

This section in each report explores the repertoire of action employed by feminist movements, in terms of contentious politics and/or of relations with state institutions. As we already observed, the last decade saw the development of innovative actions by feminist movements. From a local perspective, while some countries, like Italy, Spain and Poland, engage in feminist strikes, bridging the tradition of the labor movement to gendered issues (such as social reproductive work), others, like Greece or

Denmark, show the relevance of the use of social media, for instance in relation to transnational diffusion (from US to Europe) of the #MeToo campaign. While in some countries, such as Slovenia, forms of autonomous action (like the management of free spaces and direct social action) appear more relevant, in others, such as Denmark, lobbying and petitioning are more to the forefront. Quite often, the relationship with trans movements emerged as an important topic within feminist movements, as in the case of Slovenia, Italy, and Spain.

Policy Outcomes

The project intends to look at how the issues, frames of argument, repertoires of action, and campaigns of feminist movements influence models of democracy, and thus how state institutions do or do not take on board the stimuli of feminist movements. To do this, each report singles out, if available in the literature, the key policy-related outcomes. In some countries, opportunity to intervene in democratic processes and policy debates is almost missing, such as in the case of Poland from 2015 onwards. In other countries, feminist mobilizations had the will, and somehow the capacity, to address policy changes, as in the case of Denmark with the #MeToo movement and the consent-based rape law. Quite generally, the diffusion at the EU level of gender mainstreaming and gender equality measures increased the access to policy and favored policy changes, as in the case of Greece. Significant impacts of feminism can be detected in Spain, on issues like care and labor market, equal parental leaves, abortion, gender-based violence, and LGBTQ+ rights, because of state feminism and of the alliance between feminist movements and progressive parties in power.

National Reports

Denmark

The national report provides a literature review of the extant research on Danish feminist movements in the period 2010-22. Compared to the other Scandinavian countries, gender equality has been weakly institutionalized in Denmark, and feminist actors are often challenged by a discourse of gender and sexual exceptionalism; that gender equality has already been achieved. However, particularly the influence of the #MeToo movement in nearly all parts of Danish society since 2017 has contributed to new momentum for the feminist movements, even though it has also led to more antifeminist mobilization. Most noticeable, after years of activist campaigning the Danish Parliament passed a consent-based rape law in 2020, which was widely perceived as a real but also symbolically important victory for the feminist movements.

The literature on the feminist movements primarily includes case studies of selected feminist actors, campaigns, and debates. Except for a few studies, there is a lack of literature on the internal dynamic, democratic models, and networks within and between feminist organizations as well as activist groups. Regarding thematic areas, gender-based violence stands out as particularly prominent given the widespread impact of #MeToo, but the labour market as well as migration are also repeatedly put in focus through campaigns and discussions on issues such as the gender pay gap as well as discrimination and marginalization of women with an ethnic minority background. The most well-organized feminist actors in Denmark are women's organizations, but there is also a lively and multifaceted (albeit rather disaggregated) milieu of other organizations, activist groups, and individual debaters.

France

Most academic research on feminist movements published in the 2010-2021 period focus on the second wave of feminism, for example : Jacquemart and Masclet 2017; Pavard 2012; Ruault 2016; 2021). However, a “new wave” of feminism is analysed by a few key authors in the most recent years. The wide-range of the topics covered reflects the diversity of the feminist movement in France: from cyberactivism (Jouët, Niemeyer, and Pavard 2017), ecofeminism (Benquet and Pruvost 2019), sexual and gender violence (Lett et al. 2020; Delage, Lieber, and Chetcuti-Osorovitz 2019) to gender analysis of the movements (Bereni 2012; Jacquemart 2013).

Current divisions could be very schematically be summed up as : Universalism vs. Intersectionalism ; For / Against prostitution; Essentialists / Differentialists vs Gender and Institutionalists vs grassroots feminism (Pavard, Rochefort, and Zancarini-Fournel 2020) ; Other associated or derived debates such as Quotas in Politics (Bender, Berrebi-Hoffmann, and Reigné 2015; Laufer and Paoletti 2015) and/or Medically Assisted Procreation or Surrogate Mothers, especially when these issues intersect with single motherhood, lesbianism and trans rights. The divides in the feminist movements were shaped in the period on the backbone of rising islamophobia and several State legislation on the Islamic Veil. Those divisions can be partly analyzed as a generational divide. They play out around long-standing divisions of the French feminist movements.

Critical junctures for the feminist movements in France that were identified by the authors include: the change of Presidential Majority in 2012 and in 2017, Public Debates about same sex marriage (2013) and Medically Assisted Procreation for all (2021). Critical Junctures within the movement include the debates and legislations around the islamic veil (2004, 2010, 2016), code of labour reform (2017) and pension reform (2017).

In the period considered, the most noticeable changes in the feminist movement are the apparition of one major movement, *Nous Toutes*, that managed to gather several feminist movements for major demonstrations in November since 2018 and the apparition of structured movements framed to answer issues linked to race and religion that are struggling to be addressed in other feminist movements (i.e. *Lallab*). A nebulous of individual initiatives, small collectives (without legal structures) and new associations also appear since the beginning of the 2015's and even more after #MeToo, notably to fight against cyberviolence. Very few links with feminist transnational movements appear from the literature review.

Since 2010 France has implemented major legislation in favor of feminist thought, such as same sex marriage in 2013, extending the rights of medically assisted pregnancy to single women and couples with no men involved in 2021, implementing an age of consent (15 years old) and banning LGBTQ+ conversion therapy in 2022. Other successes linked to women's rights can be identified such as extension of abortion rights period (2022) and the creation of a national annual State led gathering with NGOs to fight against domestic violence (*Grenelle des violences conjugales*, 2019).

One of the major threats to feminist movements is the anti-gender movement, both at the political level and online. The most famous example is 'La Manif Pour Tous' (The Protest For All) formed against the 2013 same sex marriage act called 'Le Marriage Pour Tous' (Marriage For All) which lead to the failure of les "ABCD de l'égalité" (2013-2014). The rise of strong "alterfeminist" discourses in France, that recognizes some of the legacy of feminism but remains deeply differentialist and anti-gender is another, more recent development.

Greece

Research and activism on gender identities, equality and sexuality concur that in Greece the timespan 2010-2021 saw a remarkable and refreshing resurgence of feminist and LGBTQI+ theory and action after two decades of relative quiescence. Massive protests, on the streets, through mass media, online and in institutions, were staged to protest the public stigmatisation of HIV-positive women in 2012, the transphobic murder of Zack Kostopoulos in Athens in 2018, a series of femicides which received attention in mass media, the Greek #MeToo, and the 8th of March women's strikes. In addition, various forms of gender-related interventions framed a broader positive agenda which demanded institutional and legislative reforms but exceeded them, agitating for deeper transformations of heteronormative patriarchal gender stereotypes challenged from intersectional and queer perspectives.

Patriarchy, gender-based violence, LGBTQI+ recognition and rights, issues of labour, care and social reproduction, refugees and migration are the most salient topics of relevant protest and intervention. In these areas of concern and action, a host of distinct and partly new trends which carry potentials for democratic innovation become pronounced.

It becomes evident that state policies and institutional action do not suffice to dismantle the deeply embedded, centuries-long patriarchy and violence in Greek society. To this end, feminist and LGBTQI+ agency responds in the following ways which take aim at the very social construction and reconstruction of gender identities and sexualities across diverse social relations and levels: a new scheme of grassroots, non-bureaucratic and non-hierarchical mobilization; a close interaction between gender and sexuality movement; intersectionality; personal and collective experiences are positioned in their socio-political conditions and become subject to political re-elaboration; new 'activist' research and education centres are established at universities and beyond; and massive anti-austerity mobilizations, new grassroots community initiatives and multiple ventures in the social and solidarity economy mark the period of reference.

The intricate complexity of the field itself, and the several gaps and blind spots in existing research and publications on feminist and LGBTQI+ politics in 2010-2021 call for extensive further inquiries on multiple levels (institutional, grassroots, international etc.) and through various methodologies (interviews, ethnographic observation, policy and discourse analysis etc.). In particular, there is scant in-depth and comprehensive research on the internal composition of the various actors, their frames of analysis, their repertoires of action, their national and international networks, their relations with institutional actors and the political system, their policy proposals for institutions, and broader social transformation regarding labor, health and reproductive issues and migration.

Italy

In the period 2010-2021, feminist networks and campaigns have proliferated in Italy. At the beginning of the decade, there was already a great variety of collectives, groups and associations that ranged from queer approaches to the fight against gender-based violence. These groups have been strongly involved in the resistance against anti-gender/anti-feminist movements that has been highly supported by right-wing parties. From 2016 onwards, the new wave of the transnational feminist movements focused on gender-based violence conceived as a structural dimension of contemporary capitalist and neoliberal society. Starting in Argentina, the campaign soon reached Italy, where it triggered a huge mobilization at the national and local level lead by the new organization named after the Argentinian one, Non Una Di Meno - NUDM (Not One Less).

Academic and activist circles turned then their attention to new issues emerging from the feminist movements. First of all, gender-based violence was seen as a lens to understand social structures, gender socialization and the shape of state institutions. Second, there was a concern with the material dimension of feminist claims, for instance with regard to the labour conditions of women, lesbian, trans and non-binary people; the pauperization and precarization of life; increasing gender inequality; as well as the retrenchment of the welfare system and public services. Third, there was a focus on health and reproductive rights, and against the increasing attacks on abortion and women's freedom over their body. Fourth, claims for LGBTQI+ rights also addressed the parliamentary debate on the so-called DDL Zan, a proposed law on the criminalisation of homophobia and transphobia and hate crimes, which was never approved, not even under a center-left coalitional government. Finally, academic and activist circles turned their attention to migration, both because of gendered migration flows and because of the growth of a "second generation" of citizens with a migrant background.

The movement has been highly innovative also with regard to repertoire of action (with the development of the feminist strike), of composition (as an inter-generational movement), and of organization models.

Poland

Feminist activism in Poland exists since the late 1800s, however only in recent years has it gained recognition and popular support. The key issue that the feminist movement has dealt with in recent history are reproductive rights. The rise of conservative-liberal strain within the pro-democratic opposition resulted in an 'abortion compromise' in 1993 that gave Polish women one of the most restrictive abortion rights legislation in Europe. Since then, there have been numerous attempts to change the law in both directions. Similarly there were discussions about gender-based violence,

connected to the question of ratification of the Istanbul Convention. After the regime change in 1989 there has been a flowering of civil society organisations, mostly in the form of NGOs, who aimed at providing various forms of assistance and education for Polish women. Despite this, the term feminism was in Poland more of a stigma, rather than a political etiquette.

The main turning point was 2015, when the conservative and populist right-wing party Law and Justice won the parliamentary elections, securing majority in both chambers of the Parliament and also the President's office. Because of that the radical anti-choice actors gained a powerful ally and began more actively than previously to secure funds and political support for their agenda. A massive response to one of the projects to even further restrict the abortion law in 2016 became a shock for observers of political life in Poland. Massive protests that spread around the country under the label Black Protests marked a new opening for the Polish feminist movement, that gained huge popular support and the radical faction of the movement became more dominant. The next wave of protests appeared in 2020, when the verdict of the highly politicised Constitutional Court restricted legal access to abortion to a virtual minimum. This wave was much bigger than in 2016 (some observers say that these were the biggest protests since the fall of the communist regime in 1989) and around that campaign new groups and organisations emerged, attracting mostly young women to their radical agenda, creating a divide between the 'radical' groups and the formerly existing 'liberal' organisations. This new wave reflects recently observed changes in social and political activism in Poland (and beyond), being more intersectional, focused also on social issues, various forms of exclusion etc.

The long-lasting effects of the recent wave of feminist protests are crystallised networks of activists, who provide various forms of support for women: local initiatives, educational programs etc. These networks were also used to provide help for Ukrainian refugees after February 24, 2022.

Slovenia

This report examines the existing academic and expert literature that analyses feminist movements in Slovenia by including 22 studies published between 2010 and 2022. Contemporary feminist movements in Slovenia have been influenced by the initiatives from the past. However, they also emerged through ad hoc collective actions in response to broader socio-political events. Feminist mobilizations that developed after 2010 are characterized by their diffuse and plural character and expansion of themes and agendas that precede the gender framework and/or link this frame to precarity, anti-capitalism, anti-authoritarianism, autonomy and autonomous spaces, queer and queerness, LGBTQI+ rights, and gender-based violence. The literature reveals a wide variety of sporadic groups and actors operating in different fields and adopting different forms of organization, from horizontal, non-hierarchical autonomous groups to a variety of smaller organizations, including NGOs. Some actors form national and transnational alliances with other similar initiatives and/or institutions seeking institutional change, while others define their activities beyond or against institutionalism.

The predominant strategies of the feminist movement consist of a diverse repertoire of actions and frames of arguments that reflect the ideological framework of their operation, ranging from street encounters, protests, workshops, and events, to activist expression through visual and performing arts. We can observe the lack of influence of the feminist agenda on decision-making processes in Slovenia, due to the relatively fragile and temporary nature of certain initiatives and the movement's poor connections with political and state actors. However, some recent initiatives have succeeded in challenging, improving, or renewing democratic models, particularly in the area of gender-based violence. The report also outlines the recommendations for future research in order to unfold the importance of feminist movements in revitalising democratic practises in Slovenia.

Spain

Most of the literature on the Spanish feminist movements has focused on the period 1960s-1980s, when feminism struggles were hand in hand with the anti-Franco struggles and for democracy. There is not much published on the evolution of the movements beyond the 1980s (as an exception, see Gil 2011). However, together with the recent rise of feminist mobilizations, academic publications on the Spanish feminist movements are multiplying. In the last fifteen years, Spanish feminist movements and

research have focused on new issues, such as precariousness, care work and care policies, domestic work and global care chains, as well as old issues that have strongly re-emerged and are cause of internal and external conflicts (abortion, prostitution/sex work, the subject of feminism, transfeminism).

Regarding the most relevant events or campaigns of the period 2010-2021, most of the academic literature on the feminist movements of the period has focused on the 15M and the feminist strikes, but the mobilisations inbetween (protests against Gallardon's abortion bill, 7N campaigns against gender violences) have barely been explored. In the last four years, the legislation (Sexual Freedom Act; LGBTIQ+ and Trans Law) promoted by the Ministry of Equality of the centre-leftist coalition government (Partido Socialista Obrero Español [PSOE] and Unidas Podemos [UP]) (2019-2023) is causing a lot of public controversy, even within feminisms and the Spanish left. However, there is very little academic publications on these feminist controversies yet -although there is plenty of grey literature. The literature of the period has just tangentially addressed the composition of the movements, organisational models, and collective action repertoires and, when it has done so, it has always been in relation with generational divergences within feminisms, with younger generations being portrayed as more innovative, autonomous and pro-deliberative processes and less in favour of structures, representative models, formal memberships, fees and relations with institutions. Although there is this blind spot in relation to organisational models and strategies, there has been greater interest in digital feminism and social media campaigns. Apart from this, other blind spots remain: the impact of the feminist movement, and especially its strategies and negotiations to influence the decision-making process, have not been studied in depth; and, even if intersectionality and anti-feminist anti-gender discourses are gaining relevance in research, there are few analyses on how feminist social movements are introducing intersectionality.

Turkey

The literature on feminist movements in Turkey is wide and varied, reflecting the rich history of the movement. This scholarship focuses on the development, diversification and strengthening of the movement from the 1980s to the early 2000s, highlighting collaborations and successes at the policy level. The literature on the past ten years focuses on the impact of the growing authoritarianism and conservatism in the government on the movement. There is emphasis on the changing repertoires of action from lobbying to more contentious online and offline collective action in the absence of direct links to the government and the efforts to build platforms that could bring different activist groups together. The discussion also highlights the strains on the latter in a political context defined by increasing polarizations along various axes such as pro-anti-government, Islamic-Secular, Sunni-Alevi, Turkish-Kurdish and so on. The scholarship also discusses a shift in policy goals from achieving progressive change to retaining changes already achieved given the anti-feminist and anti-gender stance in the government.

The critical junctures since 2011 include the participation in the preparation and signing of the Istanbul Convention in 2011, the preparation of the 2012 Law on Protection of the Family and Prevention of Violence against Women, the 2013 Gezi mobilizations, the national elections and the end of the peace process in 2015, the 2016 coup attempt and the declaration of state of emergency for two years, the 2017 referendum which changed the political regime, and the 2019 local elections. Scholarly discussions reveal the intensity of feminist mobilization against gender-based violence and to protect health and reproductive rights. Feminist-anti-feminist confrontation in the legislation organizing alimony in case of dissolution of marriage; secularism-Islamism and the threats posed by the latter's institutionalization in the state policy making; and the impact of the Kurdish issue can be said to be issue areas specific to the case of Turkey.

There is much less literature on feminist mobilization in the issue areas of labor market and migration. Furthermore, literature on LGBTIQ+ movement in Turkey is developed, but the recent debates around trans inclusiveness have not made their way into scholarly writing yet. There is also room for more research on the feminist repertoire of action and discursive frames developed in the face of dual

threats posed by neoliberalism and neoconservatism as well as the contemporary criminalization of feminist movements by the government and associated right wing actors.

Conclusions

In the time frame 2010-2021 a new cycle of feminist transnational mobilizations and protests has begun. Although some countries, such as Poland, Turkey, Spain, and Italy, show a greater influence of the spread of mobilisations from Latin America, other countries, such as Slovenia or Denmark, where the influence of transnational mobilisations should not be overestimated, also present a certain vitality of feminist activism. With the global takeover of the neoliberal model, of general backlash related to the rise of populist and right-wing political parties, in conjunction with recurring economic, environmental and health crises, feminist movements came into action in a context of tricky political opportunity structure. The effects of globalisation, which have been targeted by social movements since the 1990s (della Porta 2003), influence political systems, social inequalities, and gender regimes. Yet, a second effect of globalisation is that it has shortened the distance between movements, and it facilitated cross-national processes of contamination and diffusion (Mayo 2005).

Innovations brought forward by feminist movements concern ideology, and the shift from the concept of difference to intersectionality; and the repertoire of action, in terms of organization, feminist strike, performances and direct social action. Mobilizations occurred through transnational networks, thanks to the extensive role played by social media.

In this report we summarize some of the common elements of feminist movements in eight European countries, in time and space. From the point of view of the framing process, it is possible to observe a shift in ideology from the concept of difference to that of intersectionality. More than ever, in some countries the critique of the gender regime is intertwined with the critique of the capitalist economic model. Recent mobilisations and protests have had the capacity to broaden political participation and bring feminist issues to the forefront of the media, the public debate and in some cases the political agenda. However, a growing consensus around right-wing, populist and anti-gender forces challenges the capacity of feminist movements to organize and have an influence on the democratic regime. Far-right and anti-gender movements intensify anti-feminist stances, e.g. in the case of Poland with regard to abortion rights, or in the case of Slovenia with regard to LGBTQI+ rights. The spread of apparent gender equality, which is mirrored by programmes of gender mainstreaming, branding and social networks, is matched by a reaction of strong conservatism stirred up by the threat to the social order based on the family and the subordination of women, lesbians, trans and non-binary people.

According to the national reports, two major trajectories can be detected. On the one hand, the NGOization of feminist movements and the development of professionalized and increasing nation-state related forms of feminist organizations. On the other hand, the SMOization, in the sense of grassroots feminist organizations gaining momentum.

More than before, feminist movements spread through young generations, also thanks to social media, that influenced the diffusion, as well as the forms of political participation, with increasing individual activism. In some countries, such as Italy and Spain, intergenerational connections appear more relevant, opening the way for transmission from one generation to the other and for innovative forms of collective action.

Among the major themes addressed by feminist movements we find health and reproductive rights, LGBTQI+ rights, and gender-based violence. While themes like migration are less relevant in some countries, they have a crucial role in others, such as Denmark. The same goes for themes like the labor market, that gains growing attention with the diffusion in some countries of the forms of action of the feminist strike.

In the last decade, feminist movements have questioned and transformed concepts and practices of democracy, by contending a progressive understanding of gender openly contested by conservative actors. Although results in terms of policy outcomes and influence on institutions, both coming from

feminist movements and from anti-gender groups, are yet to be fully estimated, these two political actors are currently addressing the main challenges to democracy.

Bibliography

Altan-Olcay, Ö. (2020). Politics of engagement: Gender expertise and international governance. *Development and Change*, 51(5), 1271-1295.

Banaszak, L.A. (ed.) (2006) *The US Women's Movement in Global Perspective*. Rowman & Littlefield, Lanham, MD.

Banaszak, L.A., Beckwith, K., and Rucht, D. (eds) (2003) *Women's Movements Facing the Reconfigured State*. Cambridge University Press, New York.

Bereni, L. « The Women's Cause in a Field: Rethinking the Architecture of Collective Protest in the Era of Movement Institutionalization ». *Social Movement Studies*, 2019.

Bereni, L. (2013). Women's Movements (Europe). *The Wiley-Blackwell Encyclopedia of Social and Political Movements*, 1-3.

Boris, E., & Prugl, L. (2016). *Homeworkers in global perspective: invisible no more*. Routledge.

Bull, A., Diamond, H., and Marsh, R. (eds) (2000) *Feminisms and Women's Movements in Contemporary Europe*. St Martin's Press, New York.

Crossley Alison Dahl Crossley, A., & McKee Hurwitz, H. (2013). Women's Movements. *The Wiley-Blackwell Encyclopedia of Social and Political Movements*.

Crossley, A. D. (2017) *Finding Feminism: Millennial Activists and the Unfinished Gender Revolution*. NYU Press, New York.

Dalla Costa, M., & James, S. (2017). *The Power of Women and the Subversion of the Community*. Falling Wall Press, Bristol.

De Jong, S. (2017). *Complicit sisters: gender and women's issues across North-South divides*. Oxford University Press.

Della Porta, D. (2013). *Can democracy be saved*. Oxford: Polity Press.

Della Porta, D. (2020). Building bridges: Social movements and civil society in times of crisis. *VOLUNTAS: International Journal of Voluntary and Nonprofit Organizations*, 31(5), 938-948.

Eschle, C. (2018). *Global democracy, social movements, and feminism*. Routledge.

Eschle, C., & Maignashca, B. (2018). Theorising feminist organising in and against neoliberalism: beyond co-optation and resistance?. *European Journal of Politics and Gender*, 1(1-2), 223-239.

Federici, S. (2004). *Caliban and the Witch*. Autonomedia.

Feree, M.M., and Hess, B. (2000) *Controversy and Coalition: The New Feminist Movement Across Four Decades of Change*, 3rd edn. Routledge, New York.

Ferguson, L. (2018). *Gender training: A transformative tool for gender equality*. Springer.

Ferree, M.M., and Mueller, C.M. (2007) *Feminism and the women's movement: A global perspective*. In: Snow, D.A., Soule, S.A., and Kriesi, H. (eds), *The Blackwell Companion to Social Movements*. Blackwell, Oxford, pp. 576-607.

Freedman, E.B. (2002) *No Turning Back: The History of Feminism and the Future of Women*. Ballantine Books, New York.

Gilmore, S. (ed.) (2008) *Feminist Coalitions: Historical Perspectives on Second-Wave Feminism in the United States*. University of Illinois Press, Urbana/Champaign.

- Halsaa, B., Roseneil, S., Sümer, S. (2012) *Remaking Citizenship in Multicultural Europe: Women's Movements, Gender and Diversity*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Hartmann, S.M. (1998) *The Other Feminists: Activists in the Liberal Establishment*. Yale University Press, New Haven, CT.
- Hurwitz, H.M. (2021) *Are We the 99%? The Occupy Movement, Feminism, and Intersectionality*. Temple University Press, Philadelphia.
- Kaplan, G. (1992) *Contemporary Western European Feminism*. New York University Press, New York.
- Krook, M. L., & Mackay, F. (Eds.). (2011). *Gender, politics and institutions: Towards a feminist institutionalism* (Vol. 1). Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Lépinard, E. (2020) *Feminist Trouble: Intersectional Politics in Post-Secular Times*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- MacKinnon, C. A. (1982). Feminism, Marxism, method, and the state: An agenda for theory. *Signs: Journal of women in culture and society*, 7(3), 515-544.
- Meyer, D. S., & Whittier, N. (1994). Social movement spillover. *Social problems*, 41(2), 277-298.
- Offen, K. (2000) *European Feminisms: A Political History, 1700–1950*. Stanford University Press, Stanford, CA.
- Outshoorn, J. (2016) *European Women's Movements and Body Politics: The Struggle for Autonomy*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Rai, S. M. (2003). *Mainstreaming gender, democratizing the state*. Manchester University Press.
- Rao, A., & Kelleher, D. (2005). Is there life after gender mainstreaming?. *Gender & Development*, 13(2), 57-69.
- Ray, R. (1999) *Fields of Protest: Women's Movements in India*. University of Minnesota Press, Minneapolis.
- Reger, J. (2005) *Different Wavelengths: Studies of the Contemporary Women's Movement*. Routledge, New York.
- Reger, J. (2021) *Gender and social movements*. Polity Press, Cambridge.
- Roth, B. (2004) *Separate Roads to Feminism: Black, Chicana, and White Feminist Movements in America's Second Wave*. Cambridge University Press, New York.
- Rupp, L.J. (1997) *Worlds of Women: The Making of an International Women's Movement*. Princeton University Press, Princeton, NJ.
- Rupp, L.J., and Taylor, V. (1987) *Survival in the Doldrums: The American Women's Rights Movement, 1945 to the 1960s*. Oxford University Press, New York.
- Staggenborg, S., and Taylor, V. (2005) Whatever happened to the women's movement? *Mobilization* 10, 37–52.
- Taylor, V. (1989) Social movement continuity: The women's movement in abeyance. *American Sociological Review* 54, 761–775.
- Taylor, V., and Whittier, N.E. (1992) Collective identity in social movement communities: Lesbian feminist mobilization. In: Morris, A.D., and Mueller, C.M. (eds), *Frontiers in Social Movement Theory*. Yale University Press, New Haven, CT, pp. 104–129.
- Walby, S. (2003). *Gender transformations*. Routledge, London.
- Walby, S. (2020). Varieties of gender regimes. *Social Politics: International Studies in Gender, State & Society*, 27(3), 414-431.

Whittier, N. (1995) *Feminist Generations: The Persistence of the Radical Women's Movement*. Temple University Press, Philadelphia.

Wulff, S., Bernstein M. and Taylor, V. (2015) *New Theoretical Directions from the Study of Gender and Sexuality Movements: Collective Identity, Multi-Institutional Politics, and Emotions*. In: Della Porta D. and Diani M. (2015) *Oxford Handbook on Social Movement Studies*, Oxford University press, Oxford.

1 DENMARK

DENMARK

WP2, deliverable 2.1

1.1 Introduction

A 2017 online opinion poll, based on more than 300,000 respondents, listed gender equality as one of the ten most important Danish values, together with the Christian cultural heritage, the Danish language, and the welfare society. As gender scholars Anette Borchorst and Drude Dahlerup argue, it is somehow a paradox that gender equality is such a cherished national value, as the example showcases, while the public debate and policy initiatives on issues relating to gender equality have, at the same time, been limited in the last two decades (Dahlerup & Borchorst, 2020). The prevalent ‘gender equality champion’ discourse stands in contrast to the more critical 2021 CEDAW (Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination Against Women) conclusions, regarding the status on gender equality in Denmark. Concerns arise regarding, e.g., the prevalence of gender-based violence, the insufficient representation of women in local politics, as well as the ways in which “[s]exism and misogyny in public and political life are causing women to refrain from participating in political and public life, including in public online debates” (CEDAW, 2021, p. 11).

Compared to other Scandinavian countries, gender equality has been weakly institutionalized in Denmark. From 2010 to 2022, it has not been at the forefront of Danish politics. This is, for instance, illustrated by the fact that shifting Danish governments have not established an independent ministry for gender equality. Instead, gender equality as a policy area has been part of quite mixed ministries such as the Ministry for Children, Gender Equality, Integration and Social Affairs (2013-15) and the newly established Ministry for Digitalization and Gender Equality (2022-). Key issues in recent years have only been introduced on the legislative agenda through EU policies; this is the case for gender quotas for company boards as well as earmarked paternity leave. In general, changes to gender equality legislation in Denmark have often been driven by the adoption and transposition of EU directives (such as the equal pay legislation).

Historically, the Danish gender equality model¹ has been based on mobilization and alliances between feminist social movements and social partners such as trade unions. Bottom-up initiatives driven with respect for the Danish model of the labor market and its social dialogue have been important in the development of policy issues such as equal pay and sexual harassment. At times this has resulted in advances in gender equality policies based on consensus in cross-party alliances; other times developments have rather been stalled and, since the 80s, feminist movements have generally not been strong (Agustín et al., 2018). Recent literature does not investigate in-depth the evolving network of feminist actors, their collaborations and encounters, and the ways in which campaigns for policy initiatives such as equal pay and consent-based rape law express existing collaborations and develop the ties between actors even further.

Based on the available literature, we can divide the 2010-2022 period into two – before and after the beginning of the 2017 #MeToo movement. Especially the second wave of the #MeToo movement from

¹ According to Borchorst & Dahlerup (2020), the Danish gender equality model is characterized by women’s economic independence through labor market integration (supported by strong welfare policies and daycare institutions), weak formal institutions and policies, and the conviction that gender equality has been achieved or will eventually be reached without significant state intervention.

2020 onwards was influential in the Danish context. Feminist campaigns against particularly gender-based violence have been more successful after 2017, like for instance the 2019 revision of the equal treatment legislation which introduced higher compensation levels in cases of sexual harassment and emphasized that the tone at the workplace is not to be considered an extenuating circumstance. Similarly, a consent-based rape law was put into force in 2021 after several years of campaigning by a large coalition of NGOs and parties. Like in other national and international contexts, the #MeToo movement has revitalized the debate on gender equality in Denmark. On the 8th of March 2018, the Danish newspaper *Kristeligt Dagblad* wrote that “The Women’s Day will not be the same as it used to be.” This headline was in striking contrast to another newspaper, *Politiken*, which, on the same date in 2013, asked “Is there still a Women’s Day?” (Ibid., p. 9). It is perhaps unsurprising that the existing literature focuses on #MeToo and its crucial role in the development of the feminist movement in Denmark in recent years.

Thus, the role of #MeToo for both feminism and antifeminism in Denmark cannot be overestimated. Since 2017, ‘feminism’ has become a more politicized and contentious term than perhaps ever before. Especially young Danish women have increasingly resorted to it to proclaim their critical stance, while others actively express their critique of how feminism has now ‘gone too far’. Even though ‘feminism’ and ‘feminist’ are labels of self-description that are not so commonly employed in Danish politics, two female prime ministers, Helle Thorning-Schmidt (2011-2015) and Mette Frederiksen (2019-), have both publicly declared themselves feminists during their periods in office. Feminism is also a contested issue across the left/right-wing divide. Even though feminism and gender equality both before and after #MeToo have primarily been advocated by left-wing political actors, right-wing feminism in Denmark is on the rise. In 2018, the newspaper *Berlingske* posed the controversial question “Where is right-wing feminism?” (Borchorst & Christensen 2022, p. 582). Right-wing actors have responded to this in different ways, such as with the campaign #EnBlandtOs (“#OneAmongUs”) against sexism in politics (2021), an initiative by both left-wing and right-wing politicians. One of the co-initiators, Camilla Søre, who actively promoted this campaign from the beginning, is a member of the Liberal Party.

Regarding the thematic areas, the available literature mainly focuses on gender-based violence as a mobilizing topic for the feminist movement. Other topics such as the role of migration, minority women, and nationhood/belonging also play an important role. Minority women organizations struggle with challenges related to lack of resources and with a political and public discourse that often targets them as passive and oppressed. It is at times white ethnic Danes instead who advocate for ethnic minority women’s presumed interests on their behalf and for their inclusion in the feminist movement and in society in general (Liinason & Meijer, 2018, p. 743-44). Such an asymmetry between a marginalized group of women and the broader feminist movement is even more extreme in the case of female sex-workers who became a topic of concern during the debate on prostitution in 2009-10. Only few female sex-workers engaged in the public debate and they did so anonymously due to stigmatization; their criticism against the feminist organizations for speaking on their behalf and for wishing to criminalize their work through a ban on prostitution was plain-spoken (Bjønness, 2012, p. 198).

Labor market, health and reproductive rights, as well as LGBTQ+ rights as thematic areas remain largely unexplored in the literature addressing the feminist movement in the years 2010-2022. However, some literature and research projects do explore the history of the LGBTQ+ movement in Denmark as well as current fat activism, to mention a few examples (see e.g., Christiansen, 2021; Petersen, 2011; Stormhøj, 2019). Despite public debate regarding issues of gender identity and legal rights, this subject has also not been addressed significantly in research. In addition, the available literature does not cover the role, both within the feminist movement and more broadly in Danish society, of some of the largest NGOs and civil society actors, such as The Danish Women’s Society (Dansk Kvindesamfund), KVINFO, and Everyday Sexism Project Denmark. An exception to this gap in the literature is Liinason & Meijer’s (2018) work on The Women’s Council (Kvinderådet), which is another of the most prominent women’s organizations in Denmark. Overall, research on the feminist movement in Denmark (2010-2022) is, in any case, scarce.

1.2 The history of the feminist movements and its context

Women's organizations and the feminist movement in Denmark have a long history, and there have typically been close ties between the state and the civil society regarding the area of gender equality (Borchorst & Dahlerup, 2020). Danish women were granted the right to vote at national elections in 1915 after decades of mobilization and political debate. In the decades before World War II, broad political alliances between women's organizations and political parties predominated, and Danish Women's Society (Dansk Kvindesamfund) mobilized women on issues such as marriage law. In the 1970s, the Danish feminist movement was at its height after the student rebellion of 1968 and a famous action on April 8th, 1970, where a group of women marched on the streets of Copenhagen to protest against the view on women portrayed by the fashion industry. Most noticeable, the so-called 'Redstocking Movement' arose in the 1970s with socialist and utopian ideas of building a better future, and separatist tendencies with projects of female-only communities. In a comparative perspective, Denmark has been characterized as more 'movement-oriented', and less institutionalized, in its equality policy approach as compared to the other Nordic countries (Borchorst, Christensen & Raum, 1999). Borchorst and Dahlerup refer to the Danish development as "conflicts without politicization" (2020, p. 29): On the one hand, we find historical periods in which gender equality has been heavily debated in relation to issues such as representation, abortion, and harassment; on the other hand, the period from the mid-90s until the emergence of the #MeToo movement has been characterized by stagnation, and in the decades before that political responses to gender equality were typically adopted by consensus with majority votes on reforms across the major political parties in parliament. Collaboration within the Danish Parliament has been strengthened through initiatives such as the Cross-Party Network for Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights, which has existed for almost 20 years (Harder, 2017). However, a 2014/15 survey shows that 1/3 of the Danish parliamentarians considered that gender equality had already been achieved or had gone too far, whereas 2/3 believed that problems of gender inequality persisted in Danish society (Dahlerup, 2020). This reflects an increased level of contestation around these issues.

Denmark had its first female prime minister, the Social Democrat Helle Thorning-Schmidt, from 2011 to 2015. A center-right government came into power from 2015 to 2019 while a minority government led by a new female prime minister, the Social Democrat Mette Frederiksen, took office from 2019 to 2022. Frederiksen regained power in 2022 and formed a majority government with a broad coalition including the Liberal Party and the newly formed center party, The Moderates. Even though the available literature does not cover the historical development of Danish feminism and its influence on politics in detail through this period, references in the literature to the development still point to several disappointments amongst feminist actors with the center-left governments. In its Government Platform document from 2011, the Thorning-Schmidt government proposed an earmarking of parental leave for fathers, as well as the introduction of gender quota on company boards. These policy initiatives were later abandoned by the government and ended up being introduced years later via EU policies instead. Other policy initiatives were, however, introduced, based on previous civil society campaigning, such as the consent-based rape law that came into effect on January 1st, 2021, as well as a national action plan against partner violence, which (as the main gender equality issue) was introduced into the Government Platform document of the incumbent government in December 2022. As regards the center-right government (2015-2019), progress was made in the aftermath of the #MeToo movement as a result of the increased focus on sexual harassment. This implied changes to the legislation on sexual harassment in the workplace.

Established feminist actors in civil society such as the Danish Women's Society (Dansk Kvindesamfund) have provided a dynamic platform for activism, networking, and political lobbying throughout the years. However, during the center-right government (2015-2019), public funding for feminist NGOs and particularly the national knowledge center for gender equality (KVINFO), that provides institutional support to the feminist movement, was curtailed. In the beginning of 2017, the Minister of Culture Mette Bock decided that KVINFO should not run a research library any longer, which meant that the center lost approximately one tenth of their funding. Former director of KVINFO from 1990 to 2014, Elisabeth Møller Jensen, called this the start of a "butchering of KVINFO" and it was perceived

by many as an ominous sign for the future. However, KVINFO and similar organizations did not lose more of their funding.

The rise of #MeToo triggered increased feminist activism on social media. For instance, the Everyday Sexism Project Denmark, which was established in 2013, is primarily active through their Facebook page, and generally speaking Facebook groups, Instagram, and Twitter accounts with feminist content have proliferated in recent years. This also means that an increasing part of the feminist movement is not (only) active through membership within established NGOs, but engages in public debate through less organized and committed ways. In connection to this, more and more public debaters, from influencers on social media to researchers, politicians, and TV personalities, have promoted a feminist agenda without it being tied to an affiliation with NGOs or other institutions. This is most clearly illustrated by the increase in publications with feminist messages such as “Free Braiding” (orig. Frit flet; Aidt, Moestrup & Knutzon, 2014), “The Slut Manifesto” (orig. Ludermanifestet; Kjølser, Klæstrup & Krarup, 2017), “Good jugs” (orig. Gode kasser; Hansen & Mieritz, 2019) as well as “The blonde’s reflections: About gender, feminism and #metoo” (orig. Blondinens betragtninger: Om køn, feminisme og #metoo; Thorning-Schmidt, 2021).

However, new challenges have also emerged for the feminist movement. The larger feminist NGOs rely on public funding, making them vulnerable to political changes. New types of mobilization on social media also challenge the more traditional feminist organizations while providing, at the same time, new opportunities for cooperation and engagement by, for instance, making it easy for dozens of different associations and groups to co-organize larger events. In this sense, the internet has both disrupted and strengthened the work of the established feminist NGOs in Denmark. Finally, a major challenge to feminist organization is the increasingly active antifeminist movement ranging from Danish users on the manosphere to new organizations such as The Men’s Council (Manderådet) and far-right politicians with easy access to mainstream media. This is particularly the case when it comes to debates addressing the #MeToo movement where part of the Danish public opinion is skeptical and often centers on accusations of witch hunts and cancel culture, arguing that feminists have gone too far in their critique and struggle against gender-based violence and sexual harassment (Askanius & Hartley, 2019).

1.3 Actors, organizations, and organizational models

Amongst the different feminist actors in Denmark, the most well-organized and established are the women’s organizations. There is a lack of literature on the internal dynamics and democratic models of these organizations, but the organizational structures are typically quite conventional (i.e., umbrella organizations with collective memberships). The member organizations have delegates with voting rights at the annual general assembly which elects the board². The Danish Women’s Society (Dansk Kvindesamfund) was established as early as 1871 and it is broadly known and recognized in the Danish population, even though their membership has dropped from 15,000, when it was at its height in the late-1940s, to around 500 in 2013 (Den Store Danske 2020)³. Scholar Bente Rosenbeck (former professor at University of Copenhagen) and Christian Groes (Associate professor at Roskilde University) argue in an interview with the newspaper Kristeligt Dagblad (2021) that the organization has found new relevance today through social media and in public debates, particularly after the #MeToo mobilizations (Mikkelsen, 2021). Other well-established and influential women’s organizations are The Women’s Council (Kvinderådet, est. 1899), an umbrella organization representing Danish women

² An exception is the Women’s House in Copenhagen which was squatted by the feminist movement in 1978. It still serves as a collective, women-only space for different feminist and lesbian movements and initiatives with a consensus-based democratic structure (decisions are made at monthly meetings open to users of the House).

³ The Danish Women’s Society has not published their membership figures in recent years.

internationally and member of European Women's Lobby (EWL), as well as the National Organisation of Women's Shelters in Denmark (Landsorganisation af Kvindekrisecentre, est. 1987), which represents 52 crisis centers for women and children. The Women's Council represents 48 organizations ranging from political parties and trade unions to interest groups and minority women's organizations who all work for gender equality and women's full participation in society. The available literature has examined the role of women's organizations, such as The Women's Council, in newer developments of the Danish feminist movement (Liinason & Meijer, 2018; Rognlien & Kier-Byfield, 2020). One of the main findings is that Danish women's organizations still play a crucial role in the feminist movement by mobilizing and empowering women through their activities. However, at the same time there are persistent tensions between those, who have more resources as well as a Danish ethnic background, and those, who are often both less resourceful and marginalized in society due to other reasons than gender. In this sense, intersectionality between gender, class, race, and nationality has primarily been a dividing factor in these organizations⁴.

There is a broad range of minority women's organizations in Denmark that are either based on country of origin, such as the Afghan Women's Association (Afhansk Kvindeforening), or focus on a specific problem for minority women, such as Sisters against Violence and Control. The research so far points to an overall strategy and recurring theme for minority women's organizations, aiming to appear active and resourceful rather than passive and oppressed, and encourage other minority women to do the same (Stormhøj, 2021). In their article, *Everyday Activism and Resistance by Minority Women in Denmark* (2020), Louise Rognlien and Sophia Kier-Byfield analyze how particularly Muslim minority women resist specific descriptions of their group by, for instance, criticizing the masking ban that was put into force by the center-right government in 2018. Some organizations, like Women in Dialogue, also argue that wearing a head scarf, or a niqab, is both a free choice of self-expression and compatible with being Danish.

Other smaller, younger, and less known organizations and movements aim to challenge traditional gender norms and gender inequality in society by means of different strategies. This is, for instance, the case of The Norm Stormers (Normstormerne), which takes a norm-critical perspective on gender, focusing mainly on education and teaching activities regarding gender, discrimination and privileges; Kapow Collective, a queer feminist DJ initiative focusing on music by women, non-binary, and gender minorities while also being a voice of strong feminist anti-capitalist and anti-fascist critique; DareGender, which seeks to engage boys and men in the debate on gender equality and focuses on masculinity, mental health, and violence prevention; Digital Responsibility (Digitalt Ansvar), targeting digital harassment and violence; and The Music Movement of 2019 (Musikbevægelsen af 2019) which seeks to create a community and mutual support among minoritized and discriminated groups (women, transpersons, non-binary persons, among others) in the music industry. Whereas these forms of mobilization are typically not covered in the existing literature, the latter example is currently being analyzed in the research project *Gendering Music Matter* (GEMMA, 2022-2024), led by Kristine Ringsager from University of Copenhagen.

A lot of public debaters and influencers are more loosely affiliated with the feminist movement in Denmark by, for instance, publishing books with feminist messages and making public statements that promote gender equality. Online activism in different forms has also been significant in introducing new issues on the agenda of the feminist movement as well as politically. Most noticeable, TV host Sofie Linde is broadly recognized as the one who sparked the so-called 'second wave' of the #MeToo protests in Denmark by giving a speech, in August 2020, about the equal pay gap and sexual

⁴ Other initiatives include businesswomen's networks that promote women in management and on company boards, and also have a focus on women in entrepreneurship and investment. However, they typically have a professional, sector-based perspective rather than an explicit political role.

harassment based on her own experiences. She has since been active in the public debate on these issues, including by talking about the repercussions that she experienced in the aftermath of her influential speech. Other examples include feminist activist Emma Holten, who in 2014 put critical focus on revenge porn and contributed to initiating the debate on consent in Denmark by taking back power after having experienced revenge porn by publishing naked photos of herself as part of the project CONSENT; as well as collective groups such as The Lumber Room Activists (Pulterkammerets Aktivister), active from 2016 to 2020, which was initiated by two brothers who were among the first to mobilize against the sharing of intimate pictures online without consent by contacting the parents of the youngsters doing this, with the aim of engaging them in dialogue with their children. There is a gap in the literature regarding the role of these types of activists and their demands and mobilization.

With regard to both women's organizations as well as other feminist actors, there are particularly three questions that have not been explored in the literature so far: 1) What role does social media play for these actors?; 2) What is the exact influence of public debaters, who are not affiliated with feminist NGOs, within the feminist movement?; and 3) What are the networks between the different organizations in the Danish feminist movement? In this sense, we lack a more detailed mapping of the Danish feminist movement in the 2010-2022 period.

1.4 Allies

We distinguish between three main types of allies to feminist actors in the Danish context: 1) Political parties and politicians who do not actively participate in feminist campaigns, for instance, but still express public support for feminist actors and listen to their input regarding new policy proposals; 2) public or private organizations (including trade unions), who provide support for feminist actors in civil society and organize common campaigns and events; and 3) other NGOs and movements (e.g., anti-racist and environmentalist actors) who might not focus on gender equality themselves but still share values with the feminist movement. In these cases, activist support, campaigning, and networking can be occasional or more stable over time. The available literature partly covers the first two types of allies, whereas there is a lack of literature regarding the third kind.

As regards the first type of ally, political parties of the left-wing, such as the Red-Green Alliance (Enhedslisten), Green Left (Socialistisk Folkeparti), the Danish Social Liberal Party (Radikale Venstre), The Alternative (Alternativet), and Independent Greens (Frie Grønne), often support feminist campaigns that call for new policy initiatives and proposals. Some of these are implemented on the parties' own political agenda. In this sense, the links between the feminist movement and the left-wing parties are much closer than with the right-wing parties. The Red-Green Alliance, The Alternative, and Independent Greens define themselves as feminist political parties. A survey conducted in 2015 (cf. Dahlerup et al. 2021, p. 1203) amongst Danish MPs shows that 16 pct. of the respondents self-identify as feminists, which is highly correlated with party affiliation in the sense that most self-identified feminists are members of a party on the Left. This resonates with the differences in gender equality norms and practices within the political parties, where the center-left is usually more committed to gender equality in party culture and targeted measures, whereas the right-wing parties are more reluctant or even resistant towards addressing, for instance, candidate recruitment through gender equality initiatives (Agustín, Fiig & Siim, 2022).

A comparative study on attitudes towards gender equality in the Swedish and Danish Parliaments (Dahlerup et al. 2021, p. 1204) shows that not all MPs, and particularly not male MPs, find it important to "promote women's interests/opinions" in parliament, even though they self-identify as feminists. Feminist male politicians in Denmark and Sweden may refrain from claims of 'acting for women' because they believe that such an approach deprives women of agency. In this sense, they probably vote for feminist policy proposals but delegate to other (female) politicians and the feminist movement when it comes to actively promoting women's interests through politics. These MPs are presumably more willing to become directly involved if a feminist campaign or specific agenda includes the advancement of all genders and not only women, like shared parental leave, for instance (Ibid.). Yet, the relationship between political support for the feminist agenda and the feminist movement still

needs to be further researched, particularly in relation to developments of the past decade (2010-2022).

Scholar Christel Stormhøj's article "'Danishness', Repressive Immigration Policies and Exclusionary Framings of Gender Equality" (2021) provides a critical analysis of the second type of ally by exploring how women's organizations influence different governmental programs, especially those targeting Muslim minority women and/or women with a migrant background. Women's organizations risk contributing to a "nationalized and racialized politics of gender equality", which defines targeted groups of women as "deficits in need of reform" (Stormhøj, 2021, p. 90). This refers to the strict immigration policy and to the ethno-nationalist discourse that has become part of the political agenda in Denmark, particularly in the 2000s. Interviews with two representatives of minority women's organizations, respectively Intercultural Women's Council (Interkulturelt Kvinderåd) and The World's Women in Denmark (Verdens Kvinder I Danmark) highlight the criticism: The representatives explicitly resist and criticize political narratives about migrant women, even while they also support, at least partly, Danish policies and the nationalist demand that one ought to follow Danish traditions. It has not been explored in the literature how other feminist actors than minority women's organizations reflect upon or negotiate their relations to institutional actors, whether public or private.

Within the second type of ally, women's/feminist groups within the trade unions have played an important role as well in terms of influencing the development of labor market-related gender equality issues, such as unequal pay (Sørensen, 2016) and sexual harassment (Borchorst & Agustín, 2017). In this sense, trade unions are an important ally for the feminist movement. In cases of sexual harassment in particular, the issue has "been kept in the media spotlight and on the political agenda by groups within the labor movement which have collaborated across unions, among other things in a task force on sexual harassment that the trade union 3F took the initiative to create in 2016" (Borchorst & Agustín, 2020, p. 72). Think-tanks with a focus on gender equality, such as Tora (est. 2020) and EQUALIS (est. 2022), have also emerged in recent years but these are not part of the existing literature. Finally, the Danish Institute of Human Rights is the national equal treatment body and as such it monitors the development of gender equality in Denmark; in this role, the institute is active in producing studies regarding gender equality issues, providing recommendations, and participating in political hearings.

Regarding the third type of ally, activist groups and campaign-oriented organizations such as Everyday Sexism Project Denmark, Amnesty International Denmark, Sex & Society (Sex & Samfund), Oxfam IBIS, as well as LGBT+ Denmark have been increasingly active in promoting a feminist agenda through their activities. Many of these organizations do not focus exclusively on gender equality in their work but they do perceive gender equality as an important topic within a broader agenda such as securing human rights or advancing the recognition of different gender and sexual identities. Volunteers in activist campaigns, which are often coordinated between different organizations, are not necessarily members of an NGO or otherwise active in the feminist movement. Particularly large organizations, such as Amnesty International Danmark and others, most often contribute with employees who coordinate, facilitate, and mobilize volunteers for the different campaigns.

1.5 Themes and agendas

1.5.1 Labor market

Gender quotas have always been controversial in Denmark, and earmarked paternity leave has often been framed as a 'daddy quota', linking it to the discursive articulation of excessive state intervention versus individuals' and families' free choice (Agustín, Siim & Borchorst, 2018). Feminist civil society actors such as The Danish Women's Society and The Women's Council do favor gender quotas in the economic sphere as a legitimate way to promote gender equality (Ibid., p. 417). However, they have not run major campaigns nor have they been very visible in Danish public debates on labor market issues (such as earmarked paternity leave or gender quotas in boards) compared to other issues, such as sexual harassment and gender-based violence. Earmarked paternity leave for 11 weeks was introduced in 2022 through an EU directive; this was an extension from the previous two weeks assigned to the father exclusively. The feminist movement did not mobilize strongly to support this

legislative measure; however, some trade unions had already introduced earmarked leave for fathers (beyond the previous two weeks) in their agreements before the legal changes were adopted (Andersen & Borchorst, 2020).

Another prominent gender equality theme that trade unions have mobilized around in the years 2010-2022 is equal pay. The Danish Nurses' Organization (Dansk Sygeplejeråd) has effectively put this on the public agenda, particularly during the large nurses' strike in June-August 2021. In this regard, the primary issue at stake is the pay gap between male-dominated and female-dominated professions with particularly nurses, pedagogues, and teachers claiming to be unjustly paid due to a historical placement of professions in the public sector within a specific pay hierarchy already established in 1969 (DIHR, 2020). Similarly, the trade union HK chose an activist legal strategy, in the 80s, to carry the issue of equal pay into the EU system, through the Court of Justice of the EU; this ultimately resulted in the introduction of shared burden of proof in the EU legal framework on equal pay (Borchorst & Agustín, 2020).

Mobilization around sex workers' rights and public debate on the criminalization of customers for the purchase of sexual services have also been addressed in the literature. In the article "Between Emotional Politics and Biased Practices – Prostitution Policies, Social Work, and Women Selling Sexual Services in Denmark" (2012), Jeanette Bjonness analyzes the role of NGOs in the public debates on this issue that was mostly discussed from 2009 to 2011. Actors such as The Nest (Reden), which runs shelters for drug-addicted women in prostitution, and The Initiative of the 8th of March, a union of 27 organizations and movements, advocated for criminalization. Especially The Nest applied a harsh and direct rhetoric by, for instance, arguing that men "buy women's bodies" and "masturbate in their orifices" (Bjonness 2012, p. 194), which also relates the issue to gender-based violence as a thematic area. The Danish Sex Worker Organization (Sexarbejdernes Interesseorganisation, est. 2008) was of a different opinion and demanded legal rights for sex workers instead. After a 2012 statement by the advisory organ to the government, the Council of Criminal Law, warning against criminalization, the center-left government decided not to introduce any criminalization of prostitution, even though all three governing parties had expressed support for this previously.

1.5.2 Health & reproductive rights

Health & reproductive rights is poorly covered in the available literature. The right to free abortion until week 12 in pregnancy is widely supported by the majority of the political parties as well as the Danish population. However, there has been increasing attention amongst feminist actors from late-2022 on whether this limit on week 12 should be raised, which is presumably connected to the fact that in 2023 it is exactly 50 years since Denmark introduced free abortion in 1973. For instance, the NGO Sex & Society recently proposed an extension of the period until week 18. But when a broad coalition of feminist organizations organized a demonstration in August 2022 in support of American women who risk losing the right to abortion, this was more an act of international solidarity rather than any expression of worry about whether Denmark might remove any rights to abortion. In this sense, the feminist movement in Denmark does not express concern about losing basic reproductive rights, unlike other countries such as Poland, for instance. However, there is occasional criticism by organizations such as The Danish Women's Society regarding the fact that the Faroe Islands, an autonomous country that is part of the Kingdom of Denmark, still prohibits abortion.

Menstrual health policies have also only been marginally addressed on the political agenda in Denmark, and research is limited in the area. In 2020, Sikandar Siddique from the party Independent Greens (Frie Grønne) proposed a 'ten days menstruation leave per year' policy. In March 2021 the same party made a proposal for a parliamentary resolution on access to free menstruation products, which was not supported by the majority. A citizen proposal to the Danish parliament (March 2022) on access to free or cheap period products in public spaces was launched, but did not receive sufficient support.

The body positivity and fat activism mobilizations have been subjects on the rise in recent years, particularly on Instagram and other social media platforms. In 2020, the research project Feminist

Activism in Transition (FAT), led by Lene Bull Christiansen from Roskilde University, started exploring these forms of online activism and what is sometimes referred to as the 'fatosphere'. According to Bull Christiansen, fat activism became known to a wider public in Denmark when the journalist Ida Rud in 2017 talked about her own fat activist Instagram account in a documentary series called "Fat Ida" (Tykke Ida). Fat activism in Denmark is mainly promoted by individual influencers even though it is also partly organized through activist groups such as Fat Front (Fed Front), which was founded in 2017. Fat Front is supported by established actors such as The Danish Women's Society, and made visible in the public sphere through television documentaries from the public Danish Broadcasting Corporation, DR. The FAT project itself publishes the podcast, "The Fat Feminists" (De Fede Feminister) which focuses broadly on fatphobia, feminism, body positivity, and fat activism. Christiansen distinguishes between different types of profiles in the 'fatosphere' where some activists focus on everyday life and motherhood while others are more politically oriented (Christiansen 2021, p. 26-27). However, they all share an aspiration to change societal norms for what counts as beautiful and healthy. Maj Hedegaard Heiselberg (2022) argues that fat activists find a community online via Instagram, which provides support and a space for sharing experiences while also posing challenges to the activists due to the mental exhaustion and stress that may arise of repeatedly using one's own experiences and images in this kind of online activism.

1.5.3 Migration

In the article "Challenging constructions of nationhood and nostalgia: exploring the role of gender, race and age in struggles for women's rights in Scandinavia" (2018), Mia Liinason and Clara Marlijn Meijer analyze the role that The Women's Council as an umbrella organization plays by facilitating cooperation between minority women's organizations and other parts of the feminist movement that often have more resources. The Women's Council participated in the large 2014 Nordic Forum conference, which brought together feminist organizations from all over Scandinavia to discuss gender equality and women's rights. Liinason and Meijer (2018) show how and why this conference was so massively criticized for having a low presence of minority women in both their steering committee and different panels. Through a survey and qualitative interviews with members, the authors also highlight how this relates to difficulties within The Women's Council (as well as other women's organizations in Scandinavia) regarding the role of minority women within their organizations. Due to language problems, lack of active members, and less funding for their activities, the minority women's organizations do not have much influence within The Women's Council. The response to this is primarily a discourse of inclusion to promote and strengthen minority women's rights organizations. But as Liinason and Meijer point out, this discourse can also contribute to deepen internal divisions by fostering the idea that the feminist movement in Denmark remains split between the majority (ethnic Danes) and the 'others' (2018, p. 744).

Minority women as individual debaters and members of organizations play an important role in the debate about feminism and antifeminism in Denmark. They typically focus upon issues such as gender-based violence and social control within families with minority background, often in cooperation with authorities. There is, however, little research on how women with migrant background navigate through the murky waters of Danish public debate and how they have organized in different minority women's organization from 2010 till today (an exception is Stormhøj, 2020, as mentioned above).

1.5.4 LGBTQ+ rights

In general, there is little research on the Danish LGBTQ+ movement, its policy influence, and the networks between LGBTQ+ organizations and feminist actors⁵. As regards the latter, the feminist movements can be considered allies of the LGBTQ+ movements, just as the LGBTQ+ movements also tend to support feminist actors in Denmark, but the issue of LGBTQ+ rights has not been high on the agenda of the feminist movements. Specific initiatives or fora such as Lesbian Feminists (Lesbiske Feminister), which is a smaller network with links to the feminist activism of the 70s, are not very visible and have not been studied in the literature. A significant conflict between Lesbian Feminists and a younger generation of queer feminists was, nevertheless, reported by the media in October-November 2019: Lesbian Feminists was excluded from the Women's House in Copenhagen due to what was considered a transphobic defense of lesbians' right to reject trans women as an object of desire (in the same way in which they would reject men).

Research on LGBTQ+ rights shows that LGBTQ+ persons in Denmark still face considerable challenges in terms of equality and justice (Stormhøj, 2019). This is particularly the case in educational settings where LGBTQ+ organizations have engaged in public-private partnerships to combat discrimination and bullying. However, heterosexist bullying and social exclusion on grounds of non-conforming gender behavior and norms remain largely unaddressed by Danish school authorities. In this regard, Stormhøj suggests that LGBTQ+ activists engage more strategically with reformist politics and hold authorities more accountable for "the security, well-being, and rights of lesbians and gays", especially with respect to children and teenagers (Ibid., p. 1318).

The public debate around 'identity politics' and 'wokeness' is often targeted against LGBTQ+ rights and social justice activists such as when the small NGO The Norm Stormers ("Normstormerne"), which provides courses for school children about gender identities, sexual orientation, and anti-discrimination, was criticized for withholding information from the public about their course material. In their essay *Questioning Normal: Overcoming implicit resistance to norm critical education* published in the journal *Woman, Gender & Research*, the two activists Liv Moeslund Ahlgren & Ehm Hjorth Miltersen provide relevant reflections on what barriers and "implicit resistance" they are met with from pupils and schoolteachers to their norm critical courses (Ahlgren & Miltersen, 2021). There is no research yet on the impact of the norm critical education that, for instance, The Norm Stormers offers to Danish schools, nor on the resistance that these initiatives are met with. However, this type of feminist activism, that focuses on education and upbringing, does face significant challenges if the repeated critique in the public debate of recent years is also indicative of a wider skepticism in Danish society.

In contrast, existing literature has focused more on the widespread acceptance of LGBTQ+ minorities in Danish society amongst political and institutional actors, even though this is often coupled with homonationalism (Puar, 2007), i.e., linking homosexuality with national norms or, in this case, linking liberal open-mindedness with being Danish (Hansen, 2021). Generally, politicians and other influential actors in the Danish public visibly support LGBTQ+ rights. There is a lack of research, however, on the response of LGBTQ+ organizations to the ongoing 'public embrace' as well as the organizations' various possibilities and strategies of political critique in the 2010-2022 period. One of the arguments regarding the emergence of countermovements is that social movements must demonstrate some sign of success for a countermovement, such as antifeminist mobilization, to arise (Corredor, 2019). Without this there is, at least, not as much to protest for the countermovement. The predominant support for LGBTQ+ rights in the public sphere and the progress in terms of rights and policies can be

⁵ As a notable exception, the research project *The Cultural History of AIDS* (PI Michael Nebeling Petersen, 2021-2024, University of Copenhagen) investigates AIDS activism and politics in the period from 1981 to 2021; results from the research project will be published in the coming years.

considered evidence of, to some degree, a successful LGBTQ+ mobilization in the Danish context. However, the exact influence of LGBTQ+ organizations, their potential alliances with feminist actors, as well as the reactions by countermovements is largely unexplored in the 2010-2022 period.

1.5.5 Gender-based violence

Most of the existing literature within the field addresses the #MeToo movement and its media coverage. In Denmark, reactions to the #MeToo movement were in large part sector-based, with trade union driven initiatives rather than legislative initiatives or broader organized calls for actions. An opinion poll carried out by Megafon for Politiken (2021) shows that 55 pct. thinks that #MeToo plays too large or way too large a role in public debate in Denmark; this is particularly the case among voters of the Social Democrats (59 pct.), the Liberal Party (62 pct.), the Conservative People's Party (65 pct.), and other right-wing parties (80 pct. of the voters of the Liberal Alliance, Danish People's Party, and the Christian Democrats). Gender and age also play a role: 65 pct. of the men and 45 pct. of the women think that the focus is too strong or way too strong, and the same goes for 60 pct. of the 40+ years age group. The media coverage of #MeToo on social media is found to be skewed in a study of the Facebook pages of nine mayor news outlets (Reestorff 2021). Negative updates more than double the positive ones, and hateful comments by users are legitimized by the media. In addition, the coverage is characterized by a predominance of opinions and rumors: "emphasis on gossip and opinion journalism is problematic because it rarely concerns the fundamental challenges raised by #MeToo" (Ibid., p. 127).

In the first wave of the #MeToo movement, a majority of Danes thought that the movement was a joke (Askanius & Hartley, 2019). However, according to the Megafon opinion poll (Politiken 2021), which was carried out during the second wave, 65 pct. agreed or fully agreed that the debate regarding the issues emphasized by the #MeToo movement is important because it contributes to create "a better balance and increased understanding between the genders." Half of the respondents thought, however, that consensus on the positive role of the movement had resulted in a lack of nuances in the debate. There are many indications in the available literature that #MeToo has profoundly changed societal norms in Danish society and particularly in mainstream public debate. Sexism and harassment have been placed firmly on the political and public agenda, and in most workplaces the discussion around these topics, and how to address them, cannot be avoided. In contrast, this can be compared with the public reception and debate about the 2014 report by the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, which ranked Denmark as the EU country with the highest occurrence of sexual assaults against women. This report was at the time widely dismissed as unreliable in mainstream media, which did not happen for similar reports and investigations of sexual assaults published after 2017 (Leine et al., 2020).

There is still a lack of research on, for instance, the Danish feminist campaigns for a consent-based rape law or the public debate about femicide and sexual assault on the streets, sparked by the international news of the murder in London of Sarah Everard in March 2021 and reignited by the murder in Denmark of Maria Skadhauge Stevn in February 2022. Research on femicide (e.g., Vaaben & Thomsen, 2022), rape (e.g., Heinskou, 2010), and trafficking (e.g., Plambech, Chemlali & Cerio, 2022), for instance, exists but the literature typically does not address activist mobilization. Similarly, the relation between the feminist movement and political actors regarding, for instance, the consent-based rape law, in force since 2021, has not been explored in the literature. With regards to stalking and online harassment as both policy issues and subjects of debate, current research confirms the pattern of state/civil society cooperation and overall consensus among the main political parties. In the case of stalking, the Danish Anti-Stalking Association (Dansk Anti-Stalking Forening) influenced the content of the stalking policy development directly, whereas especially children and youth organizations, like Save the Children, as well as The Danish Women's Society have collaborated with the relevant ministries in efforts to combat online harassment (for instance, through publication of teaching materials and public awareness campaigns) (Agustín, Faber & Nielsen, 2019). As mentioned above, trade unions have also been active, and successful, in pushing for legal changes in the area of sexual harassment (Borchorst & Agustín, 2017).

1.6 Repertoire of action

The available literature emphasizes three primary strategies that constitute a varied repertoire of action for the Danish feminist movement from 2010 to 2022. These are as follows:

1) Campaigns and engagements in the public debate targeting the Danish population in general through mainstream media and visible demonstrations. This strategy can be confrontational, such as the campaigns in 2009-11 to criminalize the purchase of sexual services by the Initiative of 8th of March, or dialogue-oriented such as the face-to-face encounters with Danes that the minority women's organization, Women in Dialogue, practiced in 2018 while wearing their Islamic face covering (Rognlien & Kier-Byfield, 2020). There are few street mobilizations and/or visible protest campaigns; exceptions include the large mobilizations on equal pay organized by The Danish Nurses' Organization in 2021, as well as smaller demonstrations against rape or related to #MeToo and annual demonstrations on International Women's Day.

2) Increasingly widespread use of social media by both established organizations as well as more loosely organized activist groups and individuals. The main purpose is to reach a wider audience of particularly young people with the aim of changing their norms and values. This is especially the case for so-called fat activists on Facebook, Instagram, and TikTok but organizations such as The Danish Women's Society, Everyday Sexism Project Denmark, and LGBT+ Denmark have also become increasingly active on digital platforms. Another purpose is to organize and mobilize activists through these means. How social media is used for this exact purpose has not been studied so far in the Danish context. Additionally, in the beginning of the 2010s it was much more common to publish and read blogs than later in the period. At least some of the feminist discussions, ideas and themes were promoted on influential feminist blogs such as The Bitter Cunt Bethany (Bitterfissen Bethany) and Manfool (Mandfjols), even though most of these blogs are either no longer active or read by as many people today.

3) Collaboration with public institutions such as the continuous funding and close relations between KVINFO and the Ministry of Culture, or between the trade unions, civil society organizations, and the political parties. Such partnerships can also involve municipalities, universities, and educational institutions (Stormhøj, 2019). The relations are institutionalized and most often incorporated into the policy-making process, where civil society organizations are consulted and participate in formal hearings, whereby they also have ample possibilities of making their voices heard. The potential of this strategy is the possibility of changing institutions from within and promoting more structural solutions to issues such as bullying, which are otherwise often individualized and depoliticized. However, from a feminist perspective the risk is that participation in governmental programs or campaigns can publicly legitimate the state in ways that the feminist movement does not wish or that the rules established for the partnership discipline the feminist actors to become less critical (Stormhøj, 2020). These issues are underexplored in the literature.

1.7 Main frames of arguments

Based on the available literature, it is possible to identify four dominant frames articulated by the Danish feminist movement throughout the period in question. Other frames are articulated as well such as an intersectional framing, but it is not clear from the literature whether intersectionality has become a dominant frame among feminist actors to the same extent as the ones mentioned below. The four dominant frames mainly relate to gender-based violence and the labor market as thematic areas.

'Women need to support other women'

Women's organizations as well as debaters and influencers on social media often emphasize how women need to support each other in their struggle for gender equality. Even though other gender identities are sometimes also included, it is most often as allies who are not supposed to work on the same issues. For instance, The Danish Men's Society (est. 2020) is a feminist ally to The Danish Women's Society but it has its own focus on the types of gender inequalities that affect men. The need

for women to support other women is expressed in countless ways, ranging from minority women's campaigns, businesswomen's networks, and advocacy for transwomen to shared stories of sexual harassment amongst female politicians (cf. Harder, 2019).

'Gender equality norms need to change'

Particularly in relation to #MeToo, the feminist movement has increasingly raised the claim that the norms for what counts as sexual harassment and what we accept as 'normal' regarding gender-based violence in Danish society ought to change. This dominant frame is largely unexplored in the available literature that mainly focuses on the media coverage and critique of #MeToo. But it is a recurring point of view amongst feminist actors that is emphasized in different contexts, from everyday life portrayed and discussed on social media to large campaigns and policy changes. For instance, the feminist campaigns for a consent-based rape law were not simply about improving legislation, but also about changing norms for what counts as rape in Danish society through such policy amendment. This frame rests on a broader counter discourse regarding the lack of gender equality progress in the Danish context, which opposes the dominant perspective (in politics and in the public sphere) that gender equality has already been achieved.

'Women's bodies should be free'

Feminist activism throughout the period has proclaimed to liberate women's bodies from excessive attention, control, or violations. This is mostly covered in the literature regarding fat activism and body positivity, that is often about changing beauty and health ideals for women, as well as in research on the #MeToo movement and the right to dress and act freely in public spaces without being sexually harassed. Even though this is not addressed in the literature, fourth wave feminism has primarily been associated with a group of 'sex-positive' feminists such as Louise Kjølsen (widely known as "Twerk Queen" and part of the feminist group Girlsquad, 2017-2018), who claims that women should be free to make sexualized appearances and performances that grasp the attention of men in public.

'Women's role in society is not valued enough'

It is often emphasized amongst feminist actors that women contribute to society in several ways that are not acknowledged culturally, politically, or economically. In the available literature, this is highlighted and analyzed most clearly in the case of minority women's organizations who criticize a public discourse that portrays them as passive and oppressed instead of active participants in society who contribute every day. However, the predominant type of feminist campaigning employing the frame concerns the equal pay gap, which culminated with the nurses' strike and mobilization in June-August 2021. Simultaneously, public debaters such as Emma Holten have also reignited a discussion on so-called 'feminist economy' and the unacknowledged economic value of care work in contemporary Danish society.

1.8 Campaigns and debates

The 2010-22 feminist campaign activities in Denmark are not covered by the available literature. An exception is the campaign for a criminalization of the purchase of sexual services in 2009-11 as well as smaller campaigns launched by minority women's organizations in 2017-18 (Bjønness, 2012; Rognlien & Kier-Byfield, 2020). However, the literature does focus on internal debates within the feminist movement about transphobia, the inclusion of minority women, the role of nationalist discourses, and dilemmas of participating in governmental programs or receiving funding from the state. These debates also reflect the effects of the widespread opinion on gender and sexual exceptionalism, which celebrates Denmark as a country where gender equality is already achieved. In this connection, ethnic minorities are often framed as the ones who are left out in the national narrative of progress for gender equality since they allegedly do not follow such an exceptionalism. Feminist actors have often found it difficult to navigate this and criticize without unduly speaking on behalf of the ethnic minorities (Stormhøj, 2020, p. 90).

It seems almost puzzling how feminist actors have had success in Danish society with both external and internal challenges. Gender equality has been declared a 'closed case' by many politicians,

feminism is not part of official political lingo, and the media coverage about #MeToo has, at least in the beginning been very critical (Dahlerup 2018; Askanius & Hartley 2019; Reestorff 2021). It is nonetheless clear that several feminist campaigns throughout the period have achieved positive results, such as the coordinated campaign for a consent-based rape law and the campaign #sygtsystem (“#sicksystem”) led by Amnesty International Denmark in 2016 to remove being transgender from the list of mental illnesses. The Danish feminist movement has been strengthened through campaigns such as these as well as through the celebration of traditions and events, such as the annual International Women’s Day on 8th March. Most noticeable for the period, the centenary of women’s right to vote in Denmark was celebrated with a parade through Copenhagen of women in white dresses, led by The Danish Women’s Society, just as the historical parade in 1915.

Yet, it remains to be explored how both the various networks and the organizational capacity of feminist actors have developed through their different campaigns and activities as well as how they have, in fact, managed to influence public debates on gender equality. For instance, to which degree has the Danish feminist movement questioned and criticized the gender and sexual exceptionalism in public debates? Additionally, in what ways and to which degree has the #MeToo movement reinvigorated debates on gender equality and remobilized feminist actors in Danish society after 2017?

1.9 Key policy related outcomes

What is most noticeable before the emergence of #MeToo is the lack of policy changes that feminist campaigns have advocated for, such as the criminalization of the purchase of sexual services or earmarked paternity leave. The role of the #MeToo movement for the enactment of policy changes on not only sexual harassment (such as the 2019 revision of the equal treatment legislation, as mentioned in the introduction) but also other issues related to gender equality has not been extensively explored in the literature. However, it would be particularly interesting to study which role the #MeToo movement has had for the feminist campaigns and the governmental decision in 2020 to introduce a new consent-based rape law. At least indirectly, the #MeToo mobilizations have presumably played a significant role in the renewed focus on femicide and sexual assaults, which has led the incumbent government to propose a new action plan on partner violence and partner murder (June 2022).

However, at least one exception to the lack of policy changes in the part of the studied time period which is prior to the #MeToo movement is the successful campaign to remove being transgender from the list of mental illnesses (2016), which was agreed to by the center-right government and officially implemented in Danish legislation from 1st January 2017. Recently, another policy outcome also related to LGBTQ+ rights was achieved based on a citizens’ proposal to the Danish parliament, namely the legal recognition of co-fatherhood (June 2022). This implies that families with two fathers are now considered equal to families with a mother and a father and families with two mothers (co-motherhood has been recognized since 2013).

However, many activities, campaigns, and debates related to the Danish feminist movement are not primarily oriented towards promoting policy changes. Rather, the focus is primarily on changing societal norms and everyday life or in a more reactive manner to prevent proposed policy changes. For instance, a significant part of feminist body positivity activism on social media is not about politics at an institutional level, but about exposing problematic body ideals and promoting acceptance of different body types throughout society. Another example is the previously mentioned group of Muslim minority women, Women in Dialogue (Kvinder i Dialog), which was created to respond to a proposed ban on Islamic face covering in 2017-18 (Rognlien & Kier-Byfield, 2020, p. 9). The purpose was to prevent a possible policy change through public awareness campaigning even though their aim was also to engage in dialogue with ethnic Danes and educate the public about self-determination in decisions concerning religious clothing. Demonstrations were held in the major cities as acts of solidarity with the minority women, yet the law entered into force in 2018. The political support for the ban has not changed significantly afterwards.

1.10 Other important issues

Attacks on academic freedom from some of the right-wing political parties were quite significant during the period (2010-2022). This concerned not least a critique of gender studies and migration studies, and a resolution on excessive activism in certain research environments was passed in the Parliament in May 2021. Whereas there have been many reactions to this from the research community as well as the relevant trade unions in Denmark, mobilization has still been scarce and there is no research as regards this issue.

1.11 Conclusion

Denmark has a strong corporatist tradition and a powerful civil society. Particularly the Redstocking Movement, with its activism and critical stance towards the political system of the 1970s, has inspired feminists in later generations and proved how influential feminists can become when they organize. But perhaps the ambition to live up to this model has shaped and weakened the strength of later feminist mobilization. Media and scholars have often declared the feminist movement to be dead and gone – or, at least, considered irrelevant by those in public debate who argue that Denmark has already achieved gender equality. As Rikke Andreassen argues “Danish mass media has collectively declared the women’s movements dead from the mid-1980s” (Andreassen, 2004, p. 73). Even though feminist mobilization and established NGOs, such as The Danish Women’s Society, never disappeared or ceased to be active, a similar conclusion can be drawn for the first part of the period 2010-22 regarding what is deemed as the lack of success of the Danish feminist movement. The beginning of the period was characterized by political stagnation, and policy proposals, that were part of the center-left governmental program from 2011, were abandoned. The feminist movement was not influential and, based on the available literature, it does not seem as if the feminist movement managed to set the agenda on gender equality issues in the public debate.

However, all of this changed with the emergence of the #MeToo movement in 2017 and perhaps a new, slowly nascent wave of feminist mobilization was sparked by the celebrations of the centenary for Danish women’s right to vote in 2015. Even though the available literature does not study in-depth the impact and role of #MeToo for the Danish feminist movement, it does seem to be clear that #MeToo is the most important event for the development of Danish feminism in the 2000s. As previously mentioned, #MeToo divides the period 2010-22 into two with campaigns, debates, and policy changes after #MeToo that were quite difficult to imagine in a Danish context before #MeToo.

International #MeToo mobilizations have led many, particularly young women, to start identifying as feminists. The success of the #MeToo movement has not happened uncontentionally since it also turned ‘feminism’ into an even more dividing term than before (Borchorst & Christensen, 2022, p. 592). But it has not been a topic of research yet how the development in the use of the terms ‘feminist’ and ‘feminism’ and the on-going debates about #MeToo have affected the public perception and societal influence of the Danish feminist movement. Neither has it been studied in-depth how the networks within the feminist movement have developed, which kind of actors have emerged and been most influential, nor what the relation between the feminist movement and political-institutional actors has been during the period in question.

1.12 List of feminist movements’ campaigns

The main feminist campaigns in Denmark in recent years have involved close collaboration between various feminist organizations, particularly in Copenhagen. The five selected campaigns have been chosen using the following selection criteria: 1) To cover the five main thematic areas of the FIERCE project, if possible; 2) to cover sizeable mobilization, broad alliances, and use of resources as well as smaller campaigns; and 3) to cover campaigns with considerable success in terms of political influence and outcome as well as not so successful campaigns.

Additionally, we have selected campaigns that are mainly driven by (broad alliances of) civil society actors, which means that otherwise relevant campaigns have not been chosen for this specific list, such

as #EnBlandtOs against sexism in politics, driven by elected Danish politicians, as well as #NotOnTheMenu against sexual harassment in the hospitality sector, driven by the trade union 3F. One of our campaigns, “Public Servant Tuesday”, was closely connected to another campaign, that of the nurses’ strike in June-August 2021, coordinated by The Danish Nurses’ Organization. In this regard, the choice of the former relates to the mobilization amongst not only nurses but activists from various professions and feminist NGOs. Particularly this campaign also showcases that feminist campaigning in Denmark often relies on close cooperation between, on the one hand, NGOs, activists, and public debaters and, on the other hand, institutionally anchored actors such as trade unions.

With this in mind, we have chosen one campaign for each thematic area. Yet, the five campaigns below are also different from each other in terms of mobilization and political/policy influence. Except for the fourth campaign that ran during 2016, all of them have presumably been shaped, at least indirectly, by the emergence and rising influence of the #MeToo movement since 2017. The five campaigns are, briefly described, the following:

i. “Let’s Talk About Yes”

This was a campaign for a new consent-based rape law in 2018, which mobilized an alliance of a large part of the feminist movements. However, the campaign was not initially successful in terms of policy change since such a law was not introduced until 2021.

ii. “Your struggle is my struggle”

This was a small social media campaign from 2021 by a minority women organization. The goal was to inform and reach out to women in vulnerable positions due to social control and gender-based violence within their family but its reach was presumably limited. Even though the campaign was small, the issue is very visible in public debate.

iii. “Public Servant Tuesday”

It was a campaign with weekly demonstrations in 2021 connected to the nurses’ strike but with a broader focus on ending the equal pay gap between professions in the public sector. The campaign was partly successful by putting the issue on the public and political agenda.

iv. “#sicksystem”

This 2016 campaign on transgender rights, led by Amnesty International, mobilized activists from several different NGOs. It was highly successful in the sense that it reached its goal of removing transgender from the list of mental illnesses.

v. “My body, my choice”

It was a brief campaign in 2022 on social media and with a single demonstration in solidarity with women in the US after the decision to end the constitutional right to free abortion. The mobilization was not large, but many different NGOs cooperated.

1.13 Appendix A - List of five feminist movements' campaigns in Denmark

Name of the campaign (original)	Name of the campaign (English)	Issue(s) addressed	Actors involved	Repertoire of action	Logo of the campaign	Web-page	Comment
Let's Talk About Yes	Let's Talk About Yes	Gender-based violence	Amnesty International Denmark, Dansk Kvindesamfund, Everyday Sexism Project Danmark, Talk Town!, Slutwalk Copenhagen, Women's March Copenhagen, Kvinfo, Center for Voldtægtsofre, Kvinderådet, Black Lives Matter Danmark, Aldrig din skyld, Danner	Collection of signatures, demonstrations		Voldtægt og samtykke (amnesty.dk)	Campaign in 2018 for a new consent-based rape law in Denmark. The campaign was mainly organized by Amnesty International Denmark but especially for the nationwide demonstrations in November many other organizations were also involved.
Din kamp er min kamp	Your struggle is	Migration	Søstre mod vold og kontrol, Nordea-fonden, Zonta	Social media, advertising	No logo	Søstre mod vold og kontrol (soestremodvoldogkontrol.dk)	Small campaign from 2021

	my struggle		Hillerød, Soroptimisterne, Odense Municipality				particularly targeted for minority women who have experienced “negative social control” and gender-based violence in their relationships. Main product was a video promoting their message.
Tjenestemandstirs dag	Public Servant Tuesday	Labour market	Dansk Sygeplejeråd, Farmakonomforeningen, Jordemødre for Ligeløn, Danske Bioanalytikere (more?)	Demonstrations, social media		#SlutMed1969 (@tjenestemandstirsdag) • Instagram-billeder og -videoer	Weekly demonstrations in Copenhagen and other cities during most of 2021 against the “public servant reform” from 1969 that is perceived as positioning women-

							dominated professions such as nurses on a lower salary level.
#sygt system	#sicksystem	LGBTQ+rights	Amnesty International Danmark, Copenhagen Pride, Transpolitisk Forum, Transkønnedes Interesseorganisation , LGBT Ungdom, LGBT Danmark	Information material, social media, collection of signatures		Transkønnedes rettigheder - Amnesty International	Campaign on social media combined with political lobbyism in 2016 to remove being transgender from the list of mental illnesses in Denmark. The campaign succeeded with new legislation implemented from 1 st January 2017.
Min krop, mit valg	My body, my choice	Health & reproductive rights	Dansk Kvindesamfund, Sex og Samfund, Amnesty International, Jordemødre for ligeløn, Dansk Mandesamfund, Volt	Social media, demonstration		"My Body, my choice" - March for frie abortrettigheder Facebook	In protest to the US Supreme Court' decision to upend the landmark Roe

			Danmark, Kvinderådet, Everyday Sexism Project Danmark, Fritt Vál, Mødrehjælpen, Women's March Copenhagen, Forældre og Fødsel				v Wade Case there was arranged a march for solidarity with many different organizations and invited speakers held on August 21 2022.
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1.14 Bibliography

- Agustín, L. R., Fiig, C., & Siim, B. (2022). Practices and Strategies of Gender Representation in Danish Political Parties: Challenges of 'Everyday Democracy'. In Lang, S., Meier, P., & Sauer, B. (Eds.). **Implementing Gender Quotas in Political Representation: Resisting Institutions (1st edition)**. Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-08931-2_2
- Agustín, L. R., Siim, B., & Borchorst, A. (2018). *Gender Equality without Gender Quotas: Dilemmas in the Danish Approach to Gender Equality and Citizenship* (pp. 400–423). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108636797.014>
- Agustín, L. R., Faber, S. T., & Nielsen, H. P. (2019). Europeanization Processes and Contemporary Politics of the Body: Stalking and Online Harassment. In Dørum, K. (Ed.). **Nordic gender equality policy in a Europeanisation perspective (1st edition)**. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429351136-9>
- Ahlgren, L. M. & Miltersen, E. H. (2021). Questioning Normal: Overcoming implicit resistance to norm critical education. *Women, Gender & Research*, 29(2), pp. 85-90-
- Aidt, N. M., Moestrup, M., & Knutzon, L. (2014). *Frit flet*. København: Gyldendal.
- Andersen, J. G. & Borchorst, A. (2020). Uligestilling i pensionssystemet. In Borchorst, A. & Dahlerup, D. (Eds.). *Konflikt og konsensus: Det danske ligestillingspolitiske regime*. (1th edition). Frydenlund Academic.
- Andreassen, R. (2004). From a Collective Women's Project to Individualized Gender Identities: Feminism, Women's Movements, and Gender Studies in Denmark. *Atlantis (Wolfville)*, 29(1), 71.
- Askanius, T., & Hartley, J. M. (2019). Framing Gender Justice: A comparative analysis of the media coverage of #metoo in Denmark and Sweden. *Nordicom review*, 40(2), pp. 19–36. <https://doi.org/10.2478/nor-2019-0022>
- Bjønness, J. (2012). Between Emotional Politics and Biased Practices—Prostitution Policies, Social Work, and Women Selling Sexual Services in Denmark. *Sexuality research & social policy*, 9(3), pp. 192–202. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13178-012-0091-4>
- Borchorst, A., Christensen, A-D., & and Raum, N. (1999). Equal Democracies. Conclusions and perspectives. In Bergqvist, C., Borchorst, A., Christensen, A., Ramstedt, V. R., Raum, N., & Strkásdóttir, A. (Eds.). *Equal Democracies: Gender and politics in the Nordic countries*. Oslo: Scandinavian University Press.
- Borchorst, A. & Agustín, L. R. (2017). *Seksuel chikane på arbejdspladsen. Faglige, politiske og retlige spor*. Aalborg: Aalborg Universitetsforlag.
- Borchorst, A. & Agustín, L. R. (2020). Ligestillingspolitikken i politiske, faglige og retlige spor. In Borchorst, A. & Dahlerup, D. (Eds.). *Konflikt og konsensus: Det danske ligestillingspolitiske regime*. (1st edition). Frydenlund Academic.
- Borchorst, A. & Dahlerup, D. (2020). Det danske ligestillingspolitiske regime: Konklusioner og perspektiver. In Borchorst, A. & Dahlerup, D. (Eds.). *Konflikt og konsensus: Det danske ligestillingspolitiske regime*. (1st edition). Frydenlund Academic.
- Borchorst, A., & Christensen, A. D. (2022). Ligestilling, feminisme og #MeToo. In Greve, B., Jørgensen, A., & Larsen, J. E. (Eds.). In *Det danske samfund: Centrale idéer og principper*. (2nd edition). Hans Reitzels Forlag. (Original work published 2012)
- Christiansen, L. B. (2021). Instagram huser ikke bare perfektionskultur – der findes også modstand. *Dansk Noter*, 1, pp. 24–27.
- Dahlerup, D. (2018). Gender Equality as a Closed Case: A Survey among the Members of the 2015 Danish Parliament. *Scandinavian political studies*, 41(2), 188–209. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9477.12116>

Dahlerup, D. (2020). Er ligestilling allerede opnået? Ligestillingspolitiske holdninger og engagement blandt Folketingets medlemmer. In Borchorst, A. & Dahlerup, D. (Eds.). *Konflikt og konsensus: Det danske ligestillingspolitiske regime*. (1st edition). Frydenlund Academic.

Dahlerup, D. & Borchorst, A. (2020). Det danske ligestillingspolitiske regime: Problemstillinger, tilgange og begreber. In Borchorst, A. & Dahlerup, D. (Eds.). *Konflikt og konsensus: Det danske ligestillingspolitiske regime*. (1st edition). Frydenlund Academic.

Dahlerup, D., Karlsson, D., & Stensöta, H. O. (2021). What does it mean to be a feminist MP? A comparative analysis of the Swedish and Danish parliaments. *Party politics*, 27(6), pp. 1198–1210. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1354068820942690>

DIHR, The Danish Institute for Human Rights (2020). Kvindefag i historiske skruetvinge: En analyse af tjenestemandreformens betydning for hierarkiet i offentlige lønninger fra 1969 til 2019. https://menneskeret.dk/sites/menneskeret.dk/files/media/document/Rapport_Tjenestemand_tilg%C3%A6ngelig.pdf

Hansen, D. & Mieritz, L. (2019). *Gode kasser*. København: Gyldendal.

Hansen, M. B. (2021). Between Two Ills: Homonationalism, Gender Ideology and the Case of Denmark. *Redescriptions: yearbook of political thought, conceptual history and feminist theory*, 24(1), pp. 60–75. <https://doi.org/10.33134/rds.339>

Harder, M. M. S. (2017). Ligestillingspolitisk repræsentation i Folketinget: en analyse af hvorvidt internt parlamentariske institutioner øver indflydelse på graden af ligestillingspolitisk repræsentation i Folketinget [Doctoral dissertation, University of Copenhagen].

Harder, M. M. S. (2019). Søstre i sangen: Tværpolitiske og institutionelle kvinde- og ligestillingspolitiske fora i Folketinget (1985-2016). In Hansen, L. L. (Ed.). *Køn, magt og mangfoldighed*. (1st edition). Frydenlund.

Heinskou, M. B. (2010). *En kompleks affære: anmeldte voldtægter i Danmark* [Doctoral dissertation, University of Copenhagen].

Heiselberg, M. H. (2022). "Coming into being as a fat person on Instagram: Potentials and moral dilemmas". Paper presented at *The Annual Conference of the Danish Gender Studies Association*. University of Copenhagen, August 18-19, 2022.

Kjølsen, L., Klæstrup, N., & Krarup, E. (2017). *Ludermanifestet*. København: Lindhardt og Ringhof.

Leine, M., Mikkelsen, H. H., & Sen, A. (2020). 'Danish women put up with less': Gender equality and the politics of denial in Denmark. *The European journal of women's studies*, 27(2), pp. 181–195. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1350506819887402>

Liinason, M., & Meijer, C. M. (2018). Challenging constructions of nationhood and nostalgia: Exploring the role of gender, race and age in struggles for women's rights in Scandinavia. *Women's history review*, 27(5), pp. 729–753. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09612025.2017.1358203>

Mikkelsen, M. (2021, February 19). Kvindekampen: Efter 150 år er målet stadig det samme. *Kristeligt Dagblad*. <https://www.kristeligt-dagblad.dk/danmark/efter-150-aars-kvindekamp-er-maalet-stadig-det-samme>

Nielsen, H. R., & Lous, E. (2020). Dansk Kvindesamfund. In *Den Store Danske*. Collected January 12, 2023, on https://denstoredanske.lex.dk/Dansk_Kvindesamfund

Petersen, M. N. (2011). "...med et regnbueflag i hånden": Fortællinger om homoseksuelle inklusioner og homonationalisme. *Lambda Nordica*, 16(1), pp. 41-68.

Plambech, S., Chemlali, A., & Cerio, M. C. (2022). **Women on the move: Trafficking, sex work and reproductive health among West African migrant women**. Dansk Institut for Internationale Studier, DIIS. DIIS Report Vol. 2022, No. 01

Politiken (2021): Megafon: Politisk skel i danskernes holdning til debatten, December 30 2021. Reestorff, C. M. (2021): The Affective Politics of Interfacial News: Danish News Media's Coverage

of #MeToo on Facebook. In Thomsen, B. M. S., Kofoed, J. and Fritsch, J. (Eds.). *Affects, Interfaces, Events*. Imbricate! Press.

Rognlien, L., & Kier-Byfield, S. (2020). Everyday Activism and Resistance By Minority Women in Denmark. *Conjunctions*, 7(1), pp. 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.7146/tjcp.v7i1.119854>

Thorning-Schmidt, H. (2021). *Blondinens betragtninger – om køn, feminisme og #metoo*. København: Forlaget 28B.

Stormhøj, C. (2019). Still much to be achieved: Intersecting regimes of oppression, social critique, and ‘thick’ justice for lesbian and gay people. *Sexualities*, 22(7–8), pp. 1309–1324. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1363460718790873>

Stormhøj, C. (2020). ‘Danishness’, Repressive Immigration Policies and Exclusionary Framings of Gender Equality. In Keskinen, S., Stoltz, P., & Mulinari, D. (Eds.). *Feminisms in the Nordic Region: Neoliberalism, Nationalism and Decolonial Critique*. (1st edition). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-53464-6_5

Sørensen, A. E. (2016). Vi har fundet os i alt for meget – de kvindedominerede fagforeningers og deres medlemmers ligestillingsprojekt 1985-2010 [Doctoral dissertation, Aarhus University].

Vaaben, L. & Thomsen, A. H. (2022). *EN FORUDSIGELIG FORBRYDELSE: Kvindedrab i Danmark*. København: Forlaget 28B.

2 FRANCE

2.1 Introduction

This report is based notably on a qualitative analysis of publications on the website Cairn.info (the main site hosting research output from French researchers) using the following keywords for publications since 2010 : “feminisms”; “feminist movement”; “activism AND feminism”; “women’s rights” “abortion AND France”, etc.. A screening then concentrated on the time period of focus of the articles and the country. In addition, we went through the publications of major feminist journals of the period : *Nouvelles Questions Féministes*; *Cahiers du Genre*; *Clio. Femmes, Genre et Histoire*; *Travail, Genre et Sociétés*. The research method also included reports from governmental institutions, publications of interest by feminist activists, journalists and conversations with feminist activists, as well as a study of the existing literature on the topic (academic publications in social sciences and literary works).

Most academic research on feminist movements published in the 2010-2021 period focus on the second wave of feminism, for example : (Jacquemart and Masclet 2017; Pavard 2012; Ruault 2016; 2021). As the editors of the double special issue of *Nouvelles Questions Féministes* - devoted to the topic of contemporary feminism - remind in their introduction, “the legitimacy of contemporary feminism is closely tied to the history of the movement” (Chaponnière, Ruault, and Roux 2017).

The wide-range of the topics covered reflects the diversity of the feminist movement in France: from cyberactivism (Jouët, Niemeyer, and Pavard 2017), ecofeminism (Benquet and Pruvost 2019), sexual and gender violence (Lett et al. 2020; Delage, Lieber, and Chetcuti-Osorovitz 2019) to gender analysis of the movements (Bereni 2012; Jacquemart 2013).

Feminist philosopher Froidevaux-Metterie sees in the 2010s period a “genital turn” of feminism (Froidevaux-Metterie 2018), with the body being central to many discussions. This was the case already in the 1970s with the battle for reproductive rights, but the difference lies, for Froidevaux-Metterie, in the renewed interest in sexuality and gender (Quéré 2022), an intimate sphere still to be conquered. This genital turn then leads to investing new topics in feminist activism and research, such as medically assisted reproduction (Hertzog and Mathieu 2021; Jouan and Clos 2020) obstetric violence (Schantz, Rozée, and Molinier 2021) or breastfeeding (Zinn et al. 2021).

Sexual and Sexist Violence is revived as a key topic of feminist mobilisations, and this already before #MeToo. A new generation of mobilisations appears on the web. A few years before #MeToo, in 2012, the blog (Tumblr) “Paye ta shnek” (shnek means “pussy” in Alsatian slang), initiated and curated by Anaïs Bourdet collected and shared thousands of testimonies of street harassment. In 2014, the hashtag #PayeTonUtérus sharing experiences of gynecological violence went viral on French twitter. It is in this context of feminist reclaiming of the body as a political space that #MeToo (2017) -- and the French version #Balancetonporc -- take place. In the next months and years, the movement has a trickle-down effect towards numerous spheres of society : several professional sectors had their own #MeToo (theater, sports, politics) as well as Lesbian and Gay #MeToo, as well as the familial sphere with #MeTooinceste.

Critical junctures identified include: in 2012, the change of Presidential Majority in 2012 and 2017, Public Debates about same sex marriage and Medically Assisted Procreation for all. Critical Junctures within the movement include the debates and legislations around the islamic veil, code of labour reform and pension reform.

Divisions among the Feminist Movements can be partly analyzed as a generational divide. They play out around long-standing divisions of the French feminist movements. These could be very schematically be summed up as:

- Universalism vs. Intersectional. Universalist feminists defend a vision of feminism based on the common experience of womanhood and therefore the erasure of individual differences. On the same basis, they defend a definition of secularity (Laïcité) based on the erasure of religious signs: supporting French laws of 2004, 2010 and 2021 law banning religious signs at school, the dissimulation of one’s

face in public space (burka and niqab) and religious signs (hijab) for parents accompanying their children during school trips, respectively. Intersectional feminists for their part highlight the different experiences of being “woman” and support individual expressions of difference, whether related to race, ability, sexuality or religion. This divide in general is generational, older 2nd wave feminists tend to be more universal in their approach, while the younger generations are increasingly intersectional. The larger movements such as *Nous Toutes* have many older universalist members, causing lots of smaller break out groups to form opposing such practices. In general these groups draw attention to a specific identity which impacts their experience of ‘womanhood’ and are intersectional in approach.

- For / Against prostitution and prohibition of prostitution (Bard 2017; Mathieu 2018). Framed either as an exploitation of women’s bodies and patriarchal violence or sex work which creates a class consciousness and the possibilities to mobilize for rights among which better working conditions. France’s policy towards prostitution leans towards prohibition rather than regulation.

- Essentialists / Differentialists vs Gender : a divide which contemporary forms show especially in relation to transgender rights. For essentialist feminists, being a woman can only be determined by birth and biological sex, and men and women are different by nature. This view excludes intersex, genderqueer, non-binary, and trans people. On their end “constructivists” feminists work around de Beauvoir’s “One is not born but becomes a woman” and gender studies. The divide between these strands of thoughts is reinforced on the question of “filiation” in the period considered (Fassin, 2001).

- Institutional vs grassroots feminism : the boundaries between the two are less marked than in the 1970s (Pavard, Rochefort, and Zancarini-Fournel 2020) but there still are political tensions between organizations funded by the government and more organic movements, especially on the topic of prostitution and intersectionality.

- Other associated or derived debates such as Quotas in Politics (Bender, Berrebi-Hoffmann, and Reigné 2015; Laufer and Paoletti 2015) and/or Medically Assisted Procreation or Surrogate Mothers, especially when these issues intersect with single motherhood, lesbianism and trans rights.

These debates more or less oppose two groups (with obviously nuanced positions within each group), with “grassroots-intersectional-support sex work-support trans rights” on one side and “institutional-universalist-anti prostitution-essentialist” on the other. The topic of surrogacy divides within these groups.

2.2 The history of the feminist movements and its context

In the 1970s, the feminist movement in France gained momentum around the issue of reproductive rights. Grassroot movements such as the Movement for the Liberation of Abortion and Contraception (MLAC), led to institutional changes through alliances with prominent intellectual and political figures. One of the most influential groups of this era was the *Mouvement de Libération des Femmes* (MLF), which was founded post May ‘68 (1970) and organized public events to raise awareness on inequalities between men and women and generate discussion on sexuality, abortion and contraceptive methods (Zancarini-Fournel 2003). In 1971, the publication of the “*Le Manifeste des 343 femmes ayant déclaré s’être fait avorter*” (Manifesto of the 343 women who declared having undergone abortion”), written by Simone de Beauvoir, was published in *Le Nouvel Observateur* at a time where abortion was illegal. In Paris, Lesbian and Gay activists joined to create the *Homosexual Front of Revolutionary Action* (FHAR) to address homophobia in society and in social movements. The influence and references to key figures from the second wave of feminism, such as Simone de Beauvoir but also Simone Veil, Gisele Halimi, Benoite Groux, Antoinette Fouque, are still very present within the feminist movements today. Some movements and structures created in the 1970’s are still important actors, such as, for instance : *Les Chiennes de Garde*, *Choisir la Cause des Femmes*, *La librairie des femmes* and the *Planning Familial*.

In the 1990s, the feminist movement entered a phase of restructuration, while ties developed with growing international anticapitalist/ alter-globalist movements (Falquet 2022). As attacks on reproductive rights continue, feminists organize an important protest on november 25, 1995, to

defend abortion. Following the march, the National Women's Rights Collective (Cndf) was created in 1996, a unique structure of feminist organizations, political parties and unions.

Third wave feminism started in France in the early 2000s, following the celebration of the 40th anniversary of the MLF, with a younger generation of feminists who came of age after the battle for abortion and contraception (Pavard, Rochefort, and Zancarini-Fournel 2020; 2020). The question of sexual violence against women in the 2000 entered the public debate with the stories of gang rapes in the French Banlieues. New movements were emerging, notably in the follow up of the movement Ni Putes Ni Soumises (NPNS) created in 2002 by Fadela Amara, which had a resonance in the whole of a French society then crisped on the issue of the islamic veil and horror stories of gang rapes in the French banlieues (Garcia, 2012).

During the early 2010s, feminist movements were struggling for visibility. The most visible feminist movements in the media were the form of actions of NPNS and FEMEN, and to some extent, La Barbe (a movement created in 2008) (Dalibert, 2017). Behaving against female gender norms, they aimed at sparking media attention and raising awareness to feminist issues around equality in positions of power (La Barbe) and revolution deconstructing patriarchy and religion (FEMEN). However, Dalibert (2021) argues that in the mainstream gender equality in France was seen as already 'completed' in the 70s, and as such there was not a huge amount of popularity for such groups or literature written about them.

Some movements, which have now gained quite strong influence such as Osez le Féminisme ! (OLF) appeared at the turn of the 2010's. OLF was created in 2009, at first to mobilize against the decrease in public funding to the historic movement of Planning Familial. They are well-known for their catchphrase "shame must change sides!" (la honte doit changer de camp!) (Pavard et al. 2020). OLF-founder Caroline De Haas then created a new movement, "Nous Toutes" in 2018 (described in section 3).

In 2012, the election of socialist François Hollande can be seen as having contributed to bringing back feminist topics on the frontstage. Hollande immediately reinstated a Ministry for Women's Rights, and gave Minister of Justice Christiane Taubira the responsibility of legalizing same-sex marriage. In the same period, the rise of social media allowed organizations such as Osez le féminisme ! to develop local committees across the country (Pavard et al. 2020, p.432). The socialist government was an opportunity for feminists to foreground their demands; for example in 2015, feminist collective Georgette Sand launched a petition to change VAT on menstrual hygiene products from 20% to 5.5%⁶.

In the following years, feminist movements were active on many topics and foregrounded in the public and media scene, leading some academics to describe the 2020s as a moment of the "success" for feminism (Viennot and Wiels, 2019). Indeed, in the past decade, feminist movements have been growing in numbers and challenged a wide-range of topics within French society. Many grassroots movements and social media accounts have focused around women's bodies, challenging patriarchal views of topics such as menstruations, body hair, postpartum bodies. Feminist movements have also called out the government and created public debates about "sexist and sexual violence" in the medical domain and in the public space, a topic that expanded to all sectors after the #MeToo moment.

There have also been several initiatives to merge anti-racism and feminist struggles, creating debates within the feminist movement. Some of these initiatives have taken the form of the creation of new organizations (Lallab, "Femmes en lutte 93") while others take the shape of public events and movements (organization of separate feminist and pride marches a few days around the mainstream event, participation in anti-racist marches). The islamophobic context and government-led and far-

⁶ <https://www.lefigaro.fr/actualite-france/2015/02/28/01016-20150228ARTFIG00182-un-collectif-feministe-denonce-la-taxation-des-tampons-et-serviettes-hygieniques.php>

right initiated debates on “islamogauchisme”⁷ (“islamo-leftism”), “gender theory” and “wokeism”⁸ have been major challenges for this branch of the feminist movement.

Opportunities and critical junctures

Feminist opportunities in the period are closely tied to political events and to highly mediatised cases of sexual violence, such as the Strauss Kahn Affair. When FMI director and potential French presidential candidate Dominique Strauss-Kahn was arrested in New York in 2011 under charges of sexual assault and attempted rape, the reactions in France were slow. At first, the framing was not one of sexual violence, some prominent French public figures defending a “féminisme à la française” (“feminism, the French way”) (Pavard, Rochefort, and Zancarini-Fournel 2020, 416). French feminists organized a protest (Falquet 2012) and defended an analysis of the event through the lens of gender and sexual violence (Delphy 2011). This frame has become much clearer in 2016, when 14 women spoke out against sexual harassment and sexual assault from the political figure Denis Baupin (Jérôme 2019; Rousseau 2019). Following its intense media coverage, the “Baupin case” became a landmark case of sexual violence in politics in France.

The arrival of a new President In 2012 marked an area of new opportunity for feminist movements. New President Hollande (Socialist) appointed Najat Vallaud-Belkacem as Minister of Women’s Rights, following 5 years with no dedicated Minister under the Sarkozy presidency. Under Holland, feminist agendas were pushed through two main projects : the same-sex marriage law “Mariage pour Tous” (2012) and the “ABCD de l’Egalité”, which focused on raising awareness on gender stereotypes at schools (2013-2014). While both feminist and anti-feminist movements took the streets in relation to same-sex marriage, only the anti-feminist movement spoke publicly against the ABCD de l’égalité, which was a major defeat for feminism (see “challenge” section below). One reason for this is tied to the fact that the feminist agenda of the ABCD de l’égalité was not prominent (Blézat 2022).

In 2017, Emmanuel Macron introduced himself as a “feminist candidate”, however his actual outcomes on women’s rights are highly contested. Notably Macron did not create a Ministry of women’s rights but a State Secretariat instead and then a “delegated” ministry, instead of a fully fledged ministry. If the budget allocated to activities “labeled” as “equality between women and men” doubled between 2016 and 2022, it remained extremely low (0,25% of general budget in 2022) (Lhote Fernandes 2022).

The global #MeToo movement starting at the end of 2017 is a critical juncture in France during this time. After decades of feminist mobilization on the question of the body (Perrot 2019), #MeToo brought attention to violence against women by people in powerful positions, both culturally and institutionally, and marked a shift in media narratives towards white men being the perpetrators of female oppression (Dalibert, 2021).

France had its own version of the hashtag #balancetonporc (“snitch on your pig”), which gathered nearly half a million tweets in one month (Pavard, Rochefort, and Zancarini-Fournel 2020, 454). Much like its international counterparts, new mass protests and feminist groups were formed, most famously Caroline de Haas’ NousToutes. The first organized protest was on the 24th of November 2018 with over 50,000 participants across France, predominantly campaigning against gender-based violence brought to attention by the #MeToo revelations (France24, 2018). However, unlike the movements originating in the US, where in the year after its virality, abusers had lost jobs, and public figures such as Weinstein were arrested, in France there has been immediate pushback. In January 2018 one-hundred women of powerful position signed an open letter declaring the #MeToo movement a puritan

⁷ A popular and derogatory term used by the right to refer to an alleged alliance between left-wing movements and islamic fundamentalism.

⁸ A popular and derogatory term used by the right to refer to allegedly overly politically correct values of left-wing movements.

overreaction which presents the woman as an eternal victim, conflates seduction with assault and represents a misandrist feminism (Albenga et al. 2019) (Le Monde, 2018). This sparked shock and anger in the newly emerged movements, and many commenters saw this as a generational divide between the feminists of the 70s and youth activists (Beardsley, 2018).

The #MeToo moment in France has been followed by an explosion of feminist voices in the media and - it seems - an explosion of feminist movements. It can be summarized as “all the rallying against sexist and sexual violence, the echo they find and their political and social impact, and more globally on the speaking space that opens for feminist ideas” (Pavard, Rochefort, and Zancarini-Fournel 2020, 453). It has been followed in France by other more specific #MeToo campaigns such as #MeTooGay (2021), #MeTootheatre (2021) or #MeToolesbien (2022).

What seems more specific to France is that #MeToo has also been followed by a #Metooinceste (2021) movement on social media in 2021, launched by Nous Toutes to ask for changes in the juridical treatment of incest (Idoiaga Mondragon, Eiguren Munitis, and Belasko Txertudi 2022). It coincided with the publication of the book *La Familia Grande* (Kouchner 2021), in which Camille Kouchner publicly speaks out about incest and the sexual abuse of her brother by one of the most recognised and influential public intellectuals, Olivier Duhamel. It followed up a series of books that got visibility in the public debate, such as *Le Consentement* (2020) by Vanessa Spingora in which she exposes the complacency of the whole society towards a pedocriminal author, who was living a flourishing career, Gabriel Matzneff or *La Consolation* (2016) in which television presenter Flavie Flament she relates the rapes by famous photographer David Hamilton.

#MeTooInceste participated in the liberation of speech in the public debate on sexual violence, in what seemed to be a much more inclusive movement than #MeToo or #Balancetonporc, which has stirred important opposition. According to Mondragon, Munitis and Txertudi (2021) “France is witnessing a liberation of speech on sexual violence and incest that has created, in an unprecedented way, a connection with the collective conscience (Varier, 2021).” What differs from the #MeToo movement is also its public reception since “no counter movement has been found defending the aggressors, not even the most famous aggressors .”

Major challenges

One of the major threats to feminist movements is the anti-gender movement, both at the political level and online. At the political level, one example is the failure of “les ABCD de l’égalité” (2013-2014). The anti-gender movement “La Manif Pour Tous” (originating in 2012 as a movement against same-sex marriage law), and their allies (including right-wing muslim parents and public personalities (Gallot et Pasquier 2018) formed a huge campaign consisting of protests, rumour bombs⁹ and targeted cyber attacks around the ABCD de l’Egalite policy. The opponents to the project claimed it to be teaching explicit sexual content to children and ‘gender theory’; eradicating any difference in genders (Harsin, 2018). Even though the first results were encouraging among participating classes, the project was canceled after a teacher received death threats (Blézat 2022).

This regression of state policy towards gender equality in educational practices was an important failure for feminism. It also highlighted the use of social media to push forward the agenda of the far-right and anti-gender movement. Beyond the ABCD de l’égalité, feminists have been regularly confronted with cyber-harassment. In 2018, Caroline De Haas decided to quit social media and especially Twitter after days of cyber-harassment following an interview where she stated that “probably one out of two or three men is an abuser” (Checknews 2018). The organization Lallab and its founder Sarah Zouak also faced several waves of misogynist and islamophobic cyber-harassment,

⁹ The term refers to false or misleading information that is spread rapidly through social media, messaging apps, or other digital channels.

one of them leading to the organization almost losing the possibility to hire state-supported volunteers (“service civique”). The organization was supported by several public personalities and researchers, including feminist sociologist Christine Delphy (Collectif 2017).

Finally, one of the challenges lies within the feminist movement : its lack of diversity when it comes to race, gender, sexuality, ability. The editors of the special issue of *Nouvelles Questions Féministes* on the new forms of feminist organizing analyze that “feminist organizing has to be able to also fight against other oppressions than those endured by women as women. (...) The legitimacy of feminism also plays out in the ability to integrate the question of intertwined power relations” (Chaponnière, Ruault, and Roux 2017).

To conclude, in the 2010-2021 period we can therefore see large changes in the French feminist movement, with the leading feminist and anti-feminist groups in 2021 not existing in 2010. Externally, the movement has been greatly impacted by a rising xenophobic climate and politics of laïcité, the international growth of anti-gender and populist movements, and, the revelations of #MeToo. Due to internal rifts - predominantly around the veil and islamophobia, trans rights and sex work - at the end of 2021 we find a large web of feminist activists and groups in France, which can at times be very conflicting. Anti-feminist groups take advantage of this, such as Némésis, who, pretending to be members, infiltrated a NousToutes protest sharing islamophobic content (Simovic, 2022).

2.3 Actors, organizations and organizational models

The galaxy of feminist movements has changed dramatically in the period considered, notably with the emergence of a very high number of individual-led and/ or small group initiatives that have gained public recognition in the media and the birth of new widespread movements.

We observed in the last 10 years a professionalization of feminism. The institutionalization of historic movements such as Le Planning Familial (see below) and individual trajectories such as those of Sandrine Rousseau and Caroline De Haas illustrate this professionalization. Sandrine Rousseau is an academic, and founding member of the French ecologist party. She became publicly known for her feminism through her commitment towards victims of sexual violence following her own accusations against Denis Baupin just before the #MeToo movement. She is currently deputy and a prominent feminist figure - making her the target of anti-feminist attacks. Caroline De Haas co-founded OLF in 2009 and Nous Toutes in 2018, which both use professional communications tools to share their messages. She is also co-founder of a company (Egaé) which provides training on sexual harassment and sexism to other companies and government entities. In 2020, she left Nous Toutes after training a team of young feminists. In 2023, she launched “The Projet” which focuses on the way sexist and sexual violence are taken into account (or not) by the police¹⁰.

As these two figures illustrate, the mainstream feminist movement is overwhelmingly made of white, cisgender, heterosexual, able-bodied women, a characteristic that is not new. It was “already discussed at the time of the MLF and it is therefore disconcertingly stable: the inclusion of the Other remains the blind spot of militant feminist practice” (Chaponnière, Ruault, and Roux 2017). Occasionally, women with disabilities will make the headlines¹¹. The divisions around race, trans rights and prostitution remain strong. Racially and gender minoritized feminists organize separately and each year there are separate March 8 protests in several French cities : one day march organized by Nous Toutes and one night march and/or march in the suburbs of intersectional feminists.

¹⁰ https://www.instagram.com/the_projet/

¹¹ such as the cover of Marie-Claire featuring lawyer Elisa Rojas, founder of CLHEE, in her wheelchair in 2021 <https://www.aufeminin.com/news-societe/c-est-historique-elisa-rojas-militante-en-fauteuil-roulant-fait-la-une-d-un-magazine-feminin-s4022820.html> ; or the fat activist, DJ and model Barbara Butch on the cover of Telerama in 2020 <https://www.telerama.fr/medias/grossophobie-contre-la-censure-des-reseaux-sociaux,-postez-la-une-de-telerama,n6601971.php>

In the following paragraphs, we focus on four of the main initiatives : Nous Toutes, Lallab, the Planning Familial and l'Observatoire des violences sexuelles en politique.

Nous Toutes

The most famous feminist movement in France today is 'Nous Toutes' (Us All). Founded by Caroline De Haas in 2018 in aftermath of the #MeToo movement, the organization seeks to promote gender equality and the rights of women in France and beyond. Nous Toutes has been the main mobilizing movement in the recent period. Its main areas of interest are issues linked to sexist and sexual violence. Nous Toutes is known for its activism and advocacy work on issues such as reproductive rights, sexual harassment and violence against women, and gender-based discrimination. The organization has also been involved in campaigns to raise awareness about these issues and to push for policy changes at the national and local levels.

The movement is collective and made up of hundreds of local micro groups and branches. All members including those in leading positions work voluntarily. As such the group incorporates a wide range of views within the larger feminist movement. Nous Toutes is an organization that adopts a deliberative model of decision-making and representation, branches hold regular meetings and discussions to solicit feedback and input from its members, and decisions are made through consensus-based processes. The organization also has a leadership structure, including a president and a board of directors, who are elected by the members and who are responsible for implementing the decisions that are made through the deliberative process. This structure is designed to promote democratic and participatory decision-making, and to ensure that the organization is representative of the diverse perspectives and experiences of women.

Nous Toutes primarily works toward its objectives through a bottom up approach of education and media representation, encouraging members to speak with the press and offering workshops on how to effectively do this. They utilize new technologies and digital social spaces greatly, WhatsApp is the branches' main organizational tool, there are live votes on different social media platforms, live Facebook informational events, and regular Q&As (Pavard et al, 2020). Their largest external social media presence is instagram, with half a million followers to date. This allows them to create their own content which is otherwise missing in mainstream media such as their famous femicide counting. The group also produces lots of physical handouts, all printable via the site to encourage collective production. Additionally, every year in November the group arranges large protests throughout France¹², for educational purposes and to put pressure on governmental figures.

Nous Toutes is non-partisan and strives for intersectional ways of working, however, there have been issues around this. During the first Nous Toutes protest a breakout group called Nous Aussi was created due to their frustration with the main groups lack of fully incorporating their political stance of tackling interlocking forms of discrimination within the organization's structure. This also came back to light towards the end of 2021, when activists in social media showed that Nous Toutes shared féminicide count did not include trans women or sex workers. A new coalition was formed in June 2022 'Inter-organisation Féminicides' which is now developing a coordinated count and involves groups such as acceptess-T, La Fédération Parapluie Rouge, Médecins du Monde, Les Dévalideuses, #NousToutes and Act Up-Paris. Included in these groups are Trans activists (acceptess-T) and promotion of sex workers rights (La Fédération Parapluie Rouge), areas which previously were missing from Nous Toutes communications. This paired with a new ongoing working group around interlocking power systems and its inclusion in their 2022 internal objectives (Noir, 2022) showcases recent work towards intersectionality.

¹² In 2019, Nous Toutes announces the largest protest in feminist history : 100 000 people in Paris and 150 000 nationally (Pavard, Rochefort, and Zancarini-Fournel 2020)

There are no exact figures as to *Nous Toutes* composition, due to both the open structure of the organization and its microgroups, and French constitutional laws prohibiting data collection on race. Linked to its earlier issues with intersectionality the group is known as predominantly white and cis-female. However, *Nous Toutes* strives to be a movement connecting feminists across axes of gender, race, class and age, and certainly its large following represents this.

Nous Toutes works on both a local scale, with micro groups formulating their own campaigns and a national scale with an elected decision making body. The national group is well connected in the larger French feminist movement, with over 60 organizations supporting them during the November 2021 protest. They also regularly form partnerships for specific campaigns, such as 'Operation #SafeBar', a campaign with associations Consentis and Act Right, against sexual violence in nightlife following the #BalanceTonBar movement. This included physical 'stop street harassment' kits, with printed info sheets to place in bars to provide aid in assault cases, and partnerships with events to have safe spaces and educators present. *Nous Toutes* have formed some minor partnerships with international groups such as Amnesty International, however, the majority of their work is on a national level.

Lallab

Much smaller, but characteristic because it works specifically on intersectionality and on discrimination faced by muslim women with a feminist and secular approach, Lallab is one of the current feminist movements that stands out, by the topics, narratives it uses and attacks it has been subject to. Lallab was created in 2016 by Sarah Zouak and Justine Devillaine in response to an increasingly xenophobic and islamophobic climate. Primarily their actions can be seen to denounce the sexism, racism and Islamophobia suffered by Muslim women, and to produce counter narratives separating muslim and French identity. Included in this is working against a western vision of muslim women being a victim of internalized misogyny, in need of liberation with laws such as the 2011 veil ban, aptly choosing the slogan «Ne nous libérez pas, on s'en charge ! » ("don't liberate us, we'll do it!"). Although this is their focus, they work within the wider intersectional feminist movement in France, describing themselves as feminist, a-religion and anti-racist, "the most important thing is to allow women to embrace all layers of their identity in France", according to their website homepage.

Lallab has a paid head office who works as the general management of the association, implementing the decisions, managing activities and volunteers, and participates in the reflection of the Board. They then have an open voluntary membership, of around 120 people at any given time, who take part in decision making through joining at least one working group per year and taking part in the annual General Assembly. Here the association's strategy is created, and the board is elected. The board is an elected voluntary body changing every 3 years who take decisions related to the strategy voted by the General Assembly.

Nationally, Lallab have a large network within the feminist community. They were part of the #NousAussi movement in 2018. They mainly disseminate their campaigns through educational means, both through social media where they have their own following (i.e. 26,000 instagram followers) and most famously through their documentary series 'Women SenseTour'. This is an ongoing series being filmed in five different predominantly muslim countries, focusing on female rights activists in each place to dispel xenophobic narratives in France and beyond.

Planning Familial (PF)

The Planning Familial (PF) was created in the late 1950s and an important figure in the legalization of abortion and contraception in France. It is organized at three levels : organizations at the department level (72), regional federations (9) and a national confederation. Members at the department level are employed through state funding for the activities of counseling and sexual education (Romerio 2018). Historically, there have been tensions related to the professionalization of the services, some activists arguing that they were losing independence, others that this would provide stability and ability to reach out and support more women (Romerio 2022). One important characteristic is that PF local organizations include many volunteers, even though the numbers and proportions vary from unit to unit.

The PF is very active in the domain of reproductive rights; on an everyday level by providing contraception and abortion information and sexual education in schools, but also on the political level. It has supported recent changes in abortion laws and campaigns such as #OuiJaiAvorté with Causette magazine in 2021 where 13 public figures talk about their abortion. Members also participate in protests around women's rights in France but also to support women and reproductive rights in other countries (US, Ukraine, Poland, Iran). Some PF also provide support to those who need to travel outside of France to get an abortion, for example through online pools¹³. Each of the PF organizations have their own social media; the national PF confederation gathers 23.5k followers on instagram, 22.6k on Twitter and 39k on Facebook.

Officially, the PF stands firm on women's individual religious choices¹⁴ and has changed its positioning in the past decades, the organization being initially in favor of the 2004 law on religious signs at schools (Romerio 2018). However, due to the scope of this organization, with PF units operating at the departmental level, the practices are heterogenous, and some local organizations are more in line with governmental policies regarding laïcité and conflate sexism to a problem stemming from the French suburbs and Islam (Romerio 2018).

An interesting characteristic of the PF is that, contrary to other mainstream organizations, the PF has been able to embrace the fourth wave of feminisms and questions around gender. Most recently (summer 2022), it has been at the heart of far right and anti-gender attacks, following a poster stating, "At the PF, we know that men too, can be pregnant" and a picture illustrating a genderqueer couple, one of them pregnant. Beyond public debates on the poster and calls to defund the organization from its critiques (see below 5. LGBTQI rights), it has also had consequences at the local level, with a generation divide between older and younger volunteers¹⁵. Still, the PF illustrates the ability for feminist organizations to embrace new movements and change and seek alliance with younger feminist groups.

Observatory of Sexual Violence in Politics

The Observatory of Sexual Violence in Politics is one of the last born of the feminist movements in France. It was founded in early 2022 by Alice Coffin, Madeline da Silva, Hélène Goutany, Fiona Texeire and Mathilde Viot, in a country where sexual violence in politics is slow and difficult to denounce (Rousseau 2018). It is a small movement. The Observatory is being active at a moment in which the cases of sexual violence are revealed in the case of major politicians in the right as well as in the left-wing movements, even those which openly refer to feminism within their manifestos and programmes (in 2022: affaire Julie Bayou in EELV, affaire Adrien Quattenens in LFI)

The Observatory approach, strategy and links differ from those of other movements, notably in that it includes in the small operational group two elected representatives at the municipal level and two persons who work with elected representatives (Fiona Texeire and Mathilde Viot). Alice Coffin is elected as an ecologist at the Paris Council. Madeline da Silva is deputy mayor of Les Lilas (a small municipality in the close vicinity of Paris), in charge of equality between women and men and the fight against sexist and sexual violence. Hélène Goutany is a journalist. The Observatory website builds on the #MeTooPolitique (2021) and states "Our approach was born from an observation: institutions and political parties treat with negligence the sexist and sexual violence suffered by the women who make

¹³ For example that of the PF of the Var department "IVG hors délai" <https://www.planning-familial.org/fr/le-planning-familial-varois/contraception/cagnotte-solidaire-ivg-hors-delai-2167>

¹⁴See the page dedicated to "Laïcité" on their website <https://www.planning-familial.org/fr/le-planning-na-jamais-renonce-la-laicite-367>

¹⁵ Personal conversation with PF members, Mounia El Kotni.

up their ranks, they treat with negligence the sexist and sexual violence committed by the men who make up their ranks.” The Observatory uses usual media platforms, such as the publication of a “Tribune” in November 2021, signed by 285 women to ask to “get the perpetrators of sexual and gender-based violence away from political life”. The Observatory also uses an ironic repertory such as the dedication of ironic Prizes (“the Godfather”, “Greatest Hopes”) to political personalities and draws on media attention in order to stop sexist and sexual violence in politics.

As a group, the core group is quite homogeneous in terms of age, socioeconomic status and race. The collective does not intend to grow in terms of participants. It does not provide information on its governance and internal functioning. L’Observatoire remains a small initiative in terms of numbers of followers. The Change.org petition gathered 36000 signatures but today. Today it has 8,256 Followers on twitter and 4800 followers on instagram in February 2023. However the members of the observatory are often contacted in the media and have a good public presence.

Feminist actors most commonly organize under the “associations” status, with a not-for-profit goal, that allows them to collect funds/ apply for funding, organize events and hire employees. Another status is the “collective” form, which is informal and does not have legal existence. Movements often start this way and then switch to an “association” status. Collectives can also be formed of several organizations, for example “PMA pour toutes” (MAP for all) is a collective of several organizations (La Barbe, les Enfants de l’arc-en-ciel, etc.).

The analysis in section 5 gives details on many other recent feminist movements.

2.4 Allies

Feminist movements cooperate with a wide range of actors, seizing opportunities provided by national and global agendas but also advance their own agenda. We have listed them by type of actors : the State (government-led initiatives, political parties, state-funded institutions, municipalities), the media (mainstream allies and feminist-led media), public figures, and other social movements.

According to political analyst Réjane Sénac, contemporary feminist organizations generally mistrust the State and the possibilities of participative democracy (Sénac 2019) system. Still, some institutional feminist organizations participate in government-led initiatives such as the Grenelle des violences conjugales (2019) which is now in the phase of follow-up regarding the recommendations.

Obviously, the opportunities to collaborate with the state vary depending on governments, but more generally feminists disagree on making the law the ultimate outcome of their battles. For example, on the topics of obstetric violence and of femicide, there continues to be a debate on whether a new law is necessary or the existing legal framework is sufficient (Roman 2020; Marie 2020).

Within political parties, there is no feminist party as such. Three left wing parties have feminist commissions (Europe Ecologie - Les Verts, France Insoumise, Nouveau Parti Anticapitaliste). Rather than parties, it seems that it is more the opportunity that creates an alliance between feminists and political representatives. For example it is Aurore Bergé, member of the presidential party LREM, that carried the proposal to include the right to abortion in the French Constitution.

Some State-funded institutions play an important role as allies of feminist movements, either by providing data on sexism and equality between women and men (High Council to Equality between men and women (HCEfh), Hubertine Auclert Center in Île-de-France region) or by acting at the regional level (Information Centers on Women’s Rights (Cidff)). Similar alliances can be found with national and international NGOs who support some feminist demands and run studies and campaigns on feminist topics. For example, Oxfam has published a report analyzing the measures taken by Macron during his first presidential mandate (Lhote Fernandes 2022); CARE France has launched a campaign #ChangeonsLesRègles to raise awareness on menstruation, and Aides on LGBTQI+ health.

At the local level, some municipalities have been allies on the thematic of gender and public space. A few small associations have been active on this questions like Genre et Ville and Féminicité, followed with municipalities which have worked on names and symbolism within the city such as Pantin

(Renamed Pantin.e in 2022) or Les MonumentalEs in Paris or on gender neutral urbanism (including gender neutral playgrounds) or inclusive urbanism (Villiers le Bel, Rouen, Nantes) or fight against sexist and sexual violence (Nantes hosted the first Assises Nationales de la Lutte contre les Violences Sexistes in 2022) (Urbanisme, 2023).

Allies of the feminist movement in the media include some traditional media: Libération was one of the first media to dedicate their cover page to obstetric violence in 2015 and Le Monde investigated sexual violence among left-wing student syndicate Unef in 2017. The main ally here seems to be the online information website Mediapart especially thanks to the work of feminist journalists Lenaïg Bredoux and Marine Turchi who have investigated on many sexual assault cases including those involving Denis Baupin (2016), former Minister Nicolas Hulot (2018, 2021) and more recently, deputy Adrien Quatennens (2022).

There are also feminists who organized within journalism, for example the Association of LGBTI journalists (AILGBT) founded in 2013; the collective “Prenons la Une!” (“Let’s take the cover”) in 2016, which share guidelines for their colleagues for treating intimate-partner violence in the media.

Feminist media include Madmoizelle (online, 2005), Causette (magazine, 2009), Cheek Magazine (online, 2013), Simone media (video, 2018, 394k followers on Instagram), Komitid (online, 2018), XY media (online, 2021) etc.

Since 2017, the year of the first feminist podcast “La Poudre” (Lauren Bastide), followed by “Un podcast à soi” (Charlotte Bienaimé) in 2018, there has been an increasing number of feminist podcasts on all topics. Their hostess, journalists for the most part, are also important allies and feminist activists themselves. Other public figures include actress Adèle Haenel who spoke out against sexual violence, journalist Rokhaya Diallo who also co-hosts a podcast on intersectionality and singer Angèle whose song “Balance ton quoi” became a feminist hit.

In relation to other social movements, there seems to be a major difficulty to find common grounds (“convergence des luttes”) like it has been the case in the past on questions of anti-globalization (Falquet 2022), for example with major organizations like Attac. One such recent intent is the 2020 Meeting of Justices (Rencontre des Justices) in Marseille, where hundreds of activists, including feminists (Sénac 2019).

In this sense the movement of the Yellow Vests of 2018 can be seen as a missed opportunity, even though the movement had strong female figures.

2.5 Themes and agendas

2.5.1 Labor market & Poverty

Feminist movements in France have tackled issues linked to the functioning of the labor market in very different ways. According to the authors of “Le Genre au travail” (2021), the decade of 2010 was that of the renewal of social and ecological struggles, where women made their voices heard. Within the “Arab Spring”, the “Yellow Vests”, against the closing of factories, whether they work in public or private services (retirement homes, hospitals, schools, commerce, cleaning), all have mobilized to denounce their working conditions, wages and employment or the reform of pensions, thereby creating a new relation to work.

One of the traditional focuses of institutional feminism is linked to the question of difference in salaries, on questions of representation of women in high positions in companies. These mobilisations have led to several legislative progressions, such as for instance the government- created index for professional equality between women and men that classifies all companies of over 50 employees : Index EgaPro, created in 2022. In the public debates and actions against the labour code reform (2016) and the pension reform (2019, 2023), feminist movements, notably those linked to political parties and workers unions have mobilised. In 2016, Osez le Feminisme (OLF) led mobilisations against the changes to labour law together with several labour unions and workers rights organisations, on the questions of the impact of the new law on women. In 2019 and 2023, feminists analysed the impacts

of such reforms on women, who often have careers with interruptions, part-time work and lower wages than men.

Precariousness due to the type of employment is one of the trigger topics for mobilisations, notably the question of subcontracting of low qualification service jobs, such as cleaning. Femmes en lutte 93 (2010-2022) references its campaigns on subcontracting, socio-economic inequalities, migrant women without legal residence papers, as some of their main topics. A recent case of Cleaners' movements against subcontracting has received the support of several feminist movements, notably those linked to Labour Unions such as Les Rosies, Attack. Saphia Doumenc (2021) highlights that the support of feminist movements to the mobilisation contributed to its success. After two years of mobilisation (2019 -2021) the Hotel Cleaners of the Ibis obtained what they were asking of their employers : a higher salary and better working conditions. According to F. Verges (2019), the Strike of the Ibis Batignolles Hotel Cleaners is also an action linked to decolonial feminism practice.

In this section we should also mention that the fight against sexist and sexual violence at work has become a key topic since the Strauss Kahn Affair (2011), notably in conditions in which there is difference of power. This mobilisation has been followed by actions by the government, such as for instance guidelines for employers about acting against sexual violence at work.

Finally, the question of women's poverty and precariousness is discussed in many ways in the feminist movements. Ouarda Sadoudi from the organization "Féminisme Populaire (Popular Feminism) phrases precariousness as a form of violence against women. Some other mobilisations highlight issues linked to purchasing power, such as the question of the "pink tax"- i.e. the fact that businesses set higher prices for items directed to women compared to those directed to men, had led to several mobilisations (Arianne Dausmesnil, Georgette Sand collective), or the question of "menstrual precariousness" (Règles élémentaires).

Recognition of prostitutes' rights is one of the dividing topics within the feminist movement. Some institutional movements such as Le Mouvement du Nid argue for the penalisation of clients (2016, 2018); other movements such STRASS (feminist sex workers union) insist on the legal protection of prostitutes. It is to note that le mouvement du nid has released transphobic statements, which may classify them among anti-gender activists.

2.5.2 Health & reproductive rights

Reproductive health and rights battles over the period include the access to Medically Assisted Procreation to single women and lesbian women ("Bioethic" law 2021). Other campaigns aimed at raising awareness on issues related to women's health and sexism in the medical sphere on the one hand and safeguarding the right to abortion the other. For the former, outstanding topics include menstruations and "menstrual activism", including raising awareness on endometriosis, (Ndiaye 2022; Rauglaudre 2018; Thiébaud 2017); obstetric violence and the feminist critique of gynecology (Blézat et al. 2020; Koechlin 2019; Quéré 2019; 2022; Schantz, Rozée, and Molinier 2021). Newer Campaigns against obstetric violence include StopVOG.

Battles to safeguard the right to abortion have been launched in response to conservative attacks by anti-choice movements in France and elsewhere in Europe and the world. During Covid lockdowns, feminist organizations such as Planning Familial and health professionals pushed for easier access to abortion by extending delays. The measure kept being debated during the French elections and was passed in 2022. Debate has now slipped to the question of the constitutionalisation of the right to abortion.

In the period, one also sees various mobilisations linked to sexuality. In 2011, OLF launched a campaign called "Osez le clito !" (Dare the clitoris) raising awareness on the lack of information about the clitoris. In 2016, independent researcher Odile Fillod created the first open access 3D model of the clitoris, allowing anyone with a 3D printer to recreate it. The news goes viral and in 2017, one science textbook editor (out of the 8 officially designed by the Ministry of Education) changes its drawings to include the clitoris. In 2019, an online and street campaign is launched to raise public awareness on this organ:

#Itsnotabretzel¹⁶. The posters and tags generate much enthusiasm from the public and are seen in all the country and gain momentum during the 2019 feminist march. At the same time, several actors on social media explore sexuality, sometimes focussed on Black Women Sexualities (Axelle Jah Njiké, #MeMySexAndI).

Finally, campaigns alert on menstrual precariousness, linked to the costs of menstrual protection. In 2017, on the occasion of International Girls' Rights Day on October 10, the Insomnia collective warns of menstrual poverty by changing the water color of Parisian fountains to blood red. Menstrual activism has been booming from then on, notably led by the movement Règles Élémentaires.

2.5.3 Intersectionality (rather than Migration)

Rather than Migration, which is not much a topic of feminist mobilisations¹⁷, intersectionality has become a topic in the last years in the feminist movement. This, on the background of an islamophobic public debate centered on women's clothing and victimization of Muslim women presented as "both a victim and an accomplice of her oppression" (Dalibert, 2021). Traditional Muslim clothing was deemed as anti-laicite and anti-feminist.

Between 2004 (Law forbidding wearing of religious symbols in schools) and 2010 (interdiction to wear burqa and niqab in public space) and up to this day (debate on interdiction of Islamic veil wearing in sports) much of the Islamophobic rhetoric in political speeches revolved around women. The prevailing narrative pictures Muslim women as unaware victims of Islam. A public narrative, recuperated by both the left and the right was formed that gender-based violence and women's issues in France were inherently anti-French. This was paired with an increasingly toxic climate towards non-white and predominantly Muslim people in France since Sarkozy's Presidency (Mballo and Bourget, 2018). Dalibert (2021) expands on this through their quantitative and qualitative analysis of all available online articles from seven main news sources in France on the subject of feminist movements in the 2000s and 2010s, consisting of 5336 articles, and finds that both the perpetrators and victims of female oppression are predominantly portrayed as Muslim. A public narrative, recuperated by both the left and the right was formed that gender-based violence and women's issues in France were inherently anti-French.

Islam and the right to wear the islamic veil has been a divisive topic for the feminist movements. Veil wearing rights have created an ongoing general political rift in France, with actors within both the left and right having opposing views: one side referring to secularism and universalism of the French Republic and citizens rights, the other side recognising intersectionality, difference and the right of women to choose for themselves what they want to/ can wear (Scott, 2010). Feminist movements fall into this rift, since many actors see the veil as a symbol of patriarchal oppression (Delphy, 2015). New Muslim-led groups and intersectional factions have emerged from this (Lallab, Les Hijabeuses, NousAussi). (Calderaro & Lépinard, 2021; Lépinard, 2015)

Intersectional feminism and afrofeminism have been gaining popularity and facing challenges from society and state institutions in the period. The perceived lack of consideration to intersectionality has been the trigger for the creation of movements outside of the mainstream movements. The politics linked to second and third generation migrants is dealt with separately by separated feminist movements or streams of thoughts, such as Lallab, or afrofeminist collective Mwasi. Moving away from historic movements such as Ni Putes Ni Soumises which framed sexism as a problem related to North-

¹⁶ Created by Julia Pietri of the Instagram account "Gang du clito"

¹⁷ Very few exceptions can be found : the Planning Familial explicitly supports access to health to all, and stands against the barriers faced by migrants and; in 2021 a national/european feminist action was organized in Nice "Feminist against European Borders" <https://toutesauxfrontieresfr.wordpress.com/feminist-action-against-european-borders-join-us/>

African men and Islam, North-African feminists act both against sexism and racism, speaking out against the islamophobia of left-wing organizations (Ali 2020; Ouassak 2020). The question of the intersection of race and feminism has recently been addressed by researchers, using for instance documentaries to try to reframe the debate such as “Ouvrir la voix” by Amandine Gay in 2017 and “Mariannes Noires” by Mame-Fatou Niang (2016), which explore the intersection of sexism and racism. Afrofeminist and Muslim Women led movements reclaim the heritage of anti-colonisation figures decolonial feminism (Vergès, 2019) and organize events in safe/caucus spaces. Pavard et al. (2020) share several instances taking place in 2017, such as the organization of safe space for racially minoritized people at Paris 8 University during the protests against the Labour Law (loi Travail) and the debates around the “Camp d’été décolonial” (Decolonial Summer Camp) organized for those struggling with “State racism”. The Nyansapo festival organized by the afrofeminist collective Mwasi (created in 2014) created a polemic around workshops for Black women only, which triggered a reaction of the Mayor of Paris, Anne Hidalgo. She intervened to say that public events must be open to all, discussion groups will take place in private places, which was what the organization had planned (Pavard et al. 2020).

2.5.4 LGBTQ+ and Trans rights

The debate in 2013 about same-sex marriage is one of the main political moments, in which LGBTQI+ rights are fully supported by the feminist movement. However, the convergence of the movement splits in 2015 around the issue of Medically Assisted Procreation (PMA in French). The debate is also crystallised around the issues of gender theory and the public debate around the ABCD de l’égalité (Fassa et al. 2010; Sinigaglia-Amadio 2010).

The main topics regarding LGBTQI+ movements defended by feminist movements in the period are those of the PMA pour toutes (Medically Assisted Procreation), topic for which movements such as La Barbe, FierEs, Enfants d’Arc-en-Ciel and APGL (association of Gay and Lesbian Parents) have mobilized, with success, since the law was passed in 2022, although it is not open to transgender people. The topic of GPA (Surrogate Pregnancy) divided the country (Jouan and Clos 2020).

A strong divide currently exists between feminists who have been labeled as TERF (trans-exclusionary radical feminist) and “trans-activists” or “radical trans-activists”. This debate came out into the public sphere in 2018 (Mathoux 2020). Marguerite Stern, ex-FEMEN, founder of the movement ‘Collages contre les Féminicides’ is one of the public figures who defend a sex-based differentialist model (against gender). This “battle” between feminists and transactivists led to several complaints of cyberharassment among those protagonists. #Toutesdesfemmes launched in 2020 following controversy is a Feminist collective of trans and cis women condemning recent controversies targeting trans women, arguing that we are #AllWomen, united against patriarchy.

2.5.5 Gender-based violence

Sexist and Sexual Violence (to follow the way feminists phrase it in the French debate) is by far the main issue French feminism focuses on. Almost all feminist groups talk about this, with Nous Toutes and #MeToo being the most famous.

The topic of Domestic violence and abuse has moved, since the 1980s, from an activist topic to a public cause (Delage 2017) following a similar trajectory than the topic of abortion and contraception. This is one of the topics which has found resonance in political circles and has been recently followed by governmental and legislative actions. One of the turning events is linked to the trial of Jacqueline Sauvage in 2012. Sauvage killed her husband after years of abuse, but the French law only recognizes self-defense when it is “immediate, proportional and necessary”. Sauvage was condemned to a 10 year jail sentence but in 2016, after feminist mobilisation and the creation of a support committee bringing together feminist activists, public figures and political personalities, President Hollande granted Sauvage presidential pardon (first partial, then full). The topic of domestic violence continued to be one of the major triggers of mobilisation. A strong mobilisation appeared as well around the public procurement of the emergency number 3919.

Harassment and sexual violence became widely discussed topics following the development of blogs and social media, which allowed women to share common experiences of sexism and harassment, but also feminist commitments and ideas (Pavard 2017). Among the early initiatives are the OLF - led blog “Vie de meuf” (“Chick life”) (2011), the Tumblr pages Paye ta shnek (2012) and “Projet Crocodiles” (“Crocodile project”, 2013). In the 2015s, online blogs calling out harassment in different professional sectors flourished (“Paye ta blouse” in the medical sector; “Paye ta robe” in the legal realm, “Paye ta fac” in academia etc.). In the academic domain, feminist collectives such as Garçes (Sciences-Po Paris) or CLASHES (Collective for the fight against sexual harassment in Higher Education, national), who were already active before the period, produce their own events and trainings on the topic, in a context of normalization of such violence, including by women themselves (Briquet 2019). Of particular relevance in the French case is the #MeTooPolitique, on the background of several revelations regarding high ranked politicians.

Feminist mobilizing on harassment includes the issue of cyber-harassment. Literature on the topic is still growing, as social media become a place of danger for women and other minorities (Bousquet et al. 2017; Hare and Olivesi 2021) but also a place of feminist activism (Breda 2017; Weil 2017). In 2016, the organization “Feminists against cyberharassment” launch #TwitterAgainstWomen to raise awareness on the impunity of sexism on the platform. In the French public space, in the aftermath of the #MeToo movement, the case of the “Ligue du LOL” (“LOL league”) was revealed in the media (2019). Ligue du LOL was a Facebook Group gathering some of the most influential journalists and advertising professionals of the times, which led to cyberharassment of individuals, mostly women or LGBTQI+, sometimes during years (Hare and Olivesi 2021). In 2020, within Covid lockdowns, young women noticed an increase in cyberharassment via “Fisha” accounts (accounts that are created specifically for cyber-harassing women and notably to share intimate sexual photos of video material, such as nude pictures or other). 12 of them, who define themselves as feminists, started the organization #StopFisha to provide support to victims of cyberharassment, including legal action against Fisha accounts (Stop Fisha 2021)\$

2.6 Repertoires of Action

In urban areas, feminist movements rely heavily on social media, either to share information or to organize events. In addition to Nous Toutes which we discussed earlier, a successful mobilization is #7novembre16h34 launched for the first time in 2016 by the feminist media Les Glorieuses¹⁸ (88k followers on Instagram). It raises awareness on unequal pay between men and women, with the catchphrase “Starting this time, women will now work for free until the end of the year”. The movement has gained popularity and every year, the #, which changes depending on annual pay difference, is heavily followed and shared in mainstream media.

Another use of social media have been individual or collective (but mostly not led by existing associations) initiatives such as #Paytonuterus (2015) on obstetric violence and #MonPostPartum (2020) on Twitter, “T’as joui¹⁹” on Instagram (482k followers).

Social media are also used to film and share feminist actions: La Barbe and Femen both have been doing it since the beginning of their movements (Dalibert 2017), and Nous Toutes and Stopvgo automatically share a live feed of their actions on social media. Group discussions on social media such as Facebook also create a first awareness of feminism (Jouët, Niemeyer, and Pavard 2017; Weil 2017).

¹⁸ Owned by Rebecca Amsellem who has been accused of racism and moral harassment from former employees <https://www.arretsurimages.net/articles/les-glorieuses-media-feministe-au-service-dune-girlboss>

¹⁹ Launched by Dora Moutot in 2018. Moutot has positioned herself as a TERF.

Online actions also can be seen through the use of videocall platforms. For example, Nous Toutes have organized free training sessions on sexism and sexual violence.

Messaging applications such as Whatsapp, Telegram and Discord are used for feminist organizing among activists.

Feminists also use online petitions to push their agenda forward (on change.org or mesopinions.com), for example: to ask for the pardon of Jacqueline Sauvage, to extend abortion delay, for a representation of the clitoris in all textbooks, etc. Those are mostly directed to the government, with the goal of changing the law, but also aim at creating a debate in society.

In-person actions include protests. One strategy implemented by Nous Toutes is to organize a different protest date in Paris than in other cities and fundraise for buses to bring activists from other French cities to Paris during March and November protests. Following the Swiss feminist strike of 2019, several feminist collectives and syndicates have called for a feminist strike in France in 2020 and following years under the #Onarretetoutes. #NousToutes demonstrations happened in 2018, 2019, 2021 and 2022. March strikes happen every year. References to international mobilisations are not absent from the French feminist movements Some Flash Mobs singing the Chilean song "Un violador en tu camino" took place in Paris, Toulouse and Lyon in 2019 (with up to 200 participants). However no strong evidence has been found by the authors of this report of systematic collaborations with Non Una di Meno (IT) or Ni Una Menos (Argentina, Spain).

In the public space, feminist actions have consisted : in renaming male street names to women's names (Nous Toutes), organizing "Days of the Matrimony" during the national "Days of the Patrimony"(Collectif Georgette Sand), and reclaiming the street through street activism such as the 'Collages féministes' movement of pasting femicide names and statistics on public walls.

In addition, several feminist festivals are regularly organized. For example: La Poudrière Festival in Dijon (2022, 3 days, 250 people), the annual WeToo festival in Pantin (Paris area) since 2020 (2 days, 3500 people), an ecofeminist gathering in Bure (Lavocat and Gauthier 2019), the 2020 Assises lesbiennes in Marseille, etc.

2.7 Frames of arguments

Gender based violence

Feminists have worked for the reframing of the question of sexual and sexist violence, highlighting that sexual violence happens in several arenas, public as well as private. The battle for a more just representation in the media and legal provisions in the case of domestic violence has been ongoing in the period analysed.

The use of the word "Femicide" is one of the recent reframings. The apparition in the public language of Féminicide is also characteristic of the period. Semantically, the word "féminicide" enters the dictionary Le Petit Robert in 2015. A Google n-gram search for "féminicide" (France : 1990-2019) shows a slow but steady increase in the use of the term since 2002, with a strong increase after 2014, the year of an OLF campaign on the topic and when the "Commission for the enrichment of French language" approved it (Cacouault-Bitaud and Jaspard 2020). The first counts of femicides started in 2016 on the blog "Féminicide par compagnon ou ex" based on media sources. The collective was recently critiqued for not taking into account the femicide of trans women in their count, leading feminist organization Nous Toutes to start their own count in 2022 (Delage et al. 2022). In 2017-2019, a new form of street activism merges around the topic of femicide : feminist activists take to the streets at night and paste the names of victims of femicides. The movement then grew to include a diversity of feminist messages related to rape culture, LGBTQI+, incest, etc. (Paris 2021)

Labour Market

The ways the feminist movements have approached issues linked to labour are linked to work/life balance, discrimination on the workplace and quotas (this has been followed by legislation)

There is an attempt to frame major political debates such as the current pension reform applying to it a gender frame, i.e. as simple as looking at the impact of the new laws about work (loi travail 2016) or the pension reform (2023) on women and on equality. Notably 50 feminist organisations have signed a media “Tribune” in 2016 raising awareness on the impact of the “Loi Travail” on women.

The other frame of argument is linked to the protection of women around maternity and the necessity of extension of paternity leave.

Health and reproductive rights

On health and reproductive rights, the genital turn of feminism can be described as a new attention to female sexuality and genitals. We mentioned the actions linked to representations of female genitals (clitoris) and sexuality. This includes movements using publicly references to menstrual blood to fight for policy changes.

Migration

Migration is not a topic that is very high on the feminist agenda. The main frame of argument is about the women who are racially minoritized or around religion. As the struggle within *Nous Toutes* shows, intersectionality is still a difficult topic in the republican universalist reference framework of many of the institutional French feminists. Discourses around intersectionality have had to develop outside of the main movements and have led to the creation of movements such as *Lallab* and *Réseau Classe/Genre/Race* by Fatima Ouassak.

LGBTQ+ rights

The debate around “gender theory” was played at the moment of the *ABCD de l'égalité* (2013), a battle lost by the defenders of gender theory, which has led to a stronger voice being given to some differentialist/ essentialist feminists, which insist on the difference of the sexes, such as the sociologist Irène Thery, and the anthropologist, Françoise Héritier or philosopher Sylviane Agacinski.

The debate about “gender theory” perceived as an importation from abroad, that would be detrimental to the child by its opponents has led to a higher number of assumed anti-trans movements, which have a revendication of being descendants of feminism, while rejecting part of its theoretical legacy (i.e. Simone de Beauvoir), such as *Les Antigones*, an extreme right wing “feminist” group (REF.).

2.8 Campaigns and debates

Several Campaigns have been described in previous sections. In this section, we mention some that have been described less, but have still been important moments of mobilisation and have led, for some, to policy outcomes.

2013: *ABCD de l'Egalité*: this campaign has been defeated by anti-gender mobilisations.

Campaign on Inclusive language : The theme of “inclusive” or “non sexist” language was heavily debated in 1997, following an op-ed signed by over 300 professors titled “We will not teach anymore that the masculine prevails on the feminine²⁰”, in reference to the French grammatical rule on adjectives). Attacks from the far-right movement led to discussion of the topic in the media and within political circles, with Prime Minister Edouard Philippe attempting to forbid its use in public administration (Loison, Perrier, and Noûs 2020; Viennot and Wiels 2019). These debates follow earlier steps towards non sexist language, such as the 1998 memorandum for public administrations to state

²⁰<https://www.slate.fr/story/153492/manifeste-professeurs-professeures-enseignerons-plus-masculin-emporte-sur-le-feminin>

the feminine form of professions and the end of “Mademoiselle” (“Miss”) and “maiden name” (replaced by “name of birth”) in public administration forms in 2012, following a feminist campaign of OLF and Chiennes de Gardes, who secured the support of Minister Roselyne Bachelot (Dalibert 2017; Rochefort 2017). The use of inclusive writing has nonetheless continued to grow, including in social science publications (Loison, Perrier, and Noûs 2020; Viennot and Wiels 2019).

2020: 3919.

In 2014, a free online number was opened for victims of violence, 3919, operated by the National Federation of Solidarité Femmes (Women Solidarity). At the end of 2020, the government, which funds the project, planned to open a public procurement call for interest open to all rather than simply renewing the contract. Several feminist organizations, including Nous Toutes, alerted the public opinion on the matter, and 3 months later the government backed out. Since 2021, the 3919 is opened 24/7 to cover all French territory and to people with disabilities, as part of the commitment taken during the Grenelle des violences conjugales (annual since 2019). However, the language of the platform is French only, and there is generally a lack of information for women who do not speak or read French, which one recently-created feminist organization (Women for Women France) aims at responding to²¹.

2021: #MeToo Incest: This mobilization led to the creation of an Independent commission on incest and sexual violence against children of France and to legislative change. “In response to this debate, in January 2021 the French senate unanimously approved a bill to protect minors under 13 years of age from sexual abuse, which establishes the notion of consent for those over that age. This bill aims to create a new sex crime for minors under thirteen years of age so that an explicit social prohibition is included in the penal code to protect children and adolescents from any sexual violence committed by adults” (Idoiaga Mondragon, Eiguren Munitis, and Belasko Txertudi 2022)

2.9 Key Policy related outcomes

In terms of policy related outcomes, we decided to include both legislative outcomes and government led initiatives.

Labour Market & Precariousness

The main policy outcomes coming out of mobilisation institutional feminist movements in the period are the following:

- 2011: Coppé-Zimmermann law on the balanced representation of women and men on boards of directors and supervisory boards and on professional equality.
- 2013: Founding of the HCE - High Council on Equality between men and women
- 2014: Law real equality between women and men. Companies must strengthen their company and branch negotiations to promote professional equality.
- 2016: VAT rate for hygienic protections changed from 20,6% to 5,5%.
- 2018: Law for the freedom to choose one's professional future.
- 2018: Law on penalisation of prostitution clients (which still stirs divisions inside the feminist movement and sex-workers unions)

²¹ The website hosts a multilingual platform www.womenforwomenfrance.org

- 2021: law aimed at accelerating economic and professional equality creates an obligation of balanced representation between women and men among senior executives and members of the governing bodies of large companies, accompanied by an obligation of transparency.
- 2022: Increased duration of paid paternity leave from 10 days to 28 days.

Health and Reproductive rights

- 2021: Medically Assisted Procreation for lesbian couples & single females legalised (PMA pour toutes)
- 2022: Macron announces national strategy against endometriosis
- 2022: Abortion window from 12 to 14 weeks of pregnancy
- 2023: Adoption of Law on Constitutionalisation of the Right to Abortion

Gender-based violence

- 2014 : creation of the 3919, a phone number dedicated to women victims of gender-based violence (FNSF)
- 2017: Macron declares Equality between men and women a National Cause
- 2018: Street Harassment law: the perpetrators of street harassment can be prosecuted and fined. Every year an annual barometer report is produced.
- 2019: Launching of the Grenelle des violences conjugales
- 2021: the 3919 becomes available 24/24
- 2021: France implemented an age of consent (15)
- 2021: The “prescription” period is extended for reporting of sexual assault on minors. It is increased to 10 years for sexual assault and 20 years for rape.
- 2021: Creation of Independent Commission on Incest and Child Sexual Abuse (or Ciivise, or Incest Commission)
- 2022: Creation of a new digital platform to fight against gender based violence - <https://arretonslesviolences.gouv.fr>
- 2022: Macron announced the launch of a “Pack New Start” (Pack nouveau Départ) to support victims of domestic violence
- 2022: French government organized together with UNESCO the Forum Generation Egalité to increase investment in initiatives in favor of gender equality and “live up to the ambitions” of the Beijing action Programme.

LGBTQI+ rights

- 2013: Same-Sex Marriage legalised
- 2021: Medically Assisted Procreation for lesbian couples & single females legalised (PMA pour toutes) + self-conservation of gametes
- 2022: conversion therapy banned
- 2022: Easing of name change for adults

Other topics:

Changing the way women are referred to / the Symbolic battle

In the arena of fighting dominant political representations of women the main policy outcomes are :

- 2012: Public administration forms do not mention "mademoiselle" or "maiden name" in forms

Political representation:

- 2013: Law on parity for the election of departmental councilors, municipal councilors and community councilors

In terms of legislative achievements, the topics that are defended by institutional feminists have largely been integrated into the legislation of the country.

On the question of Gender based violence, since 2017, there have been 4 laws passed, the launch of an annual national gathering on this topic "Grenelle contre les violences conjugales". The work with feminist groups and organizations from the civil society led to 54 commitments from the government, and some positive outcomes such as the training of police officers on GBV, an increase in emergency housing for victims of violence and an increase in the budget dedicated to the equality between men and women. However, a report by Oxfam, CARE France and feminist organization Equipop point out that this budget only represents 0,25% of the government budget (Lhote Fernandes 2022) and that the budget allocated to domestic violence is 3 times less than the needs identified by organizations.

Other laws have been passed, which improve LGBTQI+ rights, but have been faced with a very strong mobilisation of anti-gender and Christian conservative movements.

On other issues, the feminist movements are faced with the difficulty to produce statistics, for instance the femicide count is done by NGOs and by the lack of statistical data (Virage study on "Violence and gender relations: contexts and consequences of violence suffered by women and men" dates from 2015 and has not been renewed (Debauche, Mazuy, and Lieber 2019), Insee (national statistics agency) last statistics on domestic work dates from 2010) and there is no possibility of ethnic data in France. Romerio (2022) also suggests that there is an issue with the professionalization of feminism, which limits activism and progressiveness due to reliance on state funding.

Institutionally, we can also find a number of 'wins' and setbacks for the feminist movement. Macron stated women's rights to be a main part of his presidency, however, there are continued appointments to the Cabinet and other political positions that contradict this, such as the the 2020 reshuffle where Gerald Darmanin became Interior Minister while on trial for rape (2020), and Eric Dupond-Moretti, known for his repeated misogynistic remarks such as "some women regret not being whistled at" (France24, 2022), became Minister of Justice. Since 2010 France has implemented major legislation in favor of feminist thought, such as same sex marriage in 2013, extending the rights of medically assisted pregnancy to single women and couples with no men involved in 2021, implementing an age of consent (15years old) and banning LGBTQ+ conversion therapy in 2022. However parallel to this, major anti-feminist and anti-gender groups have formed in protest, one famous example is 'La Manif Pour Tous' (The Protest For All) formed against the 2013 same sex marriage act called 'Le Marriage Pour Tous' (Marriage For All).

2.10 Other Important Issues

There is important feminist work/activism on symbolism/visibility of women, about street names, gendered toys, gendered public space.

Ecofeminism is a growing renewed field of research since the publication in French of main ecofeminist texts by philosopher Emilie Hache in 2016 (Hache 2016). In the following years, sociologists studied the contemporary forms of ecofeminism in rural areas and in the self-help movement (Benquet and Pruvost 2019; Koechlin 2019). The concept gained public visibility during the 2021 primaries of the Ecological party EELV with candidate Sandrine Rousseau labeling herself "ecofeminism".

Other topics less widely discussed in the literature include:

- The prison system. Gwenola Ricordeau's work stands as an exception (Ricordeau 2019).
- The intersection between disability and gender "handi-feminism" (Blézat 2016).

2.11 Conclusions

Feminist movements have grown in numbers, reach out and debate framing power between 2010 and 2021. This period is also marked by important policy wins in areas classically associated with women rights activism (Representation of Women In High Positions in Business and Politics, Gender Based Violence) but also major changes in the fields of health and reproductive rights (MAP for all) and LGBTQI+ rights (Same Sex Marriage).

The period was also characterized by a deepening of preexisting divisions in the Feminist Movement and by the right wing radicalization of several key actors of the feminist movement on the question of gender and filiation, as well as on the question of position towards Islam and racialized minorities. An important push against gender theories, or backlash was fought for by anti-gender forces in the questions of ABCD de l'égalité in 2014 with relative success.

2.12 List of feminist movements' campaigns

Name of the campaign (original)	Name of the campaign (English)	Issue(s) addressed	Actors involved	Repertoire of action	Logo of the campaign	Web-page	Comment
Les Femmes de Chambre de l'Hôtel Ibis Batignolles à Paris	The Housekeepers of the Ibis Batignolles Hotel in Paris	Labour market & migration		Huge strike of cleaning staff in two hotels in Paris. 8 months of strikes and 22 months of protests. Also used media effectively, and gained crowdfunded support to replace their lost earnings. Successful in end - gained improved working conditions.			

<p>PMA pour toutes</p>	<p>AMP for everyone</p>	<p>health & reproductive rights LGBTQ+ rights</p>	<p>Osez le Feminisme SOSHomophobie OUTrans Les enfants de l'arc-en-ciel, Alice Coffin/La Barbe, FIÈRES, APGL (association de parents et futurs parents gays et lesbiens)</p>	<p>IVF treatment was reserved for heterosexual couples, this campaign was to extend IVF to lesbian couples & single women. There were large protests organized by OLF & SOSH. This was successful, in 2021 it became law, however, it remobilized anti-gender group la Manif Pour Tous.</p>	<p>unofficial but used often:</p>		
<p>Inter-organisation Féminicides'</p>	<p>Inter-organisation femicides</p>	<p>Gender-based violence and intersectionality within</p>	<p>acceptess-T, La Fédération Parapluie Rouge, Médecins du</p>	<p>Towards the end of 2021, activists on social media showed that</p>			

		feminist movements	Monde, Les Dévalideuses, #NousToutes, Act Up-Paris	<p>Nous Toutes famous féminicide count did not include trans women or sex workers. This count was made by a separate collective, 'femicides par conjoint ou ex', and in January 2022 Nous Toutes cut ties with them. This New coalition was formed in June 2022 to replace this and represents a move towards more intersectionality and collaboration in the French</p>			
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				feminist movement.			
#MeTooIncest e		Gender-based violence and incest	Camille Kouchner	<p>Social media movement that began in 2021 in wake of the #MeToo movement and the publication of "La Familia Grande" by Camille Kouchner to raise awareness about incest. Kouchner's book alleged that her stepfather, a prominent political figure in France, had sexually abused her twin brother.</p> <p>Encourages people to share their experiences of incest, abuse, and sexual</p>			

				<p>violence on social media using the hashtag #MeTooIncest e. The goal of the movement is to raise awareness about the prevalence of incest and to break the cycle of shame and silence that often surrounds it. The movement also calls for changes in French law to make it easier for victims to come forward and for perpetrators to be held accountable.</p>			
ExisTransInter		LGBTQ+ rights, Gender-based violence	l'Association du Syndrome de Benjamin, le Groupe Activiste Trans,	Inter-association collective who organize yearly	EXISTRANSINTER	http://existrans.org/	Formally named 'ExisTrans', this changed

			Act-Up, Sans contrefaçon, Mutatis Mutantis, Trans Act, l'Organisation Internationale des Intersexuée-s.	marches for trans and intersexual visibility and rights since 1997.			to 'ExisTransInte r' in 2020 to add visibility to the intersex community.
La Fédération Parapluie Rouge	The Red Umbrella federation (or Red Umbrella Fund is the name in international branches)	LGBTQ+ rights, sex workers rights, Gender-based violence, health & reproductive rights	STRASS (sex workers union), Acceptess-T,	Coalition of organizations linked to sex work, LGBT+ rights and LGBT+ health. Promotes safety and workers rights for sex workers. Also provides contacts for aiding sex workers i.e. help lines. Is against recent laws in		https://parapluierouge.org/	

				<p>France i.e. loi de pénalisation du client as creates more danger in prostitution.</p> <p>Often has debates with members of Mouvement du Nid who are abolitionist.</p>			
#NousAussi	#UsToo	intersectionality	Lallab, afro-fem, handi-queer, la chapelle debout, le strass, acceptess-T	<p>During the first Nous Toutes protest there was a breakout group called Nous Aussi, created due to their frustration with the main groups lack of fully incorporating their political stance of</p>			

				tackling interlocking forms of discrimination within the organization's structure. In the first Nous Toutes meetings, Nous Aussi complained there was many with a universalist feminist approach, and divisive topics such as the veil and sex work led to discrimination, predominantly islamaphobia, transphobia and sex work shaming.			
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1) labor market, (2) health & reproductive rights, (3) migration, (4) LGBTQ+ rights and (5) gender-based violence

2.13 References

- Albenga, Viviane, Armelle Andro, Pauline Delage, Samira Ouardi, Juliette Rennes, and Sylvia Zappi. 2019. "Éditorial." *Mouvements* 99 (3): 7–10. <https://doi.org/10.3917/mouv.099.0007>.
- Ali, Zahra, ed. 2020. *Féminismes islamiques*. 2e édition. Paris: La Fabrique Editions.
- Bard, Christine, ed. 2017. *Dictionnaire des féministes. France - XVIIIe-XXIe siècle*. PUF. https://www.puf.com/content/Dictionnaire_des_f%C3%A9ministes_France_-_XVIIIe-XXIe_si%C3%A8cle.
- Bender, Anne-Françoise, Isabelle Berrebi-Hoffmann, and Philippe Reigné. 2015. "Les quotas de femmes dans les conseils d'administration." *Travail, genre et sociétés* 34 (2): 169–73. <https://doi.org/10.3917/tgs.034.0169>.
- Benquet, Marlène, and Geneviève Pruvost. 2019. "Pratiques écoféministes : corps, savoirs et mobilisations." *Travail, genre et sociétés* n° 42 (2): 23–28.
- Bereni, Laure. 2012. "Penser la transversalité des mobilisations féministes : l'espace de la cause des femmes," 27.
- Blézat, Mathilde. 2016. "« Ah, t'es Sourde, désolé... mais t'es belle ! ». Femmes et Sourdes, à l'intersection des dominations." *Z : Revue itinérante d'enquête et de critique sociale* 10 (1): 118–21. <https://doi.org/10.3917/rz.010.0118>.
- . 2022. "Les ABCD de l'égalité : récit d'un fiasco." *La Déferlante* (blog). August 8, 2022. <https://revueladeferlante.fr/abcd-de-l-egalite-recit-d-un-fiasco/>.
- Blézat, Mathilde, Naïké Desquesnes, Mounia El Kotni, Nina Faure, Nathy Fofana, Hélène de Gunzbourg, Nana Kinsky, Perret Yéléna, and Marie Hermann. 2020. *Notre corps, nous-mêmes*. Edition réactualisée. Marseille: Hors d'Atteinte. <https://www.decitre.fr/livres/notre-corps-nous-memes-9782490579051.html>.
- Bousquet, Danielle, Edouard Durand, Ernestine Ronai, Alice Gayraud, and Claire Guiraud. 2017. "En Finir Avec l'impunité Des Violences Faites Aux Femmes En Ligne : Une Urgence Pour Les Victimes." 2017-11-16-VIO-030. Paris: Haut Conseil à l'Égalité entre les femmes et les hommes.
- Breda, Hélène. 2017. "La critique féministe profane en ligne de films et de séries télévisées." *Réseaux* 201 (1): 87–114. <https://doi.org/10.3917/res.201.0087>.
- Briquet, Coline. 2019. "De la banalisation des violences de genre en école d'ingénieur-e-s." *Cahiers du Genre* 66 (1): 109–28. <https://doi.org/10.3917/cdge.066.0109>.
- Cacouault-Bitaud, Marlaine, and Maryse Jaspard. 2020. "Féminicide : une qualification nécessaire... et suffisante ?" *Travail, genre et sociétés* 43 (1): 145–47. <https://doi.org/10.3917/tgs.043.0145>.
- Chaponnière, Martine, Lucile Ruault, and Patricia Roux. 2017. "Légitimité du féminisme contemporain." *Nouvelles Questions Féministes* 36 (2): 6–14. <https://doi.org/10.3917/nqf.362.0006>.
- Checknews. 2018. "Caroline de Haas dit qu'un ou deux hommes sur 3 sont des agresseurs : d'où sort cette statistique ?" *Libération*. March 18, 2018. https://www.liberation.fr/checknews/2018/03/12/caroline-de-haas-dit-qu-un-ou-deux-hommes-sur-3-sont-des-agresseurs-d-ou-sort-cette-statistique_1653301/.
- Collectif, un. 2017. "Stop au cyberharcèlement islamophobe contre l'association Lallab." *Libération*. August 23, 2017. https://www.liberation.fr/debats/2017/08/23/stop-au-cyberharcement-islamophobe-contre-l-association-lallab_1591443/.
- Dalibert, Marion. 2017. "Une mise à distance du sexisme ? Les actions d'Osez le féminisme ! et de La Barbe dans la presse." *Participations* 17 (1): 179–201. <https://doi.org/10.3917/parti.017.0179>.

Debauche, Alice, Magali Mazuy, and Marylène Lieber. 2019. "L'enquête VIRAGE (Violences et RAports de GENre)." *Cahiers du Genre* 66 (1): 37–50. <https://doi.org/10.3917/cdge.066.0037>.

Delage, Pauline. 2017. *Violences conjugales. Du combat féministe à la cause publique*. Paris: PRESSES DE SCIENCES PO.

Delage, Pauline, Delphine Lacombe, Marylène Lieber, and Magali Mazuy. 2022. "De la violence létale contre les femmes à la violence féminicide. Genèses et mobilisations." *Cahiers du Genre* 73 (2): 5–31. <https://doi.org/10.3917/cdge.073.0005>.

Delage, Pauline, Marylène Lieber, and Natacha Chetcuti-Osorovitz. 2019. "Lutter contre les violences de genre. Des mouvements féministes à leur institutionnalisation. Introduction." *Cahiers du Genre* 66 (1): 5–16. <https://doi.org/10.3917/cdge.066.0005>.

Delphy, Christine, ed. 2011. *Un trousseage de domestique*. Paris: Editions Syllepse.

Falquet, Jules. 2012. "DSK ou le continuum entre les violences masculines et les violences néolibérales." *Nouvelles Questions Féministes* 31 (1): 80–87. <https://doi.org/10.3917/nqf.311.0080>.

———. 2022. "Nos années 1990 : souvenirs de la traversée du désert." *Nouvelles Questions Féministes* 41 (2): 51–56.

Fassa, Farinaz, Helene Fueger, Nadia Lamamra, Martine Chaponnière, and Edmée Ollagnier. 2010. "Éducation et formation : enjeux de genre." *Nouvelles Questions Féministes* 29 (2): 4–16. <https://doi.org/10.3917/nqf.292.0004>.

Froidevaux-Metterie, Camille. 2018. *Le corps des femmes: La bataille de l'intime*. Paris: Philosophie Magazine Ed.

Hache, Emilie, ed. 2016. *Reclaim : Recueil de textes écoféministes*. Paris: Cambourakis.

Hare, Isabelle, and Aurélie Olivesi. 2021. "Analyser les cyberviolences au prisme du genre." *Questions de communication* 40 (2): 319–36. <https://doi.org/10.4000/questionsdecommunication.27108>.

Hertzog, Irène-Lucile, and Marie Mathieu. 2021. "Pour une analyse globale, internationale et interdisciplinaire du travail procréatif." *Enfances Familles Générations. Revue interdisciplinaire sur la famille contemporaine*, no. 38 (October). <https://journals.openedition.org/efg/12179>.

Idoiaga Mondragon, Nahia, Amaia Eiguren Munitis, and Maitane Belasko Txertudi. 2022. "The Breaking of Secrecy: Analysis of the Hashtag #MeTooIncest Regarding Testimonies of Sexual Incest Abuse in Childhood." *Child Abuse & Neglect* 123 (January): 105412. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2021.105412>.

Jacquemart, Alban. 2013. "L'engagement féministe des hommes, entre contestation et reproduction du genre." *Cahiers du Genre* 55 (2): 49–63. <https://doi.org/10.3917/cdge.055.0049>.

Jacquemart, Alban, and Camille Masclet. 2017. "Mixités et non-mixités dans les mouvements féministes des années 1968 en France." *Clio. Femmes, Genre, Histoire*, no. 46 (December): 221–47. <https://doi.org/10.4000/clio.13784>.

Jérome, Vanessa. 2019. "Violences sexuelles & ripostes partisanses." *Mouvements* 99 (3): 38–47. <https://doi.org/10.3917/mouv.099.0038>.

Jouan, Marlène, and Clémence Clos. 2020. "Le privé est politique... et économique ! Pour une économie politique du travail de gestation pour autrui." *Nouvelles Questions Féministes* 39 (2): 47–61. <https://doi.org/10.3917/nqf.392.0047>.

Jouët, Josiane, Katharina Niemeyer, and Bibia Pavard. 2017. "Faire des vagues. Les mobilisations féministes en ligne." *Réseaux* 201 (1): 21–57. <https://doi.org/10.3917/res.201.0019>.

Koechlin, Aurore. 2019. "L'auto-gynécologie : écoféminisme et intersectionnalité." *Travail, genre et sociétés* n° 42 (2): 109–26.

Kouchner, Camille. 2021. *La Familia grande*. Paris XIXe: SEUIL.

- Laufer, Jacqueline, and Marion Paoletti. 2015. "Quotas en tout genre ?" *Travail, genre et sociétés* 34 (2): 151–55. <https://doi.org/10.3917/tgs.034.0151>.
- Lavocat, Lorène, and Roxanne Gauthier. 2019. "Week-end féministe à Bure : « Le nucléaire est un monstre du patriarcat »." *Reporterre, le quotidien de l'écologie*, September 23, 2019. <https://reporterre.net/Week-end-feministe-a-Bure-Le-nucleaire-est-un-monstre-du-patriarcat>.
- Lépinard, É. (2015). *Praxis de l'intersectionnalité: Répertoires des pratiques féministes en France et au Canada*. *L'Homme & la Société*, 198(4), 149–170. <https://doi.org/10.3917/lhs.198.0149>
- Lépinard, É., & Mazouz, S. (2021). *Pour l'intersectionnalité*. Hors collection, 3–71.
- Lett, Didier, Sylvie Steinberg, Fabrice Virgili, and Camille Noûs. 2020. "Éditorial. Les violences sexuelles au cœur de l'intime." *Clio. Femmes, Genre, Histoire* 52 (2): 7–19. <https://doi.org/10.4000/clio.18646>.
- Lhote Fernandes, Sarah. 2022. "Égalité Femmes-Hommes : Grande Cause, Petit Bilan." Oxfam France / Equipop / CARE France.
- Loison, Marie, Gwenaëlle Perrier, and Camille Noûs. 2020. "Introduction. Le langage inclusif est politique : une spécificité française ?" *Cahiers du Genre* 69 (2): 5–29. <https://doi.org/10.3917/cdge.069.0005>.
- Marie, Catherine. 2020. "Condamner le féminicide sans le nommer." *Travail, genre et sociétés* 43 (1): 161–65. <https://doi.org/10.3917/tgs.043.0161>.
- Mathieu, Lilian. 2018. "L'enrôlement du féminisme dans la lutte contre la prostitution." *Cités* 73 (1): 57–66. <https://doi.org/10.3917/cite.073.0057>.
- Ndiaye, Chloé. 2022. "À La Villeneuve, un projet pour lever le tabou des règles et sensibiliser à la précarité menstruelle." *Les Cahiers du Développement Social Urbain* 76 (2): 21–21. <https://doi.org/10.3917/cdsu.076.0021>.
- Ouassak, Fatima. 2020. *La Puissance Des Mères. Pour Un Nouveau Sujet Révolutionnaire*. Paris: La Découverte. <https://livre.fnac.com/a14341411/Fatima-Ouassak-La-puissance-des-meres-POur-un-nouveau-sujet-revolutionnaire>.
- Paris, Collages Féminicides. 2021. *Notre colère sur vos murs*. Illustrated édition. Paris: DENOEL.
- Pavard, Bibia. 2012. *Si je veux, quand je veux. Contraception et avortement dans la société française (1956-1979)*. Rennes: PU RENNES.
- . 2017. "Les mobilisations féministes en France à l'ère d'internet : pour une approche sociohistorique." In *Féminismes du XXIe siècle : une troisième vague ?*, 161–73. *Archives du féminisme*. Rennes: Presses universitaires de Rennes. <https://doi.org/10.3917/pur.berges.2017.01.0161>.
- Pavard, Bibia, Florence Rochefort, and Michelle Zancarini-Fournel. 2020. *Ne nous libérez pas, on s'en charge*. *Sciences humaines*. Paris: La Découverte. <https://www.cairn.info/ne-nous-liberez-pas-on-s-en-charge--9782348055614-p-387.htm>.
- Perrot, Michelle. 2019. "Entretien." In *Cours petite fille !*, 25–28. *Essais*. Éditions des femmes. <https://www.cairn.info/cours-petite-fille--9782721006967-p-25.htm>.
- Quéré, Lucile. 2019. "Les formes ordinaires du consentement. Consciences du droit dans la consultation gynécologique." *Droit et société* 102 (2): 413–32. <https://doi.org/10.3917/drs1.102.0413>.
- . 2022. "Repousser les frontières des normes corporelles et sexuelles. Effets de l'engagement dans le self-help féministe sur la sphère intime." *Sociétés contemporaines* 126 (2): 93–119. <https://doi.org/10.3917/soco.126.0093>.
- Rauglaudre, Timothée de. 2018. "On a parlé tabou des règles avec des « activistes menstruelles »." *Vice (blog)*. December 4, 2018. <https://www.vice.com/fr/article/mby3db/on-a-parle-tabou-des-regles-avec-des-activistes-menstruelles>.

Ricordeau, Gwénola. 2019. *Pour elles toutes : Femmes contre la prison*. Montréal (Québec): LUX CANADA.

Rocheftort, Florence. 2017. "Politiques féministes du nom (France, xixe-xxie siècle)." *Clio. Femmes, Genre, Histoire*, no. 45 (May): 107–27. <https://doi.org/10.4000/clio.13523>.

Roman, Diane. 2020. "Quels mots pour penser et combattre les féminicides ?" *Travail, genre et sociétés* 43 (1): 167–71. <https://doi.org/10.3917/tgs.043.0167>.

Romerio, Alice. 2018. "Le travail féministe et le « problème musulman » au Planning familial." *Sociétés contemporaines* 110 (2): 61–88. <https://doi.org/10.3917/soco.110.0061>.

———. 2022. *Le travail féministe: Le militantisme au Planning familial à l'épreuve de sa professionnalisation*. Rennes: PU RENNES.

Rousseau, Sandrine. 2018. "Le milieu politique est-il plus propice que d'autres aux violences sexuelles ?" In *Violences sexistes et sexuelles en politique*, 17–20. *Débats*. Paris: CNRS Éditions. <https://doi.org/10.3917/cnrs.benba.2018.01.0017>.

———. 2019. "« #MeToo : le plus dur est à venir ou les forces et faiblesses du face-à-face »." In *Cours petite fille !*, 65–70. *Essais*. Éditions des femmes. <https://www.cairn.info/cours-petite-fille--9782721006967-p-65.htm>.

Ruault, Lucile. 2016. "La circulation transnationale du self-help féministe : acte 2 des luttes pour l'avortement libre ?" *Critique internationale* N° 70 (1): 37–54.

———. 2021. "Histoires d'A et méthode K." *Sociétés contemporaines* 121 (1): 139–70.

Schantz, Clémence, Virginie Rozée, and Pascale Molinier. 2021. "Introduction. Les violences obstétricales, un nouvel axe de recherche pour les études de genre, un nouveau défi pour le soin et la société." *Cahiers du Genre* 71 (2): 5–24. <https://doi.org/10.3917/cdge.071.0005>.

Sénac, Réjane. 2019. "Féminismes et « convergence des luttes » au temps de la Covid-19 et de la cancel culture." *Diogène* 267–268 (3–4): 234–53. <https://doi.org/10.3917/dio.267.0234>.

Sinigaglia-Amadio, Sabrina. 2010. "Place et représentation des femmes dans les manuels scolaires en France : la persistance des stéréotypes sexistes." *Nouvelles Questions Féministes* 29 (2): 46–59. <https://doi.org/10.3917/nqf.292.0046>.

Stop Fisha. 2021. *Combattre le cybersexisme*. Edited by Laura Pereira Diogo, Shanley Clémot Maclaren, and Rachel-Flore Pardo. Illustrated édition. Paris: LEDUC.

Thiébaud, Élise. 2017. *Ceci est mon sang*. Paris: La Découverte.

Vergès, Françoise. 2019. *Un féminisme décolonial*. 1er édition. Paris: La Fabrique.

Viennot, Éliane, and Joëlle Wiels. 2019. "Être féministe en 2020 ou Comment faire face au succès ?" *Diogène* 267–268 (3–4): 9–27. <https://doi.org/10.3917/dio.267.0009>.

Weil, Armelle. 2017. "Vers un militantisme virtuel ? Pratiques et engagement féministe sur Internet." *Nouvelles Questions Féministes* 36 (2): 66–84. <https://doi.org/10.3917/nqf.362.0066>.

Zancarini-Fournel, Michelle. 2003. "Histoire(s) du MLAC (1973-1975)." *Clio. Femmes, Genre, Histoire*, no. 18 (November): 241–52. <https://doi.org/10.4000/clio.624>.

Zinn, Isabelle, Alix Heiniger, Marianne Modak, and Clothilde Palazzo-Crettol. 2021. "Mon corps nous appartient." *Nouvelles Questions Féministes* Vol. 40 (1): 8–16.

3 GREECE

3.1 Introduction

Research and activism on gender identities, equality and sexuality concur that the timespan 2010-2021 saw a remarkable and refreshing resurgence of feminist and LGBTQI+ theory and action after two decades of relative quiescence. Massive protests, on the streets, through mass media, on-line and in institutions, were staged to protest the vitriolic assault on a migrant trade-unionist woman in 2008 (Konstandina Kouneva) right before the beginning of this period, which were rehearsed and even intensified on the occasion of the public stigmatisation of HIV-positive women in 2012, the transphobic murder of Zack Kostopoulos in Athens in 2018, a series of femicides which received attention in mass media, starting with the murder of the young student Eleni Topaloudi in 2018, the Greek #MeToo which kicked off in 2021 and gained momentum in a short time, and the 8 of March women's strikes. In addition to protest, various forms of gender-related interventions framed a broader positive agenda which demanded institutional and legislative reforms but exceeded them, agitating for deeper transformations of heteronormative patriarchal gender stereotypes challenged from intersectional and queer perspectives.

As a result of three factors -movement pressure, EU and other international policy directives, progressive initiatives in the political system taken by left- and center-left parties-, the institutional framework to promote gender equality, to enshrine LGBTQI+ rights and to combat gender violence was considerably amplified during these years. Among others, a new extensive institutional apparatus to support women subject to sexual harassment and domestic violence was put in place. In 2015, under the new coalition government led by the left-wing SYRIZA party, the Greek state grants to same-gender couples the right to enter a civil partnership contract, while in 2017, under the same government, new legislation makes the free choice of gender legally possible and acknowledged. At the same time, as the above record of lethal incidents indicates, gender violence is perpetuated but gains enhanced visibility and is more dynamically addressed by movement action and institutional mechanisms.

Hence, persisting patriarchy and gender violence -including femicides, sexual harassment and homophobic/transphobic violence- are on the top of the feminist agenda. Moreover, as feminist agency during this time was situated in circumstances of a grave socio-economic and political crisis which beset Greece since 2010, issues of care and reproduction and the quest for more collaborative modalities of social reproduction became also prominent. However, the crisis led also to more collaborative and collective solutions, redefining the domestic division of roles. Self-organization and grassroots action for solidarity and refugees was also a field in which women played a leading role, assuming positions of political leadership and engaging in activist, even conflictual forms of solidarity (Kosyfologou 2018: 40-42).

Furthermore, LGBTQI+ rights, social freedom and recognition occupy more central space in these years. The 'refugee crisis' brought on by the massive influx of refugees from 2015 onwards was also a topic of feminist concern, while new issues become also thematized, namely the relationship between gender power relations, the body, technology and art. The 'third-wave' post-structuralist critique of 'woman' as a unified category and of the heteronormative canon, queer and post-colonial theory get also more widely diffused during these years in tackling all the foregoing issues.

A diverse chorus of actors intervene in this period to engage with all the items on the above agenda as well as the 'older' topics of equal participation in positions of institutional power. This ranges from the more bureaucratic and top-down state actors, crucially the General Secretariat for Gender Equality, and other institutional agencies which are more or less hierarchical and centralized -political party organisations, university centers and laboratories, NGOs, Social Cooperative Enterprises, formal

associations- to a wild multiplicity of autonomous feminist, gender, LGBTQI+ groups, journals and art spaces.

In existing research and publications, the analysis of the organizational models, the ideology, the internal composition and the networks of feminist actors in 2010-2021 is very limited. Based on what can be drawn from it, feminist movements during this decade include the more traditional hierarchical structures, ad hoc street and on-line mobilizations, and notably two new trends. First, collectives and groups which have an informal organizational structure, tend to be small-sized and they intervene on the local level and the Internet. Sometimes they network with each other, although there is no enduring confluence. These new feminist collectives differentiate themselves from more 'traditional' feminist organizations, they engage in autonomous-queer politics and they tend to produce an intersectional discourse. Their action consists often in organizing public events-discussions, in producing and disseminating publications, posters, leaflets, in mobilizations concerning body, gender identities, sexuality and gendered power relations. Second, women took part in the anti-austerity mobilizations since 2011 and later on in new collective initiatives in the social and solidarity economy (new cooperatives, social clinics, time banks, solidarity schools, refugee support groups etc.). In this field, women played a leading role, assuming positions of political leadership and engaging in activist, even conflictual forms of solidarity, while also infusing activism with a feminist culture of sharing, mutual care, collective decision-making.

The visibility and action of gay, lesbian and trans groups rises also during this time.

Regarding ideological and generational divisions, there are apparent divides between an older generation of feminist activists involved in institutional actors (formal associations, political party organizations) or grassroots leftist movements and groups from earlier decades, and the dispersed new autonomous and queer groups with off-line and on-line presence. The collective experience around the No Tolerance campaign revealed also a gap between a generation of women in their 30s and 40s who were politicized in the political struggles at the beginning of the crisis, and a younger generation of women in their 20s whose feminism is inspired from the English-speaking Internet world, gender studies and pop culture, and who were being politicized at a time of defeat from 2015 onwards, when the crisis was experienced as a threat of dispossession in all fields of personal and social life, from the body to employment. Hence, younger women activists were driven by feelings of anger and rage, they challenge the traditional leaderships of the left, social movements and organizations, and they search for other instruments of intervention.

Finally, another important trend concerning feminist agency at the time involves feminist collectives which merge activism with theory. More specifically, from the beginning of this period, there is a tighter interaction and imbrication between gender and sexuality movements, on the one hand, and the Greek academia, research and gender studies hosted in universities and graduate programs. In parallel, there is a greater confluence between feminist and LGBTQI+ actors as the former tend to incorporate the latter in their discourse and struggles. However, there are still considerable differences in the respective fields of action, the demands and critical issues such as sex work, while certain feminist groups hold on to their female -rather than gender, constructed, queer etc.- identity.

In the secondary literature on feminist and LGBTI+ politics -academic publications and 'grey literature'- in the period of reference there is a lack of comprehensive, systematic and in-depth accounts of the internal composition and structure of the relevant actors in their variety and totality, their interconnections, their specific impact on policy outcomes, their connection with institutions, their intersection with other movements, their ideologies, frames of analysis and repertoires of action. In the following discussion of themes, agendas, campaigns and repertoires of action, the division of analysis according to the five axes (1) labor market, (2) health & reproductive rights, (3) migration, (4) LGBTQ+ rights and (5) gender-based violence is often difficult not only due to these gaps in the

literature but also due to the tight intertwinement of the foregoing axes in practice, which was further enhanced by the emphasis of feminist actors on intersectionality. The ensuing literature review reflects thus the state of existing research of feminist and LGBTQI+ politics in 2010-2021, its gaps and its foci of attention. Certain of these gaps, particularly those concerning the actors, were filled by first-hand research which is due to be conducted more systematically in the next phases of the research project.

The history of the feminist movements and its context

3.2 Greek feminism before 2010

At the end of the '80s, gender issues, inequality and male domination in its various guises had been made visible, they had been politicized and contested in multiple social practices. Equality laws informed and reshaped the national legal culture, unsettling the nation's deeply ingrained patriarchy. The law reforms of the '80s remain the most creative and significant to-date, making up for decades of inaction and retards in the institutional enactment of gender equality. However, these advances remain also vulnerable and under constant threat from public interventions and contrary political priorities. For a significant sector of the population, discrimination against women is still invisible and 'natural,' while several gender hierarchies are sustained. Sexism is still a dominant social and ideological norm, reproducing gender violence, wage differences etc. In the era of 'Metapolitefsi' feminist politics obtained the institutional fulfilment of certain core demands for equality in law, the abolition of dowry and men's 'family patronage,' the decriminalization of abortion, legal protection against rape. But this also blunted feminism's critical edges and subsumed it under a framework of 'modernization from above.' The incorporation of feminist actors in leftist parties and the 'appropriation' of feminist politics and discourse by the ruling social-democratic party of ΠΑΣΟΚ in the '80s generated a divide between institutional and autonomous feminism (Athanasidou 2017: 21, Karapanou 2017: 99, Pantelidou-Malouta 2017: 42-43, Stratigaki 2017: 115, 119, Vougiouka et al. 2022: 40, Kanaveli 2016: 14).

In the '90s, the fervent feminist agitation of previous years is on the wane. Several autonomous feminist groups and publications vanish, public activity and protests decline, and feminists probe the causes of this 'crisis' of the feminist movement. The dominant hype consumerism of the '90s re-naturalizes women's body, aesthetics and gender roles. At the same time, EU initiatives, campaigns and directives, to which national legislation and policies must be adjusted, institutional national associations (such as the Political Women's League), international networks and the introduction of gender and equality academic programs at universities become now key nodes and vehicles of feminist intervention. This decade did not see any notable legislative intervention. But it marked the beginning of the funding schemes of ΕΣΠΑ [Partnership Agreement for the Development Framework] with the significant contribution of the European Structural and Investment Funds (ESIF) of the European Union. These funding and policy programs promoted gender equality policies, such as the inclusion of women in male-dominated professions and the expansion of nurseries to facilitate women's entry in the labour market (Karapanou 2017: 99, Karamanou 2021: 301, 319-320, Sklaveniti 2017: 79, Stratigaki 2017: 117, Gazi 2017: 85, Kanaveli 2016: 14).

Until the end of this decade, the absence of a gay and lesbian public discourse is still notable. In the ranks of the three main gay organizations which are active at that time, one in Athens and two in Greece, there were very few women. Lesbian women and couples have hardly any public presence in this 'silent' decade. This is, however, a time of transition which prepares the ground for the new trends, ideas and mobilizations which would spread in the new millennium: the formation of lesbian, gay, trans and queer groupings, the organization of Athens Pride which is held annually since 2005 with an independent lesbian presence, new journals and books, cinema, theatre and art events, internet sites and blogs. The resurgence of the gay and lesbian movement in Greece is marked by the arrest of eleven

homosexual men in a gay bar in 2003. Thereafter, the first formally recognized and incorporated organization was established, the «Ομοφυλοφιλική και Λεσβιακή Κοινότητα Ελλάδας» [ΟΛΚΕ: Gay and Lesbian Community of Greece], while in the first Athens Gay Pride in 2005, gay and lesbian groups protested and paraded on the streets of Athens with their face uncovered, for the first time in such public events. The emergent 'LGBT' community acquires an increased public visibility in urban centers, mainly in Athens, although the majority does not participate in political LGBT groups. From 2007 onwards, ΟΛΚΕ campaigned for the legal recognition of gay marriage and civil partnerships. This politics of incorporation in the heteronormative Greek society is challenged by new queer groups, such as 'Queericulum Vitae,' which purport to unsettle heteronormativity as such and promote a wider range of modes of partnership and sexuality beyond heteronormative marriage and nuclear family (Kantsa 2012: 40-41, Giannakopoulos 2012: 186-193).

In the 2000s, an amendment of the constitution provides for positive discrimination action in favour of women and abolishes all exemptions from the principle of gender equality. New legislation criminalizes sexual harassment, human trafficking, domestic violence and domestic rape (in 2006). The state's General Secretariat of Gender Equality [Γενική Γραμματεία Ισότητας των Φύλων: ΓΓΙΦ] takes a leading role in the effort to implement EU directives against direct and indirect discrimination and sexual harassment (Karamanou 2021: 320, 327). Equality laws are extended now to different sexual orientations, quotas (1/3) are imposed in the local (municipal and regional) elections, while the ΕΣΠΑ funding schemes are used to advance gender studies and equality in education through teaching, research, actions to raise awareness and tackle existing inequalities (Stratigaki 2017: 118). Overall, in the period starting from the restoration of democracy (1975) till 2010, the most visible progress in gender equality was achieved in the modernization of legislation and the massive entry and academic success of women at all levels of education, outnumbering and outperforming men today in many academic fields, although some areas (Polytechnic and Natural Sciences schools) remain dominated by men (Karamanou 2021: 393-395, Thanos et al. 2022: 25-59).

Through the imbrication of academia, post-structuralist theory, research and feminist activism, and fuelled by the rise of the LGBTQI movement, gender politics in the 2000s displays a marked influence by third wave feminism, in which the identity of 'women,' gender identities and sexuality are seen and experienced as plural, relatively fluid, intersecting with race, class, ethnicity and ability, ambiguous and queer (Kanaveli 2016: 15). This is the decade in which major theoretical works on the social construction of the body, gender and sexuality, defined by power relations and informing broader social norms and structures, are published and start making an impact on both gender studies and activism. Such publications include the Greek translations of the works of Judith Butler (2008, 2009), of T. Laqueur (2003), and the collections of essays on feminism, body, gender and sexuality considered from a poststructuralist angle which were edited by Makrynioti (2004), Michailidou & Chalkia (2005), Athanasiou (2006).

The end of this period was marked by a tragic event which set the stage for revamped feminist mobilizations in the next decade: the assault on Konstantina Kouneva, an immigrant from Bulgaria, trade unionist and secretary of the Greek Trade Union of Cleaners and Housekeepers at that time, who would be eventually elected MEP in the 2014 European Parliament elections as a candidate of the left-wing party SYRIZA (Vovou 2020: 143-144).

Kouneva was working as a cleaner for a company providing services to the public urban train company, among others. On the night of 23 December 2008, and while on her way home from work, she was attacked by unknown actors with sulfuric acid which disfigured her face, ruined one of her eyes and heavily damaged her internal organs leaving her face horribly disfigured, and resulting in the loss of sight in one of her eyes. Kouneva had been repeatedly threatened on account of her activism. The eventual attack on her was arguably most severe assault on a trade unionist during the last 50 years in

Greece. The event sparked immediately protests by feminist actors and more widely by leftist and anarchist groups, trade unionist etc. under the banner 'Konstandina, you're not alone.' Public protests lasted until the end of January, numbering up to 3000 people. In January 2009, the Committee of Solidarity to Konstantina Kouneva was set up by feminist and other activists who were engaged at that time in the Greek Social Forum. This Committee highlighted the vulnerability and precarity of women workers, particularly immigrants, noting how employers' violence targets particularly 'intransigent' women. Another Feminist Initiative of Solidarity to Konstantina Kouneva, made up of women who were active in various feminist and other political organizations, voiced its solidarity to women working in the cleaners' trade union, took care of Kouneva's child, mobilized in the 8 March demonstration devoted to Kouneva and workers's rights, and organized a huge concert to raise money for Kouneva. The feminist mobilizations in this case foregrounded the intersection of gender, class and immigration and took issue with the marginalization of women in institutional trade unions, in which the number of women in positions of power is negligible (Vovou 2020: 149-153).

3.3 Feminism in Greece after 2010

The years 2010-2021 saw a notable revival and renewal of feminist agency. Along with institutional actors and the older feminist organizations, a new form of movement emerges which is composed of small radical groups dispersed across the country which critically inquire into gender and sexuality, highlighting gender power relations, and contesting them in practice (Gazi 2017: 86, Spanou 2017: 91, Kanaveli 2016: 4, 44, Vougiouka et al. 2022: 41). At the same time, formal 'state' feminism is still based on positions that were prominent in the '80s (Vougiouka et al. 2022: 41).

Moreover, from the beginning of this period, a new significant trend becomes noticeable, the encounter, tight interaction and intertwinement between gender and sexuality movements, on the one hand, and the Greek academia, research and gender studies hosted in universities and graduate programs (Apostolleli-Chalkia 2012: 13-18, Kanaveli 2016: 4, 9, 19-20).

This trend has been affirmed and enhanced throughout this period to-date. A late illustration and enactment of it is the establishment of the Κέντρο Νέων Μέσων και Φεμινιστικών Πρακτικών στον Δημόσιο Χώρο [Centre of New Media and Feminist Practices in Public Space] which started as a post-doctoral research project, it is based at the University of Thessaly (in the city of Volos in Central Greece) and its programmatic intent is to systematically bridge academic research, cultural, art practice and education (Karampa & Lykourioti 2021: 13-14).

In this period, there is a greater convergence between feminist and LGBTQI+ actors as the former tend to incorporate the latter in their discourse and struggles. However, there is still considerable divergence in the respective fields of action, the demands and critical issues such as sex work, while certain feminist groups hold on to their female -rather than gender, constructed, queer etc.- identity (Vougiouka et al. 2022: 43).

Feministic politics during these years unfolded in the dire circumstances of the socio-economic downturn and the political crisis which has affected Greece from 2010 onwards. The dismantling of public services, the shrinking of the welfare state, higher unemployment, indebtedness and precarity afflicted women disproportionately as employees and users of social services for themselves and their families. The crisis reduced gender inequalities in employment and employment in favour of women, but this occurred through a grave socio-economic regression through which wages and employment conditions deteriorated considerably for both men and women. Women's rate of employment became among the lowest in the EU, early retirement resulted in lower pensions for women, who were forced to take over increased care work for elders, children, disabled and ill relatives. Insecurity caused by unemployment and poverty challenges established masculinities constructed around work. The ensuing crisis of aggressive masculinity brought about a rigidification of gender hierarchies, deeper

conservatism and a further normalization of sexism (Vaiou 2021: 185-187, Karamesini 2015: 239-278).

The general social dislocation under the austerity regime generated thus also a broader 'gender trouble' in the sense that that traditional gendered division of labour proved to be inadequate. One could assume that the destabilization of dominant identities gave rise to gender violence manifested and legitimized by its agents as a performance of masculinity in an endangered patriarchal context, while the increased need for providing care within the household stepped up pressure on women. However, it led also to more collaborative and collective solutions, redefining the domestic division of roles. Self-organization and grassroots action for solidarity and refugees was also a field in which women played a leading role, assuming positions of political leadership and engaging in activist, even conflictual forms of solidarity (Kosyfologou 2018: 40-42).

A major event which triggered intense feminist agitation at the outset of this period was the arrest and public stigmatization of HIV-positive women who were drug addicts and worked reputedly as prostitutes in 2012. What can be described as the worst violation of human rights in Greece in recent years was in effect a new witch hunt targeting vulnerable women (Vovou 2020: 201). Police arrested more than 2000 women from prostitution houses and the streets. They forcibly tested for HIV by the Hellenic Center of Disease Control and Prevention (HCDCP), which detected HIV-positive sex workers. 32 HIV-positive women were imprisoned in April 2012, and their identities, photos and personal health condition were publicly disclosed by order of the attorney of the Athens First Instance Court with a view to 'protecting the community from contagious diseases.' The personal data of HIV-positive women have been published in newspapers, the media, social media and the Internet, in a major violation of the right to protect personal data enshrined in the Greek Constitution in Art 9.1 (Pitsou 2015). These women, including seven migrants, were prosecuted, stigmatized and publicly denounced as a 'hygienic bomb.' A big wave of solidarity was set off by feminist groups such as the Feminist Initiative for the Elimination of Violence against Women, human rights organizations, leftist political groups and parties etc. (Vovou 2020: 201-211). In June 2012, twenty-four of these women were still imprisoned in a main detention center in Athens under horrible conditions. Their release started after the first trial in January 2013 which established their innocence and was completed in March 2013. At least seven of the stigmatized women died of overdose, by committing suicide etc. (Vovou 2020: 245-249).

Since 2017-2018 women took part in the international #MeToo movement, which in Greece unfolded mainly on the Internet and mass media from 2021 onwards, in other national protests against sexual harassment and gender-based violence. Finally, the 8th of March women's strikes, which brought contemporary feminism again on the streets, sought to connect it with other modes of bottom-up organization (Spanou 2017: 90-91, Karamanou 2021: 367-370).

In regard to gender-based violence, femicides were brought into the public spotlight through feminist campaigns, internet and the press, including the emblematic tragic cases of Eleni Topaloudi in Rhodes, in November 2018, and Suzanne Eaton in Crete, in July 2019, who were raped and killed by macho men on the two islands. Although the Greek police force does not register femicides as a separate category of crime, its statistics establish that at least 106 women were killed as a result of domestic violence in 2010-2019. Other available data collected by feminist websites indicate that 41 femicides occurred in 2018-2020, killing mostly women at the age of 49-50 motivated frequently by feelings of misogyny, envy, possessiveness and the desire to exercise control over women to the point of their physical elimination. Researchers note that in Greece, the dominant pattern of femicide is murder by a close relative/love partner (Kontochristou 2021: 216-225, Petraki 2020: 11-12, 24-27, Gasouka 2020: 58, Vougiouka 2020: 79, 84, Kapsampeli 2019).

Another major incident of murderous gender violence which sparked a wide-ranging mobilization, marking perhaps a pronounced 'queer' turn in recent gender equality movements in Greece, occurred on Friday 21st of September 2018, when a person was brutally hit by the owner of a jewellery shop close to Omonoia square, at the center of Athens. Further brutalized by police and by-standers, Zacharias Kwstopoulos, also known as Zackie Oh, his drag alter ego, was murdered and was already dead when eventually carried to hospital. Zach was queer, HIV-positive, LGBTQI+ activist and artist. His murder triggered multifarious action on the streets, the police headquarters in Athens, squats, bars, open public spaces, anti-racist events and drag shows for more than two years (Athanasidou & Papanikolaou 2020: 9-11).

3.4 Actors, organizations and organizational models

3.4.1 List of actors

See appendix

3.4.2 Organizational models, ideology, internal composition, networks

In the secondary literature (academic books, edited volumes, peer-reviewed journals, dissertations, and in 'grey literature'- NGO reports etc.) there is scant information and discussion of the organizational models, the ideology, the internal composition and the networks of feminist actors in 2010-2021. The little information and analysis which is available can be summarized as follows.

The new feminist movement which takes shape in 2010 onwards includes characteristically collectives and groupings which have an informal organizational structure, they are not particularly massive, and they seek to challenge institutional power by foregrounding questions of equality and gender issues. They tend to use 'alternative means' to reach their audience, aiming at a more massive outreach and seeking to disseminate their agenda by engaging in activism through public protests, demonstrations and conflicts. Hence, they keep up the radical feminist fight to challenge the established division of social space into public and private (Kanaveli 2016: 8-9).

A number of new feminist collectives were formed in the aftermath of the major anti-austerity movements in 2011-2012 -the Greek 'square movements- in an attempt to nurture a feminist angle that was lacking in these movements. Such groups were often loose companies of women with variable degrees of experience in feminist struggles who decided to set up on-line journal to publish original or translated articles and news about feminist demands and the situation of women in Greece and abroad (Spanou 2017: 87-8). In contrast to the more militant or conventional political style of the older organizations, these groups became a source of collective joy and hope, building bonds of care, love and comradeship among their members. Their original hope and aspiration were animated by the broader social affects and 'utopianism' of this 'period of hope' (2011-2015) and were further nourished by the international rebirth of feminist mobilization. But they were gradually disillusioned and curbed by the widespread feeling of defeat besetting the anti-austerity movements from 2015 onwards (Spanou 2017: 88-89).

This type of feminist groups is more closely connected to new social movements. They can be short-lived or more durable, they intervene on the local level and the Internet, and sometimes they network with each other, although there is no enduring confluence which would collectively outline gender policies under the new social circumstances. The small feminist collectives differentiate themselves from more 'traditional' feminist organizations, they engage in autonomous-queer politics and they tend to produce an intersectional discourse. Their action consists often in organizing public events-discussions, in producing and disseminating publications, posters, leaflets, in mobilizations concerning body, gender, sexuality and gendered power relations, in ways which connect with the past but are also framed in contemporary terms (Gazi 2017: 86, Spanou 2017: 91, Kanaveli 2016: 4, 44, Vougiouka

et al. 2022: 41). At the same time, formal 'state' feminism is still based on positions that were prominent in the '80s (Vougiouka et al. 2022: 41).

The visibility and intervention of gay, lesbian and trans groups increases also during this time, while sexuality is wedded to broader projects of social emancipation. There is also a growing number of collectives, such as «Η πρίζα» [The Plug], which designate themselves as queer and are allied with autonomous/antiauthoritarian politics and groups. Films, such as Panos Koutra's *Strella*, in which a transwoman is the main actor (2009) and new spaces, such as the Athens Museum of Queer Arts (2016) enhance an activist and academic engagement with gender and sexuality from a queer perspective (Kanaveli 2016: 18-19).

The No Tolerance [Καμία Ανοχή] initiative in 2017 illustrates a new type of feminist activism and agenda marking the years from 2017 onwards. It arose in response to an open call made by a feminist grouping set up in 2012 -Fylosykis- (Fylosykis.gr) which protested against the tragic incident of an underage girl residing in the city of Larissa, in central Greece, who was forced into prostitution by a family relative. What propelled this initiative was the sentiment that feminist self-organizing was flourishing, but there was no central and dynamic intervention which could face up to the ever-harsher everyday reality of the Greek crisis (Spanou 2017: 91-92). The collective experience around the No Tolerance campaign revealed a considerable divide between a generation of women in their 30s and 40s who were politicized in the political struggles at the onset of the crisis, and a younger generation of women in their 20s who have taken their lead in feminism from the English-speaking Internet world, gender studies and pop culture, and were being politicized at a time of defeat when the social democratic negotiation against austerity had failed, and the crisis was experienced as a threat of dispossession in all fields of personal and social life, from the body to employment. As a result, violence in its most varied forms rose to prominence as a core issue of the agenda of this protest. Hence, younger women activists are driven by feelings of anger and rage, they are uncompromising in their feminist insurrection, they challenge the traditional leaderships of the left, social movements and organizations, and they search for other instruments of intervention (Spanou 2017: 92-4).

Another important trend concerning feminist agency at the time involves feminist collectives which merge activism with theory. Among them, Φεμινιστικά, edited by a group of established feminist academics and activists, pursues a feminist politics which exceeds the dualism theory/practice and continuously deconstructs it. Such a feminism constitutes another collective response to the 'critical condition' of the 10s -the neoliberal exacerbation of inequalities, the spread of racist and neofascist violence et-, foregrounding the interaction between vulnerability and possibility, between heteropatriarchal and racist violence and multiple collective or individual resistances. They are committed to the critical dialogue between feminism and queer in theory, art, subjectivities, affects, bodies and cultural practices. They aim at complex feminist/queer/antiracist interventions which undo the preconceptions of the dominant subject as white, national, bourgeois, male, full-bodied and heteronormative (feministika 2018: 4-5)

From the end of this decade onwards, the Center of New Media and Feminist Public Practices further pursues the work of translating international theory into Greek in order to deepen their understanding of our globalized condition and the possibilities of feminist discourse and practice. Its research explores the impact of new technologies on 'thanatopolitics,' surveillance practices and the commodification of bodies, among others. A main objective of the Center is to deploy a technoaesthetic feminist theory and practice to organize dynamic spaces of intervention and a range of safe spaces in order to shape the future in militant ways (Karampa & Lykourioti 2021: 15-21).

3.4.3 Allies

Since Metapolitefsi to date, the main political ally of the feminist and the LGBTQI movement in Greece is the political left, both the institutional and the non-parliamentary far-left. On the part of the movements, this confluence was experienced as a necessity, rather than an ideological identification, given the predominance of a patriarchal national narrative, the rule of conservative right-wing or authoritarian governments after the war till the '80s and the adoption by the Greek left of a civil rights and liberties agenda. The left exercises thus a hegemony over progressive social movements and radicalism, which impedes the right from championing a gender rights agenda and discourse. In relation to LGBTQI rights and politics, more specifically, the left was reluctant to actively support them. The same holds true for the contemporary parliamentary left and the coalition government in 2015-2019 led by the left party of SYRIZA. The reasons may lie in the attachment to class identities and narratives and in social conservatism (Vougioukou et al. 2022: 43- 47).

Historically, however, the Left enacted a masculine model of organisation that effectively downplayed gender issues, although there are significant women's efforts for emancipation and trade-union organizing (Gaitanou 2017). Kyriakidou (2010), for example, highlights the efforts of leftist feminists to fight sexism within left parties and associations focusing on the case of the Coalition of the Radical Left and Progress (Syriza).

With regard to the labor unions, there have been few expressions of solidarity with women's struggles, in the last fifteen years, for example when the activist and trade-union organized Konstandina Kouneva was attacked with vitriolic acid, most notably by the General Federation of Greek Workers (GSEE) and the Workers' Centre of Athens (EKA). Both condemned the attack, presenting Kouneva in their official statements as a 'tragic victim of violence.' They failed to acknowledge gender as a factor determining power relations in this sector (Kampouri & Zavos 2010).

Regarding the intersections with other movements, Gaitanou (2017) highlights the connection of the discourse on gender with alternative practices that emerged in the refugee movement in Greece. For example, the hotel squat 'Refugee Accommodation and Solidarity Space City Plaza' run from 2016 to 2019, contesting several gender norms. The squat actively contributed to women's autonomy by promoting women to decision making positions within the self-organised hotel squat as well as respecting differences of all kinds, challenging any logic of 'emancipation from the outside' (Gaitanou 2017).

In addition, in 2012, the residents of Ierissos in Halkidiki, Northern Greece, protested against the mining activities of the multinational company 'El Dorado.' Several protests were held in the region as well as in Athens and Thessaloniki, gathering thousands of people. The most notable was the one held in Thessaloniki in March 2013 (an estimated 15,000 people gathered at the Canadian consulate to protest against the mining operations; (Daskalaki & Fotaki 2017). The resistance movement itself was initiated by women. The movement had an online presence through the site 'SOS Halkidiki.' They used their bodies to demonstrate the destructive impact of mining on the environment and their communities, as they are often the first to experience the social and health impact of extractivism (Fotaki & Daskalaki, 2021, Sjöstedt & Fotaki, 2018). As highlighted by Daskalaki & Fotaki (2017: 13)

Bodies, thus, are used during neoliberal crisis and austerity politics to contest patriarchal erasures and to build the conditions, within broader activist movements, through which women can communicate their experiences, and develop a praxis that opens spaces for affectivity and embodied re-articulation of socio-spatial relationships.

The discourse of the 'SOS Halkidiki' movement opened a 'window of opportunity' for women to go beyond their personal concerns, transforming their activities into a struggle for the common good and situating their action in the broader debate over the nature and direction of 'development' in their

country (Sjöstedt & Fotaki 2018). Daskalaki & Fotaki (2021) mention that these women became part of another resistance movement fighting against water privatization in Greece.

Finally, when it comes to civil society, there incidents of broader participation in feminist mobilizations and initiatives. For instance, on Women's Day in 2021, hundreds of people that did not belong to any feminist organisation supported protestors, advocating for other matters as well.

3.5 Themes and agendas

3.5.1 Participation in institutional centers of decision-making

In the EIGE Gender Equality Index, Greece ranks last among all EU countries, scoring 53.4 (a score of 100 implying full gender equality)²². According to its 2021 analysis of data drawn mostly from 2020, persistent gender inequalities are dramatic compared to other EU countries:

Gender inequalities are strongly pronounced in the domain of power in which Greece scores 28.8 points and ranks second to last. The most room for improvement is in the sub-domains of social (25.0 points) and economic (26.4 points) decision-making, in which the country ranks 26th and 22nd, respectively...

Since 2019, Greece's score has decreased the most in the domain of money (-0.9 points), dropping from the 20th to the 23rd place. This setback is due to increasing gender inequality in the sub-domains of financial resources (-1.0 points) and economic situation (-0.6 points).

Greece's score is the highest (85.8 points) in the domain of health, where the country ranks 17th in the EU.

Since 2010, Greece's score has improved the most in the domain of time (+9.1 points). This is mainly due to improvements in the sub-domain of care activities (+16.7 points). Greece has also slightly increased its score in the sub-domain of social activities (+2.2 points). Despite this progress, Greece's ranking in the domain of time has remained consistently low among all Member States, standing at the 26th place.

Hence, participation in institutional centers of decision-making remains a key concern and item on the feminist agenda for more institutional actors (Καραμάνου 2021, Στρατηγάκη 2017). In the last 2019 elections, women were still significantly underrepresented in political institutions. In the municipal elections, out of 332 elected mayors, only 19 were women (5,7%). In the European elections, out of 21 positions held by Greece, only 5 MEUPs were women (23,8%). In the national elections, 62 women were elected MPs out of the 300 positions (20,7% of the whole). Political parties and, most notably, trade unions remain traditional bastions of patriarchy, systematically excluding or marginalizing women and failing to observe gender equality norms in their decision-making processes (Καραμάνου 2021: 353-356, 396-397).

3.5.2 Gender-based violence

After the assault on Kouneva, Katerina Goulioni's death the following year in prison, related to her refusal to be subjected to vaginal examination, and the persecution of HIV-positive women in 2012 to 'protect the Greek pater familias' issues bearing on gender, body and sexuality in relation to nationality

²² <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-equality-index/2022/country/EL>, access 21/12/2022

rise to prominence on certain feminist agendas (Kanaveli 2016: 16). More specifically, gender-based violence in its most varied forms occupies center stage in feminist action.

Patriarchy is prevalent in Greek society, buttressed by hegemonic institutions, such as traditional family structures and the Greek Orthodox Church. As a consequence, sexual violence still goes often unrecognized, unspoken of and tolerated (Chroni & Kavoura 2022). For example, until 2006, the law did not recognize marital rape as a crime since sexual intercourse was traditionally considered a general obligation of marriage (Poteyeva & Wasileski 2016). Although both men and women are victims of gender-based violence, most victims in Greece are women (Lathiotaki, Koutra, Ratsika & Saint Arnault 2021). Specifically in Greece, according to the 1st Annual Report on Violence Against Women (2019–2020) issued in November 2020 by the GSFPGE, 4872 women asked for help from counselling centers in Greece, the majority of whom (84%) reported domestic violence from a spouse or partner (Lathiotaki et al. 2021).

During the COVID-19 pandemic, and particularly during the lockdowns, there was a significant rise in the reported cases of domestic violence. The GSFPGE acknowledged that restrictions of movement, while minimising the spread of the virus resulted in increased reports of domestic violence, including more severe cases and involving women and children trapped in their homes with violent partners or husbands (Healy, Levell & Cole 2022).

The No Tolerance campaign is a characteristic mobilization of this period against gender-based violence. Violence is felt as a constant, pervasive reality for women on all levels, fomenting a type of normative fear and anxiety. Their slogans voice these feelings of generalized violence and fear: 'Justice means not to be afraid -on the street, in work, home, in company,' 'Violence is to be forced to go back home with your parents and to paternal authority because you are unemployed' (Spanou 2017: 92-3). In the 25 November call for a march, violence is defined thus:

The double exploitation and control over our bodies by bosses -yes, lower wages are violence, flexible employment relations which we are the first to experience are violence, pregnancy treated as a threat and a ground for being laid off is violence, the incidents of sexual harassment combined with the blackmail that you will be fired if you react are violence (Spanou 2017: 93-94).

Hence, for younger women activists, violence, seen from a gendered perspective which is based on personal experience and affect, becomes a tool to make sense of the everyday reality of crisis which can bring together and construct subjectivities (Spanou 2017: 94).

3.5.3 LGBTQI+ rights

Moreover, LGBTQI+ sexuality and gender become key themes of discourse and action. This is an outcome of different factors, including the development of under- and post-graduate programs in gender studies, new publications on body and sexuality, which are read and drawn upon by activist groups, publications, poster, webpages and public events produced by activists which reclaim rights, public space and visibility. Theory informs activist publications on gender and sexuality, and explicit dialogue and interaction take place in workshops such as the one organized by Athens Pride at Panteion University, and other events where researchers and academics are invited to speak on the topics of body and gender to a wider audience (Kanaveli 2016: 18-20).

Activists, researchers and academics explore the common ground of the politics and the theory of gender and sexuality, aspiring to a new 'mapping of the political,' new modes of action, knowledge production and subjectivation drawing on forms of otherness which are often defined within neoliberal contexts but also escape and challenge them. Internet fragments, interviews, ethnographies, theoretical and activist texts, workshops and research projects make up a rich mosaic which foster critical understanding and movement action for social justice beyond heteronormativity, blurring the

boundaries between the two. This marked new tendency in gender and sexuality movements in Greece is tellingly illustrated by the 2009 workshop 'Sexuality and Genders: Lesbian, Gay, Bi, Trans and Queer communities in Greece,' which was held at Panteion University, Athens, organized by Athens Pride. A first major collection of 'native' texts on these topics was published in 2012, presenting the interventions in this workshop and displaying the growing osmosis between movement and scientific discourse which was rarefied in earlier periods (Apostolleli & Chalkia 2012: 13-18).

Regarding LGBTQI+ rights, more specifically, during the past decade Greece has made important advances. Significant milestones include the reform of hate-speech and hate crime legislation, as well as of anti-discrimination laws in the workplace which were passed in 2005. Reforms considered now other spheres such as gender identity, sexual orientation, and sex characteristics. The most radical reform includes the Law 4356/2015 known as the 'cohabitation pact' legalizing civil unions for same-sex couples (Remoundou 2022).

In 2008, an amendment to the Family Code, gave to couples the right to sign a cohabitation or 'civil partnership' contract. This excluded, however, same-sex couples. This issue rose to the top of the agenda of Local LGBTQI+ organizations and especially OLKE, which embarked on a passionate campaign in support of civil same sex marriage before the passage of the 2008 bill (Kantsa 2014).

A struggle for the recognition of same-sex marriage by the law was started until the law was amended in 2015²³.

3.5.4 Labor market

Greece was severely affected in multiple ways by the global financial crisis in 2008. The Greek economic and financial crisis has evolved into a social and political crisis undermining legitimacy of the political regime of 'Metapolitefsi' established in the 1970s (Gaitanou 2018, Antennas & Viva 2014). During the past decade, the country faced an enormous financial debt, a very high unemployment rate, reduced output and the collapse of social protection and the welfare state (Kouki & Chatzidakis 2020, Gaitanou 2018, Daskalaki, Fotaki & Sotiropoulou 2018).

In Greece, although the crisis produced new forms of resilience in households and families that often challenge traditional masculine and feminine identities, women are usually occupied in less skilled and precarious jobs, are paid less than men, experience higher unemployment rates and still bear the burden of unpaid domestic work (EIGE 2022).

Since 2010, following the austerity measures imposed by IMF-EU-ECB 'Troika', several citizens in Greece engaged in 'anti-austerity' movements calling for direct democracy (Arampatzi, Kouki & Pettas 2022, Kouki & Chatzidakis 2020). However, as Gaitanou (2017: 247) points out, women's issues were not addressed by these movements, and they were even considered 'superfluous or a luxury at a time of crisis.' There is only one reference to a feminist and queer collectivity called 'Purple Bench' -a gender group at the Syntagma square encampment and mobilization in the summer of 2011- which articulated a feminist critique of an idealized ancient Greek democracy alerting people to the patriarchal and

²³see Carastathis 2019 on the 10th Athens Pride festival and the event organized on the 14th of June at Klafthmonos Square to protest discrimination in the family code and the exclusion of same gender partners from civil partnerships and marriage. Carastathis problematizes the use of 'racism by the Greek LGBTQI+ movements as an umbrella term for other forms of discrimination such as homophobia.'

exclusionary nature of the classical Athenian polis which did not enfranchise women, foreigners, and slaves (Athanasίου 2014: 3).

In addition, Athanasίου (2014: 4) points out that ‘in response to the crisis, a range of LGBTQ activisms in Athens and other cities in Greece contested the commonsensical presumption that homophobia is a secondary issue and that the struggle against it is a distraction from the truly political anti austerity agenda.’

Austerity measures and the overall neoliberal policies implemented in Greece during the crisis have created space for rapid growth and development of new grassroots community initiatives and networks as alternatives to capitalist models of growth-based development (Daskalaki et al 2018, Daskalaki & Kokkinidis 2017). These new initiatives emerged in Athens over the past decade—although not explicitly articulated as feminist and without adopting ‘typical’ feminist agendas—foregrounded women’s collective knowledge, skills, and experiences as a grassroots response to the devastating effects of a prolonged crisis, opening up new territory for women’s participation and the dissemination of feminist political principles and emancipatory practices (Kouki & Chatzidakis 2020). Fotaki & Daskalaki (2017: 11) argue that these ‘solidarity initiatives operate like networks that bring together various alternatives movements and affect resistance spaces where new subjectivities can emerge.’

However, while nurturing a more implicit feminist solidarity culture, it can be argued that the social movements of the Greek crisis in many other ways or moments failed to fully reflect on or subvert latent gender norms and divisions of labor (Kouki & Chatzidakis 2020).

Finally, protests against market-oriented policies were triggered by two major incidents of feminist mobilization at the beginning of this period, the attack with vitriolic acid on Konstantina Kouneva, a Bulgarian migrant woman who was working as a cleaner for the public transportation system of Athens, and the persecution of HIV-positive women in 2012 (Athanasίου 2014, Carastathis 2015).

3.5.5 Migration

The ‘refugee crisis’

Since 2015, Greece experienced the so-called ‘refugee crisis,’ becoming the ‘hotspot of Europe’ (Carastathis, Spathopoulou & Tsilimpounidi 2018). Due to its position as the ‘gateway’ to Europe, Greece has been assigned the role of managing ‘mixed migration flows’ to Europe in the eastern Mediterranean (Carastathis 2018). Hotspots were established in Greece on the islands of Lesbos, Chios, Samos, Leros, and Kos. According to the ‘European Agenda of Migration,’ they were conceived as registration and identification centres that would administer and facilitate the relocation of refugees in all EU member states in line with their admission quotas and needs (Carastathis 2018, Carastathis et al. 2018).

Migrants and refugees were instrumentalized in anti-austerity discourse by the xenophobic right and the radical parliamentary right (Carastathis 2018). As Carastathis, (2015) points out, the influx of migration was managed through violent means by the state and the para-state. Moreover, after the EU-Turkey deal of 2016, Greece became an area of transit and thereafter a space of detainment. Hotspots, for example, have taken another function beyond detention, such as the redistribution of those classified as asylum claimants or refugees in the Greek territory and beyond, the ‘relocation’ of those granted refugee status to ‘Europe,’ as well as the criminalization and deportation of ‘economic migrants’ back to the ‘safe third country’ of Turkey.

In Greece, the rhetoric of solidarity with refugees was shared by grassroots and parliamentary sympathizers (Carastathis 2018), a broad-based, international solidarity movement with refugees arose at that time (Carastathis 2019). In this context, grandmothers who were internally displaced

during the German occupation, on the island of Lesbos and elsewhere, welcomed refugees in their homes in villages in the middle of nowhere.

The people engaging in various solidarity initiatives were mainly small groups and individuals acting out their political beliefs and civic commitments. Their political forms of solidarity included social supermarkets, cafes and health centres, as was the case during the financial crisis (Fotaki 2021).

3.5.6 Health and reproductive rights

In Greece abortion is legal, under the condition that the woman asks/fully agrees with it and it is under the supervision of a trained doctor.

Feminist mobilisations and a prominent social media movement emerged following the announcement of the organization of '1st Panhellenic Conference on Fertility and Reproductive Autonomy: Limits and Options,' which would take place on July 2-4, 2021 in Ioannina²⁴. For example, Mov, a feminist organization and on-line journal, called for actions and mobilizations on the occasion of 'the misogynistic preaching in the holy temples' against abortion²⁵. As a result of these mobilization the conference was cancelled.

In May 2012, at a time of government cuts to public health care and services, including those related to HIV prevention and care (Athanasίου 2014: 7), Greek authorities announced the arrest of seventeen HIV-positive women who allegedly worked illegally as sex workers.

As analysed by Athanasίου, (2014: 7), the female sex workers were constructed as a public health bomb, that is, as medicalized bodies to be monitored for the sake of the nation's sanitation and safety. Their names and photographs were published on the Greek police's website accompanied by scaremongering stories about the respectful Greek married family men who could have been infected.

The decision to publish these photographs fuelled a public outcry, especially among feminist and antiracist groups. The Feminist Initiative for the Elimination of Violence against Women condemned the discriminatory, humiliating, subhuman way in which these female sex workers were treated by state authorities. The public demonstrations spurred by this governmental action illustrated the crucial affinity between the market economy and a subjectivating economy of precarized bodies exercised through securitization and normalization as technologies of power (Athanasίου 2014).

3.6 Technology and art

Finally, a new trend in this period is the feminist concern with technology and art. A late illustration and enactment of it is the establishment of the Κέντρο Νέων Μέσων και Φεμινιστικών Πρακτικών στον Δημόσιο Χώρο [Centre of New Media and Feminist Practices in Public Space] which started as a post-doctoral research project, it is based at the University of Thessaly (in the city of Volos in Central Greece) and its programmatic intent is to systematically bridge academic research, cultural, art practice and education. The Center purports to study the relationship between art, feminism and technology, and to generate relevant discourse and art. It has already contributed to the creation of new works of art and original theory and methodology. It is also intent on diffusing a new pedagogy around these topics by organizing diverse educational events and interventions based on exchanges between formal and non-formal knowledge. In 2021 it published a major new collective volume on the intertwinements

²⁴ [Research 2020mag.gr: The 'Fertility Conference' was exactly what we thought and even more - 20/20 Magazine](#)

²⁵ [PURPLE: Call to protests in temples for the right to abortion | Efimerida ton Syntakton \(efsyn.gr\)](#)

between feminism, aesthetic practices and globalized technologies (Karampa & Lykourioti 2021: 13-14).

3.7 Repertoire of action

The repertoire of action employed by feminist and LGBTQI+ actors in this period consists in a plurality of public protests and marches around the foregoing topics, as well as in solidarity initiatives that responded to austerity measures and the 'refugee crisis' (Athanasίου 2014, Remoundou 2022, Gaitanou 2018). The overall aim was to provide direct support to people who were ill or homeless, who could not afford to buy food or clothes, or to pay the bills, rent, and children's education, and so on (Kouki & Chatzidakis 2020). Examples of emerging solidarity initiative during the crisis include (Kouki & Chatzidakis 2020):

- The Urban Social Clinic which started in 2011, providing free medical assistance and medicines to those excluded from the public health system such as the unemployed, the uninsured, the poor.
- The Babylon Solidarity School which started in 2013, providing additional tuition, including foreign language and music lessons, to more than 150 students per year.
- The Mazi Food Cooperative was organized locally from 2011 to 2014, and directly connected producers with consumers.
- Limani Solidarity run by 250 volunteers started as a collective kitchen and food bank and grew to include additional classes for students, a clothes bank, and a pro-refugee support group.

Overall, during this period there is a reconfiguration of the repertoire of actions of the Greek social movement, transitioning from street protests to spaces of social reproduction that involve implicit modes of feminist solidarity which emerged through praxis (Kouki & Chatzidakis 2020, Daskalaki et al. 2018). Most social movements of the Greek crisis became social reproductive movements, facilitating the transformation of the movements' solidarity culture both in terms of their organizational choices and of their collective frames of mobilization (Kouki & Chatzidakis 2020). Daskalaki et al (2018) points out that during the financial crisis groups formed initiatives to reject conventional bureaucratic practices, resist extreme neoliberal capitalist reforms and strive for social transformation.

Moreover, many feminist groups in the decade of reference use the digital world as a window to reach out to society in Greece and across borders as well. Hence, the Greek movement has been affected by international developments. A recent example is the #MeToo movement which, even though it started in 2006, became broadly known in 2017, starting in the USA. At the beginning of 2021, the movement arrived in Greece, with the Olympic champion Sofia Mpekatorou who reported an agent of the Hellenic Sailing Federation for sexual abuse in 1998. Many actresses and actors followed her lead. Social media play a pivotal role in the movement, informing Greek society of the ongoing developments. The Greek government announced the launch of the website metoogreece.gr to facilitate the report of abusive incidents. Furthermore, women's NGOs have started digital campaigns to raise awareness. An example is the NGO Diotima, running the campaign 'Don't skip,' to sensitise society about gender-based violence and sexist behaviour in everyday life. The digital world functions thus as a channel to achieve gender equality.

3.8 Frames of arguments

In the period of reference, patriarchy remains a key theme and target of feminist and LGBTQI+ discourse since patriarchal structures of gender inequality, violence, exclusion and oppression are deeply entrenched and remain largely in place despite the considerable legislative and institutional advances of previous decades and this same period, sustained by traditional forms of family, the Greek Orthodox Church, the new and old right and the far-right.

In addressing patriarchy from a feminist perspective, contemporary Greek feminism is infused with the 'third wave' critique of the subject of 'woman' and the 'feminine' as a unified, static, given and homogeneous category. In the light of queer and post-colonial/anti-colonial critique, gender identity is not seen as the stable signifier of an essentialist category, but as a battlefield for deconstruction and re-vindication. This is so because gender is held to be constructed in non-continuous and not fully coherent ways in different historical and cultural contexts, as well as because it intersects with diverse hierarchies bearing on race, class, ethnicity, sexuality, health, ability and geopolitical position. Hence, feminist critique today needs to be simultaneously a critique of colonial, racist and homophobic discourse. Present-day feminisms in Greece re-appropriate critically and creatively the experimentations, the self-organization and the political imagination of the feminist movements in 'Metapolitefsi.' But they also search for new forms of language and formulas in which 'equality' and 'emancipation' do not suffice to express the demands of our times and to face up to the renewed configurations of conservatism and fascism. They work out new coalition politics, transversal assemblages, transnational schemes of struggle and modes of intervention which challenge simultaneously sexism, racism, employment precarity, poverty, homophobia/transphobia and militarism. Certain of these quests were anticipated by the feminisms of the '70s and the '80s, while others are new and unheard-of. In this refigured politics of feminist agonism, theory occupies center stage. A type of theory which is a reflective, lived and embodied critical work and political praxis, which provides resources to encourage and inspire those who imagine a different future beyond the established regimes of legitimate violence (Athanasίου 2017: 29-32, Pantelidou-Malouta 2017: 44-49).

Regarding labor, health and reproductive rights, migration and LGBTQI+ we should note two key tendencies. First, the solidarity initiatives which arose during the economic and the refugee crisis from 2011 onwards. Raising questions of care and social reproduction in a concrete manner, they left their imprint on feminist discourse and practice (Gaitanou 2017). Their motto was 'no one should be left alone to face the crisis,' and their main tenet was that self-organization and participation were the only way to reclaim a better life in the present and in the future. The principal objective of these initiatives was to create spaces where the local community can search for survival paths, fostering also cultural expression and creativity. Hence, in the feminist discourses and practices which have re-entered dynamically public space and debate, issues of social reproduction and care in relation to the capitalist modes of production rise to prominence, opening up new perspectives on the relationship between the personal and the political (Gaitanou 2017).

In this context, we should attend to the influence of global mobilizations for an International Women's Strike, defending reproductive rights and opposing economic, institutional and interpersonal violence. These mobilizations brought again the concept of the political struggle to the surface and linked labour and women's demands and struggles, underscoring the need for radical, combative means and modes of struggle. Their influence can be traced in the call for a self-organised Pride in June 2017. The official institution of the Pride bears a strong institutional and corporate stamp, resulting in hesitant or even no support by certain forces of the LGBTQI+ movement (Gaitanou 2017).

The second tendency is the prominence of intersectionality and queer as main angles in tackling gender-based violence, labor, health and reproductive rights, LGBTQI+ and migration particularly in collectives and movements which bridge theory and activism (Carastathis 2019, feministiqa 2018).

This is characteristically the case of the journal *Φεμινιστικά*, edited by a group of established feminist academics and activists, which pursues a feminist politics that exceeds the dualism theory/practice and continuously deconstructs it. Such a feminism constitutes another collective response to the 'critical condition' of the '10s -the neoliberal exacerbation of inequalities, the spread of racist and neofascist violence et-, foregrounding the interaction between vulnerability and possibility, between heteropatriarchal and racist violence and multiple collective or individual resistances. Its practices of

resistance challenge the norms of combat and war as they oppose gender violence, sexism, homophobia/transphobia, patriarchy, racial and class inequalities. Their radical intersectional feminism is inspired by international actions which draw upon feminism but also take on different forms of discrimination and oppression, such as Black Lives Matter and BDS. It is a feminist perspective which contests current state and NGO policies that instrumentalize feminism, co-opting it for conservative agendas. They are committed to the critical dialogue between feminism and queer in theory, art, subjectivities, affects, bodies and cultural practices. They are interested in queer politics that unsettles the reification of identities after the models of Western capitalism. They aim at complex feminist/queer/antiracist interventions which undo the preconceptions of the dominant subject as white, national, bourgeois, male, full-bodied and heteronormative (feministika 2018: 4-5).

With regard to LGBTQI+ rights, two further themes stand out. First, as noted by Carastathis (2018) who interviewed members of the LGBTQI+ groups in Greece, the interference of the Orthodox Church in politics is considered a major obstacle to legislative and social change since the Church regularly instigates interpersonal and institutional violence. Second, nation and nationalism become a main target of critique and rejection or reconstruction. To illustrate, LGBTQI+ groups have disseminated the slogan (in graffiti in public spaces, including the pedestal of a statue of national independence hero Theodoros Kolokotronis at Stadiou Avenue in Athens) 'Lesbians/Faggots, Priestesses of Disgrace/We are proud to be the shame of the nation' («Λεσβίες/Πουστάρες, Ιέρειες του Αίσχρους/Είμαστε περήφανα η ντροπή του έθνους»). Relatedly, in the case of the reportedly homophobic murder of the young student Vangelis Yiakoumakis, movement discourses denounced this as a 'murder by brave young/macho men' ['λεβέντες' in Greek] (Carastathis 2018: 215).

Furthermore, in the discourse of new feminist and LGBTQI+ groups in this period, the word experience (βίωμα in Greek), personal experience related to gender identities but also experiences from earlier actions and interventions, becomes the starting point and a point of convergence in the formation of groups and collective identities. Kyriakidou (2010: 217) highlights how feminist activists reclaim the notion of experience: 'the female public position and actions are oriented or derive from what they have experienced.' The female social experience of patriarchy combines embodied and lived subjective experience with women's collective consciousness.

Experiences are situated in a socio-political context and become subject to political elaborations, echoing thus the second wave motto 'the personal is political,' and are often read through theoretical lenses highlighting the plurality of identities and focussing on body, gender and sexuality beyond the heteronormative logic in ways which disclose affinities with third wave post-structuralist feminism. Hence, theoretical and activist discourses on gender become salient in the thought and the practice of new feminist and LGBTQI collectives. Moreover, there is an emphasis on 'creating space' for such collectives and interventions, reclaiming public space from male subjects. Issues raised by the second wave remain vital from feminist and LGBTQI action due to the fact that in the '90s feminist demands became more institutional. Moreover, in LGBTQI activism, as well, there is a close attention to issues foregrounded by third wave feminism, bearing on class, race and ethnicity. The context of the socio-economic crisis in the 2010s enhanced the relevance of intersectional factors of exclusion (Kanaveli 2016: 24-32, 39, 44).

Finally, the Center of New Media and Feminist Public Practices illustrates other recent tendencies in addressing gender-based violence and inequality. Its research explores the impact of new technologies on 'thanatopolitics,' surveillance practices and the commodification of bodies, among others. It highlights the gendered and racialized construction of vulnerability, which calls for an enhancement of the embodied capacity for resistance and self-determination. A main objective of the Center is to deploy a technoaesthetic feminist theory and practice to organize dynamic spaces of intervention. Dwelling on difference and asymmetry, cultivating historical awareness and political consciousness,

contesting biopolitical power, it seeks to construct a range of safe spaces in the present in order to shape the future in militant ways (Karampa & Lykourioti 2021: 15-21).

3.9 Campaigns and debates

A first major protest and campaign in this period was occasioned by the arrest and public stigmatization of HIV-positive women who were drug addicts and worked reputedly as prostitutes in 2012. A huge wave of solidarity was set off by feminist groups such as the Feminist Initiative for the Elimination of Violence against Women, human rights organizations, leftist political groups and parties, the Network for Political and Social rights, and NGOs such as Praksis and Act Up, LGBTQ+ groups, which staged several public events of protest (Vovou 2020: 201-211). In May, the Initiative for Solidarity to Persecuted HIV-positive Women was established to coordinate action in their support, through mobilization, information campaigns, press releases, international networking, legal aid etc... In the first demonstration organized on the 6th of June 2012, they addressed a broad range of issues concerning gender-based violence, health and reproductive rights, labor and migration. In their words, they took aim at misogyny, racism, the criminalization of female body, the fascist politics infusing Greek society, the authoritarian politics of the state under the austerity regime, sexual violence against women, the responsibility of Greek 'heads of family' who would pay prostitutes for unprotected sex, the violation of women's human rights, the criminalization of poverty and disease, the assault on illegal migrant women, prostitutes and drug addicts who are deprived of basic rights to work and health (Vovou 2020: 212-213, 218).

In June 2012, twenty-four of these women were still imprisoned in a main detention center in Athens under horrible conditions. Their release started after the first trial in January 2013 which established their innocence and was completed in March 2013. The feminist mobilization -the Initiative continued its action for several years- succeeded in eventually annulling the legal provision (ΓΥ 39Α/2012) on which their persecution was based in April 2015, under the new SYRIZA government.

A second major campaign and mobilization cropped up in protest to the murder of Zacharias Kwstopoulos, also known as Zackie Oh, in September 2018. Zach was queer, HIV-positive, LGBTQI+ activist and artist. His murder was experienced by queer, lesbian, feminist activists and other women's collectives as an instance and an effect of heteronormative thanatopolitics, sparking multifarious action on the streets, the police headquarters in Athens, squats, bars, open public spaces, anti-racist events and drag shows for more than two years. Practices of mourning and memory expressed the desire for resistance and the demand to investigate the event. A new discourse was thereby diffused, intersectional, mourning, insurrectional, affective and demanding, never-ending, calling for reflection on the grounds of everyday violence and the tolerance of thanatopolitics, which proscribes, excludes and murders people. The first massive march took place on the 29th of September 2018, and it was called 'Protest-March-Madonna.' One of Zak's mottos became the central rallying cry: 'Εγώ με τη βία δεν το είχα ποτέ' [I could not stand/side with violence]. The march set off from Gladstonos Street (a street that has been unofficially renamed 'Zackie Oh Street' with a street sign that has been erected and taken down multiple times) and culminated in the club 'Bequeer' where Zak's friends celebrated his life with a drag show accompanied by songs by Madonna, his favourite singer (Remoundou 2022). Glitter and the high heel left over by Zack on the place. Glitter became a symbol not only of memory but also of antifascist struggle. The high heel held in marches served to denounce gender, racist, normalized violence (Athnasiou & Papanikolaou 2020: 9-11).

Several groups, including ΟΛΚΕ [Ομοφυλοφιλική Λεσβιακή Κοινότητα Ελλάδας: Homosexual Lesbian Community of Greece], Colour Youth, Σωματείο Υποστηρίξης Διεμφυλικών [Association in Support of Transgender Persons], Ένωση Αφρικών Γυναικών [Union of African Women] and others formed the initiative 'Justice for Zak/Zackie.' In December 2018 they signed a petition denouncing police as a

‘repressive mechanism embodying to an absolute degree the features of aggressive and toxic masculinity, which turns its boots and its globs against bodies that do not identify with the norm’ (Athanasiou & Παπανικολάου 2020: 10-11). Under the motto ‘Wrath and Grief, we will miss Zackie/ Our lives matter,’ crowds gathered on the spot of Kostopoulos’ murder in the same month and concluded their peaceful protest outside of the Police Headquarters of Athens (ΓΑΔΑ), where hundreds of shoes were left on the steps of the building as a commemorative gesture symbolizing Zak’s ultimate sign of life that remained on the murder scene of Gladstonos Street (Remoundou 2022). The initiative ‘zackieohjustice.watch’ is still active as the trial will continue in 2023.

The diverse and massive mobilization around Zack diffused and enhanced protests against transphobia and homophobia, disseminating ‘queer’ discourse and action. The word ‘queer,’ used by Zack to describe his acts and mode of living, has been left untranslated in Greek (κουήρ) to honour its multiple genealogies. Zack came to embody and epitomise another queer politics, the promise to survive at a queer time, to produce light in dark so that love wins. The fight for social justice was connected to an agony and struggle for queer survival. Zackie Oh’s own existence and politics was explicitly affected by queer theory, using this term to intervene as drag queen, HIV-positive and intersectional feminist, turning her experience into a demand and politicizing drag. Public encounters and debates followed the massive mobilizations of mourning and protest, partaking in the affective politics of queer agonistic mourning, performing a critical politics and poetics of relational knowledge that spans the divides between academia and activism; a politics of the archive that fights oblivion, sustaining critical trouble against gender, racial, national and class brutality. This politics drew systematically upon queer and feminist theory, post-colonial studies, critical race theory, critical ability studies and the very experience of the loss to reclaim public space and combat the heteronormative power relations which inform and define it (Athanasiou & Papanikolaou 2020: 12-19).

Earlier on, a related campaign set out to monitor gender violence affecting LGBTQI+ people. The ‘Tell Us About It’ campaign purports to record incidents of homophobic, biphobic and transphobic violence and discrimination so that perpetrators face the consequences of their actions, and society is informed and sensitized. The campaign was started in response to the femicidal transphobic attack on Anna, in 2012. Anna, a twenty-six-year-old transgender student encountered transphobic/ transmisogynist and homophobic treatment when she tried to re-enrol in high school. While Anna was, in the end, granted ‘permission’ by the school administration to dress in the way that expresses her gender identity, her classmates continued to harass her and threatened her with violence. Their behaviour was legitimized by the school authorities’ transphobic ‘reality enforcement’ at the outset. These threats materialized in June 2012, when Anna was a victim of a serious attack when a pupil and his friend poured gasoline on her and attempted to set her on fire just outside the school premises (Carastathis 2018).

A third key set of campaigns addresses femicides. A major one was instigated by Eleni Topaloudi’s murder. Topaloudi, aged 21, was raped and murdered in Rhodes in November 2018. Topaloudi’s femicide gained momentum as an example of gender-based violence that mobilized the fury of a concerned public. This time the female victim, a young Greek student portrayed by the media as the ‘good’ daughter of a ‘respectable’ family, was identified as every family’s potential loss. The list enumerating casualties of wronged bodies (queer, migrants, refugees, women) grew longer and bore common characteristics, symptomatic of a society in a chronic crisis (Remoundou 2022).

Topaloudi’s case was thoroughly investigated by a police officer and a female state prosecutor who supported the rights of the victim and the plea of the family for justice. In what amounts to a historic victory for the rights of women, the Greek Criminal Code was amended in 2019 to recognize officially that all sex without consent is rape and therefore punishable by law (Remoundou 2022).

The campaign ‘No other woman killed!’ took place in 2019, while feminist movements took issue with the representation of femicide in mass media, which attributed the murders to the ‘psychopathology’

of the perpetrators, to passion or accident, occluding the patriarchal background and stereotypes underlying this phenomenon. Hence, in recent years, femicide became a topic of intense feminist concern and agitation. Feminists and women's groups sought to disseminate the term 'femicide' which has been dismissed in Greece as 'abusive,' 'nonsensical' etc.. They started tracking systematically and highlighting the incidents of gender-based violence and femicide which were made public, foregrounding the subsisting macho culture which accounts for this phenomenon (Kontochristou 2021: 216-225, Petraki 2020: 11-12, 24-27, Gasouka 2020: 58, Vougiouka 2020: 79, 84, Kapsampeli 2019).

Fourth, the Greek #MeToo set off in an online event entitled 'Start to Talk' organized on 14 January 2021 by the ministry department of Sports, in which Sophia Bekatorou, winner of Olympic medals in sailing, publicly denounced for the first time the sexual violence she was subjected to nearly twenty years ago, at the age of 21, by a strongman of the Hellenic Sailing Federation (Chroni & Kavoura 2022). An avalanche of similar denunciations by sportswomen, female university students and women employed in the showbusiness would follow, leading among others to the arrest of the well-known art director of the Greek National Theatre.

Finally, the 8th of March women's strikes brought contemporary feminism again on the streets, seeking to connect it with other modes of bottom-up organization. The strikes from 2017 onwards seemed to revive the radicalism of democratic mobilization at the beginning of this period (Spanou 2017: 90-91, Karamanou 2021: 367-370).

3.10 Key policy related outcomes

Policies

The decade 2010-2020 saw significant institutional, legal and policy innovations that foster gender equality. The new architecture of local government set up specialized structures, such as regional equality committees and political equality departments. ΕΣΠΑ funding was invested in a National Program to Prevent and Fight Violence against Women 2010-2013, which is still in place and it is coordinated by the GSFPGE. This Program established 20 municipal guesthouses, 42 counselling centers and a national Emergency Number for women and children subject to male violence and harassment. The novel supportive infrastructure remained in place during the years of the economic crisis and the austerity regime (2010-2018) thanks to the contribution of EU funding. The creation of this infrastructure considerably enhanced the quality and quantity of available statistics on gender violence. According to the 'First Annual Report on Violence Against Women,' which covers one year (1/11/2019-30/10/2020), the new services assisted 4872 women who were subject to violence and multiple discriminations and third parties (mother, adult daughter of the victim etc). The prevalent form of reported gender violence has been domestic violence (84%), followed by sexual harassment (2%) and rape (2%). The main perpetrators are husbands and partners, and the main age group of the victims consists of women who are 36-45 years old (GSFPGE /ΓΓΟΠΙΦ 2020: 24-27).

By increasing socio-economic and psychological pressure, the economic downturn exacerbated violence against women, but the latter pre-existed the crisis and was mainly made visible through the new structures of support. The same ΕΣΠΑ funding schemes contained plans to introduce 'gender mainstreaming' in all public policies and the public sector at large, which were hardly implemented.

Moreover, in 2011, the Greek state signs the 'Istanbul Convention' to combat all forms of violence against women, in all fields of their everyday life, which it ratifies only in 2018. The amendment of Law 4285/2014, the 'Law Against Racism and Xenophobia', stipulated important changes regarding hate speech and violence against LGBTIQ+ individuals or groups in Greece. This was further reinforced in 2016 with the expansion of rigid anti-discrimination protections based on sexual orientation, gender, and religion in the workplace.

In 2015 (Law 4356/2015), under the new coalition government led by the left-wing SYRIZA party, the Greek state grants to same-gender couples the right to enter a civil partnership contract, recognizing family ties between their members, without granting them, however, the right to adopt children. In 2017, new legislation is enacted that establishes the legal recognition of gender identity, through which the free choice of gender becomes legally possible and acknowledged. The law 4491/2017 simplified thus the procedures for transgender people to change their legal gender identity. Moreover, law 4538/2018 gave the right to child fostering to same-sex couples. The 4604/2019 law sets up a comprehensive and self-standing institutional framework for gender equality and the elimination of discrimination against women, laying down specific mechanisms and actors for the implementation of gender equality in public policies and private life. Finally, in 2016-2020, GSGE [General Secretariat for Gender Equality: Γενική Γραμματεία Ισότητας των Φύλων: ΓΓΙΦ] implemented a number of actions to combat gender violence by offering psychosocial and legal support, networking, information and education, in the framework of the National Action Plan for Gender Equality 2016-2020. In this context, in 2019, the Greek police set up a specialized 'Department of domestic violence.' Furthermore, in what amounts to a historic victory for the rights of women, the Greek Criminal Code was amended in 2019 to recognize officially that all sex without consent is rape and therefore punishable by law. Law 4589/2019 included an article that provided for the setup of Committees for Gender Equality (CGE) in all Greek universities. Last but not least, Greek-listed companies are mandated to meet a 25% quota on their boards of the underrepresented gender since July 2021 with law 4706/2020 (Stratigaki 2017: 119-120, Karamanou 2021: 336-339, 342, 345, Vaiou et al. 2021: 13, Mavromati-Lagani 2021: 129-133, Kavvoura 2021: 140-145, Milioni 2020: 105, Kanaveli 2016: 8, Remoundou 2022).

The National Program for Substantive Gender Equality 2010-2013, sponsored by the Ministry of Justice and the current GSFPGE, did improve legislation in family law and issues of violence against women, while also pursuing focussed equality policies in certain policy areas. The second National Action Plan for Gender Equality 2016-2020 prioritized gender mainstreaming and positive specialized action to eliminate gender inequalities. It focussed on the protection of women's human rights in vulnerable groups, such as Roma and refugees, gender violence, equality in political power, employment and health (ΓΓΙΦ 2016). But the long-term strategy of gender mainstreaming in public policies on all levels was not put into effect, and the problems in the labour market affecting women were not adequately tackled. This outcome corroborates the thesis that gender equality policies cannot 'go against the grain' when austerity policies generate socio-economic regress on a massive scale, indicating the need to challenge recent economic policies on the national and the EU level from a gender perspective (Karamesini 2015: 271-272).

However, after the government change in 2019 and the consequent political shift to the right, several of the above measures were repealed (e.g. the school subject Gender Identities and the 40% gender quota in elections have been abolished) and new conservative gender policies have been promoted in the country. Although in January 2020 a woman, Katerina Sakelaropoulou, was appointed as President of the Republic for the first time in Greece, the same year the New Democracy party voted against the explicit reference to equality regardless of gender, sexual orientation and gender identity in the constitution. The former General Secretariat for Gender Equality was renamed into 'General Secretariat of Family Policy and Gender Equality' – GSFPGE- and was demoted to a department of the Ministry of Labor.

Stratigaki (2017: 121) identifies five policy domains which most urgently call for legislative and public interventions to address Greece's sustained low performance in the field of gender equality compared to other EU countries: 1) sexist stereotypes in mass media; 2) the extent of prostitution; 3) low female participation in the centres of decision-making; 4) deficient social care infrastructures; 5) the problems of women refugees.

Kosyfologou (2018: 48-50) argues that the quest for new forms of collective organization and action should draw upon the recent experiences of self-organized solidarity movements and initiatives in 2011-2018 (social clinics, social housing, solidarity schools etc.) The paradigm of the 'green and purple' economy, informed by the principles of a non-gendered division of labour and care for the environment could become a springboard for the development of alternative strategy along with increased public investment in infrastructure and the overcoming of austerity. Generalized social security and the defence of public health and education should be also prioritized. The growth of a domain of social care organized around non-capitalist and horizontal collective initiatives could be progressive if combined with an alternative political culture that contests the gendered division of labour in employment, politics, social relationships and family, broadening effective political participation and challenging patriarchy and capitalism through collective struggles.

3.11 Conclusion

The intricate complexity of the field itself, and the several gaps and blind spots in existing research and publications on feminist and LGBTQI+ politics in 2010-2021 call for extensive further inquiries on multiple levels (institutional, grassroots, international etc.) and through various methodologies (interviews, ethnographic observation, policy and discourse analysis etc.). In particular, there is scant in-depth and comprehensive research in the internal composition of the various actors, their frames of analysis, their repertoires of action, their national and international networks, their relations with institutional actors and the political system, their policy proposals for institutions and broader social transformation regarding labor, health and reproductive issues and migration.

However, from the foregoing survey of most available secondary and 'grey' literature (including NGO and state institutional reports) several significant findings stand out, setting the stage for future research.

Patriarchy, gender-based violence (from sexual harassment to femicide and transphobic thanatopolitics), LGBTQI+ recognition and rights, issues of labour, care and social reproduction, refugees and migration are the most salient topics of relevant protest and intervention. In these areas of concern and action, a host of distinct and partly new trends which carry potentials for democratic innovation become pronounced in this period.

First, the institutional framework, regarding particularly gender equality, gender-based violence and LGBTQI+ rights, is considerably amplified and updated, enhancing the institutional supports and vehicles that women and LGBTQI+ individuals and actors can deploy to further their cause. Hence, gender-based violence gains increased visibility and several institutional means to address it. This is a result of both international (EU and other) policy initiatives and national movement pressure.

Second, it becomes evident that state policies and institutional action do not suffice to dismantle the deeply embedded, centuries-long patriarchy and gender-based violence in Greek society. Gender stereotypes, presumptions and roles in everyday life, institutions and mass media need to be contested and effectively transformed in all their variety, opacity and complexity. To this end, feminist and LGBTQI+ agency responds in the following ways which take aim at the very social construction and reconstruction of gender identities and sexualities across diverse social relations and levels (everyday, institutional etc.):

- a) a new scheme of grassroots, non-bureaucratic and non-hierarchical mobilization takes shape which is made of small radical groups dispersed across the country that critically engage with gender and sexuality, highlighting gender power relations, and contesting them in practice. The repertoire of action involves public events-discussions, publications, posters, leaflets,

interventions concerning body, gender, sexuality and gendered power relations, which connect with the past but are also cast in contemporary terms;

- b) a close interaction between gender and sexuality movements, on the one hand, and the Greek academia, research and gender studies, explores the social construction of gender and sexuality in all its complexity and searches for effective means of fight and change across social relations. This feminist politics deconstructs the dualism theory/practice, reckons with the 'critical condition' of the 10s -the neoliberal steepening of inequalities, the spread of racist and neofascist violence etc-, highlights the intertwinements between vulnerability and possibility, between heteropatriarchal and racist violence and multiple collective or individual resistances, pursues a critical dialogue between feminism and queer in theory, art, subjectivities, affects, bodies and cultural practices, and undertakes complex feminist/queer/antiracist interventions which undo the preconceptions of the dominant subject as white, national, bourgeois, male, full-bodied and heteronormative. It makes use of internet fragments, interviews, ethnographies, theoretical and activist texts, workshops and research projects to destabilize and transfigure prevalent modes of patriarchal subjectivity and to map out new figures of 'the political,' new modes of action, knowledge production and subjectivation drawing on forms of otherness which are often defined within neoliberal contexts but also escape and challenge them;
- c) in this context, intersectionality, the recognition of the tight imbrication of gender, class, race, ethnicity, sexuality and ability in the re-production of different forms of inequality, and queer, an understanding of gender identity and sexuality as fluid, contestable, complex and exceeding the heteronormative canon, become main angles in grappling with gender-based violence, labor, health and reproductive rights, LGBTQI+ and migration especially in collectives and movements which merge theory and activism;
- d) personal and collective experiences are positioned in their socio-political conditions and become subject to political re-elaboration, reflecting the second wave slogan 'the personal is political' but also foregrounding the plurality of identities, the body, gender and sexuality understood in non-heteronormative logic that reveal the influences of third wave post-structuralist feminism. Relatedly, there is an emphasis on 'creating space' for such collectives and interventions, claiming public space back from male subjects.
- e) new 'activist' research and education centres are established at universities and beyond, reclaiming and making use of the more open institutional space of public universities. Such centres also explore art and technology as field which impact on gender relations and sexuality but can be also redeployed for their transformation. Digital technologies and media are thus employed by small collectives, the #Metoo campaign and other actors as a window to reach broader segments of society and to disseminate feminist and LGBTQI+ agendas;

Third, as a consequence of the dire socio-economic and political crisis in Greece from 2010 onwards, massive anti-austerity mobilizations, new grassroots community initiatives and multiple ventures in the social and solidarity economy mark the period of reference in the country. Although they mostly lacked an explicit feminist and LGBTQI+ agenda, feminist agency and issues of care and reproduction were prominent and consequential. They brought to the fore women's collective knowledge, skills, and experiences as a grassroots response to the devastating effects of a prolonged crisis, opening up new territory for women's participation and the dissemination of feminist political principles and emancipatory practices. As the repertoire of actions of the Greek social movement shifted from street protests to spaces of social reproduction, implicit modes of feminist solidarity transfigured the movements' solidarity practices both in terms of their organizational choices and of their collective frames of mobilization. Correlatively, in the feminist discourses and practices of these years issues of social reproduction and care were raised in relation to the capitalist modes of production, throwing up new perspectives on the relationship between the personal and the political. The potential

'feminization' of social movements and the social and solidarity economy, in particular, is a notable trend that calls for further in-depth investigation to fathom the impact of feminist praxis and its impact, in turn, on feminist politics.

Regarding the innovative potentials of feminist and LGBTQI+ politics for contemporary democracy, the foregoing account points to

the significance of intersectional and queer approaches in tackling persisting inequalities and deepening equal social freedom, the democratic freedom of groups and individuals to frame their lives beyond pre-existing norms, divisions and exclusions;

the importance of combining grassroots, assembly-based and direct democratic politics with institutional interventions and reforms;

the promise of a feminized and democratized economy in which care, solidarity, ecology, equality, collective modes of social reproduction and democratic decision-making are fostered in economic relations of production and reproduction, combined with increased public investment in infrastructure, generalized social security, the defence of public health and education, and the formation of an alternative political culture that undoes the gendered division of labour in work, politics, social relationships and family.

List of feminist movements' campaigns

Name of the campaign (original)	Name of the campaign (English)	Issue(s) addressed	Actors involved	Repertoire of action	Logo of the campaign	Web-page
Justice for Zak/Zackie	Justice for Zak/Zackie	Murder of Zak Kostopoulos	ΟΛΚΕ [Ομοφυλοφιλική Λεσβιακή Κοινότητα Ελλάδας; Homosexual Lesbian Community of Greece], Colour Youth, Σωματείο Υποστηρίξης Διεμφυλικών [Association in Support of Transgender Persons], Ένωση Αφρικών Γυναικών [Union of African Women] and others	In December 2018 they signed a petition denouncing police as a 'repressive mechanism embodying to an absolute degree the features of aggressive and toxic masculinity, which turns its boots and its globs against bodies that do not identify with the norm' (Athanasίου & Παπανικολάου 2020: 10-11). Under the motto 'Wrath and Grief, we will miss Zackie/ Our lives matter,' crowds gathered on the spot of Kostopoulos' murder in the same month and concluded their peaceful protest outside of the Police Headquarters of Athens (ΓΑΔΑ), where hundreds of shoes were left on the steps of the building as a commemorative gesture symbolizing Zak's ultimate sign of life that remained on the murder scene of Gladstonos Street (Remoundou 2022). The initiative 'zackieohjustice.watch' is still active as the trial will continue in 2023.		FB: Justice For Zak/Zackie Facebook E-mail: justice4zakzackie@gmail.com
Καμία Άλλη δολοφονία	No other woman killed!	Femicides	Feminist movements	No other woman killed!' took place in 2019, while feminist movements took issue with the representation of femicide in mass media		

Χωρίς συΝΑΙεση είναι Βιασμός	Without consent is rape	Chang e of the law to recog nize that witho ut conse nt is rape	Feminist movements	In what amounts to a historic victory for the rights of women, the Greek Criminal Code was amended in 2019 to recognize officially that all sex without consent is rape and therefore punishable by law (Remoundou 2022).		FB: (1) Χωρίς συΝΑΙεση είναι Βιασμός Facebook
Πρωτοβου λία αλληλεγγ ύης στις διωκόμεν ες οροθετικέ ς γυναίκες	Initiative for Solidarity to Persecute d HIV- positive Women	Releas e of impris oned hiv- positiv e wome n	Feminist Initiative for the Elimination of Violence against Women, human rights organizations, leftist political groups and parties, the Network for Political and Social rights, and NGOs such as Praksis and Act Up, LGBTQ+ groups	A first major protest and campaign in this period was occasioned by the arrest and public stigmatization of HIV-positive women who were drug addicts and worked reputedly as prostitutes in 2012. A huge wave of solidarity was set off by feminist groups such as the Feminist Initiative for the Elimination of Violence against Women, human rights organizations, leftist political groups and parties, the Network for Political and Social rights, and NGOs such as Praksis and Act Up, LGBTQ+ groups, which staged several public events of protest (Bωβού 2020: 201-211). In May, the Initiative for Solidarity to Persecuted HIV-positive Women was established to coordinate action in their support, through mobilization, information campaigns, press releases, international networking, legal aid etc.. In the first demonstration in organized on the 6 th of June 2012, they addressed a broad range of issues concerning gender-based		Blog: https://diokomenesrothetikes.wordpress.com/

				<p>violence, health and reproductive rights, labor and migration. In their words, they took aim at misogyny, racism, the criminalization of female body, the fascist politics infusing Greek society, the authoritarian politics of the state under the austerity regime, sexual violence against women, the responsibility of Greek 'heads of family' who would pay prostitutes for unprotected sex, the violation of women's human rights, the criminalization of poverty and disease, the assault on illegal migrant women, prostitutes and drug addicts who are deprived of basic rights to work and health (Vovou 2020: 212-213, 218).</p>		
#ME TOO GREECE	#ME TOO GREECE			<p>Since 2017-2018 women took part in the international #MeToo movement, which in Greece unfolded mainly on the Internet and mass media from 2021 onwards, in other national protests against sexual harassment and gender-based violence. Finally, the 8th of March women's strikes, which brought contemporary feminism again on the streets, sought to connect it with other modes of bottom-up organization (Spanou 2017: 90-91, Καραμάνου 2021: 367-370).</p>		

Πες τη με το Όνομά της	Call it by its name	Advocating for the recognition of the term 'femicide'	22 women's organisations ²⁶ : Γυναικεία ομάδα Αυτοάμυνας Δίκτυο για την Αντιμετώπιση της Βίας κατά των Γυναικών mailto:gazililian@yahoo.gr Δίκτυο Γυναικών Συγγραφέων Κατά Της Έμφυλης Βίας και των Γυναικοκτονιών «Η φωνή της» mailto:katrapandoniou@gmail.com Διοτίμα Ελληνικό Δίκτυο για την Φεμινιστική Απεργία mailto:kanta@otoe.gr Ελληνικό Δίκτυο Γυναικών Ευρώπης Ένωση Γυναικών Ελλάδας (Ε.Γ.Ε.) Ένωση Διπλωματούχων Ελληνίδων Μηχανικών	The Initiative aims "to highlight and recognize the phenomenon of femicide as a sexist crime.		N/A
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²⁶ «Πες τη με το Όνομά της»: Πρωτοβουλία κατά των γυναικοκτονιών από 22 γυναικείες οργανώσεις - Press Crew Νέα από την Κορινθία, Πελοπόννησο και φωτορεπορτάζ (press-crew.gr)

		<p>Εργαστήριο Σπουδών Φύλου, Τμήμα Κοινωνικής Πολιτικής, Πάντειο Πανεπιστήμιο Ευρωπαϊκό Δίκτυο κατά της Βίας (ΕΔκΒ) mailto:info@antiviol ence-net.eu Κίνημα Strong me για την πρόληψη και καταπολέμηση της έμφυλης βίας mailto:strongme2021 @gmail.com ΜΗΤΕΡΑΣ ΕΡΓΟΝ Σύλλογος Πολύτεκνων Μητέρων NIMERTIS ACTIONART ΝΠΙΔ Οι μαμάδες Mother's Wings Greece Ομάδα Γυναικείων Δικαιωμάτων Κοινωνική Παρέμβαση Δυτικά Ομάδα Γυναικών του Συλλόγου Κοινωνικής και Πολιτιστικής Παρέμβασης Θρααλλίδα Πανελλήνιο Σωματείο Εργαζομένων Δικτύου Δομών ΓΓΙΦ Πρωτοβουλία Γυναικών Πειραιά mailto:protonoulia</p>			
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			<p>gynaiakonpeiraia@gmail.com</p> <p>Σύλλογος εργαζομένων Γενικής Γραμματείας Ισότητας των φύλων Σωματείο Γυναικείων Δικαιωμάτων «ΤΟ ΜΩΒ» ΧΕΝ Ελλάδος Φεμινιστική Συλλογικότητα ΘΕΟΔΩΡΑ</p>			
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References

in Greek

Apostolleli, A., Chalkia, A. (eds) (2012) *Soma/Fylo/Sexualikotithta. LOATK politikes stin Ellada*, Athens: Plethron [Αποστολλέλη, Α., Χαλκιά, Α. (επιμ.) (2012) *Σώμα/Φύλο/Σεξουαλικότητα. ΛΟΑΤΚ πολιτικές στην Ελλάδα*, Αθήνα: Πλέθρον]

Athanasiou, A. (ed.). (2006) *Feministiki Theoria kai politismiki kritiki*, Athens: Nisos [Athanasiou, A. (επιμ.) (2006) *Φεμινιστική θεωρία και πολιτισμική κριτική*, Αθήνα: Νήσος]

Athanasiou, A. (2017) 'To na "ginessai feministria" ws kritiki epitelestikotita toy politikou in Vaiou, Nt., Psarra, A. (eds) (2017) *Ennoiologiseis kai praktikes toy feminismou. Metapolitefsi kai 'meta.'* Athens: Foundation of the Greek Parliament [Athanasiou, A. (2017) «Το 'να γίνεσαι φεμινίστρια' ως κριτική επιτελεστικότητα του πολιτικού», στον τόμο Βαΐου Ντ., Ψαρρά, Α. (επιμ.) (2017) *Εννοιολογήσεις και πρακτικές του φεμινισμού. Μεταπολίτευση και «μετά»*, Αθήνα: Ίδρυμα της Βουλής των Ελλήνων]

Athanasiou, A., Papanikolaou, D. (2020) 'Introduction: "Pes to onoma tis:" H queer mnimi ws kritiki tou parontos,' in Athanasiou, A., Gkougkousis, G., Papanikolaou, D. (eds) (2020) *Queer politiki. Dimosia mnimi. Trianta keimena gia ton Zak*, Athens: Rosa Luxemburg Foundation [Athanasiou, A., Παπανικολάου, Δ. (2020) «Εισαγωγή: 'Πες το όνομά της': Η κουήρ μνήμη ως κριτική του παρόντος», στον τόμο Athanasiou, A., Γκουγκούσης, Γ., Παπανικολάου, Δ. (επιμ.) (2020) *Κουήρ πολιτική/Δημόσια μνήμη. Τριάντα κείμενα για τον Ζακ*, Αθήνα: Ίδρυμα Ρόζα Λούξεμπουργκ]

Butler, J. (2008) *Bodies that matter* [Greek translation: *Σώματα με σημασία: Οριοθετήσεις του «φύλου» στο λόγο*, μτφρ. Π. Μαρκέτου, Αθήνα: Εκκρεμές]

Butler, J. (2009) *Gender Trouble: Feminism and the subversion of identity* [Greek translation: *Αναταραχή φύλου: Ο φεμινισμός και η ανατροπή της ταυτότητας*, μτφρ. Γ. Καράμπελας, Αθήνα: Αλεξάνδρεια]

feministika (2018) v. 1, Spring 2018 [Φεμινιστικά (2018) τεύχος 1, Άνοιξη 2018, feministika.net, access 27/12/2022]

Gasouka, M. (2020) 'Palia istoria se syhrona plaisia,' in Petraki, G. (ed.) (2020) *Gynaikoktonies: diapistwseis, erotimata kai erotimatika*, Athens: Gutenberg [Γκασούκα, Μ. (2020) «Παλιά ιστορία σε σύγχρονα πλαίσια», στον τόμο Πετράκη, Γ. (επιμ.) (2020) *Γυναικοκτονίες: διαπιστώσεις, ερωτήματα και ερωτηματικά*, Αθήνα: Gutenberg]

Gazi, L. (2017) 'Oi gynaikeies organoseis kai o rolos tous ston koinoniko metaschimatismo, in Vaiou, Nt., Psarra, A. (eds) (2017) *Ennoiologiseis kai praktikes toy feminismou. Metapolitefsi kai 'meta.'* Athens: Foundation of the Greek Parliament [Gazi, Λ. (2017) «Οι γυναικείες οργανώσεις και ο ρόλος τους στον κοινωνικό μετασχηματισμό», στον τόμο Βαΐου Ντ., Ψαρρά, Α. (επιμ.) (2017) *Εννοιολογήσεις και πρακτικές του φεμινισμού. Μεταπολίτευση και «μετά»*, Αθήνα: Ίδρυμα της Βουλής των Ελλήνων]

GSFPG [General Secretariat for Demography and Family Policy and Gender Equality] (2020) *Annual Report on Violence against Women*, Athens, November 2020 [Γενική Γραμματεία Δημογραφικής και Οικογενειακής Πολιτικής και Ισότητας των Φύλων (2020) *1η Ετήσια Έκθεση για την Βία κατά των Γυναικών*, Αθήνα, Νοέμβριος 2020]

GSGE [General Secretariat for Gender Equality] (2016) *National Action Plan for Gender Equality 2016-2020*, Athens [Γενική Γραμματεία Ισότητας των Φύλων (ΓΓΙΦ) (2016) *Εθνικό Σχέδιο Δράσης για την Ισότητα των Φύλων 2016-2020*, Αθήνα]

Giannakopoulos, K. (2012) 'Politismikes ennoiologiseis ths monaxias: syggeneia, koinotita kai politikes tou LOAT kinimatos,' in Apostolleli, A., Chalkia, A. (eds) (2012) *Soma/Fylo/Sexualikotithta. LOATK politikes stin Ellada*, Athens: Plethron [Γιαννακόπουλος, Κ. (2012) «Πολιτισμικές εννοιολογήσεις της μοναξιάς: συγγένεια, κοινότητα και πολιτικές του ΛΟΑΤ κινήματος», στον τόμο Αποστολλέλη, Α., Χαλκιά, Α. (επιμ.) (2012) *Σώμα/Φύλο/Σεξουαλικότητα. ΛΟΑΤΚ πολιτικές στην Ελλάδα*, Αθήνα: Πλέθρον]

Kanaveli, E. (2016) 'Chartographisi tou feministikou kinimatos stin Ellada: Ideologikopolitikes anazitiseis kai i syneisfora tou ston dimosio choro kai logo,' Athens: *Diotima* Center of Women's Studies and Research [Καναβέλη, Ε. (2016) «Χαρτογράφηση του φεμινιστικού κινήματος στην Ελλάδα: Ιδεολογικοπολιτικές αναζητήσεις και η συνεισφορά του στον δημόσιο χώρο και λόγο», Αθήνα: Κέντρο Γυναικείων Μελετών και Ερευνών *Διοτίμα*]

Kantsa, V. (2012) 'Orata aorates/aorata orates: duo opseis tis lesviakis parousias stin Ellada,' in Apostolleli, A., Chalkia, A. (eds) (2012) *Soma/Fylo/Sexualikotithta. LOATK politikes stin Ellada*, Athens: Plethron [Καντσά, Β. (2012) «Ορατά αόρατες/αόρατα ορατές: δύο όψεις της λεσβιακής παρουσίας στην Ελλάδα», στον τόμο Αποστολλέλη, Α., Χαλκιά, Α. (επιμ.) (2012) *Σώμα/Φύλο/Σεξουαλικότητα. ΛΟΑΤΚ πολιτικές στην Ελλάδα*, Αθήνα: Πλέθρον]

Kapsampeli, S. (2019) 'Emfyles eksontoseis sto onoma tis agapis, tis atychias kai tis trelas,' MA Dissertation, Athens: University of Athens, MA in Political Science and Sociology [Καψαμπέλη, Σ. (2019) «Έμφυλες εξοντώσεις στο όνομα της αγάπης, της ατυχίας και της τρέλας», Διπλωματική εργασία, Αθήνα: ΕΚΠΑ, ΠΜΣ Πολιτική Επιστήμη και Κοινωνιολογία]

Karamanou, A. (2021) *I eiriniki eksegersi ton thylikon Sapiens 1821-2021*, Athens: Armos [Καραμάνου, Α. (2021) *Η ειρηνική εξέγερση των θηλυκών Sapiens 1821-2021*, Αθήνα: Αρμός]

Karamesini (2015) 'Diarthrwitiki krisi kai prosarmogi stin Ellada,' in Karamesini, M., Rubery, J. (eds) (2021) *Gynaikes kai litotita. I oikonomiki Krisi kai to mellon tis isotitas twn fylon*, Athens: Alexandraia [Καραμεσίνη (2015) «Διαρθρωτική κρίση και προσαρμογή στην Ελλάδα», στον τόμο Καραμεσίνη, Μ., Rubery, J. (επιμ.) (2021) *Γυναίκες και λιτότητα. Η οικονομική κρίση και το μέλλον της ισότητας των φύλων*, Αθήνα: Αλεξάνδρεια]

Karampa, E., Lykourioti, I. (eds) (2021) *Feminist theories, aesthetic practices and globalized technologies*, Volos: University of Thessaly & Centre of New Media and Feminist Public Practice [Καραμπά, Ε., Λυκουριώτη, Ι. (επιμ.) (2021) *Φεμινιστικές θεωρίες, αισθητικές πρακτικές και παγκοσμιοποιημένες τεχνολογίες*, Βόλος: Εκδόσεις Πανεπιστημίου Θεσσαλίας & Κέντρο Νέων Μέσων και Φεμινιστικών Πρακτικών στον Δημόσιο Χώρο]

Karapanou, A. (ed.) (2017) *O feminismos sta chronia tis metapolitefsis 1974-1990*, Athens: Foundation of the Greek Parliament [Καραπάνου, Α. (επιμ.) (2017) *Ο φεμινισμός στα χρόνια της μεταπολίτευσης 1974-1990*, Αθήνα: Ίδρυμα της Βουλής των Ελλήνων]

Kavnoura, Th. (2021) 'Endoikogeneiaki via kata ton gynaiikon,' in Vaiou, Nt., Petraki, E., Stratigaki, M. (eds) (2021) *Emfyli via- Via kata ton gynaiikon*, Athens: Alexandraia [Κάββουρα, Θ. (2021) «Ένδοοικογενειακή βία κατά των γυναικών», στον τόμο Βαΐου, Ντ., Πετράκη, Ε., Στρατηγάκη, Μ. (επιμ.) (2021) *Έμφυλη βία-Βία κατά των γυναικών*, Αθήνα: Αλεξάνδρεια]

Kontochristou, A. (2021) 'Apo tin emfyli via sti gynaikoktonia,' in Vaiou, Nt., Petraki, E., Stratigaki, M. (eds) (2021) *Emfyli via- Via kata ton gynaiikon*, Athens: Alexandraia [Κοντοχρήστου, Α. (2021) «Από την έμφυλη βία στη γυναικοκτονία», στον τόμο Βαΐου, Ντ., Πετράκη, Ε., Στρατηγάκη, Μ. (επιμ.) (2021) *Έμφυλη βία-Βία κατά των γυναικών*, Αθήνα: Αλεξάνδρεια]

- Kosyfologou, A. (2018) *Oi emfylyes diastaseis tou kathestotos litotitas stin Ellada: 2010-2017. Litotita, emfyli anisotita kai feminismos meta tin Krisi*, Athens: Rosa Luxemburg Foundation [Κοσυφολόγου, Α. (2018) *Οι έμφυλες διαστάσεις του καθεστώς λιτότητας στην Ελλάδα: 2010-2017. Λιτότητα, έμφυλη ανισότητα και φεμινισμός μετά την κρίση*, Αθήνα: Ίδρυμα Ρόζα Λούξεμπουργκ]
- Kouroutsidou, M., Gasouka, M. (2021) *Opseis fylou kai diakriseon*, Athens: Gonis [Κουρουτσίδου, Μ., Γκασούκα, Μ. (2021) *Όψεις φύλου και διακρίσεων*, Αθήνα: Εκδόσεις Γκόνη]
- Laqueur, T. (2003) *Making Sex. Body and gender from the Greeks to Freud* [Greek translation: *Κατασκευάζοντας το Φύλο: Σώμα και κοινωνικό φύλο από τους αρχαίους Έλληνες ως τον Φρόιντ*, μτφρ. Π. Μαρκέτου, Αθήνα: Πολύτροπον]
- Makrynioti, D. (ed.) (2004) *Ta oria tou somatos: Diepistimonikes proseggiseis*, Athens: Nisos [Μακρυνιώτη, Δ. (επιμ.) (2004) *Τα όρια του σώματος: Διεπιστημονικές προσεγγίσεις*, Αθήνα: Νήσος]
- Manrommati-Lagani, A. (2021) 'Politikes antimetopisis tis endoioikogeneiakis vias,' in Vaiou, Nt., Petraki, E., Stratigaki, M. (eds) (2021) *Emfyli via- Via kata ton gynaiikon*, Athens: Alexandria [Μαυρομμάτη-Λαγάνη, Α. (2021) «Πολιτικές αντιμετώπισης της ενδοοικογενειακής βίας», στον τόμο Βαΐου, Ντ., Πετράκη, Ε., Στρατηγάκη, Μ. (επιμ.) (2021) *Έμφυλη βία-Βία κατά των γυναικών*, Αθήνα: Αλεξάνδρεια]
- Michailidou, M., Chalkia, A. (eds) (2005) *I paragogi tou koinonikou somatos*, Athens: Katarti & Dini [Μιχαηλίδου, Μ., Χαλκιά, Α. (επιμ.) (2005) *Η παραγωγή του κοινωνικού σώματος*, Αθήνα: Κατάρτι & Δίνη]
- Milioni, F. (2020) 'Gynaikoktonia: Egklimatologikes kai nomikes diastaseis,' in Petraki, G. (ed.) (2020) *Gynaikoktonies: diapistwseis, erotimata kai erotimatika*, Athens: Gutenberg [Μηλιώνη, Φ. (2020) «Γυναικοκτονία: Εγκληματολογικές και νομικές διαστάσεις», στον τόμο Πετράκη, Γ. (επιμ.) (2020) *Γυναικοκτονίες: διαπιστώσεις, ερωτήματα και ερωτηματικά*, Αθήνα: Gutenberg]
- Ntousia, G. (2017) 'I amfisvitis tis patriarchias kai i apeleftherosi ton gynaiikon, protagmata tou autonoumou feministikou kinimatos,' in Vaiou, Nt., Psarra, A. (eds) (2017) *Ennoiologiseis kai praktikes toy feminismou. Metapolitefsi kai 'meta.'* Athens: Foundation of the Greek Parliament [Ντούσια, Γ. (2017) «Η αμφισβήτηση της πατριαρχίας και η απελευθέρωση των γυναικών, προτάγματα του αυτόνομου φεμινιστικού κινήματος», στον τόμο Βαΐου Ντ., Ψαρρά, Α. (επιμ.) (2017) *Εννοιολογήσεις και πρακτικές του φεμινισμού. Μεταπολίτευση και «μετά»*, Αθήνα: Ίδρυμα της Βουλής των Ελλήνων]
- Pantelidou-Malouta, M. (2017) 'Ti mathame gia thn emfyli anisotita: apo ti theoría stin politiki,' in Vaiou, Nt., Psarra, A. (eds) (2017) *Ennoiologiseis kai praktikes toy feminismou. Metapolitefsi kai 'meta.'* Athens: Foundation of the Greek Parliament [Παντελίδου-Μαλούτα, Μ. (2017) «Τι μάθαμε για την έμφυλη ανισότητα: από τη θεωρία στην πολιτική», στον τόμο Βαΐου Ντ., Ψαρρά, Α. (επιμ.) (2017) *Εννοιολογήσεις και πρακτικές του φεμινισμού. Μεταπολίτευση και «μετά»*, Αθήνα: Ίδρυμα της Βουλής των Ελλήνων]
- Petraki, G. (ed.) (2020) *Gynaikoktonies: diapistwseis, erotimata kai erotimatika*, Athens: Gutenberg [Πετράκη, Γ. (επιμ.) (2020) *Γυναικοκτονίες: διαπιστώσεις, ερωτήματα και ερωτηματικά*, Αθήνα: Gutenberg]
- Repousi, M. (2017) 'Feminismois tis metapolitefsis: afigimatika plaisia kai anatheoriseis,' in Vaiou, Nt., Psarra, A. (eds) (2017) *Ennoiologiseis kai praktikes toy feminismou. Metapolitefsi kai 'meta.'* Athens: Foundation of the Greek Parliament [Ρεπούση, Μ. (2017) «Φεμινισμοί της Μεταπολίτευσης: αφηγηματικά πλαίσια και αναθεωρήσεις», στον τόμο Βαΐου Ντ., Ψαρρά, Α. (επιμ.) (2017) *Εννοιολογήσεις και πρακτικές του φεμινισμού. Μεταπολίτευση και «μετά»*, Αθήνα: Ίδρυμα της Βουλής των Ελλήνων]

Sklaveniti, K. (2017) 'Autonomes feministikes omades tis metapolitefsis: Duo tria pragmata pou ksero gi' autes,' in Vaiou, Nt., Psarra, A. (eds) (2017) *Ennoiologiseis kai praktikes toy feminismou. Metapolitefsi kai 'meta.'* Athens: Foundation of the Greek Parliament [Σκλαβενίτη, Κ. (2017) «Αυτόνομες φεμινιστικές ομάδες της μεταπολίτευσης: Δυο τρία πράγματα που ξέρω γι' αυτές», στον τόμο Βαΐου Ντ., Ψαρρά, Α. (επιμ.) (2017) *Εννοιολογήσεις και πρακτικές του φεμινισμού. Μεταπολίτευση και «μετά»*, Αθήνα: Ίδρυμα της Βουλής των Ελλήνων]

Spanou, D. (2017) 'Politikopoiontas ta viomata mas stin epochi tis krisis. I empeiria mesa apo to fyllo sykis,' in Vaiou, Nt., Psarra, A. (eds) (2017) *Ennoiologiseis kai praktikes toy feminismou. Metapolitefsi kai 'meta.'* Athens: Foundation of the Greek Parliament [Spanou, Δ. (2017) «Πολιτικοποιώντας τα βιώματά μας στην εποχή της κρίσης. Η εμπειρία μέσα από το φύλο συκής», στον τόμο Βαΐου Ντ., Ψαρρά, Α. (επιμ.) (2017) *Εννοιολογήσεις και πρακτικές του φεμινισμού. Μεταπολίτευση και «μετά»*, Αθήνα: Ίδρυμα της Βουλής των Ελλήνων]

Stratigaki, M. (2017) 'Politikes isotitas sti Metapolitefsi. Thetika vimata, synechizomena kena,' in Vaiou, Nt., Psarra, A. (eds) (2017) *Ennoiologiseis kai praktikes toy feminismou. Metapolitefsi kai 'meta.'* Athens: Foundation of the Greek Parliament [Στρατηγάκη, Μ. (2017) «Πολιτικές ισοτήτας στη Μεταπολίτευση. Θετικά βήματα, συνεχιζόμενα κενά», στον τόμο Βαΐου Ντ., Ψαρρά, Α. (επιμ.) (2017) *Εννοιολογήσεις και πρακτικές του φεμινισμού. Μεταπολίτευση και «μετά»*, Αθήνα: Ίδρυμα της Βουλής των Ελλήνων]

Styllou, M. (2019) *I pali gia tin apeleftherosi ton gynaikon*, Athens: Marxistiko Vivliopoleio [Στύλλου, Μ. (2019) *Η πάλη για την απελευθέρωση των γυναικών*, Αθήνα: Μαρξιστικό Βιβλιοπωλείο]

Thanos, Th., Dimitriou, D., Douvali, A. (2022) 'Emfyles anisotites: o rolos tis anotaths ekpαιdefsis stin Ellada,' in Thanos, Th., Kogkidou, D. (eds) (2022) *Fylo kai ekpαιdefsi. Gia mia Symperiliptiki Ekpαιdefsi Xwris Via kai Diakriseis*, Thessaloniki: Tziolas [Θάνος, Θ., Δημητρίου, Δ., Δούβαλη, Α. (2022) «Έμφυλες ανισότητες: ο ρόλος της ανώτατης εκπαίδευσης στην Ελλάδα», στον τόμο Θάνος, Θ., Κογκίδου, Δ. (επιμ.) (2022) *Φύλο και εκπαίδευση. Για μια Συμπεριληπτική Εκπαίδευση Χωρίς Βία και Διακρίσεις*, Θεσσαλονίκη: Εκδόσεις Τζιόλα]

Vaiou, Nt. (2021) *I atheati ergasia ton gynaikon sti sygkrotisi tis polis. Opseis tis Athinas meta ti metapolitefsi*, Athens: Alexandria [Βαΐου, Ντ. (2021) *Η αθέατη εργασία των γυναικών στη συγκρότηση της πόλης. Όψεις της Αθήνας μετά τη μεταπολίτευση*, Αθήνα: Αλεξάνδρεια]

Vaiou, Nt., Psarra, A. (eds) (2017) *Ennoiologiseis kai praktikes toy feminismou. Metapolitefsi kai 'meta.'* Athens: Foundation of the Greek Parliament [Βαΐου Ντ., Ψαρρά, Α. (επιμ.) (2017) *Εννοιολογήσεις και πρακτικές του φεμινισμού. Μεταπολίτευση και «μετά»*, Αθήνα: Ίδρυμα της Βουλής των Ελλήνων]

Vaiou, Nt., Petraki, E., Stratigaki, M. (eds) (2021) *Emfyli via- Via kata ton gynaikon*, Athens: Alexandria [Βαΐου, Ντ., Πετράκη, Ε., Στρατηγάκη, Μ. (επιμ.) (2021) *Έμφυλη βία-Βία κατά των γυναικών*, Αθήνα: Αλεξάνδρεια]

Vougiouka, A. (2020) 'Gynaikoktonies: Diethnis Empeiria, politikes diastaseis,' in Petraki, G. (ed.) (2020) *Gynaikoktonies: diapistwseis, erotimata kai erotimatika*, Athens: Gutenberg [Vougiouka, A. (2020) «Γυναικοκτονίες: Διεθνής εμπειρία, πολιτικές διαστάσεις», στον τόμο Πετράκη, Γ. (επιμ.) (2020) *Γυναικοκτονίες: διαπιστώσεις, ερωτήματα και ερωτηματικά*, Αθήνα: Gutenberg]

Vougiouka, E., Koutsoulenti, A., Mpirmpilopoulou, A., Tsarmpopoulou-Fokianou, E., Psara, E. (2022) 'Omoethnikismos kai femoethnikismos sthn Ellada: h deksiopoiisi ton emfylon politikon taftotitas.' in Vasilaki, R., Souvlis, G. (eds) (2022) *I kanonikopoiisi tou akrodeksiou logou stin Ellada. Fylo, MME, Enoples Dynameis, Ekklisia*, Athens: Rosa Luxemburg Foundation [Vougiouka, E., Κουτσουλέντη, Α., Μπιρμπιλοπούλου, Α., Τσαρμποπούλου-Φωκιανού, Η., Ψαρά, Ε. (2022) «Ομοεθνικισμός και

φεμοεθνικισμός στην Ελλάδα: η δεξιοποίηση των έμφυλων πολιτικών ταυτότητας», στον τόμο των Βασιλάκη, Ρ., Σουβλής, Γ. (επιμ.) (2022) *Η κανονικοποίηση του ακροδεξιού λόγου στην Ελλάδα. Φύλο, ΜΜΕ, Ένοπλες Δυνάμεις, Εκκλησία*, Αθήνα: Ίδρυμα Ρόζα Λούξεμπουργκ]

Vonou, S. (2020) *Patriarchiki Dikaiosyni kai Feministikes Antistaseis*, Athens: Ano Teleia [Vonou, Σ. (2020) *Πατριαρχική Δικαιοσύνη και Φεμινιστικές Αντιστάσεις*, Αθήνα: Άνω Τελεία]

Xiradaki, K. (2020) *To feministiko kinima stin Ellada 1830-1936*, Athens: Koukkida [Ξηραδάκη, Κ. (2020) *Το φεμινιστικό κίνημα στην Ελλάδα 1830-1936*, Αθήνα: Εκδόσεις Κουκκίδα]

In English

Anastasiadou, M. (2020) Striking back: Right-wing gender politics in Greece, Gunda Werner Institute, Retrieved May 06, 2021, from <https://www.gwi-boell.de/en/2020/08/14/striking-back-right-wing-gender-politics-greece>

Antentas, J. M., & Vivas, E. (2014) The scissors of debt: Comments from Southern Europe. *WSQ: Women's Studies Quarterly*, 42(1-2), 49–64. <https://doi.org/10.1353/wsq.2014.0015>

Arampatzi, A., Kouki, H., & Pettas, D. (2022) Re-thinking solidarity movements as infrastructure during the COVID-19 pandemic crisis: Insights from Athens. *Social Movement Studies*, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14742837.2022.2134108>

Athanasiou, A. (2014) Precarious intensities: Gendered bodies in the streets and squares of Greece. *Signs: Journal of Women in Culture and Society*, 40(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1086/676917>

Avgeri, M. (2021) Transit: Transgender and gender nonconforming asylum claimants' narratives in Greece. *Sexualities*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13634607211013278>

Fotaki, M., & Daskalaki, M. (2021) Politicizing the body in the anti-mining protest in Greece. *Organization Studies*, 42(8), 1265–1290. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0170840619882955>

Carastathis, A. (2015) The politics of austerity and the affective economy of hostility: Racialised gendered violence and crises of belonging in Greece. *Feminist Review*, 109(1), 73–95. <https://doi.org/10.1057/fr.2014.50>

Carastathis, A. (2018). “gender is the first terrorist”: Homophobic and transphobic violence in Greece. *Frontiers: A Journal of Women Studies*, 39(2), 265. <https://doi.org/10.5250/fronjwomestud.39.2.0265>

Carastathis, A. (2019) Racism” versus “Intersectionality”? Significations of Interwoven Oppressions in Greek LGBTQ+ Discourses. *Feminist Critique: East European Journal of Feminist and Queer Studies*, 1(3).

Carastathis A, Spathopoulou A, Tsillimpounidi M (2018) Crisis, what crisis? Immigrants, refugees, and invisible struggles. *Refuge* 34(1): 29–38. <https://doi.org/10.7202/1050852ar>

Chroni, S. “A., & Kavoura, A. (2022) From silence to speaking up about sexual violence in Greece: Olympic journeys in a culture that neglects safety. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.862450>

Dagkouli-Kyriakoglou, M. (2021) ‘When housing is provided, but you have only the closet’. sexual orientation and family housing support in Athens, Greece. *Social & Cultural Geography*, 23(9), 1257–1274. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14649365.2021.1910989>

Daskalaki, M., & Fotaki, M. (2017) The neoliberal crisis: Alternative organizing and spaces of/for feminist solidarity. In *Feminists and queer theorists debate the future of critical management studies*. Emerald Publishing Limited.

European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) (2022) Gender Equality Index 2022 The COVID-19 pandemic and care. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2022. doi:10.2839/035888

Fotaki, M. (2022) Solidarity in crisis? Community responses to refugees and forced migrants in the Greek islands. *Organization*, 29(2), 295–323. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13505084211051048>

Fotaki, M., & Daskalaki, M. (2020) Politicizing the body in the anti-mining protest in Greece. *Organization Studies*, 42(8), 1265–1290. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0170840619882955>

Gaitanou, E. (2017) Fight like a girl: Social Movement and feminism(s) amid the crisis in Greece. *Feministische Studien*, 35(2), 243–258. <https://doi.org/10.1515/fs-2017-0028>

Gaitanou, E. (2018) Feminism in times of crisis: Woman struggle in Greece.

General Secretariat for Family Policy and Gender Equality (2020) 1st Annual Report on Violence against Women. Available online: https://www.isotita.gr/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/First-Report-on-Violence-Against-Women_GSFPE.pdf (accessed on 12 January 2022).

Healy, J., Levell, J., & Cole, T. (2022) An intersectional analysis of domestic abuse perpetrator service adaptation during COVID-19: Findings from the UK, cyprus, Greece, Italy, Romania. *Journal of Gender-Based Violence*, 6(2), 348–363. <https://doi.org/10.1332/239868021x16425822261273>

Kambouri, N., & Zavos, A. (2010) On the frontiers of citizenship: Considering the case of Konstantina Kouneva and the intersections between gender, migration and labour in Greece. *Feminist Review*, 94(1), 148–155. <https://doi.org/10.1057/fr.2009.42>

Kouki, H., & Chatzidakis, A. (2020) Implicit feminist solidarity(ies)? the role of gender in the social movements of the Greek crisis. *Gender, Work & Organization*, 28(3), 878–897. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gwao.12540>

Kyriakidou, M. (2010). 'Another World is Possible as Long as it is Feminist Too': Dissenting Discourses and Acts by Greek Leftist Feminists. *Interface: a journal for and about social movements*, 2(1), 214–220.

Lathiotaki, K., Koutra, K., Ratsika, N., & Saint Arnault, D. (2021) Trauma recovery of Greek women who have experienced gender-based violence: A narrative research. *Sexes*, 2(3), 256–271. <https://doi.org/10.3390/sexes2030021>

Poteyeva, M., & Wasileski, G. (2016) Domestic violence against Albanian immigrant women in Greece: Facing patriarchy. *Social Sciences*, 5(3), 37. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci5030037>

Remoundou, N. (2022) Wronged bodies: Gendering human rights abuses in contemporary Greek poetry. *Law and Humanities*, 16(1), 28–58. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17521483.2022.2075177>

Sjöstedt Landén, A., & Fotaki, M. (2018) Gender and struggles for equality in mining resistance movements: Performing critique against neoliberal capitalism in Sweden and Greece. *Social Inclusion*, 6(4), 25–35.

Appendix

Institutional actors:²⁷

- General Secretariat for Family Policy and Gender Equality (isotita.gr) – ‘GSFPGE’ henceforth
- Research Centre for Gender Equality (kethi.gr)
- Ombudsperson (Sector of equal treatment) (www.gov.gr)
- Gender equality committee of Central Union of Municipalities of Greece (KEDE) ([ΙΣΟΤΗΤΑΣ | KEΔΕ \(kede.gr](http://ΙΣΟΤΗΤΑΣ | KEΔΕ (kede.gr))
- Gender Equality office of the Association of Greek Regions (EN.P.E.) (enpe.gr)

In addition, there are Service units of the Ministries for Equality and municipal equality committees

Political party organisations

- Enosi Ginaikon Ellados (ege.gr)
- Federation of women of Greece (oge.gr)
- Kinisi Dhokratikon Ginaikon (parliament.gr) [no longer active]

University centers/laboratories

- Center for Gender Studies – Panteion University (genderstudies.panteion.gr)
- Culture Border Gender Laboratory – University of Macedonia <http://cbg-lab.uom.gr/en/> (cbg-lab.uom.gr)
- Center of New Media and Feminist Public Practices (centrefeministmedia.arch.uth.gr)

University gender equality committees (under formation, to be completed in the coming months)

Autonomous groups:

- Anarchically Queerect
- antifa sisterhood

²⁷ This list was drawn from the following sources: Εργαστήριο Σπουδών Φύλου και Ισότητας (panteion.gr), Χάρτης ομάδων/πρωτοβουλιών σχετικών με ζητήματα φύλου (notafeministproject.gr), Ισότητα των Φύλων - Υπουργείο Εργασίας και Κοινωνικών Υποθέσεων (ypergasias.gov.gr)

- Blender Patras
- Athens Festival of Queer Performance
- Conquerer [no longer active]
- Endropi
- Faggotaz
- bitchy 101
- Proud Parents Greece [Υπερήφανοι Γονείς]
- Fuerza femenina
- Kiouria [Κιουρί@]
- KamiaAnohi [Καμιά Ανοχή]²⁸:
- Feministiki Omada Kilotina [Φεμινιστική Ομάδα Κιλοτίνα]
- 8 March Assembly [Συνέλευση 8ης Μάρτη]
- Kontrosol [Κοντροσόλ]
- Femin@tre [Φέμιν@ tre]
- Ta tsilorifa [Τα τσιλόριφα]
- Selana – Women’s initiative against gender based violence [Σελάνα: Πρωτοβουλία γυναικών για την αντιμετώπιση της έμφυλης βίας]
- Polichromi Polipolitismiki Ombrela Ksanthis [Πολύχρωμη Πολυπολιτισμική Ομπρέλα Ξάνθης] [Πολύχρωμη, Πολυπολιτισμική Ομπρέλα Ξάνθης Π.Π.Ο.Ξ](#)
- Vlachontanes [Βλαχοντάνες]
- Thessaloniki Queer Arts Festival (TQAF)²⁹
- Queer ntekapaz
- Sabbat - Burn the Rich not the Witch
- Radical Pride [no longer active]

²⁸ The enduring initiative called ‘Kamia Anochi’ (No Tolerance) formed in 2017 after the emergence of a common assembly of various feminist organizations on the 25th November, at the International Day for the Elimination of Violence against Women (Gaitanou, 2017). According to Gaitanou (2017), it was the first time in the past years that a unified front of different collectives had emerged, with the participation of people and groups coming from different traditions (of the Left and the Anarchy) but ready to unite into common practices and debates. This initiative was to be continued through the whole year of 2017, convening once every two weeks, and leading to an equally massive mobilization on March 8, at the International Women’s Day. ‘Kamia Anochi’ is still active.

²⁹ TQAF is a grassroots initiative that sets out to alter deeply entrenched misconceptions and prejudices toward the queer and LGBTQIA community through artistic and cultural practices.

- Patras Pride [[Pride Πάτρας](#)]
- HOMOphonia Thessaloniki Pride
- Lesbian group of Thessaloniki [[Λεσβιακή Ομάδα Θεσσαλονίκης \(ΛΟΘ\)](#)]
- The house of women [Το σπίτι γυναικών]
- LGBTQI+ Refugees Welcome Athens
- Lesvos Lgbtiq+ Refugee Solidarity
- Eclipse/Alkusuf LGBTQI+ Refugees Thessaloniki [Eclipse](#)
- Protouvoulia ginaikon enantia sto xreos kai ti litothta [Πρωτοβουλία γυναικών ενάντια στο χρεος και στα μέτρα λιτότητας]
- Political Fatties
- Adesmefti kinisi ginaikon [Αδέσμευτη Κίνηση Γυναικών]

Ad-Hoc groups

- Bra stards no longer active]
- JUSTICE 4 ZAK/ZACKIE
- Without consent is rape [Χωρίς Συναίνεση Είναι Βιασμός]
- Feminist Solidarity Initiative with Konstantina Kouneva [Φεμινιστική Πρωτοβουλία Αλληλεγγύης στην Κωνσταντίνα Κούνεβα]

NGOs, Social Cooperative Enterprises [SCEs], Associations

- Colour Youth
- Emantes
- G-All
- Genderhood
- Orlando LGBT+
- Beaver³⁰
- Women on Top

³⁰ Beaver is a member of the Workers Cooperatives Network of Athens and one of the first women-only initiatives that has been established recently in Greece. Many of the democratic practices and process-oriented aspects of feminism appear to be embedded into the decision-making processes of some of these solidarity initiatives (Daskalaki & Fotaki 2017).

- Proud Seniors
- Transgender Support Association [Σωματείο Υποστήριξης Διεμφυλικών -ΣΥΔ]
- Rainbow School [[Πολύχρωμο Σχολείο](#)]
- Rainbow Families Greece [[Οικογένειες Ουράνιο Τόξο](#)]
- Gay and Lesbian Community of Greece [Ομοφυλοφιλική & Λεσβιακή Κοινότητα Ελλάδας – ΟΛΚΕ] https://www.wikiwand.com/el/Ομοφυλοφιλική_Λεσβιακή_Κοινότητα_Ελλάδας
- Thessaloniki Pride
- Athens Pride
- Phylis
- National council of Greek women
- Association of greek women scientists
- Elliniki etaireia ginaikon panepistimiakon
- YWCA Greece
- Red Umbrella
- United African Women Organization
- Istorikoi gia thn erevna sthn Istoría ton Ginaikon kai tou Filou [Ιστορικοί για την Έρευνα στην Ιστορία των Γυναικών και του Φύλου]
- LOAT AMEA
- Feminist Autonomous Center for research [Φεμινιστικό Αυτόνομο Κέντρο Έρευνας – ΦΑΚ]
- Omada SYLVIA RIVERA – Gia ena kinimatiko THESSALONIKI PRIDE [ΟΜΑΔΑ SYLVIA RIVERA – ΓΙΑ ΕΝΑ ΚΙΝΗΜΑΤΙΚΟ THESSALONIKI PRIDE]

Other

- Strap-On Unicorns
- Theatranes
- Qreclaim
- Rainbow Dance
- Queer Ink
- FemMap Project
- SexHarassMap Χάρτης [Καταγραφής σεξιστικής/έμφυλης Βίας]
- Gender Panic Collective
- Outview queer film festival

- This is not a feminist project

Art spaces/ Museum/cultural center

- The Queer Archive
- Kangelia Tromokratisch
- Ntizeza
- FYTINI [not active]
- Athens Museum of Queer Arts ([AMOQA](#)) [Αθηναϊκό μουσείο κούηρ τεχνών]

Journals

- Antivirus
- Feministiq
- Plaza Girls
- Kiouria [Κιουρί@]
- To mov
- Fyliko Oxy [Φυλικό Οξύ]
- Terminal 119
- Teflon

Club

- SLAM Athens

No information

- WildCat
- Over the Rainbow - Story Time
- Fluffy
- Ομάδα Πύραυλος
- Σασμάν
- Οι λερωμένες/οι
- Fight Back Club
- Women's collective 61

4 ITALY

4.1 Introduction

In the period 2010-2021, feminist movements in Italy have proliferated and have increased their presence in public space and institutions as well as their influence on policies. At the beginning of the decade there was a great variety of collectives, groups and associations that ranged from queer approaches to the fight against gender-based violence. These groups have been highly involved in countering the anti-gender/anti-feminist movements. From 2016 on, the new wave of the transnational feminist movements focused on gender-based violence conceived as a structural dimension of contemporary capitalist and neoliberal society (Gago and Cavallero 2019). The wave started in Argentina upon the femicide of Chiara Paez, a 14-year-old woman murdered by her boyfriend, and soon reached Italy, where it triggered a huge mobilization at the national and local level led by the new organization named after the Argentinian one, Non Una Di Meno - NUDM (Not One Less) (Barone and Bonu 2022).

Academic and activist circles turned their attention to new issues emerging from the feminist movements. First of all, gender-based violence was seen as a lens to understand social structures, gender socialization and the shape of state institutions (Terzian 2017). Second, there was a concern with the material dimension of feminist claims, for instance with regard to labour condition of women, lesbian, trans and non-binary people; the pauperization and precarization of life; increasing gender inequality; the retrenchment of the welfare system and public services (Transnational social strike platform 2018, Morini 2010, 2022). Third, there was a focus on health and reproductive rights, against the increasing attacks on abortion and women's freedom over their body (Balzano 2021, Settembrini 2020). Fourth, claims for LGBTQ+ rights also addressed the parliamentary debate on the so-called DDL Zan, a proposed law on the criminalisation of homophobia and transphobia and hate crimes, which was never approved, not even under a center-left coalitional government (Zan 2021). Finally, academic and activist circles turned their attention to migration, both because of gendered migration flows and because of the growth of a "second generation" of citizens with a migrant background (Vianello 2014, Martorano and Prearo 2020, Redini, Vianello and Zaccagnini 2020, Rigo 2022).

With regard to the composition of feminist movements, several novelties emerge. For the first time after years of highly conflictual fragmentation within the field of feminisms, the NUDM-led mobilizations keep together most feminist groups, associations and collectives, ranging from the national network of anti-violence services, called D.i.Re (women's network against gender based violence); queer and transfeminist groups; women's houses and feminist spaces; the female component of some trade unions; feminist and women's associations formed during previous waves of feminism; social centers and individuals (Cirimele and Panariello 2018, Barone and Bonu 2022, Bonu 2022). This variety of actors brings together a variety of ideologies, from historical feminism to intersectionality and queer theory. As Chironi noted, NUDM can be considered as an intergenerational movement, as it "became the point of connection between different generations and between feminist and LGBT movements, which had traditionally remained separate" (2019: 6). NUDM has been highly innovative also in terms of repertoire of action. Beside massive public protests, internal deliberative democracy and self-consciousness work, NUDM engages in the feminist strike, which were mainly called on the 8th of March, International Women's Day. This form of action "deeply re-signified the practice of striking itself, first by enacting the strike without relying on traditional trade unions, which in many cases ignored the call, and second by inviting women to withdraw both from productive work and from care and reproductive work" (Barone and Bonu 2022: #).

The literature on feminist movements has focused on some eventful protests as critical juncture. This was the case for the 25th of November 2016 – the first massive protest organized by NUDM – and the mobilizations on the same day in the following years (Montella, Picchi and Fiorletta 2019, Constelacìon Feminista 2020, Salvatori 2021) as well as for the 8th of March, the day of the feminist strike (Pavan and Mainardi 2018, Rudan and Non una di meno Roma 2018, Constelacìon feminista 2020, Salvatori 2021). These moments consolidated NUDM's collective identity, formalised its organizational model

and repertoires of action, and enabled the movement's claims and discourses to be defined. In addition, the moments of mass mobilisation increased the perception of an active, widespread and competent feminist movement in the construction of democracy, institutions and policies.

Despite the capacity to mobilise, the proliferation of feminist assemblies in local contexts and the size of public protests, highly debated issues cut across the feminist movement: first of all, the issue of sex work (Garofalo Geymonat and Selmi 2022), then, the issue of gender identity and the de-essentialisation of womanhood (Francheschini et al. 2021, Cirillo et al. 2021), finally, reproductive rights and surrogacy (Cirillo 2017).

The resurgence of feminist mobilisations has also renewed analyses, academic publications and public debate on the subject. On the one hand, these analyses have focused explicitly on the feminist movement, for example through the increased publication of books, articles, blogs, translations and events on feminist topics (see the special issue "Planetaria. Femminismi internazionali", DWF 1-2 (129-130), 2021). On the other hand, they have addressed topics on which the feminist movement has historically elaborated discourses, e.g. the role of care, women's work, abortion rights, the family, reproduction.

4.2 The history of the feminist movements and its context

Italy has been considered as belonging to a "Latin model" of access to citizenship which, contrary to the "Anglo-Saxon" and the "Nordic" model, is characterized by a long delay in terms of civic rights. In post-war Italy, women had to overcome the discriminatory provisions of Fascist laws which reduced the possibilities for women to enter certain careers, set women's salaries at 50 percent of the norm and fixed quotas for women's participation in the labor force. In the 1960s and 1970s, after several decades of democracy, the laws on contraception and abortion still dated from the Fascist regime (1926 and 1930, respectively), and the fascist Codice Rocco made adultery punishable by law for women but not for men. Democratization radically changed this situation. First of all, the principle of equality of all citizens before the law irrespective of their sex is included in the Constitution. After authoritarian rule, legal reforms established the principle of equality of obligations and rights of both spouses within marriage. Parental authority, previously assigned to the father alone, belongs now to both parents and children acquired the same rights towards their parents no matter if they are biological or adopted, or born within or out of the wedlock. Civil marriage was introduced in 1970, together with the co-responsibility for the management of material goods, as well as in the education of the children, was legally affirmed in 1975 in Italy (Sineau 1992, 543). Civil divorce has been established and access to contraception was liberalized after authoritarian rule. The Italian Abortion Act (no.194/78), passed in 1978, allows women to choose whether to have an abortion and have the right to free assistance, provided that they are over 18 years of age, have medical, social or economic reasons to abort, are within 90 days of pregnancy, and reflected on their choice for at least seven days following a medical visit. Doctors were given however the right to refuse to perform abortions for reasons of conscience.

While women in most of Europe obtained the right to vote after the First World War, in Italy this only took place with the founding of the Republic after the Second World War. Women's policy agencies emerged very late. The creation of the two main equality agencies - the Equal Status and Equal Opportunities National Committee and the Equal Status Committee for the Implementation of Equal Treatment and Equal Opportunities for Men and Women in the Workplace - constituted the main women's policy machine. They were established with the task of furthering gender equality, singling out actual instances of discrimination and promoting equality within the state administration at the regional, provincial and municipal level. At the local level, the alliance between women in party institutions and feminist groups (often consolidated through "double militancy") significantly advanced the development of women's policy agencies.

As in other Catholic countries, the alliance between first-wave feminism and the Left was very relevant also during the second wave of feminist activism with parties from the socialist and communist party families being key supporters of many women's struggles. The predominance of the socialist and

communist forces during the Resistance to fascism brought about the alignment of emerging claims with the Left, and "other" movements had to accept the leadership of the main constituency of the Left, the workers. However, the struggle against fascism represented an important political experience for many women. Women, who had mobilized in the struggle for democracy, participated in the building of the new institutions. The need to construct democratic institutions, however, reduced the space for autonomous women's movements. The legacy of the past may explain the apparent paradox of a path to women's citizenship which is led by the Left, but where social rights appear to be particularly underdeveloped in comparison with political and civic rights. In fact, it was the traditional weakness of the left-wing forces that brought about a particularistic welfare state regime, which tends to give special protection to some social groups from which women are excluded (Ferrera 1996; Esping-Anderson 1990).

For the women's movements in the 1970s and the 1980s (as well as for environmentalists and pacifists), left-wing parties were the target of criticism but also natural allies. In the "pragmatic" 1980s, the women's movement managed to take advantage of a situation in which the political parties were becoming increasingly disinterested in the concrete aspects of certain policy areas by entering into direct relations with the public administration.

In Italy, as elsewhere, the social movements of the 1970s were characterized by the claim to autonomy from the "hegemony" of class conflict, as well as by the proclamation of diversity against imposed equality. In its incubatory phase, the women's movement presented itself primarily as cultural, aiming to transform the value system and the way of doing politics. Progressively, it developed specific policy demands regarding a number of issues, including the economic system, hours of work, and discrimination in hiring practices and wages.

The Old Left influenced the organizational, ideological and strategic characteristics of the Italian women's movement. In its organizational structure, the women's movement combined the decentralized structure typical of new social movements with resources for coordination provided not only by the UDI (Italian Women's Union, connected to PCI, the Italian Communist Party) but also by parties of the Old and New Left and trade unions. The alliance with the Old Left allowed the women's movement in Italy to combine mobilization both within and beyond institutional politics, and to bring together identity-oriented counterculture with policy-oriented mobilization.

The period 2010-2021 opened in Italy with the mobilization of "Se non ora, quando? (SNOQ)" (If not now, when?), which addressed in particular the sex scandals of Prime Minister Silvio Berlusconi. The first public event, in January 2011, was intended to denounce the portrayal of women produced by the prime minister, after the public denunciation of the orgiastic festivities organized by and for him (Enslar 2012, Cavalleri and Robiony 2017). From that moment on, the movement developed through a national confederation of local groups, intended to claim women's emancipation. Over time, that campaign has slipped towards an institutionalization within party politics and a moralistic approach to feminism (Elia 2016). Nevertheless, SNOQ was for some years the main promoter of public expressions of feminist mobilisation.

In the meanwhile smaller and more diffuse feminist collectives, groups and associations continued to proliferate (Bertilotti et al. 2018). These groups carried forward both historical feminism and more recent developments, with a particular focus on queer theory, intersectionality and anti-racism. In the years characterized by the relative absence of mass mobilisations, feminist groups continued to preserve the ideology, discourses, networks and structures of the feminist movement (Taylor 1989, Bertilotti et al. 2018). As an example, since 2012 and for a few years the informal network of trans feminist and queer collectives *Sommovimento nazioAnale*³¹ (hereafter SN) developed discourses and practices on affective ties beyond the nuclear family, sex work, health and reproductive rights, trans

³¹ <https://sommovimentonazioanale.noblogs.org/chi-siamo/>, last visit 16th November 2022.

and non-binary approaches, gender strike, decoloniality, borders regime, job precariat, violence, as well as production of alternative knowledge. This network, together with LGBTIQ movements, was involved in the reaction to the first anti-gender mobilization in Italy, against the “Sentinelle in piedi” and pro-life mobilisations (Lavizzari 2019). Those mobilisations have been the basis for the birth of NUDM in the spring of 2016. Since then, NUDM has been the largest container of the movement's various souls, bringing together anti-violence centres and occupied spaces, women's associations and health counselling centres (Chironi 2019, Barone and Bonu 2022). More than claiming for women's emancipation, NUDM carries out a re-politicization of the field of feminist politics by adopting an intersectional approach in the contestation of the neoliberal order, the gender regime and the border regime (Cirimele and Panariello 2018).

As already mentioned, the SNOQ mobilization targeted the Berlusconi's government, that supported discourses and policies that were strongly conservative but also dismissive of women's emancipation (Simone 2012, Dominijanni 2014). The economic crisis and the worsening of social and gender inequalities have paved the way for a growing malaise, later conveyed within the feminist movements (Kantola and Lombardo 2017). Over time, the economic crisis spiraled with the health and ecological crises, with the ensuing worsening of women's living conditions (Marceddu et al. 2022). Moreover, gender-based violence has continued to proliferate, in the form of feminicides and of abuse, mistreatment, harassment and rape (Pietrobelli et al. 2020, Demurtas et al. 2021). In these same years, the spread of anti-gender/anti-feminist movements began to challenge the use of the concept of gender and the claims made by the feminist movement up to that time. Over time, the link between religious groups and the ultra-right became more and more evident, with an ensuing growth of radical right parties, culminating in the election of Giorgia Meloni (from “post-fascist Fratelli d'Italia, Brothers of Italy”) in September 2022 as prime minister of a coalition government of the centre and extreme right. This context of multiple crises has triggered new social demands, including that of women, lesbians, trans and non-binary people (Bonu 2022).

Quite commonly, the history of the feminist movements in the period 2010-2021 has been punctuated by eventful protests (della Porta 2020), producing innovative mobilization. As already mentioned, SNOQ called for a mobilization on the 13th of February 2011 – after a public letter against discourses and policies of the Berlusconi's government that “infringed on the dignity of women”. Protests took place in more than 100 squares across Italy, and that in Rome involved one million people. After that, promoters of the mobilizations gathered together in July to organize at the national level the campaign as a confederation of groups. The same pattern worked for NUDM, few years later. The first eventful protest took place on the 26th of November 2016, with a march for the international day against gender-based violence. Thousands of people marched in a national demonstration in Rome, and the day after around one thousand people gathered together in a national assembly that formalized the birth of NUDM feminist movement coalition. Moreover, in that occasion, the decision was made to join the call for a strike on the 8th of March of the forthcoming year launched by Ni Una Menos, the feminist movement in Argentina, so paving the way to the transnational dimension of the feminist movement and the elaboration of a new form of action – the feminist strike. The second eventful protest, on March 8th 2017, took place in hundreds of Italian cities through public protests and the withdrawal from productive and reproductive work (Del Re et al. 2020). From then on, every 25th of November and 8th of March NUDM organizes public protests – in Rome or in all the local contexts where the movement is rooted.

Feminist movements in Italy are historically strongly related to local contexts, but with some coordination at the national level. While before the birth of NUDM collectives and feminist groups were informally connected to European allies and similar groups, with NUDM the transnational connection shifted scale. Since the beginning, the movement strongly networked with other European and non-European countries (such as US, Argentina, Chile, Mexico and so on). Since 2019, after the transnational mobilization against the World Congress of Families in Verona, the network has been formalized into the “Feministas transfronterizas”, that collects dozens of groups and movements around the globe and coordinates events and transnational protests (Assemblea transnazionale di Non una di meno 2021).

So far, the major challenges the movement faced has been the advance of anti-gender/anti-feminist movements in political parties and governments, but also in local contexts. Their growing presence in institutions—including now in the national government—allows anti-gender groups to influence policies and discourses on abortion, parenthood, surrogacy, hate crimes, sex work and so on (Cirillo 2018). This is moreover not fully balanced by the presence of institutional allies as the main center-left party of the time, the Partito Democratico, including a Catholic component has been at the best lukewarm towards feminist claims while the recently emerged progressive party, the Movimento 5 Stelle (the 5 Stars Movement), while supporting some claims on civil rights, lacked historical ties with feminist mobilizations (della Porta, Kouki, Mosca and Fernandez 2019).

4.3 Actors, organizations and organizational models

The SNOQ protests were organised by women coming from different backgrounds: political parties, institutions, journalism, universities—not, however, by feminist groups and associations. Informal networks such as SN were, instead, networks of transfeminist and queer groups, autonomous social centres, self-managed feminist spaces and occupations. The mobilization forms were initially influenced by the respective capacity to call for public protests and also by the actors involved in the organizations. Indeed, the connection with mainstream media and institutions helped SNOQ to spread their message and calls for action (Elia 2016, Mattoni and Pavan 2019), while informal networks of collectives were struggling to get media attention (Cossutta 2021). However, the actors involved in NUDM were quite diverse. NUDM is structured as a multi-level organization and includes anti-violence centres and associations, social centres and civil society organizations, as well as individuals (Chironi 2019, Barone and Bonu 2022). The movement was in fact capable, especially at its origin, to attract most of feminist and women's associations, groups and collectives that had been active in Italy in the previous 20 years (Cirimele and Panariello 2018). Progressively, the movement became structured in local assemblies in which the different actors, while maintaining their own identity and autonomy, were required to converge horizontally in the collective creation of NUDM assemblies.

SNOQ had chosen a relative hierarchical organization, with a confederation of local groups and a national board (Elia 2016). SN, instead, developed mechanisms of deliberative democracy and horizontal decision-making, without internal bodies and formalized structures (Acquistapace 2022). Similarly, NUDM has adopted a consensus-based approach, without representatives and hierarchies, being composed of local assemblies that periodically gather together in a national assembly. While the main decisions regarding national campaigns and general frames are made in the national assembly, local assemblies preserve the autonomy for decisions referring to local mobilizations (Cirimele and Panariello 2018).

SNOQ referred to the feminism of difference and women's emancipation, which were quite resonant with ideas developed by state feminism (Lovenduski 2005, Elia 2016). This ideological approach considered institutions fundamental to the development of women's emancipation, develops strategies for interaction with mainstream media and institutions and has sometimes been associated with liberal feminism (Elia 2016). Queer and transfeminist ideology, instead, oriented networks of collectives to reject interactions with public institutions, and to rather develop horizontality and deliberative democracy (Mura, Peroni and Veneri 2016, Zappino 2016, Acquistapace 2022). Given its diverse internal composition, NUDM bridged the two models around some principles expressed in the "Piano femminista contro la violenza maschile sulle donne e la violenza di genere" (Feminist plan against male violence on women and gender-based violence)³². This plan sums up the common orientation of the movement, in the sense of transfeminism and intersectionality (Chironi 2019, Barone and Bonu 2022). While not advocating a direct dialogue with public institutions,

³² https://nonunadimeno.files.wordpress.com/2017/11/abbiamo_un_piano.pdf, last visit 17th of November.

NUDM proposed concrete solutions from below that would challenge public institutions to act in some directions, while remaining however outside them (Cirimele and Panariello 2018).

In terms of composition, SNOQ has been initially promoted by middle-class, middle-age, white and cis women (Cavalleri and Robiony 2017). However, as soon as mobilization developed, the composition changed by including younger and lower-class women (Elia 2016). Quite differently, the networks of queer and transfeminist collectives presented since the beginning a younger composition, mainly white, and was based on queer and LGBTQ+ people (Zappino 2016). Finally, NUDM has been launched by relatively young women, with a broad spectrum of class background, and the aspiration to involve also racialized people (despite the mainly white composition of the movement) (Barone and Bonu 2022). A major innovation of NUDM has been the cross-generational alliances between different sectors of feminisms, in terms of both age and ideology (Chironi 2019).

Despite their differences, SNOQ, SN and NUDM developed around a similar organizational model based upon local nodes and a national coordination. While SNOQ was however quite hierarchical, SN and NUDM always claimed for horizontality in the decision-making process and organization. While SNOQ was less connected at the transnational level, SN developed informal networks in Europe and beyond and NUDM formally established a global network called *Feministas transfronterizas*.

4.4 Allies

Despite an historically-rooted skeptical approach to institutions (Lussana 2012), SNOQ developed contacts with some sectors of mainstream media as well as local and national political parties and governments (Cavalleri and Robiony 2017). SNOQ openly aimed to go beyond the approach of consciousness rising within small groups, detached from the direct implication in political processes, by claiming a direct involvement in the Italian democratic institutions, oriented to challenge the conception of women underpinned by the Berlusconi's government (Elia 2016, Cavalleri and Robiony 2017). To do so, the social movement organization built relations with journalism, media, municipalities, political parties, political actors. This choice reflects the composition of the founders of the movement, made of public actors (such as journalists, academics, film-makers, professionals and so on) that had a background in feminist politics but were also involved in the Italian public sphere. Ideology and strategy, thus, are strictly connected to the framing process, that foresees women as necessarily engaged in the transformation of democracy, beyond the anti-institutional bias. At that moment, the main linkages were with institutional actors, while other connections (with the environmental movement, with the worker movements) were less developed. In this sense, the strategic approach was open collaboration with state institutions and political parties. This choice increased the distance with more radical feminist collectives that rejected to be fully involved in SNOQ mobilization because of its progressive involvement with state institutions (Cavalleri and Robiony 2017).

Among the feminist groups that occasionally took part in SNOQ mobilizations while remaining critical of them were the groups that, in 2013, gave birth to the network of *Sommovimento NazioAnale*. These groups generally adopted an anti-institutional framework, pursuing self-organization and self-management (Mura, Peroni and Veneri 2016, Zappino 2016). The creation of health services – such as the “consultorie” – happened without negotiation with local authorities (municipalities, hospitals, public health services and so on), involving instead informal networks including professional workers (doctors, gynecologists, psychologists, educators and so on) (Busi and Fiorilli 2015). Because of this ideological stance, they rejected a direct engagement with state institutions, within a strategy of total rejection. Because of their composition, frames, ideology and repertoire of action, they searched for alliances with anti-racist groups, environmentalist and workers' movements, as in the case of the social strike in 2015 or the struggle against Frontex and the progressive closure of the borders of Europe (Campesi 2015). Moreover, the network had to face anti-gender mobilization resisting which involved building alliances with LGBTQ+ groups and feminist associations (Lavizzari 2019). The alliance structure was bottom up, fluid and adaptable to mutating purposes. Starting from an anti-institutional position, the network has built alliances of purpose at local and national levels, as in the case of sex workers'

rights, queer resistance to neo-fascist and far-right movements, or the contestation of the civil unions law, which was in fact considered as offering “second-class” rights³³.

Differently, locating itself in-between the open collaboration developed by SNOQ and the total rejection of queer and transfeminist groups (Chironi 2019, 2020), NUDM developed occasional and multi-scalar negotiation with state institutions. The plurality of the organizations, that as mentioned involved since the beginning thousands of groups, associations, civil society organizations as well as individual activists, included groups that were already involved in institutional politics. As an example, the network of D.i.R.E (Donne in Rete contro la Violenza, Women in network against violence), in which feminist anti-violence centres converged, and UDI (Unione Donne Italiane, Union of women in Italy), founded between 1944 and 1945 from women involved in anti-fascist resistance and near to the Italian Communist Party. While not directly part of public institutions, these groups do collaborate, at different levels, with local and national authorities. NUDM engaged in the collective writing of a grass-root plan against male violence and gender-based violence, that aimed to connect the ideological and operational ideas of the movement, but also to connect with the institutional plan against violence that the National Committee for Equal Opportunities of the Ministry of Labour releases every three years. The document prepared by the movement was not aimed at a direct dialogue with institutions, but rather intended to propose an alternative from below through the elaboration of concepts, solutions, actions and strategies to combat violence from a radically feminist and therefore political perspective (Cirimele and Panariello 2018). The plan represents a test case to measure the movement's intention to negotiate with state institutions, collectively defining limits but also areas of contact. Another interesting case in point is the feminist strike, launched every 8th of March since 2017. In this case, the confederal trade unions are usually invited to join the strike, even if they are not directly involved in the construction of the event. This example of action represents NUDM's way of engaging in a power play on labour issues with the major institutions that have the legitimacy to organise and intervene on the issue of labour, namely the trade unions (Arfini and Busi 2020).

NUDM has built alliances with environmental movements, such as Fridays for future, with workers' movements, such as the Tuscan GKN dispute, with migrant workers, such as the Bologna migrant coordination. These alliances respond to NUDM's ideology, which is open to an intersectional feminism that recognises the axes of oppression on which social inequalities are based, and consequently produces alliances with subjects who, despite their differences, are equally subject to social inequalities (Chironi 2019).

4.5 Themes and agendas

4.5.1 Gender based violence

The strongest thematic area that brings together all the movement organizations described so far is gender-based violence. This topic gained increasing attention during the 1970s, becoming a core field of intervention for feminist movements all along the last 40 years (Pietrobelli et al. 2020). The centrality of the issue is consistent with the size of the problem: according to ISTAT (the main statistical institution in Italy), one out of three women experience forms of violence – whether physical or psychological, including rape and murder but also harassment and abuse. More than 100 women are killed every year by a partner, a friend, or a relative (Demurtas, Peroni and Mauri 2021).

In the case of SNOQ the issue of violence emerged because of sexual scandals involving then Prime Minister Berlusconi, accused of organizing orgiastic parties as well as sex-money exchanges. Thus, the stigmatization of gender-based violence mainly addressed state institutions and political actors, accused of the creation of discriminatory and dismissive representation of the role of women in the

³³ <https://sommovimentonazionale.noblogs.org>, last visit 07-12-22.

Italian society. In order to address the issue, SNOQ called the government to resign (Cavalleri and Robiony 2017). While able to influence public opinion on the issue of the mistreatment of women, the protest were however unsuccessful in changing the institutional system (as the governmental crisis was rather related with other scandals involving the Prime Minister). The reaction of the general public was ambivalent and so was the internal management of the theme and agenda within the movement. On one hand, the movement was often divided between a more normative and essentialist understanding of women and a more libertarian and critical understanding of gender socialization. On the other hand, part of the general public justified the prime minister (as following natural sex instincts) or even shared his dismissive representation and treatment of women (Elia 2016).

The network of queer and feminist groups has engaged with gender-based violence above all for what concerns gender and sexuality. In its reaction to anti-gender mobilization, it stressed that the family, which was at the centre of the claims of anti-gender groups, was the privileged site of domestic violence (Zappino 2016). It also focused on the homophobia promoted by anti-gender groups as a form of hatred and discrimination against LGBTQ+ people (Acquistapace 2022). Being strongly anti-institutional, the proposed solutions were not expressed in terms of the production of anti-discrimination laws, but rather in the form of mutualism, resistance from below and the opening of safe spaces in occupied buildings with the aim of building new forms of community and new relationships.

Finally, NUDM put the issue of gender-based violence at the centre of its political battle (Cirimele and Panariello 2018). Gender-based violence is considered structural to society and therefore part of the way that gender relations are articulated in all spheres - family, work, school, public space, institutions, borders and so on. The counterpart is not singled out simply in state institutions or harassing men, but rather in the male culture and the patriarchal system. In response to this problem, the movement has developed a number of solutions, both political and substantive such as the funding of anti-violence centres, the dissemination of gender and difference education, the fight against gender stereotypes, and the contrast to gender gap in jobs and careers (Chironi 2019). The spread of the movement has allowed the issue of violence against women to become more widespread and present both locally and nationally. Yet, it is difficult to assess how much the movement has been able to influence the decision-making process, not least because of the growing consensus towards anti-gender and far-right groups, which, on their side, propose a very different view of gender-based violence (Pavan 2020). The general public has reacted with a growing sensitivity towards the topic, even though violence is often still considered an emergency phenomenon rather than a structural element of Italian gender regime.

4.5.2 Health and reproductive rights

A second relevant issue for the feminist movement in Italy is that of health and reproductive rights. Since the 1970s, feminist movements have developed a discourse on the right to health and the way in which medicine has over time expropriated the knowledge of the body and the possibility for women to know, intervene and choose about their own bodies (Percovich 2005, Bracke 2012, 2014, Barone forthcoming). While SNOQ has not been concerned with the topic, this had acquired instead fundamental value for both SN and NUDM.

SN developed the reflection on health from a queer and intersectional perspectives, elaborating on the medicalisation of trans bodies by medical and state institutions, and the normativity of gender transition processes (Busi and Fiorilli 2015). The possibility of knowing the functioning of hormones and using them was at the centre of a work from below, in which forms of do-it-yourself, outside of medical protocols, were developed (Zappino 2016, Preciado 2013). In broader terms, the network has

studied the emptying of the meaning of public health centers³⁴ which have become centres without a feminist political content, and the experience of new forms of bottom-up and feminist health centres (Busi and Fiorilli 2015, Fuxia Block 2016, Zappino 2016, Mura, Peroni and Veneri 2017). In these places, the right to health is elaborated as a broad concept that includes not only physical health, but also environmental, psychological, emotional, relational, occupational health. The individuals are thus taken into consideration with respect to all the different parts of their lives, and health is conceived of not as the absence of disease, but as the work on the person's well-being (Fuxia Block 2015). These progressive perspectives have been largely ignored by the public institutions and remained marginal also in the public debate since the phase of dismantling public health, of progressive defunding, and of disinvestment in territorial health, thus closer to the people in the local area (Busi and Fiorilli 2015).

For NUDM, the issue of health and reproductive rights is essential (Settembrini 2021, Balzano 2021). Here too, health is considered in relations with the psychological, physical, sexual and social well-being, being conceived as an expression of individual self-determination, rather than as the mere absence of disease. The focus of health addresses bodies, needs and material conditions of existence, and the sexual dimension concerns not just reproduction but more broadly desire and pleasure (We have a plan 2017). For this reason, medicine and the health institutions are held responsible for institutionalised forms of violence against lifestyles and bodies considered to be outside the norm, which are therefore treated in pathologising or medicalising forms. Among the main problems denounced are the neonatal genital rectification of intersex people, the health treatment of transitions within a gender dysphoria framework, health conditions in prison institutions, access to social and health services considered exclusionary and discriminatory, and the treatment of the health conditions of sex workers. Furthermore, a central issue is that of law 194/1978, the law on the voluntary interruption of pregnancy (Settembrini 2021). Although abortion is a right established by law, conscientious objection of medical personnel is also allowed, and therefore only 65% of the total number of obstetrics and gynaecology departments in Italy perform pregnancy terminations (Balzano 2021). A second problem concerns pharmacological abortion, which has so far been scarcely used in Italy, and which the movement is calling for to be administered within health advisory centres. Also linked to public health is the phenomenon of obstetrical violence (a series of verbal and physical abuses suffered during childbirth assistance and in gynaecological care more generally), which is being called for to be recognised as a form of violence against women. NUDM also demands that health centres are connected to feminist anti-violence centres that can therefore accompany in the reception and care of women who experience situations of violence. In this sense, the law renamed 'Pink Code' is considered inadequate, in particular in its provision of the access code to emergency rooms reserved for women who suffer violence, coordinated by the public prosecutor's office, the region and the health authority, which risks leading to forced paths of response to violence that undermine women's freedom of choice. In order to respond to these problems, the role is instead stressed of the counselling centres, i.e. the feminist health centers that, born out of the feminist movement in the 1970s, have been progressively institutionalised and de-politicized. The consultatories are places that NUDM wishes to re-politicise, and in which the right to health as an organic and complex concept of well-being, which places the totality of the person at the centre, can find expression (Settembrini 2021).

³⁴ Women's health centres (consultori) emerged in the 1970s as self-managed places run by women, focusing on women's right to health and self-determination. In the counselling centres, women meet, discuss, research on legal and medical issues affecting women. In these places, issues relating to abortion are concretely addressed, as well as practices of self-knowledge of one's own body (self-help), the use of alternative medicine with the pooling of experience and knowledge, from political analysis with the construction of common actions and struggles (Percovich 2005).

In general, the dismantling of welfare, the corporatisation and privatisation of public health care is held responsible for these problems, which also has consequences for the quality of work of health care workers and thus for the well-being of those who access these services (Balzano 2021).

4.5.3 Labor market

Historically, part of the feminist movement in Italy developed a Marxist reading of society, which put the intertwining of patriarchy and capitalism at the basis of gender inequality and women's oppression (Dalla Costa and James 1975, Chiste, Del Re and Forti, Federici 2015, Curcio 2021). In various ways, this materialist analysis has continued to influence the feminist movement up to these days.

For SNOQ, the issue of women's work is mainly about denouncing institutional drift which has also involved the debunking of women's skills, abilities, knowledge and projects. In addition to the critique of the gender gap, in access to both work and wages, main claims concern women's career opportunities, their exclusion from positions of power, and the ancillary role women are given in workplaces. State institutions and patriarchal culture are blamed for this form of inequality. Therefore, the very labor market is interpreted as a place of women's emancipation (Cavalleri and Robiony 2017).

SN, instead, mostly focused its analysis on the precarization of the labor market and the feminization of labor (Arfini and Busi 2020). According to this interpretation, the economic model developed through neoliberalism has produced increasing fragmentation, individualization, competition and job insecurity. Women and queer people specifically suffer the consequences of this process, as they were already, on a structural level, made precarious by the labor market and the production system. In addition, certain characteristics that Marxist feminism attributed to women's unpaid work (such as caring, total availability, courtesy, demeaning work, and the ability to network and empathize with others) have progressively become characteristics demanded by the labor market more generally, but at the same time are less and less recognized and paid for (Morini 2010). These claims were put forward in the construction of the social strike, that is, the strike from all forms of labor (paid, unpaid, off the books, precarious), in an action called the strike of/gender (Mura, Peroni and Veneri 2015). As much as the issue of precarity has been debated in Italy, the gender perspective has remained marginal in the public debate, partly due to the limited capacity to mobilise and reach people's participation in claims and actions.

For NUDM, the economic issues of labor and welfare are central given the intertwining of the neoliberal system with gender and patriarchal violence, analyzed especially in a prolonged phase of economic crisis (Salvatori 2021). It is precisely in the crisis that social inequalities that assign social reproduction work and demotion and impoverishment in the labor market to women are consolidated (Arfini and Busi 2020). For NUDM the feminization of labor is also about extending certain traits related to the social production of the female gender to the entire workforce. In addition, wage inequality, harassment in the workplace, and the reduction of contractual rights and protections is structural (Peroni 2018). To counter these problems NUDM proposes the European minimum wage and the unconditional and universal self-determination income, unrelated to work performance, citizenship and residence conditions. In addition, against the drastic welfare cuts that primarily burden women, NUDM proposes universal welfare, free and accessible to all and therefore not based on the current familistic model, and policies to support shared motherhood and parenting (Abbiamo un piano 2017). In recent years in Italy, citizenship income has been approved and in some regions a "freedom income", intended for women coming out of situations of violence. Both forms represent approximations of NUDM's claims in both quantity and approach to the laws, and it is anyhow difficult to establish a direct correlation between protests and policy choices, as is often the case in social movement analysis.

4.5.4 Migration

The issue of migration has recently entered the feminist movement's agenda. Although an international and internationalist perspective had been present since the 1970s, there was for a long time a lack of clear analysis and collective action on the topic of borders, migration and reception policies (Rigo 2022, Vianello 2014). With the reception of intersectional thinking, the approach to the topic of migration has also changed. The gender lens has widened to include concerns with race, class,

age, health conditions. The feminist movement has thus developed an analysis of how the reception system, the construction of the foreigner, and the functioning of borders also have a gendered dimension (Vianello 2014, Martorano and Prearo 2020).

While, for the reasons stated above, SNOQ did not present a clear discourse on the issue of migration, for SN this was instead a central issue. On the one hand, SN questioned the violence of borders and the construction of a white Europe also based on the rhetorical use of civil rights and the inclusion of homosexuals in an exclusionary key against the 'others', who precisely on these issues were considered barbaric, uncivilised and backward-oriented (Puar 2007, Ferrante 2014). To counter this rhetoric, queer and feminist groups have instead tried to reject pink-washing and homo-nationalism, building forms of alliance with migrant people and denouncing Europe's system of internal and external borders. On the other hand, SN analysed the forms of racialisation within Italy, looking at how internal colonialism and discrimination against people from the south, considered as backward-oriented, poor, uncivilised and less advanced than people from the north, also took place within the country. This narrative of the South has material effects on public policy, to which the movement proposed to respond with a series of demands (Acquistapace et al. 2016).

For NUDM, the issue of migration is one of the main focuses. Racism and the management of migratory flows are considered to be strictly intertwined with sexism in producing a situation of double gender violence on women and LGBTQ+ migrants (Rigo 2022). Intersectionality is the frame of the movement and therefore entails not only a clear positioning against racist violence, external and internal border violence, and centres for forced repatriation, but also an alliance with migrant people. NUDM in fact opposes the global border regime and expresses its solidarity with the struggle of migrant people. This includes the demand for freedom of movement and unconditional stay inside and outside Europe (Rudan et al. 2018). This is why the institutional system of reception and the emergency logic applied to migration management, which often makes migrant women invisible and more exposed to forms of social and institutional violence, is criticised. Furthermore, NUDM rejects the representation of migrant women as victims, whose agency and capacity for self-determination has instead to be recognised. Specifically, the abrogation of Italian and European laws that limit the mobility of migrants - such as the so called Minniti- Orlando law and the Bossi-Fini law, but also international agreements and bilateral agreements, such as the one between Italy and Turkey - is demanded. A second objective is the abolition of administrative detention both in Europe and in third countries to which it is outsourced. Finally, there is the demand for unconditional and unlimited European residence, free from family and income limits, and the *ius soli*, with the right to acquire Italian citizenship for anyone born and/or raised in Italy. This is framed within the fight against the media narrative of gender-based violence, which often passes through a racist instrumentalisation of cases of violence (through the rhetoric that states that when a migrant person acts violently this is a sign of an obvious backwardness that justifies the enactment of increasingly discriminatory and repressive legislation against migrants) (Abbiamo un piano 2017). NUDM's analysis on the topic of migration has not had much influence on the public debate, partly due to the instrumental use of the topic by populist and extreme right-wing forces, which have gained increasing support in Italy, not least because of Italy's central position in the trajectories of migration flows in the Mediterranean.

4.5.5 LGBTQ+ rights

The history of the intertwining of the feminist and LGBTQ+ movement in Italy is not simple or linear. Lesbofeminism has long been present within the feminist movement, albeit with internal conflicts and moments of fragmentation (Biagini 2018). Although at the heart of the movement's concerns, the theme of sexuality was more about women's bodies than about a struggle against heteronormativity. Only later did solid forms of intersectionality develop, especially with the arrival of the queer conception in Italy (Pustianaz 2011, Arfini and Loiacono 2012).

In this sense, SN placed feminism as much at the centre as LGBTQ+ struggles, in a seamless interweaving. The new feminist subject is located on axes ranging from gender, sexual orientation, race, class and so on. Although supporting some central rights' claims, such as against homophobia and the recognition of same-sex relationships, the organization has always been very confrontational

towards attempts at legislative change (such as the Cirinnà DDL on civil unions and the Zan DDL against homophobia) because of the compromising and limited content of these measures. In addition, the movement's ideology has been oriented towards a radical and antagonistic approach to heteronormative culture, the economic system and state institutions, all of which were considered responsible for the homophobic violence and inequality experienced by LGBTQ+ people, rather than towards the recognition of civil rights (Acquistapace 2022).

NUDM was born out of this political movement culture that sees feminism and LGBTQ+ claims as closely connected. It is no coincidence that from the outset it calls itself transfeminist. According to NUDM:

“Transfeminism is a movement of resistance and a theory that considers gender, arbitrarily assigned at birth, a social construction, the very instrument of a system of power that controls and limits bodies in order to adapt them to the heterosexual and patriarchal social order. Transfeminism moves from the materiality of trans, feminist and queer lives and experiences, the complexity and multiplicity of gender and sexual placements, and recognizes the intertwining of the patriarchal and capitalist matrix of oppressions that affect all subjectivities that are not heterosexual white males.” (Abbiamo un piano 2017)

The concept of male violence against women is, in fact, gender-based and structural, and in this sense for NUDM it also affects LGBTQ+ subjectivities from their own gender and sexual identity and/or choice. NUDM considers itself as much feminist as LGBTQ+, in terms of its composition, claims, frames and goals. On the one hand, it develops a plan of claims related to rights. For example, on the issues of depathologisation of trans paths and full access to trans health, on the fight against medicalisation of intersexuality, on LGBTQ+ parental rights and the fight against homophobia, transphobia, lesbophobia (Settembrini 2021). On the other hand, it develops a broader discourse on heteronormativity as a system that organises relationships, styles of interaction, and even violence (Acquistapace 2022). In this sense, the Valentine's Day, for example, has been subverted as a day to denounce the normativity of the couple, the rhetoric of romantic, possessive, exclusive love, and rape culture. This reflection on affective and sexual forms of intimacy and relationships is part of the LGBTQ+ and queer legacy, which at the crossroads with feminism has become a frame for analysing gender violence and thus identities and relationship choices. Beyond the rights' side, LGBTQ+ issues run through all the topics addressed by NUDM, such as work, health, violence, migration, education and culture (Pavan 2020). The economic system is also challenged due to the progressive inclusion of LGBTQ+ people, called diversity management, which neutralises their conflict potential making them just another part of the production cycle (Arfini and Busi 2020).

4.5.6 Education

With the new wave of mobilisation since 2016, the theme of education came to the forefront. One of the specific areas of reflection of NUDM is education, both in terms of material conditions within the spaces of education and of gender education. According to them, the prevention and fight against male violence must go through a structural rethinking of the education and training system, because violence against women is a systemic phenomenon that innervates society in its entirety and affects all educational and training contexts, from nursery schools to universities and higher education. They often refer to “radical pedagogy” as a new way of framing education as antiracist, antifascist and antisexist. They contest gender binarism as the basis of a biased education, that prevent children from freedom and open-minded socialization processes. To this end, they advocate for the introduction of gender education or education to differences from early childhood, and the diffusion of gender studies, department and centres across Italian universities. This work is oriented to challenge gender stereotypes and formalized social roles.

4.5.6.1 Media and gender based violence

With the increasing focus on gender-based violence, claims around the topic of violence have also grown. One of the most prominent is related to the representation of violence and LGBTQ+ women and persons in the media. As they single out, media play a strategic role in fuelling or counteracting

male violence against women and narratives of violence inform collective perceptions, often interacting with judicial mechanisms, as denounced by violence-resistant women who have been re-victimised, violated and discredited by media. Among the major critics there is the representation of women *by nature*, a heteronormative view of social reality that neglects violence against LGBTQ+ people, the lack of an intersectional perspective, in which gender is also intertwined with class, race, age and disability. In the NUDM anti-violence plan, guidelines are mentioned to change the media's approach to violence, e.g., avoid portraying violence as emergent or the result of a rapture, a conscious use of language, replacing the frame of romantic love by stating that violence is not love, telling that violence affects everyone, referring to anti-violence centres for correct and timely information, avoiding the representation of women as victims, not re-victimising women by making them responsible for the violence they have experienced, avoiding the pathologisation of violent men, who are not monsters but rather children of a certain gender regime.

4.5.6.2 *Repertoire of action*

Historically, the feminist movement has innovated and subverted traditional repertoires of action (Bracke 2014). Specifically, self-consciousness and direct social action have been widespread, along with mass demonstrations, sit-ins and forms of contentious politics.

SNOQ has mostly resorted to public protests and petitions as well as lobbying, also resonant with a certain proximity to institutions (Cavalleri and Robiony 2017). While the discourse is confrontational, this is not the case for the practices.

In the case of SN, the repertoire of actions includes mostly public protests and performative actions, in which the creative and provocative approach of the network of groups was expressed (Zappino 2016). Self-help, as well, has been promoted through the diffusion of self-managed health centers, informed by trans movement, queer theory and a strong attention to the body (Busi and Fiorilli 2015).

NUDM uses a broad spectrum of actions, ranging from public protests to consciousness rising, boycotts and flash mobs. The two ritual mobilization dates of the movement are November 25th, the international day against male and gender-based violence, on which a national demonstration is always organised in Rome, and March 8, International Women's Day with usually public initiatives at the local level (Chironi 2019). The biggest innovation since 2017 has been the feminist strike on the date of 8th March, which has taken place every year since then. The feminist strike is intended to be a strike from productive and reproductive labour, that is, from all forms of labour that affect women and LGBTQ+ people. While the strike is traditionally an action promoted by trade unions, in this case, although it is a strike formally called by trade unions, it has a political connotation (Campillo 2019). The intention of the movement is to try to stop all activities in which women are present, and in to prove that, as a slogan goes, 'if we stop, the world stops' (Bonu 2022).

Forms of contentious politics are for the most part confrontational, in the sense that they represent a way of raising a public issue about events that are considered to be unrecognised or misinterpreted, as in the case of gender-based violence. The actions represent a way of expressing indignation, presenting an issue to the general public, denouncing the representation or misrepresentation of a social problem, gathering people who feel sympathetic to that problem and leading them to collectively express dissent. Spaces of dialogue with institutions are rarely opened up, although experiments of this kind are more widespread at the local level. For example, in the experience of the coordination of the Lazio health centres, the disputes on the reopening or improvement of the quality of the consultatories also involved the opening of discussion tables with local and regional institutions (Settembrini 2021, Constelacion feminista 2020).

A great deal of reflection in the development of the repertoires of the action concerned the imagery produced by NUDM. First, there is the use of colours, as black and fuchsia facilitate the attribution of the actions. The same function is fulfilled by the use of fuchsia triangular handkerchiefs, borrowed from the green triangular handkerchiefs (*pañuelos*) of the campaign for safe, free abortion in

Argentina. In the beginning, matryoshkas were used as a symbol of both as relationship (one being inside the other) and as generational exchange (from the largest to the smallest and vice versa). Every action and campaign is accompanied by a great deal of imagery work in order to make NUDM's messages understandable and easily recognizable (Cirimele and Panariello 2018).

The social media most frequently used are Facebook, Instagram, Twitter. NUDM's Facebook page has around 150,000 followers, the Instagram channel 105,000 followers and Twitter around 30,000 followers.

Emotions play a key role in the choice of actions. Because of the centrality of the topic of violence, and thus the emotions related to gender-based violence - anger, fear, pain, frustration and so on - the choice of actions is also oriented by the need to turn these emotions into a resource for action (Bonu 2022). For example, each city in which there is a NUDM node (this is in which local assemblies are called) has over time identified a symbolic place (such as a street or a square), in which every 8th of the month a ritual is performed to remember the women who died of femicide in the previous month. This ritual occasion becomes the moment when emotions, such as anger and grief, are not only shared but also transformed, and thus put into circulation for collective action. Moreover, these are moments in which collective emotions help to convey a message - the fight against male and gender-based violence. Finally, emotions build a community around the sharing and transformation of those same emotions, and thus substantiate NUDM's activists' composition, choice of themes and forms of action (Bonu 2021).

The counterparts of actions vary in time. In most cases, the target is the sexist culture, which causes the type of education, socialisation and interaction styles underlying the violence against women. In addition to this, public institutions - such as local and national governments with respect to the allocation of funds and the funding of anti-violence centres or the relationship with feminist spaces - are addressed (Salvatori 2021). Furthermore, public institutions such as hospitals, courts, services, schools - are also the object of conflict, due to their involvement in various ways in the reproduction of gender-based violence. Finally, a main counterpart is the anti-gender movement and religious forces that influence public policy (Pavan 2020).

4.6 Frames of arguments

4.6.1 Gender based violence

In this section, more attention will be given to the NUDM movement, which presents the most in-depth discourse on each of the five thematic areas.

Regarding male violence against women, the key argument developed by NUDM is that male violence against women and gender-based violence is a system that organises social life in a structural way (Cirimele and Panariello 2019, Barone and Bonu 2022). The power dynamic concerning the male and female gender is mediated by the use - the threat, the fear, the implicit - of violence, and in this sense it speaks of rape culture or structural violence. In this sense, the interpretation of gender-based violence broadens the analysis of the functioning of gender as a social construction, taking into account violence as a tool, but also an expression of gender socialisation and gender relations. This way of framing violence serves the movement in order to, on the one hand, shed light on the material consequences of gender socialisation (in the family, workplace, school, etc.) and, on the other hand, link the frames to forms of action with recognisable and common goals in the lives of LGBTQ+ women and people. In this sense, this framing of violence led NUDM to focus on concrete objectives - such as gender education or the re-funding of anti-violence centres - and to present very clear goals in all issues addressed, through the lens of combating violence (Cossutta 2022).

As already mentioned, the framing process of violence also takes place through an intersectional, queer and transfeminist approach, and thus looking at the elements of violence that do not concern gender as a natural element but as a social construction. In this sense, violence is also considered as patriarchal violence, which is also expressed between queer people and outside the heterosexual couple.

The emergence of anti-gender movements has prompted NUDM to strengthen the reading of violence within domestic contexts such as the family, which is the hero of anti-gender claims (Pavan 2020).

4.6.2 Health and reproductive rights

The main contribution in the framing process of health and reproductive rights is the understanding of the right to health as a comprehensive approach to the body, well-being, self-determination and the quality of life far beyond the mere lack of health (Settembrini 2021, Balzano 2021).

This integrated meaning of health also includes the concept of care, as a relational practice that protects people's quality of life through a bond of mutual interdependence and responsibility (Fraguito and Tola 2022).

The Western tradition of interpreting the body and its needs, which dates back to the birth of capitalism and modern medicine, considers the body as a machine, lacking an integrated approach to the cognitive sphere, the emotions, the human relationships and the relationship with the environment (Percovich 2005). The broadening of the concept of health allows NUDM to build a repertoire of actions and protest campaigns on issues ranging from abortion to quality of services, mental health, environmental issues, maternity. This approach to health in fact defines a theoretical concept that has then concrete repercussions upon the way pathways of care are conceived, the claims on the national health system and services are defined, the reflections on the way women and LGBTQ+ people are treated with respect to medical knowledge (Balzano 2021).

4.6.3 Labor market

The major frame developed on the subject of labour is that of productive and reproductive labour. Although this frame has distant roots in the feminist Marxism of the 1970s (Dalla Costa and James 1975, Curcio 2021), NUDM has expanded the concept to include developments in the contemporary labour market, processes of precarisation, the feminisation of work, increasing fragmentation and impoverishment, the distribution of care tasks and the double workload (Arfini and Busi 2020).

This framing corresponds to an analysis of the relationship between the labour market, women and LGBTQ+ people, including the persistence of forms of labour confinement by sector, the gender pay gap, the glass ceiling³⁵, bullying and harassment in the workplace. The intersectional approach has allowed NUDM to develop a frame on work that is not only about women, but about the forms of feminisation by which work is underpaid, poorly recognised and precarised (Rudan et al. 2018, Gago 2019).

The main consequence of this frame is the development of the practice of strike action and the connection with the international #metoo movement focusing on complaints of harassment in the workplace (Peroni 2018).

4.6.4 Migration

On the topic of migration, NUDM frames the management of borders and migratory flows as an expression of gender violence in an organisational structure of social life (Rigo 2022). Based on this, the systems of entry and reception of migrants, the processes of racialisation and the relationship with migrants in a country like Italy are explored in the labour market, in services and with respect to citizenship. The intersectional approach is at the basis of a framing process that does not look at LGBTQ+ women and persons as "others", but rather considers individuals as crossed by multiple lines

³⁵ The metaphor of glass ceiling refers to vertical segregation, which prevents women from attaining top positions and responsibilities in the professional sphere, thus refers to all those invisible barriers that prevent or complicate the professional growth of women workers.

of social inequality and therefore potentially able to build forms of understanding and alliance across inequalities (Martorano and Prearo 2020).

This interpretation, through the lens of gender-based violence, makes it possible to identify migrant women and LGBTQ+ people not as victims but as actors who interpret, confront and transform their own conditions, in an active path of choice and self-determination (Vianello 2014, Martorano and Prearo 2020, Rigo 2022).

In concrete terms, this framing process has produced forms of action on citizenship, the development of the network of services and the anti-violence system, education and the reception system.

4.6.5 LGBTQ+ rights

Finally, NUDM also deepened its interpretation of the concept of gender and sexuality. The intersectional, queer and transfeminist approach led NUDM to consider both gender and sexuality as social constructs resulting from interactions and power distribution systems in the social world (Cirimele and Panariello 2018, Constelacion feminista 2020).

In this sense, heteronormativity is considered as a social norm prescribing a set of behaviours - the heterosexual, monogamous, reproductive couple - of which any other form of affectivity and sexuality represents the antithesis (Acquistapace 2022).

Starting from this interpretation, the movement has focused on subjects as bearers of desires, certainly conditioned but also capable of expressing their own agency. Thus, sexual, reproductive and affective choices appear detached from a set of behavioral expectations and close to the concept of self-determination. This LGBTQ+ rights frame has led NUDM to stand in sharp opposition to anti-gender movements, affirming the field of gender and sexuality as unnatural and not-given (Pavan 2020, Cossutta 2022).

The concrete consequences of these framing process have been the fight for the introduction of sanctions against hate crimes, the cultural battle for gender education and thus for new forms of affectivity, and the opposition to the ideal of romantic love, considered at the root of the culture of gender-based violence.

4.7 Campaigns and debates

SNOQ developed a campaign upon the "dignity of women and of institutions" which condemned the conduct of Prime Minister Berlusconi and the image of women that emerged as 'objects of sexual exchange' (Cavalleri and Robiony 2017). The idea was to denounce the disregard for women's dignity at a time in which women were increasingly active in the fields of education, in the labour market and in society. The campaign, developed through public protests and appeals, called on men and women 'of all parties, religions and ideologies' to 'speak out on behalf of women's dignity offended not only by the behaviour of the premier, but also by the use of women's bodies in the media' (Elia 2016). This campaign has been poorly researched due to its short duration, an ambivalent relation with the women's movement and a general lack of interest in feminist actions, which had come from years of relative invisibility on the Italian political scene.

The main campaign developed by SN was "Veniamo ovunque", a campaign to denounce and raise awareness about the condition of queer people and their demands, culminating in the first national transfeminist march in Bologna in 2016 and the occupation of a building, which was then immediately evicted by the police. The campaign is a first example of an intersectional approach, as it brought together the issues of gender identity with sexuality, migration, labour, capitalism, knowledge production, health, colonialism, diversity management (Acquistapace 2022). Mainly transfeminist and queer collectives and individual queer activists were involved. Developed in the years of greatest visibility of anti-gender groups in Italy (Lavizzari 2019), the campaign promoted resistance against it with the defence of the traditional family, neo-Catholic and fundamentalist groups. This notwithstanding, also this campaign has not been much studied by social scientists.

Unlike their predecessors, the campaigns developed by NUDM are more widely covered in the literature, partly due to the global conjuncture of feminist mobilisations, which have brought feminism back to the centre of public debate, publishing, and academia (DWF 2021, Bonu 2022). The two main campaigns concern gender-based violence on the one hand and labour on the other. With the 25 of November as its central moment, the campaign opposing male violence against women has used a plurality of forms of actions, including summits, sit-ins and boycotts (Constelacion feminista 2020). Each year it is reworked around a different core slogan. A series of parallel campaigns emerged on the issue of health (such as Objection Rejected (Settembrini 2021), migration, LGBTQ+ rights, which are part of NUDM's larger mobilisation on the fight against gender-based violence as structural violence that crosses all spheres of society. The mobilisation involves transfeminist and queer collectives, women's associations, anti-violence centres, feminist spaces, NGOs. The campaign on violence is developed through an intersectional approach, framing all axes of inequality that produce situations of violence and marginality. The major conflicts concern the issue of sex work, the inclusion of trans people and surrogacy (Ammaturo 2020, Geymonat and Selmi 2022). On all these issues NUDM claims its strong adherence, but over time conflicts have emerged that have deteriorated some of the movement's internal alliances.

NUDM's second campaign is on productive and reproductive labour, of which the 8th of March strike is one of the main moments of mobilisation. The critique of the economic model and the production system within a gender perspective is indeed at the heart of the movement, and around this an active campaign has been built since 2016 that challenges the positions of women and LGBTQ+ subjects with the labour market, the value production system, the exploitation of reproductive labour (Constelacion feminista 2020). The counterpart is the market and the economic system as much as state institutions, which through public policies, consolidate and reproduce this system of economic organisation strongly hostile towards women. This has been compounded since 2020 by the spread of the covid-19 pandemic, which has worsened the economic and working conditions of women and LGBTQ+ people, both inside and outside the home. In fact, the health crisis has summed up with the consequences of the economic crisis, the restructuring of the labour market and a general impoverishment (Marceddu et al. 2022).

A major internal conflict concerned the issue of sex work, considered work by NUDM and instead stigmatised by some components of the feminist movement in Italy (Geymonat and Selmi 2022). The campaign is internationally coordinated (the strike is in fact called in more than 150 countries around the world every year), with shared slogans, sometimes in connection with other campaigns (as in 2018, when the strike took place with the slogan #wetogether recalling the international #metoo campaign, see Peroni 2018).

As for the general strike on March 8th, NUDM sends a letter to the trade unions. Usually it is the smaller unions that call the strike, without the consent of the confederal unions. This form of contact is not properly considered an alliance but rather a way of putting the instrument of the strike at the service of a political movement, through connection with the bodies in charge of it, such as the trade unions. In this sense, the feminist movement rejects open institutional negotiation, trying to play out a political strength in the relationship with institutional and non-institutional actors (Constelacion feminista 2020, Montanelli and Hardt 2018).

4.8 Key policy related outcomes

With regard to policies, in the period 2010-2021 several changes occurred.

In the field of gender-based violence, the Italian Parliament ratified the Istanbul Convention in 2013. In the same year, the 'Urgent provisions on security and to combat gender-based violence' were approved, with the aim of preventing and protecting victims. The legislation provides for the definition of an overall strategy by the National Equal Opportunities Department through an extraordinary three-

year plan, which was published in 2015-2017, 2017-2020 and 2021-2023³⁶. The last strategic plan was strongly contested by NUDM and the network D.i.Re of anti-violence centres, which denounced that anti-violence centres and movements were ignored in the drafting of the Plan, notwithstanding their importance in dealing with violence against women on the ground and being directly involved in its implementation³⁷. The critique also concerns the delay in the implementation, with the waste of public money, and the dramatic defunding of the anti-violence system. In this sense, precisely on the issue of violence, there has been a lack of direct involvement of the feminist movements, which have seen most of their proposals for action on the issue disattended.

Another process of change has concerned the field of health and education and training, topics on which the influence of anti-gender and anti-feminist groups is most visible. Although there have been no changes at the national level to the law on the voluntary interruption of pregnancy (law 194/1978), there are, however, widespread initiatives at the local level, such as the approval of a motion in the regional council of Veneto to provide rich funding to pro-life associations and to declare Verona a 'pro-life city'³⁸. If on this occasion the proposal of burial of aborted fetuses was not approved, foetus cemeteries in which the names of women who have resorted to abortion are indicated have been found in Rome, leading to the amendment of municipal regulations in the direction of protecting the privacy and religious freedom of women³⁹. On these grounds, however, the impact of the anti-gender/anti-feminist groups is very visible with respect to the distribution of resources, the growing rates of conscientious objection on abortion, the de-funding and de-politicisation of advice centres, and the growing climate of hostility about women's freedom and self-determination (Settembrini 2021, Balzano 2022). Furthermore, a major impact of the anti-gender movement concerned gender education, which again, especially at the local level, was severely restricted or completely prohibited by municipal or regional councils (as in the cases of Venice⁴⁰, Trento⁴¹ and Trieste⁴²).

A third issue on which policy changes have taken place is that of LGBTQ+ rights, with the approval in 2016, of civil unions (the so-called DDL Cirinnà). Passed significantly later than in most other European countries, the civil unions brings about a weak recognition of rights for the partner, excluding pension reversibility and stepchild adoption. In this case too, feminist movements have taken critical stances, stigmatizing the limits of an institution which, although filling the legislative gap on civil unions for persons of the same sex, excludes some of the most important provisions on economic and reproductive matters. This limit is seen as a sign of a persistent situation of discrimination in which the LGBTQ+ people do not have access to full citizenship and are second-class rights bearers (Acquistapace 2022). A failed policy intervention is the mentioned DDL Zan on discrimination and violence based on sex, gender, sexual orientation, gender identity and disability. It was precisely on the issue of gender identity that internal conflicts arose within the feminist movements, in which groups associated with the trans-exclusionary area contributed to the bill's scuttling. This failed legislative path is illustrative of the debates and conflicts that split feminist movements and are a further reason for slowing down legislative changes and state institutions.

³⁶ <https://www.pariopportunita.gov.it/controla-violenza-sessuale-e-di-genere/>

³⁷ <https://www.direcontrolaviolenza.it/forma-e-sostanza-i-finti-percorsi-partecipati-lettera-aperta-alla-ministra-bonetti/>

³⁸ <https://www.ilpost.it/2018/10/06/comune-verona-mozione-contro-aborto/>

³⁹ <https://www.open.online/2022/11/03/roma-stop-nomi-donne-sepoltura-feti/>

⁴⁰ <http://www.penclubitalia.it/c/95555/18249/il-sindaco-di-venezia-ritira-dalle-scuole-comunali-i-libri-gender.html>

⁴¹ https://www.repubblica.it/cronaca/2019/01/16/news/trentino_la_battaglia_sul_gender_paralizza_i_corsi_contro_la_violenza_sulle_donne-216707010/

⁴² <https://fattodavoi.ilfattoquotidiano.it/contributo/parita-tra-i-sessi-trieste-elimina-progetto-gender-nelle-scuole/>

If policy changes have taken place in the fields of labour (with the Jobs Act in 2015) and migration (with the Minniti-Orlando law in 2017) they have not taken place specifically with reference to women and LGBTQ+ people. In a climate of persistent gender inequality, the increasing precarisation of work and decreasing protections can only have even negative consequences for women, as well as in the area of migration. In both cases, feminist movements have not been directly involved in the policy process, except in contesting the design and implementation of legislation.

The greatest challenges feminist movements face with regard to policy-making concern the advance of extreme right-wing and anti-gender groups, which currently lead the national government and have a strong presence in all local administrations. This presence in state institutions has already begun to become visible, for instance with the proposed so-called Gasparri amendment to the 194/1978, aimed at recognising the legal personality of the foetus, or the transformation of the Ministry for Equal Opportunities into the Ministry for Family, Birth and Equal Opportunities.

4.9 Conclusion

The new phase of feminist mobilisation in Italy since 2016 has been partially explored in the literature (Peroni 2018, Chironi 2019, Cirimele and Panariello 2019, Bonu 2022). Yet, many blind spots remain. First of all, there is a lack of clear analysis in social movement studies of NUDM's emergence, development, organisation, repertoires of action, democratic innovation and influence on decision making process. While recent publications have begun to analyse the intersectional and intergenerational approach (Chironi 2019), the role of new social media (Pavan and Mainardi 2018), abortion campaigns (Settembrini 2021, Balzano 2021), and the conflict with anti-gender groups (Lavizzari 2019), such analyses are still at an initial stage, as there is a lack of systematic data collection on mobilisations and an analysis of how they developed and were able or not to influence state institutions, public policies and the social and cultural context. In this sense, it is necessary to proceed with an adequate data collection that is able to explain the history, frames and action of NUDM in the five thematic areas, gender-based violence, labour market, migration, health and reproductive rights, LGBTQ+ rights.

4.10 List of feminist movements' campaigns

Name of the campaign	Name of the campaign (English)	Issue(s) addressed	Actors involved	Repertoire of action	Logo of the campaign	Web-page	Comment
Verona città transfeminista	Verona transfeminist city	Health and reproductive rights	Movements, associations, NGOs	Public demonstrations and protests, international assemblies, cultural events		Web: https://nonunadimeno.wordpress.com/category/verona-transfeminista/ FB: https://www.facebook.com/events/417220915493543/	Campaign organized against the National Congress of Families in Verona, which generated a major moment of transnational mobilization

Sciopero femminista	Feminist strike	Labor market	Movements, associations, anti-violence centres	Strike, public demonstrations and protests, sit-ins, artistic performances		<p>Web: https://nonunadimeno.wordpress.com/2022/02/11/proclamazioni-sciopero-8-marzo-e-lista-singole-adesioni-di-categoria-in-aggiornamento/</p> <p>FB: https://m.facebook.com/events/1057403021470799/</p>	Annual strike every March 8 organized since 2017 in many countries around the world to challenge women's invisible and unpaid reproductive labor and the unequal productive working conditions that still remain
25th of November, International Day of mobilization	International Day of mobilization	Gender based violence	Movements, associations, anti-	public demonstrations and protests, sit-ins,		https://www.facebook.com/events/970057450215823/	Annual day of mobilization against

against gender-based violence	against gender-based violence		violence centres	artistic performances			gender based violence
Black Lives Matter	Black Lives matter	Migration	Movement, associations, civil society organizations	public demonstrations and protests, sit-ins, artistic performances, boycotts		https://www.facebook.com/BlackLivesMatterItaly	Mobilization against racism and colonialism, for right to citizenship
Pride	Pride	LGBTQA+ rights	Movement, associations, civil society organizations	Public demonstration		https://www.facebook.com/events/436686870397876/	Day of mobilization LGBTQ+ rights, lesbian feminism, queer and trans people rights, LGBT parenthood, gender identity

							and against hate crimes
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4.11 References

- Acquistapace, A. L. (2022) *Tenetevi il matrimonio e dateci la dote. Il lavoro riproduttivo nelle relazioni di intimità, solidarietà e cura oltre la coppia nell'Italia contemporanea*. Milan: Mimesis.
- Acquistapace, A., Arfini, E. A., De Vivo, B., Ferrante, A. A., & Polizzi, G. (2016). Tempo di essere incivili: Una riflessione terrena sull'omonazionalismo in Italia al tempo dell'austerità. In: Zappino, F. (2016) *Il genere tra neoliberalismo e neofondamentalismo*. Verona: Ombre corte.
- Ammaturo, F. R. (2020). Framing and shaming: LGBT activism, feminism and the construction of 'gestational surrogacy' in Italy. *Social Movement Studies*, 19(4), 447-463.
- Arfini E. A. and Lo Iacono C. (2012) *Canone inverso. Antologia di teoria queer*. Pisa: ETS.
- Arfini, E. A. (2020). Transfeminism. *lambda nordica*, 25(1), 160-165.
- Arfini, E. A., and Busi, B. (2020). The (re) production of (in) equality in Italy: feminisms and reproductive labour in the era of populism. In *Theorising Cultures of Equality* (pp. 76-93). Routledge.
- Ayoub, P. and Paternotte, D. (2014). *LGBT activism and the making of Europe: A rainbow Europe?* Belrin: Springer.
- Balzano, A. (2021) *Per farla finita con la famiglia. Dall'aborto alle parentele postumane*. Milan: Meltemi.
- Barone, A. and Bonu, G. (2022), *Ni Una Menos/Non Una di Meno*. In Snow, D., della Porta, D., Klandermans, B. and D. McAdam, *The Blackwell Encyclopedia of Social and Political Movements*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Beckwith, Karen. 1985. "Feminism and Leftist Politics in Italy: The Case of UDI-PCI Relationships." In S. Bashevkin, ed., *Women and Politics in Western Europe*. London: Frank Cass.
- Bertilotti T., Galasso C., Gissi A. and Lagorio F. (2018) *Altri femminismi. Corpi, violenza, riproduzione, cultura, lavoro*. Rome: Manifestolibri.
- Bhattacharjya, M., Birchall, J., Caro, P., Kelleher, D., and Sahasranaman, V. (2013) Why gender matters in activism: feminism and social justice movements. *Gender & Development*, 21(2), 277-293.
- Biagini, E. (2018) *L'emersione imprevista. Il movimento delle lesbiche in Italia negli anni '70 e '80*. Pisa: ETS.
- Bonu G., (2021), Gendering outcomes. Different Paths, Similar Outcomes: an Analysis of Cross-Generational Biographical Consequences of Activism in Feminist Spaces. *Partecipazione e Conflitto*, 14(3).
- Bonu G., (2022), Diving into the Tide. Contemporary Feminist Mobilizations and Protests: A Global Perspective. *AG About Gender - International Journal of Gender Studies*, 11(21).
- Bonu, G. (2022). Affect into action. Feminist movements and the production of safer spaces: a comparative research between Rome and Madrid. PhD Thesis, Scuola Normale Superiore https://ricerca.sns.it/bitstream/11384/125204/1/Bonu_PhD_Thesis.pdf.
- Bonu, G., Belingardi, C., Castelli, F., and Olcuire, S. (2022) *Gender-Based Violence and Urban Spaces: From Security to Self-Determination. Insights From the Italian Debate*. in: Bows, H. and Fileborn, B. *Geographies of Gender-Based Violence: A Multi-disciplinary Perspectives*. Bristol: Bristol University Press.
- Bosi, L., & Uba, K. (2009) Introduction: the outcomes of social movements. *Mobilization*, 14, 409-415.
- Bracke, M. A. (2012). Building a 'Counter-community of Emotions': Feminist Encounters and Socio-cultural Difference in 1970s Turin. *Modern Italy*, 17(2), 223-236.
- Bracke, M. A. (2014). *Women and the Reinvention of the Political: Feminism in Italy, 1968-1983*. Routledge, New York.
- Braine, N., and Velarde, M. (2022). Self-Managed Abortion: Strategies for Support by a Global Feminist Movement. *Women's Reproductive Health*, 1-20.
- Busi, B. and Fiorilli, O. (2015). Introduzione. Per una prospettiva (trans)femminista sulla salute ai tempi del neoliberalismo. *DWF*, 3 (4), 5:14.
- Caraffi P. (2017) *Christine de Pizan. Una città per sé*. Roma: Carocci editore.
- Castelli, F. and Carocci R. (2021) *Femminismi. Idee, movimenti, conflitti*. Rome: Nova Delphi.

- Castles, Francis G., and Maurizio Ferrera. 1996. "Casa e welfare state. Le contraddizioni dei paesi sud-europei," *Stato e mercato*, 48, 409-432.
- Cavalleri, R. and Robiony S. (2017) *Se non ora quando? Da Di Nuovo a Libere*. Rome: Castelvechchi.
- Cavarero, A., and Restaino, F. (2002). *Le filosofie femministe: due secoli di battaglie teoriche e pratiche*. Pearson Italia Spa
- Chaudhuri, M. (2005). *Feminism in India*. London: Zed books.
- Chironi, D. (2019) Generations in Feminist and LGBT Movements in Italy: The Case of Non Una Di Meno. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 1-28.
- Chironi, D. (2019). Generations in feminist and LGBT movements in Italy: The case of Non Una di Meno. *American Behavioral Scientist* 63 (10): 1–28.
- Chironi, D. (2020). A fragile shield for protecting civil rights: The European Union in the eyes of Italian feminists. *European Journal of Cultural and Political Sociology*, 7(3), 316-346.
- Chistè, L., Del Re, A. and Forti, E. (1978) *Oltre il lavoro domestico*. Feltrinelli, Milano.
- Cirillo, L. (2017) *Utero in affitto o gravidanza per altri?* Milan: FrancoAngeli.
- Cirillo, L. (2018) *Se il mondo torna uomo. Le donne e la regressione in Europa*. Rome: Edizioni Alegre.
- Cirillo, L., Cossutta, C., Guazzo, P., Muscio, M., Padovano, R., and Palvarini, M. (2021) *La terra non è piatta. Mondo lgbtiq*, femminismi plurali e femminismi escludenti*. Milan: Asterisco.
- Cirimele, N. and Panariello, M. (2018), Non una di meno. Un grido globale, in *DWF*, vol. 120, no. 4, pp. 8-14.
- Ciuffreda, Giuseppina, and Biancamaria Frabotta. 1974. *Femminismo e lotta di classe in Italia (1970-1973)*. Roma: Savelli.
- Claude-Mathieu, N. (1984). De la conscience dominée des femmes. *Les cahiers du GRIF*, 29(1), 73-75.
- Constelazione femminista (2020). *La luna che muove le maree: L'assalto al patriarcato*. Milan: Agenzia X.
- Cossutta, C. (2021). Transfeminist politics and populist counterattacks in Italy. *European Journal of English Studies*, 25(2), 154-171.
- Cossutta, C., and Habed, A. J. (2021) From Verona, with love: "anti-gender" mobilizations and transfeminist (re) actions. *Gender: Zeitschrift für Geschlecht, Kultur und Gesellschaft*, (6), 139-154.
- Craddock, E. (2017). Caring about and for the cuts: A case study of the gendered dimension of austerity and anti-austerity activism. *Gender, Work & Organization*, 24(1), 69-82.
- Crenshaw, K. (1991). Mapping the margins: Intersectionality, identity politics, and violence against women of color. *Stanford law review*, 1241-1299.
- Curcio, A. (2021) *Introduzione ai femminismi. Genere, razza, classe, riproduzione: dal marxismo al queer*. Rome: DeriveApprodi.
- D'Amelia, Marina. 1985. "Dalla differenza alle differenziazioni. Le difficili innovazioni dei gruppi," in *Memoria. Rivista di storia delle donne*, 13, 122-131.
- Dalla Costa, M., and James, S. (1975). *The Power of Women and the Subversion of the Community*. Falling Wall Press, Bristol.
- Dang, H. A. H., and Nguyen, C. V. (2021). Gender inequality during the COVID-19 pandemic: Income, expenditure, savings, and job loss. *World Development*, 140, 105-296.
- Del Re, A., Morini, C. Mura, B. and Perini L. (2020) *Lo sciopero delle donne. Lavoro # Trasformazioni del capitale # Lotte*. Rome: Manifestolibri.
- Della Porta, D. (2005). Deliberation in movement: Why and how to study deliberative democracy and social movements. *Acta politica*, 40(3), 336-350.
- Della Porta, D. (2020). Protests as critical junctures: Some reflections towards a momentous approach to social movements. *Social Movement Studies*, 19(5-6), 556-575.
- Della Porta, D., & Rucht, D. (Eds.). (2013). *Meeting democracy: power and deliberation in global justice movements*. Cambridge University Press.
- Della Porta, Donatella. 1996. *Movimenti collettivi e sistema politico in Italia, 1960-1995*. Bari: Laterza.

- Della Porta, Donatella. 2003. "The Women's Movement, the Left and the State: Continuities and Changes in the Italian Case." In Lee A. Banaszak, Karen Beckwith and Dieter Rucht, eds., *Women's Movements Facing the Reconfigured State*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Delphy, C. (2016). *Close to home: A materialist analysis of women's oppression*. London: Verso Books.
- Demurtas, P., Peroni, C. and Mauri, A. (2021) *Orientamenti e buone pratiche*. Guerini Scientifica, Milano.
- Diamond, E., Varney, D., and Amich, C. (Eds.). (2017). *Performance, feminism and affect in neoliberal times*. Berlin: Springer.
- Duggan, L. (2012). *The twilight of equality?: Neoliberalism, cultural politics, and the attack on democracy*. Beacon Press.
- Egidi, Piera. 1985. "Cronaca di una città. Torino," *Memoria. Rivista di storia delle donne*, 13, 103-116.
- Elia, E. (2016). *Se Non Ora Quando? ('If not now, when?') The birth, growth and challenges of a new voice within the feminist scenario in Italy*. In: Schwabenland, C., Lange C., Onyx J. and Nakagawa S. (2016) *Women's emancipation and civil society organisations. Challenging or maintaining the status quo?*. Bristol: Policy Press.
- Ensler, E. (2012). *Se non ora, quando? Contro la violenza e per la dignità delle donne*. Edizioni Piemme.
- Ergas, Yasmine. 1992. "La costruzione del soggetto femminile: il femminismo negli anni '60/'70." In G. Duby and M. Perrot, eds., *Storia delle donne in Occidente. Il Novecento*. Bari: Laterza.
- Ergas, Yasmine. 1980. "Femminismo e crisi di sistema. Il percorso politico delle donne attraverso gli anni ottanta." In *Rivista Italiana di Sociologia*, 4, 543-568.
- Evans, J. (1995). *Feminist theory today: An introduction to second-wave feminism*. London: Sage.
- Evans, R. (2014), *The Feminists. Women's Emancipation Movements in Europe, America and Australasia 1840-1920*. London: Routledge.
- Federici, S. (2015) *Calibano e la strega. Le donne, il corpo e l'accumulazione originaria*. Roma: Mimesis.
- Ferrante, A. A. (2014). Homo skin, hetero masks. A representation of Italian homonationalism. *Les online*, 6(1), 114-121.
- Ferrera, Maurizio. 1996. "Il modello sud europeo di welfare state," *Rivista italiana di scienza politica*, 26, 67-101.
- Fragno, M. and Tola, M. (2022) *Ecologie della cura. Prospettive transfemministe*. Napoli-Salerno: Orthotes.
- Franceschini, F., Giansiracusa, L., Gramolini, C., Zaltieri Pirola S. and Zenobi S. (2021) *Noi le lesbiche. Preferenza femminile e critica al transfemminismo*. Milan: Il dito e la luna.
- Fraser, N. (2021). *Rethinking the public sphere: A contribution to the critique of actually existing democracy*. London-New York: Routledge.
- Freeman, Jo. 1975. *The Politics of Women's Liberation. A Case Study of an Emerging Social Movement and Its Relation to the Policy Process*. New York: David McKay Company.
- Fuxia Block (2016) *Queersultoria: esperimenti di welfare dal basso per un nuovo diritto alla salute e alla vivibilità*. *DWF*, 3 (4), .
- Gago, V. (2019) *La potencia feminista. O el deseo de cambiarlo todo*. Madrid: tranfiantes de Suenos.
- Gago, V. and Cavallero, L. (2019) *Una Lectura Feminista de la Deuda. Vivas, Libres y Desendeudadas Nos Queremos*. Berlin: Rosa Luxemburg Foundation.
- Garofalo Geymonat, G. and Selmi, G. (2022) *Prostituzione e lavoro sessuale in Italia. Oltre le semplificazioni, verso i diritti*. Torino: Rosenberg & Sellier.
- Gelb, Joyce 1989. *Feminism and Politics. A Comparative Perspective*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Gelb, Joyce. 1987. "Social Movement 'Success:' A Comparative Analysis of Feminism in the United States and the United Kingdom." In Katzenstein and Mueller, eds.
- Ghadery, F. (2019). # Metoo—has the 'sisterhood' finally become global or just another product of neoliberal feminism?. *Transnational Legal Theory*, 10(2), 252-274.
- Giorgi, A. (2021). Religious feminists and the intersectional feminist movements: Insights from a case study. *European Journal of Women's Studies*, 28(2), 244-259.

- Giuliani, G., Galetto, M. and Martucci C. (2014) *L'amore ai tempi dello tsunami. Affetti, sessualità e modelli di genere in mutamento*. Verona: Ombre corte.
- Grazioli, Marco, and Giovanni Lodi. 1984. "La mobilitazione collettiva negli anni ottanta: Tra condizione e convinzione." In A. Melucci, ed., *Altri Codici*. Bologna: Il Mulino.
- Guadagni, Anna Mari. 1985. "Nuove facce dell'Udi," *Memoria. Rivista di storia delle donne*, 13, 13-30.
- Guadagnini, Marila. 1995. "The Late-Comers: Italy's Equal Status and Equal Opportunity Agencies." In Dorothy McBride Stetson and Amy G. Mazur, eds., *Comparative State Feminism*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Guillaumin, C. (2002). *Racism, sexism, power and ideology*. London: Routledge.
- Hellman, Judith. 1987. *Journeys Among Women. Feminism in Five Italian Cities*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Hellman, Stephen. 1987. "Feminism and the Model of Militancy in an Italian Communist Federation: Challenges to the Old Style of Politics." In Katzenstein and Mueller, eds.
- Hemmings, C. (2011). *Why stories matter. The Political Grammar of Feminist Theory*. Duke University Press.
- Inés Campillo (2019) 'If we stop, the world stops': the 2018 feminist strike in Spain, *Social Movement Studies*, 18:2, 252-258.
- Irigaray, L. (1985). *Speculum of the other woman*. Cornell University Press.
- Jenson, Jane. 1982. "The Modern Women's Movement in Italy, France and Great Britain," *Comparative Social Research*, 5, 341-175.
- Kantola, J. and Lombardo, E. (2017) *Gender and the Economic Crisis in Europe*. London, Palgrave Macmillan.
- Kaplan, Gisela. 1992. *Contemporary Western Feminism*. London: UCL Press and Allen & Unwin.
- Kaplan, T. (1985). On the socialist origins of International Women's Day. *Feminist Studies*, 11(1), 163-171.
- Katzenstein, Mary Fainsod. 1987. "Comparing the Feminist Movements of the United States and Western Europe: An Overview." In Katzenstein and Mueller, eds.. *The Women's Movements of the United States and Western Europe: Consciousness, Political Opportunity, and Public Policy*. Philadelphia: Temple University Press.
- Keck, W., and Saraceno, C. (2013). The impact of different social-policy frameworks on social inequalities among women in the European Union: The labour-market participation of mothers. *Social Politics*, 20(3), 297-328.
- Lavizzari, A. (2020). *Protesting gender: The LGBTIQ movement and its opponents in Italy*. London: Routledge.
- López, María Pia. Not One Less: Mourning, Disobedience, and Desire. Translated by Frances Riddle. Cambridge: Polity, 2020.
- Lovenduski, J. (2005). *State feminism and political representation*. Cambridge University Press.
- Lovenduski, Joni. 1986. *Women and European Politics: Contemporary Feminism and Public Policy*. Amherst MA: University of Massachussets Press.
- Lugones, M. (2010). Toward a decolonial feminism. *Hypatia*, 25(4), 742-759.
- Lussana, F. (2012) *Il movimento femminista in Italia Esperienze, storie, memorie*. Rome, Carocci.
- Marceddu, E., Fioretti, G. and Salvadori N. (2022) *Essere donne in pandemia. Analisi di percorsi di generazione e amplificazione delle disuguaglianze di genere*. Perugia: cultura e salute editore Perugia.
- Martorano N. and Prearo M. (2020) *Miranti LGBT. Pratiche, politiche e contesti di accoglienza*. Pisa: ETS.
- Mattoni, A., and Pavan, E. (2019). Activist media practices, alternative media and online digital traces: The case of YouTube in the Italian Se non ora, quando? Movement. In *Citizen media and practice* (pp. 152-168). Routledge.
- Mattoni, A., and Treré, E. (2014). Media practices, mediation processes, and mediatization in the study of social movements. *Communication theory*, 24(3), 252-271.
- Melucci, A. (1980) The New Social Movements: A Theoretical Approach, *Social Science Information*, 199–226.
- Monforte, Pierre. *Europeanizing Contention: The Protest against "Fortress Europe" in France and Germany*. New York: Berghahn Books, 2014.
- Montanelli, M., and Hardt, M. (2018). The Unforeseen Subject of the Feminist Strike. *South Atlantic Quarterly*, 117(3), 699-709.

- Montella, T., Picchi, S., and Fiorletta, S. (2019). 2. Il piano femminista contro la violenza di genere dalla performatività dei corpi alla presa di parola: il movimento femminista Non Una Di Meno in Italia. *Studi sulla questione criminale*, 14(1-2), 259-276.
- Morini, C. (2010) *Per amore o per forza. Femminilizzazione del lavoro e biopolitiche del corpo*. Verona: Ombre Corte.
- Morini, C. (2022) *Vite lavorate. Corpi, valore, resistenze al disamore*. Rome: Manifestolibri.
- Mura, B., Peroni, C., and Veneri, C. (2016). *Gender Strike! Il tariffario del lavoro gratuito*. Zappinno, F. (2016) *Il genere tra neoliberalismo e neofondamentalismo*. Verona: Ombre Corte.
- Muraro, L. (2017). *The symbolic order of the mother*. SUNY Press.
- Non Una Di Meno (2017). Abbiamo un piano. Piano femminista contro la violenza maschile sulle donne e la violenza di genere [We have a plan. Feminist plan against male violence over women and gender violence]. https://nonunadimeno.files.wordpress.com/2017/11/abbiamo_un_piano.pdf
- Orloff, Ann Shola. 1993. "Gender and the Social Rights of Citizenship: The Comparative Analysis of Gender and Welfare States," *American Sociological Review* 58, 303-328.
- Outshoorn, Joyce, and Johanna Kantola, eds. 2007. *Changing State Feminism*. Houndmills: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Palmeiro, C. (2020). Ni Una Menos and the Politics of Translation. *Spheres: Journal for Digital Cultures*, (6), 1-7.
- Pavan, E. (2020). We are family. The conflict between conservative movements and feminists. *Contemporary Italian Politics*, 12(2), 243-257.
- Pavan, E., and Mainardi, A. (2018) Striking, Marching, Tweeting. Studying how online networks change together with movements. *Partecipazione e conflitto*, 11(2), 394-422.
- Percovich, L. (2005). *La coscienza nel corpo. Donne, salute e medicina negli anni Settanta*. FrancoAngeli, Milano.
- Peroni, C. (2018) Il# MeToo di Hollywood e il# WeTogether di Non Una Di Meno. Dalla denuncia alla pratica collettiva contro le molestie sessuali nel/del lavoro. In: Bettaglio, M., Mandolini, N. and Ross, S. (2018) *Rappresentare la violenza di genere: Sguardi femministi sulla letteratura, il cinema, il teatro e il discorso mediatico contemporaneo*. Milan: Mimesis.
- Peto, A. (2017). How are anti-gender movements changing gender studies as a profession. *Religion and Gender*, 6(2).
- Pietrobelli, M., Toffanin, A. M., Busi, B., & Misiti, M. (2020). Violence against women in Italy after Beijing 1995: the relationship between women's movement (s), feminist practices and state policies. *Gender & Development*, 28(2), 377-392.
- Planetaria. Femminismi internazionali. *DWF*, 2021, 1-2 (129-130).
- Prearo, M. (2020). *L'ipotesi neocattolica: Politologia dei movimenti anti-gender*. Roma: Mimesis.
- Preciado, P. B. (2013). *Testo junkie: Sex, drugs, and biopolitics in the pharmacopornographic era*. The Feminist Press at CUNY.
- Puar, J. K. (2007). *Terrorist assemblages. Homonationalism in queer time*. Durham: Duke University Press.
- Pustianaz, M. (2011) *Queer in Italia. Differenze in movimento*. Pisa: ETS.
- Redini, V., Vianello F. A. and Zaccagnini F. (2020) *Il lavoro che usura. Migrazioni femminili e salute occupazionale*. Milan: FrancoAngeli.
- Ribeiro, D. (2017) *O que è: lugar de fala?* Belo Horizonte: Feminismos Plurais.
- Rigo, E. (2022) *La straniera. Migrazioni, asilo, sfruttamento in una prospettiva di genere*. Rome: Carocci.
- Rudan, P., [connessioni Precarie, and Non Una di Meno Roma. (2018) "The Strike That Made a Difference." *Critical Times*, no. 1, 241-62.
- Sabatini, F., and Palermo, G. (2021). Posizionamenti transfemministi. Saperi situati e pratiche spaziali nel movimento Non Una di Meno. *Geography Notebooks*, 4(2), 79-90.
- Salamon, G. (2008) *Transfeminism and the Future of Gender*. In: Scott, J. W. (2008) *Women's Studies on the Edge*. Durham: Duke University Press.
- Salvatori, L. "Feminism in Transit: A Study of the Transnational Feminist Movement Non Una di Meno." PhD diss., University of Leicester, 2021.

- Salvatori, L. (2018) Lost between the Waves' or Riding a New Tide? Drawing Connections between Italian and Polish Digitally Mediated Feminism. *Digital Icons*, 19, 73–91.
- Serafini, P. (2020). 'A rapist in your path': Transnational feminist protest and why (and how) performance matters. *European Journal of Cultural Studies*, 23(2), 290-295.
- Settembrini, C. (2020) *Obiezione respinta. Diritto alla salute e giustizia riproduttiva*. Milan: Prospero Editore.
- Sineau, Mariette. 1992. "Le donne nella sfera della politica: diritti delle donne e democrazia." In F.Thebaud, ed., *Storia delle donne in Occidente. Il 900*. Bari-Roma: Laterza.
- Stryker, S. (2004) Transgender Studies: Queer Theory's Evil Twin. *GLQ A Journal of Lesbian and Gay Studies* 10:2:212–5.
- Tarrow, S. (1998) *Power in Movement: Collective Action, Social Movements and Politics*, Cambridge University Press.
- Tarrow, Sidney. 1989. *Democracy and Disorder: Protest and Politics in Italy 1965-1975*. Oxford: Clarendon Press.
- Taylor, K. Y. (2017). *How we get free: Black feminism and the Combahee River Collective*. Haymarket Books.
- Taylor, V. (1989) Social movement continuity: The women's movement in abeyance. *American Sociological Review* 54, 761–775.
- Terzian, P. (2017) *The Ni Una Menos Movement in 21st Century Argentina: Combating More than Femicide*. Dickinson College Honors Theses..
- Terzian, P. (2017). The Ni Una Menos movement in 21st century Argentina: Combating more than femicide. Honors thesis. Dickinson College. https://scholar.dickinson.edu/student_honors/288 (accessed 11 November 2021).
- Toffanin, T. (2011). The Role of Neoliberal Capitalism in reproducing gender inequality in Italy. *Journal of Contemporary European Studies*, 19(3), 379-392.
- Tolbert, M. L. (2020). "Checking in with your people": food, mutual aid, black feminism, and COVID-19. *Gastronomica*, 20(3), 64-65.
- Transnational Social Strike Platform (2018). Power upside down: Women's global strike. LSE Engenderings (blog). <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/gender/2018/03/07/power-upside-down-womens-global-strike> (accessed 11 November 2021).
- Trillò, T. (2018). The Non Una di Meno Feminist Movement in Italy: Connective or Collective?. *Ciencias Sociales y Humanidades Digitales Aplicadas*, 85.
- Vergès, F., and Bohrer, A. J. (2021). *A decolonial feminism*. London: Pluto Press.
- Verloo, M. (Ed.). (2018). *Varieties of opposition to gender equality in Europe*. London-New York: Routledge.
- Vianello, F. A. (2014) *Genere e migrazioni*. Milan: Guerini.
- Zan, A. (2021) *Senza paura. La nostra battaglia contro l'odio*. Milan: Piemme.
- Zappino, F. (2016) *Il genere tra neoliberalismo e neofondamentalismo*. Verona: Ombre corte.
- Zincone, Giovanna. 1985. *Gruppi sociali e sistemi politici: il caso donne*. Milano: Angeli.

5 POLAND

5.1 Introduction

In the introduction provide the basic information on the literature on feminist movements in your country. The brief overview should focus on actors, campaigns, debates and policy outcomes that can be detected in your country in the period 2010-2021.

Polish social movement studies in general are described as provincial and are not very well developed. When it comes to the interest on feminist movement, the situation reflects the general picture. With the women's protests and strikes of 2016 and 2020, there has been a large public debate on the movement itself and its consequences. Nevertheless, there has not been interest abroad with academic circles when it comes to the newest developments in the feminist movement in Poland. What has sparked the biggest interest was the reproduction rights and the struggle to broaden them or at least to keep the status quo. The struggle for reproductive rights in Poland has a long history and can be dated back to the late 1980s. However the shift of power that took place in 2015, combined with radicalization of the discourse, emergence of the far right and anti-gender groups and networks have moved this conflict to a different level often interpreted as a struggle against the current government. The literature and especially analytical texts on the feminist movement in Poland are rare and are often connected to the activist realm as many of the authors are activists at the same time. Interestingly, the issue of intersectionality or structural influence on social movements has largely been overlooked by Polish social movement scholars, who instead focused on more descriptive approaches to presenting the feminist movement.

The 2016 protests have marked an emergence of a new wave of feminist movement in Poland that can be linked to a generational turnover. The feminist movement, although present in Poland since the late 1980s, only in the last few years have gained a bigger momentum. 2016 was different because of the geographical distribution of the protests that have emerged also in the countryside and small, provincial towns, but also have gathered a broader range of society. Participants of the 2016 and especially 2020 were much younger than their predecessors and often had no experience in activism. This undermined the previously existing division between the so-called liberal and radical feminists. The liberal feminists are often connected to the Polish Women's Congress, an event taking place annually populated by self-made women, liberal politicians, and some older celebrities. It is out of this environment that the Polish women's party emerged in the late 1990s achieving no real success in electoral politics. The Congress was often criticized for not seeing social issues connected to gendered politics and to focus on meta level politics, especially language. The radical circles on the other hand were mostly seen on the 8th of March each year when a so-called manifa was organized in biggest cities. The organizers of these events were also active in other social movements, often left leaning and of anarchist background, calling for the end of patriarchy, raising claims against sexism, gender-based violence and alike. Because of the radical language used during those protests and a rather radical agenda of the movement, the support for this group was rather limited. The radical feminists, as opposed to the liberal ones, used street protests, performances, and direct action as a main repertoire of their activism. Liberal feminists were more focused on litigation, lobbying, and charitable work. Both strains got involved in self-help networks in order to provide legal and financial assistance to women in need.

Apart from the reproductive rights and the gendered opposition to the ruling party, other elements of feminist critique were less developed, for instance struggles over alimony fund, a state-owned fund that pays alimony when people who are supposed to do that are not fulfilling their duties, as it happens in the majority of cases where alimony is supposed to be paid. In the first half of the study period there were also numerous debates about the position of women on the labor market, as women were often

underpaid, without proper job contracts and in general were exploited. However, with the rise of the far right populism and the dominance of conservative, Catholic ideology and worldview, these discussions took a more ideological stance, focused on combating the patriarchal, conservative vision of gendered politics, as it happened for both radical and liberal feminist groups.

5.2 The history of the feminist movements and its context

Based on the available literature try to briefly describe the roots of the movements and its development in the period 2010-2021.

Poland is considered a conservative country, mostly due to the political influence of the Catholic Church, and the role of pope John Paul II in public discourse. The imagined gender regime is conservative: with the man being the breadwinner for the family, and the woman taking care of the household. However, in the recent years (partially because of the process of secularisation) this image is not true anymore. To the despair of right-wing politicians, more and more women focus on their career (due to a recent poll, 68% of women aged 18-45 do not want to have children), the support for same-sex civil partnerships is growing and reached 64% in June 2022 (with 48% supporting marriage equality, 47% opposing it), and support for abortion up to 12 weeks reached 70% in November 2022 (both polls Ipsos for oko.press). At the same time Poland has one of the lowest gender pay gap in all EU countries. The growing split between the political class and the society generates new conflicts and amplifies the already existing ones.

Reproductive rights became an important topic in Polish public debate soon after the 1989 transition. Under communist rule, women had the right to abort on demand and - partly due to the lack of effective contraception - became a method of fertility regulation. In the Solidarity camp, which took a (neo)conservative turn in the mid-1980s, the anti-choice lobby is becoming stronger and more vocal. One of the points of the second meeting of Solidarity union delegates was a call for a ban on abortion in Poland. With the growing power of the Catholic fundamentalists and the ambivalent position of the liberals, there was an increasing erosion of women's reproductive rights.

The status quo was based on the 1993 legislation known as the 'abortion compromise', which allowed abortion in four situations: when the pregnancy is the result of a crime (rape or incest), when the life or health of the mother is endangered, when the foetus exhibits incurable or serious genetic defects, or because of 'serious life difficulties'. The latter case was abolished by the Constitutional Court in 1997. Over the years there have been many attempts to further restrict or liberalise the law in Poland, but the 'compromise' has remained intact. Nevertheless, a growing anti-choice lobby has been gaining power and resources, thanks to the support of the Catholic Church and international networks of religious and anti-choice organisations (Suchanow 2020).

The other context relevant for studying women's activism is connected to politics. The 2015 elections (presidential and parliamentary) in Poland have not only shifted the politics even more to the right than before (with no leftist party present in the parliament), but also have ignited a wave of hatred towards all kinds of 'others'. The dynamics of changes of the mainstream discourse can also be seen when analyzing public debate on abortion. There is an observable shift within the society towards more pro-choice positions with a simultaneous growing conservatism of the authorities that allow for more radical concepts and ideas to be discussed as potential new laws. In 2018 around 46% of the population expressed support for the idea of broadly available abortion whereas 32% were against such a solution. At the same time in a study from April 2018 44% of the society does not want any changes to the already existing law, 37% wants to liberalize it and 11% wants to restrict it even further, showing the importance of formulating questions in public surveys. In the first case the question was framed in a way of personal liberty, in the latter the question was more about legal solutions where people tend to be more restrained in their answers.

The first attempt to restrict the abortion law after PiS's victory took place in 2016. The Sejm decided to discuss a Civic Initiative written by Kaja Godek and her organization (Life and Family Foundation) proposing a total ban on abortion in Poland. This triggered mass protests by women that spread across the country, creating new inter-generational alliances and activating women in small towns. With successive waves of protests in 2017, 2018 and a much smaller one in 2019, feminist activist networks consolidated, crystallized and matured.

Monday 3 October 2016 was a day in Poland that tens of thousands of people (mainly women) took to the streets to protest against an attempt to tighten Poland's already restrictive abortion law. According to official police sources, 143 protests were organized on this day, with a total of 98,000 people taking part. According to data from the Centre for Public Opinion Research, 3 percent of the Polish population actively participated in the protests and 52 per cent supported them (58 percent of those who had heard about the protest). This discrepancy may be due to the varied forms of participation in the protest, when it is not only taking to the street that counts, but also taking a day off work or wearing black.

The majority of key developments within the Polish feminism movement are related to the struggles over reproductive rights that are described in the following sections. However, a couple of developments between 2010 and 2021 are crucial here and mostly are related to the shift within the political scene that happened in 2015 when the Law and Justice party has won both parliamentary and presidential elections and anti-choice and anti-gender organizations have gained a very strong and powerful ally. Moreover, the #MeToo campaign that emerged around 2016 also had an impact on this feminist movement and its popularity with more and more young people sympathizing with it and relating to issues of gender related violence within Polish Society. The other key element was 2020 when a nearly complete ban on abortion was introduced following the decision of the Constitutional Court that ruled one of the situations where legal abortion is allowed as unconstitutional. The anti-choice activists not only had political support of the ruling party and also some parts of the liberal opposition parties as well, but through their think tanks they managed to introduce some of their own people into key state institutions such as the Constitutional Tribunal, the Supreme court, the parliament, and others.

Over the years the Polish feminist movement began to be more and more interconnected with its EU and global counterparts. When it comes to National Networks and connection to other National actors, these include predominantly NGOs focused on topics broadly related to women's issues. The intensity of 2016 and 2020 protests and their presence also outside of Poland as 38 protest events were held outside of Poland in 2020, have brought the attention of other women's movements worldwide on the Polish feminist scene. This has led to growing cooperation between global networks, especially those struggling for reproductive rights for instance from Latin America that often is pointed out as a role model for the Polish movement. In 2016 there was also growing interest in the trajectory and achievements of the Irish women's movement, which was growing as far as the critique towards the Catholic church in Poland was rising. The international cooperation was both on the side of the radical as well as liberal groups, who were looking for international counterparts relevant to their ideological profile. These international connections differed also in the degree of formalisation / institutionalisation.

Several specific anti-choice groups have increased in popularity in recent years, with the Pro-Right to Life Foundation becoming one of the most well-known due to the new repertoire used in their activities. In particular, they sent vans with anti-abortion (as well as anti-LGBTQ) banners onto the streets of Polish cities, neglecting to lose court cases that forbade them to do so. These vans contributed to the escalation of the discourse, as the counter-group Stop the Nonsense Collective

began to block such vans and sometimes vandalised some of them, eventually leading to an escalation of the anti-LGBT campaign.

Another important actor is Ordo Iuris, an organisation founded mainly by conservative lawyers, which aims to ban the right to abortion altogether, including in vitro programmes. Ordo Iuris uses lawsuits and in recent years they have managed to secure positions in the state apparatus and among various statutory bodies. The main leader of the current wave of protests - Marta Lempart - has had several court cases brought by Ordo Iuris, and has been formally barred by a court decision from calling the 160organization "Kremlin-sponsored religious fundamentalists".

5.3 Actors, organizations and organizational models

This section aims to explore the composition of actors included in the network of feminist movements (movements, associations, anti-violence centres, NGOs, political parties).

The feminist movement in Poland – like in other places – is composed of various formalised organisations of civil society (NGOs), social movement organisations, networks, up to ad hoc mobilisations. Some scholars (Mandes 2004) also include in this picture gender studies departments present at some universities. NGOs in Poland in general take two legal forms: of foundations (fundacja) and associations (stowarzyszenie). Due to a rather simple registration process, some of the grassroots initiatives also establish front organisations to gain access limited to legalised initiatives: some types of funding, different access to public information etc. In general, the more liberal organisations tend to have a more formalised and institutionalised structure, and more radical initiatives have a more informal structure, typical for social movements. Podemski (2020, ...) points out that DZIEWUCHY DZIEWUCHOM is an example of such type, as it was organised mostly online, with a central coordinating body (called 'matecznik') and loose structure in which local chapters have a large autonomy, calling it the most de-organised group of the post-2015 pro-democratic movements in Poland.

Centrum Praw Kobiet/ Women's Rights Centre , <https://cpk.org.pl/> /foundation

Women's Rights Centre was founded in 1993/1994 with the financial support of The German Marshall Fund of the United States. The Foundation started its work in January 1995 and its first main goal was to initiate legislative changes to improve women's situation and guarantee gender equality in Poland. Later on, the Foundation started focusing also on the society and providing legal and psychological services to discrimination victims.

The Centre is supported by other institutions, such as Stefan Batory Foundation, The Ford Foundation, Open Society Institute, and Levi Strauss Foundation. It realised projects with multiple partners, including Warsaw and Masovian Voivodeship Employers Union or Prison for Women in Lubliniec, Poland. Women's Rights Centre, as the only one in Poland, took part in the European Commission's Daphne Funding Programme.

For over 20 years, the Foundation was taking a variety of innovative actions on both national and international level, including working in the Polish Parliament, Council of Europe, and European Parliament. The Centre is a founder of Women Against Violence Europe. It worked with OSCE, European Women's Lobby, Women, Law and Development International, Network of East West Women, and many other organizations focused on women's rights. The national level cooperation includes working with the Federation for Women and Family Planning, The National Women's Information Centre OŚKA, or The Feminist Initiative.

Fundacja Feminoteka/Feminoteka Foundation <https://feminoteka.pl>

Feminoteka Foundation was established in 2005. It coordinates in Poland the global action One Billion Rising and the Women's Anti-Violence Network (associating local women leaders from all over Poland

engaged in counteracting violence against women). The organisation primarily supports women experiencing violence. It provides free psychological, legal and therapeutic support, runs support groups and special yoga for women with PTSD. It organises workshops, debates and actions on violence, especially sexual violence.

Fundacja na rzecz Kobiet i Planowania Rodziny (FEDERA)/The Foundation for Women and Family Planning, formerly federation. <https://federa.org.pl/o-nas/>

It is a non-governmental organisation fighting for reproductive justice, active since 1991. It was established as an agreement between five organisations - the League of Polish Women, the Polish Feminist Association, the Pro Femina Association, Neutrum - the Association for a World Neutral State and the Association of Girls and Christian Women Poland Y.W.C.A. Since 1999, the Federation has had the status of an advisory organisation to the United Nations Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC). Since 2022, it has been operating no longer as an association but as an independent foundation.

Ogólnopolski Strak Kobiet (OSK)/The All-Poland Women's Strike (OSK) (foundation from 7 May 2019),

<https://www.facebook.com/ogolnopolskistrajkkobiet/> http://strajkkobiet.eu/?fbclid=IwAR1ul-7yfw7_lp1XBoJcx4RVy7YXVVV_cg6Qg5YXdWcNb6NJP-NvO-GpNFs

The All-Poland Women's Strike (OSK) is a Polish feminist social movement formed in September 2016. It was formed in protest following the rejection by the Polish Sejm of the 'Save the Women' bill and the simultaneous referral of the 'Stop Abortion' bill to committee work.

OSK does not formally have a head office or a board of directors (although Marta Lempart, a leader of the movement, is on the board of the OSK Foundation), only a helpdesk - a nationwide support committee run by activists (Marta Lempart and Natalia Pancewicz). The helpdesk is responsible for raising, distributing and settling funds for the OSK's activities, providing local Strike groups with visual identification and materials (poster and flyer designs, flags, banners, badges), support in overcoming formalities and other difficulties, ensuring the visibility and presence of the Strike idea and logo in the media, handling social media and traditional media. In the Women's Strike, the principle of full autonomy of local Strike groups applies. This means that when acting together, the local groups are bound by minimal rules - a common name, slogan and basis of visual identity, as well as formal and material support from the helpdesk. The scheme and content of the activities of the individual local groups is free of interference from e.g. the helpdesk.

The demands of the National Women's Strike:

1. Full reproductive rights:

- maintenance of standards of maternity care
- access to modern free contraception and sterilisation procedures
- access to safe abortion
- subsidies for in vitro
- most up-to-date generation of prenatal tests

2. State free of superstitions

- reliable sexual education
- school education in line with scientific knowledge
- non-Vatican medical care

- abolition of the so-called "conscience clause"
- religion in parishes (and not in schools as it is now) and at the expense of the Church
- an independent commission on paedophilia in the Church
- the imposition of absolute penalties on perpetrators and those guilty of covering up the crime of paedophilia in the Church

3. Implement and apply the Istanbul Convention:

- shift budgetary funding from the Church to organisations fighting violence against women
- the prosecution and punishment of perpetrators of domestic violence, with paroled / suspended sentences reduced to a minimum
- the absolute prosecution of rapists and the implementation of procedures to prevent secondary victimisation
- protection of victims and isolation of perpetrators
- cooperation between the government and non-governmental organisations in the implementation of the Istanbul Convention
- prosecute hate speech as a source of violence

4. Improvement of the economic situation of women

- retirement security for unpaid work by women
- real social security for families of persons with disabilities
- effective collection of alimony by the state and punishment of alimony debtors
- raising the threshold for entitlement to benefits from the Alimony Fund to the average salary
- equal pay regardless of gender

5. Poland for all:

- Poland that is a state under the rule of law with free courts, free elections and free media
- Poland in which human rights are for everyone, including women, LGBTQIA+ people, people with disabilities, national, ethnic and religious minorities, seniors, the economically disadvantaged
- Poland in which organisations that make reference to fascism and Nazism are outlawed and action is taken against the militarisation of society
- Poland in the European Union.

The OSK has moved from protesting to creating a network of civic support throughout the country. After the Russian invasion of Ukraine on 24 February 2022, the OSK became actively involved in helping refugees arriving in Poland from Ukraine by organising demonstrations of support for Ukraine, fundraising for Ukraine, and assistance to refugee women. The organisational structure of the OSK has made it possible to provide more local and tailor-made assistance throughout the country.

The All-Poland Women's Strike also actively supports the LGBTQ+ community. At the end of December 2022, the organization launched its social campaign for full rights for rainbow families "FamilyOriented".

Dziewuchy Dziewuchom/Gals for Gals, foundation, <https://www.dziewuchydziewuchom.pl>

Dziewuchy Dziewuchom - a grassroots nationwide social movement with around 50 local chapters. It was initiated with the founding of a Facebook group on 1 April 2016 as a response to a bill to tighten Poland's current laws regulating the termination of pregnancy. The name was registered as a trademark in 2018 by the founders of the original group. This was met with criticism from local groups. Since 2018 Dziewuchy Dziewuchom has been functioning also as a foundation.

The main objective of the group is to advocate for Human Rights regarding the possibility of abortion in Poland and to monitor actions aiming at tightening the law regulating the possibility of abortion. In addition, it deals with topics such as women's reproductive rights, sex education, sexism, and the situation (social, cultural, political) of women in Poland and abroad. The group declares itself to be politically active, but independent of any party. As it is declared on the website Dziewuchy Dziewuchom primarily target people with uteruses, but also other groups, including refugees and those in the LGBTQIAP+ community⁴³.

Dziewuchy Dziewuchom operates through social media to popularise feminist values by sharing press articles, reporting on initiatives and campaigns for gender equality, as well as reporting on abortion legislation and commenting on current events. At the same time, it aims to open up the discussion to a wider audience by providing the opportunity to speak out on the Facebook group and add comments to social media posts. In addition, it provides support for those affected by sexual violence, organises charity collections, facilitates access to information on reproductive health.

Aborcja Bez Granic/ Abortion Without Borders (Abortion Support Network), <https://abortion.eu/pl/>

Abortion Without Borders launched on 11 December 2019. It is an initiative of six organisations (Kobiety W Sieci, Abortion Dream Team, Women Help Women, Ciocia Basia, Abortion Network Amsterdam, Abortion Support Network) working together to help people access abortions at home with pills or abroad in clinics. One of the organisations working with Abortion Without Borders is Kobiety W Sieci⁴⁴ (Women on the Net), which since 2006 has been providing advice on the options available to pregnant people, including objective, fact-based information on abortion. Abortion Without Borders' services include providing practical information, financial support, making appointments, translation services, stays in accommodation or volunteer homes, creative problem-solving, advice on the most up-to-date travel restrictions and regulations during the Covid-19 pandemic and much more. Abortion Without Borders works with individuals and institutions offering abortions in England, the Netherlands, Germany and other European countries to provide access to abortion for those forced to travel abroad⁴⁵.

Porozumienie Kobiet 8 Marca/Women's Agreement of 8 March, <https://manifa.org/onas/>

Porozumienie Kobiet 8 Marca is an informal group formed in 2000 as a response to the events in Lubliniec, when the police, on the basis of an anonymous tip, detained a woman in a doctor's office where an abortion was to be performed and, without informing her of her rights, transported her for

⁴³ <https://www.dziewuchydziewuchom.pl/o-nas/>

⁴⁴ <https://www.maszwybor.net/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.asn.org.uk/pl/o-aborcji-bez-granic/>

forced gynaecological examinations. Porozumienie Kobiet 8 Marca was formed by people who at the time sent a letter of protest to the Ombudsman and decided to protest publicly every year on 8 March by organising Manifas (manifestations) and demanding equal rights for women and changes opposing discrimination of women under Polish law. The group's name refers to International Women's Day, celebrated on 8 March. The group cooperates only with NGOs, other informal groups and trade unions, refusing to work with political parties.

Stowarzyszenie Kongres Kobiet/The Congress of Women Association
<https://www.kongreskobiet.pl/o-nas>

The Congress of Women Association was established in 2009. As a non-governmental organization, it operates at the national as well as local levels with 35 regional representatives. Its mission is to ensure equal rights and opportunities for women and men in the political, social and economic spheres. One of its biggest successes was to prepare a citizen's bill on parity in political elections which was adopted by Parliament in 2011. It adopted a policy of a minimum share of 35% of women candidates. The association has proven its capacity to initiate, coordinate and implement projects, run trainings, programs and organize meetings, seminars and conferences. Every year the association organizes the Congress of Women with over 20 thematic centers, gathering around 4000- 5000 participants from all regions in Poland and from other countries. The aim of these meetings is to raise awareness, exchange information and best experiences regarding women's activism and problems in Poland. They build mutual support, deepen relationships, and have a program-building agenda.

Since its establishment the Association Council consists of well-known and influential female politicians, scientists, business women and journalists, among others: Henryka Bochniarz⁴⁶, Bogna Czałczyńska, Danuta Hübner⁴⁷, Magdalena Środa, Dorota Warakomska, Małgorzata Fuszara.

Ośrodek Informacji Środowisk Kobietych OŚKA/The National Women's Information Centre OŚKA

OŚKA is a non-governmental, non-profit foundation which assists all women-related organisations and initiatives, encourages women's participation in public life, and provides information to all those interested in women's rights and feminism in Poland and abroad. OŚka was founded in 1996 in Warsaw under the auspices of the Women's Programme of the Stefan Batory Foundation. It was established after many months of consultations with several women's organisations.

Ogólnopolskie Pogotowie Dla Ofiar Przemocy w Rodzinie „Niebieska Linia”/ The Polish Nationwide Emergency Service for Victims of Domestic Violence

<https://www.niebieskalinia.pl/>

The Polish Nationwide Emergency Service for Victims of Domestic Violence has been created in 1995 as a branch of The Psychology Health Institute under The Polish Psychologists' Association. The

⁴⁶ Henryka Bochniarz: In 1991, Minister for Industry and Trade. From 1999 to 2019 President of the employers' organisation Konfederacja Lewiatan, from 2019 Chairwoman of the organisation's General Council. Candidate for the office of President of the Republic of Poland in the 2005 elections.

⁴⁷ Danuta Hübner: Head of the Chancellery of the President of the Republic of Poland from 1997 to 1998, Head of the Office of the Committee of European Integration from 2001 to 2003, Member of the Council of Ministers in Leszek Miller's government from 2003 to 2004, first Commissioner representing Poland in the European Union (for regional policy), Member of the European Parliament for the 7th, 8th and 9th parliamentary term.

organization has been providing services within a wide range of anti-domestic violence measures and educating on this topic. Its services include:

- Counselling
- Legal Clinic
- Polish Nationwide E-mail Emergency Service
- Polish Nationwide Telephone Emergency Service
- Centre for Victims of Domestic Violence
- Training courses and advisory activities for national organisations (such as Departments, the Police etc.) as well as for private persons
- Publication of "Blue Line" magazine

Fundacja „Pomoc Kobietom i Dzieciom”/ The "Help for Women and Children" Foundation

<https://www.przemockid.pl/>

The "Help for Women and Children" Foundation started its activities on 4 July 2001. The main aim of the Foundation is to help victims of domestic violence.

The Foundation is also the only one in Poland to help victims of domestic violence by perpetrators employed in the uniformed services (Police, Army, Border Guard, Fire Brigade and CBS, ABW, BOR, etc.). The Foundation also offers assistance in, inter alia, drafting, preparing, and writing pleadings, preparing letters to authorities or administrative bodies, legal advice as well as psychological and sexological assistance. The organisation also supports victims of violence in court proceedings by acting as representatives of a non-governmental organisation.

5.4 Allies

This part explains what kind of alliances feminist movements develop, both extra-institutional and within institutions.

Around 2018, many of the activists involved in the 2016 protests tried their luck in local elections and became councillors in their towns, and in 2019 several small-town activists also became MPs. These four years of activism gave them the opportunity to gain the skills, qualifications and social contacts that allowed them to quickly and successfully organise their small-town protests in October 2020.

Eight stars (hence the name of the Eight Star Movement) was first used during the presidential campaign in the summer of 2020. In the current protest cycle, it is the most shouted slogan, causing a stir among the political class and some commentators (from the conservative and liberal side, left-wing MPs sometimes appear on TV with posters written on them ***** **). Within days, several artists recorded protest songs using the theme, one of which was viewed by Cypriots on YouTube within the first 48 hours and became the unofficial anthem of the October 2020 street parties.

Finally, there is the growing popularity of groups usually described as radicals - anti-fascists and anarchists. The self-advocacy anti-repression group Anarchist Black Cross is 'officially' a partner of women's protests, DIY guides on how to behave during demonstrations, how to interact with the police, in particular information on prisoners' rights and the like are widespread and before they became the domain of radical groups. Radical groups also use their knowledge of staging happenings and disruptive actions, often pushing for a more radical repertoire, as in the case of Poznan on 24 October, when a 10,000-strong demonstration moved from one of the main squares to the island of Ostrów Tumski, where the cathedral and the bishops' palace are located. An attempt to occupy the latter was made, but was put on hold due to the position of some organisers. Earlier in the day, an

abandoned hospital in the centre of Poznań was squatted by a group of activists and symbolically transformed into an abortion clinic.

Sometimes support for protests came from unexpected quarters. A few weeks earlier, the ruling Law and Justice party had introduced an amendment to animal welfare and protection legislation, which included, among other things, a ban on the fur industry and the religious slaughter of animals. These new laws, in particular the short 12-month *vacatio legis*, sparked protests among farmers. The popular English-language blog Notes From Poland wrote: "Although the protests were organised and led by women's rights groups such as the Women's Strike, support also came from some unexpected places. In Nowy Dwór Gdański, a town of 10,000 people in northern Poland, local farmers joined the protests by slowly driving their tractors at the head of the march, reports Wirtualna Polska. Signs on the fronts of the vehicles said: "We want a choice, not PiS-terror" (referring to the name of the ruling PiS party) and "Fuck Off." (Fuck Off), which became the slogan of the protests" (Wilczek 2020).

In addition, the large mining union August '80 issued a statement in support of the protesters. The union's leader, Bogusław Ziętek, said that the organisation considered the "violation of the compromise that has been in place in Poland for several years" to be "unacceptable". Ziętek warned that the government's assumption of the "role of super-violator of human consciences" suggests that it is "moving towards a totalitarian state". While the abortion ruling was made by the Constitutional Court, the ruling of the Law and Justice Party is widely perceived to be behind it' (Wilczek 2020).

What is significant for the last wave of engagement and activism is that these groups do not stem out from the usual environment of radical left libertarian movements in Poland, but involve and engage different social groups: former dissidents and people of the 50+ age group or students, many of whom are without prior experience in activism. Thus, they break the stereotype of "professional" and experienced activists. One event that also seems to play an important role was the Polish Women's Strike in October 2016. The new wave of feminist activists that emerged from that event began to interpret feminism more broadly, as part of a larger struggle against exclusion and oppression. One of the key slogans of the 2018 anti-fascist demonstration in Warsaw was: "Glitter, Pink, Antifascism". This is a significant step: a shift from the interpretation of queer identity questions and similar topics as "redundant" towards interest in class economic conflicts. Also, many members of Student Antifascist Committees entered their activism through Black Monday and currently they often object not only to the presence of nationalists or neo-Nazis at the universities, but also to the use of homophobic or misogynist language; such cases are immediately communicated to the public through their Facebook profiles. One of the activists of the Warsaw's section of Ogólnopolski Strajk Kobiet explains why her group joined the anti-fascist protest: *We have decided to join the anti-fascist coalition, because we believe that in 2017 it is not enough to be a feminist. Women must become anti-fascists. We are set against the wall. Neo-fascists are part of the movement that pushes us to serve a merely reproductive role. There is nothing left for us but to take matters into our own hands.*

This intersectionality not only affects the repertoire of claims and topics taken up by the activists, but also radicalizes them, as being feminist in the context of Polish post-2015 politics has also become a radical label (Muszel, Piotrowski 2018). This affects the moderate groups as well; besides the aforementioned changes in focus of the activism (Domaradzka 2016), the moderate activists are beginning to formulate political claims.

As one of the activists referred (Piotrowski, 2020):

We are less polite – and rightly so, in my opinion. People who fight in feminist organizations have ceased to be so polite. They have realized that they do not have to be, and secondly that they should not, because if their rights are broken there is no point in being polite. There was an article in "Wysokie Obcasy" [a weekend extra to a liberal daily "Gazeta Wyborcza"] claiming that women should learn to

fight with class for their rights, that they should write articles instead of going out the streets. As we were at the BlackProtest in Warsaw, our representative of the Tri-City FEBRA had a speech about what was happening in Gdynia, that the march interfered with a religious procession. Then she said that they asked them to be civil and polite, not to disturb anyone, because there were good people in the procession. And how can you be polite and cultural when people break your rights and behave the way they do?

Broadly understood feminist politics are more often the domain of leftist parties, making Poland a particularly interesting case as in the 2015-2019 term of parliament there was no leftist party in the Polish parliament. Being extra-parliamentary opposition, the influence of the Left party in Poland was much smaller, whereas after 2019 some of its members (usually with activist background) have used their legal tools to inspect police stations, intervene during protest pacification and were bringing up movements' agendas onto the floor of the parliament.

The situation in Poland and in particular the development within the area of civil society studies, as the growing intersectionality between state or institutional actors (Ombudsman offices, municipal authorities) and civil society actors, as local authorities are often in conflict with the central government and are strongholds of the liberal opposition in Poland. Such a situation, similar to the one described by Klein and Lee (2019) – raises questions about the conditions of the 'forward and backward infiltration' of the civil society sector taking place that asks for a more dynamic approach to the topic than before. In the case of feminist movement, there is an initiative 'local government friendly towards women' [samorząd przyjazny kobietom] due to which

When it comes to municipal policies, the situation has been different as big cities in Poland are the stronghold of liberal and left opposition. In the recent local elections none of the major cities has elected a right wing president or mayor, and the migrant/refugee policies have been used as one of the tools of anti-governmental struggles of the local municipalities. However, the majority of the local news policies budget comes from the central budget anyway, so the support for local NGOs has been a troubled one, and there was a bigger difficulty in funding countrywide projects.

There is an observable change in relations between grassroots activists and political parties and within the positioning of political parties versus social challenges. Previously there were numerous tensions between activists from grassroots groups (more often leaning to the radical side) and NGO activists (usually more moderate in their claims and repertoires of action), that on one hand accused themselves of 'not serious ways of doing politics' and 'becoming sellouts for the system' on the other hand (Piotrowski 2009).

The changes in the modus operandi for both the grassroots activists and the political party members resulted among others in withdrawing from no logo rule, previously a sine qua non condition for any movement-party cooperation. In the period of first PiS government (2015-2019) the cooperation looked different than nowadays, as there was no left-wing party in the Polish parliament so left parties – a natural ally of progressive grassroots groups – became an ally in extra-parliamentary politics. This allowed left wing party members to remain active on the streets and with grassroots groups, and to include such actions in the program of the left party.

Overall, the Polish activists are skeptical about cooperating with political parties during protests. In particular, they see a risk that the political parties gain further political capital from such co-organized events, while the activists end up doing a disproportion-ate amount of the grass-roots level work. In Poland grassroots activists have enforced the "no logo" rule both during smaller events and within broader coalitions as, for instance, happened during the anti-ACTA protests of early 2012. This approach limits the party's access to microphone during the protests because the activists suspect party members to use their presence at a street demonstration to promote their own party.

Such approach of grassroots activists does not seem to change much over time, however, in the case of strong polarisation of the political scene, certain topics, and growing repression from the police and counter-movements, members of political parties are more and more accepted at demonstrations organised by grassroots activists or – in particular the Left party – organise their events and invite activists to join. This can also be a result of a generational turnaround within the ranks of the Polish left party, whose many MPs have activist experience in grassroots groups, and one of the groups forming the Left party – Partia Razem – can be called a movement party without any doubt.

5.5 Themes and agendas

The research project focuses on five thematic policy areas: (1) labor market, (2) health & reproductive rights, (3) migration, (4) LGBTQ+ rights and (5) gender-based violence. Describe how these topics emerge in the feminist movements in your country and whether these policy issues are/were a trigger for feminist movements to mobilise. Define any other topics that are also important and do not fit into these five policy areas, if found in the literature. Please, organize this part of the report in five (or more) subparagraphs according to the thematic areas, but address only those areas that are covered in the literature.

One of the recent controversies that has gone through the published feminist movement was the issue of trans exclusionary radical feminists (TERFs). The phenomenon of TERFism, although publicised, is marginal in Poland - the vast majority of feminist organisations in Poland are trans-inclusive. Until 2021, the attitudes of a few people recognised as TERF (Iza Palińska, Urszula Kuczyńska, Kaya Szulczewska) were known mainly to those interested in queerness and transgenderism, on top of following these threads on social media, including closed left-wing groups on FB. The emergence of this topic from its niche came in January 2021 with the Women's Strike and the discussion around the phrase 'people with uteruses', which appeared at the demonstrations and which TERFs believed would displace the women-centred discourse.

In Poland (as in other Central and Eastern European countries), due to the cultural isolation of the People's Republic of Poland, the process of women's emancipation proceeded differently. The achievements of successive waves of feminism emerged simultaneously; women in Poland were professionally and politically active earlier than in the West, while at the same time, they were more tightly bound by domestic responsibilities. For this reason, the dispute over women's spaces, practically absent from formal structures in Poland, may seem artificial, if not simply imported from the English TERF's wars.

In general, Polish women's activism is undermined and devalued by the closed discursive structures that result from the dominance of the conservative discourse disseminated by the mainstream media. The label 'feminist activist' is seen as a challenge rather than a neutral, descriptive term. In a 2018 survey conducted for a Polish women's magazine, only 5.5 per cent of respondents admitted to being feminists and 18 per cent to having such a label. At the same time, however, 9 per cent said they supported "all feminist claims", 21 per cent - that they support "most such claims", and 42 per cent - that they agree with "only some". The authors of the survey report in question highlight that in small and provincial towns: "even fewer women self-identify as feminists and express support for feminist

claims. Only 5 percent of Polish women consider themselves feminists, although their demands are supported by the majority⁴⁸.

What was happening on the streets of Poland in 2020 shows what has happened to the generation that is now becoming adults. A large number of particularly Polish young men are actively supporting women on the streets, chanting slogans in support of women and joining other forms of protest. The support (coming even from conservative circles such as football fans and hooligans) for women's struggle for reproductive rights suggests that changes in the understanding of gender roles in Poland are much greater than previously expected.

A distinctive part of this phenomenon is the narrative of rejection of the group known as 'dzieders' (roughly translated as 'old folk') - politicians, opinion leaders and former dissidents who criticised the 'vulgar' narrative and slogans of the protests and the repertoire of protests. Mostly young people, participating in and organising strikes and women's protests, among others, coined the term and began to refuse to listen to and discuss with 'grandparents'. In Poznan, the local chapter of the Committee for the Defence of Democracy, a group often associated with people over 50 and linked to liberal circles, was expelled from the committee organising the protests under the argument of trying to hijack the protests, suggesting an alliance with football hooligans (who marched through the city chanting 'death to antifa'), and mansplaining.

For many years, abortion was a controversial topic and performing abortions was a social taboo. This is also reflected in the numbers, as around 1,000 legal abortions are performed annually. According to Ewa Majewska (2020), "unofficially, according to one of the main feminist organisations in the country, the Federation for Women and Family Planning, around one hundred thousand abortions are performed in Poland every year". As Ewa Majewska continues, "Every newspaper in Poland advertises abortion - albeit under the name of 'inducing menstruation' or 'regulating the menstrual cycle'. Many doctors who do not want to perform abortions in public hospitals agree to perform abortions in private clinics. It is all a question of money - and connections" (Majewska 2020).

Since the aborted protests for reproductive rights related to changes in abortion law, it seems that this is no longer a discursive taboo. Firstly, there are few initiatives supporting legal access to abortion in any form ('morning after pill' or helping Polish women to organise the procedure abroad, usually in Germany, Slovakia and the Netherlands). These initiatives - Legal Abortion, Abortion Dream Team, Abortion Without Borders - are increasingly publicly advertised on the Internet or on the streets with stickers and the introduction of a helpline whose number is painted on walls, pavements and sometimes on church facades. There are also numerous public statements (on the Internet, also by celebrities - also a novelty in this type of protest action - or at protests) by women who have had to have an abortion and how in many cases it saved their lives.

5.5.1 Labor market,

Women still suffer discrimination on the Polish labour market.

⁴⁸ "Wysokie Obcasy", 22 September 2018, <http://www.wysokieobcasy.pl/wysokie-obcasy/>

7,163229,23952656,tylko-5-proc-polek-uwaza-sie-za-feministki-choc-postulaty.html?disableRedirects=true#s=BoxWyboLink (accessed November 2020).

Research of Hays Poland „Kobiety na rynku pracy 2022” (Women on the labour market 2022) indicates that 53 % of women and 28% of men have encountered obstacles based on their gender in the course of their career. Female professionals and managers are more likely than their male colleagues to experience situations in which their career opportunities are determined by stereotypes, unconscious biases or discriminatory practices. They are most often confronted with cases of favouritism towards men (55%), stereotyping in hiring and promotion decisions (53%), assumption of their lower availability (48%) and lack of confidence in their qualifications (42%).

Respondents in managerial roles, on the other hand, indicated as an obstacle the negative and hurtful opinions about the so-called 'female management style', stereotypically perceived as too emotional, with an excessive tendency to compromise and a lack of obedience among subordinates.

There is still perception of women in the labour market through the prism of - even theoretical - motherhood. Parenthood and family responsibilities are still mainly identified with women, which, in the perspective of some employers, puts the hiring of female candidates at additional risk. Some decision-makers in companies still assume that, as mothers, they will take sick leave for their children or soon become pregnant and disappear from the company for a year. This is therefore a manifestation of inequality that affects both working mothers and childless women.

The scientists argue that gender differentiates both the causes and consequences of unemployment. In the case of women, the following problems are indicated: the exit from the labour market due to childbirth or child care, concomitant with the pressure for the care period prolongation, depreciation of housework, gendered ascription of the responsibility of care for the dependent, and the unequal economic resources. Caring responsibilities still largely fall on women. The belief that it is the job of mothers to take care of children is a stereotype deeply rooted in culture. In the professional space, there is often a perception that it is working mothers who take care of children when they are sick and use all the parental leave available to parents (Hryciuk&Korolczuk 2015, Mikołajczyk&Stankowska 2021, Karwacki&Suwada 2020, Wojciechowska 2012).

The ultra-conservative opinions on women's involvement in the labour market, especially in view of the demographic crisis in Poland, are heard also from politicians. Przemysław Czarnek (currently Minister of Education), giving the lecture at the Catholic University of Lublin in 2019 during the election campaign, argued : “Go and work, ride a tractor, ride a combine, study, make a career. Career first and maybe a child later. This leads to tragic consequences. The first child is born not at the age of 20-25, but at the age of 30. If you have your first child at 30, how many of these children can you have? These are the consequences of explaining to a woman that she does not have to do what God has called her to do.”

A cluster of movement-connected trade unions (mostly stemming from the syndicalist tradition) also fits into this strategy, with a different set of norms and values driving their activism, bringing such activities more to social movements rather than conventional trade unions. With a high politicisation of labour-related claims, issues raised by movement-related trade unions are more politicised and connected to the political agenda of these organisations. As an illustration, we decided to include in our article a case from Poland, where a migrant chapter of one radical trade union – Inicjatywa Pracownicza – was created by Ukrainian care workers.

5.5.2 Health & reproductive rights,

Timeline of abortion law in Poland

On 7 January 1993 in Poland a ban on abortion was introduced. The ban was called the Compromise or the Act on Family Planning, Protection of the Human Fetus and the Conditions for the Permissibility

of Abortion. Until 7 January 1993, the Act of 27 April 1956 on the conditions for permissibility of abortion was in force in Poland, which permitted abortion:

- when medical indications concerning the health of the fetus or the pregnant woman were in favour of terminating the pregnancy;
- when there was a reasonable suspicion that the pregnancy was the result of a crime;
- due to difficult living conditions of the pregnant woman.

At the time of the political transformation, Poland had one of the most liberal abortion laws in Europe.

In November 1992 - a vote on a bill banning abortion

It was in the early 1990s that Poland's first non-governmental organisation dealing with reproductive rights, the Federation for Women and Family Planning, was founded. In 1992, Barbara Labuda and Zbigniew Bujak organised an initiative involving many individuals and social organisations, known as the Bujak Committees.

It was a reaction to the provisions proposed in the bill banning abortion that had been submitted to the Sejm. The aim of the Committees was to collect signatures for a nationwide referendum on the criminalisation of women for illegal abortion, which was one of the provisions proposed in the bill.

The Labuda and Bujak Committees turned into a nationwide movement in favour of the referendum, in which both politicians and social activists, as well as many people whose daily work or social activities were not related to the issue of the right to abortion, actively participated.

Between 1 300 000 and 1 700 000 signatures were collected. Despite meeting the statutory conditions, the Sejm rejected the referendum request and the law was passed in 1993.

On 30 August 1996, the Sejm amended the 1993 law, softening it by adding the premise of a woman's difficult personal situation as permitting legal termination of pregnancy. The relaxed law lasted less than a year.

On 27 May 1997, the Constitutional Tribunal in its full 12-member body - with three dissenting opinions - ruled that the provision introducing this premise was incompatible with the constitutional provisions in force under the so-called Little Constitution of 1992.

In December 1999, it was reported in the press that the police raided a gynaecological office in Lubliniec. The media reported that as a result of an anonymous denunciation of an alleged abortion, the police raided the doctor's office, dragged a woman out of it and transported her for forced gynaecological examinations.

News of this event was the impetus for the formation of the feminist collective Porozumienie Kobiet Ósmego Marca, which organised a series of demonstrations and drafted and circulated a letter of protest on the issue.

Since this event, feminist marches called Manifas have been held every year around 8 March. On 4 February 2002, Porozumienie Kobiet Ósmego Marca (Women's Agreement of 8th March) in cooperation with the Women's Information Centre drafted the Letter of a Hundred Women, which was sent to the European Parliament.

In the letter, well-known female representatives of science, culture, art, business and politics demanded a democratic debate on the situation of women in Poland. The signatories of the letter expressed concern that "(...) there has been a peculiar agreement between the Catholic Church and the government regarding Poland's accession to the European Union. Namely, the Church will support

integration with Europe in exchange for the government's resignation from discussing amendments to the anti-abortion law. The Polish law on the possibility of abortion is - next to Ireland and Malta - the most restrictive in Europe. At the same time, in the field of abortion, the practice is even stricter than the law, as doctors in hospitals - citing the conscience clause - refuse even to perform the procedures provided for in the law in force".

This letter was read out during the Manifa in Warsaw, which took place on 8 March 2002 under the slogan: 'My life, my choice. Three times Yes. Yes to sex education. Yes to contraception. Yes to the right to abortion.'

This is how the social movement centred around the right to abortion was born again. The topic of abortion in public discourse appeared on the occasion of annual Manifas or other projects and events organised by the broad feminist movement.

In June 2003, the topic of the right to abortion featured prominently in the public debate in connection with the social action of bringing the ship 'Langenort', belonging to the Dutch organisation Women on Waves, to the port of Władysławowo.

Polish activists and campaigners for the liberalisation of abortion law were also involved in carrying out this action. The ship housed a motherhood awareness clinic and a doctor's office. Pregnancies were terminated using a pharmacological method by giving the woman abortion pills. It aroused a huge amount of public interest - both supporters and opponents of the right to terminate a pregnancy.

The presence of the Dutch ship brought the discussion about the right to abortion back to the media after a long pause, but only for a while. The topic came to life again in 2007 when the European Court of Human Rights issued a ruling ordering Poland to pay Alicja Tysic 25,000 euros in compensation. The doctors decided that Alicja's case (risk of loss of sight caused by pregnancy) did not authorise a legal abortion on health grounds.

Alicia had no choice, she gave birth, her sight deteriorated significantly and the case went to Strasbourg. In the ruling, the Court pointed out that Poland lacks clear procedures for legal abortion. The judgement also stressed that penalising doctors for performing abortions leads to a situation where they may be afraid to perform these procedures in accordance with the law.

This was the first case of its kind, Alicia Tysic was the first to come forward under her full name, and as a result she faced heckling and harassment.

Also in 2007, Marek Jurek, Speaker of the Sejm from the Law and Justice party, together with MPs and deputies of the League of Polish Families, decided to introduce a provision on the protection of the human foetus into the Constitution. The introduction of such a provision would have led to a tightening of the 1993 law. This made the issue of abortion relatively noisy again.

Feminist activists protested in front of the Sejm, and women of the media met with Maria Kaczyska, wife of the then president. The meeting resulted in an appeal to male and female parliamentarians not to tighten the law. The appeal was signed by, among others, Maria Kaczyska, wife of the then President of Poland Lech Kaczyski.

The motion to amend the Constitution was defeated in the vote.

The topic of abortion again disappeared for a longer period of time and returned in 2011 with the legislative committee 'Yes to Women'. The committee was collecting signatures for a bill on informed parenthood and other reproductive rights from August to October 2011. However, without success.

After 2011, the topic of abortion appeared incidentally in public discourse.

In 2014, the topic resurfaced due to the cruel behaviour of Professor Chazan, who concealed serious foetal defects from his patient. A demonstration was held in front of the Sejm, and Chazan himself was dismissed from his position as director of the capital's hospital, but he became a favourite of anti-abortion organisations.

Apart from the Manifas, abortion was discussed at conferences or feminist meetings. The discussions took place in a small group usually around language, strategy, and underground. The same group of several dozen people met in front of the Sejm to protest against subsequent 'Stop Abortion' projects.

A breakthrough year for abortion in Poland was 2016. In March, the Warsaw Manifa was organised under the slogan 'Abortion in defence of life', and two weeks later Ordo Iuris announced that, together with the Pro Right to Life organisation, they were submitting a civic project - not only banning abortion completely, but also introducing 'prenatal murder' and punishment for one's having an abortion.

The bill was the harshest possible and, interestingly, caused disapproval even among some organisations opposed to abortion. The Polish Federation of Movements for the Defence of Life disassociated itself from the project and criticised the idea of punishing women for abortions. "Reclaim the choice" demonstrations were held across Poland, and a Facebook group *Dziewuchy Dziewuchom* was created, which to this day is another space where people can seek support before, during and after an abortion pill.

In response to the anti-abortion bill, the Save the Women Committee was set up and developed its bill to legalise abortion. Both anti- and pro-abortion bills were presented in the Sejm at the same time - at the end of September 2016.

At the same time, in fear of drastic abortion laws, Women's Strikes - the largest demonstrations on abortion in Poland since the ban - took place in the streets of many Polish towns and cities. The accumulation of protests occurred on 3 October, the so-called Black Monday.

In October 2020, the Constitutional Court stated that the premise allowing abortion in the case of fetal defects was unconstitutional.

The Women's Strike took to the streets again and, despite the pandemic Covid-19, gathered tens of thousands of people across the country for protests. The protests continued until spring 2021.

The academic literature on the subject points out that the women's protests that began in 2016 should be placed in the broader context of the changing relationship between Polish society (especially young society) and the Church (Korolczuk and Graff, 2022). Strong and growing support for funding in-vitro conception procedures through the public health system 76% (CBOS/95/2015), despite efforts by anti-choice groups to ban these procedures.

5.5.3 Migration,

Central Statistical Office's (GUS) data show that by the end of 2019, there were over 2 million foreigners living in Poland, with the majority of Ukrainians (over 1.3 million). After this date the data available are not representative, due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine in 2022 that has resulted in 5,8 million refugees coming from Ukraine, 3,5 millions of whom have stayed in Poland for a longer time period. Around the same time (end of 2019) the official numbers indicate 12 673 refugees, 4791 asylum seekers and 1328 persons under UNHCR's statelessness mandate living in Poland. Within the last two decades Chechens were the biggest group of asylum seekers that have been coming to Poland. Although in official statistics this group is considered as Russian citizens, it is estimated that between 2003 and 2016 about 90 thousands of asylum seekers of Chechen origin claimed asylum in Poland (Anacka, 2015), but only 3-5% of them were given a positive decision to grant some form of international protection (Alieva & Jaworska, 2018).

The relatively low numbers of foreigners in Poland suggest that such a topic was not at the centre of interest of Polish feminist movements. There have been cases where activism of a specific nature, such as labour or other, have touched upon the issue of migration when it was connected to the gender of the victim. The situation changed after February 24th, 2021, when Russia attacked Ukraine. The majority of the refugees, over 50%, that came from Ukraine to Poland were women, often accompanied by kids. Few weeks later, in April, after the massacre in Bucha done by Russian soldiers became known, feminist organizations in Poland organized a number of public protests and events pointing out to the war rapes perpetrated by Russian soldiers. These protests took place in front of Russian embassies showing the universal experience of this war crime.

The second area of involvement and Intersectionality between migrant issues and women's movement in Poland is the use of networks that developed and emerged from the woman's strikes in 2016 and 2020 and to put them to use for helping Ukrainian refugees in Poland. Such help included assistance in travelling from the border to other locations in Poland, finding housing, collecting money and other Goods as a form of charitable activism. Feminist activists were also among those who organised pro Ukrainian rallies in Poland as they were often the ones that had a know-how on how to organise a demonstration. This process of helping Ukrainian women, and Ukrainians in general, is continued until today with the help being more and more specialised on helping to find accommodation and work in Poland.

5.5.4 LGBTQ+ rights

As both the LGBT and feminist movements found themselves under attack by the ruling party and their acolytes, since around 2018 there is a growing and observable connection between the two: there are flags, banners, and slogans of feminist groups during Equality Marches (Pride Parades) and there are rainbow flags very visible during women's protests. This is a result of the politics of the Law and Justice party seeking for new enemies for their populist politics and targeting women (not only in 2016 and 2020 with attempts to change the abortion law, but also with numerous ultra-conservative or even misogynistic public statements of PiS politicians), and LGBT+ people. Together with the generational shift and rejuvenation occurring within the two movements, there is an observable and growing intersectionality between the feminist and the LGBT+ movements.

In an attempt to describe the historical background, one might refer primarily to the period of the 1980s and 1990s, since it was then that the continuity of the organisational movements could be observed, among other things, that the contemporary Polish LGBT rights movement was born. The beginning of the 1980s was also the moment when the possibilities related to the registration of associations increased significantly. As a result, action initiatives within the movement, as well as other civic initiatives increased and became more visible. Of course, there had also been attempts to start activities on behalf of homosexuals in Poland before that time. One of them was the creation of the Gay and Lesbian Movement [Ruch Gejów i Lesbijek] in the 1980s. Nevertheless, it was not until 1990 that the LGBT+ community could be referred to as a movement, because it was then that the first Polish association was established that was officially active on behalf of gays and lesbians, the Lambda association, which still exists today and, together with organisations such as the Campaign Against Homophobia (Kampania Przeciw Homofobii, since 2001), the Association of Gays and Lesbians (Stowarzyszenie Gejów i Lesbijek, since 2001), the LGBT+ Movement.), the Association of Gays and Lesbians for Culture (Stowarzyszenie Gejów i Lesbijek na rzecz Kultury, since 2000), the Culture for Tolerance Foundation (Fundacja Kultury Tolerancji, since 2003), the Equality Foundation (Fundacja Równość, since 2003) are still working for the rights of non-heterosexuals.

It is not easy to find reliable scholarly texts dealing with the LGBT+ social movement. The existing scholarly papers that, apart from a historical description, describe its development are usually the master's theses of Polish students. It is much more difficult to find publications that describe

contemporary movements, post-2010. The most common sources are surveys, research reports and interviews with activists themselves. Reports on the social situation of LGBT+ people in Poland are published annually or every four years by institutions such as CBOS or the Campaign Against Homophobia.

Large organisations with a nationwide reach do not benefit from local government grants or subsidies with Lambda Warsaw being an exception. For smaller organisations, local government grants are an important source of income. Cooperation between organisations and local governments is not only about transferring funds. In the field of cooperation with local government, Love Does Not Exclude (Miłość Nie Wyklucza, MNW) is very active. In 2018, MNW prepared a Local Government Programme for LGBT+ Community. The electoral staff of the then candidate for mayor of Warsaw, Rafał Trzaskowski collaborated with MNW on this document that was signed after the elections. Representatives of the Tolerado Association sit on the city's Equal Treatment Council. Culture of Equality appears at events organised by the city authorities. Tolerado also takes part in programmes organised by local government institutions. Majority of these organisations are left-liberal oriented, although in the beginning of their activities, they were more self-help rather than political oriented. But with the growing politicisation of the identity issues, these organisations began to seek political allies, with two key figures becoming the most visible: Anna Grodzka – the first transsexual MP in the world, and Robert Biedroń, the first outed gay MP in Poland.

ILGA, International Lesbian and Gay, Bisexual and Transgender Association, has published the 2021 Rainbow Europe report, which examines the level of equality for LGBT+ people across Europe. Poland, which has been ranked penultimate for several years so far, came last in 2021 and became the country with the worst protection of sexual and gender minorities of all countries among the European Union.

Nevertheless, as opportunities have developed, methods have emerged in the LGBT movements that were not present before. One example is homokomando, a gay sports team famous in Poland. Linus Lewandowski, in an interview with Paweł Korzeniowski, explained who the homokomando activists are, saying: "We describe ourselves as a gay sports team, although of course from a formal point of view we are not registered in any way. We are a group of people who want to play sports together". Another example is the anarcho-queer collective Stop Bzdurom (Stop Bullshit), whose actions were often publicised in the public media and labelled radical. One trans-activist, Margot, in 2019 stopped and then damaged a so-called pogromobus that was driving around the streets of Warsaw and inciting hatred against LGBT people. The vehicle was festooned with banners bearing, among other things, the slogan that homosexuals are paedophiles and alike. The organiser of the 'pogromobus' action was the PRO Right to Life Foundation (Fundacja PRO - Prawo do Życia), which, despite numerous reports to the police, has not been convicted. These events sparked a very lively discussion and controversy in Poland. Another action organised by this collective was the display of rainbow flags on monuments, its aim was to draw attention to the presence of non-heteronormative people in the country. On the night of 28-29 July 2020 in Warsaw, anarchist activists from the Stop Bzdurom collective hung rainbow flags on key monuments, including Piłsudski, Jesus and the Warsaw Mermaid. In a manifesto left at the monument, one can read that the action carried out by Stop Bullshit is an 'assault and attack'. Shortly afterwards, the post, along with the collective's Facebook account, was deleted. The event was extremely criticised and considered disrespectful to Polish history. Law and Justice (PiS) MP Sebastian Kaleta wrote on the social network Twitter that he had filed a notice to the public prosecutor's office. The prosecutor's office opened an investigation, but the case was discontinued.

Accompanying structural changes in wider Polish society. Despite the anti-LGBTQ campaign launched by the Law and Order Party in the summer of 2020, there has recently been growing support for same-sex partnerships. According to a 2019 IPSOS survey conducted for OKO.press, an overwhelming majority (56%) are in favour of gays and lesbians being granted the right to enter into civil partnerships,

and as many as 41% would agree that they should be able to marry (in 2017 it was 52% and 38% respectively). Polish women are much more tolerant than Polish men, with same-sex partnerships supported by 60% of them (51% of men) and same-sex marriages supported by 47% of women and only about a third of Polish men. The support for same-sex civil partnerships is growing and reached 64% in June 2022 (with 48% supporting marriage equality, 47% opposing it) Ipsos poll for oko.press.

Politicians of the ruling party assure that Poland is a safe country for LGBT people. As evidence, they cite lower hate crime statistics compiled by the Organization for Security and Co-operation in Europe (OSCE) than in other countries.

The OSCE report gives data based on official statistics from The Ministry of Internal Affairs and Administration. This in turn reports exceptionally few cases of hate crimes against LGBT people to the OSCE. However, the low statistics do not reflect the true scale of the problem. Rather, they reflect the holes in the law and the inability (or unwillingness) of the state to detect this type of crime [115]. According to the Polish Criminal Code, hate speech against LGBT people is not prohibited in Poland. Since 2015, the ruling party (Law and Justice) has been changing the system for anti-discrimination and violence by, among other things, abolishing the Human Rights Protection Team in 2016. In fact, as research shows, the level of violence against LGBT people in Poland is high, but the reporting of such incidents is low. According to the European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights survey results (2020), in the past five years 59% of LGBTQ+ people in Poland have experienced harassment because of being LGBTQ+, while 15% reported having suffered physical or sexual violence [116]. In addition to experiencing discrimination in everyday life, aggressive attitudes towards the LGBTQ+ community are also manifested at events such as Equality Parades, for example in Białystok and Lublin in 2018 and 2019.

5.5.5 Gender-based violence.

The Council of Europe Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence Against Women and Domestic Violence (the Istanbul Convention), civil partnerships and abortion have been explicitly labelled by right-wing politicians and publicists as “promoting feminism, abortion, homosexuality and other deviant behaviour” (Piłka, 2011).

An example of the transition from the private sphere to the public sphere is given by Beata Kowalska and Radosław Nawojski: 'Until recently, domestic violence, sexual harassment or rape were not considered crimes because they took place in the private sphere'.

The issue of gender-based violence was predominantly the domain of NGOs, such as Centrum Praw Kobiet or Feminoteka. Key elements during these efforts (that started before 2010) were to introduce changes to the criminal code that would lead to redefining the crime of rape. But, as the authors of the CPK report write: “An analysis of the policies of successive governments leaves no doubt: the problem of violence against women has not been a priority for any of them. A conservative vision of the social roles of men and women and stereotypes have left their mark on the legislative and institutional solutions undertaken to varying degrees and intensities by all government teams.”

The main argument was to change the definition of rape to every sexual encounter without consent, as Polish courts - relying on previous versions of the criminal code and other factors - often acquitted perpetrators of rape in cases where there was no violence (eg. the victim was unconscious). This campaign was executed mostly through media campaigns and lobbying.

Another important node was the issue of domestic violence, a rather widespread phenomenon in Polish society, often culturally grounded. The efforts of feminist activists were to stress the crucial role of women in the process, as they mostly fell victims to such crimes. The first attempt to think about clarifying the role of key institutions in combating family violence and to think about interdisciplinary

cooperation was the Blue Cards (Niebieska Karta, NK). The first iteration of the NK procedure came into force by virtue of Order 25/98 of the Police Chief Commandant already in November 1998. The procedure evolved, but until the amendment of the Anti-Domestic Violence Act in 2010, it was essentially a police procedure and cooperation with other entities was the responsibility of the police. After the entry into force of the Act on Counteracting Family Violence, officers implementing the NK procedure were obliged to send information to social welfare centres on each case of implementation of the procedure, as well as on cases of escalation of violence in the family under the procedure.

One of the key developments for the feminist movement was the adoption and ratification of the Istanbul convention (signed by president Komorowski in 2015). Andrzej Duda's victory has strengthened the voices of the Convention's opponents. In November 2016, the first proposal to denounce it was prepared. After harsh criticism from NGOs, the media and the opposition, the Law and Justice Party withdrew from the idea. It seemed to stop at incentives not to apply the Convention. Before the next attack on the Convention, at the turn of 2018 and 2019, a draft amendment to the Law on Prevention of Domestic Violence emerged, which contained threatening proposals for changes to the law for battered women. One of these was a proposal to amend the definition of violence in the family, announcing the decriminalisation of one-off violence. Another change was the announcement that a commission would be set up to decide whether there was violence or family conflict. After the wave of criticism of the draft revealed by the media, further work on it was suspended.

The announcements of the denunciation of the Anti-Bullying Convention triggered a wave of protests despite the pandemic restrictions. Many organisations and institutions dealing with women's rights and violence against women protested, publishing their positions, following scandalous statements by, among others, Deputy Minister of Justice Marcin Romanowski. The Grand Coalition for Equality and Choice made an appeal alerting the European Commission to the Polish government's plans to denounce the Istanbul Convention. In response to the Coalition's appeal, European Commission President Ursula von der Leyen expressed criticism of the Polish government over plans to its denunciation.

Connected to these developments were the changes in the Act on Prevention of Domestic Violence that included one of feminist postulates: the mandatory separation of the perpetrator of the crime from the family. This law has been in power in the last few years, with occasional criticisms regarding its implementation.

5.6 Repertoire of action

In this part we explore the repertoires of action employed by feminist movements, contentious politics and/or how they relate to state institutions.

Besides ad-hoc organised events to show support for some proposals and solutions or to prevent change of those, there are a few repertoires that are more resilient and repetitive.

Since 1999 feminist marches called Manifas have been held every year around 8 March. On 4 February 2002, Porozumienie Kobiet Ósmego Marca (Women's Agreement of 8th March) in cooperation with the Women's Information Centre drafted the Letter of a Hundred Women, which was sent to the European Parliament. In the letter, well-known female representatives of science, culture, art, business and politics demanded a democratic debate on the situation of women in Poland.

The topic of abortion in public discourse appeared on the occasion of annual Manifas or other projects and events organised by the broad feminist movement. Contrasted to the more 'liberal' feminists, Manifas were considered as radical and contentious, at least in discursive terms with very radical slogans being chanted and radical claims (especially in the beginning) being raised.

A breakthrough year for abortion in Poland was 2016. In March, the Warsaw Manifa was organised under the slogan 'Abortion in defence of life', and two weeks later Ordo Iuris announced that, together with the Pro Right to Life organisation, they were submitting a civic project - not only banning abortion completely, but also introducing 'prenatal murder' and punishment for one's having an abortion.

The bill was the harshest possible and, interestingly, caused disapproval even among some organisations opposed to abortion. The Polish Federation of Movements for the Defence of Life disassociated itself from the project and criticised the idea of punishing women for abortions. "Reclaim the choice" demonstrations were held across Poland, and a Facebook group *Dziewuchy Dziewuchom* was created, which to this day is another space where people can seek support before, during and after an abortion pill. The 2016 (and those taking place up to 2019) protests were rather conventional – with large rallies, demonstrations, picquets etc. held throughout the country. However, the 2020 protests became more contentious – with street blockades, protests taking place (for the first time in history) inside churches, including spray-painting slogans on the churches themselves. In the case of LGBT+ movement the radicalisation took place a bit earlier that year with the arresting of a trans-activist Margot from the Stop Bzduram collective, who assaulted and demolished a van belonging to an anti-choice foundation, covered in homophobic slogans. On August 7th 2020, the police arrested 48 people who showed up to support Margot. LGBT+ activists soon joined forces with pro-abortion activists, potentially explaining the later radicalisation of women's protests.

Protesting in times of pandemic.

When a group of MPs repeated the petition to the Constitutional Court in spring 2020. During the blockade introduced in Poland, spontaneous pickets were organised. In order to avoid penalties for organising 'public assemblies', the official justification was the queue in front of shops in city centres, but the scale of these initiatives was small.

Due to the current restrictions on public assemblies due to the pandemic, some of the abortion protesters demonstrated by using their cars to block traffic and sounding their horns.

As one can read: "Yesterday [25 October], when several hundred cars took part in such a protest in Krakow, they were joined by several taxi drivers who displayed the Women's Strike logo in their windows and flew red and white Polish flags. Taxi drivers also took part in a similar protest in Warsaw, Radio Zet reports" (Wilczek 2020). Motorised protests have become a regular feature of women's protests, which were organised on a daily basis, with cavalcades of cars and motorbikes driving around cities, using their horns and blocking traffic. Sometimes tram and bus drivers stopped their vehicles to join the strike.

One of the most challenging protest slogans and hashtags is #tojestwojna or 'this is war'. In addition to the car protests, the wide variety in the repertoire of protests adopted for the current cycle is noteworthy. For example, 'remote blockades' have been organised, mainly by electronic means (mainly spamming, sending text messages, calling mobile phone numbers, creating Facebook report pages). They target MPs and officials, but also anti-choice and far-right activists. One of the key figures in the anti-choice movement, Kaja Godek, received around 1,500 text messages and 1,200 calls on the first day of protests. Her home (where her foundation is officially registered) also became a venue for protests. 'Window protests' of people quarantined or fearful of Covid-19 infection during crowd protests have also become popular, with the most common being the lightning bolt sign.

One of the repertoires and narratives used so far is the Women's Strike, already used in 2016 (Kubisa and Rakowska 2018). According to the organisers of the National Women's Strike, on Wednesday 28 October, the protest organisers planned to hold a strike, similar to the one that took place in 2016, in response to earlier efforts to restrict abortion laws. "We are not going to work. We are being supported

by more and more business owners who have not received adequate help from the state.... The state has absolutely no effective plan to help companies, so companies are supporting us," Marta Lempart, one of the protest leaders, told *Gazeta Wyborcza*.

As part of the strikes on 28 October, techno street parties were organised in Poznań, Gdańsk, Kraków and Warsaw, also relatively innovative in the Polish context, at least in a politicised context, but other events such as beach walks, bicycle protests and a Halloween protest under the slogan 'trick-or-treat' were also organised across the country.

The use of social media.

In Poland when it comes to social media Facebook is the predominant platform for communication both for individuals and for organisations. Twitter, although rather popular among officials and politicians, has never reached the popularity of Facebook. Recently new platforms are trending; these being TikTok, popular mostly among the youngest cohort of the public and the activists, Instagram that is most often used to amplify messages posted on other social media platforms, and Telegram popular mostly among the more radical activists and used mostly during protest events as it allows for communication and crowd control in real time. All links to profiles of the study groups and initiatives are mentioned alongside with description of the group. The post 2016 and 2020 groups were organised rhizomatically, in a decentralised fashion that was adopted by social movements during the global justice movement of the late 1990s. Most of the communication is done through social media, rather than through the websites of the initiatives as it allows for live communication and interaction with recipients and participants of the movement. The already mentioned young age of new coming activists and the vast popularity of contemporary feminist claims within the youngest cohort of society make it a natural way of communication, as well as parts of the language used by the activist is also highly influenced by social media and internet-based channels, often referring to memes.

The *Dziewuchy Dziewuchom* and the Women's Strike emphasise their complete lack of formalisation. Despite significant legal differences, all these initiatives also operate as much broader non-formalised civic actions that conduct a large part of their activities in public space, both real (streets, squares) and virtual, online (portals, FB). Podemski (2020) analysing contemporary social activism in Poland shows the pace at which likes on Facebook profiles grew. In November 2017 *Dziewuchy Dziewuchom* (<https://www.facebook.com/dziewuchy-dziewuchom/>) had 35k likes, Women's Strike (<https://www.facebook.com/ogolnopolskistrajk-kobiet/>) 47k. In August 2018 these numbers were: 43k for *Dziewuchy Dziewuchom* and 73k for Women's Strike.

Another measurement for popularity of online actions of the study groups is the widespread use of hashtags, with the women's strike hashtag being the most popular on the internet in Poland in 2016. Other hashtags include: „#czarny protest”, „Ratujmykobiety”, „Wolne Polki”, „wolna Polska”, „Odzyskać wybór”, „#seksedpl”, „Solidarity with Polish women” (*Dziewuchy Dziewuchom*), and „Czarny Poniedziałek”, „Międzynarodowy Strajk Kobiet”, „#DziewczynyDoWyborów”, „Pali nam się Polska”, „#Słowo na niedzielę – wieszak dla biskupa”, „#Świetne-Dzieciaki” (*Women's Strike*).

Participating in the 2020 protests, one thing is also noticeable. It is the young age of the crowds, with people in their 20s making up the vast majority of the protest crowd. Perhaps this is the reason for the radicalisation of the claims and slogans. As one of the protest organisers said: *Young people are uncompromising, they don't want to get along. They grew up with a sense of freedom and now someone wants to take it away from them.* (Muszel and Piotrowski, 2020).

Another of the protest organisers we spoke to noted the differences between the 2016 and 2020 women's protests (Piotrowski and Muszel 2020): *There is a completely different energy now. It is wonderful. These are young people who are not afraid to take to the streets and fight for their rights.*

They are looking more broadly. They are afraid that they will be deprived of more freedom, more rights, more space, that this is a dictatorship that will impose everything on them.

5.7 Frames of arguments

In this section, describe the main frames of arguments of feminist movements with reference to the five thematic areas (labor market, health & reproductive rights, migration, LGBTQ+ rights and gender-based violence).

When it comes to women's/feminist activists, there is no doubt that the discursive opportunities for this movement are limited and often met with hostility. Abortion (and also sexual education, or any issues connected to gender identity) have become an ideological battlefield close to the 1989 systemic transformation. One of the first declarations of the 2nd assembly of delegates of Solidarność movement in 1990, soon after its re-legalization, was against abortion. The current law on abortion comes from 1993 and is a result of the so-called 'compromise'. Debates on this law were very heated and the catholic church (directly or through dependent pro-life organizations) became heavily involved in the discussion (Chełstowska 2011). Since then, several attempts of restricting the law further were made and the proposal of 2016 that would practically block any access to legally performed abortion has sparked the protests (Korolczuk 2016, Murawska and Włodarczyk 2016, Król and Pustułka 2018). Anti-abortion narrative is one of the elements of the discourse that is aimed against broadly understood feminist thinking. Over the years there have been numerous waves of e.g. anti-gender campaigns, where 'genderism' was dubbed as an ideology and connected to the concept coined by John Paul II 'civilization of death'. The 'gender ideology' is said to have its roots in 'cultural Marxism' (without explaining the category in details) that falls in line with a broader anti-leftist narrative (Patternotte and Kuhar 2017). Anti-leftism is connected to the rejection of communism that took place during the systemic transformation of 1989 (Ciszewski 2013). The growing dominance of right-wing parties and groups since the mid-2000s has made anti-communism a part of the mainstream discourse (Drozda 2015), and this has resonated particularly well among young people. As one of the interviewees said: "Feminism is pejoratively associated, feminists are haunted women without a man who want to murder children. This is the message. So people who think this way, that is, they do not have this information, they are not interested and this is a huge barrier to reach". It is not that such topics usually are met with a fierce reaction, in most cases they are simply neglected.

Before the use of the term gender by the Catholic Church officials and far right activists, this concept has not been known in Poland except for outnumbers students of gender studies at the universities. Around 2014 the concept of "gender ideology" was picked up by parts of the clergy and far right activists and then was introduced into the narrative of the incumbent Law And Justice party. This is proven to be particularly effective, as almost no one understood the concept of gender and at the same time in the public debate the original English-speaking term was used instead of its Polish translation. Connected to the word ideology that has a particularly bad connotation in Polish language due to the pre-1989 history, has proven to be a good scarecrow for the public. The feminist movement seems to be hesitant to pick up the concept of gender, not making it a central concept in their narrative and more often using it as a source for jokes, understood mostly by insiders. nevertheless a process of discursive writing the colonisation could be observed with changes in the definitions of participants of the feminist movements and some of the groups began to use phrases such as "persons with cervixes" instead of women in order to be more inclusive towards the trans people communities, causing heated discussions within the movement and pushing away older hearts of the activists that had issues in understanding the complexity of the language used.

Today's feminist activism in Poland is not only about criticising capitalism and the state or even rejecting them, but also about re-defining the political. In this process, the boundaries between the

private and public (political) spheres become blurred and vague, as do the labels of “left” and “right”. To some extent, this resembles the 1970s feminist claim that “the personal is political”, and evidence supporting this can be found in many places as—using an emic concept of the anarchist writer Murray Bookchin—“lifestyle activism” seems to be more dominant than social activism in Poland, and numerous aspects of one’s life are politicised (a meatless diet, a preference for public transportation and bicycles, etc.)

In this regard, the new wave of Polish feminism is not political but rather anti-political, especially in regard to institutionalised politics, and the political categories of left and right play a much smaller role in their self-identification. Using the term suggested by John Holloway (2005), they are using anti-power instead of trying to take over power, and thus labels derived from institutionalised politics are less important.

What helped to appeal to young people was the framing of the protests as a defence of fundamental freedoms and human rights. This coincides with a change in the narrative of pro-choice organisations, but can also be seen in the framing now used by Amnesty International, which has also begun to refer to access to safe and legal abortion (without specifying the nuances of the issues to which it may have referred) as a human right. This, combined with the theme of the cycle, which affects at least half of the country's population, helped to mobilise a wider audience for the event. The protests against the Constitutional Court's verdict also coincided with other protests in Poland: the growing discontent of business owners affected by the anti-pandemic legislation (in particular restaurant and bar owners who had to close their businesses for at least two weeks from 23 October, which the government announced on 22 October), gym owners and farmers. Moreover, the government's ratings are falling as more and more people become disillusioned with the response to the unfolding COVID-19 pandemic and the worsening economic situation. The latest poll on 26 October showed a dramatic drop of around 15% in support for Law and Justice (PiS) to levels not seen since 2016.

5.8 Campaigns and debates

In order to understand the issues pursued by feminist movements, the project intends to specifically explore the campaigns and debates developed in the period 2010-2021.

Without much success in pushing the new abortion laws through parliament (sent by both pro- and anti-choice movements), a group of 119 MPs from the Law and Justice party, the nationalist Confederation with the support of the Kukiz'15 party, filed a petition to the Constitutional Court to determine whether the most popular provision in the abortion law (terminal or severe foetal defect) is constitutional. The protests in 2016 showed that any attempt to amend or introduce a new law would be challenged, so the submitted drafts were 'frozen' in the legislative procedure.

In early 2020, the petition to the Constitutional Court was repeated, and on Thursday 22 October 2020, the country's highest court issued a new ruling declaring it unconstitutional to terminate the pregnancy of a deformed foetus. This sparked nationwide and international protests that continue to this day. As Anna Grzymała-Busse (2020) wrote:

'One of the reasons why the PiS government passed the judiciary is that the majority of Poles support the foetal defects clause, even if abortion itself is controversial. The government's decision was met with a negative public perception. The question 'How do you assess the judgement of the Constitutional Court on abortion? As many as 70.7 percent of respondents assessed it negatively. 13.2 percent of respondents assessed the judgement positively. 16.1 percent of respondents have no opinion.

The *fait accompli* method that took place on 22 October changed the dynamics and radicalisation of the protests. For the first time, women did not face the possibility of a change in the law, but witnessed

a change in themselves, which made them feel powerless and angry (as some organisers told us). Unsurprisingly, the youngest participants appeared to be the most radicalised, and older activists and protest organisers told us that they started to moderate the most radical ones because of fears of police repression. It is worth mentioning here that the Polish police have shown an uneven treatment of street protests in recent years, often turning a blind eye to the actions of the far right and pacifying other protests. This was evident in the summer of 2020, when police clashed with pro-LGBTQ protesters, particularly in Warsaw, detaining 48 people, including some bystanders.

There are several factors that make the current protests very different from those in 2016, 2017 and 2018. The main change is the scale of the protests. According to the police chief, on Wednesday 28 October (the 7th day of protests), police recorded 410 events across the country, with around 430,000 people taking part.

Participation in the protests on the ground suggests that both figures could be much higher. On 30 October 2020, a mass demonstration of more than 100,000 people was organised, starting at three different locations in Warsaw and ending at one of Warsaw's central intersections (the Dmowski Roundabout) before heading to the area where Jaroslaw Kaczynski, the leader of Law and Justice, lives. This and the day before, the protests were less peaceful than previous ones. On 27 October, Kaczynski recorded a statement on the Law and Justice Facebook profile calling on his supporters to 'protect the churches', which was interpreted as a call for militant action against the protests due to the rather calm police response. Attacks on female protesters were recorded in Wroclaw, Poznan and Bialystok, where people were gassed and beaten with batons and truncheons. At a large demonstration in Warsaw (30 October), two major clashes were recorded (one at the beginning), after which police detained 37 people identified as football hooligans. However, the right-wing tactics were more elaborate - small groups of about 5 right-wing militants joined the crowd, started beating or tearing gassing people causing sporadic panic in the crowd.

On the first of November 2020, Women's Strike leaders announced the formation of the Women's Strike Consultative Council and announced the first demands. "The council is supposed to work on the voices of the protests that are taking place in Poland, bring them together and organise them," - Marta Lempart, leader of the Women's Strike, said. Among the demands are the issues of abortion and women's rights, LGBT+ rights, the elimination of the Catholic Church's influence on the state (the introduction of a true secular state) and the removal of religious lessons from public schools, the prevention of climate catastrophe or the abolition of precarious employment contracts. The strike also wants to address animal rights, education and healthcare.

Throughout November 2020, protests continued to take place across the country, but with slightly less frequency. Nevertheless, the police continued to repress women protesters. On 28 November, the 102nd anniversary of the granting of voting rights to Poles, numerous demonstrations took place across the country. During the protest in Warsaw, the police used tear gas against female protesters, including Marta Lempart and, a short while later, against an opposition MP (Barbara Nowacka) who showed her MP card to a police officer.

The scale of the protests in small towns in 2020 turned out to be even larger than in 2016, e.g. on one day alone (26 October, Monday), according to the official website of the All-Poland Women's Strike, protests took place in 201 towns, including only a few thousand (e.g. Lesko, Zelów) or even just over a thousand (e.g. Sarnaki). As in the large cities, although to a slightly lesser extent, the women protesters are also joined by men. The fact that the protests cover the whole country, including small towns, makes the protest voice stronger, more coherent and representative of all Polish women and men.

In 2020 what struck most observers and is new is the anticlerical element of the protests. Demonstrations held in the first days of the cycle usually started in front of the Law and Justice office, but quickly moved to places associated with the Catholic Church: bishop's residences, cathedrals, etc.

In the words of Grzymała-Busse (2020), "[F]or the first time ever, protests moved into churches, a symbolically eloquent move in a country where the Catholic Church has held enormous moral authority for decades. On Sunday, clergymen met protesters at mass, dressed as handmaids - a reference to author Margaret Atwood's dystopian novel about the repression of women. Other protesters sat quietly in the aisles of the church, holding signs saying 'pray for the right to abortion'. Young protesters surrounded priests outside churches, loudly denouncing clergy in small towns, traditionally a bastion of conservative Catholicism in Poland. Protesters began confronting bishops and archbishops in front of their frequented residences" (Grzymała-Busse 2020). The police report 22 acts of 'disrupting religious services' and 79 cases of church-related vandalism (in almost all cases spray-painting church facades).

This shift has had several consequences, from shocking liberal commentators to shifting the Law and Justice discourse towards a religious and civilisational battle. In a speech published on Law and Justice Facebook profile on 27 October, party leader Jaroslaw Kaczynski called on his supporters to "defend churches across the country". Unsurprisingly, there were attacks by right-wing groups during the following night of protests. However, despite the political use of the religious framework, this is perhaps the most surprising aspect of the current protests. Over the years, the Catholic Church has had a very strong position - in society and in politics (even more so after the 2015 elections) almost every public event had to be accompanied by a priest or bishop, and most children attended religious classes in schools twice a week (in many cases also in kindergartens). Until now, voices critical of the Church and its position have been described as 'radical' and 'extreme'. Now the edge of the protests against the Church and the clergy is the best evidence of the growing secularisation of the country: "The share of believers and practitioners was the lowest in the history of the 2019 survey, and the share of believers and non-practitioners and non-believers and non-practitioners was the highest". - reported by CBOS. And these changes bring it into public discourse and become political.

Another new development in the current cycle of protests is the wide range of strike supporters. As Anna Grzymała-Busse (2020) wrote:

Most of them were young women - but this time support came from a much wider cross-section of Polish society, including football fans, trade unionists, tram and bus drivers, and hundreds of taxi drivers who blocked the streets of Warsaw to allow the protests to pass. They were joined by large cities and smaller towns, including PiS electoral strongholds.

What was different in 2020 is the support from political parties and its importance. In 2016, Poland was a country with no left-wing party in parliament, but in the 2019 elections, the left-wing party received 12.56% of the vote, bringing many new faces into parliament, including former activists. This group (along with several young MPs from the liberal Civic Coalition) provided not only political support (rather symbolic in the context of the ruling Law and Justice party's majority in the lower house of parliament), but also assistance at the scene of protests, in particular intervening at police stations and negotiating conflict situations on the ground.

The coercion of various social movements in Poland after 2015 has resulted in different framing of feminist campaigns. On the one hand, many of the struggles have been framed as a part of conflict to save democracy in Poland and some of the allies joined, motivated by their resentment towards the governing Law And Justice party. The limited resources social movements have also forced them to cooperate with each other, and this is particularly visible in the cases where funding for more moderate factions of the movement represented by non-governmental organisations has been shut down by the

central government. This forced the activists to seek funding and resources either abroad, often through Norwegian funds and European grants, or locally exploiting the support of local governments often critical towards the central government. In the recent years also the development of crowdfunding has significantly changed the income side of social movements, nevertheless the corporation observed between various pro-democratic organisations such as the committee of Defense of democracy, action democracy, and feminist initiatives has been more and more visible and is perceived as a two-way learning process that overlaps generational divisions between the movements. In 2020 and later demonstrations, what was visible during feminist demonstrations were rainbow flags of the LGBT movement, silver and gold emergency blankets representing the refugee and pro migrant struggles, and numerous anti-fascist emblems.

As mentioned in the introduction, the impact of women's mobilizations and protesters in recent years had a very limited range. What has been present in the academic literature are some of the works that are all quoted in this report but are nevertheless limited to around a dozen of articles, one edited volume, and few reports that are on the border of NGO activism /Academic publishing / activist pamphlets. Vast majority of these publications focused on reproductive rights, the language used, and the relations between the feminist movement and other movements present on the Polish activist scene. Despite growing literature on the topic of Black Protests (often coming from the activists themselves, see Korolczuk 2016; Murawska and Włodarczyk 2016; Król and Pustułka 2018; Chmielewska et.al. 2017; Czarnačka 2016, 2018; Kowalska et. al. 2018), its spillover and spillout, and its meaning for the reinvigoration of the Polish feminist movement, there is a vast and surprising gap in social movements' literature.

In Poland (as in other Central and Eastern European countries), due to the cultural isolation of the People's Republic of Poland, the process of women's emancipation proceeded differently. The achievements of successive waves of feminism emerged simultaneously; women in Poland were professionally and politically active earlier than in the West, while at the same time, they were more tightly bound by domestic responsibilities. For this reason, the dispute over women's spaces, practically absent from formal structures in Poland, may seem artificial, if not simply imported from the English TERF's wars. The phenomenon of TERFism, although publicised, is marginal in Poland - the vast majority of feminist organisations in Poland are trans-inclusive. Until 2021, the attitudes of a few people recognised as TERF were known mainly to those interested in queerness and transgenderism, on top of following these threads on social media, including closed left-wing groups on FB. The emergence of this topic from its niche came in January 2021 with the Women's Strike and the discussion around the phrase 'people with uteruses', which appeared at the demonstrations and which TERFs believed would displace the women-centred discourse.

The focus of these protests was also new. In addition to the usual events in public places and in front of public offices (in this case the Constitutional Court and the Prime Minister's offices), protests were held in front of the Ordo Iuris organisation, seen as one of the key actors in the disputed changes, and in front of the private residences of Kaja Godek (the face of the anti-choice movement) or the heavily guarded home of Jarosław Kaczyński, the leader of Law and Justice. There, on 31 October, a play of the classic play 'Dziady' was staged in the windows of private flats. This had a double symbolic significance. Firstly, in 1968, when 'Dziady' was taken off the stage of the National Theatre, nationwide protests erupted, becoming a Polish symbol of 1968 and an important milestone in the development of pro-democratic opposition. The second meaning relates to the name itself, as it is reminiscent of the newly created category of 'grandparents' - people of the "old" generation rejected by the protesting crowds as a source of moral standing and wisdom for making political change.

5.9 Key policy related outcomes

The project intends to look at how the issues, frame of argument, repertoires of action and campaigns of feminist movements influence models of democracy, and thus how state institutions do or do not take on board the stimuli of feminist movements. To do this, describe, if available in the literature, the key policy-related outcomes.

In general, the Polish political system is described as close to input and initiatives coming from the outside. Although in the procedure of preceding a bill there are included consultations with the general public usually represented by experts coming from NGOs and civil society sphere, this step is either often overlooked, ignored, or the lawmakers are playing with the composition of the expert group adjusting it to their own needs. After 2015 with the change of power any political opportunity structures for the feminist movement in relation to contact with parliamentary politics was closed. The Parliamentary group of Reproductive Rights invited, as experts on the protective right, priests and Bishops, but no feminist activists. Similarly it was the case with other initiatives, such as amendments to the labor code, changes that influence education, especially sexual education, and other women related issues. Interestingly, according to the activists themselves there is no huge difference between the post 2015 situation and the previous one, when the liberal oppositional party, the Civic platform was in power.

A slightly different case is with the local governments, as numerous cities in Poland have introduced the financing of the in vitro conception in their budgets, although the level of support is lower than expected. On the contrary, the central government has decided to fund a controversial and dubbed as ineffective by scientists naprotechnology, and suggest counselling and prayers instead of hormonal treatments. Local governments are also active in the case of anti-discriminatory bills that are often overlooked by the central government.

Women's voices were heard during the Parliamentary works on the bill on parents of disabled children, which included the financial support for those who cannot work because of their duties, and doing work on the alimony fund, as the majority of beneficiaries of this fund are women.

In response to the anti-abortion bill, the Save the Women (Ratujmy Kobiety) Committee was set up and developed its bill to legalise abortion. Both anti- and pro-abortion bills were presented in the Sejm at the same time - at the end of September 2016. At the same time, in fear of drastic abortion laws, Women's Strikes - the largest demonstrations on abortion in Poland since the ban - took place in the streets of many Polish towns and cities. The accumulation of protests occurred on 3 October, the so-called Black Monday.

In 2021 the citizens' bill committee "Legal Abortion. No compromise" was presented in the Sejm. More than 200,000 signatures were collected, but the bill was rejected.

5.10 Other important issues

If there are any other important issues discussed in the literature that cannot be put into any other subchapter of this report, summarize it here.

Moreover, Poland is in an accelerated trend of secularisation. According to a report by the PEW Group, Poland is the country where religiosity is declining at the fastest rate in the world. This is observed along various indicators confirming religiosity: self-declared regular attendance at Sunday mass: about 40% for the 60+ age group and 26% for the 18-40 age group), or participation in religion classes conducted in schools (in total, about 25% of high school students participate in such classes, in some parts of the country there are schools where religion is not taught at all due to lack of interest of students). Despite these processes, the influence of the Catholic Church on politics and political parties

(with the exception of the Left party) is overwhelming and not representative when looking at the levels of religiosity of the whole society.

The spread of the protest: from metropolitan cities to small towns and cities

During both the 2016 and October 2020 protests, in addition to demonstrations in large cities, there were numerous protest events in smaller provincial towns. In 2016, the fact that protests were held across the country, including in small provincial towns whose residents are the main electoral force of the Law and Order Party in government, was one of the key factors in the success of the protesters and the maintenance of the so-called abortion compromise at the time.

Radicalisation of discourse

Attention was drawn to the new, more radical language that was used. Firstly, numerous slogans are repeated during the protests, displayed on banners and used in online communication: "the revolution is a woman" and the even more widespread "this is war!". Secondly, the most frequently shouted slogans are "fuck off" and "Fuck PiS", sometimes written down as ***** ***, under the name of a new social movement that has so far been active mainly online.

5.11 Conclusion

Outline the main findings in your local context (based on the state of the art) and point out the blind spots. Specifically, explain how the points described above interact with decision-making processes and the quality of democracy in your country, i.e. whether and how the role of feminist movements in challenging, improving or innovating democratic models emerges in the literature.

The success of Black Monday and the 2016 National Women's Strike campaign has several dimensions. Apart from the obvious tactical success of backing down from plans to tighten abortion laws, it also resulted in the emergence of a new wave of female activists and thus changed the landscape of Polish social movements, which can be considered a victory on a strategic level.

The success of Black Monday and the 2016 National Women's Strike campaign has several dimensions. Apart from the obvious tactical success of backing down from plans to tighten abortion laws, it also resulted in the emergence of a new wave of female activists and thus changed the landscape of Polish social movements, which can be considered a victory on a strategic level.

The leader of the movement, Marta Lempart, emphasised that the strength of the initiative is its local character and apolitical nature:

I would like to concentrate on local actions. I would not like to make big demonstrations in Warsaw, but to act with all my strength in the regions. It is there, in women from small towns, that there is strength. 2.3 thousand people in Jelenia Góra, a thousand people in Świdnica and 700 in Lubin could be translated into 150 thousand demonstrators in Wrocław. In Lubin, everyone votes for PiS, they leave work from KGHM at 3.30pm and there is no way any opposition could be hatched. A protest in such localities is just a big deal. [...] 'No logo' has opened up opportunities for those who want to act but don't necessarily want to sign up to a party.

The issue of attitudes towards and relationships with political parties - one of the main elements of the concept of political opportunity structures - is also one of the most important in the discussions that have been taking place in the Polish feminist movement in recent years.

The Alphabet of Revolt. Nationwide Women's Strike, <https://archiwumosiatsynskiego.pl/alfabet-buntu/>. ogolnopolski-strajk-kobiet/ (accessed June 2020).

Women's Black Protests are perceived as a sign of a "populist feminism," a gendered version of the "left populism" theorized by Mouffe (2018)[56]. Black Protest participants cohered around the idea that they were "ordinary women" – a people rebelling against an arrogant patriarchal elite (Gunnarsson Payne 2020[57]; Snochowska-Gonzalez and Ramme 2018[58], Korolczuk and Graff, 2022).

5.12 List of feminist movements' campaigns

To proceed with the definition of methodological guidelines, the project intends to focus on the campaigns of feminist movements. Through the campaigns it will in fact be possible to better define actors, problems, frames, repertoires of action on which to build sampling, methods, and data analysis. The choice to focus on campaigns allows on the one hand to translate subject areas into an empirically detectable phenomenon, and on the other hand to draw on a meaningful sample for interviews, participant observation and frame analysis. We recommend focusing on five major campaigns (one for each issue area) in your country, significant enough to bring together relevant actors, issues, and actions for analysis.

5.12.1 Gender based violence

MANIFAS

Manifa is an annual feminist demonstration organized in connection with International Women's Day on March 8 in the biggest Polish cities (by local feminist organizations). The first Manifa was organized in Warsaw in 2000 by Porozumienie Feministyczne 8 Marca ("8th March Women's Coalition) and turned into a nationwide feminist, anti-discrimination, and anti-clerical demonstration.

During Manifas, specific demands are made which are the Manifa's main subject for the year. These are: health care, childcare, parental equality, pension security for widows and women working in the home, equality in the workplace, formal financial security and inheritance rights for same-sex couples (civil partnership law), prohibition of illegal evictions, protection against gender-based violence, sex education, modern contraception and abortion rights, respect for the secularity of the state and prohibition of state funding of religious associations. The motto of the first Manifa was "Democracy without women is only half-democracy." In later demonstrations the focus was economic and employment issues, as well as other gender base violence and reproductive rights, for instance the motto of the 2011 Manifa was "Enough of exploitation! We give notice!", in March 2017 people marched under the slogan "Against the Violence of Power". In 2018 Manifa in Warsaw was focused on Poland's strict anti-abortion law and was a response to Poland's ruling party's plan to ban the possibility to abort sick foetuses, which sparked strong protests from women's organisations. A year later the Warsaw's Manifa focused again on gender based violence (slogan: "We are the Revolution. No more being nice to violent guys"). The slogan for the 21st Manifa (2020) translated stands for "We are the granddaughters of the witches, who could not be burn"

16 DNI PRZECIWI PRZEMOCY WOBEC KOBIET/ THE 16 DAYS OF ACTION AGAINST GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE CAMPAIGN

Since 2007 The Autonomia Foundation has been implementing the international 16 Days of Action Against Gender-based Violence Campaign in Krakow and supporting activities across Poland. In 2021, the activities of the Autonomia Foundation within the framework of the 16 Days of Action Against Gender-Based Violence Campaign are being implemented primarily in the project "No means no - countering violence against women with disabilities", funded by EU resources.

It is worth mentioning that over the past two decades, many social campaigns with the theme of gender-based violence have been carried out by the Women's Rights Centre. A list of these campaigns can be found at the link: <https://cpk.org.pl/co-robimy/prowadzimy-kampanie/>

5.12.2 Health and reproductive rights

CAMPAIGN RELATED TO the CIVIL PRO-CHOICE BILL 'SAVE THE WOMEN 2017'

On 23 October 2017 the Citizens' Legislative Committee 'Save the Women 2017' submitted to the Sejm a citizens' bill, the main proposal of which was to allow abortion up to the 12th week of pregnancy, and in certain cases after the 12th week. This was preceded by a campaign to collect signatures for the bill (from 24 July to 10 October 2017). The Committee protested also against the abolition of in vitro funding, supported and participated in civic protests, including the demonstrations "Free Polish Women-Free Poland. All for one, one for all" or Black Tuesday. Members of the committee also promoted the project through active participation in the national media.

„NIE JESTEŚ SAMA”/“YOU ARE NOT ALONE” (2018).

A billboard campaign organised by the pro-choice environment under the slogan 'You are not alone'. The campaign was intended to show that abortion is commonplace; it was also a response to controversial anti-abortion billboards. The campaign was organised by 'Women on the Web' and the 'Abortion Dream Team'.

Pro-choice billboards appeared in Warsaw, Krakow, Gdansk, Poznan, Wroclaw and Katowice. The graphics depicted three women and carried the slogan: "Statistically 1 out of 3 of your friends has had an abortion. You are not alone". The campaign was funded through online fundraising. The money was used to produce posters and rent billboards.

5.12.3 LGBTQ+ rights

RAINBOW FRIDAY - a campaign initiated by the association Campaign Against Homophobia to show solidarity with and support for LGBTQI young people in the school environment. The campaign aims to show that a school is a safe and welcoming place for any young person, regardless of sexual orientation, gender identity or gender characteristics. The campaign first launched on 28 October 2016 and has since been organised every year on the last Friday in October. During Rainbow Friday, support for LGBTQI people could be shown by, for example, wearing rainbow colours, wearing a rainbow pin, organising a lesson on tolerance and the problems of the LGBTQI community, putting up a poster about the campaign and organising workshops or conversations with people who face problems of aggression and intolerance.

TECZA NIE OBRAŻA/ RAINBOW DOES NOT OFFEND. The campaign was a joint initiative of Action Democracy, the Campaign Against Homophobia, the Miłość Nie Wyklucza association and the Polish Society for Anti-Discrimination Law. The campaign was a solidarity response with those facing prosecution charges for carrying a flag with a rainbow eagle at the Equality March in Częstochowa (2018), and later supported other repressed people, including three activists accused of insulting religious feelings, who in 2019 pasted stickers with an image of Our Lady of Czestochowa in a rainbow halo around St Dominic's Church in Plock.

The campaign consisted, among other things, of collecting signatures for the 'Rainbow does not offend' appeal, in which activists demanded that the Minister of Internal Affairs and Administration stop putting political pressure on the prosecution and stop his homophobic prejudices. During the campaign people were also encouraged to wear gadgets (T-shirts, badges, stickers, flags) with an eagle on a rainbow background and to promote the main slogan of the campaign in social media.

“BEZ LGBT+ NIE MA POLSKI”/ WITHOUT LGBT+ THERE IS NO POLAND

19 June 2021. - on the day of the Warsaw Equality Parade, a social campaign was launched jointly by Gazeta.pl, Wyborcza.pl, "Gazeta Wyborcza", TOK FM and tokfm.pl, the association Miłość Nie Wyklucza (Love Doesn't Exclude) and the MullenLowe Warsaw agency - the originator of the campaign.

The creative idea of the campaign and the main message was based on the "exclusion" of the letters L, G, B and T from texts on websites and in Internet services, on the front pages of newspapers and in social media. The creators of the campaign wanted to show in this way that "Without LGBT+ there is no Poland".

5.12.4 Labor market

KAMPANIA „MOŻESZ BYĆ KIM TYLKO ZECHCESZ! ZAWÓD NIE MA PŁCI”/ THE CAMPAIGN "YOU CAN BE ANYTHING YOU WANT! A PROFESSION HAS NO GENDER" organized by KARAT COALITION., <https://www.karat.org/pl/dzialania/mozesz-byc-kim-tylko-zechcesz-zawod-nie-ma-plci/#> (The Karat Coalition is an association that has carried out activities for gender equality. It was established in 1997 to combine and represent the voice of non-governmental organizations from Central and Eastern Europe and Central Asia, however in recent years the organization has focused mainly on Poland, on groups of women experiencing discrimination on the labour market due to, among others, the low level of education, gender stereotypes and related to these the barriers to accessing the professions.)

The campaign has been running since 2015 and its main goals are to draw public attention to the problems related to women on the labour market and to contribute to the changes in the system and in social awareness: creation of awareness among girls and women about current and future employment trends on the labour market when choosing a profession, encouraging girls to learn professions that will provide them with a reasonable wage and economic independence, and the fight against gender stereotypes which determine female educational choices.

'IT'S ONLY GENDER' campaign (2021-2022) under the patronage of the Women's Rights Centre is also worth mentioning here, not only for its aims of supporting women on the labour market, but because of the controversy surrounding the poor working conditions of women employed at the Women's Rights Centre. On 30 January 2023, an article was published in which former female employees of the Women's Rights Centre complain about the working conditions they experienced while working at the Centre, including bullying, lack of payment for work, wages well below the lowest national wage, lack of an employment contract, and communication difficulties with the Women's Rights Centre's management.

5.12.5 Migration

"ZOBACZ NIEWIDZIALNE"/ „SEE THE INVISIBLE" (June 2014-June 2015) campaign for migrant women in Poland organised by the Institute of Public Affairs.

The campaign focused on presenting the situation and barriers to integration of migrant women employed in Poland in seasonal jobs and in the highly feminised domestic work sector. The project also aimed to draw attention to the stories of migrant women who, contrary to the stereotypical image, have succeeded in the Polish labour market and work according to their qualifications or passion, and not solely determined by what the Polish labour market can usually offer migrant women.

The project included, among other things, a social campaign in the national press, film and radio reports on the lives of migrant women in Poland, a debate on the subject, a competition for a press report, a film presentation, a photo exhibition and an evening of intercultural reportage. The project also includes a campaign website and a book publication.

5.13 Bibliography

"Aborcjoniści jej nienawidzą. Kaja Godek zaatakowana," *Polonia Christiana*, Oct. 26, 2020.

CBOS, komunikat z badań nr 165/2016 Polacy o prawach kobiet, „czarnych protestach” i prawie aborcyjnym https://www.cbos.pl/SPISKOM.POL/2016/K_165_16.PDF [18.02.2020]

Chełstowska, Agata. 2011. "Stigmatisation and Commercialisation of Abortion Services in Poland: Turning Sin into Gold." *Reproductive Health Matters*, 19(37): 98-106.

Chmielewska, Marta, Druciarek Małgorzata and Izabela Przybysz (2017) *Czarny Protest. W stronę nowego "kompromisu aborcyjnego"*. Instytut Spraw Publicznych, Warszawa 2017.

Czarnacka, Agata (2018) *Rewolucja i co dalej? Ruchy kobiece w poszukiwaniu nowych form polityczności. Raport 2018*, Warszawa: Fundacja im. Izabeli Jarugi-Nowackiej.

Czarnacka, Agata red. (2016) *Przebudzona rewolucja, Prawa reprodukcyjne kobiet w Polsce. Raport 2016*, Warszawa: Fundacja im. Izabeli Jarugi-Nowackiej.

Fuszara, M. (2005). 'Between Feminism and the Catholic Church: The Women's Movement in Poland'. *Czech Sociological Review*, 41 (6), 1057-1075.

Grzymała-Busse, Anna (2020) 'Poland is a Catholic country. So why are mass protests targeting churches?' in *The Washington Post*, October 28th 2020, <https://www.washingtonpost.com/politics/2020/10/28/poland-is-catholic-country-so-why-are-mass-protests-targeting-churches/?fbclid=IwAR1qle0O2ZjyO8mFxTAbSuFB0gLfLfvfEqXYpAFjYJrv1xk0Qf9lauxzfc>

Gunnarsson Payne, J. (2019). *Kobiety jako „lud”: Czarne Protesty jako sprzeciw wobec autorytarnego populizmu w perspektywie międzynarodowej* w: Kowalska B., Korolczuk, E., Snochowska-Gonzalez C. i J. Ramme, *Bunt Kobiet: Czarne Protesty i Strajk Kobiet*, Gdańsk: Wydawnictwo Europejskiego Centrum Solidarności.

Katarzyna Bogdańska, "Jednoznaczny wynik sondażu. To kiepska wiadomość dla PiS," *Wiadomości*, December 19, 2021.

Kondratowicz, Ewa. 2001. *Szminka na sztandarze: kobiety Solidarności 1980-1989: rozmowy*. Warszawa: Sic!

Korolczuk, E., & Hryciuk, R. E. (Eds.). (2016). *Pożegnanie z Matką Polką?: Dyskursy, praktyki i reprezentacje macierzyństwa we współczesnej Polsce*. Wydawnictwa Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego.

Korolczuk, Elżbieta, Beata Kowalska, Jennifer Ramme, and Claudia Snochowska-Gonzalez. 2019. *Bunt kobiet. Czarne Protesty i Strajki Kobiet*. Gdańsk: Wydawnictwo Europejskiego Centrum Solidarności.

Korolczuk, Elżbieta. 2016. "Explaining Mass Protests Against Abortion Ban in Poland: The Power of Connective Action." *Zoon politikon* (7): 91-113.

Kowalska B., Pluta M., Nawojski R. (2018), 'Kobiece rewolucje wciąż trwają', in: Maria Zielińska, Dorota Szaban, Beata Trzop, *Transgraniczność w perspektywie socjologicznej. Europa - podzielona wspólnota?*, Zielona Góra: Elipsa.

Kowalska, B., i Nawojski, R. (2019). *Uwaga, uwaga tu obywatelki!: obywatelstwo jako praktyka w czarnych protestach i strajkach kobiet*. w: Kowalska, B., Korolczuk E., Snochowska C. i Ramme J. (2019) *Bunt Kobiet: Czarne Protesty i Strajk Kobiet*, Gdańsk: Wydawnictwo ECS

Król, Agnieszka and Paulina Pustułka. 2018. "Women on Strike: Mobilizing Against Reproductive Injustice in Poland." *International Feminist Journal of Politics* 20/3: 366-384.

Kubisa, Julia, and Katarzyna Rakowska. 2018. "Was it a Strike? Notes on the Polish Women's Strike and the Strike of Parents of Persons with Disabilities." *Praktyka Teoretyczna* 30(4): 15-50.

Majewska, Ewa (2020) Poland Is in Revolt Against Its New Abortion Ban, *Jacobin Magazine*, https://jacobinmag.com/2020/10/poland-abortion-law-protest-general-strike-womens-rights?fbclid=IwAR0TlpBqwQazD8wbhDvAHwqOptNgyGc_Yl_KikIG9sly_JQPX0IPg_M6Mgw

Matyenia, Elzbieta "Polish Feminism Between the Local and the Global: A Task of Translation" in *Women's Movements in the Global Era: The Power of Local Feminisms*, ed. Amrita Basu (Boulder: Westview, 2010), 202.

Murawska, Katarzyna, and Zofia Włodarczyk. 2016. *Nam się zaczęło pod dupą palić... Czarny protest w perspektywie organizatorek*. Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Krytyki Politycznej.

Muszel, Magdalena, & Grzegorz Piotrowski (2018). Rocking the small-town boat: Black Protest activists in small and provincial Polish cities. *Praktyka Teoretyczna*, 30(4), 102-128. <https://pressto.amu.edu.pl/index.php/prt/article/view/19010/18735>

Pacewicz, Krzysztof. 2018. "Zdecydowana przewaga zwolenników dopuszczenia aborcji na żądanie nad przeciwnikami!" OKO.Press, 2 June. <https://oko.press/zdecydowana-przewaga-zwolennikow-dopuszczenia-aborcji-na-zadanie-nad-przeciwnikami-sondaz/>

Pacewicz, Piotr "Gasnący płomień rewolucji? Nie, złość się odkłada, refleksja kumuluje. STRAJK KOBIEC," OKO.Press, January 14, 2021.

Socha R. (2017). 'Jak się protestuje w małych miastach'. *Polityka*, <https://www.polityka.pl/tygodnikpolityka/spoleczenstwo/1725474,1,jak-sie-protestuje-w-malych-miasteczkach.read> [30/10/2017]

Suchanow, Klementyna. 2020. *To jest wojna: kobiety, fundamentaliści i nowe średniowiecze*. Wydawnictwo Agora.

Wilczek, Maria (2020) Farmers, taxi drivers and miners show support for abortion protests in Poland, *Notes From Poland*, <https://notesfrompoland.com/2020/10/26/farmers-taxi-drivers-and-miners-show-support-for-abortion-protests-in-poland/?fbclid=IwAR00Fd5EOx19-N-TeOQfYb02gYvbNQJZFdT9FChcfcJhBn7KD-W4DXtkRCQ>

"Wtargnięcia na msze, zniszczone elewacje kościołów, zatrzymania. Dane policji," *Polsatnews*, October 29, 2020.

<http://strajkkobiet.eu/co-robimy/> [07.11.2018]

<https://archiwumosiатыnskigo.pl/alfabet-buntu/ogolnopolski-strajk-kobiet/> [20.06.2020]

[http://www.wysokieobcasy.pl/wysokie-obcasy/7,163229,23952656,tylko-5-proc-polek-uwaza-sie-za-feministki-choc-postulaty.html?disableRedirects=true#s=BoxWyboLink\[20/09/2018\]](http://www.wysokieobcasy.pl/wysokie-obcasy/7,163229,23952656,tylko-5-proc-polek-uwaza-sie-za-feministki-choc-postulaty.html?disableRedirects=true#s=BoxWyboLink[20/09/2018])

6 SLOVENIA

6.1 Introduction

The feminist movement in Slovenia in the second half of the 1980s emerged as a part of civil society movements in Slovenian and wider Yugoslav context. Jalušič (2002) notes that it first existed parallel to peace, ecological and gay and lesbian social movements and there were numerous overlaps between the actors of these movements. In the 1990s parts of the social movements from the 1980s consolidated into non-governmental organizations. Despite the fact that some feminist issues were adopted by the socialist/communist administration in the 1980s, which Jalušič (2002) categorized as a time of "state feminism" when female politicians played a pivotal role, it was not until the 1990s that these ideas were implemented more broadly. The 1990s was the period when feminist and gender issues became gradually integrated in official politics (Pajnik, 2019). Along with the institutionalization of the feminist movement, several collective claims and grass-root actions have been successfully developed. Considering the 2010-2022 as a period of scientific publication relevant for this report, we can detect that the contemporary feminist movements and mobilizations were affected and inspired by the initiatives from the past, however wider socio-political events triggered the emergence of new movements with their main focus on anti-capitalism, anti-authoritarianism, autonomy and autonomous spaces, protecting queer spaces and queerness, advocating LGBT rights and combating sexual and gender-based violence.

The beginnings of women's movement which can be referred to as the "first wave" of feminism in Slovenia can be tracked back to the end of 19th and the beginning of 20th century. The movement existed in the form of inter-war women's associations, publishing houses, and university research on 'women's issues' (Verginella & Selišnik, 2018). Nevertheless, it can be said that until the 1980s and 1990s, women's movements and groups were not able to break out of the common Slovenian cultural and national core and develop an autonomous emancipatory political strategy (Jalušič, 2002, 18). If the 1980s and 1990s represent a "second wave" of feminism in the Slovenian context, the early 2000s saw the emergence of a third wave of feminism, which is closely intertwined with queer sensitivity.

This report examines the existing literature that analyses feminist movement in Slovenia in the period between 2010 and 2022, its actors, campaigns and arguments. In the introduction to the report, we briefly describe the selection of academic and expert literature included in the analysis. What follows is the description of the main characteristics and findings of the included publications with regard to the researched topics. In the introduction we also highlight some of the challenges that emerged during the analysis, such as fragmentary coverage of the topics, diverse epistemologies and methodologies used in the literature which pose some obstacles to conducting a comprehensive comparative literature analysis.

Search strategy and study selection

Studies were collected by searching the Slovenian bibliographic system Cobiss. Simultaneous searching across collections of a number of providers and databases was carried out, e.g. Academia.edu, SAGE, Researchgate, and Google Scholar. Keywords used in the database search were the following: "feminism", "feminist movements", "feminist campaigns", "feminist activism", "feminist organizing", "LGBT rights", "sexual and gender-based violence". The search based on the above mentioned keywords was performed in Slovenian and English language.

Studies were selected based on eligibility criteria which included publication between 2010 and 2022. Scholarly articles, reports, books or book chapters that address feminist organizing and mobilization in Slovenia were included. Studies that did not deal with feminist movement explicitly, but addressed

topics related to feminist issues (e.g. the rights of LGBT community, gender-based violence, gender inequality, etc.) were excluded.

We first examined titles, keywords, and abstracts for inclusion eligibility. If the decision could not be made based on these details alone, we further conducted a full-text assessment. We also searched for expert reports and other grey literature by non-governmental groups, movements, and other members of the “critical public” that could help us gain a deeper knowledge of the subject. By manually examining the bibliographies of relevant research, additional studies were identified. In total, 22 papers met the inclusion criteria and were included in the analysis.

Study characteristics

In the period 2010-2022 the largest proportion of academic literature deals with autonomous LGBT and queer feminist organizing in Slovenia (Avtonomne feministke, 2017; Hvala, 2010a, 2010b, 2011, 2012, 2015; Oblak & Pan, 2019; Velikonja, 2013). These studies address alternative and non-mainstream feminist organizing in autonomous spaces where the political notion of autonomy is intertwined with the practices of squatting that emerged out of feminist struggles for public spaces. The struggles were frequently characterized by a response to the repression of the authorities to take away autonomous spaces that were established in the squatted areas and served as mobilization points for several grass-root collectives of feminist activists.

Another visible topic in the literature concerns the institutionalized forms of feminist action, which led to the integration of feminist issues into official policies in the area of gender equality (Kralj & Renner, 2015). One study (Antić Gaber & Kuhar, 2019) also looks in part of the development of feminist activism, focusing on the ways in which new social movements in the 1980s provided an important incentive for the institutionalisation of the feminist and LGBT movement and for the assertion of political demands for gender equality.

To some extent, feminist mobilizations are taken into consideration in a few studies dealing with referenda on same-sex marriage in Slovenia (Krašovec, 2015; Podolak, 2019). While a visible body of academic literature is devoted to discuss the anti-gender movement that mobilized around two same-sex marriage referenda (the first one in 2012 and the second one in 2015) that attempted to provide equal legal protection of heterosexual and same-sex partnerships in Slovenia, these few studies refer to feminist movement as being part of a larger network of grass-root organizing to defend equal rights for same-sex partnerships.

Another issue that has attracted attention of researchers is the Slovenian *#metoo* (*#jaztudi*) campaign which is taken into account as an important trigger of building feminist alliances in Slovenia. Završek (2020, 2021) has analysed the distinctive features of the *#metoo* campaign in Slovenian context, in comparison to its equivalents in most Western countries, and argued how it presented an important turning point in combating sexual violence.

Some authors have focused to discuss feminist movements during and around the context of the Slovenian uprising period (2012-2013) using the conceptual frameworks of social movement theory (Pajnik et al. 2020; Ribač 2016; Ribač, 2018), theories of democracy and citizenship (Pajnik 2019) in order to analyse the organizational (“actional”) and the thematic (content-related) *credo* of the movements. These research perspectives adopt a cross-movement analysis, identifying several actors, discussing their similarities and differences in topical interests and organizational practices. Mapping of left actors was carried out as a part of research (Furlan et al., 2018) that elaborated on leftist (protest) movements that came into being as a response to wider socio-political developments in Slovenia. Among others, the operation of a political youth organization that emerged during the

uprising in 2011-2012 is analysed with regard to a noticeable segment of their activities being explicitly feminist oriented.

The most recent study included in the literature review (Gramc, 2022) focuses on the development of the Slovenian transgender movement. It draws on historical account of the movement and its development, with particular reference to its internal conflicts.

Besides that, we have also identified a smaller body of expert literature that provides a valuable complement to the information on topics addressed in the academic literature. One of the sources is a collection of the testimonies during the course of *#metoo* campaign (Kovač, 2019). Hvala (2010b) has similarly collected the interviews with the organisers of the feminist and queer festival *Red Dawns* (Rdeče zore). We have also included a short chapter of a magazine *Lesbo* (Sukič, 2012), that reflects the organization of the lesbian art festival *Lesbian Quarter* (Lezbična četrt).

Reviewing the selected corpus of the literature, we can conclude that feminist movements in Slovenia are a rather fragmentary covered field in the academic and expert literature published between 2010-2022, focusing on particular areas of feminist activism, initiatives and/or campaigns, which makes it challenging to grasp the field in a comprehensive way. The literature focuses on different time periods of feminist movement between 2010-2022, which sometimes makes it difficult to trace the timeline of events solely on the basis of the academic coverage of the topic. Literature is also fragmented in terms of putting different feminist actors in a research focus. Some of the texts sporadically reference to different actors (e.g. Gramc, 2022; Kralj & Rener, 2015), while others analyse selected actors, their rationale and repertoires in a comparative perspective (e.g. Oblak & Pan, 2019; Pajnik et al. 2020; Ribač 2018) or focus more on case studies of individual actors, campaigns or initiatives (e.g. Hvala, 2010a, 2010b, 2011; Zaviršek, 2020, 2021). In terms of epistemologies and methods the studies stem from diverse backgrounds such as social movement theory, critique of gender-based violence and sexual harassment, queer theory etc. Reflecting the studies in terms of the authors and their position (in feminist initiatives), we can observe that some of the authors are or have been themselves active in feminist movements (Hvala, Kovač, Gramc) or were among the initiators of movements (Hvala, Velikonja, Zaviršek), while others address the topic from various theoretic feminist standpoints (Pajnik, Zaviršek, Kralj & Rener).

In the following chapters of this report we outline the main findings of the studies included in the literature review, including the history of feminist movements, main actors and organizations, their allies and themes and agendas that emerged during the feminist movement organizing. Furthermore, we explore what kind of repertoires of action were employed by the movement and key arguments used in campaigns and debates in order to influence the state of democracy.

6.2 The history of the feminist movements and its context

Contemporary feminist movements cannot be thought of without taking into consideration the historical course of its emergence. From the point of view of independent women's and feminist groups and organizations (that existed outside the institutions), the feminist movement in Slovenia emerged as a part of civil society movement in the 1980s, which developed and articulated under the influence of Western European feminist movements (Jalušič, 2002). The LGBT movement coincided with the emergence of feminist and the broader civil society movement in the 1980s. The lesbian movement in particular is directly linked to the feminist movement, as it materialized from it, while, in fact, all movements of the time were networked; although they addressed different issues, there was a synergy between them, and the actors were the same in different initiatives of the movement (Antić Gaber & Kuhar, 2019, 107). The breakup of Yugoslavia and the war led feminist groups down different paths. While feminist activism in Slovenia led to a strong and successful struggle to preserve women's reproductive rights in the 1991 constitution, the results in other parts of Yugoslavia were different in

the face of war. A strong oppositional feminist anti-war movement developed in Croatia and Serbia, and something similar happened in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Jalušič, 2002, 62). The feminist counterpublic in Slovenia first existed as a strand of institutional women's politics that translated the demands of the feminist movement into the political field and the institutionalised legislative processes (Ribač, 2018, 71-73). Although the cooperation between state institutions and civil society, in particular with women's movement and feminist groups and organizations, was well built in the 1990s, this practice has been discontinued later on, resulting in the loss of a direct link between the women's movement, the feminist agenda and formal, institutionalised politics (Antić Gaber & Kuhar, 2019, 106).

At the same time, we were confronted with a phenomenon that gripped the whole of post-communist Eastern Europe, which could be called the NGO-ization of civil society, characterised by the tendency of NGOs to professionalise and operate according to a model of institutional rules and hierarchies, and to focus on raising funds for their work (Jalušič, 2002, 81). In the new work environment, the lack of money was fatal. At the same time, a large part of the activities was somehow delegated to the Office for Women's Politics, established in 1992, which automatically took over some of the functions previously performed by women's groups and, in particular, began to monitor the situation of women. The office neglected the function it should have performed, which was to strengthen women's NGOs during the transition period, and began to carry out a large part of the activities of these organisations itself, presenting itself as a "state feminist". This led to the paradox that we still experience in Slovenia today: there are few institutionalised activities left of one of the strongest feminist movements in Eastern Europe (ibid., 82).

Kralj & Renner (2015) argue that feminist action in Slovenia developed around three historical time periods that addressed different gender equality issues. Women's participation and promotion of women's issues in politics came to life through the establishment of various formal institutions (e.g. Parliamentary Commission on Women's Politics established in 1990 and the government's Office for Women's Politics in 1992) (Antić Gaber & Kuhar, 2019; Kralj & Renner, 2015). These institutions encouraged women's participation and promoted women's issues in politics and especially focused on the preservation of certain achievements, such as the right to abortion, the right to paid maternity leave and widely developed network of kindergartens, that were the result of communist "state feminism" but were at the same time also a significant basis for future and autonomous life for women (Kralj & Renner, 2015, 7-9). Another important moment of mobilization is recognized around the social position of women in the ideological domain that emerged in the transition period after the independence of Slovenia in 1991, and domesticated women as "bearers of the nation". "Thus, instead of the former (mostly economically enforced) "proletarianization" and (politically enforced) "emancipation", an ideological model of domestication of women was introduced" (ibid., 11). In the 1990s, as a symbol of opposition to the above mentioned nationalist policy, women's and feminist groups succeeded in preventing the implementation of a proposal on the prohibition of abortion (see footnote 1) (ibid., 18). Since 2000s the state measures for gender equality stemmed from the fact that "women are most affected by the economic crisis in the area of labour market and employment, the extent of women's informal and unpaid work in the private sphere is increasing", while inadequate political representation of women leads to a lack of opportunities to fight back the deterioration of this situation (ibid., 14). Several important legislations were adopted in this period, including gender quotas for election, artificial insemination for single women and various laws that strive to provide equal opportunities for women and men as well as prevent violence against women. As one of the

most important, the implementation of fathers leave⁴⁹ is mentioned (Kralj & Renner, 2015), pushing for balancing work and family life and contributing to gender equality.

Feminist mobilizations in Slovenia in the past, i.e. the 1980-2000s developed in etatist/national frameworks and were marked by the professionalization and NGO-ization, while the movements developed post 2000s and around anti-austerity period since 2010, have been characterized by “diffused networking” (Pajnik et al. 2020, 348). A characteristic feature of the more recent movements is the continuous introduction of new groups, topics and also extension to content transcending the gender framework. In the last fifteen years the feminist movement became more ramified organizationally and more plural in content, by including queer topics, but above all by addressing topics that develop beyond gender frameworks or combine these frameworks with the precariat, anti-capitalism, autonomy of spaces etc. (ibid., 348-349).

The emergence of feminist initiatives between 2010-2022 has been marked by various events such as creating autonomous spaces or pursuing various actions. Within the establishment of autonomous activist practice and organisation of feminist and LGBT groups, the key was the *Autonomous Women’s Centre* (Avtonomni ženski center) at Metelkova in the capital of Ljubljana, a space created in 1993 by various autonomous women, feminist and lesbian activists who participated in the occupation of Metelkova (Hvala, 2011; Hvala, 2015, 53). The occupation of spaces has been recognized in the literature as a crucial achievement that enabled activists to provide the movement with larger, autonomous and permanent spaces, which is the basis for the creation of a more stable feminist organizing or LGBT scene and community. The premises within the Ljubljana alternative scene have allowed the counterpublic to expand and deepen its ties both in the field of building a lasting political and activist community, and in the field of leisure activities (social scene) (Ribač, 2018; Velikonja, 2013). However, the literature (Hvala, 2010b; 2011) highlights some tensions and negative aspects of the “Metelkova counterpublic”, including lack of solidarity, the absence of permanent connections between different groups, sexism, chauvinism and homophobia due to the more visible presence of feminists and sexual minorities at Metelkova (Hvala, 2011).

Apart from occupation of spaces, feminist initiatives were also united by some collective actions. For example, some of the sources (Oblak & Pan, 2019; Pajnik, 2019; Pajnik et al., 2020) have identified mass protests and uprisings (All Slovenian Uprisings in 2012-2013⁵⁰) in Ljubljana, Maribor and other cities across Slovenia as an important mobilising moment for feminist initiatives that enabled joint mobilization and feminist encounters in the streets. During the uprisings in Ljubljana they have built a common feminist bloc that united various actors and groups (see the descriptions of the actors in the next chapter) in their fight against malfunctioning of the state apparatus. The lesbian/queer feminist community first bonded on the streets, during protest, direct action, occupational actions, and initiatives such as graffiti workshops were carried out. Apart from critically emphasising violence of neoliberal capitalism against women, exposing sexism and misogyny has been an important topic of

⁴⁹ Parental Protection and Family Benefits Act (Zakon o starševskem varstvu in družinskih prejemkih) was adopted in 2001 (modified several times). The act introduced a non-transferable right on the part of the father to paternity leave of up to 90 days. In 2013, a new proposal of a change of parental leave legislation was under discussion according to which fathers should take one month of (full paid) parental leave which would not be transferable to mothers (Kralj & Renner, 2019, 20-21).

⁵⁰ The period of 2012-2013 saw a series of anti-establishment and anti-government protests across several cities in the country that started with the expression of disapproval with the corruption and detachment of the political elite from the citizenry (Ribač, 2018). The uprising started in the northeastern town Maribor in autumn 2012 and soon spread to cities throughout Slovenia. In local communities and on the streets, a diversity of groups and initiatives responded to the forced austerity measures and malfunctioning of the contemporary political system. These were the largest protests in Slovenia since its independence in 1991 (Pajnik, 2019).

autonomous feminist initiatives (Oblak & Pan, 2019, 43). The uprisings witnessed substantial LGBT participation and to a great extent coincided with the rising visibility of transgender initiatives, thus they “offered a platform upon which Slovenian transgender activists came together to address transgender issues, make trans people assume a more prominent place in the public arena” (Gramc, 2022, 134-135).

In the aftermath of the uprisings, another mobilization of a feminist coalition occurred in 2016 when the municipal authorities tried to evict the users of Autonomous Rog Factory squat by force, and to demolish the squat which coincides with the goal of gentrification of Ljubljana. To defend and obtain the space was of great importance since autonomous feminist groups lost their own space after the end of *Autonomous Women’s Centre* at Metelkova in 2001. Feminist coalition of individuals from autonomous lesbian and queer feminist groups played a significant role in defending and occupying the Autonomous Rog Factory that endured repression of the authorities. The emergence of autonomous feminist initiatives was marked by following the do-it-yourself (DIY) principles of organisation, non-hierarchical mode of organising and community building. Intense collaboration in the occupation of Rog gave impetus to forming a new heterogeneous, non-hierarchical collectives that soon sought to build its own space in the squatted area (Oblak & Pan, 2019, 44-45). Looking at the context of the emergence of the queer movement, Hvala (2012, 182) explains that queer activism was formed within the LGBT movement “as a response to the assimilationist politics of homo-conservatism”. The term “queer” was introduced when the political differentiation within the LGBT movement began to take place and was “met with curiosity, political analysis and historic memory” (ibid., 181). Its consequent refusal in large parts of LGBT community (Hvala 2012; Oblak & Pan, 2015) can also be explained by the fact that that queer activism advocates a further fragmentation of a relatively small movement. On the other hand, the introduction of queer theory coincided with the “cultural turn” in academia when “politics of recognition” became the most important theme within gender and LGBT studies (Hvala, 2012).

Several authors (Pajnik et al. 2020; Ribač 2018) are in agreement that feminist actors in Slovenia in the analysed period are characterised by the proliferation of smaller groups addressing various feminist and/or gender-related issues, occasionally building coalitions. Still, historically, the diverging actors have managed to coalesce, solidarise, mobilise and unify on important historical issues such as the battle for abortion (see footnote 1), the referendum on artificial insemination⁵¹ etc. (Jalušič, 2002). One such topic that has accelerated coalition building is gender-based violence. Women’s non-governmental organisations were the first to raise awareness about different forms of gender-based violence in Slovenia. They demanded the activation of state services in recognising gender-based violence as a harmful form of violence perpetrated mostly by men and directed against women (Zaviršek, 2020, 346; Zaviršek, 2021, 203). In the period 2010-2022 several visible initiatives, campaigns and movements against gender-based violence in post socialist countries emerged (e.g. *#I am not afraid to tell* campaign in Russia and Ukraine which prompted hundreds of women to share personal stories of sexual assault, *#StoptheSilence* (*#PrekinimoŠutnju*) campaign in Croatia in which 400 women testified about the torture inflicted on them by gynaecologists during childbirths in 2018). Because of the visibility of the above mentioned campaigns in social media and their international recognition, they had a profound impact on feminist movements in other countries, including Slovenia (Zaviršek, 2020, 348-349; Zaviršek, 2021, 205). An example was *#metoo* (*#jastudi*) campaign in Slovenia in 2018, which was initiated by public intellectuals and carried out by the feminist organization *The 8th March*

⁵¹ In 2001 the referendum on Changes to Infertility Treatment Act was held. The amendments proposed the permit to artificial insemination of healthy single women (STA, 2001).

Institute (Inštitut 8. marec). The emergence of campaigns combating gender-based violence is explained in the context of neo-patriarchy (Zaviršek, 2020, 2021), an increasingly dominant traditionalism aimed at restoring traditional values and gender inequalities. Through claims “that women were to blame for men’s powerlessness” (Zaviršek, 2020, 345) conservative religious and civil society groups have contributed to the normalization of violence against women.

Transgender movement is characterized by similar processes of establishment. Gramc (2022) argues that the rise of transgender movement was accompanied with right-wing backlash and anti-gender movements and campaigns fighting for traditional values, namely both same-sex marriage referenda in 2012 and 2015. Of special importance to transgender movement was the 2015 referendum, when the movement gained its momentum. During the referendum campaign anti-gender activists pursued several attacks against transgender activists, claiming that they promoted “gender theory”, and seized the opportunity to instrumentalise the transgender movement against marriage equality by conflating transgender people with gay and lesbian (ibid., 137).

6.3 Actors, organizations and organizational models

Some of the research perspectives (Ribač, 2016; Pajnik, 2019; Pajnik et al., 2020) approach the analysis of feminist movements recognizing the disparities between the “older” and the “newer” actors: While the “older” feminist and LGBT movements often formalized their activity organizationally and focused on a specific social group, such as women or LGBT populations, the “newer” movements more often establish a horizontal way of operating, and address heterogeneous topics such as gender inequality, precariousness, corruption etc. (Pajnik, 2019; Pajnik et al., 2020).

For example, the actors established in the 1990s thematically focus on gender inequalities and address specific social groups. In 1984 *Women’s Section* of the Sociological Association was founded, and since the creation of the *Lilith*⁵² group a year later, many smaller groups have been set up, working in different fields, developing different forms of action and pursuing different objectives related to gender equality, violence against women (*SOS telephone line for women and children victims of violence* (Društvo SOS telefon za ženske in otroke žrtve nasilja), *Association for Nonviolent communication* (Društvo za nenasilno komunikacijo)), LGBT rights (*Lesbian Lilith*), rights to political representation (*Women for Politics group*), etc. (Antić Gaber & Kuhar, 2019, 103). *Legebitra*, association which was established in 1998, focuses on LGBT rights advocacy. Similarly, *ŠKUC* (Student Cultural Centre) which is the oldest non-governmental organization in Slovenia, established a separate gay group *Magnus* in 1984 and a lesbian group named *ŠKUC LL (Lesbian Lilith)* in 1987. As the first gay and lesbian organizations in the socialist countries of Eastern Europe it pursues various activities, but, in line with the heritage of their history, they remain thematically focused. Their activities include *ŠKUC Publishing* (*Vizibilija* and *Lambda* series), a lesbian library and archive, the *Lezbomanija* radio programme (at Radio Student), and the magazine *Lesbo* (Pajnik et al. 2020, 349). The large part of autonomous activist practice and organisation of feminist, LGBT and queer groups stems from Metelkova in Ljubljana. Although Metelkova was not a constitutive space for the LGBT scene and culture, as they were already established by then, it offered an opportunity to expand its cultural and social possibilities. The premises of the so called socio-building was also given to the LGBT movement at the time of Metelkova occupation in 1993 and formed them as clubs – today known as the gay club *Tiffany* and the lesbian club *Monokel*. The identity moment is important: from the very beginning, both

⁵² In April 1985, a founding meeting of a new women’s group Lilith (Lilit) at ŠKUC-Forum took place in Ljubljana’s alternative cultural club K4. Discussions covered women’s sexualities and ended up with a party attended by more than 250 women (Jalušič, 2002).

clubs had a fundamental mission to enable stable spaces for lesbian and gay socialising, socialisation and culture (Velikonja, 2013, 68).

As indicated earlier in this report, over the last three decades Ljubljana has witnessed a series of autonomous feminist initiatives that have mostly grown in squats as an example of contemporary, alternative non-mainstream political organising, born out of a radical critique of assimilation, commercialisation and commodification of the LGBT movement (Avtonomne feministke, 2017; Oblak & Pan, 2019). Hvala (2010a, 2011) notes that new feminist groups were established at Metelkova after the year 2000. Two feminist reading circles with an anarchist agenda emerged within the framework of the Dwarf Reading Room (Škratova čitalnica) and Infoshop, a women's section was founded within the framework of the activist *Bureau of Interventions* (Urad za intervencije), and the music collective *Female's'cream* was founded. With regard to the queer movement (Hvala, 2010a, 2011; Oblak & Pan, 2015), in the first decade of the 2000s queer collective *Alter Šalter* organized street actions and discussions about queer theory in non-LGBT venues, the *Insurrection of Lezbos* (Vstaja Lezbosov) organized public actions, graffiti and video art performances that aimed at addressing lesbophobia and increasing lesbian visibility. Among others we also witness the founding of queer-identified DJ and VJ collective *Sindikát* and *Ljudjeza.org*, a transnational queer vegan feminist group.

Apart from sporadic smaller groups dealing with lesbian activism, some of the most visible feminist alliances were formed in the 2000s. Among them, *Red Dawns festival collective* (Festival Rdeče zore) was established by lesbian feminist activists at Metelkova in 2001. They managed to connect various feminist and lesbian actors across Slovenia (e.g. ŠKUC LL, *Ljudjeza.org*, *Alter Šalter*), also diverse groups such as young women and men in precarious positions, feminists, lesbians, queer, etc. to co-create the festival's programme. Due to a generous and deliberate knowledge transfer and attraction of younger people, it has been possible to sustain self-organisation for almost 15 years. By maintaining strong connections with Metelkova, Rog Factory squat and youth centres across Slovenia the *Red Dawns* manage to "temporarily occupy and reshape hosting spaces and communities and spread their influence to the contested area of 'the queer'" (Oblak & Pan, 2019, 36-37).

Another visible actor is the *Lesbian Feminist University* (Lezbično feministična univerza) established in 2010 at Metelkova as an "autonomous educational, theoretical, artistic and action space", which addresses the university, ironically, as their modes of teaching are based on the "principles of self-organization, autonomy, active participation and the democratic decision-making of all the participants" (Pajnik et al. 2020, 349). They continuously organize various lesbian and feminist events and aim to establish a community of lesbians and women. As Oblak & Pan (2019) observe, they do not deal with queer feminism.

The occasional heterogeneous feminist and queer presence in Rog Factory squat culminated in the active defence against the attempted eviction in 2016 and the subsequent struggle for physical and symbolic space in the community (Avtonomne feministke, 2017). In 2016 radical politics was enacted by a new group, the *Anarcho Queer Feminist Collective* at Rog (Anarho-kvir-feministična skupina Rog) that (re)claimed its space after the municipal authorities attempted eviction (Oblak & Pan, 2019, 45). Although autonomous public spaces and squats were important for feminist initiatives, they also created networks in order to utilise their agenda towards community building in other locations. Apart from coincidental connections, the feminist community also bonded on the streets (Oblak & Pan, 2019, 43). The uprisings in Slovenia has seen mobilization of several established feminist initiatives (Pajnik et al., 2020), as well as the engagement of more recent groups, particularly three feminist groups were actively engaged: *Not Without Women* (Nič več brez nas žensk), *Feminist Action FemA* (Feministična akcija), and *Revoltng Women Social Workers* (Vstajniške socialne delavke) (Ribač, 2018; Kralj & Renner, 2015; Oblak & Pan, 2019). They markedly contributed to public demarcation of mainstream, pro-

capitalist lesbian and gay activism and more radical, lesbian and queer feminist activism (Oblak & Pan, 2019).

Among the newer actors, two specifically operate in the field of music – the *Kombinat Female Choir* (established in 2008) and the *Z'borke Feminist Choir* (2014). They sang at almost every event of mass protest in Slovenia in 2012 and 2013 (Kralj & Rener, 2015; Pajnik et al. 2020, 349) and are actively participating at various public rallies on worker's and minority rights. The visible, long-lasting actors include the *City of Women* (Mesto žensk) and its international festival of contemporary arts for the promotion of engaged women artists, activists and researchers. One of the contemporary actors is also the *Spol.si* web portal, which started operating in 2014 as an initiative that “considers gender-related questions in the framework of the social, political and economic conditions in Slovenia and the world and in relation to age, race, nationality, religion, social status and sexual orientation” (Pajnik et al. 2020, 349).

The feminist agenda has also come to include thus far marginalized topics such as the position of transgender persons both in the LGBT community and within the broader society. *TransAkcija*, which is specifically directed towards supporting, informing and empowering transgender persons regardless of their sexual orientation, first operated as an initiative, and then in 2015 formalized its activities and became an institute (Pajnik et al. 2020, 349-352). With regard to the development of transgender movement *TransMisija* has to be mentioned; in November 2014, a group of transgender people met in Ljubljana at the first *TransMisija*, which became the most important trans-related annual gathering in Slovenia. It brought together various actors that shaped the politics of the movement in the forthcoming years and it was considered to be a crucial moment in the history of transgender organising in Slovenia. Besides *Legebitra* and *TransAkcija* a few other NGOs provide safe space for gender non-conforming people, for example *Društvo Kvartir*, established in 2010, and *Društvo Appareo*, established in 2013. Both organisations work intersectionally: while the former focuses on bisexual and transgender issues, the latter has a broader approach. Moreover, the *Trans March* took place in the Autumn of 2018, which was to date the most explicit public gesture made by the transgender movement. It was organized as an intervention that demanded a change of policies towards transgender people such as legal gender recognition and transition (Gramc, 2022, 136).

Other feminist oriented initiatives functioning over the last couple of years, consist of quite diverse smaller organizations. One of the most noticeable is the *8th March Institute* (founded in 2017) that is focused predominantly, but not exclusively, on feminist issues (Furlan et al., 2018). In mapping left actors in Slovenia Furlan et al. (2018) have recognized the political youth organization *Iskra* that was established in 2011-2012 as a unique attempt to form a strong left-oriented force in the generally politically apathetic and opportunistic context of student politics. *Iskra* consists of various working groups, one of them being *Working Committee on Feminism (DoFEM)* (Delovni odbor za feminizem). They engage in the practice of organizing protests on various occasions including a feminist protest on international women's day. Although not mentioned in the literature, some other feminist initiatives have formed in recent years. One of the most visible informal groups is a research group called *Resistance* (Rezistenca) which deals with sexual harassment and violence in Slovenian higher education (Rožman, 2021). However, we have also observed the emergence of mainstream initiatives, such as *She knows Association* (Združenje Ona ve) founded in 2021 with the aim of increasing the proportion of women speaking in the media and at public events (G.C., 2021).

Relevant to notice is a great variety of forms of organizing of different actors. Some are established as NGOs (*Legebitra*, *Škuc LL*, *Transakcija*, the *8th of March Institute*), others operate as associations (*City of Women*) or on a voluntary basis of a larger number of researchers and activists (web portal *Spol.si*) and at the grass-roots festival-level (*Red Dawns*). Several feminist movements organized ad-hoc exploring “horizontal”, non-hierarchical ways of operating characterized by the absence of a leader,

and non-representative operation (Lesbian Feminist University, Revolting Women Social Workers, Anarcho Queer Feminist Collective, Z'borke) (Pajnik et al. 2020, 350-351; see also Oblak & Pan, 2019; Gramc, 2022).

6.4 Allies

The literature sporadically refers to various practices of alliances building at the national and transnational levels. Pajnik (2019) has detected different strategies of movements in seeking allies for their causes. While some groups, generally those with longer history of operation, form networks not only with their sympathizers but also with established institutions aiming at institutional change, other groups define their operation beyond and also against any institutionalism.

Based on the interviews and focus group discussions with several protagonists of the feminist movement Pajnik (2019) found that specificities of movements' networking strategies reflect, first, the thematic foci of their work, meaning that they associate with similar initiatives and groups, and second, their networking and organization practices also reflect their ideologies. For example, *Kombinat* has connections with other self-organized choirs in the region of former Yugoslavia; their bond is their will to self-organize and express rebellion through songs. *The Red Dawns* are also networked both in and outside of Slovenia. They have organized some "half-guerrilla actions", have attended protests in cooperation with the *Revolting Women Social Workers* and the *Lesbian Feminist University*, have worked with the anarchist group gathered around Infoshop, while they have also cooperated with NGOs such as the *Association for Nonviolent Communication* and the *SOS telephone line* on actions related to violence against women (established in the 1990s in the NGO-ization period of the movement). The interviewees and focus group partners that participated in the research (Pajnik, 2019) have explained they work regionally and have partners in other EU states. They also work intensely in the Balkan region where especially the exchange between festivals remains strong (ibid.).

Operational and networking strategies are different for *Legebitra* which is formally an NGO; it is a member of several international associations, like IGLYO and ILGA Europe, they are co-founder of an informal international network of LGBT associations, bringing together groups from the Balkan region, East Europe and Scandinavian countries. They cooperate with several NGOs and governmental institutions on various issues related to human rights and anti-discrimination. The largest in scope and the most visible cases of alliance building are related to major policy issues, i.e. same-sex marriage referenda campaigns or redefinition of rape and sexual violence. Being active in the campaign *For all the families* (Za vse družine) during the first same-sex marriage referendum campaign in 2012, demanding rights for same-sex partnerships and families *Legebitra* formed a network of 13 organizations, including 3 left oriented political parties (Pajnik 2019, 257). During the second referendum campaign in 2015 the alliance of 39 parties, associations, movements and people was formed. One part of the alliance was the *It's time for Yes* (Čas je za) group, which supported the proposed amendments of the Family Code. They also received international support of Human Rights Watch NGO (Podolak, 2019; Krašovec, 2015). With the emergence of *Only Yes means Yes* (Samo ja pomeni ja) campaign new alliances were forged between various women's organisations operating in the field of violence against women, the initiators of the *#metoo* campaign, and *Amnesty International* (Zaviršek, 2021).

The Revolting Women Social Workers are also visibly networked; they have worked with Infoshop, Social Center Rog, have organized a rally against sexism together with an autonomous feminist coalition, including the *Red Dawns*, the *Lesbian Feminist University* and a feminist choir *Zborke*. Unlike *Legebitra*, the *Revolting Women Social Workers* do not cooperate with formal institutions, "because we like being autonomous so that we can attack anybody at any time, whenever we feel there is a need, and this would not be possible if we were financed by someone" (Pajnik 2019, 257).

Sympathising with non-hierarchical ways of organizing, practicing direct democracy and allying with anarchist groups the *Revolting Women Social Workers* but also the *Red Dawns* did not join *FemA* who managed to bring together several movements in the times of the uprisings in 2012 and 2013 in the demands against political and systemic corruption, clientelism, nepotism and on the restoration of property that was taken away unlawfully (ibid.).

Some other alliances are noted in the academic literature. Despite the political differentiation of the LGBT movement noted by Hvala (2012) which is also characterized by disassociating LGBT politics from the “queer paradigm”, queer collectives like *Alter šalter*, *Red Dawns* and *Sindikat* “promote public spaces and events where it is possible (at least temporarily) to transgress the strict border between the existing lesbian and gay community and the loose alliance of nonheteronormative people” (ibid., 190). In addition, these groups promote “solidarity with the LGBTI community in the politically progressive segments of the heterosexual public sphere, for example, by organizing lesbian, gay, bisexual and trans events in heterosexual venues—and queering them in the process” (ibid.). Experiments in deliberate intergenerational knowledge transfer, such as the meetings between *Lilith*, *Red Dawns* and *Lesbian Feminist University*, are also noted in the literature (Oblak & Pan, 2019, 48).

In order to gain greater visibility and recognition (beyond Ljubljana) collectives like *City of Women*, *Red Dawns*, *Lesbian Quarter* and *Deuje babe* (festival in rural area of Slovenia, for more details see the chapter on repertoires of action) have also attempted to decentralise and take their activities to rural areas. *City of Women*, for example, regularly organizes film screenings of the *Gay and Lesbian Film Festival* (Festival gejevskega in lezbičnega filma) in several cities across the country, including rural areas (not only in Ljubljana where most of the initiatives operate), while *Red Dawns* has collaborated with various youth centres throughout Slovenia (Hvala, 2015, 261).

Transgender movement has relied on the already existing activist infrastructure provided by the gay and lesbian mobilizations even though these alliances have also varied in terms of strength and durability. However, the 2015 same-sex marriage referendum caused rifts in the already fragile alliance between the transgender movement and the gay and lesbian movement. The referendum campaign led to a conflict between the liberal strand of the gay movement and the radical strand of the transgender movement. “The former sees the transgender movement as detrimental to the prime gay agenda – marriage equality – because transgender activists (allegedly) “stole” the gay movement by gaining visibility in the media and establishing themselves as an important actor within the LGBT community” (Gramc, 2022, 137-138). On the other hand, the alliances between transgender and lesbian feminist movements are less turbulent, as evidenced by the fact that many lesbian feminist events are inclusive of transgender people (ibid., 138). The transgender activists also built coalitions outside the country, on the European and especially ex-Yugoslav level, for example *Trans Network Balkan* (Trans Mreža Balkan) and *Transpozijum* (Gramc, 2022, 148).

The literature reveals some strategies of alliance building that are shared by several of the actors, such as forming coalitions and partnering with similar initiatives that share a common concern over a specific feminist/gender/queer issue. The analysis has shown that several actors seek alliances transnationally. Interestingly, some differences in alliance seeking strategies among the actors were also noted; namely some actors cooperate with state institutions while others organize against any institutionalism.

6.5 Themes and agendas

As for the themes of interest we can observe that the feminist and LGBT actors engage around gender equality, sexual violence, LGBT and trans rights, feminist autonomous spaces etc. The research by Pajnik et al. (2020) that analysed the feminist and LGBT engagement during and beyond the uprising period in 2012 and 2013 pointed that the themes of interest are visibly dependant on the type of

actors. For example, the *Lesbian Feminist University*, is focused to address specific lesbian and feminist issues framing them in a broader context of social inequalities, economic differences; they are also active in autonomous organising and lesbian feminist politics. The *Red Dawns*, an international feminist and queer festival addresses arts and culture, politics and activism, engage critically against misogyny and ethnonationalism; they have organized workshops where they debate the effects of the intersections of gender, ethnicity, age at the example of migrant women. They organize educational seminars, readings and film presentations, critically addressing issues related to gender and ethnicity as their anti-racist engagement (Pajnik 2019, 250-251).

City of Women operates as a festival offering space for female artists, addressing gender inequality in larger contexts of globalization, labour, aging, etc. *Kombinat* organizes as a female choir, addressing the need for critical thought through the songs of resistance while *Z'borke* feminist choir, addresses in songs various women's and minorities' issues. The *Kombinat Female Choir* points out that they are interested in "writing the resistance tradition with red chalk. Not on walls, but on eardrums. With our voices, we keep alive the memory of the music tradition of having a spine not subject to social scoliosis." The *Z'borke Feminist Choir*, on the other hand, acts primarily "against sexism, in a non-hierarchical and anti-capitalist way", by "encouraging equality and equal opportunities for all, especially women and minorities" (Pajnik et al. 2020, 349).

Feminist Action FemA mobilized during the uprising around various topical interests, addressing political issues, such as social inequality, sustainable development, universal health care etc. *Revolting Women Social Workers* have taken the most radical approach to political activism among feminist groups (Ribač, 2018), declining institutionalism. They were recognized for organizing various gender equality guerrilla actions, also addressing issues of corruption and detachment of the elites from citizenry (Pajnik et al. 2020). *Not without women* initiative brought active participation of feminists in defending the "achievements of the welfare state and against the privatization of public education and public health-care, and a discussion and promotion of more radical issues such as the claim for a universal basic income" (Kralj & Renner, 2015, 22-23).

The movement is also active in LGBT rights. Although the legal regulation of same-sex partnerships and families has been part of the political agenda of the LGBT movement in Slovenia almost since its emergence, this debate has intensified in the last ten years. The turning points were two legislative attempts to provide equal legal protection and recognition for heterosexual and same-sex partnerships in Slovenia, which resulted in two referenda (Antić Gaber & Kuhar, 2019). Besides that, *Legebitra* works to advocate social and systemic changes based on respect for sexual orientation and gender identity, and focuses especially on LGBT rights advocacy and services for young LGTB people. It offers support services for young homosexuals, addresses HIV and health issues, offers (online) counselling, etc. Also *ŠKUC* and *ŠKUC LL (Lesbian Lilith)* advocate for LGBT rights and work to empower the LGBT community engaging in publishing, radio emissions, organizing spaces for lesbian and gay socializing etc. (Pajnik et al. 2020, 350-351). *TransAkcija*, also *Društvo Kvartir* and *Društvo Appareo* are active in transgender topics. Further, *Transakcija* focuses on supporting, informing and empowering transgender people (offering counselling to transgender people and their close ones, such as parents, support groups, etc.).

Various autonomous lesbian/queer feminist groups hold the political stance that there is no "difference among oppressions" and thus engage in protests for the homeless people, migrants, the precarious workers, the Erased etc. and try to respond to their imminent needs. *The Anarcho Queer Feminist Collective* problematizes issues of genders, sexualities and gender-based violence in the antiracist and migrant organising at Rog (Oblak & Pan, 2019). It was formed to demand and exert continuous and definite inclusion of feminist, queer, and anarchist practices into autonomous spaces (Oblak & Pan, 2019, 45). Critically addressing lesbophobia in public spaces, increasing lesbian visibility

and discussing queer theory are themes of struggle for queer-identified DJ and VJ collective *Sindikata*, *Alter Šalter* at Rog Factory squat.

The *8th March Institute* focuses predominantly but not exclusively on feminist issues (Furlan et al., 2018), it has been the main actor in the *#metoo* campaign in Slovenia (Zaviršek, 2021) and a visible actor, together with some other NGOs such as *SOS telephone line*, *Association for Nonviolent Communication* and *Amnesty International* in campaigns against gender-based violence. In addition to feminist activism, the institute has become an important political actor in the past several years and established itself as an important platform for mobilizations beyond gender-related topics. Besides their participation in various campaigns related to gender-based violence, namely *#metoo* campaign and *Only Yes means yes* campaign for redefinition of rape and sexual violence, which are discussed later in this report, they have been active in 2021 Waters Act referendum campaign (Vrabec, 2021) and in 2022 they were one of the most visible actors in the referendum aimed to restore Slovenian public broadcaster's independence (STA, 2022).

6.6 Repertoire of action

During the uprisings in 2012 and 2013, feminist and LGBT activism was marked by the strategies that were employed on the streets, for example direct actions at the protests aimed at increasing public visibility of movement's claims, and various workshops that aimed to empower and connect the actors. Research by Pajnik et al. (2000, 352) has mapped some actions during the uprising, focusing on the *Revolting Women Social Workers* who in the time of the first uprising in November 2012, directed their actions against corruption, the political and economic elites and the worsening of the position of women in Slovenia. Among the more high-profile interventions in this period were, for example, the throwing of bloody tampons at the Mayor of Ljubljana during the 2013 Pride Parade and the creation of the graffiti "Vulva to you!" on the walls of the Faculty of Social Work in Ljubljana. During another action, they threw a few thousand flyers carrying messages such as "Unconditional right to housing, free kindergartens, education, fundamental social security – it will take all this for women to be actually equal in all areas" from the Ljubljana Skyscraper. During the local elections, they addressed representative democracy critically ("nobody represents us"), they conducted campaigns "against capital" ("hang the banks"), they addressed the problem of restricting movement, closing the borders and shutting people up in psychiatric institutions critically and they advocated anti-psychiatry and radical social work ("set madness free", "we will break all the doors") (ibid.). "Feminism to the streets – March against sexism!" was another of the slogans inviting people to join a feminist march, via Facebook, posters and other communication means, where the *Revolting Women Social Workers* played a visible role: The march critically addressed sexism as sustaining men on privileged positions pushing women towards less esteemed work in precarious positions. Further, it criticized church ideology for reducing women to the role of career of the family etc. (Pajnik 2019, 259-260). Oblak & Pan (2019, 44) note that the mass uprisings radicalised few initiatives, triggered feminist protests anew, such as the *Reclaim the Night! Rally* in 2014 (Oblak & Pan, 2019, 44) demanding that women should be able to move throughout public spaces at night.

Among the visible differences between movements in their repertoires of action is that some use institutional means for struggle while others organize protest actions, workshops, events, screenings etc. The difference also lies in relation to whether the struggle is "legal" or it breaches officially defined borders of legality/illegality in action. If, for example, *Legebitra* that operates as an NGO, and its ally the Central and Eastern European Network for Gender Issues use recognized legal means of struggle, the *Red Dawns* and the *Revolting Women Social Workers* engage in various guerrilla-like actions where the aim is to point to injustices and make authorities accountable for their actions (Pajnik 2019, 258-259). The differences of various protest groups in Slovenia in the spirit of the uprising period have been confirmed by Ribač (2016, 38, 40) who found that while certain feminist groups understand their own

work as a needed pressure on the political decision-making (*Feminist action FemA*), others (*Revolting Women Social Workers*) express scepticism towards direct engagement in policy making. On the other hand, as a young, activist organisation, *Iskra* has focused on countering right-wing populist movements at the grass-roots level in the form of various counter-appearances in cases where right-wing populist movements have taken to the streets. For example, *Iskra* formed a “visible section of the general leftist pro-refugee protest alliance – most notably, there was an anti-refugee protest organized in Ljubljana in January 2016, and in response, a counter-protest, which ultimately surpassed the original protest in numbers. Another example is that of counter protests to (smaller) anti-abortion actions in front of the abortion clinic” (Furlan et al., 2018, 49).

Oblak & Pan (2019, 48-50) differentiate identity movements from the autonomous groups arguing that the latter aim to “involve diversity and community and seek pleasure in collaboration, actions, and self-organisation away from institutions. In other words, they tend to unite on the basis of political affinities and a radical critique of systemic inequalities and assimilation”. They demarcate and criticise identity politics-based activism of mainstream LGBT groups, “especially those that remain relatively distant from the more general positioning within the anti-capitalist, anti-racist, and anti-fascist struggles” (ibid., 50). Autonomous groups are critical towards NGO-ization of feminist movements as is “leads to a de-politicisation of activist groups”, (ibid., 48) while autonomous feminist groups respond to the most accurate social happenings by organising ad hoc actions according to urgent needs. One example of an ad hoc action is the case of *Anarcho Queer Feminist Collective* which painted Rog Factory squat with anti-sexist and anti-violence graffiti, zines, posters, and actively convened and participated in meetings in Rog assemblies in order to open the debate on violence against women, lesbians, trans and queer persons in autonomous spaces. “The fact that the collective demands a response to violence against women and its prevention from the whole Rog community reveals a new feature of the Slovene squatted spaces” (Oblak & Pan, 2019, 46). They established themselves as political subjects through graffiti that aimed at creating a space that does not support sexism, sexual and other forms of violence, homophobia and transphobia (Avtonomne feministke, 2017). Furthermore, Oblak & Pan (2019) critically argue that autonomous groups do not follow any annual plans or strategies and do not immerse themselves only in short-term projects. Anarchist tradition additionally influences autonomous feminist activities, their practices of self-organisation and strategies such as practices of self-organisation, transnational networking, alternative economy, and squatting (ibid., 49).

Some of the literature, in contrast, points to the positive effects of the institutionalized initiatives such as #metoo campaign in Slovenia in 2018 which was carried out by the *8th March Institute*. The campaign took a form of stories that were published on the dedicated website, and has gained a lot of media attention, including appearances on different radio programmes and publication of several articles in the public media with “highly suggestive titles, e.g. ‘Stories not bouquets!’, alluding to the communist-era habit of men gifting bouquets to women on International Women’s Day” (Zaviršek, 2021, 206). In addition the *8th March Institute* held public readings of the stories with an aim of awareness raising and recognition of the victimised (ibid., 217).

The literature also shows that visual and performing arts are an important part of operation of (autonomous) feminist actors in Slovenia, from festivals and performances to lectures and film screenings. There are two feminist festivals in Ljubljana dedicated to the promotion of engaged women artists, activists and researchers: the international festival of contemporary arts *City of Women* and the international feminist and queer festival *Red Dawns. Deuje babe* festival, which aimed at presenting women’s activism in Cerkno (small Slovenian town with 1.500 inhabitants) was first organized in 2013 with local and international support by volunteers, members of the *Cerkljan Youth Alternative Club* (Cerkljanski mladinski alternativni klub CMAK), and was the first festival of its kind in the Slovenian periphery. Events were also organized that focused specifically on LGBT topics, such as *Gay and Lesbian Film Festival* (Gejevski in lezbični filmski festival) which was first held within the

Lesbian Film Week (Lezbični filmski teden) in Ljubljana's *ŠKUC Gallery* in 1988. This was followed by *Lesbian Quarter* festival which focuses on lesbian art and was first organized in 2012 by *ŠKUC LL* section (Hvala, 2015, 54). After an era of sporadic lesbian art festivals and events, the *Lesbian Quarter* represents a community project that binds the lesbian community and builds on the existing activities of the community, e.g. *Lezbnik*, a daily newspaper that reviews and documents lesbian events and promotes the development of lesbian art criticism; *Lesbo* magazine and *Lezbomanija* radio programme (Sukič, 2012). Some of the lesbian-queer collectives, for example the *Insurrection of Lezbos*, worked through guerrilla street actions, with activists using video production and street performance as a means of expression (Ribač, 2018, 77).

Strategies of the relatively newly emerging transgender movement mainly relate to the mobilization within various group gatherings such as *TransMisija*, a yearly meeting that addresses transgender issues and provides a platform for various transgender human rights stakeholders to come together, as well as forming external (transnational) alliances in order to gain visibility of the trans movement. The first *Trans March* took place in the Autumn of 2018 in which the protesters passed by the Ministry of Interior and the Ministry of Health where they demanded a change of policies that address transgender people, namely legal gender recognition and transition (Gramc, 2022, 136).

Research by Pajnik et al. (2020, 355, 357) analysed contemporary feminist movements' operating online, focusing to analyse their "electronic repertoires of contention". Network analysis of Web and Facebook links looked into the type of actors movements engage with online, how movements are interconnected, and how they relate to specific type of actors. Interestingly, the results of the analysis have shown an absence of links to political and governmental actors, which confirms that the contemporary movements relate their agenda intensively to their own causes, not necessarily reacting to the whereabouts of the political elite (ibid.). The authors argued that this reflects the rhizomatic, "prefigurative" character of the analysed movements. The data show that the online links to actors visibly tend to indicate a particular movement's specific field of interest: for example, the web-portal *Spol.si* has published many links to libraries and publishing houses, while the *City of Women* is most intensively connected with visual and performing arts. Thus, the authors argued that networking strategies largely align with the strategic orientation of a specific movement. Similarly, the *Legebitra* is strongly characterized by links to the actors/organizations that provide direct support to the members of the feminist/LGBT community (e.g., counselling, psychotherapy, information/consultation on sexually transmitted diseases etc.). *Revolting Women Social Workers* link to various initiatives, including feminist, LGBT/queer, ecological and socio-economic initiatives (such as *Danes je nov dan*, *Jebezasas*, *Lezbična četrt*, *Zadružništvo*, *Izmenjevalnica*, or *Svetovna kuhna*). This indicates a broad field of action and the extension of the understanding and the functioning of feminism and the feminist movement beyond the immediate thematization of gender and sexual inequality, confirming the analysis of della Porta (2015), who pointed to the trans-thematic consciousness developing within anti-austerity movements (Pajnik et al. 2020, 359-360).

6.7 Frames of arguments

The research (Pajnik et al. 2020) that has compared the newer feminist and LGBT movements in Slovenia found that the movements devise a distinct understanding of democracy: democracy is not merely a series of institutions, certain constitutional regimes, economic models and the rule of law, but rather an institution of politics itself. It is not merely about affirming new rights and equality, but also about emphasizing and acknowledging differences, which is why these groups are characterized by a pluralism of social composition and a pluralism of ideological orientation (ibid, 362). Based on focus group discussions with various protagonists of feminist movements, actors and initiatives in Slovenia (conducted in fall 2014) Pajnik (2019) found that the movements are critical of the contemporary state of democracy. On the notion of democracy, a member of *Kombinat* reflected that

what we currently experience in Slovenia is “the abuse of democracy”. She refers to corruption, corrupt politicians and the economic elite who should be stopped, fought against collectively for a kind of catharsis and “a renewal of democracy.” An activist from the *Revolt Women Social Workers* in her narrative focuses on “alternative” conceptualizations of democracy; she relates democracy with her experiences in the movement in Slovenia “where there were a lot of experiments with decision-making, with the ways of being together, and I thought this was essential for democracy” (ibid.).

Pajnik (2019, 257-259) observed that the various actors are quite “orchestrated” in their critical reflections of racism. Several actors relate racism to a plethora of discrimination and inequalities we face in societies, locally and globally. For example, a representative of *Legebitra* says that claiming that the only true family is a union of a mother and a father who live with their children, stressing heteronormativity as a norm and insisting this is the only genuine norm, is racism. Also in terms of cultural differences, sexual orientation and identity: claiming that one culture or one sexual orientation is the ultimate one is racism. An interviewee from the *Red Dawns* stresses the problem that racism, ethnonationalism and other “tactics of othering and exclusion” have become normalized in our societies; they have become the discourses that are omnipresent and “it becomes scary when you see what you actually fight”. Several interviewees are in agreement that lately most targeted groups of othering have been the poor, especially poor women, poor migrant women, and single people (ibid.).

Frames of arguments that specific movements adopt reflect the ideological *credo* of defined actors. *Iskra* for example generally insists on asserting a class-based perspective in approaching student politics. A noticeable segment of *Iskra*'s activities is explicitly feminist oriented with feminist interventions having a strong materialist, anti-capitalist, class conscious bent (Furlan et al., 2018, 48). Furlan et al. (2018) note that the division between identity based, referred to as “feminist”, and class-based discourses is to some extent a persistent subject in their internal debate. While the feminist section agrees that gender issues are to be approached from a class perspective, there are still theoretical debates over “how identity is to be understood”. *Iskra* does not often seem to venture into topics dealing with other forms of identity, except for occasional contributions on refugee issues (ibid., 49).

The literature explains the feminist political movement cultures and their relationship toward queer theory quite extensively. Elaborated usage of queer theory by feminist actors is provided by Hvala (2012). The term “queer” in Ljubljana LGBT community “represents a neoconservative politics of privacy, rather than a progressive or confrontational politics of visibility” (ibid., 190), which is why a part of the LGBT community suggests the necessity of disassociating LGBT politics from the queer paradigm. Hvala (2012, 191) argues that one of the reasons why queer theory is not welcomed among local lesbian theorists is related to its “claim that neoliberalism, patriarchy and heteronormativity affect homosexuals and heterosexuals alike”. It is argued that queer theory's relational standpoint creates discomfort because it suggests that one's “gender identity is only partly defined by one's sexual preferences, and that the latter only partly affects one's political preferences” (Hvala, 2012, 191).

Gramc (2022) theorizes the conditions that enabled trans activism in Slovenia through queer of colour critique which provides tools to unravel how race and ethnicity intersect with gender and class within the Slovenian trans movement. “Ethnicity and race are only seemingly invisible in trans activism while intersecting axes of class and gender are more visible. This is because the distancing of Slovenia from the Yugoslav space and insisting on being European relies on the unspoken Whiteness of the Slovenian nation-state project whose ideology the Slovenian transgender movement silently adopted” (Gramc, 2022, 151).

In the studies (Zaviršek, 2020, 2021) the emergence of the *#metoo* campaign is described in the context of increasing sexual and gender-based violence as a consequence of the rising of dominant traditionalism. Especially in the post-socialist countries, Zaviršek (2021, 344-345) argues, femininity was created along the lines of traditionalism. Patriarchal gender inequalities are on the rise due to the fact that “men lost their traditional role of breadwinners and strove to restore their dominant positions” (Zaviršek, 2020, 202). *#metoo* campaign aims to show how capitalist society directly contributes to the oppression of women (Kovač, 2019), and defines gender-based sexual violence as a historically a patriarchal strategy used to control women (Zaviršek, 2020). Researchers (Kovač, 2019) have argued that the *#metoo* movement has successfully revealed the very essence of the structure and functioning of patriarchy and all inequalities and antagonisms that it supports, allows and normalizes.

It generally stems from the literature that frames of arguments that are developed by a particular actor or movement pertain to their ideological orientation. For example, activists from autonomous groups reflect on meanings of democracy differently if compared to feminist NGO representatives. Not surprisingly, the actors who associate with *#metoo* campaign stem from a critical reflection of patriarchy and traditional gender roles, queer activists in particular affirm queer theory while actors who focus to critically address neoliberalism interrelate feminist and gender struggle with class issues (Pajnik et al. 2020, Zaviršek 2020, Hvala 2012, Furlan et al. 2018). In general, the literature doesn't reflect systematically the five thematic areas that are of interest to FIERCE. LGBT rights and gender-based violence / patriarchy are discussed while there is a void in the analysis that would look more closely into feminist actor's framings of labour market, migration and health and reproductive rights. One of the reasons for the lack of thematization of abortion and reproductive rights in the literature is that these issues did not experience strong feminist mobilization in Slovenia after 1991, with the exception of sporadic smaller actions of feminist initiatives that emerged in response to anti-gender actions (e.g. counter-protests against anti-abortion actions in front of the gynaecological clinic in Ljubljana). Reproductive rights were addressed by the feminist movement in the 2000s in the context of the referendum on the single women's right to vitro fertilization in 2001, while they are much less present in the contemporary mobilization.

6.8 Campaigns and debates

In the literature, sporadic references are made to the emergence of individual campaigns, actions, and debates of feminist movements. Apart from diverse repertoires of action already described in the previous chapters of this report, the literature explicitly analyses two campaigns of feminist mobilization in the period 2010-2022 (Krašovec, 2015; Podolak, 2019; Zaviršek, 2020, 2021).

As mentioned earlier in this report, feminist movement was triggered by two referenda (2012 and 2015) on same-sex marriage that attempted to propose legal amendments which would provide equal legal protection for same-sex partnerships in Slovenia. The center-left government took over in 2008 and already in 2009 it announced the reform of the Family Code (2017), which assumed full equality of all citizens on family matters, including adoption (Podolak, 2019, 49). Strong anti-gender coalition was mobilised at the time, consisting of already established networks of Roman Catholic Church and right-wing political parties. The so called *Civil Initiative for the Family and the Rights of Children* (Civilna iniciativa za družino in pravice otrok), founded in 2009 by Aleš Primc, successfully carried out a campaign and collected the required 40.000 signatures to question the adopted law in a referendum, which took place in 2012 (Kuhar, 2015; Podolak, 2019). The portrayal of homosexuality as a threat was the central focus of their discourse (Kuhar, 2015).

Another attempt to provide marriage equality began in December 2014, when the United Left presented a draft amendment to the Marriage and Family Relations Act (1976), which introduced the redefinition of marriage from a union of a man and a woman to a union of two persons. Although technically a minor change, it caused great discontent among parts of the public and representatives of conservative parties, which led opponents to begin collecting signatures to demand a referendum. New civil initiative *Children are at Stake* (Za otroke gre) was formed, run by the same actors as *Civil Initiative for the Family and the Rights of Children* (Kuhar, 2015). What followed is the Constitutional Court disagreement with the decision of the National Assembly that rejected the referendum application, citing amendments to the Constitution of prohibiting referenda on matters regarding unconstitutional circumstances. It ruled that a referendum can be held in this matter (Podolak, 2019, 51-52). The campaign was more intense in 2015 if compared to the one in 2012. Thirty-nine parties, associations, movements and people joined the campaign. Two positions were clearly evident: the camp against the amendments, which was based primarily on appeals to secure the rights of children and the future of families. On the other hand, the *It's time for Yes* group called for "the right of the child to be adopted in the most appropriate environment" and "to extend these rights to all" (ibid., 52), and was joined by some feminist organizations (among other NGOs). During the campaign, both camps also received international support; the *It's time for Yes* camp was supported by the NGO Human Rights Watch, which joined the large movement of Slovenian human rights NGOs calling for marriage equality (Podolak, 2019; Krašovec, 2015).

In both referenda, we observed a confrontational relationship between feminist and anti-gender actors. The activities of the anti-gender movement in connection with the two referenda prompted LGBT activists, feminists, and some politicians to join forces and oppose the increasingly successful and influential anti-gender movement in Slovenia. While they have succeeded in discrediting some of the anti-gender movement's claims, they have generally failed to effectively counter its populist rhetoric.

One of the recent feminist movement campaigns that gained quite extensive public attention is the case of *#metoo* campaign that was initiated by four women public intellectuals (Zaviršek, 2020, 2021). The *8th March Institute* took over the managing of the website where the stories were published. From February 2018 to January 2020, over 200 testimonies were submitted mostly by women, and published at the website. Although the campaign was global in scale, the Slovenian version had its own local peculiarities compared to its counterpart in most Western countries (Zaviršek, 2020, 2021). For example, in most Western countries, the women who initiated the *#metoo* campaign were public figures celebrities, actresses, etc. testifying against famous, rich and powerful men in order to reveal "a pattern of predatory behaviour" (Zaviršek, 2020, 344). In Slovenia, the *#metoo* campaign presented itself differently: while women were willing to talk, they largely insisted on anonymity, and were far from taking legal actions against perpetrators. Another important feature of the Slovenian *#metoo* stories was that the women focused on sexual violence, sometimes with severe physical health consequences, not only on sexual harassment (ibid., 354).

Later on the *#metoo* campaign caused multiplying effect and "contributed to the launching of new online and media-supported discussions about sexual violence, notably by Catholic priests, and the painful and demeaning treatment that women encounter in different health institutions" (Zaviršek, 2021, 199). In an online forum *Parental Chat* (Starševski čvek) women began to express their experiences during childbirth which was triggered by the events in neighbouring Croatia, namely the *#BreakTheSilence* (*#PrekinimoŠutnju*) campaign. "Women described the humiliation they suffered in the hands of midwives, nurses and doctors during child birth" (Zaviršek, 2021, 219). In early 2019 another campaign occurred (presumably triggered by the *#metoo* campaign). A group of Catholic priests, some of whom were victims of childhood abuse by the priests themselves, launched a campaign called *It is enough!* (Dovolj je!). Similar to the *#metoo* campaign, they began collecting stories from survivors and posting them on a website (ibid.).

Another societal consequence of #metoo in Slovenia was enacted in the mobilization of different groups and organizations to fight further and combat sexual violence and re-traumatization of the victims. One of the most famous events, for example, was a court decision in the Slovenian coastal region that gave a lenient sentence to a rapist who had raped a woman in her sleep. A rapid response was built up by the women's organisations working in the area of violence against women, the initiators of the #metoo campaign, and *Amnesty International*. They demanded that the Ministry of Justice implement the Council of Europe's Istanbul Convention and amend the Criminal Code of the Republic of Slovenia in accordance to the "yes means yes" model. The main argument of the campaign was that sexuality "demands consent from all parties involved and a mutual understanding of what is meant by sexuality, desire and emotions" (Zaviršek, 2021, 220).

In general we can observe that the literature discusses mobilization of feminist actors and their campaigns addressing various pertinent feminist and larger social issues, such as equality of same-sex partnership, sexual harassment etc. The literature only assesses some campaigns and we have observed a lack of a systematic analysis that would assess campaigns in a comparative trans-movement perspective.

6.9 Key policy related outcomes

The literature is relatively limited in analysing how the issues, frames of argument, repertoires of action and campaigns of feminist movements influence models of democracy or show how state institutions do or do not take on board the stimuli of feminist mobilization. Hvala (2011) critically argues that feminism had disappeared from the public sphere with the closure of the *Autonomous Women's Centre* at Metelkova, when feminist initiatives from the 1980s "dispersed" into NGOs. The effects of feminist political initiatives are often poor "due to their rare and provisional nature" (Hvala, 2010a, 31). Collaborations among academic, nongovernmental, and grass-root groups exist, but they are very fragile and arise only in response to specific instances of discrimination or hatred, and usually dissolve when the immediate threat has passed (ibid.). The network analysis of contemporary feminist movements' operating online (Pajnik et al., 2020, 355, 357) has also revealed the absence of links between movements' actors and political and governmental actors, showing that contemporary movements intensely relate their agendas to their own concerns and do not necessarily respond to the whereabouts of the political elite and policies (ibid.).

Furthermore, with regard to the campaigns described in the previous chapter, the literature addresses a few major challenges with regard to policy-making. Zaviršek (2020) notes that campaigns against sexual violence were seen as women's attacks on "traditional" masculinity. Her analysis of the #metoo campaign confirms the unified discourse on "dangerous witch-hunt feminism" prevalent in the Slovenian media, with the #metoo campaign understood as its latest manifestation (Zaviršek, 2021, 201). The analysis of different types of dailies, weeklies and online media in Slovenia showed that liberal and social-democratic media (e.g. *Delo*, *Dnevnik*, *Večer*, *Mladina*) supported the #metoo campaign, while media which address a rather conservative readership (e.g. *Slovenske novice*) were partially supportive but mostly covered the international media events of the #metoo. Media owned by the right-wing political parties (e.g. online *Nova24TV*, weekly *Demokracija*) ignored or rejected the #metoo campaign, thus it was seen in these media as another product of feminist radicalism. "Some responses explicitly emphasised how the #metoo campaign intimidates and victimises men and promotes false political correctness" (Zaviršek, 2021, 2018).

Despite this, the *#metoo* movement in Slovenia managed to mobilise different organizations into the alliance that advocated for the redefinition of rape and sexual violence in line to “yes means yes” model. The campaign, led by a strong NGO initiative, was successful; in 2021, the Ministry of Justice adopted an amendment to the Criminal Code (2008) redefining rape and sexual violence to focus on consent rather than violence (STA, 2021).

The second cluster of analysis dealt with the question of whether the referendum results indicate a shift in the Slovenian political arena. It seems that in the case of the referenda the anti-gender campaign was strategically very well prepared and implemented. Moreover, it managed to mobilise right-wing political parties and Roman Catholic Church that were able to engage the wide networks of supporters already in place (Kuhar, 2015); namely, this camp convinced the public with arguments based on “gender theory”. On the other hand, Antić Gaber & Kuhar (2019) observe that during the first referendum campaign in 2012, the LGBT community used rational, often scientific language to respond to the reservations and fears that opponents of the amendments raised. During the campaign in the second referendum in 2015 it changed its discursive tactics. This brought to the fore a more emotionally tinged language. Neither the first nor the second strategy was successful, not least because the LGBT community lacked a political base and a clear political support (ibid., 111). This resulted in both referenda on same-sex partnerships were rejected. The Family Code in 2012 was rejected with over 30 percent and just short of 55 percent of participating citizens were in favour of rejecting the new law. In the 2015 referendum, after a very fierce and often intolerant campaign, 63.5% of voters rejected the proposed amendment to the law (Podolak, 2019).

6.10 Conclusion

The report examined the existing academic and expert literature on feminist movement in Slovenia, published between 2010 and 2022. Twenty-two studies were selected for further analysis, characterised by dispersive and fragmentary coverage of the topic. Autonomous LGBT and queer feminist organizing, closely related to the practices of squatting and feminist struggles over public spaces, was found to be one of the most researched topics in the analysed period. In addition to occupying spaces, feminist initiatives were also united by collective action and triggered by various societal events (e.g. the Slovenian uprising period). On the other hand, we identified a visible body of literature dealing with specific sporadic feminist campaigns in the field of LGBT rights and gender-based violence. Besides independent feminist mobilizations, some of the literature addresses institutionalized forms of feminist action, focusing on the historical moment of the establishment of women's politics. More recent studies are emerging with a focus on transgender issues and the development of transgender movement.

One of the main characteristics of the feminist mobilizations that developed after 2010 noted in the literature review is the diffuse and plural character of the movement and expansion of its themes and agendas, which precedes the gender framework and/or links this frame to precarity, anti-capitalism, anti-authoritarianism, autonomy and autonomous spaces, protecting queer spaces and queerness, advocating LGBT rights and combating sexual and gender-based violence. A large proportion of feminist and LGBT movements in the period 2010-2022 stems from autonomous spaces, such as Rog and Metelkova in Ljubljana. Although initiatives from the past have strongly influenced the contemporary feminist movements in Slovenia, feminist mobilizations also emerged through ad hoc collective actions in response to broader socio-political events. In addition, queer activism formed within the LGBT movement, but was met with rejection by large segments of the LGBT community, according to the literature. In 2014-2015, transgender movement began to gain public visibility.

As for the actors, the literature reveals a wide variety of sporadic groups operating in different fields and using different forms of action and organization. While Ljubljana has encountered a series of autonomous (queer) feminist initiatives that have mostly grown in squats, other independent feminist initiatives have emerged outside these spaces. Other feminist-oriented initiatives that have emerged in recent years consist of a variety of smaller organizations, including NGOs. Marginalized issues such as the status of transgender persons have recently influenced the feminist agenda and led to the establishment of various actors within the transgender movement.

With regard to alliances, they are formed nationally and transnationally at different levels. Actors and organizations mainly link with similar initiatives that share a common goal regarding specific feminist issues. The literature review also shows the differences in strategies and practices in building alliances between different actors. Besides forming networks with their sympathizers, some also ally with established institutions aiming at institutional change, while other groups define their activity beyond or against institutionalism. Moreover, the literature describes examples of differentiation within movements, namely the LGBT, queer and transgender movement, which hinders the formation of “internal” alliances between actors.

The predominant strategies of the feminist movement consist of a diverse repertoire of actions, ranging from street encounters, protests, workshops, events, etc. An important part of operation of (autonomous) feminist actors is the visual and performing arts. Autonomous initiatives use different strategies that, unlike NGO actors, enable to respond to the most acute social problems by organising ad hoc actions according to urgent needs. However, some campaigns and initiatives, led by a strong NGO initiative, have also been very successful (e.g., *#metoo* and the *Only Yes Means Yes* campaign). It is common that the arguments used by a particular actor reflect its ideological framework of operation. In general, the literature does not systematically reflect the five issues of interest to FIERCE. LGBT rights, gender violence and patriarchy are addressed, while the analyses of feminist actors’ framing of the labour market, health and reproductive rights, and migration has not appeared in the literature.

We can observe the lack of influence of the feminist agenda on decision-making processes in Slovenia, which goes hand in hand with the relatively fragile and temporary nature of certain initiatives, which only emerge in response to specific events and usually dissolve when the immediate threat is over. This is also due to the fact that the movement maintains relatively poor connections with political and state actors. However, some recent initiatives have succeeded in justifying the feminist movement’s role in challenging, improving, or renewing democratic models, particularly in attempts to redefine rape and sexual violence.

In the course of the literature review, we identified some blind spots that can provide productive lines of inquiry in the future. One such blind spot is the lack of a comprehensive approach to the research of contemporary feminist movements. The publications included in the literature review treat the field in a rather fragmentary manner, focusing on specific areas of feminist activism or on specific actions and campaigns, lacking to tackle the diversity of actors and forms of action and organisation. The new feminist initiatives and actors that have emerged in recent years are an under-researched topic. We could observe that some literature discusses the functioning of feminist publics from the perspective of the people who actually create them.

In terms of addressing specific issue areas, LGBT rights and gender-based violence are relatively well-covered topics in the academic and professional literature. However, as we have shown in this report, feminist mobilizations on other relevant topics such as the labour market, health and reproductive rights, and migration are not addressed in the literature. In the context of rising conservatism, the role of feminist movements in revitalising democratic practises built on concrete alternatives and inclusive visions for the future of democracy should be explored further

6.11 List of feminist movements' campaigns in Slovenia

Name of the campaign (original)	Name of the campaign (English)	Issue(s) addressed	Actors involved	Repertoire of action	Logo of the campaign	Web-page	Comment
Samo ja pomeni ja	Only Yes Means Yes	Gender-based violence, sexual violence, sexual assault, rape, women's autonomy over their own bodies, protection of women in the legal system	Associations , NGOs (Institute 8 March, Association for Nonviolent Communication, SOS telephone line for women and children, PIC, Amnesty International Slovenia)	Public demonstrations and protests, proposal to redefine the law		Web: https://www.8marec.si/samo-ja-pomeni-ja/	The campaign produced a redefinition of the law on rape and sexual assault, redefining the perception of consent
#jztudi	#MeToo	Gender-based violence, sexual violence, sexual assault, rape	Movements, NGOs, antiviolence centers (Institute 8 march), academics (Darja Zaviršek,	Collecting and publishing anonymous or signed testimonies about sexual violence		Web: https://www.jztudi.si/	After the campaign #MeToo launched in the USA, a similar campaign under the hashtag

			Renata Šribar and Irena Šumi)	against women, analyzing and placing them in a wider social context, offering information and guidance to help victims of sexual violence			#jztudi was launched in Slovenia to raise awareness of the magnitude of sexual violence against women
#NisemPrijavila	#IDidntReport	Gender-based violence, intimate partner violence, femicide	Associations, NGOs (Institute 8 March)	Collecting and publishing personal testimonies of intimate partner violence, analyzing and placing them in a wider social context	#nisemprijav	Web: https://www.8marec.si/nisemprijavila/	After the hashtag campaign #NisamPrijavila launched by Serbian activist Nina Stojaković, a similar campaign under the hashtag #NisemPrijavila was launched in Slovenia to highlight the prevalence and

							normalization of intimate partner violence in society
Koraki za odpravo nasilja nad ženskami	Steps to end violence against women	Gender-based violence., violence against women, intimate partner violence	Associations , NGOs, antiviolence centers (Amnesty International Slovenia, Association for Nonviolent Communication, SOS telephone line for women and children), agency (Avanta Largo)	Awareness campaign on steps to eliminate violence against women, offering information and advice to help victims of violence		Web: https://www.amnesty.si/poz-21-koraki-za-odpravo-nasilja-nad-zenskami	Awareness campaign on steps to eliminate violence against women conducted during the annual »Walk Along the Wire« in Ljubljana marking courage, comradeship, peace, endurance.
Čas je ZA	It's time for yes	LGBTQ+ rights, same-sex marriage, marriage equality	Associations , NGOs (Amnesty International Slovenia, the Peace Institute, Slovenian	Proposed bill on same-sex marriage, Public debates, public events,		Fb: https://www.facebook.com/casjeZA/	The campaign was a proponent of the proposed bill on same-sex marriage in 2015. Despite the big

			Philanthropy, Journal of Criticism of Science, CAAP, Danes je nov dan, ŠKUC, Legebitra, DIH Association), political parties (the United Left, the Social Democrats, the Pirate Party of Slovenia, Solidarity, the TRS Party and the Initiative for Democratic Socialism)	cultural events			effort and scale of the campaign, the proposed bill on same-sex marriage was rejected in 2015 by the voters on the referendum.
Za vse družine	For All the Families	LGBTQ+ rights, marriage equality, children's rights	Associations, NGOs, and civil society initiatives (Amnesty International Slovenia, DIH,	Proposed bill on equality of all forms of families, roundtables, scientific research,		Fb: https://www.facebook.com/zavsedruzine/about	The campaign was a proponent of the proposed bill against discrimination of any form of family and for

			Legebitra, Pride Parade Association, Peace Institute, Rozalija, Škuc LL and Institute for the Culture of Diversity Open) and young political groups (Young Forum SD, Young Liberal Democrats, Zares Aktivni)	conversations with experts, argumentative discussions, public events			affording all forms of families the same rights in 2011. The bill was rejected in 2012 by the voters on the referendum
No Border Craft	No Border Craft	Migration, intersectionality, fighting racism and sexism	Activists, asylum seekers, migrant women with refugee status	Organizing get togethers to crochet, organizing workshops, making and selling their crochet products		Fb: https://www.facebook.com/no.border.craft.community/	No-border craft is a self-organized group/initiative of asylum seekers, migrant women with refugee status and activists who "community

							crochet and socialize without borders". The essential goal of the group is to build a social network between local residents and migrant women and to strive to strengthen the power and assert the knowledge, experience and courage of migrant women and to fight sexism, racism and closed borders.
#PrekinimoTišino	#BreakTheSilence	Health and reproductive rights, pregnancy, childbirth, malpractice, violence	Associations, NGOs (PINARD-Institute for the Development of Family-Centred	Collecting and publishing testimonies of maltreatment and violence		Fb: https://www.facebook.com/hashtag/prekinimoti%C5%A1ino	In 2018, the campaign #PrekinimoTišino (#PrekinimoŠu tnju) spread from Croatia to Slovenia. In

			Care, Institute 8 March)	during childbirth, public events			the testimonies they shared, women spoke publicly about inappropriate treatment and violence during childbirth.
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6.12 References:

Antić Gaber, M. & Kuhar, R. (2019). Identitetna gibanja in politike spola in seksualnosti v Sloveniji (Identity Movements and the Politics of Gender and Sexuality in Slovenia). In: R. Kuhar (Ed.), *Identitete na presečišču kriz* (Identities at the Intersection of Crises) (101–122). Ljubljana: Ljubljana University Press, Faculty of Arts.

Avtonomne feministke (2017). Zakaj si tako kisl, Limona? O kvirovskih in feminističnih zagatah v Rogu (Why so Sour, Lemon? On Queer and Feminist Troubles in Rog). *Časopis za kritiko znanosti*, 270(45), 135-150.

Furlan, S., Slukan, N. & Hergouth, M. (2018). *Mapping Left Actors: Slovenia*. Belgrade: Rosa Luxemburg Stiftung Southeast Europe.

Gramc, M. (2022). Tortuous paths towards trans futures: The trans movement in Slovenia. In: B. Bilić, I. Nord & A. Milanović (Eds.), *Transgender in the Post-Yugoslav Space: Lives, Activisms, Culture* (133–154). Bristol: Policy Press.

Hvala, T. (2010a). The Red Dawns Festival as a Feminist-Queer Counterpublic. *Monitor ISH*, 12(1), 7-107.

Hvala, T. (2010b). *Rdečke razsajajo! Intervjuji z organizatorkami feminističnega in kvirovskega festivala Rdeče zore* (The “Reds” are on the March! Interviews with the Organisers of the Feminist and Queer Festival Red Dawns). Ljubljana: KUD Mreža.

Hvala, T. (2011). Seksizem in homofobija »kot po navadi«, feminizem »drugače«: AKC Metelkova mesto v očeh organizatork festivala Rdeče zore (Sexism and Homophobia “as usual”, Feminism “differently”: the AKC Metelkova mesto from the Perspective of the Organisers of Red Dawns). *Borec*, LXIII / 2011, 681-684.

Hvala, T. (2012). Queer trouble in Ljubljana. In S. Mesquita (Ed.), *Import, export, transport: Queer theory, queer critique and activism in motion* (179–193). Vienna: Zaglossus.

Hvala, T. (2015). Temporary venues of persistent hope: City of women and Red Dawns. *Časopis za kritiko znanosti*, 43(261), 51–62.

Kovač, N. (2019). *#MeToo Sexual Harrassment through the Prism of Neoliberalism*. Transform! Europe EUPF. Available at: https://www.transform-network.net/fileadmin/user_upload/sl_publication_metroo_final.pdf.

Kralj, A. & Renner, T. (2015). Slovenia - from "state feminism" to back vocals. In: C. M. Hassenstab & S. P. Ramet (Eds.), *Gender (In)equality and Gender Politics in Southeastern Europe: A Question of Justice* (41-61). London: Palgrave Macmillan.

Krašovec, A. (2015). The 2015 Referendum in Slovenia. *East European Quarterly*, 43(4), 303-312.

Oblak, T. & Pan, M. (2019). Yearning for Space, Pleasure, and Knowledge: Autonomous Lesbian and Queer Feminist Organising in Ljubljana. In: B. Bilić & M. Radoman (Eds.), *Lesbian Activism in the (Post)Yugoslav Space Sisterhood and Unity* (27-60). Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.

Pajnik, M. (2019). Feminist Movements' Acts of Citizenship: Experiences from Post-Socialist Slovenia. In: B. Siim, A. Krasteva & A. Saarinen (Eds.), *Citizens' Activism and Solidarity Movements* (243-263). Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.

Pajnik, M., Vodovnik, Ž., Humer, Ž., & Mance, B. (2020). The Shape of Feminism to Come, The Networked Politics of Feminist and LGBT Movements in Slovenia. *Southeastern Europe*, 44(3), 343-365. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30965/18763332-44030001>.

Podolak, M. (2019). Rights of Sexual Minorities as the Subject of Referenda in the Republic of Slovenia. *Białostockie Studia Prawnicze*, 24(1), 45-56.

Ribač, M. (2016). Dinamika in duh vstajništva – Klasifikacija in nasprotja med protestnimi skupinami v Sloveniji (The Dynamic and Spirit of Uprisings – Classification and Differences of Various Protest Groups in Slovenia). *Družboslovne razprave*, XXXII (82), 33-49.

Ribač, M. (2018). *Vznik javnosti v času množičnih protestov v Sloveniji leta 2012 in 2013* (Rise of the Public amid Protests in Slovenia in years 2012 and 2013) (Doktorska disertacija, Fakulteta za družbene vede). Available at: <https://repositorij.uni-lj.si/lzpisGradiva.php?id=105752&lang=slv>.

Sukič, N. (2012). Lezbična četrt (Lesbian Quarter). *Lesbo*, 23.

Velikonja, N. (2013). Gejevska in lezbična scena na Metelkovi (The Gay and Lesbian Scene at Metelkova). *Časopis za kritiko znanosti*, 41(253), 60-69.

Zaviršek, D. (2020). 'This is not a Story which would Shock!': The #MeToo Campaign in Slovenia. *The Journal of Social Policy Studies*, 18(2), 343-356. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17323/727-0634-2020-18-2-343-356>.

Zaviršek, D. (2021), 'Stories Not Bouquets!': The #Metoo campaign in Slovenia and Its Social Consequences. In: S. Ramon, M. Lloyd & B. Penhale (Eds.), *Gendered Domestic Violence and Abuse in Popular Culture* (199-225). Bingley: Emerald Publishing Limited.

Sources:

Della Porta, D. (2015). *Social Movements in Times of Austerity: Bringing Capitalism back into Protest Analysis*. Cambridge, Malden: Polity Press.

Family code (Družinski zakonik). (2017). <http://www.pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=ZAKO7556>.

G.C. (2021, November, 29). *Portal Ona ve za boljšo zastopanost žensk v medijih in na javnih dogodkih* ("She knows" portal for better representation of women in the media and at public events). MMC RTV Slovenija. <https://www.rtvlo.si/slovenija/portal-ona-ve-za-boljso-zastopanost-zensk-v-medijih-in-na-javnih-dogodkih/603137>.

Jalušič, V. (2002). *Kako smo hodile v feministično gimnazijo* (How we Attended the Feminist Gymnasium). Ljubljana: Založba/*cf.

Kuhar, R. (2015). Konec je sveta, kakršnega poznamo: populistične strategije nasprotnikov Družinskega zakonika (It's the End of the World as we Know it: Populist Strategies of the Family Code Opponents). *Časopis za kritiko znanosti*, 43/260, 118–132.

Marriage and Family Relations Act (Zakon o zakonski zvezi in družinskih razmerjih). (1976). <http://pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=ZAKO40#>.

Criminal Code (Kazenski zakonik). (2008). <http://pisrs.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=ZAKO5050>.

Rožman, A. (2021, Marec 9). *Anketa, ki priča o spolnem nasilju na fakultetah* (Survey on sexual violence at universities). Dnevnik. <https://www.dnevnik.si/1042950751>.

STA (2001, May 3). *Referendum on Changes to Infertility Treatment Act to Be Held in June*. STA. <https://english.sta.si/561170/referendum-on-changes-to-infertility-treatment-act-to-be-held-in-june>.

STA (2021, June 30). *Veljati začena novela kazenskega zakonika z redefinicijo posilstva* (Amendment to the Criminal Code to redefine rape enters into force). STA. <https://www.sta.si/2917705/veljati-zacenja-novela-kazenskega-zakonika-z-redefinicijo-posilstva>.

STA (2022, October 21). *V referendumsko kampanjo o zakonu o RTV se aktivno vključuje tudi Inštitut 8. Marec* (The 8th of March Institute actively participates in the referendum campaign on the public broadcaster law). STA. <https://www.sta.si/3095935/v-referendumsko-kampanjo-o-zakonu-o-rtv-se-aktivno-vkljucuje-tudi-institut-8-marec>.

Verginella, M. & Selišnik, I. (2018) Vidnost in nevidnost žensk: zgodovina žensk in študije spolov v Sloveniji (Women's History and Gender Studies in Slovenia: Visibility and Invisibility of Women), *Javnost - The Public*, 25: sup1, S1-S17.

Vrabec, A. (2021, December 11). *Za čisto vodo povezali 682.760 ljudi* (Connecting 682.760 people for clean water). Delo. <https://www.delo.si/delova-osebnost-leta/za-cisto-vodo-povezali-682-760-ljudi/>.

7 SPAIN

7.1 Introduction

Most of the literature on the Spanish feminist movements has focused on the period 1960s-1980s, when feminism struggles were hand in hand with the anti-Franco struggles and for democracy. But, as Martínez (2019) notes, there is not much published on the evolution of the movements beyond the 1980s (as an exception, see: Gil, 2011). The study of institutional feminism and equality policies escapes this neglect, though: since the 1990s, it has awakened more interest among social scientists (Valiente, 1996; Threlfall, 1999; Bustelo, 2004; Lombardo, 2004; Astelarra, 2005). Nevertheless, together with the recent rise of feminist mobilizations, academic publications on the Spanish feminist movements are multiplying.

Second-wave feminist activism in Spain focused on civil and political rights, equal opportunities in education and employment, abortion and gender-based violence. From the late 1980s, sexuality, pornography and prostitution/sex work, the subject of feminism, queer thinking and institutional feminism entered the agenda of the movements. In the last fifteen years, however, new issues have emerged (precariousness, care work and care policies, domestic work and global care chains) or re-emerged (abortion, prostitution/sex work, the subject of feminism, transfeminism).

The academic literature of the period 2010-2021 has focused, for the most part, on the 15M movement and its relation with the feminist movement (Gámez Fuentes, 2015; Cruells & Ezquerro, 2015; Trujillo, 2016; Martínez, 2018; Galdón, 2018, 2019; Razquin, 2019; Portos, 2019; Schulz & González, 2020; Chironi & Portos, 2021). Nevertheless, other issues have attracted the attention of researchers: institutional feminism (Lombardo & Bustelo, 2012; Alonso & Poleo, 2013; Lombardo & León, 2014; León, 2016; Bustelo, 2016); transfeminism (Gil, 2011; Platero, 2011; Núñez Puente, 2016; Platero & Ortega-Arjonilla, 2016; Martínez, 2017); the protests against Gallardón's abortion bill (Platero & Guzmán, 2014; Campillo, 2018; Martínez, 2019); the 7N 2015 protests (Campillo, 2018; Galdón, 2021); the 2018 Feminist Strike (Galdón, 2018, 2019; Campillo, 2019; Martínez, 2020a); and feminist digital activism (Portos, 2019; Martínez, 2020b; Willem & Tortajada, 2021).

In the framework of this research, some publications have tangentially addressed the composition of the movements, organisational models and collective action repertoires (Martínez, 2017; Portos, 2019; Galdón, 2018, 2019, 2021). But the only publication that deals in depth with these issues is *Identidades en proceso. Una propuesta a partir del análisis de las movilizaciones feministas contemporáneas*, by María Martínez (2019).

More recently, the legislation (Sexual Freedom Act; LGBTIQ+ and Trans Law) promoted by the Ministry of Equality of the centre-leftist coalition government (Partido Socialista Obrero Español [PSOE] and Unidas Podemos [UP]) (2019-2023) is causing a lot of public controversy, even within feminisms and the Spanish left. However, there is barely any academic publication on these feminist controversies yet -although there is plenty of gray literature (see, for example: Alabao & Pérez Colina, 2019; Fernández, 2019; Rosón & Garbayo-Maeztu, 2022).

7.2 The history of the feminist movements and its context

Spanish feminist movements were born at the end of Franco's dictatorship, in the heat of the anti-Franco struggle of the 1960s and 1970s, which would leave its mark in the movements. However, 1975 is considered the starting year of the Spanish feminist movement. Some Spanish women's associations took advantage of the UN declaration of that year as International Women's Year to come out of semi-clandestinity and create the Platform of Women's Organizations and Groups. In the I Women's Liberation Conference, held in Madrid, appeared what will be the two main tendencies of the movement throughout its development: "double militancy" activists, who understand feminism as

complementary to the political struggle within political parties and/or unions, and supporters of the "single militancy", who defend the autonomy of the movement and mistrust the institutional arena. Divergences became diluted, though, within the general agreement on the need to build an autonomous feminist movement around some fundamental democratic demands (civil and political rights, equal opportunities, egalitarian family law, decriminalisation of contraception, adultery and abortion). However, the conflict between the two branches of the movement broke out soon. In 1979, during the sessions of the II Women's Liberation Conference in Granada, the so-called "independent feminists", who were a minority, decided to leave the movement unitary organisations. Even so, a unity of action for key campaigns remained.

In 1982, the PSOE won the elections with an absolute majority, approved key measures and rights (domestic work regulation, 1985; partial depenalization of abortion, 1985) and created the Instituto de la Mujer. Coinciding with the growing institutionalisation of feminism (within state bodies, parties, unions and universities) during the 1980s and 1990s, the feminist movement began to weaken and fragment, reducing its mobilising potential.

At the end of the 1980s and during the 1990s, in a period of political disenchantment, social demobilisation and institutionalisation of feminism, a second, less numerous, generation of women joined the feminist movement (Trujillo, 2009; Gil, 2011; Martínez, 2017, 2019). Most of them were university students who had become activists through their previous involvement in the student movement or in the mobilizations against Spain's entry into NATO (1985). They had grown in a democracy and, thus, their perspective and interests were already different from the generation that had led the movement in the 1970s.

As Martínez (2017) points out, the divergences between the two generations refer to the problem of the subject of feminism and to the repertoires of action. In relation to the former, young feminists of the late 1980s and 1990s criticised the centrality both of heterosexuality and of the idea of woman as mother in the discourses of the older generation. In fact, already in 1988, during the Feminist Conference Against Sexist Violence held in Santiago de Compostela, conflict over women's sexuality, prostitution and sex work became apparent. In the same manner, the 1993 Feminist Conference was key in the shift towards the inclusion of sexual choice and trans issues (Platero & Ortega-Arjonilla, 2016). Regarding the differences with respect to the repertoires action, young feminist criticised the older generation for displaying a reactive denunciation strategy that left little space to more innovative and combatif repertoires. Therefore, in the 1980s and 1990s lesbian, trans, queer, squatter, and anti-militarist groups specialising in specific issues and working at the local level spread. Even the celebration of the 8M ceased to be celebrated in a unified way at the end of the 1980s (Gil, 2011).

The turn of the millennium brought about an upsurge of feminist movements. A change in the context of political opportunity led to this resurgence. On the one hand, there was a reactivation of social movements worldwide, with the Global Justice Movement and the movement against the Iraq War. At the domestic level, after thirteen years of socialist governments, the right-wing PP came to power in 1996 (and stayed in office till 2004): not only it implemented controversial measures such as an immigration law (2000), a university reform (2001), a labour reform (2002), but it also decided to participate in the Iraq War (2003) in spite of widespread public opposition. This offered a structure of political opportunity to social movements in the country, including feminist movements. In addition, in 2000 the celebration of the World March of Women boosted feminist mobilisation and the State Federation of Feminist Organisations took advantage of the opportunity to organise a Feminist Conference in Córdoba. The event gathered around 3,000 participants, including many young women,

which astonished both the organisers and the participants. As Martínez (2019) notes, this conference is considered a key milestone, as it served as a catalyst for mobilisation: after the decline of the 1990s, a third generation of women joined the movement, which was beginning to embrace its diversity and understand it as a strength. The term “transfeminism” was used for the first time in the Córdoba Conference, where there were talks on transgenderism by trans activists (Platero & Ortega-Arjonilla, 2016). It is difficult to make an account of the feminist groups that emerged since the late 1990s because “their trajectories are marked by dispersion, discontinuity, and diffuse character” (Gil, 2011: 73) and by their local and informal nature.

After the mobilizations against Spain’s participation in the Iraq War and the 11th March 2004 Al Qaeda’s terrorist attacks in Madrid, the PSOE came to power with a programme that set equality as a priority. In fact, the Prime Minister Zapatero appointed the first parity cabinet in the history of Spain and his first term in office (2004-2008) was characterised by the implementation of measures that were long-standing demands of feminist, LGTBIQ+ and other social movements: a Gender-based Law (1/2004), a new Divorce Law (2005), same-sex marriage (2005), Dependency Law (2006), Gender Identity Law (3/2007), parity electoral lists, paternity leave and other equality rights (Equality Law, 2007).

As Martínez (2019: 111-115) notes, several phenomena can be highlighted in this new millennium: 1) the development of the academic feminism, with the consolidation of research centres and research lines and the creation of masters and other postgraduate studies in gender; 2) the strengthening of para-institutional feminism; 3) the maintenance of the already classic spaces (Barquillo in Madrid, Ca la Dona in Barcelona, Casa de la Dona in Valencia, women’s assemblies in the the Basque Country) and state organisations (such as the State Federation of Feminist Organisations) of the Spanish feminist movements; 4) the articulation of local and regional feminisms with a transnational feminism; 5) and the coalition of the diverse branches and groups of the movements for the organisation of concrete events, actions and campaigns.

It is worth mentioning three examples of this unity of action. First of all, some feminist groups launched in 2007 and 2009 a proposal for debate and action around care that led to the celebration of several national meetings and events and to the 2008 8M festivities focused on this issue. Secondly, in 2009, and as a commemoration of the 1979 Conference, a new Feminist Conference was organised in Granada, under the title ‘Feminismo... es y será’ (Platero & Ortega-Arjonilla, 2016). Lastly, in 2007 a series of arrests of people accused of performing late-term abortions highlighted the shortcomings of the 1985 Abortion Law, and reactivated feminist mobilisation around the issue of the right to the voluntary termination of pregnancy. This situation resulted in the approval of the Sexual and Reproductive Health and Voluntary Termination of Pregnancy Law (2/2010) by the PSOE.

In 2010, in the midst of the international financial crisis and pressured by the Troika, the Socialist government made a policy U-turn towards austerity: the Ministry of Equality was eliminated, public sector wages were reduced, pensions were freezed, gender equality and care policies were cut and labour and pension reforms were introduced (Campillo, 2018). These austerity measures triggered a general strike, but general malaise did not really turn into mass mobilisation until the emergence of the 15M movement a year later, which would bring with it a sustained wave of social protests.

The 15M movement brought a common sense criticism of both austerity policies and the economic and political regime inherited from the transition to democracy to the political agenda and became a critical juncture for other social movements. This movement was not particularly feminist, especially

in its first stages, as illustrated by what happened in the Puerta del Sol (Madrid) encampment, where the tearing off of a banner that said ‘Revolution will be feminist or it will not be’ was followed by applause. The incident was proof of the division of the movement with regard to feminism, but it helped to make explicit the breach and the work required to overcome it (Gámez Fuentes, 2015). From then on, the work of the Feminists Commissions in the different camps intensified and documents, talks, and workshops were organised in order to raise awareness and mainstream feminism in the movement (Trujillo, 2016; Martínez, 2018). The adoption of gender inclusive language by the 15M movement was a result of the pedagogical work of feminist activists, but the mainstreaming of feminism depended too much on the personal involvement of the feminist activists (Cruells & Ezquerro, 2015).

In the November 2011 elections, indignation about the ‘austericide’ caused the electoral defeat of the PSOE and, paradoxically, the victory with the absolute majority of the PP, which had run for government with an electoral programme that included further austerity measures and a very regressive reform of the Voluntary Termination of Pregnancy Law.

The thrust of the 15M movement and the recrudescence of the austerity agenda motivated new mass demonstrations against the Conservative government in 2012-2013, such as the various Mareas (literally, tides) in defence of public services: Marea Verde, in defence of public education; Marea Blanca, against cuts and privatisations of health services, etc. Feminists took part in the different mareas, but also created the Marea Violeta, which denounced the elimination of equality institutions, the cuts in care and equality policies and in counselling services for gender-based violence victims, the closing down of women’s shelters, and the PP plans to change the abortion law.

Since 2013 and up until the Covid-19 pandemic, feminism has been the sole state-wide social movement that not only has resisted demobilisation, but also has been able to sustain particularly massive mobilizations. The right to choose, gender violence and care work have been the main issues of this wave of feminist mobilisation (Campillo, 2019). More precisely, three milestones can be highlighted: the campaign against Justice Minister’s abortion bill, which managed to overthrow both the bill and the Minister (Campillo, 2018); the record-breaking Marcha Estatal contra las Violencias Machistas (State March Against Sexist Violence) of 7 November 2015 (Galdón Gorbella, 2021); and the 8M 2018 Strike (and that of 2019) (García et al., 2018; Campillo, 2019; Martínez, 2020a).

The campaign against Justice Minister Gallardón’s abortion bill began as soon as the process was announced and the actual bill was an undefined plan. Pro-choice mobilisations were varied and frequent and they intensified in 2013 and 2014: the 8 March campaigns from 2012 to 2014 were mainly devoted to that demand, a *escrache*⁵³ against Gallardón in his own house was organised (2013), several gatherings in front of the Ministry of Justice building or other regional Justice buildings and courts as various mass mobilisations were held in 2014. Indeed, El Tren de la Libertad (The Train of Liberty) state march organised in Madrid was surprisingly massive, but after that there were various large demonstrations and gatherings in several Spanish cities.

⁵³ The Real Academia Española Dictionary defines *escrache* as a “popular demonstration of protest against a person, usually from the political or administrative sphere, which takes place in front of his or her home or in a public place where he or she has to go”. (dle.rae.es)

The 7N movement, for its part, drew from the awareness and mobilisation work carried out by the feminist movement in the previous years, especially around the International Day for the Elimination of Violence against Women (25N). It benefited from the mobilising success of the campaign against Gallardón's abortion bill. However, unlike previous, more dispersed, campaigns, the 7N Platform was created as a state-wide platform, which contributed to its visibility. A Marcha Contra las Violencias Machistas (March Against Sexist Violence) was called for it to be held in Madrid on the 7 November 2015. The call was adhered to by hundreds of state-wide, regional and local organisations, as well as all unions and political parties, including right-wing parties, such as Ciudadanos and PP. The protest march was massive. A second march was called again on the same day the following year.

The main aim of the 7N Platform was for the Gender Violence Law to be reformed. A State Pact against Gender Violence was approved by Parliament at the end of September 2017; however, the pact did not include all the measures that were demanded and did not set a timeline or budget for each of them, which displeased most activists and led UP to abstain in the final vote in Parliament. Far from dissolving itself after the approval of the Pact, the 7N Platform became stable and continued to raise awareness against gender-based violence.

In 2016, a case of a gang rape during the San Fermín in Pamplona sparked a new cycle of mobilisations around sexual violence. Under the slogan #Yosítecreo ('I do believe you'), a wide movement of support emerged in 2017 and since then grew to denounce the treatment that the victim was given during trial, both by the judge and by the media. On the day of the judgment, in which the gang was found guilty only of sexual abuse and not of rape, there were massive spontaneous protests in every Spanish city. As a result of all this, the 25N celebrations have become more numerous, local authorities promote campaigns against sexual assault during local celebrations, and the coalition government has recently approved the Sexual Freedom Law (2022).

The third milestone of the period was the 8M 2018 Feminist Strike. Under the slogan 'If we stop, the world stops', the feminist movement organised a full 24-hour labour, education, care work and consumption strike that was backed by more than 300 organisations around the country. The strike was a success. According to the main unions, six million workers joined the labour strike and women took the public space: there were protests with pots and pans, blockages of train lines, picket lines, mass meetings and massive demonstrations. The protest wave even reached small towns and villages all over the country.

The success of the 8M 2018 Feminist Strike resided in its successful process of preparation: it started one year earlier in Madrid but soon a state-wide 8M Commission was created. Work within the platform was coordinated through different committees (communication, actions, contents, evaluation, students, international and coordination committee), with a strong emphasis in communication. In addition, local 8M Commissions were created in almost every city or town, holding monthly meetings (around 200 women attended those in Madrid), which increased in frequency in the weeks before the 8M (Campillo, 2019).

As Campillo (2019) highlights, the call brought about three novelties in terms of political and social support: first of all, it counted on the full support of the Church; secondly, it gained the support of well-established professional women's associations (including judges, researchers, professional athletes, chambermaids) and prompted the emergence of new ones centred around general and specific demands (journalists, book industry workers, health workers, teachers and educators, NGOs workers); finally, the strike call and the issues it raised (gender violence, wage gap, pensions, care work) gained

relevance in the press and all kinds of TV shows, which may be the result of women journalists' support (Campillo, 2019). Thus, it is no wonder a survey carried out in February showed that 88 percent of women and 77 percent of men thought there were sufficient reasons for the strike.

After the success of the strike, the 8M Commission decided to call for a new feminist strike the 8M 2019. The quantity of striking workers even exceeded the number of 2018 and data of participants in events and demonstrations exceeded expectations. Several members of Pedro Sanchez's cabinet as well as other political authorities attended the Madrid demonstration. But, unlike a year earlier, the process of preparation of this second strike was more turbulent: in some cities, such as Madrid and Barcelona, abolitionist feminists⁵⁴ tried to boycott the usual dynamics of the 8M Commissions with the intention of forcing a formal condemnation of prostitution/sex work. Prostitution/sex work has traditionally been one of the conflictual debates within the Spanish feminist movements, but 8M platforms have usually stuck to the consensus of denouncing trafficking (Alabao & Pérez Colina, 2019). However, this is no longer the case since the success of the 8M 2018 and the subsequent creation of the Ministry of Equality by the PSOE-UP coalition government (2019-2023). For the first time, this Ministry is not in the hands of the PSOE and its feminists, but in the hands of UP, under the lead of Irene Montero and a young team that had previously been active in the feminist movement.

Many activists agree on noting that present conflicts around the issues of prostitution/sex and trans rights have little to do with ideological divergences and more to do with a power conflict, given that PSOE feminists (within the party, but also within academia and para-institutional organisations) are losing the monopoly of the feminist voice(s) in the country (Alabao & Pérez Colina, 2019; Fernández, 2019; Rosón & Garbayo-Maeztu, 2022). In fact, during the demonstration of the 8M 2020 in Madrid, there was a confrontation between the organisers and around 200 activists from the Madrid Abolitionist Assembly who tried to usurp the (agreed in the 8M Commission) banner of the head of the demonstration and replace it by one saying "Feminist movement for the abolition of prostitution" (Martínez, 2020). These abolitionist feminists call themselves "gender abolitionists" and have been very active in the opposition to the recently passed Trans Law, whose approval they managed to slow down. As a result, a visibility campaign was organised in 2021 by different LGTB and trans organisations who carried a huge trans flag throughout the country under the message '#ExigimosLaIgualdadTrans' (We demand Trans Equality). Since that year, there have been two different 8M feminist celebrations and demonstrations in most big cities in the country.

7.3 Actors, organisations and organisational models

The academic literature of the period 2010-2021 hardly addresses the issue of actors and organisational models and, when it does, this is mainly dealt in relation to the divergences between (young and veteran) generations of feminist activists (Martínez, 2018, 2019; Portos, 2019; Galdón Gorbella, 2019 y 2021).

The network of feminist movements in Spain is made up of social movements, equality or women's secretariats of left-wing parties and unions, institutional feminism, academic feminism, and third

⁵⁴ Abolitionist feminists is how feminists who want to abolish prostitution call themselves. In recent years, many of these feminists are also using that term to encompass the fight against trans depathologisation and gender self-determination, as they contend they want to abolish gender.

sector organisations. Besides, the concrete composition of actors within the network varies between Autonomous Communities (Martínez, 2019).

The composition of the Spanish feminist social movements has changed since the 1970s. As Martínez (2019) notes, this transformation has to do with learnings within (and critiques to) other political space, with ideological stances and with generational changes. But the result has been that, since the 1980s-1990s, formal and large feminist organisations are declining, and most groups are since then autonomous, informal, small, with little or inexistent structures, limited resources and locally-based. They implement a deliberative organisational model, that is, a decision-making process based on the assembly. There is no division on labour and leaderships are flexible and mainly based on the degree of information and degree of involvement and on charisma. Decisions must be taken collectively, by consensus, avoiding voting (Martínez, 2019: 130-134). In contrast with classic feminist organisations from the 1970s, these groups emphasise self-awareness work and creative and direct action work over denunciation work and movement-institutions negotiations. However, this does not preclude them from taking part side by side with greater and formal organisations in movement platforms that are created for specific campaigns or events, such as the 7N platform or the 8M Commissions.

As mentioned above (see section 2. The history of the feminist movements), this change in organisational models and political priorities already took place at the end of the 1980s and in the 1990s and was mostly -but not necessarily- linked to a new generation of activists joining the lines of the feminist movements and, with them, a turn in ideological stances and political priorities. In general, most young groups criticised the centrality of heterosexuality and the implicit idea of women as mothers in the discourses of the older generation, were interested in sexuality and sexual orientations and introduced queer thinking in Spain. Besides, queer thinking and action opened the door to intersectional practices, with alliances and overlappings between feminist and LGBTQI+ discourses and activism being common, especially thanks to lesbian activists (Trujillo, 2009, 2016; Platero & Ortega-Arjonilla, 2016). Since the end of the 2000s, a more explicit intersectional thinking and practice began to develop, on the one hand, thanks to the work of migrant activists and, on the other, thanks to academic feminist thinking. This intersectional stance was patent in the organisation, discourses and demands of the 2018 and 2019 Feminist Strikes and, since then, has tended to remain. A couple of examples: the Madrid 8M Commission is composed of a few sub-commissions, one of which is devoted to "Migration and Anti-racism", and recently this sub-commission along with other feminist and migrant anti-racist groups have been working in the campaign #Regularizaci3n (see sub-section 5.4 on Migration).

It is difficult to conclude whether equality or women's secretariats of left-wing parties and unions are part of the feminist social movements or not. They have traditionally taken part of the unitary commissions organising the 8M or the 25N and of some campaigns platforms, but their presence is regarded as intrusive by most activists, especially the younger ones, who tend to be more suspicious of institutional politics.

The process of institutionalisation of feminism in Spain started in 1983, when the newly-appointed Socialist government, under pressure from its feminist members, founded the Women's Institute (Instituto de la Mujer, IM). The IM has stood out over the years mainly for its work as a "builder of the political agenda", promoting the implementation of equal opportunities plans and the foundation of equality bodies in the Autonomous Communities and town councils (Valiente, 1996: 178). However, it should be noted that conservative governments have tended to strip the IM of many of its competencies and funding (Threlfall, 1999). In 2008, Zapatero created the Ministry of Equality, which

was eliminated in 2010 and created again in 2019, under the present coalition government. During its term in office, this government has renamed the Instituto de la Mujer as the Instituto de las Mujeres, making a clear acknowledgment of the need to have an intersectional approach to feminism.

But feminism institutionalisation does not only refer to its crystallisation in certain state structures, but also to its penetration in academic structures and programmes, and in the world of consultancy and research. Since the 1990s, feminism and gender studies have entered university curricula and research centres and masters have been created. As Nuñez Puente (2016) highlights, Spanish academic feminism has been monopolised by Enlightenment (equality) feminists in the PSOE's orbit, most of whom are now quite active in their opposition to the Ministry of Equality and the laws it has promoted (particularly, the so-called Trans Law).

Since the 1980s, alongside feminist institutionalisation, many feminist NGOs, some of them linked to the PSOE, have been created. They are usually focused on supporting and assisting women on specific issues (sexuality, care, gender-based violence, prostitution) or on monitoring equality policies and have developed and professionalised thanks to subsidies and biddings. Martínez refers to those organisations as “para-institutional feminism” and notes that they are now more providers of services to the administration, dissociating themselves from the repertoires of the movement. Some of them have traditionally been linked to the PSOE.

7.4 Allies

There is not an explicit and detailed analysis of allies of the feminist movements in the literature of the period, but there are some points worth mentioning. First of all, despite the suspicious approach to institutions of most of the feminist social movement, especially young, autonomous and queer groups, in the framework of its unitary mobilisations and campaigns, the movement has always been in contact with authorities, political parties and unions. Left-wing parties (PSOE, Izquierda Unida, Podemos, recently UP, etc.) and unions have generally backed the movement campaigns, such as the one against Gallardón's abortion bill, the 7N campaign, and the feminist strikes. However, as we have seen, the strikes just gained the full support of the minority unions Confederación General de los Trabajadores (CGT), Confederación Nacional del Trabajo (CNT) and Intersindical, which were the ones registering the 24-hour labour strikes. The main unions, CCOO and UGT distanced themselves from the movement and just called a partial stoppage.

Although these main Spanish unions introduced gender quotas in the late nineties, they are highly masculinised and have focused mostly on traditional work settings and Fordist labour relationships, so they are having troubles connecting with young, migrant and/or female precarious or unemployed workers. Nevertheless, both UGT and CCOO have recently been key actors, along with domestic workers' associations and the feminist movement, in the several reforms of the working conditions and security rights of domestic workers, which gives us some hope as to future alliances and collaborations.

Social movements, and especially the environmentalists, have traditionally been allies of the feminist movement, and worked side by side with it to prepare the 2018 and 2019 8 March Strikes.

The municipalist movements and citizen coalitions that emerged on the eve of the 2015 municipal elections and that came into office in the so-called “cities of change” (Madrid, Barcelona, Zaragoza, Valencia, Pamplona, etc.) were great allies of the local feminist movements. Some examples of this collaboration were: the gender budgeting policies in Barcelona, the Madrid Ciudad de los Cuidados Plan (Madrid City of Care Programme), the organisation of the 1st Conference on Domestic Work and

Care by Madrid's local government, the stress local governments are placing on preventing sexual abuses and hate crimes, the promotion of feminist town planning, etc.

Finally, even if there is no strong leftist media in Spain, since 2010 some new general-interest newspapers and magazines have emerged (eldiario.es, La Marea, El Salto) that are acting as allies to feminist struggles, giving voice to feminist journalists and including contributions from feminist academics and activists. Likewise, many feminist online news platforms (such as Pikara Magazine), blogs and podcasts (Estirando el Chicle, Deforme Semanal), as well as feminist journalists (Ana Requena, June Fernández), comedians (Henaar Álvarez), "twitter stars" (Barbijaputa) and "youtubers" have emerged in the last decade, which has undoubtedly contributed to the renewed appeal of feminism to young women.

7.5 Themes, debates and campaigns

7.5.1 Labour market

In the period 2010-2021, feminist mobilizations over labour market issues have been mostly related to the financial crisis and the austerity policies adopted in response. Austerity involved, among other things, neoliberal labour reforms, deteriorated employment conditions and increased job precariousness. Civil society activism exploded with the 15M and the 'mareas', and feminist activism was part of this anti-austerity movement (Campillo 2018; Lombardo 2017). Common grievances related to precarity facilitated coalition-building; the ability to bridge socio-economic demands and feminist claims was vital for successful mobilisation (Chironi & Portos, 2021). Feminist activism contributed to the anti-austerity discourses by gendering precarity and pushing issues such as care, vulnerability and sustainability of life onto the agenda. While participation in anti-austerity struggles revitalised the Spanish feminist movement, the anti-austerity movement was not particularly feminist (Campillo 2018).

In this decade, care work has constituted the most important issue on the feminist agenda around the labour market. Care was historically a problematic matter for the Spanish feminist movement, because it developed in the context of, and in resistance to, the Franco regime and its traditional Catholic familism. The recognition and revaluation of care work were contested and challenging questions, given that such claims could potentially reinforce gender inequalities. For a long time, the movement largely ignored the issue of care, focusing instead on reproductive rights, gender violence, equal opportunities in employment, etc. (Campillo 2018, 2019). Nonetheless, care has now figured on the feminist agenda for more than a decade. Activism surrounding this issue encompasses a variety of organisational forms, networks, perspectives and political claims.

Care issues are connected to the distribution of resources, spaces and time for care. Since 2008, one of the key messages of the 8M marches highlights the need for a social reorganisation of care (*Por una reorganización social de los cuidados*). Further, feminist collectives invented the concept of "Care-tizenship", playing with the Spanish word for citizenship (*ciudadanía*) and switching the letters around to form "cuidadanía", associated with the word for care (*cuidados*). Care-tizenship highlighted a community based on caring relationships in a context of increasing vulnerability among local and migrant populations (Casas-Cortes, 2019).

The 2018 and 2019 8M Strikes and the Covid-19 pandemic have been decisive in pushing care onto the mainstream political agenda. In the 2018 Feminist Strike, the economy was one of the focal points, including issues related to the gender pay gap, labour market discrimination, precarity and unequal

pensions, inequalities that were pointed to be related with the unequal gender distribution of care work (Comisión 8 de Marzo, 2018). The strikes also addressed care, housework and the domestic sphere by encouraging a strike from unpaid work (Campillo, 2019). In addition, a key claim of the strikes was that of equalising domestic workers' rights to those of workers in other sectors.

Overall, the most relevant feminist campaign in the area of labour market has precisely been the campaign for "dignifying domestic work", promoting domestic workers' rights and demanding visibility, recognition and a social reorganisation of care. The campaign has focused on improving workers' rights, employment and working conditions, and on Spain's ratification of the ILO Convention 189 concerning Decent Work for Domestic Workers. It has effectively highlighted the dimension of care, adopting an intersectional perspective on this issue.

A wide range of organisations have been involved in the campaign, from small, locally rooted domestic workers' and migrant associations to large national organisations such as trade unions. Several domestic workers associations were created between 2000 and 2010. Since then, these have been key actors, including Territorio Doméstico, Servicio Doméstico Activo (SEDOAC), Nosotras, Sindicato Autónomo de Trabajadoras de Hogar y del Cuidado (SINDIHOGAR). Domestic workers have engaged in national and international networks, such as the National Platform of Domestic Workers' Associations and the Turin Group. Feminist actors have been involved in various ways, including feminists in academia, political parties (e.g. Podemos), trade unions, the migrants' rights movement (Geymonat et al., 2021). The issue has brought together activists from very different backgrounds and networks, like native feminist academics and migrant domestic workers (Filigrana 2020).

Domestic workers have historically been attributed weaker rights and social protection than other workers. Policies have constructed paid domestic work as different from other kinds of work. During the Franco regime, domestic workers were excluded from labour law. The Special Regime for Domestic Workers of 1985 gave them worker status but provided very weak protection (León, 2013). The ILO Convention 189 inspired changes in the regulation of domestic work. The 2011 reforms (Law 27/2011; Royal Decree 1620/2011) partially equalised domestic workers with other workers, although they were still excluded from key workers' rights, such as unemployment benefits (Campillo 2018; Gonalons-Pons, 2022). After a ruling by the Court of Justice of the European Union in 2022, domestic workers were granted the right to unemployment, and the Spanish Congress of Deputies finally ratified the ILO Convention (see Policy Impact). That domestic workers to a large extent care for children and older people is not recognized in policies on domestic work (Peterson 2018).

The struggles of women working in other precarious female dominated work sectors have also become more visible in the last decade. For example, chambermaids, known as *las Kellys*, organise and struggle for better working and employment conditions (www.laskellys.com).

The claim for equal and non-transferable parental leaves is another labour market related issue that has been on the political agenda. Promoted by feminist academics and activists, many of whom were members of the *Plataforma por los Permisos Iguales e Intransferibles de Nacimiento y Adopción PPIINA* (Platform for Equal, Non-Transferable Parental Leaves) (www.ppiina.org), the issue has definitely achieved political resonance. In 2016, the Spanish Parliament approved a motion to make maternity and paternity leaves equal lengths (Campillo 2018). After incremental increases in the paternity leave, the leave is now 16 weeks for both parents (see Policy Impact).

7.5.2 Reproductive rights

In the period 2010-2021, the most salient issues on the feminist agenda were reproductive rights and gender-based violence (Campillo, 2019). In 2010, the Socialist government adopted a progressive abortion law (Law 2/2010) granting women the right to choose to interrupt their pregnancy within the first 14 weeks. Abortion was framed in terms of individual self-determination and women's fundamental rights. At the same time, a conservative counter-movement occurred, as anti-gender civil society organisations and right-wing parties questioned advances in gender equality and women's rights. In the regions where the PP was in office, regional laws were adopted for the "protection of pregnant women" (Alonso and Paleo, 2017). The Conservative Party won the 2011 general elections with a programme that promised a radical reform of the abortion law (López, 2015). Accordingly, gender equality issues were downplayed and maternalist and "pro-life" discourses entered the political agenda (Campillo, 2018).

As mentioned previously, the campaign to defend the right to choose constitutes a milestone for the feminist movement (Alonso, 2015; Campillo, 2019; Chironi and Portos, 2021; Lombardo, 2017; Portos, 2019). This campaign was a direct response to a bill that called for the protection of the life of "the conceived unborn" and of "the rights of the pregnant woman". The reform proposed by Justice Minister Ruiz Gallardón was intended to make abortion legal only in very specific and limited situations, including rape (within 12 weeks, only for reported crimes) and serious physical or psychological health risks (within 22 weeks, with authorization of medical staff). Foetus malformation was not considered a legitimate condition. In sum, abortion would become illegal in most cases (Campillo, 2018; Lombardo, 2017).

This bill encountered total opposition from the feminist movements. Pro-choice mobilisations multiplied in various contexts and settings between 2012 and 2014. The "Violet Tide" (*Marea Violeta*), supported by more than 400 organisations, mobilised against the attack on women's rights (Chironi & Portos, 2021). Subsequently, feminists mobilised against the abortion reform by reactivating the State Platform of Feminist Organizations and forging alliances (Alonso, 2015). Thus, in 2012 more than 100 public health-related organisations came together and initiated the State Platform in Defense of Sexual and Reproductive Rights, articulating the campaign "Deciding makes us free" (*Decidir nos hace libres*).

A massive demonstration in Madrid labelled "The Liberty Train" (*El Tren de la Libertad*), February 1 2014, demanded the right to choose. The initiative had begun in a small town in Asturias and finally brought together thousands of women from all over Spain in Madrid (Alonso, 2015). After this event, feminist mobilisations grew continuously. During these years, the 8 March demonstrations largely focused on the right to choose.

The level of popular contestation played a vital role in the withdrawal of the reform, which in turn forced the resignation of Minister Ruiz-Gallardón (Campillo, 2019; Portos, 2019). It is worth mentioning that not even Conservative and Catholics expressed strong support for the bill (Campillo, 2019) and there were also internal divergences within the Conservative Party (Alonso, 2015)

Cross-generational coalitions were created as the campaign for the right to choose mobilised both veteran activists and young women. In fact, the involvement of young women in the feminist struggle increased significantly. Additionally, feminists voiced international solidarity with women in other countries where reproductive rights were also restricted, and built international alliances (Alonso, 2015; Chironi and Portos, 2021). Studies describe the struggle to defend the right to choose as a

success story for the feminist movement. At the same time, this issue tends to return to the political agenda, as it has been recently the case (see Policy Impact).

7.5.3 Gender-based violence

The problem of gender-based intimate partner violence became more visible in 1997, when the murders of women at the hands of their partners got a lot of attention in the media (Boix, 2001; Campillo 2013). Although the autonomous feminist movement had been working on the issue of sexist violences for years, these events constituted a critical juncture, putting the need for urgent and comprehensive measures at the political agenda (Valiente, 2005). The Organic Law of Comprehensive Protection Measures Against Gender Violence, approved in 2004, is the fundamental regulation, the one that institutionalised the narrative of gender violence. But other measures and regulations have been implemented since then which broaden the scope of what is considered gender-based violence and, thus, the reach of protective measures.

The campaign against gender violence certainly constitutes a landmark for the feminist movement. Articulated in terms of “7N against sexist violence. No to sexual assaults” (*7N contra las violencias machistas. No a las agresiones sexuales*), it adopted a broad and inclusive framing of the concept of gender violence, highlighting its structural nature. The historic 7N 2015 State March Against Sexist Violences (*Marcha Estatal contra las Violencias Machistas*) brought together a wide range of actors: more than 300 feminist organisations, 200 institutions, including political parties and trade unions, and 135 municipalities. According to the organisers, at least 200.000 people participated. The great mobilisation eventually led the Parliament to negotiate and approve a State Pact Against Gender Violence (Campillo, 2018; Chironi & Portos, 2021; Portos, 2019).

Campillo (2018, 2019) summarizes the key points of the 7N mobilization: gender violence is structural and related to a patriarchal system; it goes beyond intimate-partner violence; it is varied, psychological as well as physical; and all gender violence needs to be prevented and attended to by public authorities, including sexual violence. Hence, a central claim was precisely that gender violence takes various forms and that public authorities need to attend to all victims of violence through a variety of measures, resources, training and prevention. Moreover, it was highlighted that victims of gender violence need to be protected regardless of whether they report the violence to the police or not. Priority should be given to prevention, including promoting co-education, and all professionals who intervene in the process should receive specific training in the field. In addition, it was argued that parental rights should be withdrawn and shared custody eliminated for abusers. The main aim was a reform of the Law 1/2004 of Comprehensive Protection Measures against Gender Violence to include the above-mentioned points.

The 7N Feminist Platform against Sexist Violence was a state-wide organisation, which contributed to its visibility (Campillo, 2018, 2019). In addition, the Platform continued active after the organisation of the 7N march. While feminist activist narratives increasingly resonated in the media and the public debate, the 7N also gave rise to a range of different activities: for example, university assemblies forming the Feminist Student Block (Portos, 2019). A second march was organised in 2016 and, since then, every 25N big rallies were organised.

The 7N march was supported by the right-wing parties Ciudadanos and PP. This was very unusual, given that the call came from the autonomous feminist movement (Campillo, 2019). In this sense, the issue of gender violence seemed to generate wide consensus. In contrast, since the extreme right party

Vox gained political representation, it has challenged gender violence policies, arguing that violence has no gender. As Cabezas (2022b) contends, this opposition has turned gender violence into a question of political struggle, at a time of intense feminist mobilisation and feminist influence in government.

A case of sexual violence that led to enormous feminist mobilization all across Spain was the so called *Manada case*, the “wolfpack” gang rape. During the San Fermines celebrations in Pamplona in July 2016, a group of five men (including a member of the Civil Guard and a military member of the Military Emergency Unit) raped an 18-year-old girl in a doorway. The media soon came to name the case *la Manada* because this was the term the five rapists had used for their WhatsApp group, a group in which they shared videos of the rape.

The trial, which started in the fall 2017, received significant media coverage. In November, feminist groups convened demonstrations in all the major Spanish cities. Protesters reacted strongly against the way the victim was treated, by the judges of the case and the media. The judges of the court (all male) focused on whether or not the victim had clearly expressed her refusal. That the perpetrators had acted in the same way on at least one previous occasion was ignored (Abrisketa & Abrisketa, 2020). It became known that the victim’s identity had been leaked, and that she had even been spied on by a private detective hired by the defence. They aimed to show that she was leading a normal life without trauma and the evidence collected was accepted in the investigation. In addition, the video of the rape was used in the trial to evaluate whether or not the victim had suffered or enjoyed the event. Hence, the trial implied a questioning of the victim's pain, and her right to survival. As the victim of rape was being judged, messages like “Sister, I do believe you” (*Hermana yo sí te creo*) spread rapidly (Abrisketa & Abrisketa, 2020; Campillo, 2019; Chironi & Portos, 2021; Filigrana, 2020; Romano, 2022).

In the spring of 2018, the regional courts of Navarra sentenced the five men to sexual abuse, not rape. The court sentenced them to nine years in prison but concluded that physical violence had not been used, and one judge even voted for freeing the accused (Abrisketa & Abrisketa, 2020; Chironi & Portos, 2021). Remarkably, in the first hearing in April 2018, the five rapists were released on parole. A petition to disqualify the judges was circulated and widely signed. Finally, the Spanish Supreme Court reviewed the case and, in June 2019, it upgraded the sentence from abuse to aggression (i.e. rape), sentencing the rapists to 15 years in prison for the crimes committed (Abrisketa & Abrisketa, 2020).

Overall, the protests highlighted the patriarchal bias of the judges and the judicial system. The entire process was marked by feminist mobilizations, both on social media and in the streets. The Navarra court ruling caused major social outrage and the number of participants in the 8 March rallies increased in the following years. Slogans that were used in the mobilisations surrounding the Manada case also continued to be used in the 8M marches for several years: “Sister, I do believe you” (*Hermana yo sí te creo*), “You are not alone” (*No estás sola*), “No is no” (*No es no*) and “It is not abuse, it’s rape” (*No es abuso, es violación*). Feminist banners and slogans denounced rape culture and victim blaming, reclaiming the streets and women’s right to walk home alone safely (Romano, 2022).

The coalition government has responded to the feminist requests for legal reform by elaborating a Law of Sexual Freedom, also called law of “only yes is yes”, in force since 2022 (see policy impact). In the context of the Manada case, feminist debates on sexual violence have contributed to further re-defining and amplifying the meaning of gender violence. Importantly, the issue motivated activism and

gathered women and allies from all age groups, geographic regions, classes, and ideologies (Abrisketa & Abrisketa, 2020; Willem & Tortajada, 2021).

7.5.4 Migration

Feminist advocacy in relation to migration issues is definitely understudied. In any case, there have not been any wide-ranging feminist campaigns centering migration issues in the period of 2010-2021. But even though migration has not been significant on the feminist agenda, recent feminist advocacy has involved the campaign #RegularizationNow (*#RegularizaciónYa*) for a regularisation of migrants residing in Spain (<https://regularizacionya.com/>). A Popular Legislative Initiative has been elaborated with the objective of achieving regularisation for close to half a million migrants, which would involve residence and work permits. While this popular legislative initiative has been promoted by an autonomous migrant movement, it is supported by the feminist movement and domestic workers collectives. In this vein, in December 2022 over 500 000 signatures in favour of regularisation were delivered to the Congress in Madrid.

The question of regularisation has connections to the issue of domestic work, given that workers in the domestic work sector are predominantly migrant women. Many domestic workers are not helped by the recent improvements in domestic workers' rights, since they are migrants without work/residence permit and work in the informal economy. This is particularly common for those who work as live-in domestic workers. In this context, domestic workers' organisations, such as *Territorio Domestico*, have advocated regularisation for a long time. The feminist campaign on domestic and care work has included, and been articulated by, migrant women. In addition, there have been calls for extended citizenship rights for undocumented migrants, particularly for those who care for children, older people and people with disabilities (Casas-Cortes, 2019). A study by Martínez-Conde et al. (2020) indicates that feminist activism on domestic work has not been drawing on a homogenising identity as "immigrant women", but rather on the inclusion and recognition of domestic workers' different experiences, disadvantages, and political positions.

During the great feminist mobilisation against sexual violences during the Manada case, the media conveyed news on sexual abuse reported by migrant women working as seasonal workers in the strawberry harvest in Huelva. Although some collectives called for protest, the response was weak, particularly in comparison with other feminist protests at the time. Critical voices pointed at racism within the feminist movement and the marginalisation of minority and migrant women. Hence, the case of sexual violence against migrant women workers drew attention to the intersections of gender, race and class, and gave raise to internal debates (Filigrana, 2020; Sandu & Fernández, 2021).

7.5.5 LGTBIQ+ rights

Like the feminist movement, the LGTBIQ+ movement emerged as resistance to the oppressive Franco dictatorship. In this context, homosexuality (including "transvestism") was prohibited and persecuted under the so-called "Social Danger Act" (1970). During the transition to democracy, social movements struggled against legislation that discriminated against women and sexual minorities. Historically, the LGTBIQ+ movement has been closely interconnected with the feminist movement; lesbian, trans and queer feminists have pushed the agenda of LGTBIQ+ rights and recognition within both movements (e.g. Platero & Ortega, 2016). In fact, for example, trans women and groups of queer, lesbian and bisexual activists take part in the Madrid 8M Commission. In more recent years, however, the strategy of queer activism has not been primarily focused on the negotiation with institutions to achieve

specific rights, but on mobilising for social and cultural change, on the streets and in autonomous spaces. Nonetheless, these struggles have accelerated legal reforms (Trujillo, 2016). In 2005, Spain received attention in international media for advancing in LGTBIQ+ rights and equality by allowing same-sex marriage (Platero, 2007), but just two years later a Gender Identity Law was also passed by the Socialist government.

As intersectional activism, the LGTBIQ+ movement has largely moved beyond a particular focus on gay, lesbian or trans politics (Trujillo, 2016). However, trans people's rights have become an especially visible, but controversial, issue on the agenda. The historical discrimination of trans individuals has been acknowledged, going from being considered sinful, criminal and sick to being political subjects with recognized rights (Platero, 2020).

Trans and LGTBIQ+ organisations have long advocated strengthened rights for trans people, in alliance with left-wing political parties. In the period of 2010-2021, they have been able to put trans people's rights and recognition on the political agenda. In this vein, they have raised issues of improved access to legal, physical and social transition (Platero, 2020). Since 2012, 16 regional laws granting rights to trans individuals have been adopted. In addition, in November 2017, the Spanish Parliament approved a bill to allow trans people to choose their own gender without the prerequisite of a previous medical diagnosis of gender dysphoria.

In the theme of LGTBIQ+ rights, the most important campaign is the campaign promoting the so-called Trans Act, a national law on LGTBIQ+ rights and trans rights that is in the process of being adopted. Collectives that promote the law consider it a vital step towards strengthening rights and putting an end to the pathologizing of trans people. A wide range of LGTBIQ+ organizations advocate in favor of the Trans Act, among them the State Federation of Lesbians, Gays, Trans and Bisexuals (FELGTB) (*Federación Estatal de Lesbianas, Gays, Trans y Bisexuales*), Chrysallis and Fundación Triángulo. One example of the attempts to mobilise support for the law is the campaign "We demand Trans Equality" (*Exigimos La Igualdad Trans*) (see repertoires of action). Activism has been spurred by an increasing resistance against the Trans Act.

The government bill presented in September 2022, the Draft Law for the real and effective equality of trans people and for the guarantee of the rights of LGTBI people (*Proyecto de Ley para la igualdad real y efectiva de las personas trans y para la garantía de los derechos de las personas LGTBI*), aims to expand the rights of LGTBIQ+ people, including trans individuals.

Negotiations have been difficult given the internal divisions of the coalition government, between part of the PSOE and UP. Gender self-determination has been the conflictive point, particularly in relation to minors. The reform includes a change in Law 3/2007 that currently regulates the modification of individuals' gender in the national registry (Platero, 2020). According to the bill, from the age of 16 individuals will be able to change their gender in the Civil Registry without the need for parental consent. Minors aged 14-16 years must be assisted by their parents or legal guardians, and children younger than 14 years will need judicial authorization. However, the Socialists attempted to incorporate amendments that required minors under 16 years to have a judicial authorization to change their gender. This was not accepted by UP, the political force behind the initiative, and the PSOE finally withdrew their demand. The bill deals with a range of other issues as well: access to reproduction techniques in the National Health System for lesbians, bisexual women and trans people,

education on sexual, gender and family diversity in mandatory education, fundamental rights for intersex people and reinforcement of anti-discrimination legislation.

The debates surrounding the Trans Act have revealed a new kind of resistance from within (Platero & Ortega, 2016; Platero, 2020; Willem & Torjada). This resistance has been articulated by some feminist leaders in the Socialist Party, women's organisations and feminist academics. They strongly criticise the Trans Act proposal, reject progress in trans rights and delegitimise transfeminism. In their view, the Trans Act policy reform would imply harm to children and a reversal in women's rights, particularly when it comes to gender-based violence.

Critical feminist voices have been quite visible. For example, a number of feminist organisations delivered 24 amendments to the Trans Act to the Parliament, emphasising that the reform is a threat to women and children. They argued that recognition of trans people should be reserved for "people with dysphoria", rejecting gender self-determination without judicial authorization. Among the signing organisations we find: the European Women's Lobby in Spain, the Association of Women for Health, the Federation of Progressive Women, Women's Foundation, the Federation of Separated and Divorced Women, the Women for Peace Association and the Feminist Political Forum (Europa Press, 2022).

Not all studies on the feminist movement and trans activism emphasise conflict. Platero and Ortega (2016) challenge oppositional narratives. Recognizing that the relationships between cis and trans feminists have sometimes been problematic, the authors argue that Spain contrasts with Anglo-Saxon and Latin American contexts in that in Spain the LGBT movement and the feminist movement are highly interwoven and the latter included transfeminist demands long ago, in great part thanks to personal relationships between cis and trans feminists (see also DePalma, 2020). Platero and Ortega question the idea of a linear historical narrative of the achievement for each movement separately, since transwomen and transfeminist perspectives have long been part of the feminist movement.

Education regarding sex, gender and sexuality is an additional but closely connected theme. LGBTIQ+ and feminist activists have engaged in the field of education to promote anti-sexist and sexual diversity values, by developing resources and materials for teachers and schools. Organisations have elaborated teaching materials and guides, carried out research on bullying, and participated in the creation of educational protocols. Some initiatives focus particularly on social awareness, support and inclusion of gender diverse children. However, such activities have become very controversial, attacked by Conservative and religious movements that achieve a lot of media attention. Through a variety of actions, these warn that children will be imposed "sexual indoctrination" and a "gender ideology", which in turn threatens Catholic values (DePalma, 2020).

7.6 27.6 Repertoires of action

The academic literature of the period 2010-2021 addresses only tangentially the issue of the feminist movement repertoires of action and these are normally dealt with in relation to the differences between generations of feminist activists (Martínez, 2018, 2019; Portos, 2019; Galdón Gorbella, 2019 y 2021).

In analysing the 15M movement, researchers identify new repertoires of action such as the public camps, the assemblies and the use of social media. Martínez (2018) notes that, in spite of the 15M ambivalences with regard to feminism, activists of the 15M Feminist Commissions underlined that the internal functioning of the movement was intrinsically feminist, for its faith on deliberative process, horizontal structures and caring relationships. Besides, both the 15M movement and the 'Mareas' are

identified as spaces that politicised new sectors of the population, especially young people, and that helped build bridges between different groups and generations of feminist activists (Galdón Gorbella, 2018, 2019; Portos, 2019).

Public gatherings, marches and demonstrations, manifestos and lobbying work are prevailing action strategies for the whole feminist movement. However, researchers highlight that young feminists' experiences tend to be more sensorial and experience-based, and that is the reason why they also deployed repertoires such as performances, ladyfests, publication of fanzines, squatting, etc. (Portos, 2019; Martínez, 2019). In general, young feminists criticised that the older generation is too maximalist, too focused on rights and on engaging with formal institutions, too reactive and little combative and innovative. Notwithstanding, the different generations have united in the different waves of protests, main campaigns or events of the period: the 15M movement, the campaign against the Gallardon's abortion bill, to the 7N mobilisations, the #Yosítecreo mobilisations, and the celebration of international days such as the International Day against all forms of violence (25N), International Womens' Day (8M), International Safe Abortion Day (28S), or International Domestic Workers Day (30M).

A new repertoire of action stands out in this period: the use of the general strike by women, one that comprises not only a labour and students strike, but also a consumption and, more importantly, a care strike.

When analysing participants' profiles of more recent feminist mobilisations, Martínez (2020b) has found that it is more and more common to find "individual activists" that do not engage in any organisation or group but anyway display a feminist consciousness. This new diffuse feminist consciousness" (Martínez, 2019: 124) that is not produced necessarily within organisations and groups is created through the participation in collective actions and online social networks (Sola et al., 2021; Willem & Tortajada, 2021). Moreover, the recent COVID-19 pandemic has had an impact on the ways through which the feminist movement mobilises, strengthening social networks and this type of "weak" identification (Gatti, 2007 cited in Martínez, 2020b). Public massive gatherings, prevailing strategies of the movement, were prohibited during the pandemic: in fact, the 8M 2021 mobilisations were banned. Nonetheless, feminist movements managed to keep on going with their activity in this period under the slogan "Confined but active" ("Confinadas pero combativas") (Martínez, 2020b).

Social media, particularly Twitter, Facebook and Instagram, have had a prevailing role in keeping feminists "active". But the use of social media can be traced back to the 15M movement and has been key in every mobilisation of the period. With the use of hashtags such as #Yositecreo (2017), #HaciaLaHuelgaFeminista (2018), #LasPeriodistasParamos (2018), the Spanish feminist movement started implementing a communication and denunciation strategy which was made globally popular by the #MeToo movement. But the use of social media as a mobilising strategy has the counterpart that both feminist and anti-feminist movements share the same space and their narratives co-exist and contradict themselves at the same time (Willem & Tortajada, 2021). In the case of the Spanish feminist movement, online hate speeches and attacks from the anti-feminist and anti-gender movement are very frequent. Despite this, the use of social media has helped to unify the movement allowing young feminist to get involved in mobilizations and enabling a space for intersectional demands to arise (Willem & Tortajada, 2021).

As regards the relationship between feminism and institutions, the movement has deployed lobbying strategies and traditional denunciation campaigns to impact political institutions and political decision makers in topics related to abortion, gender-based violence, domestic work. In some cases, protests and negotiations have been aimed to prevent legal reforms that would harm women's rights to be passed, such as Gallardon's abortion bill. In other cases, their objective has been to demand legal reforms that would take into account feminist claims, as it has been the case in the reform of the Gender Violence Law, the approval of the State Pact Against Sexist Violences, the ratification of the ILO Convention 189 or the Popular Legislative Initiative for the regularisation of migrants residing in Spain. In brief, the Spanish feminist movement combines extra-institutional actions and institutional actions (Portos, 2019).

Although emotions play a significant role in social movements in general, and specifically in the case of the feminist movement, there is little academic literature that addresses this issue in Spain. Emotions such as rage, injustice, sorority and unity can be identified triggering different types of collective actions. In the 7N or the Manada protests, rage, anger and the feeling of injustice have undoubtedly been predominant.

7.7 27.7 Frames of arguments

There is not much feminist movement literature on “frames”. Notably, frame analysis seems more common in the analyses of gender equality policies than in the field of feminist movement. As an example, Alonso and Paleo (2017) analyse frames in relation to the question of abortion, but the main focus falls on public policies and the conservative attempts to reframe the issue and restrain reproductive rights. Nevertheless, several of the sources explore related aspects such as discourses, narratives, argumentation, and key concepts. Some studies focus on the development, (re)framing and (re)appropriation of specific concepts, for example *cuidanía/care-tizenship* (Casas-Cortes, 2019), and the *Manada/wolf-pack* (Romano, 2022). Other studies highlight narratives, ideas and discourses when analysing alliances and coalition-building, connecting different collectives, generations, grievances, movements, etc. (e.g. Garofalo Geymonat et al., 2021; Platero & Ortega-Arjonilla 2016; Portos 2019; Chironi & Portos 2021). In this vein, for example, Garofalo Geymonat et al. (2021) highlight the role of converging discourses in creating alliances between the feminist and domestic workers’ movement.

The frames of arguments depend on the specific theme, although such thematic differences in frames are not explored in the literature. In the field of labour market issues, the literature indicates that the argumentation draws on concepts related to care, precarity, vulnerability and sustainability of life, in the context of neoliberalism and austerity. The struggles of domestic workers have also involved these elements while linking them to migrant and workers’ rights and intersectionality. That the framing of this issue of domestic workers’ rights is linked to precarity and care work may have contributed to successful coalition-building.

In the field of sexual and reproductive rights, the literature shows that main arguments have centred around the right to choose, framing this as a fundamental right and freedom. Coalition-building across different collectives and generations was successful in this context. Subsequent feminist mobilizations framed gender violence as a broad and inclusive concept, going beyond men’s violence against women in intimate relationships to encompass dimensions such as sexual violence, harassment, and abuse, including both physical and psychological violence. Indeed, feminist debates on sexual violence re-defined and amplified the meaning of gender violence. Overall, gender violence has been framed as structural within the patriarchal system.

Chironi and Portos (2021) underline that feminist struggles have integrated LGTBQ+ activists, migrants, precarious workers, students, disabled people, etc. They argue that intersectional feminism emerged as unity of action between oppressed subjectivities. In addition, common grievances were articulated in the context of austerity, facilitating intersectional alliances and collaborations between different environments of the movement. Portos (2019) emphasises that younger feminists have contributed to the inclusion of ‘other’ voices, paying attention to overlapping systems of privilege and disadvantage, related to race, ethnic origin, class, and disability etc. As Marques Gonçalves and Willem (2021) show, Romani women’s struggles is an example of intersectional feminism.

Vulnerability has been part of the discourse on care, precarity and interdependence. Martinez (2018) argues that this concept has been used by some feminist in forging a ‘new’ unitary subject of feminism: the vulnerable subject. The author underlines that policies against gender violence in Spain are identity policies in the sense that they address women as a homogeneous group, assuming that any woman may potentially suffer from gender violence. It is precisely the assumed link between violence, victimhood, femininity, and vulnerability that shapes the new subject of some feminisms. Here, diversity among women is largely ignored.

Current struggles for trans people's rights raise issues regarding the deconstruction of gender and the subject of feminism. While intersectionality has been framed as vital, it is also contested. Part of the feminist movement, rejects the legitimacy of transfeminist struggles, in spite of the fact that transfeminist perspectives have long been part of the feminist movement (Platero & Ortega, 2016).

The debates within the movement can partly be understood as generational divisions. Portos (2019) argues that veteran feminists tend to link feminist identities to citizenship and women's rights, while younger feminists have embraced queer perspectives and are consequently more open to transfeminism. While the older generation of feminists is more closely connected to state feminism and political institutions, transfeminism has been articulated more as an autonomous movement using different repertoires of action (Nuñez Puente, 2016).

7.8 Key policy related outcomes

7.8.1 Care and Labour Market

The 2018 and 2019 8M strikes pushed the issue of care work onto the mainstream political agenda. Later on, the Covid-19 pandemic would also contribute to the visibility of care issues.

7.8.2 Policies improving domestic workers' rights

The campaign for the dignification of domestic work successfully put paid domestic and care work on the agenda. In the last decade, several policy changes have been achieved to strengthen domestic workers rights. Law 27/2011 updated the National Social Security System and included domestic workers, who until then had been excluded. The Royal Decree 1620/2011 created a special labour rights regime for domestic workers, which partly equalised domestic workers with other workers (Gonalons-Pons, 2022). Improvements involved aspects such as pensions, temporary disability, minimum wages, sickness benefits and working time. Minimum time of rest between workdays, recognition of 'presence time' as paid work, and delimitation of payments in kind were relevant changes for live-in workers. However, the reforms did not solve problems such as the precariousness of live-in workers, the lack of right to unemployment benefit, and the possibility of contract termination based on the employers' subjective loss of confidence.

The discrimination of domestic workers was recognized by the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) in a historic ruling in February 2022. The Court of Justice of the European Union ruled that denying domestic workers the right to unemployment was discrimination on the basis of gender. It was considered contrary to the European Directive on Equal Treatment between Men and Women in terms of Social Security. In consequence, the Spanish Congress of Deputies ratified the ILO Convention on decent work for domestic workers in June 2022 and the Royal Decree for the improvement of working conditions and social security for domestic workers was passed in September 2022.

7.8.3 Policies on equal and non-transferable parental leaves

Feminist lobbying for equal and non-transferable parental leaves has been successful. Demands have been articulated by feminist academics and activists. Particularly, the Platform for Equal, Non-Transferable Parental Leaves (Plataforma por los Permisos Iguales e Intransferibles de Nacimiento y Adopción, PPIINA) managed to get the support of left-wing political parties (Kantola & Lombardo, 2019).

The Gender Equality Law introduced a non-transferable two-week paternity leave in 2007. Since then, paternity has been expanded several times. In 2016, the Spanish Parliament approved a motion to make maternity and paternity leaves (now called Birth and Child Care leaves) non-transferable and of equal length, which would be achieved through incremental increases in paternity leave (Campillo, 2018). Eventually, in January 2021, it reached 16 weeks, thereby equalising the duration of the maternity leave. Social security contributions for a certain period of time is required to be eligible for a leave with a 100% wage compensation. There is a non-contributory maternity allowance for young people who do not fulfil the minimum contribution period.

7.8.4 New care leaves in the Families Act

Seeking to "guarantee the right to conciliation", the Government is currently preparing a Families Act, which among other things is expected to include rights related to caring for family members. This bill is promoted by the Ministry of Social Rights and includes the right to up to nine days of paid leave a year to care for family members. The preliminary draft has been approved by the Council of Ministers (El Diario, 2022).

7.8.5 Abortion

The Socialist government adopted a progressive abortion law in 2010 (Law 2/2010), which made abortion legal and accessible to women aged 16 or more during the first 14 weeks of pregnancy. However, in the following legislature, the bill presented by conservative Minister of Justice Alberto Ruiz-Gallardón posed a threat to women's fundamental rights and health (Lombardo, 2017). Massive feminist contestation forced the withdrawal of the proposal in 2014, and the resignation of Ruiz-Gallardón (Portos, 2019). However, the Conservative government adopted a smaller reform of the 2010 abortion law that restricted the rights of girls under 18, who from then on needed their parents' consent to be able to have an abortion. This requirement was recently removed by the coalition government.

7.8.6 Gender-based violence

The creation of a State Pact Against Gender Violence

Gender violence was consolidated as a policy field with the unanimous approval of the Gender Violence Law in 2004 (Cabezas, 2022b). Internationally, the policy was regarded as groundbreaking given its comprehensive character, but the truth is the definition of gender violence was limited to violence perpetrated against women by their male partner or ex-partner and was, therefore, considered reductionist by many feminists (Cabezas, 2022b). As López (2015) argues, the definition implies limits to how the problem can be addressed, as institutional actions protect only those who are recognised as victims of gender violence. Rape, sexual assault, trafficking, and sexual harassment were not included. The ratification of the Istanbul Convention in 2014 spurred further feminist claims-making on the inclusion of other forms of gender violence, such as the 7N campaign of 2015 and 2016. Its success led the Parliament to negotiate and approve a State Pact Against Gender Violence in September 2017, even if it was not provided with funding until Pedro Sanchez's government came to power (Campillo, 2019, 2018; Chironi & Portos, 2021; Portos, 2019). Meanwhile, Vox opposes gender violence policies and measures, arguing that the law is discriminatory against men. They do not refer to gender violence but domestic violence (Cabezas, 2022a, 2022b).

Adoption of the 'only yes is yes' law

As Chironi and Portos (2021) argue, the Manada case shows the close association between feminist mobilisation and legal frameworks and court rulings. In 2018, after the massive protests related to the case, all political groups agreed on a revision of the categorization of sexual offences that dated from 1995. The right-wing government at the time began a process of reviewing the penal code which defined sexual assault as requiring serious physical harm or death (Abrisketa & Abrisketa, 2020). In 2022, under the coalition government, the Law of Sexual Freedom was elaborated and approved by the Parliament, with 205 votes in favour and 141 against. Now the distinction between abuse and rape is eliminated and the need for expressed consent in sexual relations is established. Consent must be freely expressed through acts that, considering the circumstances of the case, clearly express the will of the person. As such, the law defines consent in terms of 'only yes is yes' as in the feminist slogan. Aggression is redefined from focusing on the presence of intimidation and/or violence to focusing on consent. Romano (2022) emphasises that the new law shifts the focus from the victim's behaviour to the aggressors' responsibility.

The reform was the result of feminist demands. At the same time, the right-wing PP argues that the law endangers the presumption of innocence, and VOX goes even further. Vox deputy Carla Toscano has stated that “the objective of this law is not to protect women, it is to destroy men” (Euronews, 2022). Even though the law entered into force in October 2022, the implementation has already led to controversy due to undesired consequences, namely reduced sentences for some convicted men.

LGTBI & Trans rights

Social and feminist movements have been successful in advancing the rights of LGBTBI rights in recent decades. When same-sex marriage was introduced in 2005, Spain was highlighted in international media for advancing in LGBTBIQ+ rights and equality (Platero Méndez, 2007). The approval of the Gender Identity Law in 2007 allowed trans people to change the name and sex on their IDs, provided they had a diagnosis of gender dysphoria and two years of hormone treatment. Since then, the LGBTBI and trans movement has definitely entered mainstream agenda-setting (Platero 2020) and advocated for gender self-determination in alliance with political parties. The movement achieved the adoption of 19 regional LGBTBI and/or trans laws, 16 of which recognised the right to gender self-determination. A state regulation became the following step, especially after the formation of the new left-wing coalition government.

The government bill of the LGBTBI and Trans Law stated the aim of expanding the rights of trans individuals. Negotiations, however, were difficult given the divisions within the coalition government, between part of the PSOE and UP. Gender self-determination, especially in under 16s, was a key point of conflict. Part of the feminist movement and some feminists in the Socialist Party mobilised against the law, framing trans rights as a backlash on women’s rights (Platero & Ortega, 2016; Platero, 2020).

7.9 Conclusion

In the past decade, the feminist movement has shaped political agendas, policies and politics in Spain. Thereby, feminism has made a vital contribution to democracy. The feminist movement is diverse, constituted by social movements, equality/women’s secretariats of left-wing parties and unions, institutional feminism, academic feminism, and third sector organisations. However, autonomous and locally-based groups form the core of the movement. The repertoires of action are varied and context-bound, including public gatherings, marches and demonstrations, manifestos and lobbying work, but also performances, ladyfests, etc. While social media has been key in every mobilisation in the last decade, it was crucial for activism to continue during the pandemic.

Feminist campaigns related to the right to choose and against gender violence involved several massive demonstrations across the country and achieved coalition-building across generations. Feminist debates and mobilisations framed gender violence as a multifaceted problem, highlighting its structural nature and making visible the dimension of sexual violences. Bridging socio-economic demands and feminist claims, feminist activism also drew on and contributed to the anti-austerity discourses by gendering precarity and highlighting the issue of care on the agenda. Advocacy related to the labour market has included claims for dignification of domestic and care work and for a social reorganisation of care. Policy impact is evident in the fields of reproductive rights, gender violence and domestic and care work. Migration issues have been less salient, although migrant women have been active in advocacy surrounding domestic workers’ rights. The LGBTBIQ+ movement has historically been closely interconnected with the feminist movement, but the Trans Act is currently dividing feminists with different approaches to gender and intersectionality.

Most of the academic literature on the feminist movements of the period has focused on the 15M and the feminist strikes, but the mobilisations in between as well as the feminist controversies that have burst in the last four years have been barely explored. Apart from this, other blind spots remain. First of all, there is a lack of clear analysis of composition, organisational models, repertoires of action, frames, and democratic innovation. Secondly, the consequences of the feminist movement, and especially its strategies and negotiations to influence the decision making process, have not been

studied in depth. Finally, even if intersectionality and anti-feminist anti-gender discourses are gaining relevance in research, there is a lack of analysis on how feminist social movements introduce intersectionality (Filigrana, 2020), how they react against the rise of anti-feminist groups and discourses (Cabezas, 2021) or how they are readapting their actions to the social media after the COVID-19 pandemic (Martínez, 2020b; Willem & Tortajada, 2021).

7.10 References

- Abrisketa, O. G. & Abrisketa, M. G. (2020). Sisterhood as public feminism in Spain. *Signs: Journal of Women in Culture and Society*, 45(4).
- Alabao, N. (coord.) (2018). *Un feminismo del 99%*. Madrid: Lengua de Trapo
- Alabao, N. & Pérez Colina, M. (2019, February 6). ¿Quién quiere romper el movimiento feminista?. *Ctxt Contexto y Acción*. <https://ctxt.es/es/20190206/Firmas/24296/Nuria-Alabao-Maria-Perez-Colina-conflicto-movimiento-feminista-abolicionistas-PSOE.html>
- Alonso, A. (2015). Las políticas de género en España: Retrocesos y resistencias en tiempos de austeridad. *ex aequo - Revista da Associação Portuguesa de Estudos sobre as Mulheres*, 32. <https://doi.org/10.22355/exaequo.2015.32.03>
- Alonso, A., & Paleo Mosquera, N. (2017). Políticas de salud sexual y reproductiva en España: Contramovimientos y marcos interpretativos en conflicto. *Revista Española de Sociología*, 26(3 Suplemento), 59-76. <https://doi.org/10.22325/fes/res.2017.35>
- Astelarra, J. (2005). *Veinte años de políticas de igualdad*. Madrid: Cátedra.
- Bernárdez R., A. & Padilla C., G. (2019). Liderazgo feminista en hashtags: etiquetas virales del nuevo debate político y social en España. In *The Time is Now. Feminist Leadership for a New Era*. México: UNESCO.
- Boix, M. (2001). El tratamiento de la violencia hacia las mujeres en los medios de comunicación, I Congreso Nacional sobre la Violencia contra la Mujer, Gijón, 11, 12 y 13 octubre.
- Bustelo, M. (2004). *La evaluación de las políticas de género en España*. Madrid: Catarata
- Bustelo, M. (2016). Three Decades of State Feminism and Gender Equality Policies in Multi-governed Spain. *Sex Roles*, 74(3-4). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-014-0381-9>
- Cabezas, A. (2021). Los feminismos ante la nueva extrema derecha: prácticas de acuerpe y sororidades estratégicas para la construcción de un horizonte de equidad e igualdad. *Encrucijadas*, 21(2), 1–11.
- Cabezas, A. (2022a). Silencing feminism? Gender and the rise of the nationalist far right in Spain. *Signs: Journal of Women in Culture and Society*, 47(2), 319-345.
- Cabezas, A. (2022b). Patriarchal Authoritarianism Reloaded: Gender Violence, Policy Conflict, and the Resurgence of the Far Right in Spain. *Political and Legal Anthropology Review*, 45(1), 56-76. <https://doi.org/10.1111/plar.12484>
- Campillo, I. (2013). *¿Adiós al familiarismo? Las políticas de conciliación de la vida laboral y familiar en España, 1997-2010*. 1-350, Tesis Doctoral, Universidad Complutense de Madrid.
- Campillo, I. (2018). *Economic Boom, Recession and Recovery in Spain: The Permanent Care Crisis and its Effects on Gender Equality. The Search for Feminist Alternatives*. Rosa Luxemburg Stiftung.
- Campillo, I. (2019). 'If we stop, the world stops': The 2018 feminist strike in Spain. *Social Movement Studies*, 18(2), 252-258. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14742837.2018.1556092>
- Casas-Cortes M. (2019). Care-tizenship: Precarity, social movements, and the deleting/re-writing of citizenship. *Citizenship Studies*, 23(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/13621025.2018.1556248>

- Chironi, D., & Portos, M. (2021). 'Together we stand': Coalition-building in the Italian and Spanish feminist movements in times of crisis. *European Journal of Politics and Gender*, 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.1332/251510821X16135837027525>
- Cruells, M., & Ezquerro, S. (2015). Procesos de voluntad democratizadora: La expresión feminista en el 15-M. *ACME: An International E-Journal for Critical Geographies*, 14(1), 42–60.
- Dean, J., & Aune, K. (2015). Feminist resurgent? Mapping contemporary feminist activism in Europe. *Social Movements Studies*, 14(4), 375–395.
- DePalma, R. (2020). Education as Activism: Sexual Dissidence and Schooling in Spain. In *Queer Social Movements and Outreach Work in Schools*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-41610-2_6
- El Diario (2022, December 13). El Gobierno aprueba el anteproyecto de ley de Familias que otorga hasta nueve días remunerados al año para cuidados. *Eldiario.es*. https://www.eldiario.es/sociedad/gobierno-aprueba-anteproyecto-ley-familias-otorga-nueve-dias-remunerados-ano-cuidados_1_9789235.html (accessed 19 Dec.).
- El País (2016, August 11). El número de diputadas aumenta al ritmo de una parlamentaria por año. *Elpais.com*. https://elpais.com/politica/2016/08/10/actualidad/1470853793_524496.html (accessed 19 Jan. 2023)
- Escario, P., Alberdi, I., & López-Accotto, A. I. (1996). *Lo personal es político: el movimiento feminista en la transición*. Madrid: Instituto de la Mujer.
- Euronews (2022, August 26). España aprueba la ley del "solo sí es sí". *Euronews.com*. <https://es.euronews.com/2022/08/26/espana-aprueba-la-ley-del-solo-si-es-si> (accessed 19 Dec. 2022)
- Europa Press (2022, September 27). Feministas entregan 24 enmiendas ley trans – interfiere derechos conquistados mujeres. *Europapress.es*. <https://www.europapress.es/sociedad/noticia-feministas-entregan-24-enmiendas-ley-trans-interfiere-derechos-conquistados-mujeres-20220927185146.html>
- Fernández, J. (2019, December 18). "Es un problema que el feminismo parezca una suma de individualidades". *Pikara Magazine*. <https://www.pikaramagazine.com/2019/12/es-un-problema-que-el-feminismo-parezca-una-suma-de-individualidades/> (accessed 11 Nov. 2022)
- Filigrana, P. (2020). Anti-racist Feminism or Barbarism. *South Atlantic Quarterly*, 119(3). <https://doi.org/10.1215/00382876-8601470>
- Gámez Fuentes, M. J. (2015). Feminisms and the 15M Movement in Spain: Between Frames of Recognition and Contexts of Action. *Social Movement Studies*, 14(3), 359-365. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14742837.2014.994492>
- Galdón Corbella, C. (2018). Cosmovisiones feministas en clave generacional. Del movimiento 15M a la Huelga Feminista del 8M. *Encrucijadas - Revista Crítica de Ciencias Sociales*, 16(0).
- Galdón Corbella, C. (2019). Del movimiento 15M a la huelga feminista del 8M. Un recorrido y algunas claves para entender el presente del movimiento feminista. In R. Díaz García y G. Betancor Nuez (Eds.), *Movimientos sociales, acción colectiva y cambio social en perspectiva. Continuidades y cambios en el estudio de los movimientos sociales* (pp. 87-100). Abadiño: Fundación Betiko.
- Galdón Corbella, C. (2021). "Cuando confluyamos, influimos". Una aproximación a la idea de unidad en el activismo feminista contemporáneo. *Empiria. Revista de Metodología de Ciencias Sociales*, 52(Sept-Dic), 125–150. <https://doi.org/DOI/empiria.52.2021.31367>
- García, B., Alabao, N., & Pérez, M. (2018). Spain's feminist strike. *New Left Review*, 110, 35–37.
- Geymonat, G. G., Cherubini, D., & Marchetti, S. (2021). The feminist and domestic workers' movements: Disconnected practices, discursive convergences. *European Journal of Politics and Gender*, 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.1332/251510821X16125208512228>

Gil, S. L. (2011). *Nuevos feminismos. Sentidos comunes en la dispersión. Una historia de trayectorias y rupturas en el Estado español*. Madrid: Traficantes de Sueños.

Gonalons-Pons, P (2022). *Servants of Production: The Politics of Domestic Workers' Labor Rights*. *Social Politics: International Studies in Gender, State and Society*, 29(3) Fall 2022, pp. 932-954.

Kantola, J., & Lombardo, E. (2019). *Populism and feminist politics: The cases of Finland and Spain*. *European Journal of Political Research*, 58(4), 1108-1128. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1475-6765.12333>

León, M. (2013). *A real job? Regulating household work: the case of Spain*, *European Journal of Women's Studies*, 2(2): 170–88.

León, M. (2016). *The Quest for Gender Equality*. In A. N. Guillén & M. León (Eds.), *Re-writing women as victims : from theory to practice* (pp. 98–111). *The Spanish Welfare State in European Context* (pp. 75-89). Abingdon: Routledge.

Liedo, B. (2022). *Juntas y revueltas: La sororidad en el feminismo contemporáneo*. *RECERCA. Revista de Pensament i Anàlisi*. <https://doi.org/10.6035/recerca.6539>

Lombardo, E. (2004). *La europeización de la política española de igualdad de género*. *Revista Española de Ciencia Política*, 9, 63-80.

Lombardo, E. (2017). *Austerity Politics and Feminist Struggles in Spain: Reconfiguring the Gender Regime?* In *Gender and the Economic Crisis in Europe* (pp. 209-230). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-50778-1_10

Lombardo, E. & Bustelo, M. (2012). *Political Approaches to Inequalities in Southern Europe: A Comparative Analysis of Italy, Portugal, and Spain*. *Social Politics: International Studies in Gender, State & Society*, 19 (4), 572–595. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sp/jxs019>

Lombardo, E., & León, M. (2014). *Políticas de igualdad de género y sociales en España: Origen, desarrollo y desmantelamiento en un contexto de crisis económica*. *Investigaciones Feministas*, 5(0). https://doi.org/10.5209/rev_infe.2014.v5.47986

López, S. (2015). *Relatos que condicionan experiencias: Implicaciones de los relatos de las políticas públicas sobre violencia contra las mujeres y aborto en España*. *Revista de Estudios Políticos*, 167: 165-191.

Manifiesto 8M (2018). Retrieved from <http://hacialahuelgafeminista.org/manifiesto-8m/>

Marques Gonçalves, G., & Willem, C. (2021). *Lucha feminista gitana en España, lucha interseccional: El combate contra el Antigitanismo en las redes sociales en España*. *Investigaciones Feministas*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.5209/infe.69520>

Martinez, M. (2017). *Troisième vague, transféminismes et la question générationnelle: Reconfigurations des féminismes dans l'Espagne contemporaine*. In K. Bergès, F. Binard, & A. Guyard-Nedelec (Eds.), *Féminismes du XXIe siècle: Une troisième vague?* (pp. 75-85). Rennes: Presses universitaires de Rennes. <https://doi.org/10.3917/pur.berges.2017.01.0075>

Martínez, M. (2018a). *La revolución será feminista o no será: reflections on feminisms and the 15M*. In B. Tejerina Montaña & I. Perugorría (Eds.), *Crisis and social mobilization in contemporary Spain: the 15M movement* (pp. 73–94). New York: Routledge.

Martinez, M. (2018b). *From the subjected subject to the vulnerable subject: An unfinished discussion in contemporary Spanish feminisms*. *Signs*, 43(2). <https://doi.org/10.1086/693548>

Martínez, M. (2019). *Identidades en proceso. Una propuesta a partir del análisis de las movilizaciones feministas contemporáneas*, Madrid: Centro de Investigaciones Sociológicas.

- Martínez, M. (2020a). Collective actions and organisation against gender violence in Spain: when victims became activists. In M. J. Gámez Fuentes, S. Núñez Puente, & E. Gómez Nicolau (Eds.), *Rewriting women as victims : from theory to practice* (pp. 98–111). Abingdon: Routledge.
- Martínez, M. (2020b). Feminismos en España en tiempos de pandemia: Entre continuidades y mutaciones. In *Anuario de Movimientos Sociales*. Fundación Betiko. http://fundacionbetiko.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/anuario_2020_maria_martinez.pdf
- Martínez-Conde, C. Á., Boteman, C. E. R., Leal, K. F., & Montenegro, M. (2020). Memories of the struggles for the rights of immigrant women in Barcelona. *Critical Social Policy*, 40(2), 215–233. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0261018319895499>
- Méndez, R. P. (2007). The Limits of Equality The Intersectionality of Gender and Sexuality in Spanish Policy Making. *Kvinder, Køn & Forskning*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.7146/kkf.v0i1.27937>
- Núñez Puente, S. (2016). Activism Trouble: Transfeminism and Institutional Feminism in Spain. *Feminist Formations*, 28(2). <https://doi.org/10.1353/ff.2016.0026>
- Peterson, E. (2018). ‘Struggles for recognition and redistribution: family carers and domestic workers in Spanish eldercare’. *International Journal of Care and Caring*, 2(4), 459–76. <https://doi.org/10.1332/239788218X15411481093113>
- Platero, L. R., & Ortega-Arjonilla, E. (2016). Building coalitions: The interconnections between feminism and trans* activism in Spain. *Journal of Lesbian Studies*, 20(1), 46-64. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10894160.2015.1076235>
- Platero, R. (2011). The narratives of transgender rights mobilization in Spain. *Sexualities*, 14(5), 597–614. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1363460711415336>
- Platero, R. L. (2020). Redistribution and recognition in Spanish transgender laws. *Politics and Governance*, 8(3), 253-263. <https://doi.org/10.17645/pag.v8i3.2856>
- Platero, R. & Guzmán, P. (2014). The critical intersections of disability and non-normative sexualities in Spain. *Annual Review of Critical Psychology*, 11(March), 357-387.
- Portos, M. (2019). Divided We Stand, (Oftentimes) United We Fight: Generational Bridging in Spain’s Feminist Movement and the Cycle of Antiausterity Mobilizations. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 63(10). <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764219831730>
- Razquin, (2019). Etnografía del impulso feminista y la deriva patriarcal en las asambleas del movimiento 15M. In R. Díaz García y G. Betancor Nuez (Eds.), *Movimientos sociales, acción colectiva y cambio social en perspectiva*. Continuidades y cambios en el estudio de los movimientos sociales (pp. 73-86). Abadiño: Fundación Betiko.
- Romano, M. (2022). Occupying the streets, occupying words. Reframing new feminisms through reappropriation. *Discourse and Society*, 33(5), 631-649. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09579265221093649>
- Rosón, M. & Garballo-Maeztu, M. (2021, January 20). “Algunos debates niegan una realidad: la incorporación de las mujeres trans a la lucha feminista”. *Ctxt Contexto y Acción*. <https://ctxt.es/es/20220101/Politica/38478/feminismos-justa-montero-historia-aborto-maria-rososon-maite-garbayo.htm>
- Sandu, A., & Fernández, V. P. (2021). The Fight goes on! Intersections of Oppression in the Spanish Feminist Movement. *Journal of International Women’s Studies*, 22(9).
- Schulz, R., & González, M. A. C. (2020). Young feminist militancy in madrid post-15m. *Cuadernos Pagu*, 2020(58). <https://doi.org/10.1590/18094449202000580001>
- Sola Morales, S.; Hernández Conde, M.; Arencón Beltrán, S.; Sierra Caballero, F. (2022). Mitos e imaginarios del activismo digital feminista. Análisis de memes de la cibercampaña #FuckGenderRoles. *Teknokultura. Revista de Cultura Digital y Movimientos Sociales*, 18(1), 43-54. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5209/TEKN.76690>

Trujillo, G. (2009). Del sujeto político la Mujer a la agencia de las (otras) mujeres: El impacto de la crítica queer en el feminismo del Estado español. *Política y sociedad*, 46 (1), 161-172.

Trujillo, G. (2016). La protesta dentro de la protesta. Activismos queer/cuir y feministas en el 15M. *Encrucijadas. Revista Crítica de Ciencias Sociales*, 12, 1-18.

Threlfall, M. (1999). "¿Feminismo de Estado o feminismo de partido? Las estrategias políticas feministas", *Revista Internacional de Sociología*, 23 (Mayo-Agosto), 209-36.

Valiente, C. (1996). The rejection of authoritarian policy legacies: Family policy in Spain (1975–1995). *South European Society and Politics*, 1(1), 95-114. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13608749608454718>

Valiente, C. (2005), "The women's movement, gender equality agencies and central-state debates on political representation in Spain" en J. Lovenduski (Ed.), *State Feminism and Political Representation*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press: 174-94.

Watkins, S. (2018). Which feminisms? *New Left Review*, 110, 5–75.

Willem, C., & Tortajada, I. (2021). Gender, Voice and Online Space: Expressions of Feminism on Social Media in Spain. *Media and Communication*, 9(2), 62-71. <https://doi.org/10.17645/mac.v9i2.3851>

7.11 List of feminist movements' campaigns

Name of campaign (Spanish)	Name of campaign (English)	Issue addressed	Actors involved	Repertoire of action	Logo	Web-page	Comment
Por la dignificación del trabajo doméstico (2006-2022)	Dignifying domestic work	Labour market	Feminist movement, domestic workers associations, migrant associations, at trade unions	Feminist strikes, 8M demonstrations, public protest, national and international networks, national conference, social media, 30M protests		FB: https://www.facebook.com/territoriodomestico/?locale=es_ES FB: https://www.facebook.com/sedoac/	Campaign to equalise domestic workers' rights to other workers, demanding visibility and social re-organization of care
“Decidir nos hace libres” (Plataforma estatal en defensa de los derechos sexuales y reproductivos- 2012)	The right to decide makes us free (State Platform in defence of sexual and reproductive rights- 2012)	Reproductive rights	Feminist movement, associations, health related organisations,	Public demonstrations and protest, international networks and alliances, social media		Web: http://www.eltrendelalibertad.com/ Web: https://www.mujeresparalasalud.org/decidir-nos-hace-libres-nueva-campana-para-defender-los-derechos-sexuales-y-reproductivos/	Campaign against the abortion bill reform, pro right to choose

<p>7N contra las violencias machistas. No a las agresiones sexuales (2015-2016)</p>	<p>7N against sexist violence. No to sexual assaults.</p>	<p>Gender violence</p>	<p>Feminist movement, associations, civil society. (Parties, public institutions and municipalities).</p>	<p>Mass mobilizations and public protests, social media</p>		<p>Web: https://plataforma7n.wordpress.com</p>	<p>Campaign against gender violence, adopting an inclusive frame of gender violence, problems and solutions.</p>
<p>#RegularizaciónYa</p>	<p>#Regularization Now</p>	<p>Migration</p>	<p>Migrant and feminists movements, domestic workers associations</p>	<p>Popular Legislative Initiative, public protests, social media</p>		<p>Web: https://regularizacionya.com/</p>	<p>Campaign in favour of migrant residents in Spain demanding residence and work permits.</p>

<p>#ExigimosLaIgualdadTrans (2021)</p>	<p>#WeDemandTrans Equality</p>	<p>LGBTIQ+ rights</p>	<p>Trans and LGBTQ+ organizations (e.g. State Federation of Lesbians, Gays, Trans and Bisexuals - FELGTB)</p>	<p>Visibility campaigns (huge flag), public testimonies, social media campaigns, public protests</p>		<p>Web: https://exigimoslaigualdadtrans.org/</p>	<p>Campaign in defence of the Trans Bill that avoids the pathologizing of trans people and guarantees equal rights for LGTBIQ+ community.</p>
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8 TURKEY

8.1 Introduction

The literature on feminist movements in Turkey is wide and varied, reflecting the rich history of the movement in the country, especially since the 1980s.

The literature analyses the development and diversification of the movement in the 1980s and the 1990s. For this period, there is much written on the ways in which the movement has diversified along ethnic lines (Turkish-Kurdish), ideological/religious beliefs (secularism-Islam) and was able to achieve collaboration among these different stances through alliances on issues such as gender-based violence. These have resulted in successes in pushing for progressive policy and legislation changes in the early 2000s in the Criminal and Penal Codes as well as the preparation and signing of the Istanbul Convention and the relevant national violence against women code 6284 in 2011 and 2012 respectively.

The literature on the past ten years focuses on the regressive turn in the country. This is a period in which feminist and pro-feminist women's organizations have been marginalized and feminist activism is increasingly criminalized. This is a recent development on which writing is being currently produced. This scholarship shows the regressing of collaborative efforts across ideological lines given the current political polarization. The divides within the women's movement (not necessarily feminist) are often discussed in terms of conflictual identifications, many connected to existing polarizations: pro-anti government, Islamic-Secular, Sunni-Alevi, Turkish-Kurdish, trans exclusive-inclusive, and so on.

There is emphasis on the changing repertoires of action from intensive, institutionalized lobbying efforts to more contentious online and offline collective action in the absence of direct links to the government and the continuous efforts to build platforms that could bring different groups together. The scholarship also discusses a shift in policy goals from achieving progressive change to retaining changes already achieved. There is also some discussion of generational divides within the movement, but this latter theme is not voluminous, at least in scholarly writing.

The critical junctures brought up often include, for this recent period, 2011 participation in the preparation and signing of the Istanbul Convention, the preparation of the 2012 Law on Protection of the Family and Prevention of Violence against Women, the 2013 Gezi mobilizations, the national elections and the end of the peace process in 2015, the 2016 coup attempt and the declaration of state of emergency for two years, the 2017 referendum which changed the political regime, and the 2019 local elections. The repertoires of action exemplified for the contemporary context include indirect lobbying, street protests, discussion circles, petitioning, digital feminism, feminist knowledge production (regular reports, shadow reports etc.), trial watches, feminist litigations, and conducting funded projects for feminist advocacy.

In terms of the issue areas in this project, we see a prevalence of discussions on feminist mobilization against gender-based violence. This is followed closely by feminist mobilizations aiming to protect achieved rights in health and reproductive rights. While there are well developed literatures on the political economy of and labor market in Turkey from a feminist perspective as well as a voluminous, interdisciplinary literature on migration (especially the Syrian refugee crisis), there is much less on the connections between these issue areas and feminist mobilization. There is also some literature on LGBTQ+ movement in Turkey and their activisms, but the recent controversies around trans inclusiveness have not made their way into scholarly writing yet. Three additional issues of importance arise for the case of Turkey: feminist-anti-feminist confrontation in the legislation organizing alimony in case of dissolution of marriage; secularism-Islamism and the threats posed by the latter's institutionalization in the state policy making; and the ways in which the Kurdish issue is reflected in feminist mobilization's different groups.

8.2 The history of the feminist movements and its context

8.2.1 Genesis of the movement in 1980s

The genesis of the contemporary feminist movement is often traced back to the post-1980 coup in Turkey. The post-1980 military coup period is often described as a unique political opportunity structure: As the state repressed organized leftism, feminists saw a thinning of actors in the advocacy space, which they could fill, and faced a state, which, at that moment, did not see women's rights groups as an existential threat (Arat, 1994; Sirman, 1989; Tekeli, 1986, 1992). Some scholars call the feminist mobilization that emerged in this moment second wave feminism because of its affinity with what was happening in North America and Europe in terms of priorities, activities, organizational strategies, and interactions with the state. They explain their conceptualization of the second wave in terms of post-coup state repression of organized leftism, value changes, and the disillusionment with state-centred reforms (Ozcurumez & Sayan-Cengiz, 2011). Others, however, point to major contextual differences in the Turkish case, a country which was just starting its path toward building a neoliberal state and neoliberal economy during this period (Coşar & Özkan-Kerestecioğlu, 2017).

Empirical work does show that, during the 1980s, identity- and social rights-based advocacy continued in tandem with one another (Coşar & Özkan-Kerestecioğlu, 2017). Tekeli (1992) also argues that these feminists eschewed nationalism and tended towards gender universalism. This tendency was unique, when compared with most movements in the Third World or in the Middle East, where questions of colonialism, national identity, and their interaction with the woman's question continued to play a central role (Tekeli, 1992). Part of the reason might be found in the background of the intellectual leaders of the movement. Regarding the feminist pioneers of early 1980s, Coşar and Özkan-Kerestecioğlu (2017) mention their background as writers and translators which was reflected in the plethora of magazines published at the end of the 1980s such as *Yeter*, *Feminist*, and *Sosyalist Feminist Kaktüs*. They engaged in collective translations from European feminist literature to Turkish and appropriated concepts such as patriarchal domination, sexism, gender inequality, and positive discrimination. They engaged with international networks, experienced first-hand transnational feminist solidarity and witnessed the relative success of their European counterparts in terms of organizing against and raising public awareness of gender inequality (Tekeli, 1992).

In terms of organization, in the early 1980s these feminist pioneers leaned toward a spontaneous, autonomous, non-hierarchical, voluntary and small groups format. Some groups were established solely for consciousness raising, others aimed at ideological exchanges, collective translations, and publishing (Düzkan & Ahıska, 1994; Tekeli, 1986). Sirman (1989) acknowledges Western feminist influences behind this organizational approach though she says several contextually specific factors also rationalized it: organizing on an "ad hoc" basis, feminists could boost their independence from established ideologies such as orthodox leftism and state feminism. Ahıska and Düzkan (1994) admit that, except for temporary and periodic campaigns which united activists from different groups around a single issue, small groups fulfilled feminists' organizational needs for this period. Furthermore, several authors saw in this pluralistic and decentralized organization the constitution of the most-advanced democratic impulse in civil society (Arat, 1994; Tekeli, 2010). Several studies also identify the use of classical social movement repertoire such as lobbying, press statements, petitioning, faxing, and demonstrations to achieve state reform, particularly legislative changes regarding women's equal status and bodily rights (Arat, 1994, 2009; Tekeli, 1986, 1992, 2010).

One of the important focal areas in this initial period was violence against women (Acuner, 2002; Işık, 2002; Sirman, 1989). As Alnıaçık (2022) explains, the movement activists framed male violence against women as a common condition for all women and one that could be seen as evidence of "women's oppression as a sex." After an initial mobilization around the problem of "wife-beating," feminists first sought to expand the meaning of gendered violence through a campaign against sexual harassment in streets, public transportation, and work places ("*Bedenimiz bizimdir! Cinsel tacize hayır! Kampanyası*," 1989) and then concentrated their efforts at building feminist-minded anti-violence institutions and changing the state's legal and institutional response to domestic violence (Bora & Günal, 2002; Işık, 2002; Tekeli, 1992; Yüksel, 1995).

Several studies define the initiators of the feminist movement in the early 1980s as urban, middle-class, well-educated, and mostly middle-aged professional women, who had been involved in leftist activism before the 1980's military coup (Arat, 1994, 2009; Tekeli, 1986, 1992). These women embraced different variants of feminism such as socialist feminism and radical feminism (Arat, 2009). The urge for independence from the state and organized leftism and their vocal disillusionment from both united these feminists with different persuasions (Ozcurumez & Sayan-Cengiz, 2011). In these studies, focusing on the genesis of the movement, the year 1989 marks a critical juncture (Bora & Günal, 2002; Tekeli, 1992). Following the two events in 1989 - 1st Feminist Weekend (Ankara) and 1st Women's Convention (İstanbul), Bora and Günal (2002) point to the waning of enthusiasm and excitement among women's groups, the inflaming of political and ideological confrontations, and the increasing need for establishing permanent structures.

8.2.2 Blooming of the movement: the 1990s and 2000s

Moving onto the 1990s, scholars agree that this decade witnessed two coeval trends. First, women's groups with different persuasions created new claims for women's rights and gender equality. Second, many authors describe it as the period of institutionalization (Bora & Günal, 2002). This concept can be defined in three interrelated ways: inception of new civil society organizations, formalizing feminist networks; successful inroads into the state policy and law-making spheres; and the expansion of what is often called "project feminism."

In terms of civil society organizations, the most concrete outcome of the feminist campaign against violence against women was the establishment of the Mor Çatı Kadın Sığınağı Vakfı (Purple Roof Women's Shelter Foundation, or Mor Çatı) in Istanbul in 1990. This was followed by two autonomous feminist initiatives in 1993; Kadının İnsan Hakları - Yeni Çözümler (Women's Human Rights – New Ways, or KİH) in Istanbul and Kadın Dayanışma Vakfı (Women's Solidarity Foundation) in Ankara. Numerous others followed these in the coming decades. Arat (2009) notes that until 1982 the number of women's organizations hovered around 10, and between 1983-1992 this number had reached to 64, and by 2004, it had exceeded 350. These organizations encompassed civil society associations and community and neighbourhood organizing not just in the metropolitan centres but also away from them, and women's groups in professional organizations such as bar associations and trade chambers as well as LGBTQ+ associations (Arat, 2009; Esim & Cindoglu, 1999). They included women's studies research centres at universities and publication groups. These newly established organizations had different foci and conducted a diverse set of activities, ranging from policy advocacy to communication and networking, solidarity building to awareness raising over to knowledge production (Arat, 2009). This period of institutionalization (Bora & Günal, 2002) was in tandem with the global trends (Molyneux et al., 2021).

There is a well-developed literature on the emergence of an intra-movement debate about professionalization and projects that inescapably accompanied institutionalization in these years. As projects were added to the repertoire of the movement, a discussion about "project feminism," which was mostly perceived negatively in activist circles, emerged (Bora & Günal, 2002; Coşar & Özkan-Kerestecioğlu, 2017; Diner & Toktaş, 2010; Ertürk, 2006). While many organizations remained underfinanced and limited in their ability to achieve institutionalization (Esim & Cindoglu, 1999), those who could access funds did so by successfully reaching out to local embassies and consulates of European governments and international organizations (Arat, 2009). External dependence risked thinning of feminist demands and agenda, in an effort to make them more palatable to potential supporters (Bora & Günal, 2002). Coşar and Özkan-Kerestecioğlu (2017) explain, for example, the embracing of the concept of "women's rights advocacy" instead of "feminism" from the 1990s onwards and throughout the 2000s as one result of "marketization-cum-civil societalization of the feminist movement."

A second aspect of this institutionalization meant the entry of former activists into policy making arenas. One of the most significant developments of the late 1990s and the early 2000s was the struggles and achievements of the women's movement in eliminating the basis of gender inequality in legislations and policies (Anıl et al., 2005; İlkaracan, 2010; İlkaracan & Ercevik-Amado, 2011;

Müftüler-Bac, 1999). In consensus with international comparative research (Alvarez, 2000; Keck & Sikkink, 1998; Merry, 2006; Weldon, 2002), researchers interested in policy developments of this period have extensively investigated the roles of international institutions and gender equality discourses and feminists' use of these frameworks in confronting and pressuring the state (Aldıkaçtı-Marshall, 2009, 2013; Dedeoğlu, 2012; Kandiyoti, 2010; Kardam, 2005). To this end, scholars emphasize that the CEDAW framework and the initiation of Turkey's candidacy for EU membership in 1999 became significant windows of opportunity. Activists used these as anchors in making their demands to a state committed to the accession process, which meant changes in the legal infrastructure regarding women's status among other things (Arat, 2009; Coşar & Özkan-Kerestecioğlu, 2017). Scholars diverge on the impact of the EU process, however. For example, İlkaracan and Ercevik-Amado (2011) suggest that the impact of the accession process was limited and the reforms were driven primarily by the efforts of the local feminist movement. Özdemir (2014) proposes that the EU has been indirectly influential in local policy-making through the changes it introduced to the domestic opportunity structures. Regardless of the degree of effect or its direct versus indirect nature, scholars note that the loss of this hope in later years did translate into loss of power on the part of feminist advocacy.

In 1998, the first domestic violence law, the Law on the Protection of the Family, was enacted. In the 2000s, the Civil Code and the Penal Code were revised, partially including feminist demands specific to the treatment of gender-based violence (Dedeoğlu, 2012; İlkaracan & Ercevik-Amado, 2011). In the 2000s, the parliament established several investigative committees on domestic violence and particularly on honor crimes at the request of parliamentarians belonging to the pro-Kemalist Republican People's Party and successive political parties aligned with the Kurdish movement. The establishment of these committees to gather knowledge on gender-based violence and the execution of several state-sponsored studies indicate that the issue was being reframed as a political, governance issue (Alnıaçık, 2022).

Turkey's active role in drafting and signing of the Istanbul Convention in May 2011 and the enactment of a new national violence against women act titled "The Law on Protection of the Family and Prevention of Violence against Women" in March 2012 were the last successful collaborative events between pro-feminist women's organizations and the government. Several feminist activists participated in the drafting of this national law and publicly endorsed the final form it took, except for the last-minute addition of the phrase "protection of the family" to the title (Gülel, 2021). After the passing of the legislation, they continuously cautioned against potential failures of implementation and pressured the government through research and reports published on institutional practices (Mor Çatı, 2014; Moroğlu, 2012; Uçan et al., 2016). This episode of collaboration came to an end as an emboldened AKP began initiating GONGOs and excluding all feminist organizations from the law and policy making processes (Çelebi, 2022; Diner, 2018; Ehrhart, 2022; Gülel, 2021). Accordingly, it is apt to end this period of successful engagement with state and feminist law making with the enactment of the national domestic violence legislation in 2012.

One final characteristic of the 1990s and the first decade of 2000s is the diversification of women's claim-making that was often imprinted with identity-based divisions and conflicts within the movement (Arat, 2009; Bora & Günal, 2002; Diner & Toktaş, 2010).

In response to the rise of an independent feminist activism in the 1980s, several Kemalist women repositioned themselves as "Kemalist feminists" and bestowed upon themselves the task of fulfilling and restoring the "revolutionary" logic of early republican reforms that purged religious elements from the legal system (Arat, 2009; Çelikel, 1998). In these decades, they came together in women's platforms established to create a feminist impact on the revisions in civil and penal codes (Anıl et al., 2005), while keeping intact the centrality of secularism in their identification and struggle (Mutluer, 2016). One of the important developments, to this end, was the organization of Republican Rallies in 2007 in different urban centres prior to the presidential elections, protesting the perceived threat of an Islamist president (Eslen-Ziya & Korkut, 2010). However, despite the semblance of unity that the rallies aimed for, the divisions within Kemalist feminists became apparent as some who criticized

militarist demands voiced in these rallies were later excluded from their organization (Mutluer, 2016). This was also the period in which some Kemalist feminists started embracing a more tolerant, if not inclusive approach, against Kurdish women activists with whom they encountered in joint women's platforms (Mutluer, 2016).

The literature points to Kurdish women's groups, also becoming more vocal throughout the 1990s and 2000s (Acik, 2014; Belge, 2012; Bora & Günel, 2002; Çağlayan, 2007, 2012; Diner & Toktaş, 2010). These studies widely agree that the Kurdish women's movement fought against two fronts simultaneously. They advocated against the patriarchal norms embedded in the Kurdish society and the Kurdish political movement (Acik, 2014; Belge, 2012; Çağlayan, 2007, 2012). They also opposed the "Turkish" character of feminist movement and the ways in which this ethnic blindness caused silence among Turkish feminists on the Kurdish question and the specific burdens of civil war women endured in the region (Acik, 2014; Bora & Günel, 2002; Diner & Toktaş, 2010).

This is the period in which Islamist women's movement was also gaining pace. Islamist women's movement confronted Islamist men's tendency to ignore the unjust treatment of women in Islamic communities and the feminist movement for their "elitism," arguing that being pious did not contradict with refusing to be oppressed as women (Bora & Günel 2002; Diner & Toktaş 2010). The headscarf ban constituted the main focal point of Islamic women's political activism (Acar & Altunok, 2012; Arat, 2016). Organizing against the ban in the universities was followed by electoral mobilization to support Islamist political parties' winning of local and general elections and the founding of women's associations that brought Islamist ideas into the sphere of institutionalized women's movement (Arat, 2016; Ayata & Tütüncü, 2008; Ozcetin, 2009).

Acar and Altunok (2012) note that a few Muslim women's groups collaborated with feminist activists in the campaigns to reform Civil and Penal Codes in 2001 and 2004, respectively and to monitor national practices around the CEDAW framework in 2004 and 2010. However, they did not break their silence on issues related to women's sexuality and homosexuality, as they carefully avoided the areas which might conflict with religious dictates (Acar & Altunok 2012). Writing in 2012, which is relatively early, given the extent of the change in AKP's gender politics since then, and the repositioning of some profeminist religious women vis-à-vis the AKP, Acar and Altunok (2012) argued that these groups were yet to claim their autonomy from Islamist conservative patriarchy.

One final axis of differentiation that would spill into the following decades was the building up of a generational conflict. Bora & Günel (2002) argued, as early as 2002, that project feminism went hand in hand with the "aging" of organized feminists. Projects required certain professional skills such as fundraising, organization, and management as Tekeli (1992) describes them. Feminist ideas might have been spreading among the younger generation, but this generation was not interested in organized feminist activism and their projects (Bora & Günel 2002). On the other hand, women and gender studies departments and research centres provided new venues for the spread of feminist ideas among young generations and qualifications for young generations who would work in the expanding gender equality project market involving both NGOs and state institutions.

Overall it can be said that the decades between 1980 and 2010s marked a vibrant period for the feminist movement. The main opportunity structures were the post-military coup regime, which ironically opened a space for feminist activists, the gradual liberalization in the country and the transnational connections that expanded the issues and the strategies which feminist groups targeted and employed, and the diversification within the movement that led to heated debates on definitions of gender equality, questions of cultural authenticity, meanings of secularism, issues of exclusion and inclusion on the basis of religious belief and ethnic identity. The process was also supported by the hopes around EU accession and the legal windows of opportunity EU candidacy generated.

8.2.3 Changing political opportunity structure in 2010-2021

From the 2010s onwards there were major reversals in the political opportunity structure. At the institutional level, there has been a growing authoritarianism in the government. With AKP threatened by rising social mobilization, diversified electoral choices, and later a coup attempt, it incrementally

shrank the space for civil society activism and possibilities for lobbying at the state level. As a result, much of feminist activism has either shifted to street politics or switched institutional activities to local governments where the opposition parties are in power.

In scholarship, there is mention of a meeting held with the representatives of women's organizations in 2010, in which the then prime minister Erdoğan publicly announced that he is against gender equality because men and women, "by nature" are "different" and, therefore, occupy "different roles in society." Gülel (2021) mentions that many feminist activists interpreted this event in hindsight as a "crossroads," marking the start of a new phase in feminists' (dis)engagement with the state. This initial statement against the principle of equality was followed by the bashing of feminists, who were presented to be culturally inauthentic and foreign to "Turkish-Muslim civilization" (Çağatay, 2018). This has created a relative closure of the state sanctioned discussions of gender equality, to be replaced by religious discourses of women and men's roles in societies (Çelebi, 2022; Coşar, 2021; Diner, 2018).

These discursive shifts are directly linked to the dramatic changes in the political realm. After the Gezi mobilization in 2013, alarmed with the electoral victory of HDP, the Kurdish party collaborating with extra-parliamentary opposition in 2015, and the growing popularity of the annual Pride Parade, AKP began a series of legislative and policy moves to repress opposition (Özkazanç, 2020). With the termination of the peace process in 2015, the tensions along the Turkish and Kurdish divide were amplified and Kurdish-dominated regions were further securitized. The failed July 15, 2016 coup attempt which was used to justify a state of emergency rule, further squeezed civic and political space where feminists could voice their demands and organize against the government's policies (Gülel, 2021). In its aftermath, AKP leaned closer to the ultranationalist party MHP, consolidating its leadership among the right-wing constituency (Çağatay, 2018). In two years of state of emergency rule, the AKP government pursued a full-blown attack on social opposition including feminists, journalists, writers, and activists (Çağatay 2018). Gülel (2021) and Çağatay (2018) document the imprisoning of Kurdish politicians, including feminists' allies in the parliament, the appointing of trustees to Kurdish local governments, and the closing of Kurdish women's organizations and municipality-run crisis centres serving women in the southeast of Turkey. The government began using decrees intensively to rule the country, silencing opposition-political parties and civic associations (Ertan, 2020). The culmination of this repressive turn came in 2017 when as a result of a very close referendum, the country transitioned from a parliamentary system to a presidential system. This was followed by a presidential election in July 2018, won by AKP's Erdoğan. The presidential system debilitated the parliament, which was the primary ground for feminist lobbying (Gülel 2021).

Yet, another political opportunity structure lost during this period was the EU pressure and the ways in which progressive activists, including feminist groups, could use EU accession as an anchor to advocate for legal change, the meaningful implementation of changes made and alignment of public discourses with global gender equality regimes (Aldıkaçtı-Marshall, 2009, 2013; Çağatay, 2018; Dedeoğlu, 2012; Gülel, 2021; İlkkaracan & Ercevik-Amado, 2011; Özdemir, 2014). Gülel (2021) and Aydın-Düzgüt and Kaliber (2016) call this latest period de-Europeanization, by which the authors mean the "loss or weakening of the EU/Europe as a normative/political context and as a reference point in domestic settings and national public debates." In this last phase, women's activism, Gülel (2021) suggests, has become more about survival and not losing the achievements of the past than moving existing laws further along a progressive path.

While the situation is bleak, there are also two windows of opportunity.

The first is tied to the surprising and encouraging results of the local elections held in 2019, in which the opposition won in all major cities of the country. This has meant for feminists building of new relations at the local level and the spread of profeminist policy making and institutionalization in municipalities won by opposition parties (Çağatay et al., 2022; Ehrhart, 2022). Çağatay (2018), for instance, observes the 'sidestreaming' of feminist politics into oppositional political parties in the parliament, especially HDP, the pro-Kurdish People's Democracy Party and CHP, the Kemalist Republican People's Party who nominated feminist M.P.s in general elections, embraced a feminist discourse, and extended the reach of feminism among other oppositional communities. This is a

window of opportunity through which feminist activists collaborate with allies in the opposition to make their voices continue to be heard.

Second, some argue that the consolidation of the authoritarian neoliberal regime and increased polarization might also have a surprising outcome. Çağatay (2018) proposes that AKP's efforts to consolidate its constituency using a polarizing populist discourse has meant that feminists are now positioned together with a variety of oppositional actors. This, she suggests, means that demands for gender equality might become a focal point for struggles for democratization against the AKP rule (Çağatay 2018). Özkazanç's (2020) positioning of gender as the very Achilles' heel for the government and its right-wing ideology supports this observation. Ogan and Bas (2020) discuss, for instance, the extent of the social media outcry around five cases of GBV and show how people shared reactions against these cases in a vociferous manner despite the shrinking space for activism. Perhaps continuing Çağatay's expectation, the public outcry around cases of gender-based violence signals a public more responsive to gender equality demands precisely because AKP is insistently bringing up a conservative gender ideology.

8.2.4 Critical junctures

Critical junctures that have marked the reinvigoration of the feminist movement during this period between 2010-2021 can be outlined in terms of specific mobilizations against AKP's proposed policies, policy changes and highly publicized gender-based violence cases.

2011 Turkey is the first signatory to the Istanbul Convention: Turkey's active role in drafting and signing of the Istanbul convention in May 2011 led feminists, especially those with successful lobbying experience, to push for a more progressive national gender-based violence legislation (Gülel, 2021). Organized in the Stop Violence Platform (Şiddete Son Platformu), they eventually won in lobbying efforts and a new violence against women law no 6284 was enacted in March 2012 (Aksoy, 2018). Some feminists recalled years later that this was the last time the Ministry of Family was open to cooperation and communication with feminist groups (Gülel, 2021).

2012 attempt to ban abortion: In the immediate aftermath of the president resembling abortion to a massacre, AKP proposed a policy to restrict and ban abortion and C-section births. Following massive protests by feminists and their allies, the proposal was withdrawn (Gülel, 2021).

Gezi mobilization in 2013: These widespread protests took place across Turkey during the summer of 2013. The protests, which began against government plans to demolish a park in a city centre in Istanbul, quickly expanded to the rest of Turkey and transformed into large-scale mobilization against the increasing authoritarianism and conservatism of the government. Many women joined the protests individually and as part of feminist organizations (Kılıçoğlu, 2021; Turkmen, 2018). Not only that, some of the most circulated symbols of the protests depicted women protestors, making women the icons of Gezi and active agents in challenging sexist and homophobic language use (Eslen-Ziya & Erhart, 2015). Scholars writing on the role of feminist movements' participation see Gezi as an important moment in which women's groups' coalitionary efforts sped up (Çelik & Göker, 2021; Eslen-Ziya & Bjørnholt, 2022) and possibly initiated the 'sidestreaming' of feminism into parallel, progressive social movements (Çağatay, 2018). Gezi mobilization also widely increased the popularity of the annual Pride Parade. Because the feminist and LGBTQ+ groups were essential to the protests, many people joined the Pride events immediately on the heels of Gezi, creating the most crowded Pride Parade in the history of Turkey (Mutluer, 2019; Nahrwold, 2014; Savcı, 2020).

2015 parliamentary elections: This sidestreaming continued with the Kurdish party HDP's electoral victory in 2015, surpassing the national electoral threshold of 10% in the first election that they entered as a political party. While this election was repeated in November when AKP blocked efforts to build a coalition government, the opposition parties HDP and CHP became increasingly vocal on women's rights from here onwards (Çağatay, 2018). At the same time, the repetition of this election was a new development, which would recur in the local elections in 2019 when AKP lost Istanbul to CHP.

2016 “marry your rapist” bill proposal: In 2016 AKP attempted to change the regulation of child sexual abuse in order to legalize underage marriages, proposing a bill in which cases of statutory rape could get exemption if the perpetrator married the victim. There were massive street protests and the proposal was withdrawn (Ertan, 2020; Gülel, 2021).

2021 Presidential decree withdrawing from the Istanbul Convention: This withdrawal was preceded by a concerted attack against the convention beginning in 2019. In the end, in 2021 the president announced in a midnight decree the country’s withdrawal from the convention. While this was a sure sign of the institutionalization of gender-regressive norms advocated by the government, some scholars also argue that AKP’s open patriarchal assaults on women’s advances including the withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention, create the unintended effect of strengthening feminist advocacy which turned to grassroots organizing and sought largest coalitions possible (Eslen-Ziya & Bjørnholt, 2022).

Infamous femicides and child sexual abuses: A series of critical junctures invigorating feminist mobilization during the past decade, involve femicide cases and child sexual abuses, including but not limited to murders of Özgecan Aslan in 2015, Şule Çet in 2018, Emine Bulut in 2019, Pınar Gültekin in 2020 and several cases of child abuse and murder in and around homes and public institutions. These have also produced tremendous public anger and social protests, creating platforms for feminist advocacy (Çaltekin, 2022; Cayli Messina, 2022; Ogan & Bas, 2020).

A recent ongoing development that seems to have reinvigorated feminist mobilization is related to the government’s effort to change the constitution to include a definition of marriage / family as an entity formed between a man and a woman. Still an ongoing development, there is no scholarship on this, yet.

8.2.5 Major challenges

The scholarship identifies four main challenges which intersect with one another 1) the coeval expansion of conservatism and neoliberalism; 2) polarization along nationalist lines; 3) polarization along the secular - Islamist divide; and 4) a political environment which changes at lightning speed.

There has been much written in feminist scholarship in Turkey over the past 20 years on the coeval growth of conservatism and neoliberalism (Buğra, 2014; Coşar, 2021; Coşar & Özkan-Kerestecioğlu, 2017; Kandiyoti, 2016; Yazar, 2018, 2020). Their intersection is seen as a major challenge for feminist activism, which can no longer afford to focus on one, ignoring the other. The challenge is to demand a public space based on rights, which both neoliberalism and neoconservatism risk diminishing (Coşar & Özkan-Kerestecioğlu, 2017). This requires, Yazar (2018) suggests, a new set of advocacy strategies challenging neoliberalism and Islamist conservatism simultaneously and a new language that avoids the pitfalls of identity politics but without totally rejecting it.

As indicated before, there has been a growing authoritarianism in the state. Multiple studies show that as AKP loses sections of society, formerly supporting it, it has been trying to consolidate its power by polarizing the political sphere along several axes (Kandiyoti, 2016; Kütük-Kuriş, 2022). One of these is the Turkish-Kurdish divide, which has been heightened especially since AKP has partnered with the extreme nationalist party (MHP) to control the government. As mentioned above, the state of emergency rule that followed the failed coup attempt in 2016 disproportionately affected Kurdish women's organizations, leading to their closure, censorship, and punishment. Under these circumstances, supporting Kurdish women has also become riskier. As a result, heightened fear and avoidance in the women's movement has hampered efforts to build a broader coalition for gender equality (Şimşak & Göker, 2021). Nevertheless, Çelik and Göker (2021) do not see this moment as foreclosed altogether because of two facts: alliances within the women’s movement constantly shift and there is a longer history of encounters and successful episodic collaborations among these groups.

Yet another axis of polarization concerns the role of religious belief in public space; this could be described as the religious-secular divide or along sectarian lines of Sunni Islam vs. Alevis. The literature presents different interpretations of the effect of polarization on the feminist movement. For instance,

Ünal (2019) argues that increased polarization along this divide limits coalitionary possibilities. Accordingly, the more political polarization centres on women's bodies and sexualities, the less room for manoeuvre remains for coalitional efforts trespassing the Islamic-secular divide (Ünal, 2019). In contrast, Çağatay (2018) proposes that positioning feminists in broader opposition to the AKP may be positive for the movement's future, in particular, leading to wider adoption of its goal of gender equality. Çağatay (2018) also observes that recent feminist initiatives, aware of the challenges of polarization, have strategically refrained from framing their mobilization as exclusively feminist. In this manner, the goal has been to further destabilize the border between secularity and piety, and seek to link the movement to the grievances of the larger public (Çağatay 2018). To that end, scholars have also proposed that despite AKP's persistent efforts to centralize the headscarf issue and fix the meaning of headscarf, it has been losing its political significance (Çağatay, 2018; Dinçer, 2020). In fact, political divisions between veiled women are becoming apparent, with more expressing their discontent with AKP's gender politics and identifying unequivocally as feminists (Çağatay et al., 2022; Özdemir, 2022).

A final challenge noted for the Turkish context is the dizzying speed with which the political agenda changes, including but not limited to back-to-back political emergencies that the country wakes up to (Dinçer, 2020; Ünal, 2019). Accordingly, the tremendous centralization of power together with the control of mainstream media, the government has enlarged its agenda setting and changing capacity. Under these circumstances, the activists usually do not have enough time to build and enhance dialogue within the movement community and align their frames to achieve broader and more sustainable coalitions. For Ünal (2019), under the current authoritarian gender regime in Turkey, the challenge facing feminist advocacy is to forge sustainable political ties while responding quickly and critically to political emergencies.

8.3 Actors, organizations and organizational models

The network of feminist movements in Turkey include independent feminists and civil society actors, but are not limited to them. What is remarkable is the development of a mode of organization commonly called "platform" or "initiative" in Turkish, a network of individuals and organizations that ally with one another either on a permanent basis, while retaining individual autonomy, or when specific issues arise, requiring extensive collaboration. A fourth kind of actor emerges from the recently established digital collectives. Ideological compositions vary across organizations and within platforms, reflecting partially the existing political divides in the country, but also the intra-feminist divides across generations, classes, ideologies and ethnic groups, not to mention disputes over the best strategies for achieving gender equality.

8.3.1 Independent feminists

Turkey has a rich history of feminist professionals who have been involved in women's rights mobilizations: these have ranged from femocrats that worked in national bureaucracies to those that rose in the ranks of international organizations, experts that were elected to the monitoring committees of international conventions to academics who participated in their drafting (Kandiyoti, 2010). Independent feminists historically involve those interested in grassroots mobilization, as well (Binder, 2017). In the current context, for instance, feminist lawyers are leading the charges against ultra-conservative groups who want to change the existing alimony laws to the detriment of women (Özcan, 2020). These lawyers narrate their clients' stories of victimhood, speak on behalf of "women," and act as mediators between the disadvantaged women and the feminist-friendly media (Özcan 2020). Often, they are the main source of information for pro-feminist media. These lawyers are also often well-organized within their bar associations. Through meticulous tracking of court cases on violence against women, being present in court sessions in solidarity with the survivors, they help publicize the cases and create a public opinion (Çaltekin, 2022).

8.3.2 Feminist non-governmental organizations

There is also a long history of prominent non-governmental organizations, established by feminists. Long-standing examples include Mor Çatı Kadın Sığınağı Vakfı (Purple Roof Women's Shelter Foundation, or Mor Çatı), established for the purpose advocating against domestic violence and providing shelter for survivors in 1990, Kadının İnsan Hakları - Yeni Çözümler (Women's Human Rights – New Ways, or KİH) pursuing women's human rights agenda since 1993, Kadın Dayanışma Vakfı (Women's Solidarity Foundation) established in Ankara in 1993; Uçan Süpürge focusing on communication and networking among women's organizations established in 1996; KADER, aiming for increasing women's political participation and representation since 1997; KAMER, established in the southeast of Turkey to promote women's rights among the Kurdish population in 1997; KADAV, founded in 1999, following the Marmara earthquake; KAOS-GL and LambdaIstanbul, both advocating for the rights of LGBTQ+ groups established in 1994 and 1993 respectively.

These organizations often organize events on days of significance (March 8, November 25, etc.), write press releases in response to political developments, organize protests, run active websites to disseminate information, run women's solidarity centres, and some do project-based work. They have a wide range of ideologies: while most identify as feminist openly, they show a variation in terms of their position with respect to the meaning of the republic, Turkish nationalism, Kurdish nationalism & rights, secularism, and the role of religion in defining citizenship (Coşar & Özkan-Kerestecioğlu, 2017).

8.3.3 Platforms (i.e. networks, initiatives, coalitions)

Turkish feminists have a lot of experience in terms of establishing successful single-issue platforms or networks that could supersede existing divisions within the movement (Dinçer, 2020). This characteristic is emphasized so much in the literature so that coalition building stands out as the most important achievement of the movement (Fisher Onar & Paker, 2012).

Fisher Onar and Paker (2012) discuss the success stories of such platforms in the early 2000s: for instance, Civil Code Women's Platform and Penal Code Women's Platform were instrumental in the progressive changes adopted in legislation (Dinçer, 2020; Fisher Onar & Paker, 2012; Oder 2019). Other platforms mentioned include Women's Coalition for Elections, Equality Watch Platform, the European Women's Lobby-Coordination for Turkey, the Women's Labor Platform, the Woman Platform for Perpetual Peace, and the We Are Looking After Each Other Initiative, as well as the Women's Constitutional Platform (Fisher Onar & Paker, 2012). Oder (2019) highlights intensive lobbying efforts of the Constitutional Platform for the explicit inclusion of gender equality during the constitutional amendment process in 2007, drafting its own proposal. Fisher Onar and Paker (2012) list CEDAW meetings, the Woman Platform for Perpetual Peace, and the We Are Looking After Each Other initiative as more inclusive of different groups. They also discuss how coalitions are sustained through recurrent interactions in joint platforms. These platforms often united different groups of women, seculars and Islamists, when, for instance, religious men made misogynist statements targeting women's "revealing" clothing. In this early piece, Fisher Onar and Paker (2012) observe a change in the attitudes of the more established Turkish feminist community toward Muslim and Kurdish women concluding that iterative encounters could reconcile thick identities and thin commitments. Accordingly, a common thin commitment to women's wellbeing, especially on issues related to empowerment, violence, and education can lead to cross-cutting mobilizations.

These platforms/initiatives have continued into the second decade of the 2000s, especially given the need for collaboration against a government, increasingly intent on demonizing feminist advocacy. To that end, the issue area of gender-based violence has been abundant with coalitions. Dinçer (2020) argues that the success of coalitionary attempts in this specific issue area is due to the fact that the frame of "violence against women" could resonate with diverse groups. In contrast with the discursive frame of "honor killings" which dominated the political talk on gendered violence until the mid-2000s, the frame of "violence against women" does not make orientalist claims about culture and ethnicity. This frame is more universalistic and less confrontational as it hypothetically positions every woman as potentially a victim of violence (Alnaçık, 2022). Therefore, it can mobilize women with diverse

ideological, religious, national, and ethnic backgrounds (Çağatay, 2018; Dinçer, 2020). In fact, some of the enduring platforms have been organized on this issue.

We Will Stop Femicides Platform (Kadın Cinayetlerini Durduracağız Platformu, KCDP) is a platform established after the murder of Münevver Karabulut in 2009, a femicide that received major media attention and was the subject of numerous protests because of the prolonged investigation and mistakes committed by the public authorities during the court case (Akçay, 2021). The platform was initially established by leftist women, organized around the Laborist Movement Party. On the one hand, scholars argue that its leaders often distance themselves from the broader feminist movement (Yıldız Tahincioğlu, 2015). On the other hand, there is the observation that their diverse repertoire of action contributes significantly to the feminist movement. Çaltekin (2022) considers this platform as the most energetic women's organization campaigning against femicides in Turkey. Anıt Sayaç, a digital monument which lists the names of every woman who has been murdered in recent years, and trial watches, collective monitoring of cases of gendered violence in local courts, are the most popular activities of the platform (Akçay, 2021; Çaltekin, 2022).

The Assembly of Women's Shelters and Solidarity Centres (Kadın Sığınakları ve Dayanışma Merkezleri Kurultayı) has been active since 1998, organizing annual meetings each year in different cities to provide activists and field practitioners a space for sharing experiences and identifying policy demands. The Assembly is especially noted for its success in overcoming the East-West divide in Turkey through these meetings, which enable iterative encounters between women with diverse ideological and ethnic origins, building a space for mutual existence (Dinçer, 2020). However, this does not mean that the annual meetings do not become host to very heated debates occasionally, in one case the police intervening at the invitation of some of the participants (Dinçer 2020).

Past platforms which similarly focused on gender-based violence are said to be Stop Violence Platform, which drafted a new violence against women act following the signing of the Istanbul Convention in May 2011 (Aksoy, 2018), Istanbul Convention Monitoring Platform which monitored and reported on the implementation of the convention and the national law (Altıok & Somersan, 2015; Baytok, 2021; Gülel, 2021), and The Initiative of Muslims Against Violence Against Women, which was said to utilize a feminist lens, distinguished from other Muslim organizations and willing to collaborate with secular feminists (Ünal, 2019).

EŞİK (Eşitlik için Kadın Platformu-Women's Platform for Equality) is another platform that grew out of coalitions fighting against the proposed "marry your rapist" and anti-alimony bills. When the government actors began signalling that they could consider a withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention, the platform was formally established in 2020 with the participation of over 300 women's and LGBTQ+ groups (Arat, 2021; The Advocates for Human Rights, 2021). The platform has transnational connections and has held meetings with participants from other countries where feminists are fighting backlash.

The scholarship also cites Nafaka Haktır Kadın Platformu (Alimony is a Right Women's Platform) as another single-issue platform which has been active since the mobilization of a right-wing movement to abolish/amend existing alimony legislation in Turkey because the bill could lock numerous women in violent marriages in the absence of independent economic resources (Özcan, 2020).

The Women's Coalition is comparable to the Assembly of Women's Shelters and Consultation Centres in terms of endurance and inclusivity. Founded in 2002, the Coalition focuses on women's political participation and representation (Dinçer, 2020).

The Women's Peace Initiative was founded in 2009, explicitly to ensure that women are involved in the peace negotiations between the Turkish state actors and the Kurdish leadership (Göksel, 2018). Not active anymore, the Initiative brought together many activists, with different backgrounds and organizational affiliations, whose political positions range from pacifism to the right to armed defense (Al-Ali & Tas, 2017). After the breakdown of the peace talks in 2015, the network was vocal in challenging the state's brutal crackdown on the Kurdish in south-eastern Turkey, the broader state repression and authoritarianism (Al-Ali & Tas, 2017; Göksel, 2019). Focusing on the gendered effects

of ethnic conflict, the initiative articulated women's demands for peace and organized petition drives and street protests.

Kadınlar Birlikte Güçlü (Women are Strong Together) is another (more general) platform, which grew out of a campaign organized by independent feminists in collaboration with independent women's organizations and those linked to various political organizations (Çağatay, 2018). The platform locates itself as opposed to the patriarchal state and avoids targeting the AKP government singularly. It also pursues an issue-based activism strategy and embraces a loose organization. This ensures the ability of activists belonging to parallel social movements and sometimes opposing political ideologies to choose a mode of participation depending on the agenda. According to Çağatay (2018), the Platform "contain"s these divisions, but the participants cannot "transcend" them because the same loose structure does not provide much space for political deliberation. The Platform, so far, has addressed the following issues with different density: the state institutions' gender politics based on Islamist notions of biological destiny (fitrat) and complementarity between sexes, the Religious Affairs' Directorate's patriarchal fatwas, gender-based violence, gendered outcomes of the Kurdish conflict, neoliberalism, and heterosexism (Çağatay, 2018; Çağatay et al., 2022).

Feminist Night March should also be cited among platforms, which come together on a periodic basis. The purpose of the platform is to organize the annual Feminist Night March that takes place in Beyoğlu, Istanbul on March 8th. This is a platform known for its focus on creating deliberative spaces, with its participants changing every year (Çağatay et al., 2022). It owns up to a radical framing of feminist issues (Ünal Abaday, 2021) and is often showcased as "intersectional feminist politics in action" because it is inclusive of different generations of women, LGBTQ activists as well as activists concerned with state violence and repression of the Kurdish minority (Al-Ali & Taş, 2019; Çağatay et al., 2022).

8.3.4 Digital collectives

A final set of actors are the feminists who have initiated digital collectives. These digital collectives bring together writers and activists, who write periodically to set the feminist agenda, disseminate news, operate online and offline discussion forums and translate contemporary, influential feminist writing into Turkish. Their reach and composition in terms of participants vary greatly, from those that are more connected to official power holders, such as major opposition parties, to younger women writing on individual experiences of patriarchy. They are also diverse in terms of their ideological origins.

Equality, Justice, Woman Platform (Eşitlik, Adalet, Kadın Platformu), a digital platform, grew out of a two-day Justice, Equality, Women Summit organized in 2017 by a civil society actor and a member of the main opposition secular, Kemalist party, CHP (Republican People's Party). This summit brought together 363 civil society organizations and around 900 women from 48 cities (Çağatay, 2018). Except for Kurdish gender equality activists, the summit invited speakers with different persuasions and included a wide range of gender and LGBTQ+ issues in its agenda. The organizers' will to build alliances with profeminist Islamic women was apparent in the presence of covered women as speakers and participants, a specific panel on "gender equality and egalitarian interpretations of Islam" and the fact that the agenda and final declaration did not underline secularism. The motto of the Summit "Where there is equality, there is justice" was also chosen deliberately: Çağatay (2018) interprets this motto as demonstrating the organizers' aim to oppose Women and Democracy Association's (Kadın ve Demokrasi Derneği, KADEM), the most prominent anti-feminist GONGO, and the AKP government's promotion of "gender justice" as an alternative and superior principle to gender equality. Formally established in 2018, the Platform releases a weekly bulletin composed of broadly defined gender-related news. Whereas the summit excluded Kurdish women activists and did not include issues of ethnic conflict and feminist efforts for peace in its agenda, today the platform covers these issues regularly in its e-bulletin. Çağatay (2018) also mentions Pro-Kurdish HDP members' participation in the launching ceremony of the Platform.

Çatlak Zemin and 5 Harfliler, which share a wide range of feminist writing, are other online platforms, often seen as less establishment than Eşitlik, Adalet ve Kadın Platformu because the writers are of a

younger generation (Göker, 2019). 5 Harfliler means ‘five-lettered’ in English, the five letters signifying the letters that make up the word for woman in Turkish. The platform was initiated by a few feminists in their twenties, now in their thirties, and has grown exponentially to the point that they write and receive grants, and commission authors today (Göker 2019). Çatlak Zemin, which means “cracked ground,” was established in 2016. The initiators were feminists which had been involved with the Istanbul Feminist Collective, another umbrella organization which had dismantled itself to seek new ways of organizing across differences (Göker 2019). What distinguishes these two platforms is their attention to collective, non-hierarchical and deliberative decision making, Göker argues (2019).

In recent years, there has also been an upsurge in online blogs and platforms run by young Muslim women, who question the patriarchal interpretations of Islam. Reçel Blog, for instance, is an outcome of young pious women finding a “feminist vein” in themselves (Özyeğin 2015, discussed in Çağatay 2018). Through Reçel Blog, established in 2014, these women discuss a variety of issues such as child sexual abuse, divorce, and virginity utilizing a “gender-conscious” lens (Ünal 2019). Reçel means ‘jam’ in Turkish, and the name is a sarcastic reference to an essay entitled “Muslim women who do not make jam” written by an Islamist male intellectual in which he advocates for traditional gender roles (Göker 2019). A number of feminist women from the circles of this blog have later established Havle, a civil society organization which now has the capacity to conduct large scale projects (Ünal, 2022). Compared to their elders, this young generation of feminist Muslim women do not prioritize voicing their resentment against the secular women’s movement (Ünal 2019). Rather, many self-identify as feminists, seek to position themselves as actors, rather than allies, of movement, and object to the imposition of “gender equity” or “gender justice” discourse as the proper frame for pious women (Çağatay et al., 2022; Özdemir, 2022).

Yalnız Yürümeceksin (You Won’t Walk Alone, YY) is an online platform where Muslim women share their stories of the imposition of Islamic dictates on their everyday lives (Arda & Akdemir, 2021; Gülel, 2022). The blog was originally created by a Muslim woman who decided to unveil. Over time it has evolved into a platform where veiled and unveiled women share individual stories anonymously on their ideas about and decisions of removing the headscarf. Arda and Akdemir (2021) do not state whether YY explicitly self-identifies as a feminist site or not, but they say that the platform does not necessarily advocate for unveiling but rather positions itself as supporting everyone’s individual free will. Comparing it to movements such as #MeToo, which too became widespread through personal testimonies, the key difference here is that the stories are anonymous. While this protects the writer from being identified by members of the largely conservative communities in which they continue to live, it also means the absence of the goal of evolving into a collective mobilization (Arda & Akdemir, 2021; Gülel, 2022).

Göker (2019) argues that these websites also constitute important feminist projects: they commemorate the history and gains of the feminist movement and produce an archive of misogynist policies and legislation in Turkey. They also connect these macro-political frames to everyday experiences of gender inequality through personal essays.

8.4 Allies

According to existing scholarship the allies of the feminist movement are broadly located in other progressive movements, civil society organizations and opposition parties. The literature discusses the Kurdish movement, some Muslim women’s organizations and profeminist Muslim activists, LGBTQ+ actors and organizations as sometimes part of the feminist mobilization, and at other times, they are considered allies. In our categorization, we have decided to categorize the younger generations of Muslim women’s groups who define themselves as feminist as actors and those who utilize feminist principles and/or support feminist activism without necessarily calling themselves feminists as allies. Other allying movements are considered to be workers’ movement and environmentalists, although there is less discussion on the latter two.

8.4.1 Profeminist pious women (scholars, columnists, authors, and activists)

Women's associations broadly associated with Islam are wide and varied. While some of these organizations and actors do not use the term feminist, the ideas they proffer are close to feminist objectives and these are likely to collaborate with secular and feminist organizations on an issue-based format. Several authors have suggested that these particular activists themselves object to being described as Islamic or Islamist because these terms are reminiscent of political parties, or more specifically position them in an alignment with the government, which they actually also criticize (Dinçer, 2020; Ozcetin, 2009; Özdemir, 2022; Ünal, 2021).

Many authors argue that profeminist religious women and organizations can be important allies for the feminist movement (Arat, 2016; Çağatay, 2018; Özdemir, 2022; Şimşak & Göker, 2021; Ünal, 2019, 2021). Accordingly, their importance lies in their capacity to spread feminist ideas to a larger section of the society (Arat, 2016). Their narratives can enhance collaboration between women belonging to different ideological positions that might, at first glance, seem irreconcilable (Ünal, 2019). The authors underline the urgent need for creating and following up on deliberative civic spaces in which women's concrete needs are addressed and strategic alliances are built. They point out to the history of some feminists' advocacy against the headscarf ban and the collaboration between Islamist and secular feminist women's organizations during the CEDAW monitoring processes for substantiating their claim for the viability of alliance between religious women and feminists (Fisher Onar & Paker, 2012; Şimşak & Göker, 2017). One example of Muslim women's group which could be considered as an ally is the Başkent Kadın Platformu (Capital City Women's Platform), an organization founded in 1995 by a leading Muslim scholar and public intellectual. The organization has never declared itself as feminist, but several influential members of it have utilized progressive secular feminist principles and notions in their work (Çelebi, 2022; Ünal, 2021).

Notwithstanding these coalition and bridging possibilities, the same authors also write on the limitations of these practices. Ünal (2019) considers the possibility that increased polarization along the Islamism-secularism divide might constrain coalitionary possibilities. Similarly, Şimşak and Göker (2017) draw attention to the divisive effects of gender equality vs. gender justice debate and how this debate, marked with partisan politics, increased the bifurcation in the women's movement.

8.4.2 The Kurdish movement

Previous studies on the relation between Turkish and Kurdish activists underline the divisiveness of the ethnic conflict and state repression and talk about patronizing attitudes of Turkish feminists and widespread resentment among Kurdish activists (Acik, 2014; Bora & Günel, 2002; Çağlayan, 2007; Diner & Toktaş, 2010). In contrast, recent research reports more positive relations: for instance, Al-Ali and Taş (2019) mention "considerable recognition of achievements and respect for Kurdish women activists" among the Turkish activists. This is supported by the increased visibility and power of women in the Kurdish movement, the institutionalization of women and men's co-leadership, and the larger number of female parliament members from HDP (Sancar, 2018; Şimşak & Göker, 2021). Dinçer (2020) notes the recently developed apologetic stances of Turkish activists for their past excessive behaviours like calling the police on Kurdish activists. Similarly, Çağatay (2018) underlines that even Kemalist feminists try to be inclusive of Kurdish feminists as in the case of the Equality, Justice, and Women's Platform. Al-Ali and Taş (2019) argue that there is a new generation of Turkish feminists, rejecting the nationalist undertones of earlier mobilizations. Yet, in recent years, a new round of criminalization of Kurdish activism and the breaking off of the peace process have strained collaborations because of escalating fear among women's organizations (Çelik & Göker, 2021; Şimşak & Göker, 2021).

8.4.3 The labor movement

Traditionally, feminists have allied themselves with the labor movement especially when it comes down to individual cases of mobilization for female workers' rights (Arı, 2022; Fougner & Kurtoğlu, 2010; Saygılıgil, 2018; Urhan, 2014; Üstübcü, 2010). To this end, there have been a few articles focusing on specific workers' strikes in factories, where the majority of the workforce is women. Among cases that attracted significant attention are the Novamed strike in 2006 and the Desa resistance in 2008;

The Women's Initiative Against Male Domination in Trade Unions and Professional Chambers, which was established when a woman was sexually harassed within the premises of the Cinema Workers Union (Sine-Sen) in 2009; and more recently, the Flormar Resistance, in which feminist groups acted in solidarity with women workers with protests in metropolitan city centres, picket line visits, consumer activism through boycotts, and petition drives (Ari, 2022; Fougner & Kurtoğlu, 2010; Fougner & Kurtoğlu, 2011). Ari (2022) mentions several other workplaces in which women workers were recently at the forefront of resistances and strikes, resisting not only companies' attack on their rights to unionize, terrible wages, and working conditions, but also against widespread gender discrimination in the labor process.

What needs to be noted here is the persistence of labor unions as masculinist spaces, where women organizers have made some inroads but not much. This means, in many cases, women have to struggle for representation and gender equality not only in employment relations but also within unions (Ari, 2022; Urhan, 2014). Unions continue to not recognize the ways in which employment relations assume and exacerbate gender-based inequalities and segregation in the labor market, contributing in Turkey to some of the lowest rates of women's participation in the labor market and in unions among comparable economies (Ari, 2022).

Ekmek ve Gül (Bread and Roses) might be cited in this section on the labor movement as this digital media organization focusing on issues related to women workers' rights collaborates with feminists sporadically (Çağatay et al., 2022). Connected to socialist-leaning Labor Party, this platform does not identify as feminist and, in fact, opposes the use of the term in joint platforms. Despite several but intense disagreements, this organization stays in permanent pro-feminist networks established in urban contexts and strategically joins all-embrasive platforms such as the one established following anti-gender/anti-feminist attacks on the Istanbul Convention (Çağatay et al., 2022).

8.4.4 The environmental movement

During and in the aftermath of Gezi mobilization, feminists have established close ties with parallel social movements including environmentalist groups (Kılıçoğlu, 2021). For Türkmen (2018), women gaining protest experience during Gezi mobilization have become a main actor of subsequent urban, political, and ecological resistances. Kılıçoğlu (2021) supports this statement with examples from Ida Mountain protests in 2019 and Canal Istanbul Project protests in 2020, most recent widescale cases of environmental mobilization.

8.4.5 LGBTQ+ movement

As indicated before, the positioning of the LGBTQ+ movement with respect to the feminist movement is complicated. We have included them among the actors of the feminist movement, but it is apt to include them also in the allies section recognizing their very specific and important demands as well as separate organizing strategies.

Furthermore, in recent years, the literature has noted the tensions between cis women feminists and trans people. While there is not much written on this topic, Zengin (2016b) notes that the tension has flared up in the past in the form of a debate on whether trans women should be part of the Feminist Night March organized every March 8. She also notes that while the debate does not encompass all cis-women feminists, some have questioned whether trans activism is another form of identity politics less interested in women's liberation. Similarly, trans activists have interpreted these objections as biological essentialism. These have raised intensely debated questions on what feminism is, whose feminism "counts," and what a "woman's experience" means (Zengin, 2016a). And yet the author continues that given the shared experience of violence and death, however unresolved the debate is, there is a common political ground that can be established around "gender killings" (Zengin, 2016a).

In addition to some of the oldest LGBTQ+ organizations, which we have categorized as feminist actors, there are several solidarity organizations established by families of individuals identifying as lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer, intersex, asexual. Among these organizations, Az (2022), lists LISTAG, established as a legal association in 2008, LADEG+12 (Support Group for the Families and

Friends of LGBTQ+ People), and GALADER (Ankara Rainbow Families). Az (2022) notes that these groups, especially LİSTAG, gained visibility because of a 2013 documentary directed by Can Candan, called *Benim Çocuğum* (My Child), in which families shared their stories of parenthood. The movie was widely distributed throughout the country.

It has to be noted that legally recognized LGBTQ+ organizations are increasingly being investigated, censored, and closed down by the state since 2016 (Az, 2022; Özbay, 2022; Savcı, 2020). Against this, the movement has been trying to establish and sustain safe spaces for organizing and community building like Boysan's House, a volunteer run informal organization established in Istanbul in 2016 or Keskesor ("rainbow" in Kurdish), an informal LGBTQ+ collective established in 2012 in Diyarbakır (Az, 2022; Çağatay et al., 2022).

8.4.6 Other civil society organizations

In Turkey there are many professional organizations, such as chambers, bar associations, and business associations. Some of these have been vocal in their demands for gender equality in various issue areas and have spoken out against government policies or discourses which hamper this possibility. The civil society field is large and divided between those likely to ally with the right-wing government and those likely to ally with the opposition, albeit in a more cautious manner. The efforts of Gelincik Center established under the premises of Ankara Bar are much noticed in the literature focusing on feminist mobilization against gender-based violence (Çaltekin, 2022). We can add to this list, other civil society organizations, independent human rights organizations, especially the İnsan Hakları Derneği (İHD-Human Rights Association) which has been historically vocal in cases of state violence against political activists (Babül 2020). İHD continues to take part in joint urban platforms such as in Diyarbakır, collaborating with much repressed profeminist Kurdish women's organizations (Çağatay et al., 2022). We could also highlight women's business organizations such as KAGİDER and TİKAD within this list, which Ertan (2020) considers as "elite allies," better positioned to access decision makers, reach out to other organizations, convey feminist concerns, and eventually impact the direction of policy making in ways organizations and coalitions known as staunchly feminist cannot.

8.4.7 The public institutions & opposition parties

As indicated before, dramatic centralization of power and growing authoritarian trends have reduced possibilities for feminist participation in state level policy making (Coşar, 2021; Ehrhart, 2022; Gülel, 2021). However, there have been other developments, which as Çağatay (2018) says, 'sidestream' feminist politics in opposition parties in the parliament and municipalities won by the mayoral candidates of opposition parties in the 2019 local elections. The influence of feminist politics on the pro-Kurdish People's Democracy Party and the Kemalist Republican People's Party stands out in this sense. These parties have nominated feminist M.P.s in general elections, embraced a feminist discourse, and extended the reach of feminism among other oppositional communities. This follows in the footsteps of an alliance between feminists and Kurdish movement representatives at the parliament since 2007 and active efforts of Kurdish women to mainstream women's movements goals in the Kurdish movement and advocate for recognition of minority rights as part of the feminist agenda (Fisher Onar & Paker, 2012; Gülel, 2021).

8.4.8 Transnational connections

According to existing scholarship, feminist movement has historically been connected to the transnational feminist movement (Arat, 2009; Oder, 2019). It has had historical links with the European Women's Movement, has been institutionally connected to international bodies such as CEDAW and the European Council, all utilized for domestic advocacy (İlkkaracan Ajas, 2008; Kandiyoti, 2010). Recent studies point to continuation in this pattern, involving newly established connections through grassroots organizations (Çağatay et al., 2022). Çağatay et al. (2022) give the examples of Ni Una Menos, International Women's Strike, #MeToo, Las Tesis, and White Wednesdays as adopted by Turkish feminists who have been eager to find new ways to express their growing rage against the government. Çağatay (2022) adds recently intensified transnational social media campaigns around

the Istanbul Convention and participation in transnational networks such as Essential Autonomous Struggles Transnational (EAST).

8.5 Themes and agendas

8.5.1 Labor market

Turkey has major gender inequality issues in the labor market: these include strong indications of gender segregation, gender pay gap, and extremely low participation of women in the labor market. The AKP government has been consolidating, through a variety of policies, a gendered division of labor whereby women are responsible for unpaid domestic care labor in the family as well as for paid care labor, marketized under exploitative work conditions (Akkan, 2018; Alniaçık et al., 2017; Arı, 2022; Atasü-Topcuoğlu, 2022; Can, 2019; Candaş & Silier, 2014; Sumbas & Dinçer, 2022). There is little done within the existing labor unions to address these problems, primarily due to resilient masculinism in union work, the very low numbers of unionized workers, and even lower percentages among female workers (Arı, 2022; Birelma, 2021; Özar, 2015; Urhan, 2014). Arı (2022) shares official statistics from July 2022 and shows that the overall rate of unionization is 13.6 percent, the same rates for men and women are 15.21 and 9.67 percent respectively.

The literature on feminist mobilization around the labor market issues is limited. What is written focuses on worker mobilizations in individual factories where women make up the majority of the workforce. In the case of Turkey, these mobilizations often demand the right to unionize and for collective bargaining. Feminist activists support the workers by transnationalizing their causes especially in cases where the work place is part of a multinational conglomerate (Ford & Gillan, 2022; Fougner & Kurtoğlu, 2011; Saygılıgil, 2018; Üstübcici, 2010). Yet the same writing also acknowledges that feminists and labor movement activists have become allies only in individual cases and that there is no-long term sustained engagement between the movements (Arı, 2022; Urhan, 2014). Limited gray literature published by a feminist organization, KADAV, emphasizes the masculinist environment in labor unions and the ways in which women organize within the unions to try to address this issue (Arı, 2022; Urhan, 2014). Arı (2022) points to the partial success of the Purple List Campaign in 2019, the most recent intervention of a number of feminist activists on masculinist domination in union work. The founding of a recent digital collective, Kadın İşçi, by a number of feminists, some of whom have had experience in union work, needs to be added here, though there is no scholarly or gray literature on its influence, yet.

8.5.2 Health & reproductive rights

Turkish law grants women the right to abortion. However, in the past decade there have been political attacks by the government on this right, beginning with a speech made by the president. The framing he used resembling abortion to massacre amplified the right-wing frame that abortion is akin to murder, a “hot button” language (Ferree et al., 2002). In its immediate aftermath, AKP proposed a policy to restrict and ban abortion and C-section births. Massive protests organized by feminists followed. Eslen and Bjørnholt (2022) notes that these protests were the result of an ‘intersectional and egalitarian profeminist coalition.’ However, the frames used by different groups varied. While secular women’s groups used a frame that focused on women’s bodily independence and rights, religious women’s groups chose to focus on health and socio-economic concerns. There was not an eventual frame alignment (Ünal, 2019). The massive protests resulted in success in the sense the policy proposal was withdrawn. The literature on the feminist movement’s engagement with this issue in the past decade focuses on this early episode of confrontation with the state. However, we also know that state hospitals, in practice, have restricted abortion procedures. Only limited scholarly and gray literature mostly produced by related women’s organizations cover how the legal right to abortion was made de facto inaccessible following this confrontation (KİH-YÇ & Mor Çatı, 2021; O’Neil et al., 2020; Sığınaksız Bir Dünya, 2016). Esin et al. (2021) adds increasing limitations as well in access to reproductive rights knowledge and increasing discrimination against LGBTQ+ in health services in recent years. The

publication of these reports by feminist organizations indicates that this issue remains on the agenda of the movement through production of knowledge and monitoring of state practices.

8.5.3 Migration

There are currently 3+ million Syrian refugees in Turkey. This is a hot issue for a variety of reasons and has become a ground of contestation between the government, the opposition as well as the society at large. There is a massive scholarship emerging on Syrian refugees, government policies and societal perception of refugees. However, interestingly we have found little intersection between the scholarship on migration and feminist movements. One article notes that the legal measures applied for Syrian refugees create gendered form of legal violence: the article delineates the explosion in the number of child brides and polygamous marriages performed by imams, religious clerics appointed by the state with the task of officiating prayers in mosques, and the unwillingness of the government to do anything about this problem; the laws regarding refugees' employment (work permit access times, work permit percentages), and the loopholes through which extremely precarious conditions of work are made possible (Kivilcim, 2016). Another article focuses on KAMER's rights-based feminist NGO work in Gaziantep (Özgür Keysan & Şentürk, 2021). The article argues that in contrast with needs-based NGOs and other rights-based NGOs working in the region, KAMER's feminist standpoint benefits Syrian women in terms of the collective dimension of empowerment. Specific to this issue area, these questions remain to be answered with further research: Is there a distinct frame deployed by feminist activism that addresses the recent refugee crisis? Has it had an impact on policy making and if yes, how?

8.5.4 LGBTQ+ rights

In Turkish legislation, homosexuality has never been criminalized (Çağatay et al., 2022). In fact, up until LGBTQ+ mobilization from the 1990s onwards, there has been little public discourse regarding sexual orientation and gender identity. The absence of public discourse found its counterpart in the policy realm in terms of systematic blindness to equal rights and protection (Çağatay et al., 2022; Muedini, 2018). Zengin (2016b) notes that gender reassignment has been legal since 1988, however it has been subjected to severe surveillance in various state institutions. Same-sex relationships are still not legally recognized and non-conforming gendered existences in public spaces might be subjected to punishment relying on the Law of Misdemeanors (Savcı, 2020). Even though today the Criminal Code article (no 122) on hate and discrimination provides some protection, there has been little done to prevent and prosecute crimes against LGBTQ+ groups, especially the murders of trans women (Zengin, 2016a, 2016b).

During the Gezi movement, the active participation and visibility of LGBTQ+ groups in the park became a turning point for their favorable public recognition, celebrating their non-violent and creative protest styles (Göker, 2019). In fact, the annual Pride Parade that took place in the same year saw record numbers of participants from all walks of society (Mutluer, 2019; Nahrwold, 2014; Savcı, 2020). The year following Gezi, the documentary *My Child*, based on the testimonies of the families of LGBTQ+ individuals, was widely circulated (Az, 2022). The emotive framing of LGBTQ+ individuals through their parents was also a success story, following on the heels of Gezi.

However, as the 2010s progressed, this increased public visibility was met with backlash from public officers. Several authors note how LGBTQ+ activism was violently targeted since 2015, the first year the Pride Parade was banned (Mutluer, 2019; Savcı, 2020). As a result, legally established organizations, which have always been under threat from the state, are now even more subject to pressure (Az, 2022; Çağatay et al., 2022). Smaller organizations have either been dismembered or been driven underground due to social pressures mounting in small towns (Çağatay et al. 2022). Yet even under these circumstances, LGBTQ+ activism remains resolute especially around the issue of trans murders, using a long-standing slogan "Trans cinayetleri politiktir" (Trans murders are political) and demanding a hate crime law (Savcı, 2020; Zengin, 2016a).

The tensions between feminisms of cis women and trans people are also noted in the literature. This debate revolves around the question of "who is capable of being 'the political actor of feminism'"

(Zengin, 2016a). Sometimes this debate escalates, at other times, it is on the backburner while dialogue continues. Writing in 2016, Zengin (2016a) said that the conflict around this question was only partially resolved. In the summer of 2019, there was a new escalation of the conflictual stances around the question of who the legitimate actors of the feminist movement are, which took place right before an organized, ongoing anti-gender mobilization in Turkey. Neither has been the subject of scholarship yet.

8.5.5 Gender-based violence

Several studies emphasize that gendered violence was a significant issue in the mobilization and institutionalization of the feminist movement in Turkey in the 1980s (Acuner, 2002; Işık, 2002; Sirman, 1989). From the very beginning, feminist activists prioritized reforming state policies and practices addressing male violence against women (Ekal, 2015). Aldıkaçtı-Marshall (2009) states that feminist activists held back from entering state institutional structures in order to maintain their organizational independence, simultaneously confronting and pressuring the state to reform its gendered violence policies. Scholars focusing on the development of gender-based violence policies, highlight the success of feminist legislative mobilization in this issue area compared to other areas such as quotas and sexual liberties (Aldıkaçtı-Marshall, 2009; Anıl et al., 2005; Y. Arat, 2016; İlkaracan, 2010). The Penal Code revision in 2004, Turkey's role in the drafting of the Istanbul Convention in 2011, and the 2012 national violence against women act no. 6284 attest to this success.

Despite this success, gender-based violence continues to be the most important issue on which activists criticize the AKP government (Özkazanç, 2020). Many online and offline direct-action campaigns, all based on individual cases of gender-based violence have been organized in the last ten years (Çaltekin, 2022; Cayli Messina, 2022; Ogan & Bas, 2020). These campaigns have been successful in raising awareness on the growing negligence of the government. The government responded to this activism with fast-tracking of some of these court cases and changing relevant legislations to increase sentences, though there is no scholarship on these policy developments, yet. When the country withdrew from the Istanbul Convention in 2021 with a presidential decree in the aftermath of an anti-gender campaign, some saw this as the ultimate institutionalization of gender regressive norms, others predicted that this could actually strengthen feminist advocacy (Eslen-Ziya & Bjørnholt, 2022). And true to the point, there continues to be a widespread feminist campaign in social media and real life, declaring that women of the country do not recognize this withdrawal; though, this campaign has not been the subject of scholarship, yet.

8.5.6 Alimony

Another important area for feminist activism has been the strife to protect the legal stipulations that enforce, in divorce, equal division of marital property and the requirement that the ex-spouse with more economic capital pay alimony to the other. This legislation was built on feminist advocacy that emphasized the widespread economic vulnerability of women in Turkey, where many are homemakers and even when they are in employment, their earning capacity is severely limited (Aldıkaçtı-Marshall, 2009, 2013; Anıl et al., 2005; Gülel, 2021).

Yet, this right has been under attack from men's rights activists and religious leaning newspapers and intellectuals, especially since 2018 (Telseren, 2020). Against this development, in June 2019 feminist activists started a campaign, composed of a petition drive and a Twitter thread named the "Alimony Story." The campaign was named "Don't Touch Women's Right to Alimony," defined alimony as an acquired right, and argued that existing legislation should be kept intact (Özcan, 2020). In this campaign they demanded that changes to the alimony legislation can only be considered if the Turkish government fulfilled its promise for full gender equality and enabling equality in the job market, first (Özcan, 2020). This is an ongoing campaign, as the issue remains hot in the agenda of men's rights groups, who seem to have already convinced the AKP government and to some extent KADEM, of their rightfulness (Özcan, 2020; Özkazanç, 2019).

8.5.7 Institutionalization of political Islam

Scholars emphasize the growing influence of the religious-conservative climate in the aftermath of 2007. This intensification has shown itself in discourses on biological destiny, demands for three-children families, and attempts to ban abortion. It can also be traced to a variety of policy shifts. The Ministry of Family and Social Services (which used to be the Ministry of Women and Family) have intensified collaborations with the Presidency of Religious Affairs in promoting an Islamic notion of heterosexual family (Coşar, 2021; Mutluer, 2019). The Presidency of Religious Affairs itself has been expanding its sphere of influence since the establishment of Family Spiritual Guidance and Counselling Desks in 2003 (Adak, 2021; Coşar, 2021; Kocamaner, 2019). These units expanded the reach of the Presidency beyond the mosques into the private sphere of households in an effort to religiously sanction AKP's anti-feminist politics (Adak, 2021; Çavdar & Yaşar, 2019). The Presidency's counselling activities along this line often involve breaches of women's and children's legally recognized rights. Pro-feminist groups can still successfully call the institution to account for its activities (Çavdar & Yaşar, 2019). There are new policies that have outlawed co-ed dorms and gave religious clerics, officials working at the local bureaus of Presidency of Religious Affairs, the right to perform civil marriage ceremonies (Gülel, 2021). The bill that authorized religious clerics to conduct civil marriage ceremonies passed in the context of the state of emergency, making mass mobilization nearly impossible for feminists (Gülel 2021). Activists who still sought mobilization against this bill saw it as another case of institutionalization of political Islam, aimed at rolling back secular regulation of the family institution. There is also an intensification of discourses by anti-gender activists inside and outside of the government that international conventions aim to destroy the Turkish/Muslim society and introducing LGBTQ+ rights through the backdoor (Eslen-Ziya, 2020; Ünal, 2021). Anti-gender activists argue that such conventions are promoted as universal rights but are actually based on Western women's experiences and operate as global impositions on local cultures (Eslen-Ziya, 2022; Kandiyoti, 2022; Özkazanç, 2019).

Against these developments, feminist groups have been steadfast in their framing of women's rights and gender equality (Çağatay et al., 2022; Ehrhart, 2022; Gülel, 2021). The secular groups' past alliances with Muslim women in securing the right to veiling is also invoked frequently as an empirically founded challenge against the polarizing discourse of the government (Fisher Onar & Paker, 2012; Simga & Goker, 2017). Interestingly, among educated devout women in urban contexts, some scholars observe a trend of unveiling, as attested to by the growing popularity of the blog *Yalnız Yürümeyeceksin* (You will not walk alone) (Arda & Akdemir, 2021; Gülel, 2022). Kütük-Kuriş (2021), based on interviews with women who have removed the veil, argues that there is a fatigue of being associated with the ruling party and an increasing inclination to describe political affiliation in terms of liberal and/or human rights conceptions such as justice, women's equality, and freedom of expression. She interprets this in terms of a new quest for individualism against politicized displays of piety, against family pressures, and so on. Yet, they still do not use the frame of women's bodily autonomy (Kütük-Kuriş, 2021).

8.6 Repertoire of action

On the one hand, in the past decade, feminist mobilization in Turkey has expanded and diversified. On the other hand, there are mounting pressures on feminist and LGBTQ+ activism both from growing anti-feminist and anti-gender mobilizations and through state violence (Çağatay, 2019; Çağatay et al., 2022; Özkazanç, 2019, 2020). Even organizing protests on internationally recognized days such as March 8 and November 25 now requires tremendous strategizing to avoid police violence (Çağatay et al., 2022). As a result of this contextual shift, activists have had to find creative solutions to survival while continuing with advocacy work. This has meant changing forms of organizing, alliance building, and lobbying. In response to this context, the emotions that pervade activist circles are noted to fluctuate "between feelings of anxiety and disheartenment on the one hand, and anger and frustration on the other" (Çağatay et al., 2022).

8.6.1 Changing patterns of lobbying

Scholarship shows that feminist activism and the repertoires of action activists have utilized have been contextually and temporally specific. Aksoy (2018) follows the trajectory of repertoires of action deployed by four groups (feminists, Islamists, Kemalists, Kurds) and says that they have utilized different strategies during the democratization phase and the democratic backsliding phase of the recent decades. Those groups that had access to state institutions in the early 2000s pushed for policy change, using a combination of lobbying and public outreach. This was the period Aksoy (2018) says many gender progressive reforms were undertaken and she calls this period of strategizing pro-active. The Kurdish women's movements, initially outcasts, were able to join these efforts when Kurdish political actors came into the parliament from 2007 onwards. However, the de-democratization phase began in 2011 and many groups, which earlier had had access to policy making circles were shut out (feminists, Kurdish, Kemalists) or co-opted (Islamists).

A similar categorization emerges from the work of Eslen-Ziya and Kazanoğlu (2022) and Eslen-Ziya (2013). Accordingly, during the democratization phase, when the EU accession process was going strong, feminists could target political actors directly and use EU accession as an anchor, garnering collaborative ties with the European Women's Lobby (Oder, 2019). However, with the onset of democratic backsliding and the waning of hopes regarding the EU process, the same groups had to adapt their strategies and go via women's groups which still had ties with the government, former colleagues now with the AKP, to continue indirect lobbying efforts. They approached companies and garnered resources from their social responsibility projects. As the European Women's Lobby lost its credibility among Turkish feminists, when it kept its silence on discriminatory actions, policy attempts and discourses, they began contacting individual EU states and local women's NGOs in other countries for building transnational alliances.

8.6.2 Social media campaigns

As direct institutional ties became weaker and the Turkish government became more closed off to the activists, feminist groups began using social media campaigns more intensively (Çaltekin, 2022; Cayli Messina, 2022; Göker, 2019; Ogan & Bas, 2020; Özcan, 2020). There are several examples of successful social media campaigns, getting the right-wing government actors to step back and/or raising widespread awareness of the issues in question. Examples abound.

Earlier, feminist campaigns against the proposed abortion ban in 2012 and 2013 involved a social media tier, though social media use was relatively less spread in these years. This social media centred outreach that targeted other NGOs, the press, the public, and the media finally got the parliament to hear what they were saying, and the proposed bill was withdrawn (Eslen-Ziya, 2013). "Close Your Legs, Don't Occupy My Space," a campaign initiated against men's bodily sprawling in public transportation occupying more space than women, took place in 2014. Following on the heels of Gezi mobilization, which enormously expanded the use of social media for mobilizing purposes, this campaign was also relatively successful in terms of the attention it received (Alnıaçık, 2019). The social media outcry against the "marry your rapist law," as activists call it, is another successful campaign, which led to withdrawal of the proposal in 2016 (Ertan, 2020; Gülel, 2021).

Other digital campaigns include the Twitter page of the Alimony Story (Nafaka Hikayesi) launched in April 2019, a year after the Platform for Divorced People and the Family began a campaign (Özcan 2020) and "You Won't Walk Alone" (Yalnız Yürümeyeceksin), which started out as a social media campaign and turned later into a blog collecting stories from Muslim women on their experiences of community pressures of attire (Arda & Akdemir, 2021; Gülel, 2022). Recently, women who chose to unveil have made use of the 10-year challenge campaign on Instagram and Twitter to announce their decision to unveil, posting veiled photographs from the past with current unveiled pictures. Attracting a lot of media attention, though, this campaign was not directly linked to feminist organizations (Kütük-Kuriş, 2021).

Turkish feminist activists extensively use social media for mobilizing purposes. The examples provided here constitute only those campaigns that are covered in the existing literature.

8.6.3 Street activism

As state-civil society relations deteriorated, this decade saw feminist and queer struggles increasingly relocated to what Çağatay et al. (2021) call the realm of counter-hegemonic struggles. In this decade feminist and queer struggles have also expanded despite all the pressure, responding to the growth of sexism, homophobia, gender-based violence, including those against women, trans and queer people, state negligence of these issues in combination with broader problems of the rise of Turkish nationalist, Sunni Islamist discourses, destruction of the environment, and the escalation of neoliberal policies (Çağatay et al., 2022; Kilic, 2021; Özbay, 2022; Özbay & Öktem, 2021; Turkmen, 2018).

In the 2010s, thousands marched in Feminist Night Marches and Pride Parades despite violent police interventions (Çağatay et al., 2022; Mutluer, 2019; Özbay & Öktem, 2021; Savcı, 2020). Activists' resoluteness in street activism shows itself in gathering of thousands in these marches and pushing through police barricades, despite official bans announced days ago, police barricades closing city centres from the morning onwards, heavy use of police violence against protesters, and massive detentions during the protests. In addition to these mass gatherings, activists in cities across Turkey have been responding to every brutal case of gender-based violence with direct action, though the literature lacks a comprehensive analysis of these mobilizations.

8.6.4 New organizing strategies

Progressive civil society organizations have been facing tremendous pressure from the state in the form of state prosecutor-initiated court cases, investigations, and threats of closure (Çağatay, 2019; Ertan, 2020). This has meant not only little hope for influencing legislative processes through traditional lobbying channels, but the very act of establishing civil society organizations for feminist and queer causes can mean unwarranted state surveillance (Az, 2022; Çağatay et al., 2022). The new generation of activists have been turning to the grassroots instead of organizing around formal CSOs to lead nation-state level policy changes through lobbying (Ehrhart, 2022). Çağatay et al (2022), for instance, discuss the case of Women's Defense Network (Kadın Savunma Ağı), pursuing this strategy. While the Network has established a legal CSO for practical purposes like being able to rent a space for the group's gatherings, in the activists' eyes, this legal CSO is almost a non-entity. On the other hand, Boysan' House, that Az (2022) discusses in her work as a case LGBTQ+ community organizing, did not need to form a legal body, as the House did not have any logistical concerns. Nevertheless, Çağatay et al. (2022) states that these cases should not be considered as implying the continuation of negative attitudes among activists against what was called NGOization of the 1990s and 2000s. Organizations are no longer seen as co-opted precisely because they are excluded from the formal process of policy making and because of mounting state pressure against them (Çağatay et al., 2022). Rather, these organizations have been also turning to grassroots to recruit new staff and survive in the face of repressive policies (Ehrhart 2022).

As delineated before, a strategy that goes back to the early 2000s is establishing single- or multi-issue platforms or networks that could supersede existing divisions within the women's movement (Dinçer, 2020; Fisher Onar & Paker, 2012; Negrón-Gonzales, 2016). These have continued into the second decade of the 2000s, especially given the need for collaboration against state actors, increasingly intent on demonizing feminist advocacy. To that end, the issue area of gender-based violence has been abundant with coalitions (Çağatay, 2018; Dinçer, 2020). These alliances are also a means to survive and protect achievements of past eras (Gülel, 2021). While these platforms are mentioned and shown as examples of coalition building under very polarized circumstances, the scholarship does not discuss in detail how they are actually established and sustained in the everyday.

As another case of new organizing strategy, we could also include organized feminist practice of showing presence during and following gender-based violence court cases and tracking the trajectory of case law. While this does not constitute direct lobbying, this sustained presence is intended to put pressure on the judiciary and make visible practices of lenient sentencing against violent perpetrators (Çaltekin, 2022). This is a practice that feminists have always deployed; what has changed is how organized, systematic, and voluminous it has become (Alniaçık, 2022). Formal women's organizations

increasingly make official application to courts to become interveners on the ground that cases of gendered violence harm their activities. Activists follow hearings in a concerted manner, making press releases before and after court hearings to demand full and just implementation of the laws (Çaltekin, 2022).

8.6.5 Knowledge production and expertise

Feminist activists have also been utilizing especially their webpages for knowledge production aiming to rebut right-wing discourses. One line of knowledge production contributes to sustaining past achievements by making sure that young generations are aware of Turkish feminist history and advocacy (Göker 2019). Another line concerns producing and disseminating individual, everyday testimonials that challenge and confront right-wing discourses about meanings of family, experiences of domestic violence, divorce, dress codes and so on (Arda & Akdemir, 2021; Gülel, 2022; Özdemir, 2022; Ünal, 2019). Women's organizations also continue publishing monitoring reports to publicize the state's neglect and failure in implementing pro-gender equality legislation. A final knowledge production concerns the work done by feminist lawyers and feminist groups following court cases: this work involves producing knowledge on the gender inequality realities that makes alimony payments crucial for women's financial well-being, producing systematic knowledge on femicides and how court decisions are made so that the structural and political nature of existing problems are laid out for the general public (Çaltekin, 2022; Özcan, 2020).

8.6.6 Spatiality and activism

While less discussed in literature, there are also well-known examples of spaces collectively utilized and sustained by feminist activists to congregate, hold meetings and discussion groups, organize protests and campaigns while sustaining solidarity through a variety of everyday initiatives. Some examples include Mor Mekan (the Purple Space), two spaces utilized for this purpose in Ankara and Istanbul and run by Kadın Dayanışma Ağı (Women's Solidarity Network) organized in more than a dozen cities across Turkey (Çağatay et al., 2022). Another is the Feminist Mekan (Feminist Space), known especially for hosting the organizations of annual Pride Parades and Feminist Night Marches (Çağatay et al., 2022). Another example is Boysan'ın Evi (Boysan's House), a house privately owned by the family of a queer activist, turned into a community center after his passing (Az, 2022). What makes these spaces unique and different from official civil society organizations is the fact that they are often privately owned, rented by private individuals or organizations such as publishing houses and then sustained in the everyday with collective effort. This is how activists manage to stay relatively under the radar of the state while also providing much-needed safe spaces for activists.

8.7 Frames of arguments

Scholars observe that on a variety of issue areas, different feminist groups have chosen to utilize and attempt to disseminate frames ranging from culturally resonant to radical frames (Ünal Abaday, 2021; Ünal, 2019).

Feminist Night Marches organized every March 8th in different cities are well known for their widespread use of radical frames (Çağatay et al., 2022). Ünal (2021; 2022) gives the examples of banners underlining women's sexuality, inclusive of non-normative or non-conforming gender identities, criticizing discourses of familialism and "appropriate" womanhood, damning the family as an institution and so on. In these marches as well as in the annual Pride Parades, activists target homophobic and misogynist language, using humor and sarcasm reminiscent of Gezi mobilizations (Erhart, 2014).

In the campaigns against anti-abortion discourse and the associated policy proposal, feminists also utilized radical frames such as "my body, my decision" and the frame of women's right to bodily autonomy, though their religious allies called for the use of culturally resonant frames (Dinçer, 2020; Ünal, 2019). Feminists regarded the government's attempt to ban abortion and limit C-section births as an opportunity to shatter hegemonic discourses and institutionalize a radical understanding of women's bodily autonomy (Dinçer 2020). Pro-feminist Muslim groups, however, did not use this frame

because it contradicted their Islamic idea of divine authority over individual bodies (Dinçer, 2020; Ünal, 2019). Instead, they resorted to more culturally resonant framings such as sexual violation, health emergency, and economic difficulty. Under these conditions, they proposed, abortion could be legitimate. This way they could produce perspectives in alignment with the assumed worldviews of pious women. There were also some reformist calls within the secular feminist mobilization that pointed out the limitations of the “my body, my decision” frame (Dinçer, 2020; Ünal, 2019). These reformist voices argued that the conception of self in this frame was too individualistic and ignored social structures which imprint women’s decisions and acts. This critique, however, was not mainstreamed in feminist mobilization. In the end, there wasn’t a broad frame alignment and coalition (Ünal, 2019).

In the case of gender-based violence, frames have increasingly focused on violence against women as a problem common to all women (Dinçer 2020). This was a radical improvement from the discursive frame of “honor killings” of the 1990s and early 2000s: Because “violence against women” as a discursive frame does not make orientalist assumptions about culture and ethnicity, this frame could be more universalistic and less confrontational (Alnıaçık, 2022; Koğacıoğlu, 2004, 2011). In fact, the potential of the universalistic violence against women frame to mobilize women with diverse ideological, religious, national, and ethnic backgrounds is well addressed in the literature (Çağatay, 2018; Dinçer, 2020). This frame has often been in conflict with the long-standing right-wing framing of domestic violence as an issue of family privacy, which will be breached if the state intervenes on behalf of women. It is, as well, opposed to recently intensified state discourse constructing the category of “proper woman” and marking violence as something happening to women who resist and do not know their places, who are immodest, and who betray the ‘divine careers’ of wifedom and motherhood bestowed on them (Atuk, 2020). The campaigns organized in the aftermath of femicides made infamous by the media have been battlegrounds, showing how women, from all walks of life can be killed in the hands of immediate family members, boyfriends, husbands, ex-husbands and so on.

In the alimony debates, the frame has been one that confronted the anti-alimony activists on the question of who the “real victim” is. While those who wanted to restrict or remove altogether alimony payments portrayed men as the victims, feminists through testimonies and statistical knowledge production attempted to show how women were the victims because of uncollected alimony debts, years of unpaid domestic work, and limited access to jobs and employment and if alimony is not there, because of the sheer financial impossibility of not being able to walk out of abusive marriages (Özcan, 2020). Özcan (2020) also shows that the 2019 campaign by feminist activists used a rights-based framing, defining alimony as an acquired right for women. The campaign challenged proposed changes by arguing that these changes can only happen in a world where the Turkish government fulfills its promise for full gender equality and especially equality in the job market, first (Özcan 2020).

In fact, the use of rights-based master framing has been common across all issue areas (Dinçer 2020). The literature recognizes especially the pivotal role *Kadının İnsan Hakları - Yeni Çözümler* (Women’s Human Rights – New Ways, or KİH) played in translating women’s human rights discourse and the related United Nations language into the Turkish political landscape (Aldıkaçtı-Marshall, 2013; Alnıaçık, 2022). This language was also appropriated by women’s organizations such as KAMER, established in Southeast Turkey targeting Kurdish women (Arat & Altınay, 2015; Belge, 2012). Finally, the human rights frame has also been widespread in the knowledge production by the LGBTQ+ movement organizations whereby they report regularly on discrimination and violence against LGBTQ+ individuals in various aspects of life (Muehlenhoff, 2019; Savcı, 2020).

A final frame has been the notion of equality that feminists constantly emphasize, especially against the frame of “gender justice/equity” pushed forth by the pro-government Muslim women’s groups in alliance with other Islamic justice groups, all of whom define equity and justice in terms of binary gender roles and their so-called complementary nature (Çağatay, 2018; Çelebi, 2022; Ehrhart, 2022; Şimşak & Göker, 2021). In that sense, this increasing emphasis on the gender equality frame could be considered as an outcome of growing anti-gender/anti-feminist politics. Some feminists’ positioning of LGBTQ+ vis-a-vis the gender equality frame has been ambivalent: Zengin (2016a) advocates for a

broader understanding of gender so that it includes lived experiences of both cis-women and trans people and lead to building successful coalitions inclusive of LGBTQ+ actors.

8.8 Campaigns and debates

Much of the campaigns during this period focused on the issues of gender-based violence and health and reproductive rights as two major areas of contention. At the beginning of the period, campaigns to support and facilitate the signing of the Istanbul Convention and the enactment of an aligned national violence against women act included lobbying, although, in the later years, this channel would be more or less closed to feminists (Coşar, 2021; Gülel, 2021). Proactive demands marked these earlier campaigns as well; they called for progressive state reform in this issue area. A similar pattern was observed in the campaign organized against attempts to restrict access to abortion in 2012 (Ünal, 2019). Despite originating as a defensive campaign, as it grew, it also included proactive demands such as extending the time limit for legal abortion. Roughly, from 2013 onwards, though, feminist campaigns reveal a change in structure, from one that includes institutionalized lobbying efforts to those composed of grassroots organizing and more contentious and disruptive online and offline activism (Çağatay, 2018; Çağatay et al., 2022; Ehrhart, 2022). This change was accompanied by changes in the composition of the movement's demands from being proactively demanding new, progressive legislation to defensive; that is, fighting to preserve the gains the feminist movement had achieved in the face of rising anti-gender and anti-feminist mobilization (Çağatay et al., 2022; Gülel, 2021). In these latter campaigns, there is visible impact of anti-gender/anti-feminist rhetoric that aimed to downplay the problem of gender-based violence, paint a picture of international conventions and domestic legislation as “breaking up the family”, and develop policies to restrict access to legal protection in the case of violence.

Compared to the volume of studies focusing on the changing nature of the relationship between the state and women's organizations in these years, studies that focus attention on specific feminist movement campaigns are limited. For instance, Ogan and Bas (2020) studies social media campaigns, all based on individual cases of gender-based violence in the last ten years. These campaigns, while not able to push for favourable institutional change, have been successful in raising awareness on the growing negligence of the government on this issue. Çaltekin (2022), on the other hand, focuses on one feminist campaign around a murder, originally suspected as suicide, and shows how activists' mobilizing of a counter discourse was successful in achieving their aims. The scholarship also notes the social media campaign against the proposed changes in the regulation of child sexual abuse in the Penal Code, promptly called “Marry Your Rapist Bill,” as another successful case, leading to the withdrawal of the proposal (Ertan, 2020; Gülel, 2021). Besides these campaigns, perhaps because of the recent timing, the İstanbul Sözleşmesini Uygula (Implement the Istanbul Convention) campaign that feminists initiated in July 2020 with the intensification of anti-gender/anti-feminist attacks on the Convention is not mentioned in the literature. These campaigns more broadly could not stop the withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention in 2021 but were able to pause policy proposals aiming to restrict the application of the national legislation on violence against women.

Another issue area the literature pays attention to concerns the alimony campaign. This issue has also been facing attack from men's rights activists and religious leaning media, both more vocal in recent years (Özkazanç, 2020; Telsemen, 2020). The feminist campaign in this front aimed to share women's testimonies together with the structural inequalities in Turkey, leading to little financial independence for married women (Özcan 2020). With feminist lawyers managing the campaign and motivated to protect the relevant articles of the Civil Code seen as an outcome of successful mobilization of the early 2000s, the campaign did not publicize alternative feminist positions that oppose marriage, heterosexism, and gender binary, though these views existed in the wider feminist public (Özcan 2020). No legislative roll back has been observed in this issue yet. However, Özcan (2020) suspects that the feminist campaign may ultimately not be successful because the recent presidential programs include references to “resolving the alimony question.”

Don't Meddle with My Outfit! (Kıyafetime Karışma!) is another campaign that the literature discusses. This is a campaign launched by the "We Will Stop Femicide" Platform (KCDP) in the summer of 2017 to protest the increasingly misogynist discourses about women's clothing and the accompanying escalation in verbal and physical violence against women deemed "immodest" in their attire in public (Akçay, 2021; Çağatay, 2018). Throughout the campaign, the Platform kept itself in the background like a 'choreographer' and underlined that the campaign belonged to all women (Akçay, 2021). Except for implicit references to secularism, the campaign deliberately did not name any ideology or organization. To appeal to a wider audience, campaigners also framed their cause as a dress code and lifestyle issue and linked it to the increasing violence against women in society (Çağatay 2018). Reminiscent of the feminist "take back the night" protests, activists held demonstrations in places where women were attacked because of their clothing. Their repertoire of action was relatively varied including civil disobedience actions (i.e., hanging shorts in public transportation), picnics, and setting up wishing trees. Protesting women who literally flagged their miniskirts in street demonstrations were also joined by a number of veiled women. One of these women carried a placard that read "Don't meddle with my shorts or my headscarf!" The combination in this slogan increased the protests' visibility. For Çağatay (2018) and Ünal (2019), this placard signaled that the campaign had the potential to include the voices of pious and secular women together. While noting the several constructive features of the campaign, Çağatay (2018), nevertheless, contends that the campaign lacked an understanding of how class positions intersected with lifestyle-based discrimination. She points to how lower-class women, who do not abide by arbitrarily imposed norms of chastity, are the group most discriminated against especially because they are likely to have to apply for state social provisioning.

There is less focused scholarship on campaigns originating from women's peace- and labor-related activism. Available literature, nevertheless, mentions that several campaigns have been organized in the last decade. For instance, Al-Ali and Taş (2017) mention the "We Are on the Side of Life, Not Death!" campaign organized by the Women's Peace Initiative in 2016. The authors report that 165 feminist and LGBTQ+ organizations supported the petition drive. This campaign also involved regular vigils and a number of high-risk street activism and solidarity events. Academics for Peace petition drive also involved a number of feminist scholars, though this campaign was not led by feminists exclusively (Aykaç, 2018). Regarding the labor market related issues, Arı (2022) mentions two feminist campaigns organized in 2019: one, supporting women workers' unionization efforts in a private company, Flormar, and the other, Purple List campaign, demanding an equal say for women in the administration of the union in Kadıköy Municipality, Istanbul. In this issue area, an ongoing campaign that emerged in January 2022 is titled Yoksulluğa Feminist İsyân (Feminist Revolt against Poverty). There is no literature on this campaign yet given how recent it is. These peace and labor market related campaigns might be further scrutinized to understand feminists' handling of intersectionality issues in the Turkish context.

As mentioned above, migration does not constitute an important issue area in the agenda of Turkish feminist activists. The issue receives less attention than even the labor market area: there is no documentation of organized, systematic campaigns on migration related issues. In May 2022, there was a petition drive called Kadın Dayanışması Sınır Tanımaz! (Women's Solidarity Does Not Recognize Borders!) (Ekmek ve Gül, 2022). However, possibly because of its recent timing we have not encountered any reference to it in the existing scholarly or gray literature.

Taken together, these campaigns reveal a changing structure, now building more intensive alliances across ideological spectrums. These alliances are organized around single- or multiple-issues, sometimes leading to the establishment of more permanent structures, which continue organizing social media campaigns, street protests, petition drives and the like, together. Some are organized as websites where there is intensive effort to produce and disseminate knowledge. The intersectional nature of these campaigns, though not systematically studied, can be seen in the efforts to transcend the ethnic divide across Kurdish and Turkish groups and the ideological divides between secular and religious groups and in the will to build alliances with actors inhabiting parallel social movements like in the case of labor movement.

The debates during this period, noted in the literature, heavily focus on the several axes of polarization in the country and the ways in which feminist movement actors try to transcend them (Al-Ali & Tas, 2017; Al-Ali & Taş, 2019; Arat, 2016; Çağatay, 2018; Çelik & Göker, 2021; Dinçer, 2020; Göker & Çelik, 2022; Özdemir, 2022; Simga & Goker, 2017; Şimga & Göker, 2021; Ünal, 2019, 2021). These debates focus on positions regarding religiosity and nationalism more than others. The intensity of polarization debates and women's alliances to overcome these, should be related to the state's efforts for criminalizing feminist advocacy (Çağatay et al., 2022). There is also some discussion on trans inclusiveness, less so compared to the issue of polarization, tracking the activist debates in real life (Az, 2022; Zengin, 2016a). Overall, it can be said that the political context of polarization, authoritarian government discourses and actions, and the right-wing movements have an impact on feminist campaigns, their advocacy strategies, and focus areas.

8.9 Key policy related outcomes

The role of feminist movements in impacting policy-making has changed tremendously between the 1980s and the last ten years. From the 1980s until the early 2010s, feminist movement's various factions were incrementally central to policy making in the area of women's rights and gender equality in general (Aldıkaçtı-Marshall, 2009, 2013; Arat, 2009; Bora & Günel, 2002; Cosar & Onbasi, 2008; Gülel, 2021; Kandiyoti, 2010; Kardam, 2005; Müftüler-Bac, 1999). Even though Işık (2002) suggests that the relation between the state actors and feminist movement zigzagged in the 1990s, by appealing to international gender policy structures (Kardam, 2005) and through "sustained pressure" (Aldıkaçtı-Marshall, 2009) feminists succeeded in prompting the state to change its gender policies and legislations.

The results of these earlier lobbying efforts resulted in the 1998 Law on Protection of the Family, which for the first time began tackling issues of domestic violence; the progressive revisions in the Civil and Penal Codes in 2001 and 2004, partially including feminist demands specific to the treatment of gender-based violence (Anil et al., 2005; Dedeoğlu, 2012; İlkkaracan & Ercevik-Amado, 2011). Turkey's active role in drafting and signing of the Istanbul Convention in May 2011 and the enactment of a new national violence against women act ended up being the last successful collaborative events between profeminist women's organizations and the government (Coşar, 2021; Gülel, 2021). After these, with the establishment of KADEM, most influential GONGO specialized on women and family issues, in March 2013, the AKP government marginalized feminist organizations in policy making processes and resorted to working with GONGOs and aligned conservative women's groups (Diner, 2018; Ehrhart, 2022; Güneş-Ayata & Doğangün, 2017; Keysan, 2019; Koyuncu & Özman, 2019; Yabancı, 2019). In the last decade, scholars note that much of feminist activism was outside of institutional structures and when they attempted to influence nation-state level policy making through indirect lobbying means, Muslim women's groups with moderate leanings played some role (Aksoy, 2018; Ertan, 2020; Eslen-Ziya & Kazanoğlu, 2022).

From another vantage point, much of feminist influence, where it existed in policy making, was resisting right-wing proposals to amend existing legislation and produce regressions in existing rights. In 2012, when the anti-abortion bill was proposed, as a result of the multi-pronged campaign organized by feminist groups, the proposed bill was withdrawn (Çavdar & Yaşar, 2019; Ünal, 2019). Similarly feminist campaigns were able to push the government to rescind the "marry your rapist law" proposal in 2016 (Ertan, 2020; Gülel, 2021). Though not discussed in the literature, the government also responded to the growing activism against femicides and child sexual abuses with fast-tracking of some cases resulting in heavy punishments for perpetrators and changing relevant legislations to increase sentences. However, despite the multi-year feminist campaign opposing the right-wing attack on the Istanbul Convention, feminists could not stop the AKP government, as a presidential decree was issued in 2021, announcing Turkey's withdrawal from the Istanbul convention.

8.10 Other important issues

N.A.

8.11 Conclusion

The scholarship on feminist movements in Turkey, first of all, is rich in its exploration of the long history of mobilization in the country. This literature emphasizes that, over the decades, depending on the ideological position of the government and the political context, feminist groups have created a multiplicity of strategies to advocate for political, legal, and societal change toward gender equality. While there was more room for lobbying and actively participating in the changing of existing legislation in the 90s and early 2000s, this has been a closed off possibility as AKP consolidated its power. In the recent decade, we see, therefore, feminist activists pursuing strategies such as coalition-building, social media campaigns, street protests, and petition drives. We also see a move toward knowledge production that connects conservative dictates and their experience in everyday life. There are intensive efforts for maintaining past feminist gains in a political environment defined by concerted attack against them. Because some of these developments are happening in real time, there is need for more studies of how feminist groups are strategizing under the dual attack by government actors as well as right-wing forces connected to them. What needs to be noted is the need to study the new repertoires of action and discursive practices in a very volatile political and economic environment.

There is much discussion of a unique model of organizing that retains independence for individual feminist organizations while standing with others to garner power in the face of government wrath. Whether more permanent or based on singular issues, these alliances, often called platforms or initiatives, bring together feminist civil society organizations, independent feminists, and allies in other movements to raise collective voice against various gender-related atrocities. There is a past of success to such alliances in ensuring the government implemented CEDAW, withdrew its reservations, reformed the civil and penal codes' relevant articles, signed the Istanbul Convention and so on. These alliances can be seen as an important democratic model in the making, going beyond historical and entrenched axes of polarization in the country. It remains to be seen what these coalitions can do in the contemporary context of criminalization of feminist activism and heightened political polarization and volatility.

Another contribution feminist groups have made, over the decades, to possibilities for democracy in the country, and is well documented in scholarship, has been in ensuring that discourses and practices that normalize violence and inequality in the so-called "private" spaces are a real threat to women's lives. In recent years, it has been their sustained activism that keeps gender-based violence on the societal radar, documenting blatant governmental regression on this front.

There is a need for more scholarly writing on the following themes. We need more writing on how feminists are individually and organizationally reacting to very violent attacks they are facing in real time, today. Such scholarship can enhance existing discussions of repertoire of action and discursive frames used by exploring the question of what happens to progressive movements under conditions of threat and attack. Furthermore, while feminist literature recognizes the need to bring studies of neoliberalism and neoconservatism together, existing scholarship is lacking in its attention to how feminists deal with these issues together. As a corollary, there is a need for scholarship that explores attempts to connect feminist and labor mobilizations to see what has worked and what did not.

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8.13 References

Acar, F., & Altunok, G. (2012). Understanding Gender Equality Demands in Turkey: Foundations and Boundaries of Women's Movements. In S. Dedeoğlu & A. Y. Elveren (Eds.), *Gender and Society in Turkey: The impact of neo-liberal policies, political Islam and EU accession*. I.B. Tauris.

- Acik, N. (2014). Re-defining the role of women within the Kurdish national movement in Turkey in the 1990s. In C. Gunes & W. Zeydanlioglu (Eds.), *The Kurdish question in Turkey: New perspectives on conflict, representation and reconciliation*. Routledge.
- Acuner, S. (2002). 90'li yıllar ve resmi düzeyde kurumsallaşmanın doğuş aşamaları. In A. Bora & A. Günel (Eds.), *90'larda Türkiye'de Feminizm*. İletişim.
- Adak, S. (2021). Expansion of the Diyanet and the Politics of Family in Turkey under AKP Rule. *Turkish Studies*, 22(2), 200–221. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14683849.2020.1813579>
- Akçay, E. (2021). Halkla ilişkilerdeki “Sosyo-Kültürel Dönüşüm”e Kampanyalar Üzerinden Bakmak: #KıyafetimeKarışma Kampanyası Üzerine Bir İnceleme. *Fe Dergi*, 13(2), 44–59. <https://doi.org/10.46655/federgi.936714>
- Akkan, B. (2018). The Politics of Care in Turkey: Sacred Familialism in a Changing Political Context. *Social Politics*, 25(1), 72–91. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sp/jxx011>
- Aksoy, H. A. (2018). Gendered strategies between democratization and democratic reversal: The curious case of Turkey. *Politics and Governance*, 6(3), 101–111. <https://doi.org/10.17645/pag.v6i3.1423>
- Al-Ali, N., & Tas, L. (2017). “War is like a blanket” Feminist convergences in Kurdish and Turkish women’s rights activism for peace. *Journal of Middle East Women’s Studies*, 13(3), 354–375. <https://doi.org/10.1215/15525864-4179001>
- Al-Ali, N., & Taş, L. (2019). Clashes, collaborations and convergences: evolving relations of Turkish and Kurdish women’s rights activists. *Journal of Balkan and Near Eastern Studies*, 21(3), 304–318. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19448953.2018.1497754>
- Aldıkaçtı-Marshall, G. (2009). Authenticating Gender Policies through Sustained-Pressure: The Strategy Behind the Success of Turkish Feminists. *Social Politics: International Studies in Gender, State & Society*, 16(3), 358–378. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sp/jxp014>
- Aldıkaçtı-Marshall, G. (2013). *Shaping Gender Policy in Turkey*. State University of New York Press.
- Alnıaçık, A. (2019). The Body and the Question of Subversion. *American Sociological Association 2019 Annual Meeting*.
- Alnıaçık, A. (2022). *The Politics of Discourse on Gendered Violence in Turkey, 1980-2005: From Family Disaster to Honor Killings*. University of Pittsburgh.
- Alnıaçık, A., Altan-Olcay, Ö., Deniz, C., & Gökşen, F. (2017). Gender Policy Architecture in Turkey: Localizing Transnational Discourses of Women’s Employment. *Social Politics: International Studies in Gender, State & Society*, 24(3), 298–323. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sp/jxx007>
- Altıok, Ö., & Somersan, B. (2015). *Building “a new Turkey”: gender politics and the future of democracy*. <https://www.opendemocracy.net/en/5050/building-new-turkey-gender-politics-and-future-of-democracy/>
- Alvarez, S. E. (2000). Translating the Global Effects of Transnational Organizing on Local Feminist Discourses and Practices in Latin America. *Meridians*, 1(1), 29-67.
- Anıl, E., Arın, C., Hacimirzaoğlu Berktaş, A., Bingöllü, M., İlkaracan, P., & Amado Erçevik, L. (2005). *Turkish Civil and Penal Code Reforms From a Gender Perspective: The Success of Two Nationwide Campaigns*. Women for Women’s Human Rights (WWHR) – New Ways.
- Arat, Y. (1994). Toward a Democratic Society: The Women’s Movement in Turkey in the 1980s. In *Women’s Studies Int. Forum*, 17(3), 241-248.
- Arat, Y. (2009). Contestation and collaboration: women’s struggles for empowerment in Turkey. In R. Kasaba (Ed.), *The Cambridge History of Turkey, Volume 4*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/chol9780521620963.016>

- Arat, Y. (2016). Islamist Women and Feminist Concerns in Contemporary Turkey. *Frontiers: A Journal of Women Studies*, 37(3), 125-150.
- Arat, Y., & Altınay, A. G. (2015). "KAMER, a women's center and an experiment in cultivating cosmopolitan norms." *Women's Studies International Forum*, 49, 12–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wsif.2015.01.001>
- Arat, Z. F. K. (2021). *What women say in Istanbul*. <https://www.ingenere.it/en/articles/what-women-say-istanbul>
- Arda, B., & Akdemir, A. (2021). Activist communication design on social media: The case of online solidarity against forced Islamic lifestyle. *Media, Culture & Society*, 43(6), 1078–1094. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0163443720986002>
- Arı, S. (2022). *Kadınların Sendikalaşma Deneyimleri Sendikaların Kadın Politikaları*. KADAV.
- Atasü-Topcuoğlu, R. (2022). Gender inequality, the welfare state, disability, and distorted commodification of care in Turkey. *New Perspectives on Turkey*, 66, 61–87. <https://doi.org/10.1017/npt.2020.35>
- Atuk, S. (2020). Femicide and the speaking state: Woman killing and woman (Re)making in Turkey. *Journal of Middle East Women's Studies*, 16(3), 283–306. <https://doi.org/10.1215/15525864-8637409>
- Ayata, A. G., & Tütüncü, F. (2008). Party Politics of the AKP (2002–2007) and the Predicaments of Women at the Intersection of the Westernist, Islamist and Feminist Discourses in Turkey. *British Journal of Middle Eastern Studies*, 35(3), 363–384. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13530190802525130>
- Aydın-Düzgit, S. & Kaliber, A. (2016). Encounters with Europe in an Era of Domestic and International Turmoil: Is Turkey a de-Europeanising Candidate Country? *South European Society and Politics*, 21(1), 1–14.
- Aykaç, Ç. (2018). On resistance, Women and the Petition of the Academics for Peace. *Les Cahiers Du CEDREF*, 22, 193–205. <https://doi.org/10.4000/cedref.1165>
- Az, E. I. (2022). Little prayer: Ambiguous grief in the LGBTQIA+ movement in Turkey. *European Journal of Women's Studies*, 29(4), 523–541. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13505068221125726>
- Baytok, C. (2021). *The Istanbul Convention, Gender Politics and Beyond: Poland and Turkey*. Hafıza Merkezi Berlin.
- Belge, C. (2012). *OHAL'de feminizm: Nebahat Akkoç anlatıyor*. Ayizi Yayınları.
- Binder, C. (2017). *Research Project Report "Comparing women's movements in different cities in Turkey."* https://www.uni-bremen.de/fileadmin/user_upload/fachbereiche/fb12/fb12/pdf/A-IB/Forschungsergebnisse/III.3.B.Binder_ENG.pdf
- Birelma, A. (2021). Türkiye'de Sendikal Hareketin ve Hakların Yukarıdan Görünümü: Niteliksel Bir Araştırma. *Çalışma ve Toplum*, 3, 1839-1870.
- Bora, A., & Günal, A. (2002). *90'larda Türkiye'de Feminizm*. İletişim.
- Buğra, A. (2014). Revisiting the Wollstonecraft Dilemma in the Context of Conservative Liberalism: The Case of Female Employment in Turkey. *Social Politics: International Studies in Gender, State & Society*, 21(1), 148–166. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sp/jxt001>
- Çağatay, S. (2018). Women's Coalitions beyond the Laicism–Islamism divide in Turkey: Towards an inclusive struggle for gender equality? *Social Inclusion*, 6(4), 48–58. <https://doi.org/10.17645/si.v6i4.1546>
- Çağatay, S. (2019). *Varieties of anti-gender mobilizations. Is Turkey a case?* <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/gender/2019/01/09/Varieties-of-Anti-Gender-Mobilizations-Is-Turkey-a-Case/>.

- Çağatay, S. (2022). Turkey and Eastern Europe: Historicising Geopolitical Convergences in Gender Politics. In D. Huber & L. Kamel (Eds.), *Decolonising (Knowledge on) Euro-Mediterranean Relations: Insights on Shared Histories and Futures*. Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI) Research Series.
- Çağatay, S., Liinason, M., & Sasunkevich, O. (2022). *Feminist and LGBTI+ Activism across Russia, Scandinavia and Turkey Transnationalizing Spaces of Resistance: Thinking Gender in Transnational Times*. Springer.
- Çağlayan, H. (2007). *Analar, yoldaşlar, tanrıçalar: Kürt hareketinde kadınlar ve kadın kimliğinin oluşumu*. İletişim.
- Çağlayan, H. (2012). From Kawa the Blacksmith to Ishtar the Goddess: Gender Constructions in Ideological-Political Discourses of the Kurdish Movement in post-1980 Turkey. *European Journal of Turkish Studies*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.4000/ejts.4657>
- Çaltekin, D. A. (2022). Women's Organisations' Role in (Re)Constructing the Narratives in Femicide Cases: Şule Çet's Case. *Laws*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.3390/laws11010012>
- Can, B. (2019). Caring for solidarity? The intimate politics of grandmother childcare and neoliberal conservatism in urban Turkey. *New Perspectives on Turkey*, 60(1), 85–107. <https://doi.org/10.1017/npt.2019.4>
- Candas, A., & Silier, Y. (2014). Quietly Reverting Public Matters into Private Troubles: Gendered and Class-Based Consequences of Care Policies in Turkey. *Social Politics: International Studies in Gender, State & Society*, 21(1), 103–123. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sp/jxt018>
- Çavdar, G., & Yaşar, Y. (2019). *Women in Turkey: Silent Consensus in the Age of Neoliberalism and Islamic Conservatism*. Routledge.
- Cayli Messina, B. (2022). Breaking the silence on femicide: How women challenge epistemic injustice and male violence. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 73(4), 859–884. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-4446.12968>
- Çelebi, E. (2022). How do women's GONGOs influence policymaking processes in Turkey? *Journal of Civil Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17448689.2022.2125417>
- Çelik, A. B., & Göker, Z. G. (2021). Dialogue in polarized societies: Women's encounters with multiple others. *New Perspectives on Turkey*, 64, 31–54. <https://doi.org/10.1017/npt.2020.36>
- Çelikel, A. (1998). Cumhuriyetimizin 75. yılının düşündürdükleri. In N. Arat (Ed.), *Aydınlanmanın kadınları*. Cumhuriyet Kitapları.
- Coşar, S. (2021). Regime Change in Turkey: Old symbols into new settings. In E. Babacan, M. Kutun, E. Pinar, & Z. Yılmaz (Eds.), *Regime Change in Turkey: Neoliberal Authoritarianism, Islamism and Hegemony*. Routledge.
- Cosar, S., & Onbasi, F. G. (2008). Women's movement in Turkey at a crossroads: From women's rights advocacy to feminism. *South European Society and Politics*, 13(3), 325–344. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13608740802346585>
- Coşar, S., & Özkan-Kerestecioglu, İ. (2017). Feminist Politics in Contemporary Turkey: Neoliberal Attacks, Feminist Claims to the Public. *Journal of Women, Politics and Policy*, 38(2), 151–174. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1554477X.2016.1198656>
- Dedeoğlu, S. (2012). Equality, Protection or Discrimination: Gender Equality Policies in Turkey. *Social Politics: International Studies in Gender, State & Society*, 19(2), 269–290. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sp/jxs004>
- Dinçer, P. (2020). The potential for dialogical transversal politics and coalitional solidarities in the contemporary women's movement in Turkey. *Women's Studies International Forum*, 80, 102366. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wsif.2020.102366>
- Diner, Ç. (2018). Gender Politics and Gongos in Turkey. *Turkish Policy Quarterly*, 16(4), 101-108.

- Diner, C., & Toktaş, Ş. (2010). Waves of feminism in Turkey: Kemalist, Islamist and Kurdish women's movements in an era of globalization. *Journal of Balkan and Near Eastern Studies*, 12(1), 41–57. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19448950903507388>
- Düzkan, A., & Ahıska, M. (1994). *Feminism in Turkey in the 1980s. An interview: Ayşe Düzkan and Meltem Ahıska*. Women Living Under Muslim Laws Network.
- Ehrhart, A. (2022). Women's Rights vs. Gender Justice? Exploring Oppositional Women's Organizations and the Reshaping of Feminist Engagement in De-democratizing Turkey. *Zeitschrift Für Mittelmeerstudien*, 2, 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.46586/ZfM.v2022.1-27>
- Ekal, B. (2015). Women's Shelters as State Institutions. In M. Aymes, B. Gourisse, & É. Massicard (Eds.), *Order and Compromise: Government Practices in Turkey from the Late Ottoman Empire to the Early 21st Century* (pp. 317–332). Brill.
- Ekmek ve gül. (2022). *Göçmenlere ırkçı saldırılara karşı imza kampanyası: Kadın dayanışması sınır tanımaz!* <https://ekmekvegul.net/gundem/gocmenlere-irkci-saldirilara-karsi-imza-kampanyasi-kadin-dayanismasi-sinir-tanimaz>
- Erhart, I. (2014). United in protest: From 'living and dying with our colours' to 'let all the colours of the world unite.' *International Journal of the History of Sport*, 31(14), 1724–1738. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09523367.2014.929116>
- Ertan, G. (2020). Collective Action, Civil Society, and Public Policy in Turkey. *Journal of Comparative Policy Analysis: Research and Practice*, 22(1), 66–81. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13876988.2019.1617958>
- Ertürk, Y. (2006). Turkey's Modern Paradoxes: Identity Politics, Women's Agency, and Universal Rights. In M.N. Ferree & A.M. Tripp (Eds.), *Global Feminism: Transnational Women's Activism, Organizing, and Human Rights*. New York University Press.
- Esim, S., & Cindoglu, D. (1999). Women's organizations in 1990s Turkey: Predicaments and prospects. *Middle Eastern Studies*, 35(1), 178–188. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00263209908701261>
- Esin, A., Mihçioğur, S., Demir, C., & Kanal, G. (2021). *Türkiye'deki Cinsel Sağlık ve Üreme Sağlığı Durum Analizi Raporu*. CİSÜ Platformu.
- Eslen-Ziya, H. (2013). Social media and Turkish feminism: New resources for social activism. *Feminist Media Studies*, 13(5), 860–870. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14680777.2013.838369>
- Eslen-Ziya, H. (2020). Right-wing populism in new Turkey: Leading to all new grounds for troll science in gender theory. *HTS Theologiese Studies / Theological Studies*, 76(3), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.4102/hts.v76i3.6005>
- Eslen-Ziya, H. (2022). Establishing networked misogyny as a counter movement: The analysis of the online anti-Istanbul convention presence. *Convergence*, 28(6), 1737–1753. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13548565221089218>
- Eslen-Ziya, H., & Bjørnholt, M. (2022). Men's Rights Activism and Anti-Feminist Resistance in Turkey and Norway. *Social Politics: International Studies in Gender, State & Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sp/jxac011>
- Eslen-Ziya, H., & Erhart, I. (2015). Toward postheroic leadership: A case study of Gezi's collaborating multiple leaders. *Leadership*, 11(4), 471–488. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1742715015591068>
- Eslen-Ziya, H., & Kazanoğlu, N. (2022). De-democratization under the New Turkey? Challenges for women's organizations. *Mediterranean Politics*, 27(1), 101–122. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13629395.2020.1765524>
- Eslen-Ziya, H., & Korkut, U. (2010). Political Religion and Politicized Women in Turkey: Hegemonic Republicanism Revisited. *Totalitarian Movements and Political Religions*, 11(3–4), 311–326. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14690764.2010.546088>

- Ferree, M. M., Gamson, W. A., Gerhards, J., & Rucht, D. (2002). *Shaping Abortion Discourse*. Cambridge University Press.
- Fisher Onar, N., & Paker, H. (2012). Towards cosmopolitan citizenship? Women's rights in divided Turkey. *Theory and Society*, 41(4), 375–394. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11186-012-9171-y>
- Ford, M., & Gillan, M. (2022). Understanding global union repertoires of action. *Industrial Relations Journal*, 53(6), 559–577. <https://doi.org/10.1111/irj.12386>
- Fougner, T., & Kurtoğlu, A. (2010). Victory through solidarity? The story of a women workers' strike in Turkey's Antalya Free Zone. In A. Bieler & I. Lindberg (Eds.), *Global Restructuring, Labour and the Challenges for Transnational Solidarity*. Routledge
- Fougner, T., & Kurtoğlu, A. (2011). Transnational Labour Solidarity and Social Movement Unionism: Insights from and beyond a Women Workers' Strike in Turkey. *British Journal of Industrial Relations*, 49(Suppl. 2), 353–375. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8543.2010.00801.x>
- Göker, Z. G. (2019). Memories, stories and deliberation: Digital sisterhood on feminist websites in Turkey. *European Journal of Women's Studies*, 26(3), 313–328. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1350506819855414>
- Göker, Z. G., & Çelik, A. B. (2022). Women's dialogic encounters: agonistic listening and emotions in multiple-identity conflicts. *Third World Quarterly*, 43(6), 1251–1269. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01436597.2021.1977621>
- Göker, Z. G., & Polatdemir, A. (2022). The quest for gender equality in universities at the crossroads of neoliberal and anti-gender pressures: the case of Turkey. *Globalisation, Societies and Education*, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14767724.2022.2121690>
- Göksel, N. (2018). Peace and Beyond: Women's Activist Alliances under Turkey's "Regime of Emergency." *Critical Times*, 1(1), 149–157. <https://doi.org/10.1215/26410478-1.1.149>
- Göksel, N. (2019). Gendering Resistance: Multiple Faces of the Kurdish Women's Struggle. *Sociological Forum*, 34(S1), 1112–1131. <https://doi.org/10.1111/socf.12539>
- Gülel, D. (2021). Feminist movement and law-making in Turkey: a critical appraisal from 1998 to 2018. *Women's History Review*, 30(1), 2–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09612025.2019.1695357>
- Gülel, D. (2022). 'I Want to Break Free!' A Study on Women Who Seek Freedom from Religion and the Islamic Veil in Turkey. *Interdisciplinary Journal for Religion and Transformation in Contemporary Society*, 8(2), 487–528. <https://doi.org/10.30965/23642807-bja10046>
- Güneş-Ayata, A., & Doğangün, G. (2017). Gender politics of the AKP: Restoration of a religioconservative gender climate. *Journal of Balkan and Near Eastern Studies*, 19(6), 610–627. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19448953.2017.1328887>
- İlkkaracan Ajas, İ. (2008). *Birleşmiş Milletler CEDAW sürecinde sivil toplum örgütleri ile savunuculuk ve lobicilik Türkiye gölge raporları: 1997 & 2005 deneyimleri*. Kadının İnsan Hakları (KİH) - Yeni Çözümler Derneği.
- İlkkaracan, P. (2010). Re/forming the Penal Code in Turkey from a gender perspective: The case of a successful campaign. In J. Gaventa & R. McGee (Eds.), *Citizen action and national policy reform: Making change happen*. Zed Books.
- İlkkaracan, P., & Ercevik-Amado, L. (2011). Legal reforms on violence against women in Turkey. In Ennaji Moha & F. Sadiqi (Eds.), *Gender and violence in the Middle East*. Routledge.
- Işık, S. N. (2002). 1990'larda kadına yönelik aile içi şiddetle mücadele hareketi içinde oluşmuş bazı gözlem ve düşünceler. In A. Bora & A. Günel (Eds.), *90'larda Türkiye'de Feminizm*. İletişim.
- Kandiyoti, D. (2010). Gender and women's studies in Turkey: A moment for reflection? *New Perspectives on Turkey*, 43, 165–176. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S089663460000580X>

- Kandiyoti, D. (2016). Locating the politics of gender: Patriarchy, neo-liberal governance and violence in Turkey. *Research and Policy on Turkey*, 1(2), 103–118. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23760818.2016.1201242>
- Kandiyoti, D. (2022). *Gender Studies in the Crossfire: Explorations Through Time and Space*. https://perspectivia.net/publikationen/pera-blaetter/36/kandiyoti_crossfire
- Kardam, N. (2005). *Turkey's engagement with global women's human rights*. Routledge.
- Keck, M. E., & Sikkink, K. (1998). *Activists beyond borders: Advocacy networks in international politics*. Cornell University Press.
- Keysan, A. Ö. (2019). *Activism and Women's NGOs in Turkey*. I.B. Tauris.
- KİH-YÇ, & Mor Çatı. (2021). *Kadınların Üreme Sağlığı Hizmetleri ve Kürtaj Deneyimleri Araştırma Raporu*. KİH-YÇ, & Mor Çatı.
- Kilic, O. (2021). "Every Parade of Ours is a Pride Parade": Exploring LGBTI+ digital activism in Turkey. *Sexualities*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13634607211060510>
- Kivilcim, Z. (2016). Legal Violence Against Syrian Female Refugees in Turkey. *Feminist Legal Studies*, 24(2), 193–214. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10691-016-9323-y>
- Kılıçoğlu, Z. (2021). Contextualising Feminist Global Justice Activism: A Case Study of the Gezi Park Protests. *Feminist Encounters: A Journal of Critical Studies in Culture and Politics*, 5(1), 13. <https://doi.org/10.20897/femenc/9750>
- Kocamaner, H. (2019). Regulating the family through religion: Secularism, Islam, and the politics of the family in contemporary Turkey. *American Ethnologist*, 46(4), 495–508. <https://doi.org/10.1111/amet.12836>
- Koğacioğlu, D. (2004). The Tradition Effect: Framing Honor Crimes in Turkey. *Differences*, 15(2), 118–151. <https://doi.org/10.1215/10407391-15-2-118>
- Koğacioğlu, D. (2011). Knowledge, Practice, and Political Community: The Making of the "Custom" In Turkey. *Differences*, 22(1), 172–228. <https://doi.org/10.1215/10407391-1218283>
- Koyuncu, B., & Özman, A. (2019). Women's rights organizations and Turkish state in the post-2011 era: ideological disengagement versus conservative alignment. *Turkish Studies*, 20(5), 728–753. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14683849.2018.1539622>
- Kütük-Kuriş, M. (2021). Moral Ambivalence, Religious Doubt and Non-Belief among Ex-Hijabi Women in Turkey. *Religions*, 12(1), 33. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel12010033>
- Kütük-Kuriş, M. (2022). The rise and fall of support for the Istanbul Convention: Understanding the case of KADEM. *Women's Studies International Forum*, 93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wsif.2022.102601>
- Merry, S. E. (2006). *Human rights and gender violence: Translating international law into local justice*. University of Chicago Press.
- Molyneux, M., Dey, A., Gatto, M. A. C., & Rowden, H. (2021). *New Feminist Activism, Waves and Generation*. UNWOMEN. <https://www.unwomen.org/en/digital-library/publications/2021/05/discussion-paper-new-feminist-activism-waves-and-generations>
- Mor Çatı. (2014). *6284 Sayılı Kanun Uygulamaları İzleme Raporu*. <https://morcati.org.tr/izleme-raporlari/255-6284-sayili-kanun-uygulamalari-izleme-raporu/>
- Moroğlu, N. (2012). Kadına yönelik şiddetin önlenmesi 6284 sayılı yasa ve İstanbul Sözleşmesi. *Türkiye Barolar Birliği Dergisi*, 99, 357-380.
- Muedini, F. (2018). *LGBTI Rights in Turkey: Sexuality and the State in the Middle East*. Cambridge University Press.

- Muehlenhoff, H. L. (2019). Neoliberal governmentality and the (de)politicisation of LGBT rights: The case of the European Union in Turkey. *Politics*, 39(2), 202–217. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0263395718770890>
- Müftüler-Bac, M. (1999). Turkish women's predicament. *Women's Studies International Forum*, 22(3), 303–315.
- Mutluer, N. (2016). Kemalist feminists in the era of the AK Party. In Ü. Cizre (Ed.), *The Turkish AK party and its leader: criticism, opposition and dissent*. Routledge.
- Mutluer, N. (2019). The intersectionality of gender, sexuality, and religion: novelties and continuities in Turkey during the AKP era. *Journal of Southeast European and Black Sea*, 19(1), 99–118. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14683857.2019.1578049>
- Nahrwold, J. (2014). *Urban utopia: A feminist perspective on the Gezi resistance*. <https://oc.citizensforeurope.org/ojs/urban-utopia-a-feminist-perspective-on-the-gezi-resistance/>
- Negrón-Gonzales, M. (2016). The feminist movement during the AKP era in Turkey: challenges and opportunities. *Middle Eastern Studies*, 52(2), 198–214. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00263206.2015.1125339>
- Oder, B. E. (2019). Women and Constitution-Making in Turkey: From Ottoman Modernism to a Constitutionalism of Women's Platform. In R. Rubio-Marin & H. Irving (Eds.), *Women as Constitution-Makers: Case Studies from the New Democratic Era*. Cambridge University Press
- Ogan, C. L., & Bas, O. (2020). Use of Social Media in the Struggle Surrounding Violence Against Turkish Women. In *International Journal of Communication*, 14, 5556–5574. <http://ijoc.org>.
- O'Neil, M. lou, Altuntaş, D., & Keskin, A. Ş. (2020). *Türkiyede Kamu Hastanelerinde (Eğitim ve Araştırma Hastaneleri, Devlet Hastaneleri, İlçe Hastaneleri ve Şehir Hastaneleri) Kürtaj Hizmetleri Araştırması Raporu*. <https://gender.khas.edu.tr/sites/gender.khas.edu.tr/files/docs/2020-12/2020-kurtaj-arastirmasi-raporu.pdf>
- Özar, Ş. (2015). Türkiye'de 1980 Sonrası Dönemde Kadın Emeği ve İstihdamı Politikaları: Kadın Hareketi, Sendikalar, Devlet ve İşveren Kuruluşları. In A. Makal & G. Toksöz (Eds.), *Geçmişten Günümüze Türkiye'de Kadın Emeği*. İmge.
- Özbay, C. (2022). State Homophobia, Sexual Politics, and Queering the Boğaziçi Resistance. *South Atlantic Quarterly*, 121(1), 199–209. <https://doi.org/10.1215/00382876-9561657>
- Özbay, C., & Öktem, K. (2021). Turkey's queer times. *New Perspectives on Turkey*, 64, 117–130. <https://doi.org/10.1017/npt.2021.4>
- Özcan, E. (2020). Framing the Alimony Debates in Turkey: Struggle Between Feminist and Antifeminist Discourses to Represent "Women's Rights." *International Journal of Communication*, 14, 5597–5615. <http://ijoc.org>.
- Ozçetin, H. (2009). "Breaking the Silence": The Religious Muslim Women's Movement in Turkey. *Journal of International Women's Studies* 11(1), 106-119. <https://vc.bridgew.edu/jiws/vol11/iss1/8>
- Ozcurumez, S., & Sayan-Cengiz, F. (2011). On resilience and response beyond value change: Transformation of women's movement in post-1980 Turkey. *Women's Studies International Forum*, 34(1), 20–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wsif.2010.09.015>
- Özdemir, B. (2014). The Role of the EU in Turkey's Legislative Reforms for Eliminating Violence against Women: A Bottom-Up Approach. *Journal of Balkan and Near Eastern Studies*, 16(1), 119–136. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19448953.2013.864187>
- Özdemir, Ş. (2022). Discursive Activists or Patriarchal Bargainers? Religion, Gender, and Neoliberal Governance in the "New" Turkey. *Social Politics*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/sp/jxab051/6513397>

- Özgür Keysan, A., & Şentürk, B. (2021). Philanthropists, Professionals and Feminists: Refugee NGOs and the Empowerment of Syrian Women in Gaziantep, Turkey. *International Migration*, 59(1), 143–164. <https://doi.org/10.1111/imig.12728>
- Özkazanç, A. (2019). *The new episode of anti-gender politics in Turkey*. <https://Blogs.Lse.Ac.Uk/Gender/2019/05/20/New-Episode-Anti-Gender-Turkey/>.
- Özkazanç, A. (2020). Anti-Gender Movements in Europe and the case of Turkey. *Baltic Worlds*, 8(1), 45-55.
- Sancar, S. (2018). *Siyasal Kararlara Katılımda Toplumsal Cinsiyet Eşitliği Haritalama ve İzleme Çalışması*. CEID Yayınları.
- Savcı, E. (2020). *Queer in Translation-Sexual Politics under Neoliberal Islam*. Duke University Press.
- Saygılıgil, F. (2018). *Serbest Bölge’de Kadın Olmak: Bir Kadın Grevi*. Güldünya Yayınları.
- Şimğa, H., & Goker, G. Z. (2017). Whither feminist alliance? Secular feminists and Islamist women in Turkey. *Asian Journal of Women’s Studies*, 23(3), 273–293. <https://doi.org/10.1080/12259276.2017.1349717>
- Şimğa, H., & Göker, Z. G. (2021). Women’s perceptions on peace and justice: The case of the Kurdish issue in Turkey. *Women’s Studies International Forum*, 87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wsif.2021.102499>
- Sirman, N. (1989). Turkish Feminism: A Short History. *New Perspectives on Turkey*, 3(1), 1-34.
- Sığınaksız bir dünya. (2016). *Kadın Sığınakları ve Da(ya)nışma Merkezleri Kurultayı Bileşen Örgütleri Kamu Hastaneleri Kürtaj Uygulamaları Araştırma Raporu*. <https://www.morcati.org.tr/attachments/article/370/kamu-hastaneleri-kurtaj-uygulamalari-arastirma-raporu.pdf>
- Sumbas, A., & Dinçer, P. (2022). The substantive representation of women parliamentarians of the AKP: the case of maternity leave and part-time work. *Politics, Groups, and Identities*, 10(1), 146–151. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21565503.2021.1992288>
- Tekeli, Ş. (1986). Emergence of the New Feminist Movement in Turkey. In D. Dahlerup (ed.), *The New Women’s Movement*. Sage.
- Tekeli, Ş. (1992). Europe, European Feminism, and Women in Turkey. *Women’s Studies International Forum*, 15(1).
- Tekeli, Ş. (2010). The Turkish Women’s Movement: A Brief History of Success. *Quaderns de la Mediterrània*, 14, 119–23.
- Telseren, A. (2020). Changing Gender Politics in Turkey throughout the 2000s: A Feminist Analysis of Gender Policies Pursued by Justice and Development Party (Adalet ve Kalkınma Partisi - AKP) Governments. *Interdisciplinary Political Studies*, 6(2), 357–395. <https://doi.org/10.1285/i20398573v6n2p357>
- The Advocates for Human Rights. (2021). *Turkey’s Withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention: A Step Backward for Women’s Human Rights*. <https://www.theadvocatesforhumanrights.org/res/byid/9110>
- Turkmen, B. (2018). The Gezi Revolt and the Solidarist Individualism of “Çapulcu” Women (marauder). *Les Cahiers Du CEDREF*, 22, 109–127. <https://doi.org/10.4000/cedref.1133>
- Uçan, A., Gürkan, D., Bayram, D., Günel, H., Gaidzik, P. M., Meşeli, P., & Kaner, S. (2016). *Türkiye’de Erkek Şiddetiyle Mücadele Mekanizmaları İzleme Raporu*. Mor Çatı Yayınları.
- Ünal Abaday, D. (2021). Positioning the Critical Pious Self vis-à-vis Authoritarian Populist Body Politics: Limits of Feminist Dissent in Pious Women Columnists Narratives in Turkey. In H. Alkan, A. Dayi,

- S. Topçu, B. Yazar (Eds.), *The Politics of Female Body in Contemporary Turkey: Reproduction, Maternity, Sexuality*. I. B. Tauris.
- Ünal, D. (2019). The Abortion Debate and Profeminist Coalition Politics in Contemporary Turkey. *Politics & Gender*, 15(4), 801–825. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1743923X18000703>
- Ünal, D. (2021). The Masculinist Restoration Project in the Rhetoric of Anti-Gender Movements. In O. Hakola, J. Salminen, J. Turopoinen & O. Winberg (Eds.), *The Culture and Politics of Populist Masculinities*. Lexington Books.
- Ünal, D. (2022). “Are You God? Damn Your Family!”: The Islam–Gender Nexus in Right-Wing Populism and the New Generation of Muslim Feminist Activism in Turkey. *Religions*, 13(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel13040372>
- Urhan, B. (2014). *Sendikasıız Kadınlar, Kadınsız Sendikalar*. KADAV yayınları.
- Üstübcü, A. (2010). Serbest bölgeler ve örgütlenme: Novamed “kadın grevi” örneği. *Birikim*, 258, 46–51.
- Weldon, S. L. (2002). *Protest, Policy, and the Problem of Violence against Women a Cross-national Comparison*. University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Yabancı, B. (2019). Turkey’s tamed civil society: Containment and appropriation under a competitive authoritarian regime. *Journal of Civil Society*, 15(4), 285–306. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17448689.2019.1668627>
- Yazar, B. (2018). Reflecting on The Oppositional Discourses Against the AKP’s Neoliberalism and Searching for a New Vision for Feminist Counter Politics. *Les Cahiers Du CEDREF*, 22, 23–67. <https://doi.org/10.4000/cedref.1101>
- Yazar, B. (2020). Neoliberal-neoconservative feminism(s) in Turkey: politics of female bodies/subjectivities and the Justice and Development Party’s turn to authoritarianism. *New Perspectives on Turkey*, 63, 113–137. <https://doi.org/10.1017/npt.2020.18>
- Yıldız Tahincioğlu, N. (2015). Sola Kadın Eli Değince: Kadın Cinayetlerini Durduracağız Platformu. In A. Bora (Ed.), *İradenin İyimserliği: 2000’lerde Türkiye’de Kadınlar*. Ayizi Yayınları.
- Yüksel, Ş. (1995). A Comparison of violent and non-violent families. In Ş. Tekeli (Ed.), *Women in Modern Turkish Society*. Zed Books.
- Zengin, A. (2016a). Mortal Life of Trans/Feminism. *TSQ: Transgender Studies Quarterly*, 3(1–2), 266–271. <https://doi.org/10.1215/23289252-3334487>
- Zengin, A. (2016b). Violent intimacies: Tactile state power, sex/gender transgression, and the politics of touch in contemporary Turkey. *Journal of Middle East Women’s Studies*, 12(2), 225–245. <https://doi.org/10.1215/15525864-3507650>

8.14 List of feminist movements' campaigns in Turkey

Name of the campaign (original)	Name of the campaign (English)	Issue(s) addressed	Actors involved	Repertoire of action	Logo of the campaign	Web-page	Comment
İstanbul Sözleşmesini Uygula	Implement the Istanbul Convention	Gender equality, gender-based violence, LGBTQ+ rights	Independent feminists, formal and informal feminist and LGBTQ+ movements and organizations	Public demonstrations and protests, petition drive, social media campaigns		N.A.	Campaign initially organized against the anti-feminist/anti-genderist attacks on the Istanbul Convention in July 2020, and later grew into a general advocacy platform fighting against gender-based violence, and for gender equality following

							the Presidential decree announcing Turkey's withdrawal from the Convention in March 2021.
Yoksulluğa Feminist İsyan	Feminist Revolt against Poverty	Poverty, economic crisis, Productive and reproductive labour	Independent feminists, formal and informal feminist organizations, women organized in mixed gender leftist organizations	Public demonstrations and protests, artistic performances, solidarity visits to picket lines formed in front of workplaces at strike and neighbourhoods protesting urban renewal projects		<p>Medium: https://yoksullugafeministisyan.medium.com/</p> <p>Twitter: https://mobile.twitter.com/feminist_isyan</p> <p>Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/feministisyan/</p>	An ongoing campaign that emerged in January 2022.

<p>Feminist Gece Yürüyüşü</p>	<p>Feminist Night March</p>	<p>Gender equality, gender-based violence, productive and reproductive labor, LGBTQ+ rights, reproductive rights, state repression, peace</p>	<p>Independent feminists, formal and informal feminist movements, women organized in mixed gender leftist organizations</p>	<p>Public demonstrations and protests, civil disobedience actions, and social media campaigns</p>		<p>Twitter: https://twitter.com/8MartYuruyus</p>	<p>The Feminist Night March, held annually in Istanbul since 2003, attracted participants up to 50,000 till 2019, the first year it was banned. Since 2019, thousands have continued to gather in the city centre despite police violence and mass detention.</p>
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<p>Onur Haftası</p>	<p>Pride Week</p>	<p>LGBTQ+ rights</p>	<p>Independent feminists and LGBTQ+s, formal and informal LGBTQ+ movement organizations</p>	<p>Public demonstrations and protests, artistic events, panels, social media campaigns</p>		<p>Webpage: https://archive.prideistanbul.org/</p>	<p>The Pride Parade, held annually in Istanbul since 2003, attracted participants up to 50,000 till 2015, the first year it was banned. Since 2015, thousands have continued to gather in the city centre despite police violence and mass detention.</p>
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<p>Kıyafetime Karışma</p>	<p>Don't Meddle with My Outfit!</p>	<p>Gender-based violence, women's attire</p>	<p>Independent activists, formal and informal women organizations</p>	<p>Public demonstrations and protests, civil disobedience actions, social media campaigns</p>		<p>Twitter: https://twitter.com/kadinmeclisleri https://twitter.com/KadinCinayeti</p>	<p>A campaign launched by the We Will Stop Femicide Platform (KCDP) in the summer of 2017 to protest the increasingly misogynist discourses about women's clothing and the accompanying escalation in verbal and physical violence against women deemed "immodest" in their attire in public.</p>
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<p>Cinsel Sağlık Senin Hakkın</p>	<p>Sexual Health is Your Right</p>	<p>Health and reproductive rights</p>	<p>Formal feminist and LGBTQ+ movement's organizations, civil society organizations, university research centres, activists and academics</p>	<p>Knowledge production, awareness raising, and monitoring through digital activism and publishing</p>		<p>Webpage: https://cisuplatform.org.tr/cinsel-saglik-senin-hakkin/</p> <p>Spotify: https://open.spotify.com/show/13zEtG47QHl6d0WvGY7FXg</p>	<p>A recent campaign initiated by the Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights Platform Turkey (CISU) which is a national network bringing together a range of actors working on SRHR and/or gender equality. This is a recent campaign / platform, which grew out of an EU funded project and counts among its</p>
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							members the major feminist and LGPTQI civil society organizations.
Kadın Dayanışması Sınır Tanımaz	Women's Solidarity Knows No Borders	Migration	Independent feminists, formal and informal feminist movement organizations, women organized in mixed gender leftist organizations	Public demonstrations, petition drive, digital activism		Twitter: https://mobile.twitter.com/SnrszKdnDynsms	Campaign organized to protest increasing anti-migrant discourse and action. This is the only campaign we could find in this issue area and this one has had very limited activities.
Ölümden Değil, Yaşamdan Yanayız	We Are on the Side of Life, Not Death!	Peace	Independent feminist, formal and informal feminist movement	Public demonstrations and protests, vigils, petition		Twitter: https://twitter.com/barisicinkadin	A campaign led by Women's Peace Initiative in 2016 to

			<p>organizations, women organized in mixed gender leftist organizations</p>	<p>drive, solidarity actions</p>			<p>challenge the state's crackdown on the Kurdish mobilization in south-eastern Turkey and to articulate women's demands for peace. While this campaign produced very well-known petition drives and made it into mainstream media, as a result of severe government repression, it is no longer active.</p>
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Appendices

Step by step guide for WP2 T2.1

Relevant parts from the FIERCE application

1.1 Objectives (WP2)

- To understand the structural and contextual conditions at national and transnational levels for the development of feminist movements in eight different country contexts over the period 2010-21.
- To identify how gender frames and narratives are disseminated and communicated by feminist movements.
- To analyse internal practices, strategies and tools for democratic innovations.
- To investigate debates or tensions within the feminist movements.
- To explore the relationship between feminist movements and other political actors and their impact on policy debates.

Work package 2 has three parts:

Part	Tasks	Time frame
T2.1	a. Literature review b. Preparation of the methodological guidelines	M1 - M6
T2.2	a. Interviews with feminist activists b. Document analysis c. Social network analysis	M7 – M26
T2.3	a. Study of parliamentary debates b. Interviews with key social and political actors	M7 – M26

These guidelines refer to part 1 of the work package 2 (T2.1)

Description of work

T2.1: Setting up the research framework, mapping actors, campaigns, debates and policy outcomes and prepare methodological guidelines (Leader: SNS, Duration: M1-M6)

Task 1: Review of academic and expert literature, internal knowledge, online archives (covering the period from 2010 to 2021):

- Map the development and challenges of national and European feminist movements
- Map actors, campaigns, debates and key policy related outcomes at the national and European level
- Identify five main thematic domains (labour market; health and reproductive rights; migration; LGBTQ+ rights; gender- based violence) and “hot topics” of feminist mobilizations within those domains (or new ones that may arise as politically relevant)

Task 2: Preparation of methodological guidelines:

- a. Preparation of frame analysis according to the main thematic domains (labour market; health and reproductive rights; migration; LGBTQ+ rights; gender- based violence) on documents and relevant campaign material by feminist movements
- b. Preparation of the interviews guide
- c. Preparation of eventual participant observation on salient cases emerging from the mapping of actors, campaigns and debates

Working definitions

Feminist movements

In our project, we refer to feminist movements to mean all those collective actors who contest the gender regime and the social production of gender based on inequality.

Contemporary feminist movements have strived to support, develop and apply an intersectional analytical framework to fully grasp (and counteract) the multiple and intersecting forms of power and oppressions. Intersectionality also constitutes the aspired basis for national, transversal and transnational alliances and coalition-building with other movements and civil society actors. Yet, these undertakings are not unproblematic and can unleash tensions, internal conflicts and divisions that at times unravel the presence of very different (when not directly contradictory) approaches to feminist struggles, priorities, and potential allies.

The project aims to provide a concrete laboratory of ideas to identify, reinvigorate and renew democratic practices that build upon concrete alternatives and inclusive visions for the future of democracy. At the same time, it allows us to identify the internal challenges to these inclusive practices, by more openly addressing tensions, controversies and disagreements hindering the efforts to convey intersectionality in praxis.

Conceptions of Democracy

The central focus of our research is democratic innovation in social movements with a focus on the feminist movement. We do not wish, however, to measure degrees of democracy, but to conceptualize the various models of democracy that are present, in more or less 'pure' form. A main assumption of our research is that the general principles of democracy such as power (kratos) by/from/for the people (demos) can be combined in different forms and with different balances: representative versus participatory, and majority versus deliberative. We assume that the plurality of repertoires that have been identified in contemporary movements is also reflected in the variety of conceptions of democracy they express.

Social movements do not limit themselves to presenting demands to decision makers; they also more or less explicitly express a fundamental critique of conventional politics, thus shifting their endeavours from politics itself to meta-politics.

Social Movement Organizations

We look at the conception of democracy in social movement organizations (SMOs), defined as formal and informal networks of individual and groups, with different degrees of structuration. We look at organizations both as mobilization agents and as spaces of deliberation and value construction. First, we consider organizations as socializing agents and norms producers; second, we look at formal as well as informal practices; third we seek for cognitive mechanisms: organizations do not automatically adapt to their environments; environmental pressures are filtered by organizational actors' perceptions, derived from ethnomethodology and phenomenology and their focus on everyday action

and practical knowledge; Fourth, in line with research on the feminist movement, we will look at organizations as emotional spaces, in which affective and cognitive dynamics interact.

While considering environmental constraints as potentially important in shaping organizational behaviour, we believe that organizations play an important and active role in shaping their environments. For social movements, as for other social actors, the organization is therefore not just a means, but also an end in itself.

Democratic Innovations in Social Movements

Within a general attention to the participatory and deliberative qualities, visions and practices of democracy, debates tend to develop on two main dimensions. First, participatory conceptions that stress inclusiveness of equals (high participation) are contrasted with those based upon the delegation of power to representatives (low participation).

In this sense, we expect the continued presence of direct forms of democracy that put a strong emphasis on the assembly, but also processes of institutionalization of social movement organizations have spread a principle of delegation of power. A second dimension refers to the prevalence of a majoritarian decision making based upon vote versus the one that assign a special role to public discussion, the common good, rational arguments, and transformation of preferences. On this, we expect that the traditional use of vote as decision making mechanism even within assembleary organizational model is challenged by an emerging emphasis on values and practices that stress instead good communication. By exploring democratic innovations within feminist movements, we seek for how they challenge, coalesce or enhance democracy at the national and international level.

Step by step guidelines for work package 2 (T2.1)

Literature review (state of the arts)

The documents to collect in the first step of our project include existing literature that presents, analyzes, and discusses feminist movements, main actors, their campaigns, debates and policy outcomes. The project pays specific attention to five main thematic domains: labour market; health and reproductive rights; migration; LGBTQ+ rights; gender- based violence, but other “hot topics” within those domains are likely to emerge in the mapping phase.

The collection of documents includes:

1. scholarly articles, book chapters, monographs, conference papers, etc.
2. Expert reports and other "gray literature" (any type of text (report, pamphlet, book, article, etc.) that cannot be classified as scientific but contains "expert knowledge" on the topic. These reports are usually produced by non-governmental organizations, movements, journalists, and other members of the "critical public"

Collect all documents listed above that cover the period from 2010 to 2021 in your country with regard to feminist movements (including transnational and EU-related texts if they relate to your country). To this aim, refer to scholarly literature and to secondary sources (press news, parliamentary debates, documents released by social movements and political actors, social media publications).

Please upload any collected documents that will be used for this analysis to our "Cloud library" on Teams HERE (Teamsa > Documents > General > O2_WPs > WP2 – Movements and Demo > 01 – Cloud Library – State of the Arts). This will allow us to refer and go back to the original sources when writing reports, articles, etc.

The result of the literature review is a national state of the arts report that should be organized according to these guidelines and the template below.

The template provides the basic structure of the report (i.e., chapter titles) and includes numerous research questions for each chapter. Use these questions to help structure the report and identify blind spots in the currently available literature in your country and add EU-related issues in all sections of the report when they are relevant to depict the national situation

Structure of the report

Introduction

In the introduction provide the basic information on the literature and secondary sources on feminist movements in your country. The brief overview should focus on actors, campaigns, debates and policy outcomes that can be detected in your country in the period 2010-2021.

- Do academic and activist circles in your country in the last ten years turn their attention to new issues emerging from feminist movements and how did they do that?
- What composition of feminist movements emerges from these studies (generational differences, ideology, repertoires of action)?
- On what specific turning points has the literature on feminist movements focused?
- Which are debates, controversies and conflicts addressed by recent studies?
- How widespread and relevant was the analysis of feminist movements with reference to the context (elections, gender/LGBT policies, institutional changes) in the period 2010-2021 in your country?

The history of the feminist movements and its context

Based on the available literature try to briefly describe the roots of the movements and its development in the period 2010-2021.

- What changes in the context of political opportunity structure have favoured or influenced the development of feminist movements in the period 2010-2021?
- What critical junctures have marked the emergence or re-emergence of feminist movements (events, marches, meetings and so on)?
- How did the movement develop?
- What are the connections to other actors (national, EU, transnational)?
- What are the major challenges that feminist movements have faced (institutional attacks, contestation by anti-gender/anti-feminist groups and so on)?

Actors, organizations and organizational models

This section aims to explore the composition of actors included in the network of feminist movements (movements, associations, anti-violence centres, NGOs, political parties).

- What actors/organisations make up the network of feminist movements in your country?

- What organisational models do they implement (deliberative, hierarchical, etc.)?
- What ideology do they refer to, also in relation to the type of organisational model adopted?
- What is their internal composition (in relation to the axes of gender, race, class, age, etc.)?
- What kind of local, national and transnational network do they develop?

Allies

This part explains what kind of alliances feminist movements develop, both extra-institutional and within institutions.

- Who are the allies of feminist movements? How do they cooperate?
- What intersections exist with other movements (environmentalist, anti-racist, workers' and so on)?
- What kind of relationship exists, apart from the movements, with public institutions, civil society, associations, NGOs?
- What is the relationship with state institutions and political parties (total involvement, open collaboration, occasional negotiation, total rejection...)?

Themes and agendas

The research project focuses on five thematic policy areas: (1) labor market, (2) health & reproductive rights, (3) migration, (4) LGBTQ+ rights and (5) gender-based violence. Describe how these topics emerge in the feminist movements in your country and whether these policy issues are/were a trigger for feminist movements to mobilise. Define any other topics that are also important and do not fit into these five policy areas, if found in the literature. Please, organize this part of the report in five (or more) subparagraphs according to the thematic areas, but address only those areas that are covered in the literature.

- What are the prevalent issues addressed by feminist movements also in relation to the context of your country (according to the political/social/economic situation)?
- Who are the counterparts held responsible, or referred to by feminist movements, with regard to these problems?
- What kind of solutions do they propose and how are they explained?
- Which topics convey forms of cooperation and which, on the other hand, forms of internal conflict within feminist movements?
- To what extent have they succeeded in influencing the decision-making process?
- How the general public responds to this framing process?

Repertoire of action

In this part we explore the repertoires of action employed by feminist movements, contentious politics and/or how they relate to state institutions.

- What are the prevailing strategies used by feminist movements?
- Are these strategies mostly confrontational or do they tend to open up spaces for interaction with institutions?
- How is social media used?
- What role do emotions play in choosing and implementing certain repertoires of action instead of others?
- What are the counterparts in the choice of action repertoires?

Frames of arguments

In this section, describe the main frames of arguments of feminist movements with reference to the five thematic areas (labor market, health & reproductive rights, migration, LGBTQ+ rights and gender-based violence).

- What are their key arguments (gender subordination, male violence against women, gender stereotypes, contestation of the traditional family, gender pay gap, crystal ceiling, and so on)?
- How is the term gender used according to different political movement cultures, and what kind of openness/relationship does it exist with intersectionality, queer theory, trans movements?
- How has the emergence of anti-gender/anti-feminist groups changed the definition of certain concepts and terms, such as gender, by feminist movements?
- How does the choice of frames of arguments influence repertoires of action, campaigns, counterparts?

Campaigns and debates

In order to understand the issues pursued by feminist movements, the project intends to specifically explore the campaigns and debates developed in the period 2010-2021.

- What kind of campaigns were developed in the period 2010-2021, and around which major issues?
- Through which repertoires of action were the campaigns developed? Which actors, alliances and counterparts were involved in carrying out the campaigns?
- What role did the intersectional approach play in the development of the campaigns?
- What effects, if any, have they produced in the literature?
- What were the debates that animated the feminist movements?
- Around which issues did forms of alliances or conflicts develop?

- How have these conflicts been influenced by the emergence and spread of anti-gender/anti-feminist rhetoric (gender identity, stepchild adoption, surrogacy, medically assisted procreation and so on)?

Key policy related outcomes

The project intends to look at how the issues, frame of argument, repertoires of action and campaigns of feminist movements influence models of democracy, and thus how state institutions do or do not take on board the stimuli of feminist movements. To do this, describe, if available in the literature, the key policy-related outcomes.

- With reference to the action of feminist movements in the five thematic areas (labour market, health and reproductive rights, migration, LGBTQ+ rights and gender-based violence), what policies have been developed in your country?
- Is there a direct or indirect involvement of feminist movements in the development of these policies?
- How has the role of feminist movements in policy-making changed, also in historical perspective (e.g. in the 1960s and 1970s), with the emergence of anti-gender/anti-feminist groups?
- What major challenges do contemporary feminist movements have with regard to policy-making?

Other important issues

If there are any other important issues discussed in the literature that cannot be put into any other subchapter of this report, summarize it here.

Conclusion

Outline the main findings in your local context (based on the state of the art) and point out the blind spots. Specifically, it develops how the points described above interact with decision-making processes and the quality of democracy in your country, i.e. whether and how the role of feminist movements in challenging, improving or innovating democratic models emerges in the literature.

12. List of feminist movements' campaigns

To proceed with the definition of methodological guidelines, the project intends to focus on the campaigns of feminist movements. Through the campaigns it will in fact be possible to better define actors, problems, frames, repertoires of action on which to build sampling, methods and data

analysis. The choice to focus on campaigns allows on the one hand to translate subject areas into an empirically detectable phenomenon, and on the other hand to draw on a meaningful sample for interviews, participant observation and frame analysis. We recommend focusing on five major campaigns (one for each issue area) in your country, significant enough to bring together relevant actors, issues and actions for analysis.

List of five feminist movements' campaigns in Italy

Name of the campaign (original)	Name of the campaign (English)	Issue(s) addressed	Actors involved	Repertoire of action	Logo of the campaign	Web-page	Comment
Verona città transfemminista	Verona transfeminist city	Gender equality, freedom of choice over the body, sexuality, family, right to abortion, gender self-determination	Movements, associations, NGOs	Public demonstrations and protests, international assemblies, cultural events		Web: https://nonunadimeno.wordpress.com/category/verona-transfemminista/ FB: https://www.facebook.com/events/417220915493543/	Campaign organized against the National Congress of Families in Verona, which generated a major moment of transnational mobilization

<p>Sciopero femminista</p>	<p>Feminist strike</p>	<p>Productive and reproductive labor</p>	<p>Movements , associations , anti- violence centres</p>	<p>Strike, demonstrations and protests, sit-ins, artistic performances</p>		<p>Web: https://nonunadimeno.wordpress.com/2022/02/11/proclamazioni-sciopero-8-marzo-e-lista-singole-adesioni-di-categoria-in-aggiornamento/</p> <p>FB: https://m.facebook.com/events/1057403021470799/</p>	<p>Annual strike every March 8 organized since 2017 in many countries around the world to challenge women's invisible and unpaid reproductiv e labor and the unequal productive working conditions that still remain</p>
<p>Etc.</p>							

Please use the APA referencing system and provide the bibliography at the end of the report.

This report should be finished by month 4,5 (mid-January 2023) to allow for comments, review and editing.

Preparation of methodological guidelines

Preparation for frame analysis

Preparation of frame analysis according to the main thematic domains (labour market; health and reproductive rights; migration; LGBTQ+ rights; gender- based violence) on documents and relevant campaign material by feminist movements.

Preparation of the interviews guide

This step involves the preparation of the interview guide, for the semi-structured interviews that will be conducted in phase T2.2. In order to build the fieldwork, an interview outline will be prepared for feminist movement activists, key political actors and/or key informants. As mentioned earlier, we suggest selecting five campaigns carried out in feminist movements in your countries that refer to the five thematic areas included in the project. For each campaign (and therefore thematic area), you will subsequently need to identify at least two people, so that at least 20 interviews will be collected for each country.

Preparation of eventual participant observation

According to political ethnography approach of the project, we aim to complement document analysis, social network analysis and interviews with participant observation. Depending on the context of the country and the conditions of feasibility, we suggest that following campaign mapping and interviews one feminist group of particular interest and relevance be selected with whom to carry out a phase of participant observation. In this way it will be possible to develop an in-depth approach to the study of feminist movements in the national context through participation in demonstrations, marches, events, and internal assemblies.